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**Colometric Analysis of Paul's Letters:
Methodological Foundations and Application
to 2 Corinthians 10–13**

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Priscille Marschall

Introduction

This PhD dissertation project started after I read Margaret Ellen Lee and Bernard Brandon Scott's monography, *Sound Mapping the New Testament* (abridged *SMNT*). In this book, published in 2009, Lee and Scott set forth a step-by-step method for producing and analysing "sound maps" of ancient Greek texts. They describe a sound map as "a visual display that exhibits a literary composition's organisation by highlighting its acoustic features and in doing so depicts aspects of a composition's sounded character in preparation for analysis."¹ In other words, sound mapping is a visually-based method of aural analysis (or alternatively, "sound analysis"). The objects of study are the aural characteristics of a given text, and the method of investigation consists of illuminating these characteristics by visually depicting them in the form of sound maps. Sound mapping is designed as a historico-rhetorical approach, provided that the criteria of analysis are based on ancient sources (especially Greek and Latin rhetorical treatises). "Colometry" plays a key role in the process of analysis, as the two initial steps of the sound mapping methodology are the identification of "côla" and their grouping into "periods." Accordingly, a sound map consists of a colometric display of the text studied: one cōlon to a line and one period to a paragraph. Later in the process of analysis, different aural features (e.g., anaphora, alliterations, repetitions of the same sequence of sounds, hiatus, consonant clashes) are observed and signalled by visual cues such as, for instance, boldface, underscoring, and alignment of parallel elements.

In view of the target audience of the present study—primarily New Testament scholars—I shall say here a few words on the key terms that will repetitively occur throughout the following pages: "cōlon," "comma," "period," as well as the the noun-adjective-adverb triad "colometry," "colometric," and "colometrically." These terms are generally little-known in NT scholarship. Moreover, when they do appear in works by biblical scholars, it is often in ways that depart from the strict definitions that I will refer to in this study. To clarify: in the present study, all of these terms refer to the structuration conventions of Greek and Latin prose as described in the ancient rhetorical treatises. Rhetoricians describe a system for structuring prose texts in cōla (cōlon, Greek: κῶλον, Latin: *membrum*), commata (comma, Greek: κόμμα, Latin: *incisum* or *caesum*), and periods

¹ Lee and Scott, *Sound Mapping the New Testament*, 168. The method for developing sound maps is detailed in the fifth chapter ("Developing Sound Maps"), on pages 167–195.

(Greek: περίοδος, Latin: *ambitus, circuitus, comprehensio*, etc.²). These notions are not easy to define—defining them appropriately will constitute one critical aspect of this study. As a first approximation and to keep it in terms of syntax, we can say that a *côlon* generally corresponds to what would today be termed a “clause,” and sometimes (less often) to a “phrase.” Here are three different examples of *côla*: (1) τάδε γράφω, ὡς μοι δοκεῖ ἀληθέα εἶναι (“I write these things as they seem to me to be true”)³; (2) ἔπου θεῶ (“follow God”)⁴; (3) μάλιστα μὲν εἵνεκα τοῦ νομίζειν συμφέρειν τῇ πόλει λελύσθαι τὸν νόμον (“chiefly because I thought it was in the interest of the state for the law to be repealed”).⁵ A comma is a special sort of *côlon* that is very short (the second example above, ἔπου θεῶ, is a comma). A period consists of a combination of several *côla* and/or *commata* and thus corresponds broadly to a complex or a compound sentence.⁶ Here is a classical example of a period from Demosthenes (the slashes indicate the *côla*-boundaries): μάλιστα μὲν εἵνεκα τοῦ νομίζειν συμφέρειν τῇ πόλει λελύσθαι τὸν νόμον / εἶτα καὶ τοῦ παιδὸς εἵνεκα τοῦ Χαβρίου / ὠμολόγησα τούτοις, ὡς ἂν οἷός τε ᾧ, συνερεῖν. (“Chiefly because I thought it was in the interest of the state for the law to be repealed / but also for the sake of Chabrias’ boy / I have agreed in their support, to the best of my ability, to speak.”)⁷ For their part, the terms “colometry,” “colometric” and “colometrically” are modern terminology that refer to this ancient system of structuration.

There are five canons or “steps” of rhetoric (*inventio* [“invention”], *dispositio* [“arrangement”], *elocutio* [“style”], *memoria* [“memory”], and *actio* [“delivery”]);⁸ the art of

² Multiple Latin terms are used as equivalents to the Greek περίοδος (see Cic. *Or.* 204 and 208; Quint. *Inst.* IX,4,124–125).

³ See Dem., *Eloc.* 12 (the extract is from Hecat. of Miletus, *Gen.* I).

⁴ See Dem., *Eloc.* 9.

⁵ See Dem., *Eloc.* 10 (= Demost., *Lept.* 1).

⁶ Note that the terms “*côlon*” and “period” are also commonly used in relation with ancient poetry. With respect to poetry, a *côlon* is a rhythmical unit that consists of a combination of two, three, four, or more rarely five or six feet, and of which the unity was probably given by its having one ictus (stress) being stronger than the rest. In contrast with the prose *côlon*, the metrical *côlon* of poetry does not always end with the end of a word, meaning that a word can be divided into two *côla* (see C. B. Heberden, “Rhythmica,” 2560–2562). As to the period of poetry, it is a combination of several *côla* that always ends with the end of a word, and after which a distinct pause is admissible. Depending on its length, a period encompasses one or more verses (see C. B. Heberden, “Rhythmica,” 2562–2564; see also G. Schade, “Periode”). On the colometry of choral poetry, specifically of the different kinds of periods, see M. Dominicy, “Colométrie, période et rythme dans le lyrisme choral en Grèce ancienne.”

⁷ See Dem., *Eloc.* 10. The extract is from Demost., *Lept.* 1 (trans. D. C. Innes).

⁸ A presentation of these five canons can be found in Quintilian, *Inst.* III,3. For a short modern synthesis, see Walde and M. Weissenberger, “Rhetorik” (part V, “Das rhetorische System”); for more detail on each of

arranging the discourse colometrically intervenes at the third step, which is concerned with *how* something is said. More specifically, colometry operates in what Dionysius of Halicarnassus described as the second movement of style, “arrangement,” or *synthesis* (σύνθεσις),⁹ particularly when putting the previously chosen words together in order to “weave”¹⁰ the discourse. However, colometry is not only a matter of style. Arranging the discourse into *côla*, *commata*, and periods begins with *elocutio* and builds towards *actio* (“delivery”) by taking into account a series of constraints linked to oral delivery. Thus, the conventions of dividing the discourse into *côla* and periods involves very pragmatic aspects, such as the limited respiratory capacity of speakers (allowing frequent places for breathing) or the cognitive process of listening (including sufficiently frequent pauses that allow the audience ample time to understand what has just been said).

Being deeply impressed about Lee and Scott’s work—which, following Arthur J. Dewey, I would qualify as “a fundamental breakthrough for biblical studies”¹¹—I enthusiastically endeavoured to produce sound maps of various passages from Paul’s letters. Initially, my intention was to apply Lee and Scott’s methodology to an entire letter or at least to a few chapters in the hope of uncovering a kind of sound logic that would illuminate the micro-structure. One aspect I was especially interested in was the extent to which the identification of *côla* and periods might help to disambiguate syntax in those passages containing punctuation issues (i.e., passages where the choice of punctuation impacts on the meaning). However, in my initial essays of practicing sound mapping, I felt incapable of making choices of delineation (or I was often unable to argue convincingly for these choices). It seemed as if the guidelines set forth by Lee and Scott were too vague. This impression was soon confirmed by my reading of Dan Nässelqvist’s

these canons, see the *Handbook of Classical Rhetoric in the Hellenistic Period* edited by S. E. Porter (M. Heath, “Invention”; W. Wuellner, “Arrangement”; G. O. Rowe, “Style”; T. H. Olbricht, “Delivery and Memory”).

⁹ The first part is ἐκλογή τῶν ὀνομάτων, namely the “choice of words” (see Dion. Hal., *Comp.* 2).

¹⁰ The metaphor of weaving is found notably in Dion. Hal., *Comp.* 23,3. Note that such a metaphor is also present in the origin of the word “text,” which comes from the Latin *textum*, which itself derives from the verb *texere*, “weave.” The first image associated with *textum* is that of fibers that are intertwined in the context of weaving or braiding (see, e.g., Ovid, *Metamorphoses* 8,641, where *textum* refers to a fabric). By extension, *textum* can also designate the way elements of language are arranged to form a discourse (see, e.g., Cicero, *Ad Familiares* IX,21,DCLVIII; Quint., *Inst.* IX,4,13, and *ibid.*, 4,129), or the result of such an arrangement, hence a “composition” or a “piece of discourse.”

¹¹ See A. Dewey’s comment on the back cover of *SMNT*: “A fundamental breakthrough for biblical studies ... It will revolutionize the way scholars analyze and interpret texts.”

then recently defended PhD dissertation.¹² In this essay, Nässelqvist elaborates on Lee and Scott's method while pointing out some of its limits—notably concerning the approach to ancient colometry. He proposes a more detailed discussion on this topic, which yields a refined set of criteria for delineating cōla and periods.¹³ Nevertheless, even with the help of this refined version of sound mapping, I found that Paul's letters resisted analysis in terms of colometry. This time, it seemed as if the model was too strict to adapt to Paul's style—or perhaps it was Paul who took considerable liberty with the model?

At this stage of my enquiry, the following questions briefly arose: may it be that Paul did not follow the stylistic conventions described by rhetoricians, or that he did so in a very loose manner? Was he either unaware of these conventions, unable to use them consistently, or reliant on other conventions? These questions were supplemented (though they would reappear later in a modified form)¹⁴ by the suspicion that Nässelqvist's refined criteria might also fail to reflect the ancient sources in a fully satisfactory manner—despite the fact that these criteria are in some ways more historically-informed than those that Lee and Scott previously proposed. This suspicion proved true when I started to engage seriously with ancient rhetorical treatises.¹⁵ Working with these treatises also made me realise how difficult it is to study ancient colometry, not only because of the difficulties related to the interpretation of the rhetoricians' theories, but also because the corresponding “field of research” in classical scholarship resembles a vast and varied jungle. Studies are divided between rhythmical analyses, syntactical approaches, and micro-studies dealing with the theory of individual rhetorician. As such, I have doubts as to whether it makes sense to speak of a “field of research” on ancient colometry. At the very least, there are not no detailed descriptions that fully encompass the different aspects of colometry (including the issues of the length of cōla and periods, their semantic and syntactic nature, and the role of figures) and upon which it would be possible to build a criteriology for delineating cōla and periods. The following statement that Thomas Habinek made 35 years ago still appears valid today:

Let it only be noted that there is need for a full-scale study of the ancient occurrences of these terms [cōlon, comma, period] – one that would take into account their etymologies and

¹² D. Nässelqvist, *Public Reading in Early Christianity: Lectors, Manuscripts, and Sound in the Oral Delivery of John 1-4*. I am much grateful to Dan Nässelqvist for having sent to me a printed version of his work prior to its publication.

¹³ D. Nässelqvist, *Public Reading in Early Christianity*, 119–180 (Chapter 4, “A Method of Sound Analysis”).

¹⁴ See below, Chapter 1, section 3.1.3.

¹⁵ For a list of the treatises considered, see below, Chapter 3, section 1.1.

connotations, as well as their transference, adaptation, and redefinition as parts of rhetorical systems.¹⁶

The present study does not aim to fulfil Habineck's call. Nevertheless, being convinced that a correct delineation of cōla and periods is a crucial point for the future development of sound mapping, I decided to dedicate a significant portion of my research to the study of the primary sources at our disposal, in the hope of achieving a more comprehensive understanding of ancient colometry. This signifies a fundamental change in perspective compared to my initial intention. Rather than exploring an application of sound mapping to one of Paul's letters, I decided to take a step back and work on the methodology itself. My research on the rhetorical treatises progressively led to a more comprehensive understanding of the notions of cōlon, comma, and period, as well as a better understanding of the ways these can combine to form the discourse. On the basis of this refined understanding, it became possible to formulate a set of delineation criteria that should better reflect the ancient conventions of analysis and enables us to reinforce the status of sound mapping as a historico-rhetorical approach. I will call this set of criteria a "method of colometric analysis." The simple expression "colometric analysis" will more broadly refer to the process of delineating cōla and periods, whether using this particular method or another set of criteria.

While this study focuses on the development of a historically informed method of colometric analysis, it will also deal with two supplementary issues. The first has to do with the very idea of looking for cōla, commata, and periods in Paul's letters. Is this approach to Paul's prose really justified? This is essentially the question of the adequation between the method and the object of study. Second, we will explore the relationship between colometry and punctuation; more specifically, the potential benefits that a colometric approach offers in terms of determining how Paul's letters should be segmented and punctuated by means of modern punctuation marks.

Before turning to the first chapter—which is devoted to the state of the research and a description of the aims, methods, and structure of this study—, I wish to acknowledge my profound debt to Margaret Ellen Lee, Bernard Brandon Scott, and Dan Näsaelqvist. Although I will part company with them somewhat to focus more clearly on the technical issue of cōla and periods delineation—and, in so doing, regularly put into question some aspects of their work—it was their researchs that initially stimulated my

¹⁶ T. Habineck, *The Colometry of Latin Prose*, 21.

interest for ancient colometry. The present study would never have existed without their pioneering and inspiring works.

CHAPTER I

Ancient Colometry and the New Testament: State of Research and Aims of this Study

This chapter presents the state of research on New Testament scholarship's engagement with colometry. It will also detail the aims that I will pursue in the present study. The presentation comes in three parts. The first part (section 1) showcases the recent interest for NT colometry as expressed for one decade in the movement of "sound mapping," while endeavouring to situate sound mapping among other current approaches and methodologies that deal with NT orality. The second part (section 2) refocuses the attention more strictly on colometry, beginning with a concise history of NT scholars' interest in this topic. It will then present the guidelines for delineating cōla and periods that are typically used by scholars involved in sound mapping and outline the first reception of sound mapping that manifested in NT research in the past few years. Then, in the third part of this chapter (section 3), I will formulate a few critiques of how sound mapping uses ancient colometry. This will bring us to clarify the aims that the present study is pursuing and to detail how the survey will be conducted throughout the next four chapters.

I. Recent Interest for Colometry in NT Scholarship

I.I. *A visually-based method of aural analysis: Lee and Scott's method of "sound mapping"*

In recent NT scholarship, the study of ancient colometry is closely associated with the names Margaret E. Lee and Bernard B. Scott—more specifically with their 2009 book *Sound Mapping the New Testament* (commonly abridged "SMNT"). In this book, Lee and Scott propose identifying cōla¹ and periods as the first and second steps, respectively, of a visually-based method of sound analysis (or "aural analysis"). The core idea is to depict the aural properties of a text in the form of what they call a "sound map."² After the initial steps of delineating cōla and grouping those cōla into periods, the analysis

¹ Lee and Scott spell "colon, cola" without an accent. I personally favour the spelling "cōlon, cōla" because it prevents any confusion with the "colon" as it refers to the punctuation mark.

² Lee and Scott define a sound map as follows: "a visual display that exhibits a literary composition's organisation by highlighting its acoustic features and in doing so depicts aspects of a composition's sounded character in preparation for analysis" (Lee and Scott, *SMNT*, 168). Their method for creating and analysing sound maps is described in *SMNT*, 167–195.

progresses through “identify[ing] sound patterns,” “identify[ing] compositional units,” “describ[ing] sound quality,” and finally “analys[ing] the relation between style and subject.”³ A “sound map” of a given text essentially consists of a colometric layout of the text that has one colon to a line and one period to a paragraph. In addition to making the colometric structure explicit, sound maps also highlight various acoustic features (anaphora, alliterations, repetitions of the same sequence of sounds, hiatus, consonant clashes) with visual cues such as boldface and italic type, underscoring, alignment of parallel elements, colours, and hash signs. This process of sound analysis is explicitly designed as a preparatory phase for exegesis.⁴ Lee and Scott posit that the making of sound maps is a new tool that helps to integrate a text’s aural characteristics into exegesis.⁵ They insist on the exegetical benefits of sound mapping:

Rediscovering the New Testament as it is organized by sound opens new doors for exegesis and sheds light on stubborn interpretative problems. To compensate for a modern, silent reader’s inability to process sounds in real time, sound mapping graphically represents sound features thereby presenting new data for analysis and creating new possibilities for interpretation.⁶

Simply put, this turn towards sound analysis is warranted, as “exegesis that ignores sounds, ignores clues to interpretation.”⁷

In the decade following the publication of *SMNT*, several scholars began to employ sound maps as a tool either to address specific exegetical issues, or more broadly to depict the soundscape of a text (see below, section 2.3.3). Although not all of these scholars strictly follow the step-by-step method of analysis developed by Lee and Scott, they all refer to *SMNT* as a background and inspiration for their research. In this sense, it can fairly be said that Lee and Scott’s work—specifically their 2009 book—laid the foundation for a new discipline within NT studies. The resulting discipline can be labelled “sound mapping,” as despite some variations in the methodology and in the aims pursued, the scholars involved in it share the core idea of producing “sound maps” as a means to visually depict the soundscape of the texts studied.⁸

³ Lee and Scott, *SMNT*, 167–195 (“Developing Sound Maps”). See also Lee, “Sound Mapping.”

⁴ Lee and Scott, *SMNT*, 168: “Becoming reoriented by sound requires first the mapping and then the analysis of a composition’s sounds as a prelude to exegesis.”

⁵ Lee and Scott, *SMNT*, 168.

⁶ Lee and Scott, *SMNT*, 168.

⁷ Lee and Scott, *SMNT*, 268.

⁸ See the article devoted to sound mapping in the *Dictionary of the Bible and Ancient Media* (M. E. Lee, “Sound Mapping”), where “sound mapping” no longer designates the specific method developed by Lee

1.2. Sound mapping within orality studies

1.2.1. The turn of biblical studies towards orality

In situating Lee and Scott's project among current approaches in NT studies, we can say that it is the expression of a "turn towards orality" that informed biblical studies for nearly four decades now—if we take Werner H. Kelber's 1983 *The Oral and the Written Gospel* as the starting point.⁹ In the aftermath of Kelber, biblical scholars engaged in various studies dealing with orality or the interplay between orality and literacy—most of which mirror the studies undertaken by classicists.¹⁰ Among the topics discussed, we can mention the ancient reading and writing education, including the question of the literacy rate (which was very low, perhaps somewhere around 5–10%, depending on the estimations);¹¹ compositional practices (usually involving dictation to a scribe);¹² the materiality of texts and the status of written word;¹³ the production and circulation of

and Scott, but more broadly refers to an emerging movement within NT studies. See a similar use of the term in the collective work edited in 2018 by M. E. Lee, *Sound Matters: New Testament Studies in Sound Mapping*, for example in the introduction to the volume, on page 6.

⁹ W. H. Kelber, *The Oral and the Written Gospel: The Hermeneutics of Speaking and Writing in the Synoptic Tradition, Mark, Paul, and Q*. For an overview of biblical scholars' engagement with orality in the last third of the 20th century and early 21st century, see H. E. Hearon, "The Implications of Orality for Studies of the Biblical Text"; also see K. R. Iverson, "Orality and the Gospels: A Survey of Recent Research." Also noteworthy is *The Dictionary of the Bible and Ancient Media* (ed. by C. Keith, T. Thatcher, R. F. Person and E. R. Stern), published in 2017, which offers many entries on orality and covers a variety of approaches and studies that together give a good idea of the state of research.

¹⁰ Within classical studies, the interest in orality can be traced back to the late 1920's, when Milman Parry first observed the presence of "formulas" (i.e., fixed expressions that are regularly used and under the same metrical conditions) in the Homeric epics (M. Parry, *L'épithète traditionnelle dans Homère. Essai sur un problème de style homérique*). Parry's research on the Serbian oral epic poetry in 1933–1935—conducted in association with his assistant Albert Lord in the Balkans—yielded to the so-called "oral-formulaic theory" (also known as the "Parry-Lord theory"). This theory posits that formulaic structures such as that found in Homer are evidence of an oral composition (see M. Parry [ed. by A. Parry], *The Making of Homeric Verse: The Collected Papers of Milman Parry*; A. Lord, *The Singer of Tales*). Parry and Lord's research on living oral tradition was later extended by John Foley (Foley, *The Theory of Oral Composition: History and Methodology*; Id., *The Singer of Tales in Performance*). The oral-formulaic theory was the starting point for countless studies on orality and the interplay between orality and literacy, which are commonly labelled "orality studies" or sometimes "media studies."

¹¹ See the reference work by W. Harris, *Ancient Literacy*. On the process of learning to write and to read, including insightful reflections on what it concretely means to be able to "write" and to "read," see R. Cribiore, *Gymnastics of the Mind: Greek Education in Hellenistic and Roman Egypt*. On literacy and illiteracy in Roman Palestine, see M. Bar-Ilan, "Illiteracy in the Land of Israel in the First Centuries C.E"; C. Hezser, *Jewish Literacy in Roman Palestine*.

¹² See notably T. Dorandi, *Le stilet et la tablette. Dans le secret des auteurs antiques*. The composition process of Paul's letters has been the object of a detailed study by E. R. Richards, *Paul and First-Century Letter Writing: Secretaries, Composition and Collection*; see also the 1974 article by R. N. Longenecker, "Ancient Amanuenses and the Pauline Epistles."

¹³ See, among others, A. Petrovic, I. Petrovic, and E. Thomas (eds), *The Materiality of Text: Placement, Perception, and Presence of Inscribed Texts in Classical Antiquity*; J. P. Small, *Wax Tablets of the Mind*;

books;¹⁴ the importance of memorisation;¹⁵ reading practices (mostly aloud and often before an audience);¹⁶ or the role of *recitatio* (public reading) in a work's publication process.¹⁷

Some NT scholars also began to discuss the implications of the oral-aural environment in which early Christian texts were composed in order to better understand their structure and stylistic characteristics. Thus, in 1990, Paul J. Achtemeier asserted that “the alternative to visual structuring of a manuscript to indicate organization of meaning is to include oral indications of structure within the material.”¹⁸ He illustrated this with some examples from the NT, showing how sound repetitions relate to the structuration of texts while also drawing the listeners' attention to specific words or sequences of words.¹⁹ A few years later, John Harvey explored “oral patterning” in Paul's letters. He endeavoured to show that “rhetorical forms” such as chiasmus, inversion, ring-composition, or concentric symmetry not only contribute to the overall structure of these letters, but also bring attention to particular elements that the author intended to emphasise.²⁰ During the same time period, Casey Davis explored how the principles of orality influence the structure of the Epistle to the

L. Alexander, “The Living Voice: Skepticism Towards the Written Word in Early Christian and in Graeco-Roman Texts.”

¹⁴ See, among others, R. Starr, “The Circulation of Literary Texts in the Roman World”; L. W. Hurtado and C. Keith, “Writing and Book Production in the Hellenistic and Roman Periods”; H. Gamble, *Books and Readers in the Early Church*, esp. 82–143; L. Alexander, “Ancient Book Production and the Circulation of the Gospels”; K. Haines-Eitzen, *Guardians of Letters: Literacy, Power, and the Transmitters of Early Christian Literature*.

¹⁵ See notably J. P. Small, *Wax Tablets of the Mind*. See also the recent edition of a selection of Marcel Jousse's texts in the series “Biblical Performance Criticism” under the title *Memory, Memorization, and Memorizers*. On the role of memory in scribal practices, see J. Ready, *Orality, Textuality, and Homeric Epic: A Study of Oral Texts, Dictated Texts, and Wild Texts*.

¹⁶ See, among others, the collective work edited by W. A. Johnson and H. N. Parker, *Ancient Literacies: The Culture of Reading in Greece and Rome*, which contains articles dealing with the different reading practices in antiquity. As concerns the reading practices among early Christian communities more specifically, see D. Nässelqvist, *Public Reading in Early Christianity*, 63–118; see also S. Buttica, “‘Que cette lettre soit lue à tous les frères’ (1 Th. 5,27). Les lettres de Paul et le rôle du *lector* dans l'Antiquité.”

¹⁷ See notably E. Vallette-Cagnac, *La lecture à Rome*, 111–170; R. Starr, “The Circulation of Literary Texts in the Roman World,” esp. 215. On Christian texts specifically, see H. Gamble, *Books and Readers in the Early Church*, 82–143; P. J. Botha, “Authorship in Historical Perspective.”

¹⁸ P. J. Achtemeier, “*Omne Verbum Sonat*: The New Testament and the Environment of Late Western Antiquity,” 17.

¹⁹ P. J. Achtemeier, “*Omne Verbum Sonat*,” 19–25.

²⁰ J. D. Harvey, *Listening to the Text: Oral Patterning in Paul's Letters*. Harvey describes eight “rhetorical forms”: chiasmus, inversion, alternation, inclusion, ring-composition, word-chain, refrain, and concentric symmetry (*Listening to the Text*, 97–118).

Philippians, developing a method he called “oral biblical criticism.”²¹ A few years later, Chrys Caragounis insisted on the acoustic dimension of communication, particularly with respect to the impact that sounds may have on an audience.²² Noteworthy is also Rachel Merda de Villeneuve’s recent PhD dissertation on the *elocutio* in *I Corinthians*, in which she provided a detailed analysis of Paul’s use of sound echoes.²³

It is worth noting that these initiatives merging stylistic analysis with the study of orality-aurality did not originate within the school of rhetorical criticism—even though they are, in a broad sense, interested in the “rhetoric” of NT texts. With *rhetorical criticism*, I am strictly referring to the historico-rhetorical approach initiated in the field of NT by Hans Dieter Betz and George A. Kennedy in the 1970s²⁴ that was then endorsed by a countless number of exegetes with applications on various NT texts.²⁵ Within this movement, little attention has been paid to the orality that emerges from NT texts. To be clear, this does not mean that the scholars involved in rhetorical criticism completely ignored the oral aspect of the first Christian literature. On the contrary, in Kennedy’s famous handbook of rhetorical criticism, it is made perfectly clear that NT literature was meant to be read aloud and thus received with the ears.²⁶ This is also the case in the *Socio-Rhetorical Commentary* series directed by Ben Witherington III, where a particular emphasis is put on the “oral disposition” of ancient

²¹ C. W. Davis, *Oral Biblical Criticism: The Influence of the Principles of Orality on the Literary Structure of Paul’s Epistle to the Philippians*.

²² C. Caragounis, *The Development of Greek and the New Testament: Morphology, Syntax, Phonology, and Textual Transmission*. See esp. 397–474.

²³ R. Merda de Villeneuve, *L’elocutio en I Corinthiens: Inventaire, stratégie et herméneutique*. Note that the author integrates some aspects of the sound analyses methods proposed by Lee and Scott and Nässelqvist. She does not, however, rely a lot on colometry.

²⁴ H. D. Betz, “The Literary Composition and Function of Paul’s Letter to the Galatians”; Id., *Galatians: A Commentary on Paul’s Letter to the Churches in Galatia*; cf. also Id., *Der Apostel Paulus und die Sokratische Tradition*; G. A. Kennedy, *New Testament through Rhetorical Criticism*. Note, however, that the application of classical rhetorical categories to the Bible has a much longer history: see C. J. Classen, who traces the history of rhetorical criticism up to Melanchthon (C. J. Classen, “St Paul’s Epistle and Ancient Graeco-Roman Rhetoric,” esp. 8–9; Id., *Rhetorical Criticism of the New Testament* 99–117). For an overview of the origin of the movement, see D. F. Watson, *Invention, Arrangement, and Style: Rhetorical Criticism of Jude and Second Peter*, 1–8. On the history of research (up to 2015), see C. J. Classen, “Can the Theory of Rhetoric Help Us to Understand the New Testament, and in Particular the Letters of Paul?”; also see (up to 2009), C. Grappe, “Paul et la rhétorique. Regard sur l’histoire et les enjeux d’un débat.”

²⁵ For a bibliography that testifies to the importance of the rhetorical criticism movement, see D. F. Watson, *The Rhetoric of the New Testament: A Bibliographic Survey*; Watson and Hauser, *Rhetorical Criticism of the Bible: A Comprehensive Bibliography with Notes on History and Method*.

²⁶ The process of analysis was exposed in G. A. Kennedy, *New Testament Interpretation through Rhetorical Criticism*, esp. 33–38. On the oral nature of NT texts, see notably pp. 5, 22, 37 (“The NT was intended to be received orally”), and 91.

cultures.²⁷ Yet, it is clear that the main intent of scholars engaged in rhetorical criticism was not the exploration of the oral-aural aspects of the texts. The focus was primarily on the first two “canons of rhetoric” (*inventio* and *dispositio*, i.e. the invention of arguments and then their general arrangement), at the expense of the more oral-oriented canons (*memoria* and *actio*, i.e., “memory” and “delivery”).²⁸ Scholars have mainly shown interest in the issues of the three “species” of rhetoric (deliberative, epideictic, judicial)²⁹ and of the overall arrangement or “macro-structure” of texts (*exordium*, *narratio*, *probatio*, *refutatio*, *peroratio*).³⁰ The aspects related to *memoria* and *actio*—which are more clearly oriented towards orality—have been largely neglected.³¹ As to the art of *elocutio* (“style”), it has also often been neglected within the movement of rhetorical criticism³²—although Kennedy’s proposed methodology involves the

²⁷ This series of 10 volumes was published under the direction of B. Witherington III, who is also the author of the majority of the volumes (B. Witherington, *1 and 2 Thessalonians: A Socio-Rhetorical Commentary*; B. Witherington, *Grace in Galatia: A Socio-Rhetorical Commentary on Paul’s Letter to the Galatians*; B. Witherington, *Paul’s Letter to the Philippians: A Socio-Rhetorical Commentary*; B. Witherington and D. Hyatt, *Paul’s Letter to the Romans: A Socio-Rhetorical Commentary*; D. A. de Silva, *Perseverance and Gratitude: A Socio-Rhetorical Commentary on the Epistle “to the Hebrews”*; B. Witherington, *The Acts of the Apostles: A Socio-Rhetorical Commentary*; B. Witherington, *The Gospel of Mark: A Socio-Rhetorical Commentary*; C. Keener, *The Gospel of Matthew: A Socio-Rhetorical Commentary*; B. Witherington, *The Letters to Philemon, the Colossians, and the Ephesians: A Socio-Rhetorical Commentary on the Captivity Epistles*).

²⁸ On the canons of rhetoric, see the general Introduction to this study above, n. 8. On the “literate” perspective of the traditional rhetorical criticism approach, see the remarks and suggestions of Loubser, “Reconciling Rhetorical Criticism with Its Oral Roots”; cf. also B. Oestreich, *Performanzkritik der Paulusbriege*, 15–28; cf. also G. S. Holland, “‘Delivery, Delivery, Delivery’: Accounting for Performance in the Rhetoric of Paul’s Letters.”

²⁹ On the three species of ancient rhetoric (and other subspecies), see G. A. Kennedy, “The Genres of Rhetoric.” On the applications of these species to Paul’s letters, see a good survey in D. F. Watson, “The Three Species of Rhetoric and the Study of the Pauline Epistles”; more generally on *inventio*, see T. W. Martin, “Invention and Arrangement in Pauline Rhetorical Studies,” esp. 75–117. For a critical view, see, among others, C. Forbes, “Ancient Rhetoric and Ancient Letters: Models for Reading Paul, and Their Limits,” 144–148.

³⁰ For a survey on *dispositio* in Paul’s letters, see for instance T. W. Martin, “Invention and Arrangement in Pauline Rhetorical Studies,” esp. 50–75.

³¹ Kennedy evokes this point in his handbook of rhetorical criticism. He explains that “discussion of memory and delivery [...] will be omitted here, for they relate to oral presentation, about which we know little” (*New Testament Interpretation through Rhetorical Criticism*, 14).

³² See this statement for example in S. E. Porter, “The Theoretical Justification for Application of Rhetorical Categories to Pauline Epistolary Literature,” 103–104 (“Authors [...] usually concentrate upon determining the species of discourse and suggesting a suitable outline of its organization, while neglecting style almost entirely [or at least placing it a distance third in importance].”) See a similar remark in the recent doctoral dissertation of R. Merda de Villeneuve, *L’elocutio en 1 Corinthiens: Inventaire, stratégie et herméneutique*, 53–54). Notable exceptions are D. F. Watson, *Invention, Arrangement, and Style: Rhetorical Criticism of Jude and Second Peter* (see also Id., “The Role of Style in the Pauline Epistles: From Ornamentation to Argumentative Strategies”) and, in 2006, C. Jacon, *La Sagesse du Discours. Analyse rhétorique et épistolaire de 1 Corinthiens* (see esp. pages 88–102).

analysis of style.³³ Moreover, the few scholars who include style in their analyses treat it almost exclusively in terms of its literate dimension. Concretely, they tend to reduce style to figures and tropes; the connection with orality and the principles of colometry are absent.³⁴ This arguably evidences a kind of “literate bias” that was still very present in NT studies in the last decades of the 20th century.

In the wake of the various studies on the oral-aural dimension of the NT writings, scholarship gradually turned to consider the potential exegetical implications of this dimension. The new issue addressed the following question: how does the interpretation of a text change when considered as an oral, rather than a silent, composition? Against this general background, sound mapping could be described as one of the two main disciplines that emerged with the purpose of integrating this rediscovered dimension in exegesis. The other discipline that emerged—which is better known—is performance criticism. Below I say a few words on these approaches and on how they relate to each other.

1.2.2. *Sound mapping and biblical performance criticism*

Biblical performance criticism is perhaps the most popular of the contemporary approaches that deal with the orality of biblical texts.³⁵ In the field of NT studies, the term was first used by David Rhoads in a 2006 two-part article in which he described “performance criticism” as an emerging discipline designed to explore and investigate the oral dimension of early Christian life and literature.³⁶ As its name suggests,

³³ G. A. Kennedy, *New Testament Interpretation through Rhetorical Criticism*, 25–33.

³⁴ The focalisation of stylistic analysis on figures and tropes can be observed for example in D. F. Watson, *Invention, Arrangement, and Style*, 22–26, and even more strikingly in C. Jacon, *La Sagesse du Discours*, 88–102. Note the ambiguous case of C. Davis, *Oral Biblical Criticism*. In this study—which combines a rhetorical approach inspired by G. A. Kennedy with discourse analysis—Davis considers the oral dimension of *elocutio*. He even employs the term “colon” in his analysis. However, his definition owes more to discourse analysis and modern linguistics than to the ancient sources (see below, section 1.3). A similar remark is made by Lee and Scott, *SMNT*, 138–140.

³⁵ For a good presentation of the method and its aims, see B. Oestreich, *Performanzkritik der Paulusbriefe*, 7–86.

³⁶ D. Rhoads, “Performance Criticism: An Emerging Methodology in Second Testament Studies—Part One”; “Performance Criticism: An Emerging Methodology in Second Testament Studies—Part Two.” Rhoads himself refers to Doan and Giles (*Prophets, Performance, and Power: Performance Criticism of the Hebrew Bible*) for the first use of this terminology. As Rhoads underlines, the interest in performance within biblical studies owes a lot to the SBL section “The Bible in Ancient and Modern Media,” founded in 1983 by T. Boomershine (see Rhoads, “Performance Criticism 1,” 120). On the origins of performance criticism, also see D. Rhoads and J. Dewey, “Performance Criticism: A Paradigm Shift in New Testament Studies.”

performance criticism focuses on the event of delivery (designated as “performance”) and involves both the performance of the speaker and the reactions of the listeners. It also considers the role of performance in the compositional process of texts.³⁷ From the early 2000’s onwards, numerous scholars have engaged in performance criticism of various NT texts, including the Gospels (Mark’s Gospel has received the most attention³⁸), the Acts of the Apostles,³⁹ or Paul’s letters.⁴⁰

The method of performance criticism is informed by the ancient descriptions of the act of delivering. For instance, in the eleventh book of his *Institutio oratoria*, Quintilian details how to plead a case.⁴¹ This account includes a detailed description of clothing, posture, voice, gestures (movements of the head, hands, and feet), and facial expressions. The choice of the terminology “performance”—instead of a more neutral expression such as “delivery” or “reading aloud”—is meaningful. This typically refers to a delivery made from memory (rather than read from a manuscript) that involves a quasi-theatrical aspect.⁴² Note that such a representation of the event of delivery has been harshly criticised—notably by Larry W. Hurtado—as minimising the importance of the written medium in the ancient communicational process and as confusing between the figures of the *actor* and the *lector*.⁴³

For its part, “sound mapping” centres on what might be called the “soundscape” of NT texts, with a specific focus on the visually depiction of sound structures. The

³⁷ From 2009 onwards, a significant proportion of these studies have been published in the series “Biblical Performance Criticism,” published by Cascade Books under the direction of David Rhoads. Note that this series also contains studies that are only loosely connected with the “strict” methodology of performance criticism.

³⁸ T. Boomershine, *The Messiah of Peace*; Id., “Mark 14–16 told in Greek”; W. Shiner, *Proclaiming the Gospel: First-Century Performance of Mark*; E. S. Malbon, *Hearing Mark: A Listener’s Guide*; J. Dewey, “Mark as Interwoven Tapestry: Forecasts and Echoes for a Listening Audience”; Id., “The Gospel of Mark as an Oral-Aural Event: Implications for Interpretation”; A. C. Wire, *The Case for Mark Composed in Performance*; R. Horsley, J. Draper, J. M. Foley (eds), *Performing the Gospel: Orality, Memory, and Mark*.

³⁹ W. D. Shiell, *Reading Acts: The Lector and the Early Christian Audience*.

⁴⁰ B. Oestreich, *Performanzkritik der Paulusbriefe*; P. Botha, “Letter Writing and Oral Communication in Antiquity: Suggested Implications for the Interpretation of Paul’s Letter to the Galatians.”

⁴¹ Quint., *Inst.* XI,3. See esp. W. D. Shiell, *Reading Acts*, 34–136 (see also Id., *Delivering from Memory: The Effect of Performance on the Early Christian Audience*); W. Shiner, *Proclaiming the Gospel*, 77–95; 127–139.

⁴² See notably the description of performances given by D. Rhoads, “Performance Criticism I,” 123–124.

⁴³ L. W. Hurtado, “Oral Fixation and New Testament Studies? ‘Orality’, ‘Performance’ and Reading Texts in Early Christianity.” On the distinction between the figures of the *actor* and the *lector*, also see D. Nässelqvist, *Public Reading*, esp. 74–77. See also Kelly R. Iverson’s response to Hurtado’s article, “Oral Fixation or Oral Corrective? A Response to Larry Hurtado.” Iverson argues that presentations of the movement of performance criticism, including that proposed by Hurtado, often caricature the movement by focusing on some aspects misleadingly considered as its “key assumptions.”

relationship between sound mapping and performance criticism requires further comment: the former might either be presented as a part of the latter, or as a distinct approach. In fact, in a broad sense, sound mapping is part of performance criticism; in both concepts, it is understood that the biblical texts were originally intended for oral delivery. Furthermore, both address the implications of this point for interpretation. Thus, in his 2006 article that presents performance criticism, Rhoads mentioned the early works of Dean and Scott as a part of the origin of the movement.⁴⁴ Moreover, among the scholars who work with Lee and Scott's method, many are also more broadly involved in NT performance criticism.⁴⁵ Nevertheless, it would be erroneous to reduce sound mapping to an internal development within performance criticism. Rather, sound mapping represents an independent approach with its own object of study (it concentrates more on style [in its oral-aural dimension] than on delivery) as well as its own methodology of analysis. It is crucial to note here that when practicing sound mapping—whether strictly following Lee and Scott's method or another one—there is no need to posit a specific scenario for the context and modalities of composition and delivery.⁴⁶ In fact, the aural features looked for are “in the text,” meaning that sound mapping can be practiced regardless of the scenario one assumes regarding the modes of composition, circulation, and delivery of texts. To the risk of oversimplifying the picture, we may say that in performance criticism, the “event” of performance is the object of study, whereas sound mapping is a more “text-centred” approach. In sum, sound mapping can certainly serve as a tool for exegetes involved in the performance criticism approach, but it can also be used independently. In this sense, sound mapping can fairly be considered as an emerging discipline on its own.

With relation to the use they make of the ancient rhetorical treatises, both performance criticism and sound mapping continue the movement of rhetorical criticism of the NT that Betz and Kennedy initiated some 40 years ago. Indeed, each of

⁴⁴ D. Rhoads, “Performance Criticism: An Emerging Methodology in Second Testament Studies—Part One,” 120. Also see P. S. Perry, “Biblical Performance Criticism: Survey and Prospects,” 4–5. We may also notice that the 2018 collective work on sound mapping edited by M. E. Lee (*Sound Matters: New Testament Studies in Sound Mapping*) has been published in the series Biblical Performance Criticism (see above, n. 37).

⁴⁵ Thus K. B. de Waal, *Aural-Performance Analysis of Revelation I and II* (see also Id., “A Sound Map of Revelation 8:7–12 and the Implications for Ancient Hearers”); T. Boomershine, *The Messiah of Peace* (see also Id., “The New Testament Soundscape and the Puzzle of Mark 16:8”).

⁴⁶ See a close statement in Lee, “Introduction,” 6. One example of a scholar who practices sound mapping while criticising the typical representation of “performances” found in the movement of performance criticism is Dan Nässelqvist (see in particular *Public Reading in Early Christianity*, 63–118).

these new disciplines shines a light on one canon of rhetoric that was neglected in traditional rhetorical criticism. Specifically, performance criticism introduces the study of *actio* (“delivery”) and *memoria*,⁴⁷ while sound mapping expands the traditional study of *elocutio* (“style”) by bringing attention to the oral-aural orientation of ancient Greek stylistical conventions.

1.3. Other approaches to colometry in NT studies

The introduction above should not be taken to imply, however, that the interest for ancient colometry is a completely new phenomenon within NT studies and that this is attached solely to the movement of sound mapping. On one hand, the idea to dispose NT texts colometrically is not completely new, as evidenced by the 1920s works of Roland Schütz,⁴⁸ Roman Woerner,⁴⁹ Albert Debrunner,⁵⁰ and James A. Kleist.⁵¹ A short presentation of this earlier interest for NT colometry will be proposed in the below state of research (see section 2.1.). On the other hand, the terms “côlon” and “period” are sometimes employed by NT scholars without any direct connection with Lee and Scott’s work. For example, this is the case in a recent article by S. M. Baugh, who has studied the structural role of hyperbaton in the Epistle to the Hebrews, showing how hyperbata mark the boundaries of “basic informational units” (i.e., *côla*) as well as, sometimes, of larger discourse units (periods).⁵² My point here is rather to state that Lee and Scott’s sound mapping methodology has initiated an unprecedented interest for ancient colometry within NT studies. To this point, I would add that the movement of sound mapping thus far seems to be the sole arena in which scholars have sought to establish clear criteria for delineating *côla* and periods.

⁴⁷ On the relationship between rhetorical criticism of the NT and performance criticism, see B. Oestreich, *Performanzkritik der Paulusbriefe*, 15–28, esp. 17–18.

⁴⁸ R. Schütz, “Die Bedeutung der Kolometrie für das Neuen Testament”; *Der Jakobusbrief nach Sinnzeilen ins Deutsche übertragen*; Id., *Das Neue Testament für die deutsche Jugend nach Sinnzeiler aus dem griechischen übertragen*.

⁴⁹ R. Woerner, *Die Frohen Botschaft nach Markus, nach Matthäus, nach Lukas, nach Johannes*; Id., *ΑΠΟΚΑΛΥΨΙΣ*.

⁵⁰ A. Debrunner, “Grundsätzliches über Kolometrie im Neuen Testament.”

⁵¹ J. A. Kleist, “Colometry and the New Testament”; Id., “Colometry and the New Testament (Concluded).”

⁵² S. M. Baugh, *Hyperbaton and Greek Literary Style in Hebrews*. Baugh defines hyperbaton as “the separation of words or groups of words in speech or writing that are semantically and syntactically interconnected” (195). He often refers to an article by the classicist Daniel Markovic, “Hyperbaton in the Greek Literary Sentence.”

In addition, it should be noted that the terms “colometry” and “colon” (most often without the accent) are used by biblical scholars in various areas and with various meanings—sometimes with only a loose connection to the principles of ancient rhetoric. Thus, some scholars involved in NT discourse analysis practice a so-called “colon analysis,” following the model initiated by Johannes P. Louw.⁵³ This approach notably led to a colometric disposition of the entirety of Matthew’s Gospel⁵⁴ that was edited by the New Testament Society of South Africa between 1977 and 1983. Later, it inspired Casey W. Davis’ research on the structure of the Epistle to the Philippians.⁵⁵ In this context, a “colon” is described without reference to the dynamics of sounds, but rather according to the insights of modern linguistics: as a syntactic unit formed around a nominative and predicate structure.⁵⁶ Moreover, the notion of the period is absent from this perspective. The term “colometry” is also commonly found in discussions of the structure of Hebrew verse.⁵⁷ Various methods are proposed to define the so-called Hebrew “cola,” such as an attention to Massoretic accentuation, for instance.⁵⁸ In the field of codicology, “colometry” designates a way of disposing texts in sense-lines that is in opposition with the more common convention of “stichometry.”⁵⁹ Thus, the codex Bezae (5th century, bilingual Greek-Latin), the codex Claromontanus (6th century, bilingual Greek-Latin), the codex Coislinianus (6th century, Greek), and the codex

⁵³ J. P. Louw, *Semantics of New Testament Greek*; Id., “Discourse Analysis and the Greek New Testament.”

⁵⁴ Nuwe-Testamentiese Werkgenootskap van Suid-Afrika, *The Structure of Matthew 1–13: An Exploration into Discourse Analysis*; Id., *Structure and Meaning in Matthew 14–28*.

⁵⁵ C. W. Davis, *Oral Biblical Criticism: The Influence of the Principles of Orality on the Literary Structure of Paul’s Epistle to the Philippians*.

⁵⁶ J. P. Louw, *Semantics of New Testament Greek*; Id., “Discourse Analysis and the Greek New Testament”; also see S. E. Porter, “Discourse Analysis and New Testament Studies.” As S. E. Porter summarises, “Colon analysis consists of breaking the text down into its constituent cola. A colon is a unit that is formed around a nominative and predicate structure. These cola are first isolated and then their interconnections are re-established in diagrammatic form, illustrating the semantic relations among them as increasingly larger semantic units are formed.” (Porter, “Discourse Analysis,” 33).

⁵⁷ See e.g., M. C. A. Korpel and J. C. de Moor, *The Structure of Classical Hebrew Poetry: Isaiah 40–55*; W. T. W. Cloete, “The Colometry of Hebrew Verse”; W. T. Koopman, *Joshua 24 as Narrative Poetry*; A. Niccacci, “Analysing Biblical Hebrew Poetry.”

⁵⁸ The idea to delimit Hebrew cola based on Massoretic accentuation was formulated by W. T. Koopman, *Joshua 24 as Narrative Poetry*. See the critical assessment by R. de Hoop, “The Colometry of Hebrew Verse and Massoretic Accents: Evaluation of a Recent Approach (Part 1).”

⁵⁹ See E. M. Thompson, *An Introduction to Greek and Latin Palaeography*, 67–71; B. M. Metzger, *Manuscripts of the Greek Bible*, 39–40; R. W. Mathisen, “Palaeography and Codicology,” 155–157. See also Gamble, *Books and Readers in Early Christianity*, 229–230.

Amiatinus (7th or 8th century, Latin), are all said to adopt a colometric disposition.⁶⁰ To these different usages, we may add that the term colometry is sometimes employed in a broad sense to designate a display of texts in sense-lines. This is the case, for example, with regard to Jaqueline de Chevigny’s bilingual editions of the four gospels (Greek-French), which are sometimes considered “colometric” because each line contains a sense-unit.⁶¹ This is also the case in the research of Michael Theobald.⁶² Below, I will skip through these different usages, as these are only loosely connected with the topic of our study—despite the common terminology. I shall rather focus on colometry in a strict sense by referring to the theories exposed in ancient Greek and Latin rhetorical treatises—hence the specification “ancient” in the title of the present chapter.

2. Ancient Colometry and the NT: History of Research

2.1. German exegesis in the 1920s

In the first third of the 20th century, colometry saw a rise of interest. Several German scholars manifested a curiosity in the orality that emerges from the biblical writings. In this post-romantic period, scholars were plenty aware that biblical texts must be read “with the ears”—to retake a formulation by Johannes Weiss.⁶³ As such, it became popular to seek to restore the oral-aural dimension of Jewish and Christian sacred texts through “colometric presentations,” wherein each breath unit is placed on its own line. Martin Buber and Franz Rozenzweig’s translation *Die Schrift* (1926–1938) is probably the most well-known representation of this trend. This German translation of the Hebrew Bible is arranged in breath units (“Atemeinheiten”), which Buber and Rosenzweig named “Kola.” However, these “Kola” were not technically defined with reference to the

⁶⁰ On the issue of dating of these manuscripts, see B. M. Metzger and B. D. Ehrman, *The Text of the New Testament*, 70–76; 106. Noteworthy also are the colometric dispositions of the Hebrew poetic texts in the codex Vaticanus, in the codex Sinaïticus, and in the codex Alexandrinus (on this, see B. M. Metzger, *Manuscripts of the Greek Bible*, 39).

⁶¹ J. de Chevigny, *Évangile selon Marc*; Id., *Évangile selon Matthieu*; Id., *Évangile selon Luc*; Id., *Évangile selon Jean*. The qualification “colometric” in reference to these editions is employed, for example, by D. Nässelqvist, *Public Reading*, 130 (note, however, that J. de Chevigny does not herself employ the lexical field of colometry).

⁶² See e.g., M. Theobald, “Der Kanon von der Rechtfertigung (Gal 2,16; Röm 3,28). Eigentum des Paulus oder Gemeingut der Kirche?” esp. 166–167.

⁶³ J. Weiss specifically made this statement in relation to Paul’s letters (*Beiträge zur paulinischen Rhetorik*, 166). See also C. F. G. Heinrici, who paid attention to sound figures (“Klangfiguren”) in his commentary on 2 Corinthians, *Der zweite Brief an die Korinther*.

rhetorical treatises, but rather more broadly as “easily speakable, easily perceptible and thus rhythmically ordered” units.⁶⁴

In NT scholarship, the idea of disposing texts colometrically emerged in parallel and seemingly independently from Buber and Rosenzweig’s undertaking.⁶⁵ It can be traced back to Eduard Norden, who, in his 1913 *Agnostos Theos*, called for presenting the Greek text of the NT colometrically.⁶⁶ However, it is Roland Schütz who was the first to take up the implications of ancient colometry for the study of the NT—beginning in 1922 with an article entitled “Die Bedeutung der Kolometrie für das Neuen Testament.” In contrast with Buber and Rosenzweig, Schütz clearly referred to ancient colometry in a relatively technical sense, with explicit references to the ancient rhetorical treatises and discussion of the notions of *côlon* and period. A few years later, two other scholars—Albert Debrunner and James Kleist—reinforced Schütz’s point, agreeing that NT texts should be presented colometrically.⁶⁷ Kleist made this appeal:

If a translation of the New Testament different from the versions in common use were at all desirable, I think [it] should be for presenting the sacred text in colometric form. [...] Colometry would do away with two somewhat disturbing things in reading the Bible, first, with that artificial division of the text by chapter and verse, and second, with division of the text by paragraph.⁶⁸

The idea to present NT texts colometrically was embodied in the form of German colometric translations. Thus, in 1922, Schütz published a colometric translation of the Epistle of James. This was followed in 1928 by a selection of other NT texts that were translated “nach Sinnzeiler” (i.e., in sense-lines).⁶⁹ In parallel, Roman Woerner published colometric translations of the four Gospels and of the Apocalypse—in 1922 and 1924, respectively.⁷⁰ Both Schütz and Woerner referred to Jerome of Stridon as a

⁶⁴ M. Buber, “Aus den Anfängen unserer Schriftübertragung,” 322–323 (ET: “From the Beginnings of our Bible Translation,” 179–180).

⁶⁵ See also in this sense, F. J. Hoogewoud, “From ‘Writteness’ to ‘Spokenness’: Martin Buber and His Forgotten Contemporaries on Colometry,” 106–110.

⁶⁶ E. Norden, *Agnostos Theos*, 361–364.

⁶⁷ A. Debrunner, “Grundsätzliches über Kolometrie im Neuen Testament”; J. A. Kleist, “Colometry and the New Testament”; Id., “Colometry and the New Testament (Concluded).” Debrunner’s article comprises a few examples from the NT, including a colometric analysis of Lc 9:1–4 (“Grundsätzliches über Kolometrie im Neuen Testament,” 231–233).

⁶⁸ J. A. Kleist, “Colometry and the New Testament (Concluded),” 27.

⁶⁹ R. Schütz, *Der Jakobusbrief nach Sinnzeilen ins Deutsche übertragen*; Id., *Das Neue Testament für die deutsche Jugend nach Sinnzeiler aus dem Griechischen übertragen*.

⁷⁰ R. Woerner, *Die Frohen Botschaft nach Markus, nach Matthäus, nach Lukas, nach Johannes*; Id., *Ἀποκάλυψις*.

precursor of the practice of disposing biblical texts “per cola and commata.”⁷¹ Specifically, they consulted the edition of the Vulgate that was at the time under publication by John Wordsworth and Henry White.⁷² This edition was modelled on the so-called colometric disposition of the codex Amiatinus (late 7th or early 8th century), a disposition which itself is sometimes thought to reproduce the presentation *per cola and commata* that Jerome supposedly established a few centuries before that in his Latin translation of the Bible.⁷³ In addition, Schütz and Woerner paid attention to parallelisms in their colometric translations, on the model of the poetic texts from the Hebrew Bible.⁷⁴

In short, there was a genuine interest in ancient colometry among NT scholars in the 1920s. However, it should be acknowledged that this did not lead to the development of a “method” for delineating cōla and periods (in the sense of a series of guidelines or criteria that would justify the delineation choices).⁷⁵ Two different reasons may explain this fact. First, the lack of interest in delineation criteria might stem from the fact that scholars at time were not focused on the implications of colometry for exegesis but were instead concentrating more modestly on highlighting a kind of oral-aural logic and aesthetics in the NT writings. Another point that perhaps prevented Schütz, Woerner, Kleist, and Debrunner from discussing delineation methods might be the difficulties encountered when it comes to describing the notions of cōlon, comma, and period in a precise manner. Kleist’s following comment seems to be representative of biblical scholars’ general approach to ancient colometry in the 1920’s: “In view of this

⁷¹ R. Schütz, “Die Bedeutung der Kolometrie für das Neuen Testament,” 170–172. On this, see F. J. Hoogewoud, “From ‘Writteness’ to ‘Spokenness,’” 110.

⁷² I owe this information to F. J. Hoogewoud, “From ‘Writteness’ to ‘Spokenness,’” 110. Wordsworth and White’s edition contains three volumes, published between 1889 and 1954 under the title *Novum Testamentum Domini nostri Iesu Christi Latine*.

⁷³ See Jerome, *Prol. Isaiah* 1 [=PL vol. 28, 771]; *Prol. Ezechiel* 2 (=PL vol. 28, 938–939). R. Schütz (“Die Bedeutung,” 170) seems to think that Jerome applied a colometric disposition to his entire translation of the Bible; a similar assertion is made by Thompson (*An Introduction to Greek and Latin Palaeography*, 70). This point is uncertain, however, as the mention of a disposition *per cola et commata* occurs only in the prefaces to Isaiah and Ezekiel. It is also unsure that the codex Amiatinus genuinely reproduces Jerome’s proposed disposition.

⁷⁴ Prior to his article on the significance of colometry for the NT, R. Schütz published notes on the various parallelisms present in Mark’s Gospel as well as in the First Epistle to the Corinthians, showing that these texts exhibit features of parallelisms that are generally associated with the poetic texts of the Hebrew Bible (R. Schütz, *Der parallele Bau der Satzglieder im Neuen Testament*). On parallelisms as a structuring device in Greek, see also E. Norden’s remarks, *Agnostos Theos*, in 355–366 (“Semitischer und hellenischer Satzparallelismus”).

⁷⁵ See a similar remark in Lee and Scott, *SMNT*, 138.

lack of more precise information from ancient sources we are justified in allowing ourselves a certain latitude in applying the colometric system to ancient texts.”⁷⁶

In contrast with Buber and Rosenzweig’s translation of the Hebrew Bible, which became well-known and inspired subsequent translations, Schütz and Woerner’s translations did not meet much success.⁷⁷ After the 1920s, the enthusiasm for analysing NT texts in terms of *côla* faded, thus simultaneously extinguishing the exegetes’ interest in ancient theories on colometry. Nonetheless, the practice of producing translations of NT books in sense-lines did not completely disappear. Friedrich Streicher’s translations in German, published in the 1960s, are worth mentioning. These are disposed “in sense lines” (*Sinnzeilen*) in explicit imitation of Woerner’s work.⁷⁸ More recently, in 2005, Ton Veerkamp published a “colometric translation” (*kolometrische Übersetzung*) of John’s Gospel.⁷⁹ To a certain extent, Jacqueline de Chevigny’s Greek-French editions of the four gospels in “lines” (*lignes*) belong to the same movement.⁸⁰

2.2. Colometry within “Rhetorical Criticism” of the NT

Provided the rhetorical treatises from the Graeco-Roman world constitute the main source on the topic of ancient colometry, a marked interest for colometry would be expected in the modern school of NT “rhetorical criticism.”⁸¹ Indeed, rhetorical criticism is a historico-rhetorical approach that takes the Graeco-Roman rhetorical tradition as its theoretical foundation, meaning that the precepts expressed by ancient rhetoricians are consistently referred to. However, colometry is virtually absent in the works that adopt the methodology of rhetorical criticism. If the terms *côlon*, comma, and period occasionally appear—for instance, in G. A. Kennedy’s foundational book *New Testament through Rhetorical Criticism*⁸²—there is no discussion of the colometric structures of NT texts. Moreover, many (and perhaps even most) works that adopt a rhetorical approach to early Christian texts do not even use the terms. For instance, the terms “*côlon*” and “period” (at least in reference to rhetoric) never appear in Hans

⁷⁶ J. A. Kleist, “Colometry and the New Testament (Concluded),” 26–27.

⁷⁷ On this topic, see F. J. Hoogewoud, “From ‘Writteness’ to ‘Spokenness,’” 112–113.

⁷⁸ F. Streicher, *Neues Testament aus dem Urtext in Sinnzeilen übersetzt*.

⁷⁹ T. Veerkamp, *Das Evangelium nach Johannes in kolometrischer Übersetzung*.

⁸⁰ See above, n. 61.

⁸¹ Here again, I refer strictly to the methodology initiated, in the field of NT, by Hans Dieter Betz and George A. Kennedy (see above, n. 24).

⁸² See G. A. Kennedy, *New Testament through Rhetorical Criticism*, 30. 51. 136.

Dieter Betz's well-known rhetorical *Commentary on Paul's Letter to the Churches in Galatia*,⁸³ nor in Carl Joachim Classen's *Rhetorical Criticism of the New Testament*,⁸⁴ nor in B. Witherington's *Introductory Guide to the Art of Persuasion in and of the New Testament*,⁸⁵ and are only seldom used in the 10 volumes of the *Socio-Rhetorical Commentary* series.⁸⁶

2.3. *Sound Mapping the New Testament*

2.3.1. *The beginnings and the handbook by Lee and Scott (SMNT, 2009)*

It was not until the end of the 20th century that ancient colometry once again received attention in NT scholarship. The catalyst was a 1993 SBL paper that was jointly presented by Margaret E. Dean (the former name of Margaret E. Lee) and Bernard B. Scott, in which they explored the possibility of producing a sound map of the Sermon on the Mount.⁸⁷ Dean then laid the foundation for a method of sound mapping, in a 1996 article entitled "The Grammar of Sound in Greek Texts: Toward a Method for Mapping the Echoes of Speech in Writing." In this article, she suggested that "grammar focuses on speech as a synthesis of sound," referring to "the science of grammar" as "the Greeks' own method of aural analysis."⁸⁸ Her research was later extended in a PhD dissertation, published in 2005 (much of which would later be reproduced in *SMNT*). Furthermore, her collaboration with Scott continued until it eventually yielded *Sound Mapping the New Testament* in 2009, the handbook that now serves as the reference work for practitioners of sound mapping. This book proposes a six-steps methodology for developing and analysing sound maps. These steps are as follows:

- Step 1: delimit côla.
- Step 2: group côla within periods.
- Step 3: identify sound patterns.

⁸³ H. D. Betz, *Galatians: A Commentary on Paul's Letter to the Churches in Galatia*.

⁸⁴ This book consists of a collection of essays by C. J. Classen. It was published in 2000.

⁸⁵ B. Witherington, *New Testament Rhetoric: An Introductory Guide to the Art of Persuasion in and of the New Testament*.

⁸⁶ See above, n. 27. For instance, I found the term "period" (used in a rhetorical sense) only twice in B. Witherington, *Conflict and Community in Corinth: A Socio-Rhetorical Commentary on 1 and 2 Corinthians* (both uses are on page 1215).

⁸⁷ Published as M. E. Dean (= Lee) and B. B. Scott, "A Sound Map of the Sermon on the Mount." For an overview of the origins and early history of sound mapping, see M. E. Lee, "Sound Mapping Reassessed," 9–11.

⁸⁸ M. E. Dean (= Lee), "The Grammar of Sound in Greek Texts: Toward a Method for Mapping the Echoes of Speech in Writing."

- Step 4: identify compositional units.
- Step 5: describe sound quality
- Step 6: analyse the relationship between style and subject.⁸⁹

As noted above, colometry plays a key role in the process of creating sound maps, since it represents the first and second steps of the method and therefore determines the entire process of analysis. In contrast with Schütz, Woerner, Debrunner, and Kleist's previous research, this approach attempts to clarify and even to justify (with references to ancient sources) the way *côla* and periods are delineated. That is, Lee and Scott not only seek to explain in broad strokes what defines *côla* and periods in ancient rhetoric, but they also provide guidelines as to how modern exegetes may delineate these units in NT texts.

Another element that distinguishes Lee and Scott's approach from earlier studies on NT colometry is the particularly clear exegetical orientation of their method. Although sound mapping is not in itself "an analytical tool, nor an interpretative method or exegetical approach,"⁹⁰ it is envisioned as a potential tool for exegesis. Lee and Scott's project goes beyond highlighting the oral-aural properties of early Christian texts, and includes discussions on how sound mapping may contribute to inform exegesis. In other words, sound mapping is designed as a prelude to exegesis.⁹¹ In the second part of *SMNT*— following the establishment of the method—Lee and Scott present examples.⁹² They propose six test cases that each illustrates how sound maps help to renew exegesis: Mark's crucifixion (Mark 15:11–41); the Epistle to Philemon; the resurrection narrative in John 20; Luke's nativity scene (Luke 2:1–2:20); the Sermon on the Mount (Matt 5–7); and a comparison between Matthew and Luke's versions of Jesus' discourse on anxiety (Matt 6:25–35 and Luke 12:22b–32). For each of these passages, Lee and Scott discuss a few exegetical issues, showing how the sound mapping approach sheds new light on the debates. The benefits of sound mapping often have to do with issues of sectional divisions (such as delimiting the pericopes boundaries or internal division within a passage) and questions of emphasis (such as determining the climax of a passage). For example, sound analysis of the Sermon on the Mount reveals the

⁸⁹ M. E. Lee and B. B. Scott, *SMNT*, 167–195.

⁹⁰ M. E. Lee and B. B. Scott, *SMNT*, 385

⁹¹ M. E. Lee and B. B. Scott, *SMNT*, 168.

⁹² M. E. Lee and B. B. Scott, *SMNT*, 197–384.

presence of eight sections that are structured in progressively more complex ways throughout repeated opening and concluding sounds.⁹³ The sound map of Mark's crucifixion reveals that the listing of women in Mark 15:40–41 still belongs to the crucifixion scene and should thus not be treated as an isolated scene or as a part of the burial scene that comes next.⁹⁴ Or, with respect to the resurrection passage in John 20, Lee and Scott conclude that the sound map shows that "Thomas's confession [20:28] is not the climax but one in a series of examples of coming to faith."⁹⁵ This result contrasts with common views expressed by commentators.⁹⁶

2.3.2. *Lee and Scott's guidelines for delineating cōla and periods*⁹⁷

Since the present study's focus will be on the methodology for delineating cōla and periods, I shall present below the guidelines set forth by Lee and Scott. The term "guidelines" is perhaps more appropriate than "criteria," as Lee and Scott do not provide a series of binding criteria but rather give a few indications that might guide the process of analysis. Beginning with the cōlon, they indicate that it "is the basic building block of analysis because it represents a breath unit, a unit of speech."⁹⁸ They note that cōla "span sense units,"⁹⁹ and the guidance they provide for delineating them comes primarily in terms of syntax:

Sometimes a colon can be identified as a predicate and all of its related elements ... In compositions with complex syntax and multiple levels of grammatical subordination, colometric boundaries frequently circumscribe a sense unit controlled by a finite verb or some other verbal element, such as a participle or infinitive ... Sometimes no verbal element is present, but εἶναι is implied ... At other times, the verbal element is implied elliptically in parallel cōla ... Conversely, sometimes a colon contains more than one finite verb. This frequently occurs with brief cola and compound predicates ...¹⁰⁰

⁹³ Lee and Scott, *SMNT*, 314–316.

⁹⁴ Lee and Scott, *SMNT*, 216.

⁹⁵ Lee and Scott, *SMNT*, 268.

⁹⁶ Lee and Scott, *SMNT*, 266.

⁹⁷ The following sections (2.3.2 and 2.3.3) retake some material previously published in P. Marschall, "Refining the Criteria for Delineating Cōla and Periods: Some Remarks on the First and Second Steps of 'Sound Mapping.'"

⁹⁸ Lee and Scott, *SMNT*, 169.

⁹⁹ Lee and Scott, *SMNT*, 169.

¹⁰⁰ Lee and Scott, *SMNT*, 169–170.

In other publications, Lee formulates a simpler rule, which she describes as “a rule of thumb”: a colon consists of a predicate, expressed or implied, and all nominal elements related to that predicate.¹⁰¹

Then, as a second step of the method, Lee and Scott propose ways to group *côla* into periods. They indicate that “*côla* can be combined paratactically or by means of grammatical subordination.”¹⁰² It should be specified that, in their view, “all prose can be understood to consist of periods”—even though they specify that style can be more or less “periodic.”¹⁰³ To put it another way, Lee and Scott distinguish different kinds of periods, indicating that “well-rounded and balanced periods could be distinguished from those that merely met certain minimal technical requirements.”¹⁰⁴ Concretely, the periods that they name “well-formed” typically exhibit *rounding* (sounds at the end of the period that echo sounds at the beginning), *balance* (parallel or antithetic *côla*), or *elongation* (the final *côlon* is longer than those that precede it and/or ends with multiple long vowels).¹⁰⁵ When such sophisticated periods follow one another, the style is qualified as “periodic.”¹⁰⁶ At the other extreme, some periods simply consist of a set of *côla* that together express a thought. When such periods succeed one another, they form a “continuous,” or “disjointed” style.¹⁰⁷ To summarise Lee and Scott’s view: whereas all prose consists of periods, the way that *côla* are combined draws a distinction between *periodic style* (made up of “well-formed” periods) and *continuous style* (made up of less-sophisticated periods).

2.3.3. First reception (J. Brickle, K. de Waal, T. Boomershine, D. Nässelqvist)

Sound Mapping the New Testament received an enthusiastic reception. Reviewers were unanimous in considering it as a breakthrough, audacious initiative.¹⁰⁸ In the few years

¹⁰¹ Lee, “A Method for Sound Analysis in Hellenistic Greek,” 169–171; Id., “Colon,” 63; see also Id., “Sound Mapping Reassessed,” 17.

¹⁰² Lee and Scott, *SMNT*, 171.

¹⁰³ Lee and Scott, *SMNT*, 179–180.

¹⁰⁴ Lee and Scott, *SMNT*, 179–180.

¹⁰⁵ Lee and Scott, *SMNT*, 171.

¹⁰⁶ Lee and Scott, *SMNT*, 179–180.

¹⁰⁷ Lee and Scott, *SMNT*, 180–181.

¹⁰⁸ See J. Pilch, review of M. E. Lee and B. B. Scott, *Sound Mapping the New Testament* (2010); Holly Hearon review of M. E. Lee and B. B. Scott, *Sound Mapping the New Testament* (2011); W. H. Kelber, review of M. E. Lee and B. B. Scott, *Sound Mapping the New Testament* (2016). See also the editorial reviews of W.H. Kelber and A. J. Dewey on the back cover of *SMNT*.

following the publication of this handbook, Lee and Scott’s method of sound mapping—or slightly different versions of their method—has been employed by multiple scholars for application on various NT texts. The first important work that demonstrated Lee and Scott’s influence is a 2012 monography by John Brickle, entitled *Aural Design and Coherence in the Prologue of First John*. Brickle discusses the possibility that “modern scholarship on the Prologue [of 1st John] may have overlooked a critical element in the passage’s underlying make-up: aural design.”¹⁰⁹ Using a method of aural analysis that is clearly indebted to Lee and Scott—yet not identical—he shows how aural patterns such as euphony, rhythm, and sound repetitions illuminate the structure of 1 John 1:1–4. This is particularly notable in light of frequent claims that the complex syntax of this passage reflects confusion. Regarding colometry specifically, however, Brickle does not go into detail. He display the text in “line units.” While the resulting disposition closely recalls Lee and Scott’s colometric presentations, Brickle does not claim that these lines strictly correspond to the ancient côla.¹¹⁰

In 2015, three monographies were published that also employ sound maps. In his *Aural-Performance Analysis of Revelation I and II*, Kayle B. de Waal addresses the question of how the first audience of the Apocalypse of John would have heard it by investigating the audience’s perception of the book’s structure. His method involves the use of sound maps as a means to shift “the focus away from authorial intent toward an audience’s experience of the performance.”¹¹¹ Thomas E. Boomershine, in his *Messiah of Peace*, explores the benefits of aural analysis for understanding the Passion-Resurrection narrative in Mark’s Gospel.¹¹² Similar to de Waal, Boomershine integrates sound mapping in a performance criticism approach, using sound maps as an additional tool for studying the performance event.¹¹³ Finally, Dan Nässelqvist’s *Public Reading in Early Christianity* is an even more clear continuation of Lee and Scott’s work; it includes significant discussion of the methodology of sound mapping.¹¹⁴ Nässelqvist sets forth a slightly different version of Lee and Scott’s method,¹¹⁵ notably including a

¹⁰⁹ J. E. Brickle, *Aural Design and Coherence in the Prologue of First John*, 107.

¹¹⁰ J. E. Brickle, *Aural Design and Coherence in the Prologue of First John*, 17, n. 85.

¹¹¹ K. B. de Waal, *An Aural-Performance Analysis of Revelation I and II*, 125.

¹¹² T. Boomershine, *A Performance-Criticism Commentary on Mark’s Passion-Resurrection Narrative*.

¹¹³ Boomershine’s book is accompanied by a website that provides video recordings of Mark 14:1–16:8 being performed in Greek and in English (www.messiahofpeace.com).

¹¹⁴ D. Nässelqvist’s, *Public Reading in Early Christianity: Lectors, Manuscripts, and Sound in the Oral Delivery of John 1-4*.

¹¹⁵ D. Nässelqvist, *Public Reading*, 119–180.

refined, more precise criteriology for cōla and periods delimitation,¹¹⁶ as well as tools for identifying the passages that are aurally emphasised.¹¹⁷ Insisting on the correspondence between composition and delivery, Nässelqvist applies his method to John 1–4 and shows how aural compositional features can inform us about the oral delivery of the Fourth Gospel.

In addition to these books, dozens of articles using sound maps have been published in the past decade. To begin with the most recent ones, we can mention the collection of essays edited in 2018 by Margaret E. Lee, in a volume entitled *Sound Matters: New Testament Studies in Sound Mapping*. This book contains ten studies that, to borrow Lee’s words, “root sound mapping more deeply in the interpretative endeavour and expand its application to a community of scholars.”¹¹⁸ Lee opens the volume with a survey of the origin and early reception of the movement, also alluding to some critics and open questions (see below, section 2.4).¹¹⁹ Adam G. White tests sound mapping on 1 Cor 1:18–31 and comes to the conclusion that a sound analysis of this passage largely affirms his previous insights on the Corinthian correspondence.¹²⁰ Bernard B. Scott uses sound maps to uncover compositional strategies for the incorporation of parables in Luke’s Gospel.¹²¹ Jeffrey E. Brickle focuses on the core technique of sound mapping—the visual depiction of a text’s aural profile—and further discusses how we might “translate the sayable into the seeable, while simultaneously reversing the process.”¹²² In his essay on the “sound message” of Phil. 1:27–2:18, Bernhard Oestreich offers fresh insights on the issue of Greek pronunciation in connection with sound mapping.¹²³ Dan Nässelqvist discusses some potential exegetical benefits of sound mapping for NT exegesis, showing how sound analysis produces various kinds of interpretative clues that can assist the exegete’s task.¹²⁴ Based on a different approach to colometry—one built upon

¹¹⁶ For cōla, see 126–133. For periods, see 134–138.

¹¹⁷ Nässelqvist uses the term “aural intensity” to characterise ways that sounds can highlight a composition’s areas of focus (*Public Reading*, 164–178).

¹¹⁸ Lee, “Introduction,” 6.

¹¹⁹ Lee, “Sound Mapping Reassessed.”

¹²⁰ A. G. White, “New Adventures in Sound Mapping: A First-Timer’s Attempt at a New Methodology.” Also see White’s major work on 1 Cor 1–4, *Where is the Wise Man?: Graeco-Roman Education as a Background to the Divisions in 1 Corinthians 1–4*.

¹²¹ B. B. Scott, “Luke’s Strategy for Interpreting Parables.”

¹²² J. E. Brickle, “Caves, Cattle, and *Koinonia*: Acoustic Shadows Across Textual Walls.” The quotation comes from page 69.

¹²³ B. Oestreich, “Investigations into the Sound’s Message of Philippians 1:27–2:18.”

¹²⁴ D. Nässelqvist, “Underexplored Benefits of Sound Mapping.”

modern linguistics—Frank Scheppers develops a sound map of Mark’s crucifixion narrative.¹²⁵ Kayle B. de Waal explores how a sound map of Revelation 8:7–12 can assist in understanding the role of this passage in the wider context of the imagery of the seven trumpets (8:1–11:19). Nina E. Livesey discusses the role of rhythm for persuasion, focusing on rhythm in the rhetoric of Paul’s letters.¹²⁶ Finally, Thomas E. Boomershine re-examines the “puzzle” of Mark 16:8. He argues that when this verse is considered as “a composition of sounds rather than as a text of visual signs,” it makes perfect sense as the ending of Mark’s Gospel.¹²⁷

Also in 2018, Nässelqvist published an article in which he proposes using ancient colometry as an argument in the debate on the punctuation of John 1:3–4.¹²⁸ Specifically, he argued that an attention to the colometric structure of the passage favours the option of placing a strong break before ὁ γέγονεν rather than after (thus καὶ χωρὶς αὐτοῦ ἐγένετο οὐδὲ ἓν. ὁ γέγονεν ἐν αὐτῷ ζῶν ἦν), as this leads to more balanced cōla.¹²⁹ The link between colometry and punctuation is also a topic that I discussed at the EABS 2017 meeting, in a session of the unit “Orality and Literacy in Early Christianity.” In this paper, I used 2 Corinthians 10:8–11 as a case study to illustrate how an attention to the ancient principles of colometry provides new arguments that renew long-standing punctuation debates¹³⁰ (on this passage, see Chapter 5 below, section 3.2).

With regard to the earlier studies that engaged in sound mapping, we can mention a 2012 article by Nina Livesey in which she employed Lee and Scott’s method to explain the presence of the second τοῖς in Rom 4:12 (this τοῖς is sometimes omitted by modern interpreters on the basis of it being regarded as a scribal slip).¹³¹ We can also note Arthur J. Dewey’s 2009 colometric disposition of Rom 1:1–7, which is explicitly inspired by Lee and Scott’s method.¹³²

¹²⁵ F. Scheppers, “Discourse Segmentation, Discourse Structure, and Sound Mapping.” On Scheppers’ work, see the excursus below, page 38.

¹²⁶ N. Livesey, “Rhythm, Sound, and Persuasion.”

¹²⁷ T. Boomershine, “The New Testament Soundscape and the Puzzle of Mark 16:8.” The quotation comes from page 215.

¹²⁸ D. Nässelqvist, “The Question of Punctuation in John 1:3–4: Arguments from Ancient Colometry.”

¹²⁹ D. Nässelqvist, “The Question of Punctuation in John 1:3–4,” 186–187.

¹³⁰ See the resulting article, P. Marschall, “Punctuating Paul’s Letters in Light of the Theory of Cōla and Periods.” This article contains a first draft of the method of colometric analysis that I develop in the present study; also see Id., “Christ est-il appelé Dieu en Rm 9,5? L’argument des figures gorgianiques” (forthcoming).

¹³¹ N. Livesey, “Sounding out the Heirs of Abraham.”

¹³² A. J. Dewey, “Competing Gospels: Imperial Echoes, A Dissident Voice,” 70.

2.4. Critical reception of SMNT

To date the methodology proposed by Lee and Scott has not required a consequent critical reception.¹³³ Two distinct critiques can be noticed, however. The first has to do with the problem of the pronunciation of ancient Greek. The second critique concerns the first and second steps of the method (i.e., the way cōla and periods are delineated).¹³⁴

2.4.1. The issue of koine Greek pronunciation

In *SMNT*, Lee and Scott do not discuss the pronunciation of ancient Greek. They are of the opinion that determining the pronunciation does not really matter when practicing sound analysis, provided that “the phonetic character of the Greek language ensures that letters and diphthongs would be voiced consistently.”¹³⁵ Such a firm position was then nuanced by some of the scholars who engaged in sound mapping (including Jeffrey E. Brickle, T. Boomershine, and Bernhard Oestreich).¹³⁶ Brickle tested and compared two different systems in his analysis of the prologue of First John, namely the so-called “Erasmian pronunciation”¹³⁷ and the “historical Greek pronunciation” as reconstructed by Chrys Caragounis.¹³⁸ In his performance-criticism commentary on Mark’s Passion-Resurrection narrative, Boomershine argued that “in Mark’s time Greek

¹³³ Here I do not integrate my own critiques that were formulated in P. Marschall, “Refining the Criteria for Delineating Cōla and Periods: Some Remarks on the First and Second Steps of Sound Mapping,” and Id., “L’analyse colométrique du Nouveau Testament. Quelques remarques sur le projet de ‘cartographie sonore’ (sound mapping)” (forthcoming).

¹³⁴ On these two early critiques, see M. E. Lee, “Sound Mapping Reassessed,” 15–18.

¹³⁵ Lee and Scott, *Sound Mapping*, 81; also see Lee, *Method for Sound Analysis*, 4; Id., “Sound Mapping Reassessed,” 15 (“The phonetic character of the Greek language ensures that letters and diphthongs would be voiced consistently”); cf. also Id., “Sound and Structure in the Gospel of Matthew,” 98–99. Nässelqvist makes a close remark (*Public Reading*, 123–124).

¹³⁶ J. E. Brickle, *Aural Design and Coherence in the Prologue of First John*; T. Boomershine, *The Messiah of Peace*; B. Oestreich, “Investigations into the Sound Message of Philippians 1:27–2:18.” See also J. J. Pilch, review of M. E. Lee and B. B. Scott, *Sound Mapping the New Testament*, 955.

¹³⁷ This refers to Erasmus’ reconstruction of ancient Greek pronunciation (see his *De recta latini graecique sermonis pronuntione*), a system which has been traditionally used for teaching ancient Greek in Western schools. Note, however, that the actual pronunciation typically used in the academic world today does not entirely corresponds to that advanced by Erasmus. The pronunciation typically used in academic teaching rather consists of a mix between Erasmus’ proposal and the pronunciation of modern Greek (on this topic, see M. Dillon, “Erasmian Pronunciation”).

¹³⁸ The “historical Greek pronunciation” refers to the system exposed by C. Caragounis in *The Development of Greek*.

was pronounced more like modern Greek than the Erasmian pronunciation.”¹³⁹ Finally, in his 2018 contribution to *Sound Matters*, Oestreich insisted on the importance of working with the appropriate model of pronunciation, pointing out that we would miss certain rhymes and alliterations if we did not take into account the evolutions of the Greek phonological system.¹⁴⁰

2.4.2. Nässelqvist’s refined criteriology for cōla and periods delineation¹⁴¹

A second critique made against Lee and Scott’s method concerns the guidelines for identifying cōla and periods. The problem is that the proposed criteria remain rather vague, thus leaving too much room for interpretation. This critique was raised primarily by Nässelqvist in his PhD dissertation (published in 2015 under the title *Public Reading in Early Christianity*). In an attempt to achieve greater precision in the description of the notions of cōlon and period, Nässelqvist re-examines the ancient rhetorical treatises. Working from the ancient sources enabled him to provide more accurate criteria for delineation. The resulting criteriology is not only more precise, but also openly conflicts with Lee and Scott’s guidelines on occasion.¹⁴² Nässelqvist’s remarks essentially fall into two categories: the length of cōla and the concept of the period.

Regarding cōla, Nässelqvist suggests that we should add the criterion of length. Indeed, as he argues, the fact that cōla are breath units (i.e., meant to be uttered without internal respiration) has a direct effect on the acceptable length; basically, cōla should be neither too short nor too long. Based on the recommendations of rhetoricians and numerous examples found in the treatises, Nässelqvist distinguishes between a standard length (9–23 syllables) and an acceptable length (7–30 syllables).¹⁴³ This represents a significant revision of Lee and Scott’s guidelines that can have a considerable impact on the choice of delineation. Regarding the syntactic nature of cōla, Nässelqvist stands in agreement with Lee and Scott, although he perhaps slightly

¹³⁹ T. Boomershine, *The Messiah of Peace*, 385. However, when himself performing Mark 14–16 (see “Mark 14–16 told in Greek”), Boomershine makes use of the so-called “erasmian pronunciation” that modern listeners are more familiar with.

¹⁴⁰ B. Oestreich, “Investigations into the Sound Message of Philippians 1:27–2:18,” esp. 86–91. The model retained by Oestreich is summarised on pages 90–91.

¹⁴¹ This section also integrates material from a previous study (P. Marschall, “Refining the Criteria for Delineating Cōla and Periods”).

¹⁴² Nässelqvist, *Public Reading*, 126–140.

¹⁴³ Nässelqvist, *Public Reading*, 129.

restrict the range of syntactic units that qualify as a cōlon by formulating a more clear equivalence between cōla and “clauses.”¹⁴⁴ He specifies that these clauses can be built upon a non-finite (infinitive, participle) or an implied verb.¹⁴⁵ In addition, he states that it occasionally happens that a cōlon encompasses two clauses.¹⁴⁶ This is especially the case when a cōlon would otherwise be too short, being under the lower limit of seven syllables.

When it comes to how cōla are grouped within periods, Nässelqvist significantly challenges Lee and Scott’s observations. He describes the period as an artistic arrangement of cōla, indicating that periods are more codified than our modern sentences. Specifically, the difference “lies in the sophisticated composition of the period.”¹⁴⁷ Hence, in the process of sound mapping, only those cōla that have specific characteristics that closely associate them with one another should be grouped into periods. Other cōla belong to “continuous prose.” Nässelqvist explains that in this alternative style, cōla are simply juxtaposed, without any periodic contour.¹⁴⁸ Note that Nässelqvist employs the same terminology (“continuous”) that Lee and Scott utilised; however, in contrast with his predecessors, he argues that the cōla of a continuous style are not combined into periods. Among the features that are typically found in periods, Nässelqvist mentions elongation (long final cōlon), hyperbaton (“abnormal word order, in which an essential idea is left suspended until the end of the sentence”¹⁴⁹), and symmetry (sound echoes, antithesis, similarity in length). Nässelqvist also suggests that periods should exhibit a “well-turned ending.”¹⁵⁰

3. Object of this Study: Colometric Analysis of Paul’s Letters

This study pursues three aims, two of which relate to issues representing “limits” in the movement of sound mapping (see section 3.1. below). The third aim more specifically

¹⁴⁴ Nässelqvist, *Public Reading*, 132: “The colon is a sense unit, which means that it *consists of* an entire clause with at least one verbal form and its related elements” (italics are mine); *ibid.*, 342. See also Id., “The Question of Punctuation,” 186: “a colon should consist of an entire clause.”

¹⁴⁵ Nässelqvist, *Public Reading*, 132, also see page 342.

¹⁴⁶ Nässelqvist, *Public Reading*, 133, n. 55.

¹⁴⁷ Nässelqvist, *Public Reading*, 125.

¹⁴⁸ Nässelqvist, *Public Reading*, 138–139.

¹⁴⁹ Nässelqvist uses the definition of hyperbaton proposed by Fowler, “Aristotle on the Period,” 98, n. 41.

¹⁵⁰ Nässelqvist, *Public Reading*, 134–138.

deals with the implications of colometry for the punctuation of Paul's letters (see section 3.2 below).

3.I. Strength and limits of sound mapping

3.I.I. A promising approach

Sound mapping is incontestably an appealing, promising approach. It has the potential to allow scholars to transcend the simple and often-made statement that early Christian texts were intended to be read aloud and received “with the ears,” and to explore how this is concretely manifested in the style of these texts. Judging by the various applications proposed so far by various scholars, the exploration of the aural properties of the NT has been fruitful for exegesis. Crucially, this new perspective brings to light elements that are hardly perceptible when a traditional “mute” perspective is adopted.

Furthermore—if we put aside the hermeneutical benefits aspect to reason at a more theoretical level—the sound mapping approach has an excellent theoretical foundation. In fact, it can rely on plenty of ancient sources. Colometry is discussed in numerous Greek and Latin rhetorical treatises, including Aristotle's *Rhetoric*, Pseudo-Demetrius' *On Style*, Cicero's *Orator*, Dionysius of Halicarnassus' *On Literary Composition*, or Quintilian's *Institutes of Oratory*, to cite only a few.¹⁵¹ While some of these treatises only mention colometry in passing, others provide detailed discussions that include definitions, examples, and an impressive range of recommendations. Still with respect to ancient sources, it is worth to note that these attest of the practice of analysing various kinds of prose texts in terms of colometry. Rhetoricians do not only apply the categories of cōlon and period to orations, but also to other genres, such as philosophical dialogues (e.g., Plato's *Republic* and *Menexenus*) or history (e.g., Herodotus' *Histories*, Thucydides' *Peloponnesian War*, Xenophon's *Anabasis*, or Hecataeus of Miletus' *Genealogies*).¹⁵² This transversal aspect of colometry gives some legitimacy to the idea that the different types of texts contained in the NT can be analysed in terms of cōla and periods. In this regard, sound mapping even has a theoretical advantage over traditional rhetorical criticism, as rhetorical criticism is usually focused on the two canons of rhetoric (*inventio* and *dispositio*) that are more clearly connected with

¹⁵¹ See a more complete list in Chapter 3 below.

¹⁵² For Plato, see Dem., *Eloc.* 205; Dion. Hal., *Comp.* 9,4. For Herodotus, see Dem., *Eloc.* 12 and *ibid.*, §17; Hermog., *Id.* 1,3,12; cf. also Arist., *Rhet.* III,9,1. For Thucydides, see Dem., *Eloc.* 45; Dion. Hal., *Comp.* 7,4. For Hecataeus of Miletus, see Dem., *Eloc.* 2 and *ibid.*, §12. For Xenophon, see Dem., *Eloc.* 2–3 and *ibid.*, §6.

speeches. In other words, analysing early Christian texts in terms of colometry (or more broadly in light of ancient stylistic theories) appears—at least as far as the rhetorical treatises are considered—more justifiable than analysing them through the lens of the three species of rhetoric and/or explaining their micro-structure in light of the ancient theories of *dispositio*.¹⁵³

Another methodological strength in the approach of sound mapping is its focus on the text itself as an object of study. The aural features that sound mapping is looking for lie *in the text*. Such a text-oriented perspective has the advantage of limiting the need for assumptions on extratextual elements, particularly as concerns the modalities of delivery. Concretely, one can analyse the aural features of a given text without positing a specific scenario regarding the modalities of delivery (from memory or from the manuscript, with or without a series of gestures, degree of interaction with the audience, etc.).¹⁵⁴ This point gives to sound mapping somewhat of an “advantage” over the performance criticism approach, which for its part is more heavily dependent upon attempts at reconstructing the event of delivery.¹⁵⁵

For all of these reasons, the methodology of sound mapping should undoubtedly be further employed and its potential hermeneutical benefits further explored in NT studies. Yet, I wish to point out here two limits that can be identified in the movement. The first limit might be deemed “technical,” as it concerns the description of *côla* and periods, as well as the way these are delineated. This limit concerns both the initial guidelines set forth by Lee and Scott and the refined criteriology developed by Nässelqvist. The second limit I wish to point out has to do with the small interest for the justification of the approach itself—specifically the analysis of the style and micro-structure of NT texts through the categories of *côlon* and period. Is it really justified to do so? That is, did early Christian authors really comply with the colometric conventions of structuration that Greek and Latin rhetoricians described? Furthermore, when performing colometric analysis on NT texts, is there not a risk of simply finding what we are looking for—*côla* and periods? I will briefly explore both of these limits and present how I will endeavour to address them within the study.

¹⁵³ See close remarks (concerning style more broadly, not colometry specifically) in S. E. Porter: “If one wants to consider the epistles as the ancients would have, so far as their explicit relation to rhetoric was concerned, one must analyse style.” (“The Theoretical Justification,” 116–117); C. Forbes, “Ancient Rhetoric and Ancient Letters,” 148; B. Witherington III, *New Testament Rhetoric*, 7sq.

¹⁵⁴ This point has been noticed by M. E. Lee, “Introduction,” 6.

¹⁵⁵ See above, section 1.2.2.

3.1.2. *Limits of the current criteria for delineating cōla and periods*

Without entering into great detail here, it can be anticipated that the criteria for delineating cōla and periods that are used in the sound mapping movement can appear problematic when they are confronted with the ancient sources.¹⁵⁶ In brief, the guidelines proposed by Lee and Scott for identifying cōla are rather vague, and their understanding that cōla should always be grouped together to form periods conflicts with the rhetoricians' precepts. In her contribution to the 2018 collective book *Sound Matters*, Lee evokes the limits of the criteriology she and Scott developed, acknowledging that "we still need more specific criteria for delineating cola and methods for analysing how cola are combined."¹⁵⁷ However, she suggests that such a task is complicated because the data from the treatises would be insufficient: "The problem resides in our sources ... Our ancient sources fail to provide more specific criteria for period and colon delineation"¹⁵⁸ This last remark is a bit reminiscent of Kleist's conclusion quoted above that the vagueness of ancient sources should allow us "a certain latitude in applying the colometric system to ancient texts."¹⁵⁹

In contrast with these pessimistic views, I share Nässelqvist's understanding that the ancient sources at disposal are not that unclear¹⁶⁰—at least when they are considered as a group and analysed carefully. The rhetorical treatises indeed provide substantial data on the topic of colometry. There are not only definitions associated with models—which represent "ideal" cōla, commata, and periods—, but also different kinds of recommendations, and last but not least, numerous extracts of classical literature that are commented on in terms of their colometric structure. Taken together, all this data permit us to build a precise—albeit imperfect—picture of what cōla, commata, and periods were in the minds of ancient rhetoricians.

That being said, I do not completely concur with Nässelqvist's views when it comes to the interpretation of the ancient material on colometry. The criteria that Nässelqvist established are indeed more specific than the guidelines that were previously formulated by Lee and Scott. However, some of these criteria appear overly precise. As I

¹⁵⁶ See the detailed discussion in Chapter 3. See also my previous remarks in P. Marschall, "Refining the Criteria for Delineating Cōla and Periods," esp. 313–323, and in Id., "L'analyse colométrique du Nouveau Testament" (forthcoming).

¹⁵⁷ M. E. Lee, "Sound Mapping Reassessed," 18.

¹⁵⁸ M. E. Lee, "Sound Mapping Reassessed," 17–18.

¹⁵⁹ J. A. Kleist, "Colometry and the New Testament (Concluded)," 26–27.

¹⁶⁰ See D. Nässelqvist, *Public Reading*, 132.

will detail in Chapter 3, some of the criteria that Nässelqvist sets forth are revealed to be too restrictive when confronted with the full range of data from the rhetorical treatises.¹⁶¹ Crucially, Nässelqvist's refined criteriology fails to account for the high flexibility of the notions of cōlon and period. As we shall see, one major difficulty in the development of criteria involves finding the right balance between criteria that are sufficiently precise and efficient, yet at the same time broad enough to reflect the flexibility of the system that ancient rhetoricians described.¹⁶²

This brings us to the first and main purpose of the present study, which is to improve the way that cōla and periods can be identified. The object is to develop criteria for delineation that better reflect the ancient sources at disposal. This task obviously constitutes a key point for the future development of sound mapping, since colometry stands at the very beginning of the process of analysis and thus influences all the rest of the process. This is especially important if we wish to use colometry as an argument in exegetical debates, such as, for example, defending a specific way of dividing or punctuating a passage (see below, section 3.2.). Concretely, refining the criteria for delineation first requires a re-examination the ancient sources (the rhetorical treatises from the Graeco-Roman world) in order to clarify the descriptions of cōla and periods. This will be addressed in Chapter 2 through an investigation into the data from some ten different treatises. Chapter 2 will also contain an assessment of the potential discrepancies between the theories of the different rhetoricians, in order to confirm that it makes sense to work with the notion that there was indeed some sort of unified "colometric system." As a second step, Chapter 3 will include a discussion on how to transform the data from the treatises into delineation criteria. This will eventually yield a method of colometric analysis. Lastly, the operationality of this method will be tested in Chapter 4, using 2 Cor 10–13 as a test case.

Excursus: Ancient colometry as an object of study by classicists

With respect to the announced need to work closely with the rhetorical treatises, one may wonder about the studies on colometry already conducted so far by classicists. Could these studies provide a sufficiently complete picture of the ancient system of colometry, such that we could develop a criteriology for cōla and periods delineation based upon them directly, thus sparing us the task of re-examining the ancient sources in detail? Indeed, an

¹⁶¹ See the detailed discussion in Chapter 3. See also my previous remarks in P. Marschall, "Refining the Criteria for Delineating Cōla and Periods," esp. 313–323, and in Id., "L'analyse colométrique du Nouveau Testament" (forthcoming).

¹⁶² See below, Chapter 3, section 1.2.

interest for ancient colometry can be observed in classical studies from the second part of the 19th century in the works of Emanuel Bernhardt,¹⁶³ Friedrich Blass,¹⁶⁴ Richard E. Volkmann,¹⁶⁵ and Adolf du Mesnil especially.¹⁶⁶ In the late 19th century, du Mesnil produced a lengthy article of nearly 100 pages devoted to the three “art forms” (*Kunstformen*) of speech (côlon, comma, and period), which long remained a reference when it came to discussing ancient colometry. Following these early works, the study of ancient colometry in the 20th century may be summarised in three parts (albeit in a simplified manner): (1) colometry through a rhythmical perspective; (2) colometry through a syntactical perspective; and (3) “philological studies” that involve analysing the material present in one or more rhetorical treatises. Below is a concise overview of the three types of existing studies and their limits.

(1) *Colometry through a rhythmical perspective: Theory and practice of rhythm in Cicero*

The turn of the 20th century marked the beginning of a vivid interest in the rhythm of Latin prose and its connection with the system of colometry. Researchers focused primarily on Cicero’s use of rhythmical clausulae (i.e., rhythmical patterns that occur at the end of periods or cōla), investigating the theory exposed in *Orator* 174–236 and *De Oratore* III, 173–198 as well as Cicero’s use of metrical feet in his own speeches and letters. Following the ground-breaking study in which Tadeusz Zieliński (1904) made an impressive effort to tabulate the various metrical feet that occur in the whole corpus of Cicero’s speeches,¹⁶⁷ many scholars discussed the topic of Latin prose rhythm, using various approaches and reaching contrasting conclusions.¹⁶⁸ Thus, A. W. de Groot (1918) looked for fixed sequences of syllables throughout speeches rather than limiting his analysis to clausulae.¹⁶⁹ Henry D. Broadhead (1922) stressed the role of accent as an essential factor in producing prose rhythm.¹⁷⁰ Walter Schmid (1959) insisted that rhythm is not confined to the ends of periods but runs all throughout prose,¹⁷¹ and also advanced the idea that rhythm should not be reduced to the question of metrical feet since it can be achieved through the use of certain figures of speech as well. Adolf Primmer (1968) somewhat re-engaged with Zieliński’s statistical approach to produce tables that present the use of different clausulae in many of

¹⁶³ E. Bernhardt, *Begriff und Grundform der griechischen Periode*.

¹⁶⁴ F. Blass, “Zur Frage über die Stichometrie der Alten,” esp. 528; Id., “Stichometrie und Kolometrie.” See also Blass’ major work in 4 volumes, *Die Attische Beredsamkeit*.

¹⁶⁵ R. E. Volkmann, *Die Rhetorik der Griechen und Römer*, esp. 505–519.

¹⁶⁶ A. du Mesnil, “Begriff der drei Kunstformen der Rede: Komma, Kolon, Periode, nach der Lehre der Alten.”

¹⁶⁷ T. Zieliński, *Das Clauselgesetz in Ciceros Reden. Grundzüge einer oratorischen Rhythmik*. Zieliński concluded that the fundamental foot is the cretic, and that Cicero’s clausulae essentially come in the three following forms: (1) cretic + trochee, (2) cretic + cretic, (3) cretic + double trochee. Prior to Zieliński, we can mention the study by H. Bornecque, *La prose métrique dans la correspondance de Cicéron* (published in 1898).

¹⁶⁸ In 1963, Wilkinson commented that “the theory of prose-rhythm is a vast and varied jungle” (*Golden Latin Artistry*, 139). See a close comment in E. Laughton’s review of E. Fraenkel, *Leseproben aus Reden Ciceros und Catos*, 188.

¹⁶⁹ A. W. de Groot, *A Handbook of Antique Prose-Rhythm*.

¹⁷⁰ H. D. Broadhead, *Prose Rhythm: A New Method of Investigation*.

¹⁷¹ W. Schmid, *Über die klassische Theorie und Praxis des antiken Prosarhythmus*.

Cicero's speeches.¹⁷² He also discussed the role of the so-called "Gorgianic figures"¹⁷³ in achieving rhythm. Barbara Stäterhoff (1995) published colometric editions of Cicero's *De imperio Gnaei Pompei* and of extracts from Livius that include statistics on the frequency of the different rhythmical patterns.¹⁷⁴ As to Marie Formarier (2014), she investigated both the theoretical principles of Latin rhythm and its practice in Cicero, in Augustine, and in Caesarius of Arles.¹⁷⁵ The recent digital-assisted approach of Tom Keeline and Tyler Kirby is also noteworthy for easing the production of statistics on prose rhythms.¹⁷⁶

Such studies on rhythm, however, have not yielded a method for delineating cōla and periods, nor a detailed description of these two notions. In fact, the study of rhythmical patterns is not primarily conceived as a means of identifying cōla and periods; rather, the identification of cōla and periods serves as a framework for determining where rhythmical clausulae should be looked for. Accordingly, cōla and periods are delineated in these studies using criteria other than rhythm. For instance, in her colometric editions of Cicero and Livius, Sträterhoff¹⁷⁷ relied on the segmentation criteria developed by Eduard Fraenkel (see below).

(2) *Colometry from a syntactical point of view: Eduard Fraenkel's notion of "kolon"*

From the 1930s onwards, Eduard Fraenkel produced important research on ancient Greek and Latin word order, in which he employed the concept of "Kolon."¹⁷⁸ A key point in his approach is the so-called Wackernagel's law, which posits that certain words—including a range of particles—tend to occur in the second position of a clause¹⁷⁹. Fraenkel crucially demonstrated that this law applies not only to clauses but also to smaller Greek and Latin syntactical units. He called these smaller units "Kola."¹⁸⁰ In later studies, he also showed that vocatives generally occur at Kola boundaries.¹⁸¹ Following Fraenkel, many scholars have applied the term "Kolon" (or the English form "colon") to short units of speech that can be found in Greek and Latin texts on the basis of criteria such as the position of certain enclitics and vocatives. It should be stressed here, however, that Fraenkel never claimed that the cola he discussed are exactly the same thing as the cōla described by ancient rhetoricians.¹⁸² This does not mean that his notion of colon is not related to ancient

¹⁷² A. Primmer, *Cicero numerosus. Studien zum antiken Prosarhythmus*.

¹⁷³ On this terminology, see M. P. Noël, "Gorgias et l' "invention" des γοργία σχήματα."

¹⁷⁴ B. Sträterhoff, *Kolometrie und Prosarhythmus bei Cicero und Livius. De imperio Cn. Pompei und Livius 1,1-26,8 kolometrisch ediert, kommentiert und statistisch analysiert*.

¹⁷⁵ M. Formarier, *Entre rhétorique et musique. Essai sur le rythme latin antique et médiéval*.

¹⁷⁶ T. Keeline and T. Kirby, "Auceps syllabarum: A Digital Analysis of Latin Prose Rhythm."

¹⁷⁷ B. Sträterhoff, *Kolometrie und Prosarhythmus bei Cicero und Livius*.

¹⁷⁸ E. Fraenkel, "Kolon und Satz. Beobachtungen zur Gliederung des antiken Satzes. I"; Id., "Kolon und Satz. Beobachtungen zur Gliederung des antiken Satzes. II"; Id., "Nachträge zu 'Kolon und Satz II'"; Id., *Noch einmal Kolon und Satz*; Id., *Leseproben aus Reden Ciceros und Catos*. A good overview of Fraenkel's work can be found in E. Laughton, review of E. Fraenkel, *Leseproben aus Reden Ciceros und Catos*; also see a instructive summary in F. Scheppers, *The Colon Hypothesis*, 7–17.

¹⁷⁹ See D. Goldstein, "Wackernagel's Law I."

¹⁸⁰ For a synthetic presentation of Fraenkel's notion of kolon, see F. Scheppers, *The Colon Hypothesis*, 7–14.

¹⁸¹ See E. Fraenkel, *Noch einmal Kolon und Satz*, 12–30.

¹⁸² See the remarks of E. Laughton, review of E. Fraenkel, *Leseproben aus Reden Ciceros und Catos*.

colometry; nevertheless, his work cannot precisely be considered as a study of the ancient notion of *côlon* as was formalised by rhetoricians.

A more recent significant study that sets forth criteria for segmenting ancient Greek texts into *cola* is Scheppers' 2011 monograph, entitled *The Colon Hypothesis: Word Order, Discourse Segmentation, and Discourse Coherence in Ancient Greek*. His work owes a lot to Fraenkel's research (Scheppers proposes a revised version of Fraenkel's typology of colon¹⁸³), while also building on Wallace L. Chafe's discourse analytical approach (with respect to the use of the notion of an "intonation unit" [IU]¹⁸⁴). Scheppers' basic hypothesis is twofold: "the colon is the unit to which Greek word order rules [P2-rules, P1-rules] are applicable," and "the colon is the elementary discourse unit, in other words: discourse *essentially* comes in *cola*."¹⁸⁵ He stresses that *cola* represent the natural speech units of ancient Greek and points out the similarity between *cola* and IUs.¹⁸⁶ Using his proposed segmentation criteria, Scheppers disposes extracts of Lysias and Plato into *cola*.¹⁸⁷

These studies certainly illuminate important structuring devices operating in ancient Greek and Latin prose. In so doing, they perhaps also shed light on particular aspects of ancient colometry. However, because these approaches are not based on the rhetorical treatises, there remains uncertainty as to whether all the units Fraenkel and his successors label "*cola*" would effectively have been considered *côla* by ancient rhetoricians.¹⁸⁸ Actually, it seems to me that the approach initiated by Fraenkel permits the identification of *potential* *côla* boundaries; namely to determine where *côla* boundaries *might* occur from a syntactic viewpoint. In any case, the point remains—as will be further discussed in Chapters 2 and 3—that ancient *côla* are more than syntactic units and therefore they cannot be identified on the sole basis of syntactic criteria. By way of example, in examining the colometric dispositions of Lysias and Plato that Scheppers provides, we regularly find very short units of one or two words that are labelled "*cola*."¹⁸⁹ However, it appears unlikely that all constitute *côla* when attention is paid to the examples of *côla* provided by ancient rhetoricians.¹⁹⁰

(3) *Philological studies throughout the 20th century*

In addition to the rhythmical and syntactic perspectives, there are of course studies that deal more directly with the material from the ancient treatises. These are somewhat scattered. To risk oversimplification, we can say that on the one hand there are micro-studies that centre on a specific notion of individual rhetoric; on the other hand, more general studies on style or commentaries on a specific treatise treat colometry only in

¹⁸³ See the discussion in F. Scheppers, *The Colon Hypothesis*, 10–15.

¹⁸⁴ On the notion of "intonation unit," see F. Scheppers, *The Colon Hypothesis*, 18–35. See also W. L. Chafe, *Discourse, Consciousness, and Time. The Flow and Displacement of Conscious Experience in Speaking and Writing*.

¹⁸⁵ F. Scheppers, *The Colon Hypothesis*, 17 (italics in the text).

¹⁸⁶ See F. Scheppers, *The Colon Hypothesis*, 177.

¹⁸⁷ F. Scheppers, *The Colon Hypothesis*, 227–268.

¹⁸⁸ Despite Thomas Habinek's efforts to demonstrate that Fraenkel's *kolon* essentially concurs with the ancient notion of *côlon* (T. Habinek, *The Colometry of Latin Prose*).

¹⁸⁹ See F. Scheppers, *The Colon Hypothesis*, 227–270.

¹⁹⁰ See below, Chapter 3, section 2.1.2.

passing, therefore keeping the descriptions in general terms. In the former case, one common question is whether Aristotle had a rhythmical or a syntactical definition of the period.¹⁹¹ In the latter case, colometric elements are found within broader commentaries on a particular treatise or in studies on style in general. In this context, the notions of cōlon and period tend to be treated in a general manner, without detailed discussions. As a result, the general impression that emerges from these studies is that they are either too specific or too general when it comes to implementing colometric analysis. The field lacks an overall survey that would provide detailed descriptions of the notions of cōlon, comma, and period by taking into account the various sources at disposal while also questioning the potential evolutions of these concepts and the nuances between rhetoricians. The most detailed descriptions so far are probably those found in Heinrich Lausberg's *Handbuch der literarischen Rhetorik* and in Ueding's *Historisches Wörterbuch der Rhetorik*. The devoted articles in these encyclopaedias provide detailed descriptions of the cōlon, the comma, and the period, in terms of both length and syntax.¹⁹² However, even these articles cannot be used to establish a convincing criteriology for colometric analysis. Although these descriptions are directly based upon the definitions and models that are given by ancient rhetoricians, they do not embrace the large quantity of supplemental data present in the treatises (examples, comments, recommendations, etc.), thereby resulting in a very theoretical, "ideal" picture of the ancient system of colometry. For example, important questions are not directly addressed, such as the maximal length that is acceptable for cōla, or the boundary between periodic and non-periodic styles.

Conclusion: Necessity of working directly from the ancient sources

In considering the few elements presented above, it becomes clear that none of the research undertaken so far by classicists can serve as a sufficient basis to identify cōla in a given text, nor to determine when cōla should be grouped within periods. In other words, the existing studies—despite their usefulness for understanding certain aspects of ancient colometry or the doctrine of individual rhetorician—prove insufficient when it comes to formulating clear criteria for delineation. Consequently, the one who wishes to set forth historically informed criteria for sound mapping has no choice but to re-examine the rhetorical treatises.

3.1.3. The justification for the application of the categories of cōlon and period to the New Testament writings

Turning now to the second of the issues raised above—that which concerns the legitimacy of applying the categories of cōlon and period to early Christian texts. The essential question might be formulated as follows: does it make sense to apply these categories that come from classical rhetoric to texts whose authors probably never

¹⁹¹ See, among others, J. Zehetmeier, "Die Periodenlehre des Aristoteles," 192–208, 255–284, 414–436; G. A. Kennedy, "Aristotle on the Period"; R. L. Fowler, "Aristotle on the Period (Rhet. 3.9)"; P. Chiron, "La période chez Aristote," 103–130.

¹⁹² See H. Lausberg, "Elocutio," esp. §923–947; also see P. Dräger, "Periode"; Id., "Kolon"; Id., "Komma." The more recent articles in the *Handbook of Classical Rhetoric* (Rowe, "Style," 151–153) and in the encyclopaedia *Der Neue Pauly* (West, "Kolon"; G. Schade, "Periode") are less detailed.

attended rhetoric classes? The underlying question is the adequation between the method and the object of study.¹⁹³ It seems that this question has been given too little attention in the first developments of sound mapping. When reading Lee and Scott's handbook, the general impression that emerges is that they assume that early Christian writings all and logically comply with the stylistic conventions described by Greek and Latin rhetoricians. Indeed, such an assumption is not completely unfounded in view of the socio-cultural context in which NT texts were composed and first circulated. One may reasonably suppose—with respect to colometry—that the rhetorical treatises at hand do nothing but codify conventions of structuring prose that were widely shared among Greek and Latin authors at the time. In some sense, there is no reason to think that early Christian authors would not adhere to these conventions. This seems to be the foundational reasoning of Lee and Scott's project that has largely been accepted by early practitioners of sound mapping.

In pursuing the line of argument from a socio-cultural context, we may advance two more arguments. First, as mentioned above (see section 3.1.1), the rhetorical treatises clearly suggest that the principles of colometry were used for a large range of prose texts and were not specifically designed for orations. This point lends further weight to the assumption that also the different forms of early Christian texts—whether compositions of a narrative nature (such as the Gospels and the Acts of the Apostles), apocalyptic literature, or apostolic letters—were structured colometrically. Second, one can find ancient attestations of the application of colometry to biblical texts. For example, Augustine, who analysed 2 Cor 11:16-30 in terms of *membra*, *caesa*, and *ambitus*,¹⁹⁴ or Jerome, who disposed some parts of his Latin translation of the Bible *per cola et commata* (at least Ezekiel and Isaiah).¹⁹⁵

All in all, many arguments can be advanced to justify the practice of analysing NT texts's style in terms of colometry. Yet, these arguments are in themselves not fully satisfying. Even Augustine and Jerome's uses of colometry—which at first may seem like a strong argument—are not a proof that early Christian authors structured their texts in *côla* and periods. This is, at best, an argument of authority. Indeed, their

¹⁹³ This echoes a long-standing debate over the justification for application of graeco-roman rhetoric to Pauline letters: see e.g., J. F. Reed, "Using Ancient Rhetorical Categories to Interpret Paul's Letters: A Question of Genre" and S. E. Porter, "The Theoretical Justification for Application of Rhetorical Categories to Pauline Epistolary Literature"; Id., "Paul as Epistolographer and Rhetorician?."

¹⁹⁴ August., *Doct. Chr.* 7,12–13.

¹⁹⁵ Jer., *Prol. Isaiah* 1 (= PL vol. 28, 771); Id., *Prol. Ezechiel* 2 (= PL vol. 28, 938–939).

testimonies are temporally quite distant from the writing of the first Christian literature. Moreover, Jerome also applied colometry to prophetic books of the Hebrew Bible, the authors of which are unlikely to have followed the precepts of Graeco-Roman rhetoric. To clarify: reasoning from a socio-cultural context certainly permits us to draw what might be called a “framework of plausibility” for the hypothesis that NT texts are formed of *côla* and periods. However, even if we add the empirical argument that sound mapping “works” (in that it has already proven efficient as an analytical tool aimed at illuminating aural logic in various NT texts), the question of the *degree of correspondence* between the stylistic principles employed by early Christian authors and those described by rhetoricians remains. This is a crucial question to address if we wish to use the insights from colometric analysis to address precise exegetical issues. For example, if using ancient colometry as an argument to discuss punctuation issues (see below, section 3.2), it becomes necessary to ensure that the colometric approach is not only somewhat appropriate but is genuinely appropriate. Otherwise, there is a risk of simply finding what we are looking for (that is, finding *côla* and periods in NT texts because we began with the assumption that these texts are indeed structured that way). Empirical testing ought to be used to evaluate the extent to which early Christian authors comply with the colometric conventions of structuration. The sole option is to observe the texts studied in light of the rhetoricians’ precepts and then to critically assess the degree of correspondence between the two.¹⁹⁶

It goes without saying that the question of the appropriateness of the colometric approach for the NT cannot be answered once and applied to the whole corpus, given that the NT is not a homogeneous corpus. The books that compose it were not all written by a single author, and arguably not with the exact same audience in mind. Some may have been originally composed in Hebrew or Aramaic.¹⁹⁷ It is also debatable whether all NT texts were intended for oral “performances.” Perhaps some of them (e.g., certain letters) were not conceived with an oral delivery in mind, in which case the question arises as to whether these texts also exhibit oral-aural features? In the limits of this study, I will only discuss the case of the so-called proto-pauline letters; that is, the seven letters that contemporary scholarship almost unanimously recognises to have

¹⁹⁶ On the need for empirical tests to validate the colometric approach for NT texts, see also the discussion in P. Marschall, “L’analyse colométrique du Nouveau Testament. Quelques remarques sur le projet de ‘cartographie sonore’ (*sound mapping*)” (forthcoming).

¹⁹⁷ See a similar remark in J. J. Pilch, review of M. E. Lee and B. B. Scott, *Sound Mapping the New Testament*, 955.

been composed by Paul of Tarsus in the 50s (and perhaps early 60s) of the 1st century CE (Romans, 1 Corinthians, 2 Corinthians, Galatians, Philippians, 1 Thessalonians, Philemon).¹⁹⁸ Specifically, I will discuss the appropriateness of colometry for Paul's letters on the basis of an essay of colometric analysis of 2 Cor 10–13. The strategy is to observe the results of this essay and then assess whether there are sufficient elements indicating that the principles of colometry were respected in the text. This will be discussed in the second part of Chapter 4. As a preface to the discussion, it can already be said that the results are encouraging. They tend to confirm that Paul's letters effectively comply with the conventions of colometry described by ancient rhetoricians to a significant extent.

3.2. The implications of colometry for punctuating Paul's letters

In the introduction, I mentioned that one of my early point of interest in sound mapping was related to the possibility of using the principles of colometry to address punctuation issues in Paul's letters. Indeed, as far as grammar is concerned, Paul's prose is regularly ambiguous. Notably, it sometimes happens that the syntax allows for different segmentations, with a word or a sequence of words that can be construed either with what precedes it or with what follows it. In those cases, paying attention to the colometric structure of the passage at hand might help to orient the debates by illuminating often neglected aural devices of structuration. This initial interest did not disappear.¹⁹⁹ To be transparent, it is this interest in punctuation that originally convinced me that it was worth taking the time to develop a more detailed criteriology for delineating *côla* and periods. Indeed, the one who wishes to argue for punctuation choices on the basis of colometry should be able to provide solid justification for his or her delineation choices.

The implications of colometry for the punctuation of Paul's letters will be discussed in the final chapter (Chapter 5). After presenting a preliminary discussion on the role of punctuation marks and the connection between colometry and "oral punctuation," I will explore two different areas of application. To begin with, I shall investigate the

¹⁹⁸ The literature on Paul of Tarsus is immense. To cite only a few reference works, we can mention J. Becker, *Paulus: Der Apostel der Völker*; O. Wischmeyer (ed.), *Paulus. Leben – Umwelt – Werk – Briefe* (ET: *Paul: Life, Setting, Work, Letters*); U. Schnelle, *Paulus. Leben und Denken* (ET: *Apostle Paul: His Life and Theology*); K. Dorn, *Paulus. Geschichte – Überlieferung – Glaube*.

¹⁹⁹ See P. Marschall, "Punctuating Paul's Letters in Light of the Ancient Theory of *Côla* and Periods," and Id., "Christ est-il appelé Dieu en Romains 9,5 ? L'argument des figures gorgianiques."

potential benefits of colometric analysis for punctuation disputes. 2 Corinthians 10–13 will once again serve as a test case for doing so, with a discussion of several extracts included. As will be demonstrated, an attention to the colometric structure of Paul’s prose occasionally helps to orient the debates concerning the appropriate segmentation—and thus, the appropriate punctuation—of ambiguous passages. I will also show that a colometric approach seriously challenges the habits of punctuation that are proposed in current critical editions of the NT. Furthermore, I will discuss how a colometric approach can suggest ways to punctuate Paul’s letters in a manner that better reflect their inner, aural logic.

3.3. *Recapitulation: Aims, methods, and structure of the present study*

Let us summarise the three aims of the present study, as well as highlight how the investigation will be conducted throughout the next four chapters.

First, this study aims to develop a method of *colometric analysis*—understood as a set of criteria that may guide the delineation of *côla* and periods in ancient Greek texts. The purpose is to develop a criteriology that is as historically informed as possible; concretely, a criteriology that best reflects the data found in the rhetorical treatises from the Graeco-Roman world. This will constitute a major part of the study and will be achieved in three steps: first, a lengthy examination of the data from the treatises (Chapter 2); then, a discussion of how these data might be transformed into a set of criteria (Chapter 3); finally, a test of operationality of the method through the case study of 2 Corinthians 10–13 (Chapter 4). Beyond the strict purpose of developing a method of colometric analysis, the final intent is that the proposed delineation criteria may later be employed by exegetes involved in sound mapping or in the study of *elocutio* more broadly.

Second, the present study aims to ensure that the very idea of applying the categories of *côlon* and period to the correspondence of Paul of Tarsus makes sense. It is a question of justifying the use of a colometric approach in analysing Paul’s letters. This will not be discussed theoretically but will be achieved empirically through the essay of colometric analysis of 2 Cor 10–13 presented in Chapter 4. More specifically, I will show that there are a few pieces of evidence that strongly suggest that Paul employed the colometric conventions of structuration.

Finally, following these three chapters that all deal with the methodology of colometric analysis, Chapter 5 will include a discussion on the practical implications of

colometry for the interpretation of Paul's letters. Specifically, we will explore how a colometric approach may assist the efforts for punctuating Paul's prose in a manner that better takes account for its oral logic. The discussion will once again be based on the case study of 2 Cor 10–13.

CHAPTER 2

Côla, Commata, and Periods: The Data from the Rhetorical Treatises

I. Introduction and Method

I.I. *Purpose of this chapter*

Having established the need to further investigate the notions of cōlon, comma and period, we now turn to consider our primary ancient sources; namely, the rhetorical treatises from the Graeco-Roman world. This chapter is entirely devoted to a lengthy examination of the data provided in these treatises: the term “data” should here be understood in a broad sense, comprising definitions, recommendations, models (i.e., typical examples that rhetoricians give to illustrate the definitions or the recommendations they provide¹), as well as extracts of classical works that are analysed in terms of their colometric structure. This journey through the rhetorical treatises will serve two distinct purposes. The first and main purpose is of course to collect the data that will serve as the basis for establishing the method of *colometric analysis*. The second purpose, which will be pursued in parallel, is to affirm the stability of the three notions of cōlon, comma and period that were used by different rhetoricians and over diverse time periods. Of course, it would be naive to simply assume that all of the ancient rhetoricians fully agreed on what cōla, commata and periods comprised² and how they should be used to structure prose “texts.”³ This chapter will therefore provide a lengthy review of the evidence that rhetoricians shared a common view of colometry, so as to defend the use of data from their different works to build a common set of criteria for colometric analysis. To put it another way, we have to ensure that expressions such as “the ancient system of colometry” or “the theory of cōla, commata and periods,” in the singular, make sense. Otherwise, the risk would be to reconstruct a composite theory that fails to reflect ancient reality.

¹ As Habinek remarks, “the examples cited by an ancient rhetor in support of his claims can be more informative than the claim itself” (*The Colometry of Latin Prose*, 26).

² The absence of a strong diachronic perspective constitutes a major limitation of current approaches to colometry in the field of sound mapping—and, more generally, of biblical scholars’ approach to ancient rhetoric (on this, see R. D. Anderson Jr., “Use and Abuse of Lausberg,” esp. 75). Indeed, when developing their respective methods for delineating cōla and periods, both M. E. Lee and B. B. Scott (*Sound Mapping the New Testament*) and D. Nässelqvist (*Public Reading in Early Christianity*) tend to pick up scattered elements from different treatises, without paying sufficient attention to the issue of the stability and/or the different nuances of the rhetoricians’ precepts.

³ “Text” refers here to a “piece of discourse,” that may or may not circulate via a written medium. On my use of the term “text,” see the remarks above in the general introduction, footnote 10.

1.2. *Treatises considered*

The treatises that will be discussed in this chapter are listed below. The work of each rhetorician will be considered on its own, in an attempt to avoid mapping one rhetorician's doctrine onto another's. The discussion will follow a chronological order, from the *Rhetoric* of Aristotle, dated to the second half of the 4th century BCE—making it the oldest testimony on colometry⁴—to Hermogenes' *On Ideas*, dated to the late 2nd century or early 3rd century CE:

- Aristotle, *Art of Rhetoric* (*Rhet.* – second half of the 4th century BCE)
- Pseudo-Demetrius of Phalerum, *On Style* (*Eloc.* – late 2nd or early 1st century BCE [?])⁵
- [Anonymous], *Rhetoric for Herennius* (*Rhet. Her.* – '80s BCE)
- Cicero, *On the Orator* (*De or.* – 55 BCE); *Orator* (*Or. Brut.* – 46 BCE)
- Dionysius of Halicarnassus, *On Literary Composition* (*Comp.* – late 1st century BCE)
- Quintilian, *The Orator's Education* (*Inst.* – '90 s CE)
- Alexander, *On Figures* (*Fig.* – middle of the 2nd century CE)
- Pseudo-Aelius Aristides, *On Political Discourse* (*Pol.* – 2nd century CE)
- Hermogenes of Tarsus, *On Ideas* (*Id.* – late 2nd or early 3rd century CE)

Of course, this survey could have been extended to include slightly later treatises, notably Pseudo-Herodian's *On Figures* (which may go back to the 2nd century CE),⁶ Anonymous Seguerianus' *Art of Political Speech* (first part of the 3rd century CE [?]),⁷ Aspines of Gadara's *Art of Rhetoric* (first part of the 3rd century CE),⁸ Cassius Longinus'

⁴ To be sure, this does not mean that Aristotle invented the conception of prose as comprising *côla* and periods. According to the Souda, the first usage of *περίοδος* and *κῶλον* in a rhetorical context goes back to Thrasymachus, a sophist from the 5th century BCE (Θρασύμαχος, in *Suidae Lexicon*, 508). However, little is known about the origin of the rhetorical use of the terms *περίοδος* and *κῶλον*. It is sometimes thought that the two terms originated in metrical terminology; see e.g. O. Schroeder, *Nomenclator Metricus*, 36; E. Norden, *Die Antike Kunstprosa*, 42 n. 2; Zehetmeier, "Die Periodenlehre des Aristoteles," 274 n. 53. In contrast, T. Flemming ("The Origin of the Period") argues that the rhetorical use of *περίοδος* was borrowed from musical theory and lyric poetry.

⁵ The dates are uncertain for many of these treatises. Some indications and references are given below in footnotes to the respective introductions to each of the treatises.

⁶ See the Greek text established by K. Hajdú, *Ps.-Herodian, De figuris*. On the issues of date and authorship, see *ibid.*, 19–23; cf. also E. Dickey, "A Catalogue of Works Attributed to the Grammarian Herodian," 340.

⁷ M. R. Dilts and G. A. Kennedy (ed. and trans.), *Two Greek Rhetorical Treatises from the Roman Empire*. On datation and authorship, see the discussion by M. Patillon in the introduction to his edition of the treatise (Patillon, "Introduction" [*Anonyme de Séguier: Art du discours politique*], xvii–xxv).

⁸ M. R. Dilts and G. A. Kennedy (ed. and trans.), *Two Greek Rhetorical Treatises from the Roman Empire*. On the date and authorship of this treatise, see the discussion by M. Patillon in the introduction to his edition of the treatise (Patillon, "Introduction" [*Aspinès, Art rhétorique. Problèmes à faux-semblant*], xii–ix).

Art of Rhetoric (mid-3rd century CE),⁹ Aquila Romanus' *On Figures* (mid-3rd century CE [?]),¹⁰ Pseudo-Hermogenes' *On Invention* (3rd or 4th century CE, but possibly based on a work from the 2nd century CE [?]),¹¹ and so on. Indeed, these treatises also preserve significant developments on the topic of colometry. Nevertheless, a detailed examination of these later treatises is not necessary in the context of this study, for at least two reasons. First, the date of Paul's letters, which is almost unanimously placed in the middle of the 1st century CE, meaning that the timeframe covered in this chapter already extends about one and a half century after Paul's activity as a letter writer.¹² Second, the treatises considered already provide sufficient data to paint a comprehensive picture of ancient conventions that shaped the micro-structure of prose texts.

Only those treatises that contain useful data for the purposes of this study have been retained in the discussion below. The *Rhetoric for Alexander* (second part of the 4th century BCE)¹³ and Pseudo-Longinus' *On the Sublime* (early or mid-2nd century CE [?])¹⁴ have therefore been excluded. These treatises only make occasional use of the terms colon, comma, and period (the term period does not even appear in the *Rhetoric for Alexander*) and are consequently of little help.

⁹ A critical edition including a French translation has been published in 2001 by Les Belles Lettres: M. Patillon (ed. and trans.), *Longin, Fragments. Art rhétorique. Rufus, Art rhétorique*. According to Patillon's numbering, Longinus' *Art of Rhetoric* corresponds to fragment 48.

¹⁰ A critical edition including an Italian translation has been published in 2007 by M. Elice (*Romani Aquilae De figuris*). On the issues of dating and authorship, see the introduction of this edition (Elice, "Introduzione," XXXIX-LII).

¹¹ A critical edition including a French translation has been published in 2012 by Les Belles Lettres: M. Patillon (ed. and trans.), *Pseudo-Hermogène, L'Invention. Anonyme, Synopse des Exordes. Anonyme, Scolies au traité Sur l'Invention du Pseudo-Hermogène (= Corpus Rhetoricum, tome III)*. For an English translation, which relies mainly on the Greek text established in the early 20th century by H. Rabe, see G. A. Kennedy, *Invention and Method*. On the issues of date and authorship, see G. A. Kennedy, "On Invention: Introduction," xiii–xix: "On *Invention* might be based to a considerable extent on a work of the mid-2nd century C.E., thought largely written in the 3rd or even 4th century and revised into its present form in the 5th or 6th when it was adapted to fill out the Hermogenic 'Art of Rhetoric,'" p. xvi); cf. Patillon, "Introduction" (*Corpus Rhetoricum III*), xi–xv.

¹² There is a consensus concerning the date of the following seven letters: Romans, 1 Corinthians, 2 Corinthians, Galatians, 1 Thessalonians, Philippians, and Philemon. These are considered by virtually all scholars as having been composed by the apostle Paul himself, in the '50s and possibly early '60s of the 1st century CE. See e.g. F. Vouga, "Le corpus paulinien"; cf. also R. E. Brown, *An Introduction to the New Testament*, 1054–1074.

¹³ This treatise is sometimes thought to be the work of Anaximenes of Lampsacus. On the issues of authorship and date, see G. A. Kennedy, *A New History of Classical Rhetoric*, 49–51. A critical edition including an English translation can be found in R. Mayhew and D. C. Mirhady (ed. and transl.), *Aristotle, Problems, books 20–38. Rhetoric to Alexander* (LCL).

¹⁴ On the issues of date and authorship, see G. A. Kennedy, *A New History of Classical Rhetoric*, 191–192. A critical edition including an English translation can be found in *Aristotle: Poetics. Longinus: On the Sublime. Demetrius: On Style* (trans. W. Hamilton Fyfe, revised by D. A. Russell; LCL).

2. Aristotle, *Art of Rhetoric* (Τέχνη ρητορική / *Ars rhetorica* [*Rhet.*] – second half of the 4th century BCE)¹⁵

Aristotle (ca. 384–ca. 322 BCE) is credited with laying the foundations of the system of rhetoric that would then be used throughout the Hellenistic and Roman periods.¹⁶ Indeed, the influence of his thought on the development of the art of rhetoric cannot be overestimated: he is often considered to be the father of the Western rhetorical tradition, in the same way as Socrates and Plato are referred to as the fathers of Western philosophy.¹⁷ Aristotle’s reflections on colometry are found primarily in the third book of the *Art of Rhetoric*, which deals with style and delivery: specifically, the discussion of cōla and periods—the term “comma” does not appear in the *Rhetoric*—is concentrated in chapter 9. This work is generally thought to be the result of Aristotle’s activity in Athens from 335 to 322, when he was running his own school, the Lyceum, which gave rise to the peripatetic tradition. However, some of the content arguably dates from as early as 350–340, while Aristotle was still a member of Plato’s Academy.¹⁸ The *Rhetoric* is a difficult work, written in a highly compressed style¹⁹ and containing apparent inconsistencies, probably because it was written at different times and with potentially different audiences in mind.²⁰ Its compressed style may indicate that the text was originally not intended for publication but rather served as a lecture aid for Aristotle’s courses.

2.1. *Two kinds of style: “sewn” (εἰρομένη λέξις) and “interwoven” (κατεστραμμένη λέξις)*

Aristotle begins his presentation of colometry by distinguishing two kinds of *lexis*: the εἰρομένη λέξις (“sewn” or “fastened together in rows” *lexis*) as opposed to the κατεστραμμένη λέξις (“interwoven” *lexis*), an opposition that draws a distinction

¹⁵ *Art of Rhetoric* (trans. J. H. Freese, revised by G. Striker, based on the Greek text established by R. Kassel; LCL). The translations below are mine, based on the Greek text presented in the LCL edition; at certain places I am indebted to the translation by Freese and Striker or to that by G. A. Kennedy (*On Rhetoric: A Theory on Civic Discourse*).

¹⁶ For short introductions to Aristotle’s life and his work on rhetoric, we can mention those by G. A. Kennedy (*A New History of Classical Rhetoric*, 51–63) and J. M. Atwill (“Aristotle,” in *Classic Rhetorics and Rhetoricians*, 51–64). Cf. also Freese and Striker, “Introduction” (*Art of Rhetoric*), xi–xxiii.

¹⁷ The rich tradition of commentaries on the *Rhetoric* testifies to the great impact of this work on the Western rhetorical tradition. See on this topic the collective volume recently edited by F. Woerther, *Commenting on Aristotle’s Rhetoric, from Antiquity to the Present*.

¹⁸ G. A. Kennedy, *A New History of Classical Rhetoric*, 53–54.

¹⁹ See G. A. Kennedy, *A New History of Classical Rhetoric*, 54.

²⁰ G. A. Kennedy, *A New History of Classical Rhetoric*, 55.

between two basic means of expression or two “styles.” The relevant discussion runs as follows:

It is necessary for the expression [λέξις] to be either *sewn* [εἰρομένη] and united only by connecting particles, like the non-strophic structure of dithyrambs [ὥσπερ αἱ ἐν τοῖς διθυράμβοις ἀναβολαί],²¹ or *interwoven* [κατεστραμμένη] and like the antistrophes of the ancient poets. The sewn style [λέξις] is the ancient one [[for example, “Of Herodotus of Thurii this is the account of the investigation”]].²² It was formerly used by all, but now is used only by a few. I call sewn that which has no end [τέλος] in itself and only stops when the thing expressed has been made complete. It is unpleasant, because it is unlimited [ἄπειρον]; for all wish to foresee the end. That explains why runners, when they have just reached the goal [καμπτήρες], lose their breath and strength, whereas before, when the end is in sight, they show no signs of fatigue. Such is the sewn style [λέξις]; the other style consists of periods. I call *period* a saying [λέξις] that has a beginning and end in itself [ἀρχὴν καὶ τελευτὴν αὐτὴν καθ’ αὐτὴν] and a magnitude that can be easily grasped [μέγεθος εὐσύνοπτον].²³

The εἰρομένη style is said to be the most ancient. In texts belonging to this style, sayings are juxtaposed, being fastened or strung together by “connecting particles”—lit., “by a fastening” (τῷ συνδέσμῳ μίαν)—according to a model that proceeds by addition (a + b + c, etc.). Those sayings, Aristotle explains, “[have] no end in [themselves],” as they simply stop when the thing expressed has been completed.²⁴ In the first clause of Herodotus’ *Histories* (Ἡροδότου Θουρίου ἡδ’ ἱστορίας ἀπόδειξις), which is the only illustration he provides of this style, there is indeed no internal clue signalling that the thought has come to its end, such that a continuation is almost expected after the final word. However, as has been regularly noted in scholarship, the presence of this example raises many questions, especially given that Pseudo-Demetrius would later quote the first clause of the *Histories* as a model of the period!²⁵ Hence, we may wonder whether the remainder of the opening of the *Histories* must not be supplied, and if so, up to

²¹ For the translation of ἀναβολαί, I follow the suggestion of R. L. Fowler, “Aristotle on the Period,” 90–91 (see also the short discussion in P. Chiron, “La période chez Aristote,” 111–112). Freese’s original translation (*Art of Rhetoric* 1926) has “like the dithyrambic preludes” a choice kept in the recent revision by Striker (*Art of Rhetoric*, 387); cf. Dufour and Wartelle, who propose the French word “prélude.”

²² Herod., *Hist.* 1.1.0. The double brackets indicate that some scholars consider this example to be a later interpolation (see below, n. 27).

²³ *Rhet.* III,9,1–3. It is difficult to find a satisfactory English equivalent for the term λέξις, which appears many times in this extract. This lexeme can take on different meanings: it can signify a means of expression (i.e., a kind of style), but it can also designate the expression itself, which may consist of a short passage (a specific saying) or an entire speech. On the meaning of λέξις in Aristotle, see A. Cotaric, *Aristotle on Language and Style: The Concept of Lexis*, esp. 14–38.

²⁴ On the concept of ἄπειρον (“unlimited,” “infinite,” “indefinite,” “endless”), see a few remarks in P. Chiron, “La période chez Aristote,” 113–114.

²⁵ Demetrius regards this clause as a monocōlon period (*Eloc.* 17). For an overview of the many questions raised by the presence of this example in the *Rhetoric*, see J. Dillery, “Herodotus’ Proem and Aristotle.”

where? In other words, does Aristotle really have only the clause he quotes in mind, or does his comment apply in fact more broadly to the first lines of the *Histories*, or perhaps even to Herodotus' style in general (which is indeed commonly recognised as non-periodic)?²⁶ Or should we rather, with G. A. Kennedy and R. L. Fowler, regard this example as a later interpolation, possibly by some confused student?²⁷ As a third alternative explanation, advanced notably by J. Dillery and P. Chiron, we could note that the formulation kept in the *Rhetoric* differs from the text transmitted by other sources, including Demetrius, where ἦδε stands as the final word (Ἡροδότου Ἀλικαρνασῆος Θουρίου ἱστορίας ἀπόδειξις ἦδε).²⁸ We could therefore argue that the placement of ἦδε earlier in the saying destroys its periodic character, such that the version present in the *Rhetoric* indeed belongs to non-periodic style.²⁹ In any case, the fact that there is only one example of εἰρομένη λέξις means we cannot grasp precisely Aristotle's meaning here, especially with respect to the syntactic relation between the sayings that are "sewn together." There is little more to learn about this style: Aristotle briefly concludes that it should be avoided because its endless aspect makes it unpleasant, before he turns to discuss the κατεστραμμένη λέξις.

Different English translations have been suggested for εἰρομένη λέξις. One frequently found—and which is also retained in the field of sound mapping—is "continuous style,"³⁰ which insists on the idea that the end of the sayings is barely marked. Other propositions include "loose style"³¹ and "strung-on style."³² The latter has the advantage of remaining close to the meaning of the verb εἶρω ("string," "fasten

²⁶ See D. M. Schenkeveld, who considers that the remainder of the introduction of Herodotus' *Histories* must be supplied, up to the words "ἐπολέμησαν ἀλλήλοις" (thus: Ἡροδότου Θουρίου ἦδ' ἱστορίας ἀπόδειξις, ὡς μήτε τὰ γενόμενα ἐξ ἀνθρώπων τῷ χρόνῳ ἐξίτηλα γένηται, μήτε ἔργα μεγάλα τε καὶ θωमाστά, τὰ μὲν Ἕλλησι τὰ δὲ βαρβάροισι ἀποδεχθέντα, ἀκλεᾶ γένηται, τὰ τε ἄλλα καὶ δι' ἣν αἰτίην ἐπολέμησαν ἀλλήλοις). Schenkeveld comments that "then it will be clear that Herodotus does not express himself here in units limited by rhythm [i.e., periods] but merely connects groups of words." (*Studies in Demetrius' On Style*, 38). Cf. Demetrius' comment that Herodotus' style is generally non-periodic (Dem., *Eloc.* 12).

²⁷ The original text would thus have stood as follows: "The sewn *lexis* is the ancient one. For it was formerly used by all, but now is used only by a few." See further G. A. Kennedy, "Aristotle on the Period," 285; Id. (ed.), *On Rhetoric*, 214, n. 83; cf. R. L. Fowler, "Aristotle on the Period," 95; cf. also R. Kassel (*Aristotelis Ars Rhetorica*, 164), who thinks that the misquotation of Herodotus might be a later addition by Aristotle himself.

²⁸ Dem., *Eloc.* 17.

²⁹ Dillery, "Herodotus' Proem and Aristotle," 528; P. Chiron, "La période chez Aristote," 116–117; Id., *Un rhéteur méconnu*, 87–90.

³⁰ See e.g. the reference translation by Freese and Striker, *Art of Rhetoric*, 387, or that by Fowler, "Aristotle on the Period," 90; see also, in the field of NT studies, Lee and Scott, *Sound Mapping*, 112–114. Nässelqvist prefers "continuous prose" or "continuous composition" (*Public Reading*, 138–139).

³¹ For "loose style," see notably the translation by R. Waterfield, *Aristotle, The Art of Rhetoric*, 133.

³² For "strung-on," see notably the translation by G. A. Kennedy, *Aristotle, On Rhetoric*, 214.

together in rows”).³³ However, I would rather suggest *sewn* style, a translation which echoes the metaphor of weaving that can be found in the expression κατεστραμμένη λέξις (*interwoven* style)³⁴ and thus perhaps better captures the contrast that Aristotle points out between the two styles.³⁵

Turning then to the *interwoven* λέξις, Aristotle states that this type of composition is formed of *periods*. He defines the period (περίοδος, litt. “way around”)³⁶ as a saying that has both “a beginning and an end in itself” and “a magnitude that is easily grasped” (or “easily taken at a glance”). Two different yet linked ideas are present in this definition. Let us begin with the issue of magnitude: this probably refers to the idea that the end of the period should be in sight from the beginning. Or, to borrow from Aristotle’s metaphor of a race, the goal is already in sight from the starting point, so that the runners—or, in the case of speeches, the speakers—show no sign of fatigue while running towards it.³⁷ Concretely, the “magnitude” has to do both with prosody and with the limited length of periods.³⁸ Aristotle indeed indicates, a few lines later, that periods should be “easy to breathe,”³⁹ that is, easy to utter without taking a breath, which obviously limits their length. He also explicitly states that periods should not be too

³³ In Homer, εἶρω is used to refer to necklaces of gold that are strung with amber beads (e.g., *Od.* 15,460; and *ibid.*, 18,296).

³⁴ The verb καταστρέφω has a rich semantic field. In the active form, it can mean “turn down,” “trample on,” “overturn,” but also “turn back,” “return (intr.),” or “direct,” esp. towards an end, hence “finish” or “bring to an end” (LSJ); however, as noticed by P. Chiron, it takes on a substantially different meaning in the passive voice: “be subdued,” “be forced,” “be constrained,” hence “be closely woven” (“La période chez Aristote,” III, n. 2; *Id.*, *Un rhéteur méconnu*, 72). This is the metaphor of weaving, attested e.g. in the *De Audibilibus* (*Audib.*, 803 a 28) attributed to Aristotle (but most probably the work of Strato of Lampsacus; on the question of authorship, see A. Barker, “The Peripatetic *De Audibilis*,” 98–99). Cf. also Dionysius of Halicarnassus’ comparison of polite harmonia with “finely woven cloths” (εὐήτριτοι ὕφη) in *Comp.* 23,3 (cf. also *Comp.* 23,5, where Dionysius specifies that polite harmonia is entirely formed of periods). It is this metaphor that I retain in my translation: this indeed describes well the typical arrangement of cōla that is found in periodic style, i.e., a construction where cōla are closely woven; I am indebted here to P. Chiron, who uses the French term “tressé” (“La période chez Aristote,” 107–108). Other possible translations include “rounded style” (e.g., Fowler, “Aristotle on the Period,” 90), “turned down style” (e.g., G. A. Kennedy, *On Rhetoric*, 214–215), “structured style” (Waterfield, *Art of Rhetoric*, 133), and “bounded style” (Freese and Striker, *Art of Rhetoric*, 386–389, but simply “periodic style” in the original translation by Freese).

³⁵ I follow here P. Chiron’s suggestion regarding the translation of εἰρομένη—he proposes the French “cousu” (“La période chez Aristote,” III–III, esp. n. 2), even though the usage of the verb εἶρω in the precise sense of “sew” is not attested. Another convincing way to render this contrast would be to translate εἰρομένη with “continuous” and κατεστραμμένη with “bounded,” as Striker does in her revision of Freese’s translation (*Art of Rhetoric*, 386–389).

³⁶ See below, n. 183.

³⁷ *Rhet.* III,9,2; cf. 9,6, where a second use of this metaphor is possibly found (see in this sense H. Harris, “A Simile in Aristotle’s *Rhetoric* (III.9.6),” 178–179).

³⁸ In this sense, see also Schenkeveld, *Studies in Demetrius’ On Style*, 30.

³⁹ *Rhet.* III,9,5.

long because this would “cause [the hearer] to be left behind.”⁴⁰ In his view, the longest periods are made up of two “côla,” each of which should not exceed the length of a full hexametre (i.e., 16–17 syllables); concretely, then, the longest periods are still relatively short sayings of 30–35 syllables.⁴¹ As to the remark that periods have a beginning and an end “in themselves,” this means that the period has limits that stem from the form itself, not from external elements. D. A. Russell and M. Winterbottom suggest a translation that expresses this idea more clearly: “a beginning and end *determined by its own structure*.”⁴² The numerous examples Aristotle provides right after his definition show the various ways in which the beginning and the end of periods can be signalled. This has to do with the content (semantics), with the choice of words, and with the syntactic construction, as I shall discuss below (section 2.2).

Aristotle strongly recommends that we should favour the *interwoven style*, because what is composed in periods is, in his words, both “pleasant and easy to learn.”⁴³ The pleasant aspect of periodic compositions, he explains, is due precisely to the presence of clear limits—which contrasts with the “endless” aspect of the non-periodic style. And if periodic compositions are *easy to learn*, this is merely because they possess number (ἀριθμόν). In this context, it is unclear whether “number” refers strictly to the presence of metrical feet—as is arguably the case in chapter 8, which concerns the use of metrical feet in prose⁴⁴—or should be understood more broadly to also include the various effects of symmetry imparted by the so-called “Gorgianic figures” (see below, section 2.2.3).⁴⁵ In view of the different examples of periods provided in chapter 9, a broad meaning seems more likely.

⁴⁰ *Rhet.* III,9,6.

⁴¹ Such indications in terms of the number of syllables are not found in Aristotle. These are uniquely based on the observation of the examples provided in *Rhet.* III,9.

⁴² D. A. Russell and M. Winterbottom, *Ancient Literary Criticism*, 148 (my emphasis).

⁴³ *Rhet.* III,9,3: ἡδεῖα δ’ ἢ τοιαύτη καὶ εὐμαθής.

⁴⁴ *Rhet.* III,8.

⁴⁵ Cf. Cicero, *Or. Brut.* 219–220, who explicitly states that the rhythmical aspect of prose relies not only by the presence of metrical feet, but also *concinntitas*, i.e., symmetry, typically that which is created by the use of antithesis, côla of equal length, or sound echoes

2.2. Characteristics of periods⁴⁶

2.2.1. Periods as complete thoughts

Of clear relevance to the issue of clear delimitations is that of the semantic nature of periods. A few lines after defining the period, Aristotle specifies that “the period must also be complete in thought [δεῖ δὲ τὴν περίοδον καὶ τῇ διανοίᾳ τετελειώσθαι].”⁴⁷ This comment should not be misread as revealing a correspondence between the concept of the period and the modern concept of the sentence. To begin with, Aristotle accepts a very limited length for periods, namely, a maximum of two *côla*. As a result, many complex “sentences” that are found in classical literature, including e.g. those by Demosthenes or Isocrates, are just far too long to meet his requirements.⁴⁸ Furthermore, nothing in Aristotle’s discussion indicates that syntactic dependency between subsequent segments of speech would automatically imply that these segments together form a period.⁴⁹ Rather, it appears that the periodic character of a saying is strongly linked with the stylistic features this saying exhibits, especially with the so-called “Gorgianic figures” and the presence of rhythmical patterns at the extremities (see below, sections 2.2.3 and 2.2.5).

2.2.2. Division of periods into *côla*

Aristotle introduces the notion of *côlon* in his discussion of the internal structure of periods:

A period may be either composed of *côla* [ἐν κώλοις], or simple [ἀφελής]. That in *côla* is a complete saying [τετελειωμένη λέξις], distinct in its parts [διηρημένη], and easy to repeat in a breath [εὐανάπνευστος], not according to the division,⁵⁰ but taken as a whole. The *côlon*

⁴⁶ Aristotle’s doctrine on the period has been abundantly studied, with scholars offering widely different interpretations: see notably J. Zehetmeier, “Die Periodenlehre des Aristoteles”; G. A. Kennedy, “Aristotle on the Period”; R. L. Fowler, “Aristotle on the Period (*Rhet.* 3.9)”; T. Adamik, “Aristotle’s Theory of the Period”; Chiron, “La période chez Aristote”; cf. also G. Kaibel, *Stil und Text der Πολιτεία Ἀθηναίων des Aristoteles*, vol. 1, esp. 64ff; W. Schmid, *Über die Klassische Theorie und Praxis des antiken Prosarhythmus*, 112–130; D. M. Schenkeveld, *Studies in Demetrius On Style*, 28–31; A. Primmer, *Cicero Numerosus*, 45–49.

⁴⁷ *Rhet.* III,9,4. Cf. also *ibid.*, 9,5.

⁴⁸ As G. A. Kennedy notes (*On Rhetoric*, 214), “Aristotle quotes parts of Isocrates’ complex sentences as examples of periods, but does not analyse the sentences as a whole. Apparently he viewed a long Isocratean sentence as made up of several periods.”

⁴⁹ See also Chiron, “La période chez Aristote.” Commenting on the examples of periods given in *Rhet.* III,9, Chiron remarks that these “ne correspondent presque jamais à ce que nous appellerions *phrase*” and concludes that “ces exemples nous conduisent à penser que la période [chez Aristote] est inanalysable grammaticalement” (here pages 122–123).

⁵⁰ Following “not according to the division,” some manuscripts read ὥσπερ καὶ ἡ περίοδος (“as the period”) or ὥσπερ καὶ ἡ εἰρημένη περίοδος (“as the sewn period” or “as the continuous period”). On this textual difficulty, and for a convincing argument in favour of omitting this comparison, see P. Chiron, “La période chez Aristote,” 117–119; cf. Id., *Un rhéteur méconnu*, 64–66.

is one of the two parts of this period. By a simple period, I mean one that consists of only one cōlon.⁵¹

Etymologically, the term κῶλον designates a “limb” (especially the legs), and by extension a “member” or “a distinct part of a whole.” In his *Rhetoric*, Aristotle applies this term to the period’s parts. Specifically, he distinguishes between two different kinds of periods, according to whether the period comprises only one cōlon (“simple periods”)⁵² or two cōla (“composed periods”).⁵³ He then focuses on the composed period by detailing three of its properties. First, Aristotle states that it is a complete saying (τετελειωμένη λέξις), a remark that possibly echoes with his previous statement that periods must be “complete in thought”⁵⁴ (though it is unclear here which kind of completeness is at stake). Second, the composed period is “distinct in its parts,” meaning that there is a clear boundary between its two cōla. Third, this kind of period should be “easy to utter in a breath” or, literally, “easy to breathe” (εὐανάπνευστος): this arguably alludes to the idea that it should be possible to utter the period without taking a breath in the middle.⁵⁵

Regarding cōla, Aristotle does not define these in and of themselves, but only in relation to the period.⁵⁶ A cōlon is one of the two parts of a composed period, or, in the case of the monocōlon period, it is equivalent to the period in its entirety. Thus, in terms of semantics, a cōlon corresponds either to one part of a complete thought, or to a complete thought. What about the semantic and syntactic characteristics of those cōla that are only “part of a thought”? Even if Aristotle’s remarks are extremely brief on this issue (the composed period is simply said to be “distinct in its parts”), one has only to look at the numerous examples provided to notice that the division between the two cōla is placed in ways that respect both semantics and syntax. Concretely, each cōlon has a relative semantico-syntactic independence, generally corresponding to a clause or a phrase.

⁵¹ *Rhet.* III,9,5.

⁵² On the simple period, for which Aristotle does not provide any examples, see a short discussion in Primmer, “Schlichter Stil und eingliedrige Periode in Aristoteles’ Rhetorik III 9.”

⁵³ P. Chiron argues that the Aristotelean limit of two cōla might be due to the close link he asserts between the concept of period and the concept of enthymeme (Chiron, “La période chez Aristote,” 127–129).

⁵⁴ *Rhet.* III,9,4.

⁵⁵ The final part of the comment “not according to the division, but taken as a whole” makes clear that the property of being easy to breathe refers to the entire period, and not to each of its two cōla. See P. Chiron, “La période chez Aristote,” 117–119.

⁵⁶ This also contrasts with what is found in many later treatises, where the cōlon is described in itself and not solely in connection to the period. See e.g. Dem., *Eloc.* 2–3; *Rhet. Her.* IV,19,27; Quint., *Inst.* IX,9,123; Ael. Arist., *Pol.* 169 (ed. Patillon).

2.2.3. Gorgianic figures

Composed periods can take on two different forms, depending on whether their *côla* are *divided* or *opposed*.⁵⁷ The opening of Isocrates' *Panegyricus* is provided as an example of a divided period: "Often have I admired those gathering together for panegyric festivals / and those instituting athletic contests" (πολλάκις ἐθαύμασα τῶν τὰς πανηγύρεις συναγόντων / καὶ τοὺς γυμνικοὺς ἀγῶνας καταστησάντων).⁵⁸ These two *côla* are complementary, the second one still being part of the object introduced by τῶν in the first *côlon*. *Côla* are said to be *opposed* when "in each of the two *côla*, one contrary is brought close to another, or the same word is coupled with both contraries."⁵⁹ For instance: "it often happens in these circumstances that the wise fail / and the foolish succeed"⁶⁰; "some of them perished miserably / others saved themselves disgracefully"⁶¹; or "though they are citizens by nature / they were deprived of the rights of citizenship by law."⁶² As Aristotle makes clear, *antithesis* should be understood in a broad sense: there are also false antitheses, i.e., when *côla* seem to be opposed due to the formulation, but in fact have the same meaning. Hence, the following period is still considered an antithesis, even if its two *côla* in fact express the same idea: "at one time I was in their house / at another I was with them."⁶³

Periods also typically exhibit two other figures of speech, both of which are based on the similarities between the *côla*. The first is *pariosis* (παρίσωσις), which is when the two *côla* have the same length. The second is *paromoiosis* (παρομοίωσις), which is when there are similarities in sounds. Such sound echoes can take place either at the beginning or the end of *côla*. As an example of *côla* with echoes at the beginning, Aristotle quotes an extract of the *Iliad*: δωρητοί τ' ἐπέλοντο / παράρρητοί τ' ἐπέεσσιν ("ready for gifts they were/ and [ready] for persuasion by words").⁶⁴ We should note that in this case the similarity does not begin with the first syllable: it only occurs in the two last syllables of the first words (δωρητοί and παράρρητοί). For an example of final

⁵⁷ τῆς δὲ ἐν κώλοις λέξεως ἡ μὲν διηρημένη ἐστὶν ἡ δὲ ἀντικειμένη (*Rhet.* III,9,7).

⁵⁸ *Rhet.* III,9,7 (= Isocrates, *Paneg.* 1).

⁵⁹ *Rhet.* III,9,7.

⁶⁰ συμβαίνει πολλάκις ἐν ταύταις καὶ τοὺς φρονίμους ἀτυχεῖν / καὶ τοὺς ἄφρονας κατορθοῦν (*Rhet.* III,9,7 = Isocrates, *Paneg.* 48)

⁶¹ οἱ μὲν γὰρ αὐτῶν κακῶς ἀπώλοντο / οἱ δ' αἰσχροῦς ἐσώθησαν (*Rhet.* III,9,7 = Isocrates, *Paneg.* 149).

⁶² Isocrates, *Paneg.* 105: καὶ φύσει πολίτας ὄντας / νόμῳ τῆς πόλεως στέρεσθαι (quoted in *Rhet.* III,9,7).

⁶³ τόκα μὲν ἐν τήνων ἐγῶν ἦν / τόκα δὲ παρὰ τήνοισ ἐγῶν. This is a verse of Epicharmus, quoted in *Rhet.* III,9,10.

⁶⁴ Hom., *Iliad* IX,526; quoted by Aristotle in *Rhet.* III,9,7.

paromoiosis,⁶⁵ we can mention, among others: τί ἂν ἔπαθες δεινόν / εἰ ἄνδρ' εἶδες ἀργόν (“what ill would you have suffered / if you had seen an idle man?”).⁶⁶ In this case, the similarity concerns the last syllable of each cōlon. Aristotle specifies that these three figures are sometimes present together in the same period.⁶⁷

It is clear that these three “Gorgianic figures” (antithesis, pariosis, paromoiosis)⁶⁸ are not only an ornament designed to please the ears of the hearers, but that these also act as structuring devices: specifically, they give dicōloi periods a sense of stylistic unity, they underline their openings and endings, and they mark the internal division into their two cōla. In view of the fact that these figures appear in all the examples of periods that Aristotle provides in chapter 9, we may even think that these figures constitute a necessary characteristic of dicōloi periods.⁶⁹

2.2.4. *Verb at the end*

For periodic style, the placement of the verb at the very end of cōla seems also to be encouraged. Aristotle does not state this explicitly, but this phenomenon is sufficiently common in the examples he gives in chapter 9 of his *Rhetoric* for us to speak of a strong tendency. To cite only one more example, in addition to those previously quoted (see section 2.2.3 above): εὐθύς μὲν τῶν ἀριστείων ἤξιώθησαν / οὐ πολὺ δὲ ὕστερον τὴν ἀρχὴν τῆς θαλάττης ἔλαβον (“at once worthy of the prize of valour *they were deemed* / and not much later the command of the sea *they won*”).⁷⁰ Such a placement of the verb comprises an efficient way of signalling the internal division between the two cōla, while also helping to make the end of periods easy to identify.

⁶⁵ This special form of paromoiosis is called ὁμοιοτέλευτον (*Rhet.* III,9,9).

⁶⁶ *Rhet.* III,9,9.

⁶⁷ *Rhet.* III,9,9.

⁶⁸ These three figures are commonly treated as a group by rhetoricians. They are often qualified “Gorgianic” in reference to the sophist philosopher and rhetorician Gorgias (5th–4th centuries BCE). In the case of Aristotle, however, the term “Gorgianic figures” is anachronistic: according to M. P. Noël, it might have been coined by Dionysius of Halicarnassus, who saw in Gorgias the paradigm of the excessive use of these figures (Noël, “Gorgias et l’“invention” des γοργίεια σχήματα”). However, the link between Gorgias and this set of figures is older. For instance, it can be observed in Demetrius, *Eloc.* 15 and 22–29, and in Cicero, *Or. Brut.* 165.

⁶⁹ See in this sense A. Primmer (*Cicero Numerosus*, 45–49), who argues that sound-figures constitute the core of the definition of the composed period.

⁷⁰ Isocrates, *Paneg.* 72; quoted by Aristotle in *Rhet.* III,9,7.

2.2.5. *Rhythm*

Rhythmical patterns are another device that helps frame periods.⁷¹ In the previous chapter (chapter 8), Aristotle discusses which feet are appropriate in prose. He insists that “prose should have rhythm but no metre [ῥυθμὸν δεῖ ἔχειν τὸν λόγον, μέτρον δὲ μὴ]; otherwise it would be a poem. The rhythm should not be exact: this will be achieved if it is regular only up to a certain point.”⁷² Aristotle especially recommends the paeon, as, in his view, “it is the only one of the rhythms that is not metrical, so that it is most likely to be undetected.”⁷³ He explains that the heroic rhythm (i.e., the dactylic hexametre) would be too dignified for prose, while the iambic is considered too commonplace, owing to the fact that it is used in everyday speech.⁷⁴ Paeons should be found both in openings and endings: the first paeon is found in openings and begins with one long syllable and ends with three short (– u u u), while the fourth paeon is found in endings and begins with three short syllables and ends with one long one (u u u –).⁷⁵

⁷¹ The exact role of rhythm in Aristotle’s conception of the period is a complex and much debated issue. There is a debate between scholars who understand the Aristotelean period to be a logical unit, and those scholars who think that the essential feature of the period is that its beginning and its end are marked by specific rhythmical patterns. In favour of the logical definition, see G. Kaibel, *Stil und Text der Πολιτεία Αθηναίων des Aristoteles*, 64ff; A. W. de Groot, *Der Antike Prosarhythmus*; L. P. Wilkinson, *Golden Latin Artistry*, 167ff; Fowler, “Aristotle on the Period.” For a rhythmical definition, see, among others, J. Zehetmeier, “Die Periodenlehre des Aristoteles,” 192–208; W. Schmid, *Über die klassische Theorie und Praxis des antiken Prosarhythmus*, 112–130; T. Adamik, “Aristotle’s Theory of the Period”; cf. also D. M. Schenkeveld, *Studies in Demetrius on Style*, 28–29. The definition in terms of rhythm was more common at least up until the 1980s, when R. L. Fowler made strong objections against it and argued rather for a logical definition. Fowler understands the period to be “a syntactic structure with an inner cohesion produced by the logical, pre-planned arrangement of its parts according to the requirements of the whole” (“Aristotle on the Period,” 89). It seems to me that the Aristotelean period is simultaneously a logical unit *and* a rhythmical unit, with the two aspects being necessary characteristics; however, I would define rhythm in a much broader sense than the presence of metrical feet at the extremities of the period, namely, as comprising also the sense of rhythm brought by the use of Gorgianic figures (see above, section 2.2.3; cf. also footnote 69). See also the discussion in P. Chiron, “La période chez Aristote,” 123–125.

⁷² *Rhet.* III,8,3.

⁷³ *Rhet.* III,8,5. As G. A. Kennedy notes (*On Rhetoric*, 213), this statement is somewhat surprising, given that the examples of paeons Aristotle quotes in *Rhet.* III,8,6 are taken from poetry, and that paeons are not especially common in prose.

⁷⁴ *Rhet.* III,8,4. This is at least Aristotle’s opinion. However, K. J. Dover has observed that the rhythms rejected by Aristotle are nevertheless well present in eminent prose writers (*The Evolution of Greek Prose*, 160–186).

⁷⁵ Aristotle does not make completely clear in this context which openings and endings he is speaking about: is he referring solely to the extremities of periods or also to the extremities of cōla? This point is also unclear in *Rhet.* III,8,6, where Aristotle stresses the importance of having a long syllable at the end: “For the short syllable, owing to its endless aspect, mutilates the cadence. On the contrary, the end should be brought to a close and made manifest by a long syllable [ἀλλὰ δεῖ τῇ μακρᾷ ἀποκόπτεσθαι καὶ δῆλην εἶναι τὴν τελευτήν]: not by the scribe or by a graphical mark [μὴ διὰ τὸν γραφέα, μηδὲ διὰ τὴν παραγραφὴν], but rather by the rhythm itself.” Although some translations supply the term “period” in *Rhet.* III,8,6 (so J.H. Freese’ original translation [1926], *Art of Rhetoric*, 387: “the period should be broken off

It is somewhat surprising to observe, then, that the examples of periods Aristotle gives in chapter 9 do not systematically exhibit paeons at their extremities, and rarely exhibit perfect paeons. We can, nevertheless, notice a tendency for *côla* and periods to begin and finish with long syllables, a feature that might be interpreted as the presence of “imperfect paeons.” Perhaps the core idea is simply that long syllables should be placed at the extremities, as Demetrius suggests when he comments on the Aristotelean doctrine of the paeon?⁷⁶ But, if this is so, why does Aristotle insist on the paeon without also mentioning the cretic (long-short-long), which has the same proportion as the paeon and is more common in prose?⁷⁷ In any case, it is clear that the Aristotelean doctrine on rhythm should not be regarded as a strict rule. We may even think that the Gorgianic figures also help to make prose rhythmical through the various effects of symmetry they create.⁷⁸

2.2.6. Length of *côla*

Concerning the length of *côla*, Aristotle does not stipulate any precise limits. He only indicates that *côla* must be neither too short nor too long.⁷⁹ If they are too short, he explains, the *côla* bring the listeners up short because of the sudden stop; but if they are too long, they leave the listeners behind. Concretely, the examples found throughout chapter 9 exhibit *côla* that range from 5 to 17 syllables,⁸⁰ with most of them having between 10 and 15 syllables. It is probably no coincidence that the maximum length found in the examples coincides with the maximum length of a hexametre verse.⁸¹

2.3. Results

In the third book of his *Rhetoric*, Aristotle discusses how prose should be structured at the micro-level. He distinguishes between two different methods of composition, or two

by a long syllable”), there is nothing in Aristotle’s wording to indicate that he is referring solely to the end of periods. Cf. Demetrius, who takes up the Aristotelean doctrine concerning rhythm in prose but makes clear that paeons should also occur within periods, at the extremities of *côla* (*Eloc.* 39 and *ibid.*, 41)

⁷⁶ Dem., *Eloc.* 41.

⁷⁷ See this remark in G. A. Kennedy, *On Rhetoric*, 213–214. Cf. also footnote 73 above.

⁷⁸ In this sense, see A. Primmer, *Cicero Numerosus*, 45–49.

⁷⁹ *Rhet.* III,9,6.

⁸⁰ There are many instances of 17-syllables *côla*, among which *πολλάκις ἐθαύμασα τῶν τὰς πανηγύρεις συναγόντων* (Isoc., *Paneg.* 1), and *οὐ πολὺ δὲ ὕστερον τὴν ἀρχὴν τῆς θαλάττης ἔλαβον* (Isoc., *Paneg.* 72). For a 5-syllables *côlon*, see the first *côlon* of this period: *ἢ ζῶντας ἔξειν / ἢ τελευτήσαντας καταλείψειν* (Isocr., *Paneg.* 186). These examples are all quoted in *Rhet.* III,9,7.

⁸¹ Later rhetoricians clearly draw a parallel between the hexametre in poetry and the *côlon* in prose. See e.g. Dem., *Eloc.* 1; *ibid.*, 4; Cic., *Or. Brut.* 222.

“kinds of style,” depending on whether the segments of speech are *sewn* or *interwoven*. In the sewn style (εἰρομένη λέξις), which is described as the ancient style, speech is “unlimited” or “endless” (ἄπειρον): that is, the sayings do not possess an end in themselves, but rather seem to have been “sewn together” with connecting particles. Aristotle considers such a style to be unpleasant, due to its lack of clear limits, and therefore suggests it should be avoided. In contrast, in the interwoven style (κατεστραμμένη λέξις) that Aristotle favours and so discusses in greater detail, the sayings are “interwoven” to form periods, a period being defined as a saying that “has a beginning and end in itself and a magnitude that is easily grasped.”⁸² As we have seen, the reference to the “easily grasped magnitude” has to do with both the limited length of periods and with prosody. Indeed, Aristotle indicates that periods should not be made too long: they should rather comprise either one cōlon (simple periods) or two cōla (composed periods), with neither cōlon exceeding the length of a full hexametre, meaning that the upper limit for periods is situated around 30–35 syllables. Aristotle also specifies that the period should be “easy to breathe”: the idea here is probably that periods correspond to prosodic units meant to be uttered without taking a breath, even when they are divided into two cōla.⁸³ As concerns the notion of clear delimitations that is alluded to in the first part of the definition (“the period has a beginning and end in itself”), this idea is certainly related to the semantic content of periods—Aristotle says elsewhere that the period should be “complete in thought”⁸⁴—but also with the use of figures and the presence of rhythmical patterns at the extremities. Specifically, dicōloi periods often (or even always? This point remains unclear) exhibit one or more of the so-called Gorgianic figures: *antithesis* (to be understood in a broad sense), *pariosis* (i.e., equality of length between the cōla), and *paromoiosis* (i.e., sound echoes at the extremities of cōla). Beyond their obvious ornamental aspect, these three figures play a crucial role in structuring periods, in that they mark both their extremities and their internal division. Another phenomenon often found in the examples is the placement of the main verb at the end of cōla. Finally, we have seen that Aristotle insists that the extremities of periods, and perhaps also the extremities of cōla,⁸⁵ are typically outlined by the presence of a paeon or a rhythmical pattern that resembles a paeon.

⁸² *Rhet.* III,9,3.

⁸³ *Rhet.* III,9,5.

⁸⁴ *Rhet.* III,9,4; cf. 9,5.

⁸⁵ See above, footnote 75.

3. Pseudo-Demetrius of Phalerum, *On Style* (*Περὶ ἐρμηνείας* / *De Elocutione* [*Eloc.*])
– late 2nd or early 1st century BCE (?)⁸⁶

The treatise *Περὶ ἐρμηνείας* (*On Style*), arguably dated to the late 2nd century or early 1st century BCE,⁸⁷ is entirely devoted to the art of *elocutio*. The traditional attribution to Demetrius of Phalerum (ca. 360–ca 280 BCE)⁸⁸—a student of Theophrastus, who was himself a student of Aristotle—is generally rejected by modern scholars. Most now believe that the treatise is the work of a later writer, commonly referred to as “Pseudo-Demetrius” or sometimes simply “Demetrius.” Because it is plausible that the author was really named Demetrius, I will use this name in the discussion below.⁸⁹ *On Style* is a major work for anyone interested in the history of the stylistic tradition. Numerous aspects of the Demetrian thought were adopted by later rhetoricians, whether Greek or Latin.⁹⁰ Moreover, this treatise offers what is probably the clearest and most comprehensive account of *côla*, *commata* and periods found in the ancient sources.

Demetrius offers his definitions of the *côlon*, the comma and the period at the beginning of his treatise (§ 1–35), where they are already associated with some general recommendations regarding compositional style. In the remainder of the treatise (§ 36–304), Demetrius presents four “types of style” (*χαρακτῆρες λέξεως*): “elevated style,” “elegant style,” “plain style,” and “forcible style.”⁹¹ For each of these Demetrius offers multiple recommendations concerning word choice, as well as the characteristics of

⁸⁶ *Du style* (ed. and trans. P. Chiron; Les Belles Lettres; 2002). The translations below are mine, based on the Greek text established by Chiron; at some places, they are influenced by Roberts-Innes’ English translation, *Aristotle: Poetics, Longinus: On the Sublime, Demetrius: On Style* (LCL; ed. and trans. D. C. Innes, based on the translation by W. R. Roberts). For a good introduction to the treatise, see Chiron, “Introduction” (*Démétrios: Du style*), VII–CXXXVIII; see also Chiron’s major study of the Demetrian stylistic theory, *Un rhéteur méconnu: Démétrios (PS.-Démétrios de Phalère). Essai sur les mutations de la théorie du style à l’époque hellénistique*.

⁸⁷ There is no definitive consensus about the date of the treatise: the proposed dates span from the 3rd century BCE to the 2nd century CE. However, many arguments can be advanced in support of a date in the middle of this range (late 2nd century–early 1st century BCE): see P. Chiron, “Introduction” (*Démétrios: Du style*), XIII–XL; Id., *Un rhéteur méconnu*, 362–370; cf. D. C. Innes, “Introduction” (*Demetrius: On Style*), 310–319; cf. also a synthesis of these arguments in C. C de Jonge’s review of N. Marini, *Demetrio: Lo stile*.

⁸⁸ The reference to Demetrius of Phalerum is found in the superscription of the Parisinus Graece 1741 (= P, 10th century). In the subscription of the same manuscript, however, the text is simply attributed to a certain “Demetrius” (Δημητρίου περὶ ἐρμηνείας). Earlier references also ascribed the treatise to “Demetrius,” without specifying which Demetrius this is; on this issue, see P. Chiron, “Introduction” (*Démétrios: Du style*), XV–XVIII.

⁸⁹ P. Chiron, “Introduction” (*Démétrios: Du style*), XVI.

⁹⁰ On the strong influence of Demetrius’ stylistic theory on his successors, see P. Chiron, *Un rhéteur méconnu*, 109–115.

⁹¹ This typology departs from the classical division of style into three “levels” (plain, middle, and grand; see the first attestation of this doctrine in *Rhet. Her.* IV,8,11–11,16). On the Demetrian doctrine, see P. Chiron, *Un rhéteur méconnu*, 117–172; cf. D. M. Schenkeveld, *Studies in Demetrius’ On Style*, 51–87.

côla and periods (length, figures, etc.) and the different mistakes and excesses to be avoided. In order to illustrate these recommendations, he also provides numerous extracts from classical literature; these examples often come with comments that sometimes include a precise delineation of côla and periods.

3.1. *Côla and commata*

3.1.1. *Structuring role in prose*

The côlon is introduced from the first line of the treatise. Such a position testifies to the importance of the notion of the côlon for Demetrius' general theory of *elocutio*. Indeed, in his view côla are the primary building blocks of prose texts. Their structuring role is comparable to that of metres in poetry:

Just as poetry is organised by metres (such as trimetres,⁹² hexametres, and others), so too is prose expression organised and divided by what are called *côla*. These *côla* give a sort of rest [ἀναπαύοντα] to both the speaker and what is actually being said; and they mark out the boundaries of the discourse at frequent points, since it would otherwise continue at length without any limits and make the speaker run out of breath.⁹³

Côla mark the points of articulation in prose. In other words, they mark the places where breaks are needed. Such a system of structuration, Demetrius explains, serves two practical goals: to give a kind of rest to both the speaker and to the discourse itself. These two goals are directly related to the constraints of oral delivery: the first goal relates to the speaker's need for enough room to rest and, if needed, to take a breath (it would otherwise "make the speaker run out of breath"); the second goal arguably relates to the cognitive process of the listeners, i.e., the audience's need for adequate time to understand what has just been said.

3.1.2. *Length*

Demetrius indicates that, in principle, côla should be neither too long nor too short. The discussion runs as follows:

Côla should not be made very long; otherwise the composition lacks measure [ἄμετρος] and is hard to follow. Even poetry rarely goes beyond the length of the hexametre. It would

⁹² The manuscripts have ἡμιμέτροις, which is a hapax in the context of rhetoric (i.e., with the meaning "half-line"; see P. Chiron, *Démétrios, Du Style*, 85, n. 1). An alternative reading, which I decided to follow in my translation, is "trimetre." This solution was already suggested in the 19th-century critical edition by L. Spengel (*Rhetores Graeci* III, p. 12). It is notably followed by D. C. Innes ("Period and Côlon," 41, n. 23) and P. Chiron (review of N. Marini, *Lo Stile*, 381–382). As Chiron argues, the reading ἡμιμέτροις may well be the result of confusion in an earlier majuscule manuscript.

⁹³ *Eloc.* 1.

indeed be ludicrous if metre [μέτρον] had no measure [ἄμετρον],⁹⁴ so that by the time the line comes to an end we should have forgotten when it began! But if long cōla are out of place in discourse because they lack measure, so also are brief cōla, because they produce the so-called “arid” composition, exemplified in the words “life is short / art long / opportunity fleeting” [ὁ βίος βραχύς / ἡ τέχνη μακρά / ὁ καιρὸς ὀξύς]. The composition here seems to be minced, shredded and negligible because everything about it is so tiny.⁹⁵

Long cōla are to be avoided in principle because they “lack measure” and thus carry the risk that the beginning has already been forgotten when the end comes—here again, this remark refers to the cognitive process by the listeners. Brief cōla should also be avoided, because they produce, in our author’s terms, an “arid” composition. With respect to the normal length, Demetrius makes a comparison with verses in poetry, which rarely go beyond the length of the hexametre, that is, a maximum of 17 syllables. In the numerous examples provided throughout the treatise, however, we can observe a great variety in terms of length: cōla range from 3 (or 4?)⁹⁶ to 31 syllables!⁹⁷ Nevertheless, we can note that most cōla are between 10 and 20 syllables. Moreover, Demetrius tends to comment on their brief or long aspect when they fall outside of these boundaries.⁹⁸ We can therefore conclude that the standard length for cōla, in the author’s mind, is between approximately 10 and 20 syllables, which indeed corresponds more or less to the length of a hexametre.

After these general recommendations, Demetrius explains that long or brief cōla are nonetheless suitable in specific cases.⁹⁹ In particular, long cōla are appropriate for “great subjects”; for example: “at times God himself guides this universe and helps to roll it in its course” (τὸ γὰρ δὴ πᾶν τόδε τὸ μὲν αὐτὸς ὁ θεὸς πορευόμενον ποδηγεῖ καὶ συγκυκλεῖ).¹⁰⁰ Here, Demetrius comments that the elevation of the language corresponds to the length of the cōlon (25 syllables).¹⁰¹

⁹⁴ γελοῖον γὰρ τὸ μέτρον ἄμετρον εἶναι. Here there is a wordplay on the two meanings of μέτρος: “verse” (in poetry) and “true measure.”

⁹⁵ *Eloc.* 4. The example is taken from Hippocrates, *Aphorisms* I,1. Cf. Quint., *Inst.* IX,4,126 (“A membrum that is too long is slow [*tardum*]; one that is too short is unstable [*instabile*].”)

⁹⁶ An instance of a 3-syllables cōlon (καλὸς δέ) is possibly found in *Eloc.* 8 (see below, n. 104). Cōla of 4 (ἔπου θεῶ) and 5 syllables (γνώθι σεαυτόν) respectively are found in *Eloc.* 9; see also *Eloc.* 4, where there are three instances of 5-syllables cōla.

⁹⁷ For a 31-syllables cōlon, see *Eloc.* 45 (ὁ γὰρ Ἀχελῷος ποταμὸς ῥέων ἐκ Πίνδου ὄρους διὰ Δολοπίας καὶ Ἀγριανῶν καὶ Ἀμφιλόχων = Thuc., *Pelop.* II,102,2). Also see a 28-syllables cōlon in *Eloc.* 44 (Θουκυδίδης Ἀθηναῖος ξυνέγραψε τὸν πόλεμον τῶν Πελοποννησίων καὶ Ἀθηναίων).

⁹⁸ See e.g. *Eloc.* 17; cf. §44.

⁹⁹ *Eloc.* 5–9.

¹⁰⁰ Plato, *Politics*, 269c; quoted by Demetrius in *Eloc.* 5.

¹⁰¹ In the remainder of this reply by the “Stranger” (Plato, *Politics*, 269c) the cōla are also especially long.

He also specifies the circumstances in which a short cōlon is appropriate, mentioning three different cases: first, when the subject addressed is something “small”; second, when infusing the speech with vehemence; third, when expressing maxims. As an illustration of the first case, he quotes a passage from Xenophon, who describes the river Teleobas in the following terms: “it was not large / beautiful it was, though” (οὗτος δὲ ἦν μέγας μὲν οὐ / καλὸς δέ).¹⁰² In this saying, Demetrius comments, “the short, broken rhythm brings into relief both the smallness and the beauty of the river.”¹⁰³ Assuming that my understanding is correct, this saying comprises two cōla of 8 and 3 syllables respectively.¹⁰⁴ Then, concerning vigorous passages, Demetrius explains that “there is greater vigour and intensity when much meaning is conveyed in a few words,”¹⁰⁵ and a few lines later he compares the use of short cōla with “a wild beast [who] gathers itself together for an attack.”¹⁰⁶ As an illustration, he proposes Λακεδαιμόνιοι Φιλίππῳ / Διονύσιος ἐν Κορίνθῳ (“The Lacedemonians to Phillip / Dionysius at Corinth”), which has a much more forceful impact than if the formulation was longer, e.g., “Although once a mighty tyrant like yourself / Dionysius now lives in Corinth as an ordinary citizen.”¹⁰⁷ Finally, Demetrius states that brevity also suits apophthegms and maxims, as “it is a mark of superior skill to compress much thought in a small space, just as seeds potentially contain entire trees.”¹⁰⁸ Two examples are provided: γνῶθι σεαυτὸν (“Know yourself”); and ἔπου θεῶ (“Follow God”).¹⁰⁹

Following these examples, Demetrius indicates that such short cōla are called *commata* (κόμματα), literally “cut-off pieces.”¹¹⁰ He defines the comma simply as “that which is less than a cōlon.”¹¹¹ In light of the examples provided in this context, the limit between the cōlon and the comma appears to be situated around 7–8 syllables. It is worth noting, however, that short cōla are not systematically qualified as *commata*, as is the case in the above example ὁ βίος βραχύς / ἡ τέχνη μακρά / ὁ καιρὸς ὄξύς, where

¹⁰² *Eloc.* 6; Demetrius refers to Xen., *Anab.* IV,4,3 but modifies the text. The text of Xenophon, at least as it was transmitted through direct sources, stands as follows: οὗτος δ’ ἦν καλὸς μὲν, μέγας δ’ οὐ.

¹⁰³ *Eloc.* 6.

¹⁰⁴ The Greek text is ambiguous. See a similar division into two cōla in D. M. Schenkeveld, *Studies in Demetrius*, 24. Alternatively, this saying might be interpreted as one single cōlon of 11 syllables (see notably P. Chiron, *Un rhéteur méconnu*, 78).

¹⁰⁵ *Eloc.* 7

¹⁰⁶ *Eloc.* 8.

¹⁰⁷ *Eloc.* 8.

¹⁰⁸ *Eloc.* 9.

¹⁰⁹ *Eloc.* 9.

¹¹⁰ The term derives from the verb κόπτω, which means “smite” (e.g., smite pieces of money, or smite with a weapon), but also “slaughter” (an animal), and by extension “cut off,” “chop off” (LSJ).

¹¹¹ *Eloc.* 9.

units of 5 syllables are still called *côla*. This makes it clear that *commata* are not treated by Demetrius as a separate category, but simply as a subcategory of *côla*, which are distinctively short.

3.1.3. *Semantics and syntax*

Immediately after the comparison between prose and poetry, Demetrius turns to definitional elements that fall under the umbrella of semantics: “the proper function of such *côla* is to delineate [ἀπαρτίζειν] a thought [διάνοιαν].”¹¹² A *côlon* can therefore be described as a unit of thought. Of course, the question arises as to what exactly is meant here by “thought” (διάνοια). Demetrius provides a detailed explanation: two different situations are distinguished, depending on whether *côla* are semantically complete in themselves or consist of subparts of longer thoughts. In the first case:

... the *côlon* forms a complete thought in itself, as for example when Hecataeus opens his “History” with the words “Hecataeus of Miletus thus relates” [Ἐκαταῖος Μιλήσιος ὧδε μυθεῖται]. In this case a complete *côlon* coincides with a complete thought and both end together.¹¹³

A few paragraphs later in the treatise (§12), Demetrius makes it perfectly clear that such “complete *côla*” belong to the non-periodic style, as he takes up the opening of Hecataeus’ *Genealogies* to illustrate the “disjointed style.”¹¹⁴ This highlights a crucial difference between Demetrius and Aristotle: while the author of the *Rhetoric* defines the *côlon* with reference to the period (as either a subpart of the period or the period in its entirety),¹¹⁵ Demetrius also uses the term *côlon* to designate the segments of non-periodic compositions.

Then, in the second case:

... the *côlon* constitutes not a complete thought, but a part of it, yet a complete part. For just as the arm, which is a whole of a certain kind, has parts such as fingers and the forearm which themselves again are wholes, inasmuch as each of them has its proper limits, and itself is made up of parts; so also a complete thought, when it is extensive, may very well comprise within itself parts which themselves are integral. An example will be found at the beginning of the “Anabasis” of Xenophon:¹¹⁶ “Darius and Parysatis” up to “the younger Cyrus.” This is a fully complete thought. However, the two *côla* contained in it are parts of this thought; and each of these, within its own limits, conveys a thought which is complete.

¹¹² *Eloc.* 2.

¹¹³ *Eloc.* 2. The example is the opening of Hecataeus of Miletus’ *Genealogies*.

¹¹⁴ See *Eloc.* 12.

¹¹⁵ Arist., *Rhet.* III,9,5.

¹¹⁶ Xen., *Anab.* I.

Take the first words “Darius and Parysatis had sons” [Δαρείου καὶ Παρυσάτιδος γίνονται παῖδες]. The thought that sons were born to Darius and Parysatis has its own completeness. The second cōlon, in the same way, conveys the complete thought that “the elder was Artaxerxes, the younger Cyrus” [πρεσβύτερος μὲν Ἀρταξέρξης, νεώτερος δὲ Κύρος].¹¹⁷

Here the cōlon still delineates a thought, but one that is incomplete and therefore needs the support of other cōla to express the entire thought. In this example, the thought is made complete with two cōla. Even if the term περίοδος does not yet appear in this context, it will be made perfectly clear later in the treatise that the picture of the arm composed of many subparts (forearm, fingers, etc.) is in fact a metaphor for the period. Indeed, Demetrius will take up the same example from Xenophon’s *Anabasis* as a model of a “narrative period.”¹¹⁸ In other words, the “parts which themselves are integral” correspond to the cōla of periodic style.

3.1.4. Two kinds of style: “disjointed” (διηρημένη) vs “interwoven” (κατεστραμμένη)

Much like Aristotle, Demetrius distinguishes between two kinds of composition or two “kinds of style,” one that is periodic and one that is non-periodic.¹¹⁹ In contrast with Aristotle, however, who deemed the non-periodic style unpleasant and recommended that one should compose only using periods, the author of the *Περὶ ἑρμηνείας* does not express any preference for either of these styles. He recognises the value of each of them, and suggests that they should be alternated to produce discourse that is “simultaneously elaborate and simple ... neither too ordinary nor too artificial.”¹²⁰

Demetrius calls the periodic style “interwoven” (κατεστραμμένη). This is the same term that Aristotle used, but as we shall see in the discussion below (section 3.2), this does not mean that the two rhetoricians work with exactly the same conception of the period. Demetrius indicates that such a style is found “in the discourses of Isocrates, Gorgias and Alcidamas, in which periods succeed one another with no less regularity than the hexametres in the poetry of Homer.”¹²¹ He also compares the cōla of periodic

¹¹⁷ *Eloc.* 2–3. G. M. A. Grube (*A Greek Critic*, 60, n. 3) rightly remarks that the second cōlon of the example might also be regarded as two distinct cōla, πρεσβύτερος μὲν Ἀρταξέρξης and νεώτερος δὲ Κύρος. As P. Chiron suggests, there is probably only one single cōlon in Demetrius’ view because the idea of “elder” implies that of “younger,” so that the two ideas should be understood as together forming a single thought (*Du style*, 2, n. 5).

¹¹⁸ *Eloc.* 19.

¹¹⁹ See the discussion of the two styles in *Eloc.* 12–15. Demetrius uses the word ἑρμηνείας, which we could render “expression.”

¹²⁰ *Eloc.* 15.

¹²¹ *Eloc.* 12.

style to “stones which support and hold together the roof that encircles them.”¹²² A typical example would be this period from Demosthenes’ *Against Leptines*: μάλιστα μὲν εἵνεκα τοῦ νομίζειν συμφέρειν τῇ πόλει λελύσθαι τὸν νόμον / εἶτα καὶ τοῦ παιδὸς εἵνεκα τοῦ Χαβρίου / ὠμολόγησα τούτοις, ὡς ἂν οἷός τε ᾧ, συνερεῖν (“Chiefly because I thought it was in the interest of the state for the law to be repealed / but also for the sake of Chabrias’ boy / I have agreed to speak to the best of my ability in their support.”)¹²³ Here the three *côla* that together form the period are indeed closely “interwoven,” in the sense that they support each other in such a way that none of them could be read separately. Or, to take up the semantic description mentioned above (section 3.1.3), we could say that periodic *côla* are “integral parts” of a complete thought, the complete thought being the period. Each *côlon* conveys a thought that has its own completeness, but which still needs to be supported by one or more other *côla* in order to express the entire δίανοια.

As concerns the non-periodic style, Demetrius calls it “disjointed” (διηρημένη, lit. “divided into parts”) or sometimes “loose” (διαλελυμένη), in reference to the fact that “the *côla* into which it is divided are not closely united.”¹²⁴ We can already note the terminological difference with Aristotle, who used the term εἰρομένη (“continuous” or “sewn”)¹²⁵ to designate the non-periodic *lexis*. At first glance, the Aristotelian and Demetrian terminologies even seem to be conflicting, as εἰρομένη insists on the presence of bonds between the *côla*, while διηρημένη and διαλελυμένη both stress the disconnection between the *côla*. Nevertheless, as representatives of this non-periodic style, Demetrius mentions Hecataeus, Herodotus, as well as “the older writers in general”: this suggests that he and Aristotle have more or less the same thing in mind, because Aristotle also presents the non-periodic style as the older one and considers Herodotus to be a typical representative of it.¹²⁶ In this style, Demetrius explains, “the *côla* seem thrown upon one another in a heap without binding together or buttressing, and without the mutual support that is found in periods.”¹²⁷ He then continues by comparing the *côla* of disjointed style with “stones which are simply thrown about near

¹²² *Eloc.* 13.

¹²³ Demosthenes, *Lept.* 1. This extract is used twice by Demetrius: in §10, where it illustrates the definition of the period (see below, section 3.2.3), and then in §20, where it serves as a model for the “rhetorical period” (see below, section 3.2.5).

¹²⁴ *Eloc.* 12. The two terms seem to be interchangeable and appear twice together in the same context (when Demetrius defines the non-periodic style, in §12, and then when he discusses the characteristics of the “conversational period,” in §21).

¹²⁵ Arist., *Rhet.* III,9,1–3.

¹²⁶ *Eloc.* 12; cf. Arist., *Rhet.* III,9,2.

¹²⁷ *Eloc.* 12.

one another and not built into a structure.”¹²⁸ This metaphor indeed applies well to the model of disjointed style that Demetrius proposes: Ἐκαταῖος Μιλήσιος ᾧδε μυθεῖται / τάδε γράφω, ὡς μοι δοκεῖ ἀληθέα εἶναι / οἱ γὰρ Ἑλλήνων λόγοι πολλοί τε καὶ γελοῖοι, ὡς ἐμοὶ φαίνονται, εἰσὶν (“Hecataeus of Miletus thus relates. I write these things as they seem to me to be true. For the tales told by the Greeks are, as it appears to me, many and absurd.”)¹²⁹ To return to the issue of semantics (see section 3.1.3 above), we can note that each cōlon of this example contains a thought that is “complete in itself.” To put it another way, the cōla of disjointed style are syntactically independent from each other—at least so far as this example is considered.

In Demetrius’ view, the “disjointed” and “interwoven” styles are merely two different ways of combining cōla to form the discourse: in periodic style the cōla are closely interwoven to form periodic structures, while in non-periodic style the cōla are “disjointed,” as if they were thrown one upon another without an overarching structure. While it is easy to grasp in broad terms what distinguishes these two styles, it is much more difficult to explain precisely where the boundary between them is situated. In particular, in view of the aim of our study, the question arises as to which devices enable a set of cōla to be linked with a period. Is it a matter of semantics? Of semantics and syntax? Of semantics, syntax and style? In other words, what does it concretely mean for cōla to be “interwoven”? To answer these questions, we must now consider the Demetrian doctrine of the period.

3.2. *Periods*

Demetrius offers a long discussion of the period (§10–34), which includes a definition and many examples, some metaphors, a discussion of the acceptable length, a few allusions to the Aristotelean doctrine, a typology according to three categories (the rhetorical, the narrative, and the conversational period), and recommendations concerning the use of Gorgianic figures. Let us first consider the easiest aspect of this discussion: the length of periods.

¹²⁸ *Eloc.* 13

¹²⁹ Hecataeus, *Genealogies* 1; quoted in *Eloc.* 12. The final cōlon is arguably a monocōlon period (cf. *Eloc.* 17).

3.2.1. Length of periods

On this issue, Demetrius' opinion departs from that of Aristotle. Whereas the author of the *Rhetoric* recognises only the monocôlon and the dicôloi periods,¹³⁰ Demetrius stipulates that “the shorter periods consist of two cōla, the longest of four.”¹³¹ Anything beyond four cōla, he comments, would transgress the boundaries for a period: we may of course think here of the constraints related to the practice of oral delivery.¹³² Then, right after this general rule, Demetrius adds that there are also “simple periods” (ἀπλᾶι περίοδοι) consisting of a single cōlon. This concurs with Aristotle's doctrine. The discussion on monocôlon periods runs as follows:

Every cōlon that possesses the requisite length and rounds off at the end [καμπὴν κατὰ τὸ τέλος] forms a monocôlon. For example: “Herodotus of Halicarnassus sets forth in this History the result of his inquiries” [Ἡροδότου Ἀλικαρνασῆος ἱστορίας ἀπόδειξις ἦδε].¹³³ Again: “Clear expression sheds much light on the hearers' minds” [ἡ γὰρ σαφὴς φράσις πολὺ φῶς παρέχεται ταῖς τῶν ἀκουόντων διανοίαις]. For the simple period these are the two essentials, the length of the cōlon and its rounding off [καμπή] at the end. In the absence of either of these conditions, there is no period.¹³⁴

The category of the monocôlon period appears to be a very specific one. Demetrius insists on the fact that both a minimum length and a “rounding off” (καμπή) at the end are necessary. Indeed, we can note that the examples have 20 and 22 syllables respectively, which exceeds the standard limit for cōla.¹³⁵ The “rounding off” at the end may refer to the fact that ἦδε and διανοίαις appear as the final words of the first and the second periods respectively. To put it differently, in these two cases the καμπή consists of the delay of a key term (i.e., a term that is needed if the saying is to be understood) until the end. It is likely that this emphasis on the need for both a certain length and a rounding off is an attempt to clarify the distinction between a monocôlon period and a cōlon of disjointed style.¹³⁶

¹³⁰ Arist., *Rhet.* III,9,5.

¹³¹ *Eloc.* 16. A look at §34 reveals that Demetrius is fully aware that he departs from Aristotle on this point. Apparently, Demetrius is not the first to recognise that periods may comprise more than 2 cōla: in §34, he mentions that Archedemus (probably Archedemus of Tarsus, who flourished in the middle of the second-century BCE) already departed from the Aristotelean binary vision.

¹³² Cf. the remarks concerning the need for the speaker to breathe (*Eloc.* 1).

¹³³ Herodotus, *Hist.* 1. Cf. Arist., *Rhet.* III,9,1–3, where the same extract is quoted as a model of a non-periodic saying. Scholars have proposed various views on how this surprising fact might be explained: see the discussion above, under section 2.1.

¹³⁴ *Eloc.* 17.

¹³⁵ See section 3.1.2 above.

¹³⁶ Cf. Aquila Romanus, *Fig.* 28,14–18 Halm [= p. 31 Elice], who argues that the concept of a monocôlon period does not make any sense, since a period is by definition composed of many cōla.

We can add a comment here regarding the number of syllables that a period can comprise. The standard length of *côla* (10–20 syllables) implies that the standard length for periods is situated between 20 (one long *côlon*, or two *côla* of 10 syllables) and 80 syllables (four *côla* of 20 syllables). This aligns well with what we can concretely observe throughout the *Περί ἑρμηνείας*. In fact, among the examples of periods provided by Demetrius, the shortest has 15 syllables,¹³⁷ while the longest extends slightly beyond 80 syllables.¹³⁸

3.2.2. *Definition of the period*

A more complex matter is the definition of the period that Demetrius provides in §10. This definition is difficult to interpret, not only because of the polysemy of certain terms, but also because of the existence of variants in the textual tradition.¹³⁹ As we shall see, these difficulties are reflected in the multiple and diverging translations proposed by scholars. The text that I retain stands as follows:

Ἔστιν γὰρ ἡ περίοδος σύστημα ἐκ κώλων ἢ κομμάτων εὐκαταστροφῶν πρὸς τὴν διάνοιαν τὴν ὑποκειμένην ἀπηρτισμένον. [“A period is a system of interwoven *côla* or *commata*, which perfectly fits with the underlying thought.”]¹⁴⁰

The difficulties can be grouped according to two major issues. The first is in the choice between the adjective plural *εὐκαταστροφῶν*, attested in P² and M, and the adverb *εὐκαταστροφῶς*, found in the original reading of P.¹⁴¹ The adjective would qualify the

¹³⁷ *Eloc.* 25 (= Hom., *Iliad* IX,526): δωρητοὶ τε πέλοντο / παράρρητοὶ τ’ ἐπέεσσιν. Many other examples of short periods are found in *Eloc.* 22–26.

¹³⁸ *Eloc.* 45 (= Thuc., *Pelop.* II,102,2): ὁ γὰρ Ἀχελῷος ποταμὸς ῥέων ἐκ Πίνδου ὄρους διὰ Δολοπίας καὶ Ἀγριανῶν καὶ Ἀμφιλόχων / ἄνωθεν παρὰ Στράτον πόλιν ἐς θάλασσαν διεξιεις παρ’ Οἰνιάδας / καὶ τὴν πόλιν αὐτοῖς περιλιμνάζων / ἄπορον ποιεῖ ὑπὸ τοῦ ὕδατος ἐν χειμῶνι στρατεύεσθαι. The division into *côla* is mine.

¹³⁹ On the manuscript tradition, see P. Chiron, “Introduction” (*Du style*), CVII–CXXXV. The direct tradition is found mainly in P (Parisinus Gr. 1741), dated to the 10th century, and M (Marcianus Gr. 508), dated to the 12th century, to which we can add many later manuscripts (15th–16th centuries) that are for most part derived from P. P contains corrections by a second hand (P²), made shortly after the initial copy, and which are arguably the result of a comparison with a second Vorlage (let us call it x) belonging to the same family as M (P. Chiron, “Introduction” (*Du style*), CXVI–CXVII). Chiron has also convincingly argued that P and M both derive from the same 9th-century original in majuscules, with M having x as an intermediary (*ibid.*, CXX–CXXII); if this scenario is correct, M and P² *might* even preserve at some places readings that are older than those found in the first reading of P, and hence both P² and M should be taken seriously when establishing the text.

¹⁴⁰ *Eloc.* 10.

¹⁴¹ The first reading of P (P¹, 10th century) stands as follows: καὶ ἔστι περίοδος σύστημα ἐκ κώλων ἢ κομμάτων εὐκαταστροφῶς [εἰς?] τὴν διάνοιαν τὴν ὑποκειμένην ἀπηρτισμένον; this was later modified by a second hand (P²) into: ἔστιν γὰρ ἡ περίοδος σύστημα ἐκ κώλων ἢ κομμάτων εὐκαταστροφῶν πρὸς τὴν διάνοιαν τὴν ὑποκειμένην ἀπηρτισμένον. M supports the reading of P². See P. Chiron, “Introduction” (*Du style*), CXVI.

côla and the commata, while the adverb would be built with the participle ἀπηρτισμένον. As far as the Thesaurus Linguae Graecae database can inform us, the terms εὐκαταστροφῶν and εὐκαταστροφῶς are attested nowhere else, except for one use of the adjective εὐκαταστροφός in Eustathius' 12th century commentary on *Iliad* XVII.59. In this specific context, however, the term is used in a physical sense, in reference to an olive tree that can be uprooted by turning it. In addition, it is difficult to determine the meaning of these terms, since the etymologic link with καταστρέφω allows various interpretations modelled on the different meanings of the verb that are associated with the prefix εὐ: e.g., the notion of completion or ending, the idea of something that “turns back” or “bends back,” the notion of something well-turned (i.e., a formulation that is “constrained” in an elegant manner), or even the image of weaving.¹⁴² Regarding the choice between the adjective and the adverb, it should be noted that the adverbial form is more frequently retained in scholarship, possibly because P¹ has long served as the reference for critical editions, while M and P² were neglected.¹⁴³ Various translations have been proposed, e.g., “dexterously,”¹⁴⁴ “brought to a good conclusion,”¹⁴⁵ “well,”¹⁴⁶ “well-turned,”¹⁴⁷ “well-rounded,”¹⁴⁸ “in guter Unterordnung,”¹⁴⁹ “with a well-turned ending,”¹⁵⁰ “wohlgerundet,”¹⁵¹ “dans un contour parfait.”¹⁵² In my view, however, there is no decisive reason to retain the adverb, and I think that the adjective εὐκαταστροφῶν in fact makes more sense in this context, especially in view of Demetrius' use of the related term κατεστραμμένη to designate the periodic style.¹⁵³ Indeed, it is possible to render the adjective with “interwoven” or “intertwined,” which concurs with the definition of the periodic style as an interweaving of côla. As an alternative, if we refer to the meaning of the noun

¹⁴² See above, n. 34.

¹⁴³ On the importance attributed to each of the manuscripts of the *Περὶ ἔρμηνείας* in modern editions, see the short overview in P. Chiron, “Introduction” (*Démétrios: Du style*), CVII-CXXXVII. Note that the adverb is also retained in most of the recent editions, including P. Chiron (*Du style*, 5); D. C. Innes (*On Style*, 351); and N. Marini (*Lo Stile*, 50).

¹⁴⁴ W. R. Roberts, *Demetrius On Style*, 73.

¹⁴⁵ LSJ.

¹⁴⁶ G. M. A. Grube, *A Greek Critic: Demetrius on Style*, 63.

¹⁴⁷ LSJ; cf. also Schenkeveld, *Studies in Demetrius*, 26.

¹⁴⁸ D. M. Schenkeveld, *Studies in Demetrius*, 26.

¹⁴⁹ J. Zehetmeier, *Die Periodenlehre des Aristoteles*, 424.

¹⁵⁰ See e.g., Innes, *On Style*, 351; Id., “Period and Cōlon: Theory and Examples in Demetrius and Longinus,” 45; cf. also D. Nässelqvist, *Public Reading*, 134.

¹⁵¹ E. Orth, *Demetrius vom Stil* (see the reference in Schenkeveld, *Studies in Demetrius*, 25).

¹⁵² P. Chiron, *Du Style*, 5.

¹⁵³ *Eloc.* 12.

καταστροφή as “end, close, conclusion,” then the derived adjective might be understood as “having a good conclusion” or “brought to a good conclusion,” hence the *côla* and *commata* are “brought to a good conclusion.” In support of the choice of the adjective, we can also note that it is attested in both M and P², which *might* suggest that this represents an earlier version than the adverb.¹⁵⁴

The second issue in Demetrius’ definition of the period concerns the specification that the system of *côla* or *commata* πρὸς τὴν διάνοιαν τὴν ὑποκειμένην ἀπηρτισμένον.¹⁵⁵ The heart of the problem lies in how we understand the relation between the middle-passive participle ἀπηρτισμένον, which qualifies the “system of *côla* or *commata*,” and the noun phrase that precedes it (τὴν διάνοιαν τὴν ὑποκειμένην: “the underlying thought”). This issue is complicated by the polysemy of the verb ἀπαρτίζω, which can mean “make even, complete, finish smth” (passive: “to be completed, to be brought to perfection”), but also, as an intransitive, “be complete,” “fit exactly,” or, when associated with πρὸς τι, “suit perfectly smth” or “square with smth.”¹⁵⁶ Hence, we may consider that “the underlying thought” functions either as (1) a direct or (2) an indirect object of ἀπηρτισμένον, or alternatively (3) that πρὸς τὴν διάνοιαν τὴν ὑποκειμένην represents an adjunct that specifies the relation between ἀπηρτισμένον and τὴν διάνοιαν. These are, as far as I understand, the three interpretative lines reflected in the translations that exist today. Let us now consider these three options.

According to the first option, the participle should be taken in the sense of “complete,” “finish”: namely, the system of *côla* and *commata* “completes the thought,” or “has brought the underlying thought to a conclusion.” This works well if the adverb εὐκαταστρόφως is retained rather than the adjective, as this would then qualify how the thought is brought to a conclusion, e.g., “dexterously” or “with a well-turned ending.” According to this interpretative line, the ending of the period plays a key role. Hence, we find many translations that stress the role of the ending, as for example the translation proposed by D.C. Innes: “A period is a combination of clauses [*côla*] and

¹⁵⁴ See above, n. 139 and n. 141.

¹⁵⁵ In P, the corrector erased some letters before τὴν διάνοιαν and replaced them by πρὸς. According to H. Schenkl, this blank space should be completed with εἰς (“Zur Kritik der Schrift des Demetrios Περὶ ἐρμηνείας,” 67). This suggestion is based on a closely-worded definition found in Pseudo-Aelius Aristides’ *On Political Discourse*, that *might* attest to an earlier version of Demetrius’ text. Pseudo-Aelius Aristides’ definition stands as follows: [περίοδος] ἐστὶν σύνταξις κῶλων καὶ κομμάτων εἰς διάνοιαν ἀπηρτισμένη [φράσις] (*Pol.* 167 [= p. 507 Sp., *RG* II]; see below, section 9.1.2). This proposition was then followed by W. R. Roberts (*Demetrius On Style*, 72), whose critical edition was published in 1902 and represented the reference English edition throughout the 20th century. Note that εἰς has also been found more recently in the edition by N. Marini (*Lo Stile*, 50). However, although the original presence of εἰς in P¹ is not unlikely, I think there is no decisive reason to assume that this would represent an earlier state of the text than πρὸς.

¹⁵⁶ LSJ.

phrases [commata] arranged to conclude the thought *with a well-turned ending*.¹⁵⁷ Among NT scholars involved in sound mapping, D. Nässelqvist retains a close translation: “a combination of cōla or commata which has brought the underlying thought to a conclusion *with a well-turned ending*.”¹⁵⁸ However, it seems to me that we find here a grammatical problem with the syntactic construction, as the presence of πρὸς makes it difficult to understand “the underlying thought” as functioning as a direct object of ἀπηρτισμένον.¹⁵⁹ This grammatical difficulty remains even if the preposition εἰς is retained instead of πρὸς, as is possibly the case in the original reading of P.¹⁶⁰ Moreover, as we shall see below (section 3.2.3), such an emphasis on the ending of the period seems inconsistent with the recommendations Demetrius later gives in the treatise. This first interpretative line should therefore be abandoned.

According to the second option, where πρὸς introduces an indirect object, the system of cōla and commata “squares with” or “fits exactly with” the underlying thought.¹⁶¹ In my view, such an interpretation works well with the choice of the adjective plural εὐκαταστρόφων, which could then describe how the cōla and/or the commata are linked together within the period, i.e., they are “closely interwoven” or “perfectly interwoven.”¹⁶² This understanding corresponds to the translation I proposed above: “A period is a system of interwoven cōla and commata, which perfectly fits with the underlying thought.”¹⁶³ Or, in a more literal way and in order to better render the resultative sense conveyed by the perfect participle, we may even translate “[a system] which has been adjusted to the underlying thought.” Alternatively, if εὐκαταστρόφων is understood in the sense of “having a good conclusion,” then the system of cōla and commata is qualified in two different manners: not only does this system have some

¹⁵⁷ D. C. Innes, *On Style*, 351 (my emphasis).

¹⁵⁸ D. Nässelqvist, *Public Reading in Early Christianity*, 134 (my emphasis). This translation seems in fact to be taken from Innes’ earlier proposition, made in her article “Period and Cōlon: Theory and Examples in Demetrius and Longinus,” 45.

¹⁵⁹ To be fair, the scholars mentioned do not say that they understand ἀπηρτισμένον to be the direct object of τὴν διάνοιαν τὴν ὑποκειμένην. They do not explain how they understand the grammar of the sentence, such that my critique refers to how I reconstruct their understanding based on the translations they propose. It is of course possible that I might have misunderstood their interpretations.

¹⁶⁰ See above, footnote 155. D. Nässelqvist is one of those scholars who retain the reading εἰς (*Public Reading*, 134, n. 56).

¹⁶¹ For a usage of ἀπαρτίζω πρὸς in the sense of “fit perfectly” or “square with,” see e.g. Arist., *Pol.* 5, 1313 a 7.

¹⁶² See *Eloc.* 12, where the periodic style is qualified as κατεστραμμένη, “interwoven” (see above, section 3.1.4).

¹⁶³ In this sense, see e.g. W. R. Robert, *Demetrius On Style*, 73: “Now the period is a collection of members or phrases, arranged dexterously to fit the thought to be expressed” (my emphasis). Cf. also D. M. Grube (*A Greek Critic*, 63): “fits the thought.”

sort of well-turned ending, but it also perfectly fits with the underlying thought. In this case, however, it would be a little bit surprising not to have a coordinative particle between εὐκαταστροφῶν and πρὸς τὴν διάνοιαν. What if the adverb εὐκαταστροφῶς was retained instead of the adjective? If so, the adverb would qualify how the system fits with the thought, i.e., “in a well-turned manner” or possibly “according to a perfect outline,” as e.g. in the French translation by Pierre Chiron: “La période est un ensemble de cōla ou de commata qui, *dans un contour parfait, s’ajuste exactement à la pensée à exprimer.*”¹⁶⁴ This last proposition is in my view appropriate to express the force of the adverb. However, as argued above, I personally think that it makes more sense to retain the adjective plural εὐκαταστροφῶν, as this better echoes the use of κατεστραμμένη to qualify the periodic style.

Finally, the third interpretative option would be to read πρὸς τὴν διάνοιαν τὴν ὑποκειμένην as an adjunct. This makes it possible to consider πρὸς as expressing the relation between the system’s characteristic of “being complete” and “the thought to be expressed.” In other words, the system of cōla or commata “has been completed *in respect of* the underlying thought,” or “has been brought to a conclusion *in view of* the underlying thought.” The preposition πρὸς might even express a sort of finale: the system “has been brought to a conclusion *with a view to* the thought.” Semantically speaking, this third option may concur with either the first or the second interpretative line, depending on whether the adjective or the adverb is retained. If we take the adjective plural εὐκαταστροφῶν in the sense of “interwoven,” then the general idea remains close to the translation I proposed above, as the core point is still that of a perfect correspondence between the formulation and the thought. A possible translation in this sense would be: “a period is a system of interwoven cōla and commata, which has been completed in view of the underlying thought.” In contrast, if the adverb εὐκαταστροφῶς is retained, then it becomes possible to introduce again the notion of a well-turned ending, as, e.g. in the translation proposed by Schenkeveld: “A period is a combination of cola and commata, which *in view of the underlying thought* has been brought to a well-turned end.”¹⁶⁵ With regard to the meaning, this last suggestion stands closer to the second interpretative line. However, as I will argue below, this translation still insists too heavily on the importance of the ending, which is inconsistent with the subsequent development on periods found in the treatise.

¹⁶⁴ P. Chiron, *Du Style*, 5 (my emphasis).

¹⁶⁵ D. M. Schenkeveld, *Studies on Demetrius*, 25, n. 2 (my emphasis); see also the discussion on page 25.

3.2.3. *The issue of the ending of periods*

It is worth trying to understand what caused many scholars to favour translations that put such a strong accent on the ending of periods. The main cause is arguably the immediate context of the passage.¹⁶⁶ Indeed, immediately after the definition of the period in §10, Demetrius offers an example from the opening of Demosthenes' speech *Against Leptines*:

For example: μάλιστα μὲν εἵνεκα τοῦ νομίζειν συμφέρειν τῇ πόλει λελύσθαι τὸν νόμον / εἶτα καὶ τοῦ παιδὸς εἵνεκα τοῦ Χαβρίου / ὠμολόγησα τούτοις, ὡς ἂν οἷός τε ᾧ, συνερεῖν [“Chiefly because I thought it was in the interest of the state for the law to be repealed / but also for the sake of Chabrias' boy / I have agreed to speak to the best of my ability in their support.”] This three-côla period has a rounding off [καμπήν] and a compactness [συστροφήν] at the end.¹⁶⁷

This example of tricôloi period indeed comprises a sophisticated ending. As Demetrius indicates, this period exhibits both a καμπή (“rounding off”)¹⁶⁸ and a συστροφή (“compactness”)¹⁶⁹ at the end. The καμπή is arguably due to the fact that the thought is finished only with the final word of the third cōlon (the verb συνερεῖν, “advocate,” “speak in support”). Such an interpretation is supported by §17, where the two examples of monocôlon periods, both of which are said to possess a καμπή, present the same phenomenon of the delay of a key syntactic element until the end.¹⁷⁰ Then, more concretely, the term καμπή may refer to “ce moment où la voix, après avoir atteint l'intensité maximum, commence à baisser, pour aboutir aux derniers mots qui viendront compléter le sens resté en suspens jusqu'à eux [...]”¹⁷¹ As concerns the συστροφή, this might allude to the presence of a specific rhythmical pattern in the

¹⁶⁶ That the notion of a well-turned ending is suggested by the immediate context of the passage is explicitly stated in Schenkeveld, *Studies in Demetrius*, 26–27.

¹⁶⁷ *Eloc.* 10. The extract is from Demosthenes, *Lept.* 1; the same example is taken up again in §11 and later in §20.

¹⁶⁸ P. Chiron translates καμπή “courbe” (*Du Style*, 5). Innes proposes “backward bend” (*On Style*, 351; see also “Period and Cōlon: Theory and Examples in Demetrius and Longinus,” 45–46, n. 36). Roberts (*Demetrius on Style*, 73) suggests “a certain bend.” The term designates a flexing or ending; figuratively, it can also designate an inflexion of the voice (e.g. Aristophanes, *Nub.* 969.).

¹⁶⁹ This translation choice for συστροφή is somewhat neutral; it is notably made by D.C. Innes (*On Style*, 351). Roberts employs “concentration” (*Demetrius On Style*, 73). The core idea is indeed that of density or concentration at the end of the period. P. Chiron also seems to follow this idea (“[la période] se ramasse sur elle-même”; *Du Style*, 6). An alternative and somewhat less neutral translation would be: “this period [...] twists around itself at the end” (in reference to a possible meaning of συστροφή as “twisting together,” e.g. of yarn, as in Plato, *Plt.* 282e).

¹⁷⁰ *Eloc.* 17 (see above, section 3.2.1).

¹⁷¹ This is the interpretation proposed by P. Chiron, who continues: “[...] c'est le point de rebroussement, le moment où la période commence à se refermer sur elle-même.” (*Pseudo-Démétrios de Phalère. Un rhéteur méconnu*, 80–81).

closing syllables that creates a sort of concentration or density at the end of the period. In this example, the rhythm of the closing syllables indeed resembles a fourth paeon (συνερεῖν: u u –), which Demetrius—who follows Aristotle in this respect—regards as the best rhythmical clausula.¹⁷² Therefore, as far as the model of period provided in §10 is considered, it seems appropriate to understand the definition of the period as involving the notion of a well-turned ending.

Nevertheless, a glance at §19–21 reveals that the picture is in fact more complex. In those paragraphs, Demetrius establishes a typology of periods: these are classified into three types, the rhetorical, the conversational, and the historical, each of which has its own characteristic features. Specifically, the *rhetorical period* is described as having “a structured and circular shape”; the *conversational period* is “loose and simple to the point that it scarcely shows that it is a period”; while the *historical period*, which is a mix between the two others, “should neither be too carefully rounded nor too loose.”¹⁷³ Each of these types is illustrated by a model. Interestingly, Demetrius picks up again the opening of Demosthenes’ *Leptines*, which served to illustrate the general definition of the period in §10, as a model for the rhetorical period. This time his comment stands as follows: “Almost right from the very beginning such a period is well-structured, which shows that it will not stop on a simple ending.”¹⁷⁴ It is likely that the final remark (“it will not stop on a simple ending”) refers to both the *καμπή* and the *συστροφή* which are, according to §10, present at the end of this period.¹⁷⁵ In contrast, conversational periods have neither *καμπή* nor *συστροφή*. Their end is said to be very discrete: “when we reach the end, we can hardly realise that the words formed a period.”¹⁷⁶ In other words, this typology makes clear that a well-turned ending is not necessary in all kinds of periods: “rounding off” and “compactness” at the end are typical of rhetorical periods, while, at the other extreme, conversational periods do not exhibit any specific features to mark their conclusions.

To conclude our discussion of the issue of the ending of periods, it is also worth noting how the author of the *Περί ἑρμηνείας* refers to the Aristotelean definition. After providing his own definition of the period, Demetrius also quotes the definition found in the *Rhetoric* and qualifies it as “excellent and apt.”¹⁷⁷ Nevertheless, the subtlety resides

¹⁷² *Eloc.* 39–41. Cf. Arist., *Rhet.* III,8.

¹⁷³ *Eloc.* 19–21. On this typology, see section 3.2.5 below.

¹⁷⁴ *Eloc.* 20.

¹⁷⁵ *Eloc.* 10.

¹⁷⁶ *Eloc.* 21.

¹⁷⁷ *Eloc.* II.

in the fact that only the first part of Aristotle’s definition is quoted. Whereas Aristotle said that a period is “a saying that has a beginning and end *in itself* and a magnitude that is easily grasped,”¹⁷⁸ Demetrius simply states: “the period is a saying that has a beginning and an end.”¹⁷⁹ It is likely that the precision “in itself,” that was crucial to Aristotle’s doctrine on the period, has been omitted intentionally, with the intention of expanding the definition of the period. To put in another way, Demetrius does not completely agree with Aristotle on what a period constitutes—but for some reason he avoids open conflict with him. Not only does he reject the Aristotelean binary vision by extending the acceptable length to four *côla*, but he also works with a less strict idea of how the extremities of periods should look.¹⁸⁰

3.2.4. *The metaphor of a circle and the role of synthesis*

Having defined the period, Demetrius turns to an illuminating metaphor. He compares the period with a race-course, and more specifically with a *circular course*:

For the very use of the word “period” implies that it has had a beginning at one point, will end at another, and is speeding towards a definite goal, like runners sprinting from the starting place. For at the very beginning of their race the end of the course is already before their eyes. Hence the name “period,” an image drawn from paths which go round and are in a circle [ἀπεικασθεῖσα ταῖς ὁδοῖς ταῖς κυκλοειδέσι καὶ περιωδευμέναις].¹⁸¹

The comparison between a period and a race was already found in the *Rhetoric*.¹⁸² Nevertheless, Demetrius introduces a new development with this metaphor, by exploring the circular meaning of *περί-ὁδός* (“way around”).¹⁸³ Such an image was not present in Aristotle, who arguably had in mind the *δίαιλος* (i.e., the traditional double race where runners had to reach a turning post before racing back to the starting line).¹⁸⁴ In contrast, the metaphor of circularity plays a key role in Demetrius’ thought.

¹⁷⁸ *Rhet.* III,9,3.

¹⁷⁹ *περίοδος ἐστι λέξις ἀρχὴν ἔχουσα καὶ τελευτὴν* (*Eloc.* II).

¹⁸⁰ In my view, Demetrius is fully aware that he moves away from Aristotle’s thought on this point, but he avoids making this explicit because he wishes to stress the continuity with Aristotle. Cf. the different interpretation in D. M. Schenkeveld, who thinks that Demetrius has misunderstood Aristotle (*Studies in Demetrius On Style*, 30–31).

¹⁸¹ *Eloc.* II.

¹⁸² *Arist., Rhet.* III,9,2.

¹⁸³ LSJ mentions the following meanings as referring to the idea of something “circular”: “way round,” “circumference,” “circuit,” “compass,” “going round in a circle,” “cycle of time,” “periodic recurrence of events,” “orbit of a heavenly body.”

¹⁸⁴ Aristotle does not state explicitly in the *Rhetoric* that he has the *δίαιλος* in mind. Nonetheless, this interpretation is strongly suggested by Aristotle’s binary vision of the period, each *côlon* being comparable to half of a *δίαιλος*. Significantly, the term *κῶλον* can designate one of the two parts of the

The very term κύκλος (“circle”) also appears several times in the treatise in relation to periods, for example in the expression “the circle of the period.”¹⁸⁵ This is an extremely powerful image, since it alludes to all the positive connotations of the circle: perfection, fluidity, and completion.

What does it mean, concretely, for a period to be “circular”? Apparently, in Demetrius’ view, this has a lot to do with *synthesis* (σύνθεσις), i.e., the “composition” or the “arrangement of words.” What he calls σύνθεσις cannot be reduced to word order: this designates, more broadly, the way words are put together, including the choices of verbal mode and aspect, the case of nouns, and the use of conjunctions. *Synthesis* plays such a crucial role in creating periods that our author states:

A period is nothing more nor less than a particular arrangement [σύνθεσις] of words. If its circular form [τὸ περιωδευμένον] should be destroyed and the arrangement changed, the subject matter remains the same, but there will be no period.¹⁸⁶

In order to illustrate how a rearrangement of words can cause a saying to lose its periodic aspect, Demetrius alters the Demosthenean period that was already quoted in §10:

Periodic version: μάλιστα μὲν εἶνεκα τοῦ νομίζειν συμφέρειν τῇ πόλει λελύσθαι τὸν νόμον / εἶτα καὶ τοῦ παιδὸς εἶνεκα τοῦ Χαβρίου / ὠμολόγησα τούτοις, ὡς ἂν οἴός τε ὦ, συνερεῖν

Non-periodic version: συνερῶ τούτοις, ὧ ἄνδρες Ἀθηναῖοι / φίλος γάρ μοι ἐστὶν ὁ υἱὸς Χαβρίου, πολὺ δὲ μᾶλλον τούτου ἢ πόλις / ἧ συνερεῖν με δίκαιόν ἐστιν.¹⁸⁷

Let us compare the two versions: in the periodic one, the three cōla were interlinked so that it was impossible, from a syntactic point of view, to stop before the last cōlon. Moreover, owing to the placement of συνερεῖν as the final word, there was a perfect correspondence between the end of the period and the end of the thought expressed. In contrast, in the modified version, it is possible to stop at least after ἄνδρες Ἀθηναῖοι, and possibly also after ἢ πόλις. Indeed, after πόλις the discourse continues with the relative ἧ, which may be seen here as having the function of a demonstrative, meaning that strong punctuation (e.g. a full stop) is warranted. A possible translation would therefore be as follows: “I will support the complainants, men of Athens. For Chabrias’ son is dear to me, and much more so is the city. In its favour [that of the city] it is right

διάυλος (see e.g. Aeschylus, *Agamemnon*, 344). Aristotle’s use of καμπτήρες (*Rhet.* III,9,2), which is a technical term used to designate the turning-point of the διάυλος (cf. Aeschylus, *Agamemnon*, 344.), also supports this understanding.

¹⁸⁵ See e.g. *Eloc.* 31.

¹⁸⁶ *Eloc.* II.

¹⁸⁷ *Eloc.* II. The division into cōla is mine.

for me to plead.”¹⁸⁸ In this example, breaking the circularity consists concretely of a syntactic reorganisation that has deleted the relations of syntactic dependency between the *côla*, thereby resulting in the splitting of the period into many independent *côla*. A similar example is found later in the treatise, where Demetrius breaks the circular movement of a Thucydidean period:

Thucydides' original period: ὁ γὰρ Ἀχελῶος ποταμὸς ῥέων ἐκ Πίνδου ὄρους διὰ Δολοπίας καὶ Ἀγριανῶν καὶ Ἀμφιλόχων / ἄνωθεν παρὰ Στράτον πόλιν ἐς θάλασσαν διεξιείς παρ' Οἰνιάδας / καὶ τὴν πόλιν αὐτοῖς περιλιμνάζων / ἄπορον ποιεῖ ὑπὸ τοῦ ὕδατος ἐν χειμῶνι στρατεῦσθαι [“The river Achelous, flowing from Mount Pindus through Dolopia and the land of the Agrianians and Amphilocheians / passing by the city of Stratus on the way into the sea near Oeniadae / and surrounding that town with a marsh / by its floods makes impossible any winter attack.”]¹⁸⁹

Non-periodic version: ὁ γὰρ Ἀχελῶος ποταμὸς ῥεῖ μὲν ἐκ Πίνδου ὄρους / ἐκβάλλει δὲ παρ' Οἰνιάδας ἐς θάλασσαν / πρὸ δὲ τῆς ἐκβολῆς τὸ Οἰνιαδῶν πεδῖον λίμνην ποιεῖ / ὥστ' αὐτοῖς πρὸς τὰς χειμερινὰς ἐφόδους τῶν πολεμίων ἔρυμα καὶ πρόβλημα γίνεσθαι τὸ ὕδωρ¹⁹⁰

In this example of reformulation, breaking the circle of the period means basically removing the relations of syntactic dependency between the *côla*. In this case, the change has consisted merely of replacing the participles ῥέων, διεξιείς, and περιλιμνάζων by the finite verbs ῥεῖ, ἐκβάλλει and ποιεῖ (τὸ πεδῖον λίμνην), which permits each *côlon* to stand on its own. In fact, in the original periodic version, the formulation with participles makes it impossible to stop before the fourth *côlon*; the suspense even lasts until the final word, the infinitive στρατεῦσθαι (“advance with an army”). In the modified version, on the other hand, it is possible to place strong punctuation marks within the saying, after ὄρους, θάλασσαν, and ποιεῖ. A possible translation would thus be:

“The river Achelous flows from Mount Pindus. It makes its way into the sea near Oeniadae. But before reaching its outlet it turns the plain of Oeniadae into a marsh. As a result, the floods form a defence and protection against enemy attack in winter.”

To be clear, the emphasis on the role of *synthesis* does not mean that circularity is solely a matter of arranging the words in such a way that the thought is left suspended until the end. In fact, Demetrius' comments at other places in the treatise offer a glimpse into

¹⁸⁸ According to this proposition, *συνερω̄ τούτοις, ὧ̄ ἄνδρες Ἀθηναῖοι* and *ἧ̄ συνεπιεῖν με δίκαιόν ἐστιν* are autonomous *côla*, while *φίλος γάρ μοί ἐστιν ὁ υἱὸς Χαβρίου / πολὺ δὲ μάλλον τούτου ἢ πόλις* would consist of a short period comprising two *côla*. Cf. the punctuation proposed in Innes' edition (*On Style*, 352): *συνερω̄ τούτοις, ὧ̄ ἄνδρες Ἀθηναῖοι. φίλος γάρ μοί ἐστιν ὁ υἱὸς Χαβρίου, πολὺ δὲ μάλλον τούτου ἢ πόλις, ἧ̄ συνεπιεῖν με δίκαιόν ἐστιν.*

¹⁸⁹ Thucyd., *Pelop.* II,102,2; quoted in Dem., *Eloc.* 45. The division into *côla* is mine.

¹⁹⁰ *Eloc.* 46. The division into *côla* is mine.

other devices that may also help give periods a “circular aspect.” We can mention the use of specific rhythmical patterns, especially clausulae that mark the end of periods; the avoidance of hiatus that brings an impression of fluidity; and also, possibly, the phenomena of parallelisms between the *côla*, especially those induced by the so-called Gorgianic figures of speech,¹⁹¹ as such parallelisms give a sense of regularity and sophistication to the discourse. To be fair, however, it is difficult to grasp in a precise manner what Demetrius means by “circularity”: the term seems to be an umbrella term that encompasses a series of effects related to the positive connotations of the circle (completion, perfection, fluidity), but these effects can arguably be achieved through a variety of devices that the treatise does not enumerate in a comprehensive way.

3.2.5. “Degrees of circularity”: a typology of periods

Based on the two above examples of reformulations, one might be tempted to understand periodicity and circularity as strictly synonymous—since destroying the periodic character of the periods has consisted of destroying their circular characteristics. This conclusion, however, is too simplistic. The link between the periodic status of a given saying and its circular aspect is ambiguous. On the one hand, such a link is obvious, in view of the very meaning of the term *περίοδος*; but on the other hand, some sayings that do not exhibit circular characteristics, or may be described as “barely circular,” are still called periods. This somewhat surprising fact can be observed in the typology of periods to which I already alluded:

§19 There are three kinds of periods, the historical, the conversational, and the rhetorical.

The historical period should be neither too carefully rounded nor too loose [μήτε περιηγμένη, μήτ’ άνειμένη σφόδρα], but between the two, in such a way that it is not thought rhetorical and unconvincing because of its rounding [διὰ τὴν περιαγωγὴν], but has the dignity and aptness for history from its simplicity, as in the passage from “Darius and Parysatis” up to “the younger Cyrus.”¹⁹² Its closing words resemble a firm and securely based ending.

§20 The form of the rhetorical period is well structured [συνεστραμμένον] and circular [κυκλικόν]; and it needs well-rounded mouth and hand gestures to follow each movement of the rhythm. For example: “Chiefly because I thought it was in the interest of the state for the law to be repealed / but also for the sake of Chabrias’ boy / I have agreed to speak to the

¹⁹¹ See *Eloc.* 22–29.

¹⁹² This example was already given in *Eloc.* 2–3, in the development concerning the two kinds of *côla*. For the Greek text, see above, section 3.1.3.

best of my ability in their support.”¹⁹³ Almost right from the very beginning such a period is well structured [συνεστραμμένον],¹⁹⁴ which shows that it will not stop on a simple ending.

§21 The conversational period is one which is even looser and simpler [ἀνειμένη και ἀπλουστέρα] than the historical period, and scarcely shows that it is a period. For instance: “I went down yesterday to Piraeus” as far as the words “since they were now celebrating (it) for the first time.” Cōla are flung one on top of the other, as in the disjointed style, and when we reach the end we can hardly realise that the words formed a period. For the conversational period should be a form of composition midway between the disjointed and the interwoven style, compounded of both and resembling both.

There are thus these different kinds of periods.

In this typology, Demetrius comments on what could be termed the “degree of circularity” of the different kinds of periods. Let us begin with the rhetorical period, whose form is described as “well-structured and circular.” By way of illustration, he quotes the first lines of Demosthenes’ *Against Leptines*: μάλιστα μὲν εἵνεκα τοῦ νομίζειν συμφέρειν τῇ πόλει λελύσθαι τὸν νόμον / εἶτα καὶ τοῦ παιδὸς εἵνεκα τοῦ Χαβρίου / ὠμολόγησα τούτοις, ὡς ἂν οἷός τε ᾧ, συνερεῖν. With the help of Demetrius’ previous comments on this period, in §10 and §11 (see sections 3.2.3–3.2.4 above), we can enumerate different features that all arguably contribute to its circular aspect. The most obvious point is that the three cōla are intrinsically linked, both on the semantic and the syntactic level. Not only does the μὲν ... δέ construction link the two first cōla, but the core of the thought is retained up to the third cōlon. It is even impossible to stop before the final word, συνερεῖν (“speak in the support”), as the thought is made complete and intelligible only at this point—a feature that Demetrius previously called καμπή (“rounding off”). In addition, the end of the period is marked by “compactness” (συστροφή), in this case a rhythmical pattern that resembles paeon (συνερεῖν: υυ–).¹⁹⁵ Finally, we can note the quasi absence of hiatus and consonant clashes¹⁹⁶: this gives the

¹⁹³ Demost., *Lept.* 1. This is the third use of this example in the treatise (see §10 and §11).

¹⁹⁴ The middle-passive perfect participle συνεστραμμένον, which appears twice in §20, is difficult to understand. Here I follow P. Chiron’s somewhat neutral interpretation (*Du Style*, p. 9), which retains the idea of something “well structured” (“forme structurée,” and then “caractère structuré”). Alternatively, or maybe in parallel, συνεστραμμένον may convey the idea that the rhetorical period is “rolled up” or “twisted up”: in this sense, rhetorical periods would have a “spiral structure,” which echoes the idea that these periods are circular. In contrast, Innes (*On Style*, 359) suggests the translations “compact” (“the form of the rhetorical period is compact”) and “compactness” (“such a period has compactness”). I am not convinced by this proposition, even if this has the merit of highlighting the etymological link with the συστροφή (“compactness”) of the period mentioned in *Eloc.* 10. In fact, it seems to me that *Eloc.* 10 treats “compactness” as a feature that is specific to the end of this period. In this sense, it seems improper to take up the same translation in §20, where συνεστραμμένον is clearly a characteristic of the entire period (“almost right from the very beginning such a period is συνεστραμμένον”).

¹⁹⁵ On rhythmical clausulae in Demetrius, see *Eloc.* 38–43.

¹⁹⁶ By consonant clash, I mean here the meeting of specific consonants, which results in an unpleasant sound; see Dion., *Comp.*, 14–16; cf. also Dem., *Eloc.* 48–49.

period a smooth texture, a kind of fluidity that might be thought as contributing to the perfection of the circle.

At the other extreme, the conversational period is said to be “loose.” Such a period, Demetrius explains, is close to the disjointed style, since its *côla* are “flung one upon another.”¹⁹⁷ As a result, the conversational period “scarcely betrays the fact that it is a period.” The model proposed by Demetrius is the opening of Plato’s *Republic*:

κατέβην χθές εἰς Πειραιᾶ μετὰ Γλαύκωνος τοῦ Ἀρίστωνος / προσευξόμενός τε τῇ θεῷ / καὶ ἄμα τὴν ἑορτὴν βουλόμενος θεάσασθαι τίνα τρόπον ποιήσουσιν / ἅτε νῦν πρῶτον ἄγοντες (“I went down yesterday to the Piraeus with Glaucon, the son of Ariston / in order to offer up my prayers to the goddess / and also because I wanted to see how they would organise the festival / since they were celebrating (it) for the first time.”)¹⁹⁸

Here there is neither delay of a key element up to the end, nor a specific rhythmical pattern that would underline the ending.¹⁹⁹ Additionally, as regards the syntactic structure, we can observe that the *côla* are not as closely interwoven as in the model of the rhetorical period: at first glance, we could even stop at the end of the first, the second, or the third *côlon* (i.e., after Ἀρίστωνος, θεῷ, or ποιήσουσιν), in the sense that such a division would still keep the coherence of the first part of the period. Given that it lacks the typical “circular” characteristics of periods, we may wonder what makes this saying a period. The periodic character is arguably ensured by the syntactic construction, which still makes clear that the four *côla* function together. Specifically, the second and the third *côla* are both subordinated to the first one due to the participle forms προσευξόμενός and βουλόμενος; the second and the third *côla* are closely linked by means of the τε ... καὶ construction; and the fourth *côlon* is then subordinated to the third one through the conjunction ἅτε (“because”).²⁰⁰ As Du Mesnil has rightly noted, these kinds of syntactic relations between the *côla* of conversational periods are precisely what distinguishes these *côla* from those of disjointed style.²⁰¹

¹⁹⁷ See *Eloc.* 12–13.

¹⁹⁸ Plato, *Republic* I,1; my translation. The division into *côla* is mine (cf. Demetrius’ comment in *Eloc.* 205).

¹⁹⁹ But cf. Innes, who argues that there is still a well-turned ending in this period, as “the participle ἄγοντες ‘bends the sentence back’ at the end to pick up its comparatively distant grammatical object ‘the festival’” (Innes, “Period and *Côlon*: Theory and Examples in Demetrius and Longinus,” 46).

²⁰⁰ Alternatively, ἅτε could be understood as a relative pronoun referring to τὴν ἑορτὴν: “... the festival / which they were celebrating for the first time.” But even in this case, the fourth *côlon* would keep a causal function—given by the participle form of the verb ἄγοντες—so that it would be impossible to separate it from what has gone before.

²⁰¹ Du Mesnil, “Begriff der drei Kunstformen der Rede,” 85. On the characteristics of *côla* of disjointed style, see above, sections 3.1.3 to 3.1.4.

Finally, the historical period, which is presented as a blend of the two others, possesses an intermediate degree of circularity: it should be “neither too carefully rounded, nor too loose, but between the two.” The example is a dicôloi period: Δαρείου καὶ Παρυσάτιδος γίνονται παῖδες / πρεσβύτερος μὲν Ἄρταξέρξης, νεώτερος δὲ Κῦρος.²⁰² From a strictly syntactic point of view, each cōlon could stand on its own. This time, there is no strict syntactic dependency, even if the second cōlon lacks a verb and if πρεσβύτερος and νεώτερος are to be understood relative to παῖδες. What, then, makes this saying a period? We can note two points. First, we can say that something more is expected after the first cōlon, as the information that Darius and Parysatis had sons logically necessitates that it be completed with additional information regarding the number and/or the names of those sons.²⁰³ Second, as Demetrius mentions, this period exhibits a “firm and securely based ending”: this arguably refers to the rhythmical clausula (Νεώτερος δὲ Κῦρος: u–u–u– –), where the final two long syllables give stability to the ending.²⁰⁴

To sum up, “circularity” is a characteristic that can be more or less present in periods. Therefore, we have to accept the peculiar idea that some periods are “more periodic” than others, if we refer to the circular connotation of περίοδος. Specifically, rhetorical periods are “highly circular”: these are the periods *par excellence*, the ideal periods—remember that, in the definition of the period in §10, it was a rhetorical period that was provided as an illustration.²⁰⁵ The circular character of historical periods is already less obvious, even if it is still present. Conversational periods are “barely circular,” to the point that they resemble disjointed style. How Aristotle might have regarded the Demetrian conversational periods? The author of the *Rhetoric* would perhaps—I would even say would *probably*—have rejected such loose structures as being part of the sewn *lexis*, as they exhibit none of the Gorgianic figures, nor any other feature that would clearly mark their extremities.²⁰⁶ To put it another way, Demetrius’

²⁰² Xen., *Anab.* I. This is the second use of this example in the treatise; see *Eloc.* 2–3.

²⁰³ In this regard, it is interesting to note that Demetrius omits the precision δύο that was initially present in this extract: Δαρείου καὶ Παρυσάτιδος γίνονται παῖδες δύο.

²⁰⁴ I follow here a suggestion advanced by P. Chiron, *Du Style*, 90, n. 32; cf. Id., *Un rhéteur méconnu*, 271.

²⁰⁵ We may think that even the definition of the period in *Eloc.* 10 itself consists of a rhetorical period (made of two cōla), since the sense is left suspended up to the final word: ἔστιν γὰρ ἡ περίοδος σύστημα ἐκ κώλων ἢ κομμάτων εὐκαταστροφῶν / πρὸς τὴν διάνοιαν τὴν ὑποκειμένην ἀπηρτισμένον. The placement of ἀπηρτισμένον at the very end not only emphasises the very idea of correspondence between the thought and the formulation, but also provides a typical example of how this correspondence can be achieved: in this case, it is achieved by means of the delay of a key element up to the end. In other words, the Demetrian definition of the period is an instance of “hidden theory” (on this notion, see D. C. Innes, “Period and Cōlon,” 45–48).

²⁰⁶ Cf. Aristotle’s doctrine on the period, *Rhet.* III,9.

account on the period suggests that he works with a much broader definition than that of Aristotle.

3.2.6. *Gorgianic figures of speech*

Following the conclusion to his discussion on the three kinds of periods, Demetrius turns to the so-called Gorgianic figures of speech.²⁰⁷ The transition is somewhat abrupt: “There are thus these different kinds of periods. There are also periods which are formed of opposed *côla* ... There are also similar *côla* ...”²⁰⁸ The discussion consists merely of a paraphrase of Aristotle, and most of the examples are the same as in the *Rhetoric*.²⁰⁹ Concerning *antithesis*, Demetrius specifies that the opposition can reside either in the content or in the language, or sometimes in a combination of the two. Moreover, he mentions the existence of “false antithesis”, that is, when “*côla* are not antithetical but suggest an antithesis owing to the antithetical form in which they are written.”²¹⁰ Similarities in sound—corresponding to Aristotle’s *paromoiosis*—and similarity in length—corresponding to Aristotle’s *pariosis*—are presented as two variations of “similar *côla*” (παρόμοια κῶλα). Equality of syllables is also called *isocôlon*. From the example provided (ὡς οὔτε ὧν πυνθάνονται ἀπαξιούντων τὸ ἔργον / οἷς τε ἐπιμελὲς εἶη εἰδέναι οὐκ ὀνειδιζόντων),²¹¹ it is clear that equality has to be understood in an approximative manner. The number of syllables does not need to be strictly identical; in the above example the *côla* comprise 16 and 17 syllables respectively.

With respect to the use of these Gorgianic figures, Demetrius seems less enthusiastic than Aristotle. While he admits that Gorgianic figures are useful in some cases,²¹² he insists that “the use of such *côla* is full of risk.”²¹³ Specifically, the risk is that their overdone, artificial look dissipates the force of emotions and therefore destroys the vehemence of the speech.²¹⁴ This reluctance might partly explain the abrupt transition between the typology of periods (§19–21) and the discussion on Gorgianic figures (§22–29). As an alternative or complementary explanation for this abrupt

²⁰⁷ *Eloc.* 22–29. On the terminology “Gorgianic figures,” see above, n. 68.

²⁰⁸ Περίοδων μὲν εἶδη τοσάδε. Γίνονται δὲ καὶ ἐξ ἀντικειμένων κῶλων περίοδοι ... Ἔστι δὲ καὶ παρόμοια κῶλα ... (*Eloc.* 21–25)

²⁰⁹ Cf. Arist., *Rhet.* III,9,7–10.

²¹⁰ *Eloc.* 24; cf. a close remark in Arist., *Rhet.* III,9,10.

²¹¹ “Since neither do those who are questioned disown the deed / nor do those who are concerned to know censure it.” (Thucyd., *Pelop.*, 1,5,3, quoted by Demetrius in *Eloc.* 25).

²¹² *Eloc.* 29.

²¹³ *Eloc.* 27.

²¹⁴ *Eloc.* 27. See also §247.

transition, we may assume that Demetrius does not have a clear idea of how Gorgianic figures relate to the issue of circularity, such that he chooses to treat them in a disconnected way from the development that precedes.

3.2.7. *Rhythm*

Regarding the use of rhythms in prose, Demetrius remains close to the Aristotelean doctrine of the paeon.²¹⁵ It should be noted, however, that his recommendations are found within a discussion of “grand style,” such that they cannot be assumed to apply to prose in general. Demetrius recommends avoiding the dactyle, which is too noble for prose,²¹⁶ and the iambe, which is too commonplace.²¹⁷ The most appropriate foot is the paeon: the first paeon at the beginning, and the fourth paeon at the end.²¹⁸ Here Demetrius makes clear that the extremities at stake are not only those of periods, but also those of *côla*.²¹⁹ It is also specified that paeons do not need to be perfect: it is enough, Demetrius explains, to give a paeonic aspect to the discourse, “for example by placing long syllables at the beginning and at the end.”²²⁰ As an example of this paeonic aspect, he quotes the following *côlon* from Theophrastus: τῶν μὲν περὶ τὰ μηδενὸς ἄξια φιλοσοφούντων.²²¹ Here the *côlon* begins with two longs syllables followed by three short (– – uuu), and ends with three syllables followed by two long (uuu– –).

3.2.8. *Periodic côla as syntactic units*

To bring the discussion of the period to a close, let us briefly turn to the issue of the syntactic nature of periodic *côla*. In the numerous examples provided throughout the *Περὶ ἑρμηνείας*, we can note a strong tendency for *côla* to correspond to a single clause, whether a main clause or a subordinate clause. This is not an absolute rule, however. There are also a few instances where a *côlon* encompasses two clauses, as is notably the case in the second *côlon* of the model of the historical period (πρεσβύτερος μὲν Ἀρταξέρξης, νεώτερος δὲ Κῦρος) or in the third *côlon* of the model of the rhetorical period (ὠμολόγησα τούτοις, ὡς ἂν οἷός τε ᾧ, συνερεῖν [“I have agreed to speak to the

²¹⁵ *Eloc.* 38–43; cf. Arist., *Rhet.* III,8.

²¹⁶ *Eloc.* 42; cf. Arist., *Rhet.* III,8.

²¹⁷ *Eloc.* 43; cf. Arist., *Rhet.* III,8.

²¹⁸ *Eloc.* 38–39; cf. Arist., *Rhet.* III,8,5.

²¹⁹ *Eloc.* 42–43; cf. Aristotle, who was more ambiguous on this question (*Rhet.* III,8,6).

²²⁰ *Eloc.* 41.

²²¹ *Eloc.* 41; the extract is probably from Theophrastus’ *Περὶ λέξεως* (fr. VI = p. 114 Mayer).

best of my ability in their support]).²²² It also happens that a *côlon* consists of a nominal phrase where the head is a substantivized participle,²²³ as e.g. “τῶν μὲν περὶ τὰ μηδενὸς ἄξια φιλοσοφούντων [“Those who are philosophers about what is worthless”].²²⁴ In addition, there is at least one example of a prepositional phrase that is also called a *côlon* (ἐν Ἐλέᾳ τῆς Ἰταλίας [at Elea in Italy]).²²⁵ This last example clearly shows that *côla* do not systematically contain a verbal form or an implied verb.

3.3. Results

After this inquiry into Demetrius’ account on colometry, let us sum up the main elements and highlight both the continuities and the points of evolution from Aristotle. Much like Aristotle, Demetrius distinguishes between two basic kinds of style for prose, one that is periodic (“interwoven,” κατεστραμμένη) and one that is non-periodic (“disjointed,” διηρημένη, or sometimes διαλελυμένη, “loose”). However, in contrast with the author of the *Art of Rhetoric*, Demetrius does not express any preference for one of these styles, but instead recommends using both in a balanced mix. In Demetrius’ mind, the two styles in fact represent two different ways of combining the *côla* to compose the speech. In the *disjointed style*, the *côla* are juxtaposed: each of them consists of a complete thought, which could in fact be labelled a “short sentence” in modern terms in view of its semantico-syntactic autonomy. In contrast, the *côla* of *interwoven style* are closely linked, being “interwoven” to form a complete thought called a *period*. In this case, each *côlon* comprises a thought that is somewhat complete in itself, but that still needs to be completed by one or more other *côla*. On the syntactic level, this often—but not always—involves relations of dependency, whether grammatical subordination or coordination by means of pairs of particles, such as μὲν ... δέ or τε ... τε.

As concerns the length of *côla*, Demetrius seems to be more or less aligned with Aristotle: as a general rule, *côla* have approximatively the extent of a hexametre verse (i.e., 12–17 syllables). Demetrius nevertheless specifies that longer (up to around 30 syllables) or shorter *côla* are acceptable and are even welcome in specific situations. We have seen that when they are especially short (let us say under 8–9 syllables, though

²²² See above, section 3.2.5.

²²³ Cf. also in this sense Habinek, *The Colometry of Latin Prose*, 29–30.

²²⁴ *Eloc.* 41; see above, n. 221.

²²⁵ *Eloc.* 182. The following saying is explicitly described as being composed of two *côla*: ἐν Ἐλέᾳ τῆς Ἰταλίας / πρεσβύτη δὴ τὴν ἡλικίαν ὄντι.

the boundary seems to be porous), *côla* are given the special name of *commata*, lit. “cut off pieces.”

Regarding periods, Demetrius departs from Aristotle’s binary vision by extending the acceptable length to four *côla*.²²⁶ Beyond the issue of length, the *Περὶ ἑρμηνείας* also testifies to a decisive development in the theory of the period, one that concerns the very definition of this notion. Crucially, the metaphor of a race, which was already rooted in Aristotle, is developed further by referring to the original meaning of the term *περίοδος* (“way around”): Demetrius compares the period to a *circular race*. Such a metaphor then allows him to extend the definition of the period by introducing the idea that periods can be more or less “circular.” As we have seen, Demetrius addresses the issue of the boundary between the periodic and the non-periodic style, and proposes an intermediate style made of “conversational periods.” The conversational period is described as “loose and simple, to the point that it scarcely shows that it is a period.”²²⁷ Such a loose period would obviously never enter into Aristotle’s strict definition of the period, provided that it does not have *an end in itself*: in other words, the author of the *Rhetoric* would arguably have rejected “conversational periods” as belonging to the non-periodic *lexis*. Significantly, when Demetrius refers to the Aristotelean definition,²²⁸ the latter is quoted only partially, the crucial characteristic of the “end in itself” being omitted. This also partly explains why the Aristotelean terminology for the non-periodic style, *εἰρομένη* (“continuous” or “sewn”), is changed into *διηρημένη* (“disjointed”): the two rhetoricians simply do not place the boundary between the two styles at exactly the same place. To put it another way, Demetrius works with a much broader conception of the period, one that is closer to our modern concept of the sentence—even if the concept of the period remains more codified than what is usually meant by a “sentence.”

4. *Rhetoric for Herennius (Rhetorica ad Herennium [Rhet. Her.] — 80s BCE)*²²⁹

Formerly attributed to Cicero itself, but in fact constituting the work of an unknown author, the *Rhetorica ad Herennium* is the oldest surviving Latin book on rhetoric,²³⁰

²²⁶ Demetrius is fully aware that he departs from Aristotle on this point; see *Eloc.* 34.

²²⁷ *Eloc.* 21.

²²⁸ *Eloc.* 11; cf. Arist., *Rhet.* III,9,5.

²²⁹ *Rhetorica ad Herennium* (trans. H. Caplan, based on the Latin text established by F. Marx; LCL; 1954). The translations below are mine; at certain places they are influenced by that of Caplan.

²³⁰ For a general introduction to the *Rhetoric for Herennius*, see H. Caplan, “Introduction,” vii–xliv; cf. G. A. Kennedy, *A New History of Classical Rhetoric*, 121–127; R. L. Enos, “*Rhetorica ad Herennium*.”

generally dated to between 86 and 82 BCE.²³¹ The treatise, which is dedicated to an unknown Gaius Herennius, comprises four volumes and covers the five canons of rhetoric in a highly structured form and with abundant detail. The elements of style (*elocutio*) are found in book IV. In this volume, the author begins by justifying at length why the presentation is illustrated by models composed by him- or herself—a choice that indeed departs from the Greek tradition of quoting extracts from classical literature. He or she then presents the three “types” or “levels” of style (*genera dicendi*) that would later become traditional in rhetoric: the grand style, the middle style, and the simple style. Then comes a long discussion on figures of speech: it is within this development, specifically in chapter 19, that the definitions of the *membrum* (= cōlon), the *articulus* (= comma) and the *continuatō* (= period) are found.²³²

A somewhat surprising point is that these three technical terms barely appear in the treatise outside the passages where they are defined.²³³ This might be attributed to the fact that it was still very early in the use of these terms to describe Latin prose, such that the author *ad Herennium* may not have been used to employing them to discuss the structure of texts.²³⁴ In any case, the result is that many of the examples are open to considerable interpretation. It is also somewhat confusing that the author does not discuss the internal structure of *continuationes* in terms of *membra* and *articuli*, meaning that we cannot be completely sure that he or she would agree with using this terminology to designate the parts of *continuationes*. In the discussion below, I will

²³¹ This date reflects the political events mentioned in the treatise, the latest being the references to Sulpicius’ tribunate of 88 (*Rhet. Her.* I,15) and Gaius Marius’ seventh consulship in 86 BCE (G. Achard, “Introduction,” vi–xiii; cf. G. A. Kennedy, *A New History of Classical Rhetoric*, 122; Caplan, “Introduction” [*Rhetorica ad Herennium*], XXVI). Note, however, that the anteriority of the *Rhetoric ad Herennium* over Cicero’s rhetoric treatises has recently been called into question by W. Stroh, *Die Macht der Rede. Eine kleine Geschichte der Rhetorik im alten Griechenland und Rom*, who suggests that the *Rhetoric for Herennius* would in fact be based on Cicero’s *De Oratore* (see esp. pages 359–361).

²³² There seems to have debates among rhetoricians as to whether cōla, commata and periods should themselves be classified as figures: see e.g. Quintilian, who lists the *membrum* and the *articulus* among items that are sometimes regarded as figures, but which, from his point of view, “are not figures at all” (Quint., *Inst.* IX,3,98).

²³³ Apart from the contexts of their respective definitions (*Rhet. Her.* IV,19,26–27), *membrum* appears also in IV,20,27; *continuatō* appears also in III,13,23, IV,12,18 and IV,32,42; *articulus* appears nowhere else.

²³⁴ The fact that Cicero, in the middle of the 1st century BCE, discusses the appropriate Latin translation for the Greek words κῶλον, περίοδος and κόμμα (Cic. *Or. Brut.* 204; 208; 211; 223) indeed suggests that the formal use of these notions to analyse Latin prose was quite new.

nevertheless make use of the terms “membrum” and “articulus” to refer to the subparts of *continuationes*, by analogy with what is found in later Latin rhetoricians.²³⁵

4.1. *Membrum* (= *côlon*)

4.1.1 *Definition*

In chapter 19, the author begins by presenting the *membrum*, which is the Latin equivalent to the Greek κῶλον²³⁶:

Membrum is the name given to an element that is brief and complete, but which does not express the entire thought [*sententia*], and which is in turn supplemented by another membrum, as follows: “on the one hand you were helping your enemy” [*et inimico proderas*]. That is one so-called membrum. It ought then to be supplemented by a second: “and on the other you were hurting your friend” [*et amicum laedebas*]. This figure can consist of two membra, but it is neatest and most complete when composed of three, as follows: “You were helping your enemy / you were hurting your friend / and you were not consulting your own best interests” [*Et inimico proderas / et amicum laedebas / et tibi non consulebas*]. Again: “You have not consulted the welfare of the republic, nor have you helped your friends, nor have you resisted your enemies [*Nec rei publicae consuluisti / nec amicis profuisti / nec inimicis restitisti*].”²³⁷

The membrum has the double characteristic of being at the same time “brief” and “complete.” This completeness, however, does not encompass the entire thought (*sententia*): for this reason, our author explains, a membrum needs to be supplemented by a second, or better, a second and a third membra. Of course, the question arises as to whether such combinations of membra are considered periods—or, to use the terminology of the treatise, whether these combinations should be regarded as *continuationes*, or if they rather succeed one another outside any periodic structure. The least that can be said is that our author is not very clear concerning the status of the examples given, such that the two interpretations are equally plausible.

In support of the interpretation of the above combinations as periods, it can be argued that the definition of the membrum is close to the Demetrian description of periodic *côla*. Demetrius indeed explained that the *côlon* that belongs to a period is somewhat complete, but that it needs to be supplemented by one or more other *côla* in order to express the complete thought.²³⁸ Crucially, it can be noted that Demetrius,

²³⁵ Both Cicero and Quintilian mention the term *continuatio* as an equivalent to the Greek περίοδος (Cic., *Or. Brut.* 204; Quint., *Inst.* IX,4,124); both of them also make explicit that periods are made of several *membra*.

²³⁶ The original meaning of the Greek and Latin terms is the same, that is, “a limb,” and by extension “a member” or “a distinct part of a whole.” Cf. Cicero, *Or. Brut.* 223, where the correspondence between the Greek *côlon* and the Latin *membrum* is explicitly affirmed.

²³⁷ *Rhet. Her.* IV,19,27.

²³⁸ Dem., *Eloc.* 2–3; cf. § 10 and § 19.

when first describing the possibility of combining many *côla* to form a complete thought, did not use the word *περίοδος* to designate the resulting combination: the equivalence between, on the one hand, a combination of *côla* that together form a complete thought and, on the other hand, a period, was made explicit only later in the treatise.²³⁹ Thus, we may think that the author *ad Herennium* works with the same logic. In support of the view that the two above models of combined *membra* do form *continuationes*, it can also be noted that they exhibit approximative equality in length (a figure the author calls *conpar*)²⁴⁰ as well as sound echoes at their extremities (in the first example: *et ... eras / et ... ebas / et ... ebas* ; in the second example: *nec ... uisti / nec ... uisti / nec... isti*). As we have seen in Aristotle and Demetrius—not to mention later rhetoricians—these figures are typically used in periods.²⁴¹ We may add that the above combinations of *membra* could be understood as instances of “false antitheses,”²⁴² provided that “helping your enemy” and “hurting your friend,” on the one hand, as well as “not helping your friends” and “not resisting your enemies,” on the other hand, seem to be opposed, owing to their language, but in fact convey the same idea. And our author precisely mentions “contrasts” (*contraria*) as one of the typical contexts where *continuationes* are to be used.²⁴³

That being said, the opposite understanding is also defensible, especially in view of the fact that each of the *membra* above could stand on its own as a short sentence. Each *membrum* indeed consists of an independent clause, which is reminiscent of Demetrius’ non-periodic style.²⁴⁴ It is also unclear whether the author *ad Herennium* would personally consider the above sayings as instances of “contrasts,” since the models he or she provides to illustrate the figure of *contrarium* are all quite different: specifically, the models of contrasts exhibit syntactic dependency between their two opposed parts.²⁴⁵ Furthermore, that the period as conceived by our author typically involves syntactic dependency between its *membra* appears clearly if we review the models of periods he or she gives (see below, section 4.3.1). In addition, we may note that our author does not use the technical term *continuatio* in the context of the discussions

²³⁹ Dem., *Eloc.* 10; cf. §19.

²⁴⁰ *Rhet. Her.* IV, 20. The concept of *conpar* in the *Rhetoric for Herennius* perfectly concurs with Aristotle’s *παρίσωσις* (Arist., *Rhet.* III,9,7) and with Demetrius’ *ισόκωλον* (Dem., *Eloc.* 25).

²⁴¹ See Arist., *Rhet.* III,9,7–10; Dem., *Eloc.* 22–26.

²⁴² On false antithesis, see Arist., *Rhet.* III,9,10; cf. Dem., *Eloc.* 24.

²⁴³ See *Rhet. Her.* IV,19,27.

²⁴⁴ That these combinations of *membra* are of non-periodic style (“style coupé”) is advanced, e.g., in the edition by M. Nisard, *Rhétorique, à C. Herennius*, 86. On Demetrius’ disjointed style, see *Eloc.* 12–14.

²⁴⁵ See examples in *Rhet. Her.* IV,18,26; cf. also the model provided in 19,27.

concerning equality in length and sound echoes,²⁴⁶ such that the link *ad Herennium* personally establishes between the use of pariosis and paromoiosis and the notion of period is unclear. All in all, the question raised above seems to be irresolvable.

4.1.2 Length

As concerns the length of membra, the author *ad Herennium* seems to be fully in line with Demetrius. Membra have extremely various lengths: based only on those examples where the membra are easily identified—i.e., when two or more membra are built according to obvious parallelisms—we can state that they range from 6 up to almost 30 syllables.²⁴⁷ Note that the shortest of them would probably be better called *commata*, or, to use the terminology of the treatise, *articuli*.

4.2. *Articulus* (= *comma*)

Immediately after the definition of the membrum, the author continues with the unit he or she calls *articulus*. The discussion runs as follows:

It is called articulus when single words are set apart by pauses [*intervallis*] in staccato speech [*caesa oratione*], as follows: “by your vigour / voice / looks / you have terrified your adversaries” [*acrimonia / voce / vultu / adversarios perterruisti*]. Again: “your enemies by jealousy / injuries / influence / and perfidy / you have destroyed” [*Inimicos invidia / iniuriis / potentia / perfidia / sustulisti*]. There is this difference between the last sort [i.e., the articulus] and the one preceding [i.e., the membrum]: the former moves upon its object more slowly and less often, the latter strikes more quickly and frequently. Hence, in the first category it seems that the arm draws back and the hand whirls about to bring the sword to the adversary’s body, while in the second his body is as it were pierced with quick and repeated thrusts.²⁴⁸

Articuli are very short units, composed of one or two words. That the articulus is a sort of short membrum is made clear by the fact that our author is careful to specify the difference between the two units. The author explains the difference in terms of the

²⁴⁶ Some translations supply the word “period” in the discussion on sound echoes (*Rhet. Her.* IV,20,28); see e.g. Caplan, *Rhetorica ad Herennium*, 299 (“The figure called Homoeoptoton occurs when in the same period [*in eadem constructione verborum*] two or more words appear in the same case, and with like terminations”); cf. H. Bornecque, *Rhétorique à Herennius* (“L’ornement du style est dit à désinences casuelles semblables, lorsque, dans une même période [*in eadem constructione verborum*], on emploie deux ou plusieurs mots de même cas et de désinence semblable”). This is indeed a possible understanding of the expression *constructio verborum*, but the author does not explicitly affirm that this expression designates here the *continuatio*.

²⁴⁷ Short membra are found e.g. in *Rhet. Her.* IV,20,28; for long members, see *Rhet. Her.* IV,22,31.

²⁴⁸ *Rhet. Her.* IV,19,27.

impact on the audience, using the metaphor of a sword fight: whereas the membrum is comparable to a well-prepared hit (the arm draws back, the hand whirls), the effect of articuli is like quick and repeated stabs that pierce the body.²⁴⁹ This description is clearly reminiscent of the Demetrian notion of the comma as being a very short cōlon, the use of which invests the discourse with vehemence.²⁵⁰

Here again, we may ask whether the above combinations of several articuli can be called periods.²⁵¹ This time, in the two examples at hand, the articuli are syntactically dependent on each other. The two examples even have the verb at the end, such that the thoughts are made intelligible only with the final words (respectively *perterruisti* [“you have terrified”] and *sustulisti* [“you have destroyed”]). In view of these characteristics, Demetrius would certainly regard these examples as periods, and the same arguably holds true also for Aristotle²⁵²—as well as for most of the later rhetoricians. It is also likely that the author *ad Herennium* would approve of such a classification,²⁵³ as syntactic dependency seems to play a key role in his or her conception of the *continuatio*, as we shall see below.

4.3. *Continuatio* (= period)

4.3.1. Definition and examples

Let us now turn to the definition of the period (*continuatio*), which appears immediately after that of the membrum and the articulus. Our author specifies that periods should not be used everywhere: they are especially recommended to express a “maxim” [*sententia*], a “contrast” [*contrarium*], or a “conclusion” [*conclusio*], even if their use is not restricted to these contexts. This remark of course echoes the division between the periodic and the non-periodic style that was established by Aristotle and Demetrius; however, the author *ad Herennium* does not theorise such a distinction as particularly crucial, and nowhere does he or she discuss or propose a term to designate the non-periodic style. Rather, the author seems to consider the *continuatio* as a figure of speech

²⁴⁹ See a similar image in Cic., *Or. Brut.* 224.

²⁵⁰ Dem., *Eloc.* 7–9.

²⁵¹ Note that some translations supply the term “period” in this context, e.g. Nisard, *Rhétorique*, à C. Hérennius, 60: “On appelle Article chacun des mots qui sont séparés par des repos, et qui coupent la période.”

²⁵² I think that Aristotle would consider those sayings to be monocōlon periods, as they possess “ends in themselves” by means of the placement of the verbs at the end. See Arist., *Rhet.* III,9,3.

²⁵³ See the similar conclusion of M. Heckenkamp, “Περίοδος und *continuatio*: Der Wandel der Metaphorik und der Konzeption der Periode von Aristoteles zu Cicero,” 158.

whose usage is linked to specific contents. Below are the definition and the associated examples:

A *continuatio* is a dense and uninterrupted group of words embracing a complete thought [*densa et continens frequentatio verborum cum absolute sententiarum*]. We shall use it best in three places: in a maxim [*sententia*], in a contrast [*contrarium*], and in a conclusion [*conclusio*]. In a maxim as follows: “Fortune cannot much harm the one who has built his support more firmly upon virtue than upon chance” [*Ei non multum potest obesse fortuna qui sibi firmiter in virtute quam in casu praesidium conlocavit*]. In a contrast, as follows: “For if a person has not placed much hope in chance / what great harm can chance do him?” [*Nam si qui spei non multum conlocarit in casu / quid est quod ei magnopere casus obesse possit?*]. In a conclusion, as follows: “But if Fortune has her greatest power over those who have committed all their plans to chance / we should not entrust our all with Fortune / lest she gain too great a domination over us” [*Quodsi in eos plurimum fortuna potest qui suas rationes omnes in casum contulerunt / non sunt omnia committenda fortunae / ne magnam nimis in nos habeat dominationem*]. But in other cases as well it is often proper, although not imperative, to express certain thoughts by means of *continuationes* of this sort.²⁵⁴

This definition refers to different categories. First, with respect to semantics, the period consists of a complete thought [*sententia*], in the sense of a thought that does not need the support of any other saying. Then, the remark that a period is “a dense and uninterrupted group of words” may refer at the same time to syntax and to prosody. As to syntax, we can note that the three examples provided are constructed in such a way that it is impossible to stop before the end. In other words, the “*membra*” that compose these periods—assuming that this terminology is appropriate—depend on each other, such that stopping before the end would result in the incompleteness of the resulting parts. This remark also holds true for the majority of the examples of “contrasts,”²⁵⁵ the majority of the examples of “maxims,”²⁵⁶ and also the other example of a “conclusion” found later in the treatise.²⁵⁷ The description of the period as “a dense and uninterrupted group of words” may at the same time refer to prosody, namely to the idea that periods are to be delivered as utterances, in a single prosodic movement. In view of the examples given, this description cannot entail that there is no break at all within a period. It rather suggests that there are no strong breaks, i.e., no breaks that interrupt the flow of speech. In fact, if we take the third example given above, we can note that it is almost impossible to utter this entire saying without taking a breath at some point, owing to its length of nearly 60 syllables. In any case, it is impossible to pronounce it without some silences where the speaker can, at least, rest a little bit.

²⁵⁴ *Rhet. Her.* IV,19,27.

²⁵⁵ *Rhet. Her.* IV,18.

²⁵⁶ *Rhet. Her.* IV,17.

²⁵⁷ *Rhet. Her.* IV,30,41.

Moreover, from a semantic point of view, some breaks are necessary to underline the main articulations: namely, after *contulerunt* and *fortuna*, places that arguably correspond to the boundaries between the *membra*.

4.3.2. Length

The author *ad Herennium* expressly recommends that periods should not be too long. This would, he or she states, constitute a vice of composition: “One should likewise avoid a long period [*longam verborum continuationem*], which does violence both to the ear of the listener and to the breathing of the speaker.”²⁵⁸ Such a warning is based on pragmatic reasons related to the habits of reading aloud. No precise limit is given, however, either in terms of the number of syllables or the number of *membra*. The matter is further complicated by the fact that very few sayings are explicitly identified as *continuations* in the treatise. As concerns the number of syllables, if we consider only the three models that directly illustrate the definition, we can state with certainty that our author accepts *at least* periods between 30 (the model of “maxim”) and 60 syllables (the model of “conclusion”). Previously in the treatise are some examples of maxims that are shorter, around 20 syllables, and also one which has only 9 syllables. But the question arises as to whether such a short saying still forms part of the category of *continuat*o.²⁵⁹ As to the maximum length, another example found elsewhere in the treatise has around 60 syllables,²⁶⁰ but there is no example that extends beyond this limit. What about the number of members? Provided that our analysis is correct, it seems that our author recognises *at least* periods with one single *membrum* (e.g., the model of maxim above²⁶¹), with two *membra* (e.g., the model of contrast above²⁶²), and with three *membra* (e.g., the model of “conclusion” above²⁶³).

²⁵⁸ *Rhet. Her.* IV,12,18.

²⁵⁹ See the development on maxims in *Rhet. Her.*, IV,17.

²⁶⁰ *Rhet. Her.* IV,30,41. This example also consists of a “conclusion.”

²⁶¹ But cf. H. C. Gotoff, “The Concept of Periodicity in the *Ad Herennium*,” 222, who regards the model of a maxim as made of two members (with a division between *fortuna* and *qui*). In *Rhet. Her.* IV,17, there are many other instances of maxims that can be analysed as monocôlon periods.

²⁶² More examples comprising two members are found in the development on “contrasts” (*Rhet. Her.* IV,18).

²⁶³ See *Rhet. Her.* IV,30,41 for a second example of a “conclusion” that can also be analysed in three members. But cf. H. Caplan (*Rhetorica ad Herennium*, 297, n. c), who takes the model of *conclusio* in IV,19 as a tetracôlon period. Cf. also H. C. Gotoff, “The Concept of Periodicity in the *Ad Herennium*,” 222, who argues that this model presents a bipartite structure.

4.4. Results

In view of the descriptions and examples of the *membrum*, *articulus* and *continuatio* found in the *Rhetoric for Herennius*, it appears that these three notions correspond, at least in the main lines, to the Demetrian colon, comma, and period. The *membrum* is a short unit of thought that can reach, at its maximum length, around 30 syllables. The *articulus* is a shorter unit, often comprising one single word, and whose usage brings vehemence to the speech. As concerns the *continuatio*, its description as a “dense and uninterrupted group of words embracing a complete thought” is also reminiscent of the description Demetrius gives for the period, especially in view of the key idea of the correspondence between a formulation and a complete thought. Specifically, the different examples given by the author *ad Herennium* recall the Demetrian “rhetorical” period,²⁶⁴ where the syntactic construction means that the thought is left in the air until the final word. As to the maximum length of periods, the author *ad Herennium* also follows Demetrius in breaking with Aristotle’s binary vision and very restricted length: precisely, he or she extends the acceptable length to at least 3 members and around 60 syllables. However, nowhere does the author discuss what are the minimal characteristics that a saying needs to possess in order to warranting being called “*continuatio*”—perhaps he or she would not even consider this question to be relevant—such that we cannot evaluate to what extent his or her doctrine of the period is in line with that of Demetrius.

5. Cicero, *On the Orator (De oratore [De or.] – 55 BCE); Orator (Orator ad Brutum [Or. Brut.] – 46 BCE)*²⁶⁵

From the Roman orator, statesman, lawyer and philosopher Marcus Tullius Cicero (106–43 BCE), there survives a large body of speeches, as well as an extensive collection

²⁶⁴ Cf. Dem., *Eloc.* 20.

²⁶⁵ *On the Orator, Book 3. On Fate. Stoic Paradoxes. Divisions of Oratory* (ed. and trans. H. Rackam; based on the Latin text established by V. Bétolaud; LCL; 1942); *Brutus. Orator* (ed. and trans. H. M. Hubbell; LCL; 1939). The translations below are mine, based on the Latin text presented in these editions. However, at certain places my translation is strongly influenced by that of H. Rackham and H. M. Hubbell. Cicero is the ancient orator to have received the greatest attention when it comes to the study of colometry. For examples of colometric arrangements of Cicero’s speeches, see W. Schmid, *Über die Klassische Theorie und Praxis des antiken Prosarhythmus*, 162–203, which contains a colometric layout, with indication of rhythms, of Cicero’s *Sixth Phillipic*; C. J. Robbins, “A Colometric Arrangement of Cicero”, which offers a colometric layout of Cicero’s *Third Oration Against Catiline*; B. Sträterhoff, *Kolometrie und Prosarhythmus bei Cicero und Livius*, which contains a colometric layout of Cicero’s *De imperio Cn. Pompei*. The aspect of the Ciceronian colometry that has attracted the most scholarly attention is the use of metrical feet: see below, footnote 281.

of letters and some twenty philosophical and rhetorical treatises.²⁶⁶ Elements concerning cōla (*membra*), commata (*incisa* or *caesa*) and periods (for which different terminologies are used: *ambitus*, *circuitus*, *comprehensio*, *continuatio*, *circumscriptio*) are mainly found in two different treatises: in the third volume of the *De Oratore*, dated to 55 BCE,²⁶⁷ and in the *Orator ad Brutum*, dated 46 BCE.²⁶⁸ The first takes the creative form of a dialogue featuring prominent orators of the preceding generation (Antonius, Crassus, Scaevola, Catulus, and Strabo) talking with two promising young orators (Sulpicius and Cotta). The second work adopts the more traditional form of a treatise: it is an attempt to describe the perfect orator, in response to Marcus Junius Brutus' request. Much like the author *ad Herennium*, Cicero uses mainly contemporary examples of his own creation; that being said, he abundantly and explicitly builds on the theories of his Greek predecessors, discussing, for example, the appropriate Latin translations of the Greek terms περίοδος, κῶλον, and κόμμα.²⁶⁹

5.1. *Periodic vs non-periodic style*

Cicero distinguishes between two kinds of style for prose texts. The first comprises short independent units, called *membra* and *incisa* (or occasionally *caesa*), and is referred to with the expression “speak in *incisa* and *membra*” or simply “speak in *membra*.”²⁷⁰ In the second kind of style, by contrast, several *membra* and/or *incisa* are grouped in order to form periods. It is clear that the distinction between these two styles plays a crucial role in the Ciceronian conception of prose, even though Cicero shows little interest in discussing the boundary between them. Cicero follows Demetrius in validating both the periodic and the non-periodic style.²⁷¹ In his view, each style is appropriate to specific literary genres: the periodic style for the epideictic genre, as well as for works of history, while the judicial and the deliberative genres require the alternation of periods and independent *membra* and/or *incisa*.²⁷²

²⁶⁶ On Cicero's life and work, see G. A. Kennedy, *The Art of Rhetoric in the Roman World*, 149–282; cf. also R. L. Enos, “Marcus Tullius Cicero,” 101–110.

²⁶⁷ G. A. Kennedy, *The Art of Rhetoric in the Roman World*, 205.

²⁶⁸ R. L. Enos, “Marcus Tullius Cicero,” 108. Some changes in Cicero's thought may be observed between the *De oratore* and the *Orator*: on this topic, see e.g. P. Laurens, “Cicéron, maître de la *breuitas*,” 29–41.

²⁶⁹ *Or. Brut.* 204; 208; 211; 223.

²⁷⁰ See e.g. *Or. Brut.* 212 and *ibid.*, 222.

²⁷¹ See e.g. *De or.* III, 191–192.

²⁷² *Or. Brut.* 207–211.

5.2. *Periods*

5.2.1. *The metaphor of the circle*

The metaphor of the circle that was widely used by Demetrius when describing periods is also strongly present in Cicero. Among the five different Latin terms he mentions as possible translations for the Greek περίοδος (*ambitus*, *circuitus*, *comprehensio*, *continuatio*, *circumscriptio*),²⁷³ three bear the notion of the circle: *ambitus* means “cycle, circuit, orbit,” or, if the participle origin is retained, “encircled”; *circuitus* has a close meaning (“circuit, revolution, cycle”); and *circumscriptio* designates either a circle or its outline and, by extension, a circumference or a boundary. Cicero also refers to periods with expressions such as “circuit of words” (*verborum ambitus*)²⁷⁴ and “rounded form of expression” (*circuitus orationis*).²⁷⁵ He even explains that in periods, the language “runs on as if enclosed in a circle” (*tanquam in orbe inclusa currat oratio*).²⁷⁶ Commenting on the style appropriate to history and epideictic oratory, he writes:

... in history and epideictic oratory, it is desirable to have everything done in the style of Isocrates and Theopompus, that is, in delimited and rounded sayings, so that the language runs on as if enclosed in a circle until it comes to an end with each saying complete and perfect.²⁷⁷

In view of this comment, it seems that the typical periodic tour is one where sayings have a clear outline that evokes the contour of a circle, as well as a certain speed or rhythm that is comparable to the movement of a race. Cicero is here very close to the Demetrian metaphor of a circular race.²⁷⁸ The question now arises as to what concretely gives periods a clear outline and a certain speed. Cicero does not provide an exhaustive answer to this question. Based on the examples he proposes, we can mention the placement of the main verb at the very end of periods.²⁷⁹ This phenomenon, which we already observed in Demetrius and in the *Rhetorica ad Herennium*,²⁸⁰ not only makes the end of periods easy to identify—as the thought and the formulation end together—but

²⁷³ *Or. Brut.* 204; cf. also *ibid.*, 208. For a list of the occurrences of the different terms in Cicero, see H. Bornecque, “Comment Cicéron rend le mot grec περίοδος”; cf. the discussion in W. Stegemann, “Ciceros Ausdrücke für περίοδος und ihre griechischen Äquivalente.” Note that according to M. Heckenkamp, the term *continuatio* in Cicero does not always function as an equivalent to περίοδος (“Περίοδος und *continuatio*: Der Wandel der Metaphorik und der Konzeption der Periode von Aristoteles zu Cicero,” 151–155).

²⁷⁴ *De or.* III, 186.

²⁷⁵ *Or. Brut.*, 204.

²⁷⁶ *Or. Brut.*, 207.

²⁷⁷ *Or. Brut.*, 207.

²⁷⁸ *Dem., Eloc.* II.

²⁷⁹ See also Du Mesnil, “Begriff der drei Kunstformen der Rede,” 46.

²⁸⁰ *Dem., Eloc.* II; cf. §17 and §20; *Rhet. Her.* IV, 19, 27.

also gives periods the appearance of a race, as the delay of the verb up to the end creates a form of suspense. Another feature that seems to play a crucial role is rhythm (*numerus*), which Cicero understands in a broad sense.

5.2.2. *Rhythm*²⁸¹

In Cicero's view, the presence of rhythm (*numerus*) is a key characteristic of periods.²⁸² Rhythm can be considered the way in which the period "runs" towards its end; or, to use Cicero's formulation, we can say that the period "is carried along by the rhythm in a vigorous movement until it comes to the end and stops."²⁸³ In this context, *numerus* is not restricted to metrical feet, but should rather be understood in a broad sense: "prose becomes rhythmical, not only by the use of metrical feet [*numeri*], but also because of the arrangement of words and a kind of symmetry."²⁸⁴ With the expression "arrangement of words" (*compositio*), Cicero expresses the idea that word order can produce a kind of natural rhythm, without any apparent effort on the part of the orator. As to the "kind of symmetry" (*concinnitas*), it refers to the different symmetrical effects created by the use of the so-called Gorgianic figures of speech (antithesis, equality in length, and sound echoes).²⁸⁵

In a narrow sense (i.e., in the sense of metrical feet), *numeri* should not be present in all places. Using metrical feet in an excessive manner would indeed make prose too similar to poetry, a lapse in taste Cicero warns against: "It is clear, then, that prose should be bound or restricted by rhythm, but that it should not contain actual verses."²⁸⁶ Specifically, metrical feet are encouraged at the beginning and even more at the end of periods; when at the end, Cicero specifies that *numeri* can be spread over the

²⁸¹ Cicero's theory on metrical feet in prose as well as the use of rhythms in his own speeches and letters has been extensively studied. Classical studies on the topic include H. Bornecque, *La prose métrique dans la correspondance de Cicéron*; T. Zieliński, *Das Clauselgesetz in Ciceros Reden*; Id., "Der constructive Rhythmus in Ciceros Reden"; A. W. de Groot, *De numero oratorio latino commentatio*; H. D. Broadhead, *Latin Prose Rhythm: A New Method of Investigation*; W. Schmid, *Über die Klassische Theorie und Praxis des antiken Prosarhythmus*, 4–112; A. Primmer, *Cicero Numerosus. Studien zum antiken Prosarhythmus*; G. O. Hutchinson, "Rhythm, Style, and Meaning in Cicero's Prose"; B. Sträterhoff, *Kolometrie und Prosarhythmus bei Cicero und Livius*. Cf. also the articles by M. Formarier, "Rythme et persuasion chez Cicéron – Qu'est-ce que le rythme latin?"; Id., "ῥυθμός, *rhythmos* et *numerus* chez Cicéron et Quintilien."

²⁸² To be sure, this does not mean that *numerus* is completely out of place in non-periodic style (*De Or.* III,190; *Or. Brut.* 222; 224); on this issue, see M. Formarier, "Modéliser le rythme 'haché' de Cicéron: propositions et perspectives."

²⁸³ *Or. Brut.* 187.

²⁸⁴ *Or. Brut.* 219; see also 220.

²⁸⁵ See *Or. Brut.*, 164–167; cf. *ibid.*, 220.

²⁸⁶ *Or. Brut.*, 187; 227. Cf. a similar warning in Arist., *Rhet.* III,8,3.

two or three final feet, but not beyond.²⁸⁷ The list of recommended feet is extended beyond what was found in Aristotle's *Rhetoric* and in Demetrius' *On Style*, where only the paeon was praised.²⁸⁸ At the beginning of periods, Cicero recommends placing either a dactyl (– u u), a first paeon (–u u u), or a cretic (– u –).²⁸⁹ However, he insists above all on the clausulae of periods, where metrical feet have the crucial function of marking the end point, and thus “stopping” the period. In this regard, the role of *numeri* at the end might even be compared to that of punctuation marks.²⁹⁰ For the final foot, Cicero suggests the dichoree (– u – u), the cretic (– u –), the first paeon (– u u u), the fourth paeon (u u u –), the spondee (– –), or the dochmius (u – – u –). He indicates that the iambe, trochee, dactyle and dochmius are appropriate as the penultimate foot, on the condition that the final foot is a choree (– u) or a spondee (– –). Finally, Cicero stresses that none of these feet should be preferred above the others or used systematically, since “in prose nothing is so vicious as to keep the rhythm always the same.”²⁹¹

5.2.3. Length

In contrast with Aristotle and Demetrius, Cicero does not seem to distinguish between the simple (monocôlon) and the composed period. At least, when he comments on the period “*Quem, quaeso, nostrum fefellit / ita vos esse facturos?*,” he specifies both that it contains two membra and that it represents the shortest possible form,²⁹² which suggests that he rejects the concept of a monocôlon period. With respect to the standard length of periods, Cicero's discussion is rather vague. He explains that the “full period [*plena comprehensio*] consists of four membra, each approximatively equal to a hexametre verse.”²⁹³ This gives a length of around 60 syllables, or even 40–80 syllables, depending on how “approximatively” is understood and the various possible length of a hexametre verse (i.e., between 12 and 17 syllables). In the same context, Cicero adds a remark that only brings more confusion: “it happens [...] frequently that one must stop sooner, or continue further in order to prevent the ear from being seemingly cheated by

²⁸⁷ *De or.* III, 193; *Or. Brut.* 216.

²⁸⁸ See the extended discussion in *Or. Brut.* 207–226. Cf. Arist., *Rhet.* III,8; Dem., *Eloc.* 38–43. Note Cicero's personal reluctance to use the paeon (*Or. Brut.* 215; cf. in the same sense Quint., *Inst.* IX,4,111).

²⁸⁹ *De or.* III, 191; cf. also *ibid.*, 182–183.

²⁹⁰ *Or. Brut.* 228.

²⁹¹ *Or. Brut.* 212.

²⁹² *Or. Brut.* 225.

²⁹³ *Or. Brut.* 222; cf. also 221.

brevity or wearied by length.”²⁹⁴ While “stop sooner” can mean, at the extreme, stopping after two short membra—as in the example of the “shortest possible form” of period above—it is impossible to determine the maximum length that Cicero considers acceptable. It is made perfectly clear, however, that a period cannot extend *ad infinitum*, as Cicero specifies that periods are not “longer than the strength and the breath [*vires atque anima*] can last.”²⁹⁵

5.3. *Membrum and incisum*

The term *membrum* is used by Cicero as an equivalent to the Greek κῶλον.²⁹⁶ To translate κόμμα, he suggests *incisum* or *caesum*, the two terms having the same meaning as the Greek word, i.e., “a cut off piece.”²⁹⁷

5.3.1. *Length*

Cicero does not provide any definitions of the membrum or the incisum. As concerns the formal difference between these two units, it appears to be merely one of length, the incisum being shorter than the membrum. From the examples provided, we can deduce that the boundary is situated around 7 syllables.²⁹⁸ Apart from its length, the incisum also differs from the membrum in terms of its impact on the audience: *incisa*, Cicero explains, should be used like “little daggers,” an image that closely recalls the description of the *articulus* found in the *Rhetorica ad Herennium*²⁹⁹ while also echoing the Demetrian association between commata and vehemence.³⁰⁰

Regarding the maximum length of membra, Cicero’s view is open to interpretation. In fact, the examples explicitly referred to as membra in his work never exceed 17 syllables, a point which at first glance suggests that units longer than hexametres are rejected (or, rather, that these units are subdivided into two or more membra). However, Cicero does not systematically identify membra in the extracts he quotes,

²⁹⁴ *Or. Brut.* 221.

²⁹⁵ *De or.* III, 191. Cf. a close remark in *Rhet. Her.* IV,12,18.

²⁹⁶ *Or. Brut.* 211.

²⁹⁷ *Caesum* and *incisum* derive respectively from the verbs *caedo* (chop, hew, cut into pieces) and *incido* (slit, hew, cut off). Cf. above, n. 110.

²⁹⁸ Some units of 7 syllables are qualified as *incisa*, while others of the same length are called *membra* (see *Or. Brut.*, 222–223; 225). Cicero also comments on the length of *incisa* in terms of feet: the *incisum*, he indicates, generally consists of one or two feet, to which part of a foot can be added (*Or. Brut.*, 224).

²⁹⁹ *Or. Brut.* 224; cf. *Rhet. Her.* IV,19.

³⁰⁰ Dem., *Eloc.* 7.

meaning that the range of examples is too restricted to draw definitive conclusions on the maximum length he would have personally accepted.

5.3.3. Syntactic nature

When it comes to non-periodic membra, Cicero explains: “If we wish to speak in membra, we stop, and when necessary, easily and often turn off from a course [the period’s course] which offends.”³⁰¹ At first glance this may give the impression that “to speak in membra” is only a matter of prosody; namely, a special way to deliver a speech, which would concretely consist of placing stronger breaks between the membra. However, if we review some examples, it appears that to compose a-periodically also has a lot to do with syntax:

Missos faciant patronos. Ipsi prodeant [“Let them dismiss their advocates. Let them appear in person”] [...] *Cur clandestinis consiliis nos oppugnant? Cur de perfugis nostris / copias comparant contra nos?* [“Why do they attack us with secret plans? Why from our own deserters / do they prepare a militia against us?”]. The first two are what the Greeks call commata, we call incisa; the third they call cōlon, we membrum; the last is a short period [*comprehensio*]—it is complete with only two verses, that is membra – with spondaic cadence.³⁰²

Domus tibi deerat? At habebas. Pecunia superabat? At egebas. [“Did you lack a house? Yet you had one. Was there money left? Yet you were in want.”] Here are four incisa; the following falls into two membra: *Incurristi amens in columnas. In alienos insanus insanisti.* [“You have madly dashed against the columns. You have raved wildly against strangers.”] Then the whole passage is set, as it were, on the foundation of a longer period [*comprehensio*]: *depressam, caecam, iacentem domum / pluris quam te et quam fortunas tuas aestimasti* [“A fallen, dark and prostrate home / you thought more valuable than yourself and your fortunes.”]³⁰³

A speech formed of incisa and membra is very efficient in actual practice, particularly in passages of demonstration or refutation, as in our second speech for Cornelius: *O callidos homines! O rem excogitatam! O ingenia metuenda!* [“What shrewd men! What ingenuity! What dangerous cleverness!”] So far it is in membra; then with a caesum: *Diximus* [“We have spoken”]; then again a membrum: *Testis dare volumus* [“We wish to offer witnesses”]; last comes the period [*comprehensio*], composed of two membra, the shortest possible form: *Quem, quaeso, nostrum fefellit / ita vos esse facturos?* [“Who of our number, I pray, failed to know / that you would act thus?”]³⁰⁴

³⁰¹ *Or. Brut.* 222. *Sin membratim volumus dicere, insistimus atque, cum opus est, ab isto cursu invidioso facile nos et saepe diiungimus.*

³⁰² *Or. Brut.* 222–223. Cicero specifies that this example is borrowed from Crassus, his teacher.

³⁰³ *Or. Brut.* 223–224 (trans. H. M. Hubbell). This example is an extract from Cicero’s *Pro Scauro* XXII,45. For a rhythmical analysis of this extract, see W. Schmid, *Über die Klassische Theorie und Praxis des antiken Prosarhythmus*, 142–151.

³⁰⁴ *Or. Brut.* 225. This example is an extract from Cicero’s second speech for Cornelius, of which only fragments have been preserved (see Cicero, *The Orations*, vol. II, 146).

In the above extracts, we can note that all the *membra* and *incisa* that do not belong to a period are autonomous from a grammatical point of view: “Let them dismiss their advocates,” “Let them appear in person,” “Why do they attack us with secret plans?” “Did you lack a house?” “Yet you had one,” “Was there money left?” “Yet you were in want,” “You have madly dashed against the columns,” “You have raved wildly against strangers,” “What shrewd men!” “What ingenuity!” “What dangerous cleverness!” “We have spoken,” “We wish to offer witnesses.” In modern terms, such *membra* and *incisa* could be labelled “short sentences,” if a sentence is understood as a unit that has sufficient autonomy to stand on its own. To put it another way, the possibility of stopping and “turning off” from the period’s course results from a specific construction that invests each *membrum* and each *incisum* with a semantico-syntactic independence.

Turning now to *membra* and the *incisa* that are part of a period, from the illustrations Cicero provides, it can be noted that these units always possess a relative semantico-syntactic completeness. Most of the time, *membra* and *incisa* correspond to a clause, either independent or dependent. However, it also happens that a *membrum* consists of only a part of a clause, as in the below example, where a single clause is divided into two *membra*: *Cur de perfugis nostris / copias comparant contra nos?* (“Why from our own deserters / do they prepare a militia against us?”).³⁰⁵ Here, the first *membrum* simply consists of a prepositional phrase preceded by the interrogative *cur*.

5.4. *Results*

Generally speaking, the theory outlined by Cicero appears very close to that of Demetrius. We find the same distinction between periodic style and a style made of autonomous *membra* (= *côla*) and *incisa* (= *commata*), as well as the same recommendation to alternate between these styles depending on the context and the intended effect on the audience. Another obvious parallel with the Demetrian theory is the use of the metaphor of a circle to refer to the period. In Cicero’s view, the circular aspect of periods has to do with the way a key element is delayed right until the end, as well as with rhythmical *clausulae* and, apparently, with symmetrical effects created by the Gorgianic figures of speech. As concerns the issue of the maximum length of periods, Cicero goes a step further than Demetrius, as he accepts combinations of more than four *membra* and does not fix a precise limit, though he refers to the “strength and

³⁰⁵ *Or. Brut.* 223. Cicero explicitly states that this saying is a *dicôloi* period, although he does not specify where the division occurs.

breath” of the speaker as a limitation. Finally, if we were to mention only one major development introduced by Cicero, it would be his reflexion on the rhythmical aspect of prose, which includes a detailed discussion of the different feet appropriate for clausulae.³⁰⁶

6. Dionysius of Halicarnassus, *On Literary Composition* (Περὶ συνθέσεως ὀνομάτων / *De compositione verborum [Comp.]* – late 1st century BCE)³⁰⁷

Among the several rhetorical treatises written by the Greek historian and rhetorician Dionysius of Halicarnassus (ca. 60 BCE–ca. 8 CE),³⁰⁸ the most useful for our study is the Περὶ συνθέσεως ὀνομάτων—literally “on the arrangement of words,” but commonly referred to as *On Literary Composition*. This treatise is considered one of the last works of Dionysius, dated to the end of the 1st century BCE.³⁰⁹ Dionysius’s style can be described as atticistic, since it imitates the style of the so-called Attic orators of the classical era. In this respect, Dionysius’ supreme model is Demosthenes, whose speeches are abundantly referred to in the treatise.

On Literary Composition is focused solely on σύνθεσις, that is, on the way words are put together. Dionysius wishes to demonstrate that the arrangement of words plays a more important role in prose composition than the choice of words themselves. *Synthesis*, he explains, not only creates the general rhythm of speech—by alternating between long and short syllables—but also determines the presence or the absence of consonant clashes and hiatus, as well as the presence of sound echoes at the extremities. It is thus the arrangement of words that determines, to a large extent, the general impression that a text conveys: pace, precipitation, slowness, harmony, melody, harshness, etc.³¹⁰ Dionysius begins by outlining the nature, goals, effects and processes of σύνθεσις (chapters 2–20); the following part of the treatise is devoted to presenting the three types of composition or “harmonies” ([ἁρμονίαι] austere, polite, and well-

³⁰⁶ Cicero himself states, “we have written more about rhythmical prose than anyone before us” (*Or. Brut.* 226).

³⁰⁷ *Critical Essays, Volume II. On Literary Composition. Dinarchus. Letters to Ammaeus and Pompeius* (ed. and transl. S. Usher; LCL; 1985). The translations below are mine, based on the Greek text present in this edition; at some places, my translation is also influenced by that of Usher.

³⁰⁸ On Dionysius of Halicarnassus’ life and work, see G. A. Kennedy, *The Art of Rhetoric in the Roman World*, 342–363; cf. J. Walker, “Dionysius of Halicarnassus,” 137–141.

³⁰⁹ G. A. Kennedy, *The Art of Rhetoric in the Roman World*, 344–345. For a chronology of the different works of Dionysius of Halicarnassus, see G. Aujac and M. Lebel (ed. and transl.), “Introduction” (*Opusculs rhétoriques*, vol. I), 22–29.

³¹⁰ On euphony in the works of Dionysius of Halicarnassus, see e.g. J. Vaahtera, “Phonetics and Euphony in Dionysius of Halicarnassus.”

tempered; chapters 21–24)³¹¹; the final chapters then focus on the link between prose and poetry (chapters 25–26). The terms κῶλον and περίοδος appear many times throughout the treatise, where they are constantly used when analysing extracts of classic literature. The term κόμμα, by contrast, appears only a few times at the end of the treatise, when Dionysius compares prose with poetry. It should be specified that Dionysius does not provide definitions of these notions, meaning that we have to reconstruct his thoughts based on the examples he proposes and the comments that he makes concerning them.

6.1. *Côla and commata*

Dionysius applies the term cōlon and more rarely comma to the subparts of periods.³¹² It is unclear whether he would use the same terminology to refer to the sayings of non-periodic style.

6.1.1. *Length*

Among those examples that are explicitly labelled cōla, the length ranges from 5 to 26 syllables.³¹³ The vast majority of cōla are between 8 and 20 syllables, which perfectly aligns with what was observed in the previous treatises. With respect to the notion of the comma, this appears only at the end of the treatise, when Dionysius compares prose with poetry. In this context, he describes commata as units shorter than cōla,³¹⁴ such that the difference between the cōlon and the comma seems to be solely a question of length.³¹⁵ From the few examples where a distinction between cōla and commata is made, we may deduce that the limit is situated around 7–8 syllables.³¹⁶

³¹¹ This system of three ἀρμονίαι is not to be confused with the traditional system of the three “levels of style” (plain, medium, low), the earliest attestation of which is found in *Rhet. Her.* IV,8,11–11,16. Dionysius distinguishes between the types of composition (ἀρμονίαι) and the levels of style. Specifically, as R. S. Reid explains, “[Dionysius’] Austere, Polished, and Well-Blended Types of Composition array distinctions concerning the manner in which sentences are composed at the level of syntactical invention—how the subject matter of one clause gets harmoniously related or subordinated to another clause—while the Types of Style [i.e., levels of style] system of classification tended to be primarily concerned with general aspects of diction and the use of figures of speech.” (R. S. Reid, “Dionysius of Halicarnassus’s Theory of Compositional Style and the Theory of Literate Consciousness,” 50).

³¹² *Comp.* 2,4–5. Cf. Dion. Hal., *Thuc.* 22.

³¹³ For short cōla, see *Comp.* 7,4–5, where ἡ μόνη ἐλπὶς is regarded as a cōlon. A 3-syllable cōlon is possibly found in *Comp.* 9,9 (ἐάσω), but the analysis is uncertain in this context. For an example of a 26-syllable cōlon, see *Comp.*, 22,27 (πολύβατον οἱ τ’ ἄστεος ὀμφαλὸν θυόεντα ἐν ταῖς ἱεραῖς Ἀθήναις οἰχνεῖτε); cf. also a long cōlon in 22,41.

³¹⁴ *Comp.* 26,2.

³¹⁵ My ideas here differ slightly from those of T. Viljamaa, who suggests that the difference between the cōlon and the comma also lies in their grammatical characteristics. While the cōlon is grammatically complete, grammatical completeness is not typical of the comma (“Cōlon and Comma. Dionysius of

6.I.2. *Côla as semantico-syntactic units*

Dionysius does not comment on the semantic nature of *côla*. Nevertheless, he provides enough examples to allow us to describe *côla* in terms of semantics and syntax. Specifically, we find mainly clauses, either independent or dependent. In the examples below, these appear as the first three *côla* of the first period, the first and third *côla* of the second period, or the third *côlon* of the third period.

- 1) ἔργων γὰρ εὖ πραχθέντων / λόγῳ καλῶς ῥηθέντι / μνήμη καὶ κόσμος γίνεται / τοῖς πράξασι παρὰ τῶν ἀκουσάντων. [When deeds have been nobly done / then through speech finely uttered / there comes honour and remembrance / to the doers from the hearers.]³¹⁷
- 2) πρῶτον μὲν, ᾧ ἄνδρες Ἀθηναῖοι, τοῖς θεοῖς εὐχομαι πᾶσι καὶ πάσαις / ὄσσην εὖνοιαν ἔχων ἐγὼ διατελῶ τῇ τε πόλει καὶ πᾶσιν ὑμῖν / τοσαύτην ὑπάρξαι μοι παρ' ὑμῶν εἰς τουτοῖ τὸν ἀγῶνα. [First of all, men of Athens, I pray to all the gods and goddesses / all the loyal affection I bear my whole life through to the city and all of you / may this be accorded by you to support me in this trial.]³¹⁸
- 3) ὑμεῖς τε ᾧ Λακεδαιμόνιοι / ἡ μόνη ἐλπίς / δέδιμεν μὴ οὐ βέβαιοι ᾗτε [O you, Lacedaemonians / our only hope / we fear that you are not steadfast.]³¹⁹

However, we should not hastily claim that the ancient concept of the *côlon* is equivalent to the modern concept of the clause. It appears that, in Dionysius' view, a phrase or a combination of phrases can also qualify as a *côlon*. From the examples above, we can mention τοῖς πράξασι παρὰ τῶν ἀκουσάντων (which is a combination of a nominal phrase and a prepositional phrase), ὄσσην εὖνοιαν ἔχων ἐγὼ διατελῶ τῇ τε πόλει καὶ πᾶσιν ὑμῖν (which consists of a nominal phrase in which a relative clause is embedded), the vocative expression ὑμεῖς τε ᾧ Λακεδαιμόνιοι, as well as the nominal phrase ἡ μόνη ἐλπίς (which is arguably a comma, as it contains only 5 syllables).³²⁰ In sum, periodic

Halicarnassus on the Sentence Structure," 171–172). In my view, this difference is just the logical consequence of the difference in length between the *côlon* and the comma.

³¹⁶ See *Comp.* 26,11–12. Previously in the treatise, the generic term κῶλον was used to designate indifferently long *côla*, *côla* of normal length, and commata: see e.g. *Comp.* 7,4–5 and 9,2–8, where very short units are still called *côla*.

³¹⁷ *Comp.* 9,4 (= Plato, *Menex.*, 236e). Dionysius identifies only the last *côlon*, but the proper division of the remaining part can be easily deduced from his comment regarding the equality of length between the *côla*.

³¹⁸ The opening of Demosthenes' *On the Crown*; quoted by Dionysius in *Comp.* 18,16–19.

³¹⁹ Thucyd., *Pelop.* III,57,4; quoted by Dionysius in *Comp.* 7,4 (cf. also *ibid.*, 7,5). For a short discussion of the delineation of *côla* in this period, see Habinek, *The Colometry of Latin Prose*, 31–32, esp. n. 20.

³²⁰ Other examples of *côla* or commata consisting of phrases are found in *Comp.* 26,11–12.

côla correspond to different kinds of syntactic units,³²¹ but share in common the relative semantico-syntactic completeness that they possess.

6.2. *Periods*

6.2.1. *Length*

In the *Περὶ συνθέσεως ὀνομάτων*, the examples of periods have either two, three or four côla.³²² There is also one passage that apparently alludes to the concept of the monocôlon period, namely, when Dionysius indicates that in the polite harmonia “it is not possible to write a passage without periods, a *period without côla*, or a côlon without symmetry.”³²³ Precisely, the specification “a period without côla” suggests that it is possible, in other contexts, to have single-côlon periods. Then, in terms of the number of syllables that a period can comprise, the longest example explicitly qualified as a period has around 60 syllables.³²⁴ That being said, longer periods up to around 80 syllables are arguably also found in the treatise, even if they are not explicitly identified. See for example the preamble of Demosthenes’ *Against Aristocrates*, where Dionysius quotes prose that resembles poetry as a model,³²⁵ or in the opening of Isocrates’ *Areopagiticus*,³²⁶ which is mentioned as an illustration of “polite harmonia.”

³²¹ This has been rightly noticed by Du Mesnil (“Begriff der drei Kunstformen der Rede,” 59–60); cf. also Habinek, *The Colometry of Latin Prose*, 30–33.

³²² Dicôloi periods are found e.g. in *Comp.* 18,9 (ἔργω μὲν ἡμῖν οἶδε ἔχουσιν τὰ προσήκοντα σφίσιν αὐτοῖς / ὧν τυχόντες πορεύονται τὴν εἰμαρμένην προεῖαν [= Plato, *Menex.* 236d]) and in 22,40–41 (ἀρξάμενος εὐθύς καθισταμένου / καὶ ἐλπίσας μέγαν τε ἔσεσθαι καὶ ἀξιολογώτατον τῶν προγεγενημένων [= Thucyd., *Pelop.* I,1,1]). For tricôloi periods, see e.g. *Comp.* 18,3 (οἱ μὲν πολλοὶ τῶν ἐνθάδε ἤδη εἰρηκότων / ἐπαινοῦσι τὸν προσθέντα τῷ νόμῳ τὸν λόγον τόνδε / ὡς καλὸν ἐπὶ τοῖς ἐκ τῶν πολέμων θαπτομένοις ἀγορεύεσθαι αὐτόν [= Thucyd., *Pelop.* II,35,1]), or 18,17–19 (πρῶτον μὲν, ὧν ἄνδρες Ἀθηναῖοι, τοῖς θεοῖς εὐχομαι πᾶσι καὶ πάσαις / ὄσην εὖνοιαν ἔχων ἐγὼ διατελῶ τῆ τε πόλει καὶ πᾶσιν ὑμῖν / τοσαύτην ὑπάρξαι μοι παρ’ ὑμῶν εἰς τουτονὶ τὸν ἀγῶνα [= Demosth., *On the Crown* 1]). For tetra-côloi periods, see *Comp.* 9,2–3 (ὁ γὰρ οἷς ἂν ἐγὼ ληφθῆῖν / ταῦτα πράττων καὶ κατασκευαζόμενος / οὗτος ἐμοὶ πολεμεῖ / κἄν μήπω βάλλῃ μηδὲ τοξεύῃ [= Demosth., *Phil.* 3,17]); or 9,4–5 (ἔργων γὰρ εὖ πραχθέντων / λόγῳ καλῶς ῥηθέντι / μνήμη καὶ κόσμος γίνεται / τοῖς πράξασι παρὰ τῶν ἀκουσάντων [= Plato, *Menex.* 236e]).

³²³ *Comp.* 23,5.

³²⁴ *Comp.* 18,16–19 (see above, section 6.1.2, example 2).

³²⁵ *Comp.* 25,4.

³²⁶ *Comp.* 23,19.

6.2.2. Characteristics of periods: Circularity, figures, rhythm

Much like Demetrius and Cicero, Dionysius makes use of the metaphor of the circle in reference to periods. This can be notably seen in his comments on the opening of Isocrates' *Areopagiticus*:

It is these characteristics [i.e., no dissonance of vowels and few dissonances of semivowels and voiceless consonants] that are responsible for the melodious effect of the passage, and also the symmetry between the cōla [ἡ τῶν κῶλων συμμετρία πρὸς ἄλληλα], and the circle of the periods [τῶν τε περιόδων ὁ κύκλος] ...³²⁷

It appears that Dionysius also shares with Demetrius the idea that periods can be more or less “circular,” depending on the kind of harmonia one wishes to compose.³²⁸ Polite harmonia,³²⁹ to which the passage from the *Areopagiticus* belongs, is periodic *par excellence*: it requires sophisticated arrangements where the cōla are “interwoven [συνυφάνθαι] with one another and achieve their final form together as period.”³³⁰ A mere glance at the opening of the *Areopagiticus* reveals that this “interweaving” between cōla has a lot to do with syntax: concretely, the cōla that together form a period are typically dependent on each other from a syntactic point of view, meaning that it is impossible to isolate them. Polite harmonia is also characterised by the abundant use of figures, as Dionysius notes in the remainder of his comment:

... and beyond all these features there are the figures of speech, full of youthful exuberance: antitheses, assonances [παρόμοιοι], balance [πάριστοι], and others like these, through which the language of ceremonial oratory is perfected.³³¹

Here we can recognise the triad of Gorgianic figures, which are traditionally associated with the periodic style.³³² Finally, the periods of polite harmonia are rhythmical, exhibiting notably metrical clausulae to mark their endings.³³³ These different features make it easy to discern the contour of polite periods; it is as if these periods were

³²⁷ *Comp.*, 23,22; Dionysius comments here on Isoc., *Areop.* 1–5.

³²⁸ Dem., *Eloc.* 19–21.

³²⁹ On polite harmonia, see *Comp.* 23.

³³⁰ *Comp.* 23,5; cf. *ibid.*, 23,3, where Dionysius states that polite harmonia looks like “finely-woven cloths” (εὐήτραιοι ὕψη).

³³¹ *Comp.* 23, 23.

³³² Cf. Arist., *Rhet.* III,9,7–10; Dem., *Eloc.* 22–29; Cic., *Or. Brut.* 164–167.

³³³ *Comp.* 23,6. The emphasis Dionysius places on rhythm brings him in close contact to Cicero. Indeed, in Dionysius' conception, rhythm creates the general movement of speech and contributes to its fluidity: the presence of metrical feet is thus not limited to the extremities of cōla and periods, but feet can be found everywhere. In the two final chapters of his treatise (*Comp.* 25–26), Dionysius even proposes extracts of prose analysed as poetry, and vice-versa; cf. also the examples of scansion found in 18,3–21.

somewhat placed on a pedestal.³³⁴ All in all, such periods strongly recall the circular sayings that Demetrius called “rhetorical periods.”³³⁵

At the opposite extreme, austere harmonia³³⁶ is characterised by an absence of sophistication, a quest for simplicity and natural arrangements, which results in periods that could be labelled “non-circular.” Moreover, Dionysius indicates that, in this kind of harmonia, periods should not be voluntarily composed but should rather emerge accidentally from the flow of words. Such “accidental” periods, he explains, should have an unstudied and simple character.³³⁷ Hence, Dionysius recommends “not using any additional words that contribute nothing to the sense merely in order to complete the circle [ἵνα ὁ κύκλος ἐκπληρωθῆ] [of periods].”³³⁸ He also specifies that the periods of austere harmonia lack metrical clausulae and that their ends are barely discernible.³³⁹ As to the syntactic construction of these “austere periods,” the examples reveal that their cōla are not as closely interlinked as the cōla of “polite periods.” All these characteristics make Dionysius’ austere periods close to Demetrius’ “conversational periods.”

6.3. *Non-periodic style*

Although Dionysius focuses his discussion on how to arrange cōla into periods, it seems that he admits both the possibility of writing without periods and the necessity of doing so in certain contexts. This admission can be found in his comments regarding austere harmonia—see above, section 6.2.2—where he indicates that whoever wishes to achieve this harmonia should not voluntarily compose periods.³⁴⁰ It is even clearer in the two following comments:

These [= the periods] too must precede or follow one another in a closely harmonious sequence, every time that it is appropriate to use periods [ὅταν ἐν ταῖς περιόδοις προσήκη τὸν λόγον ἐκφέρειν].³⁴¹ Of course, *the periodic style* [τὸ ἐμπερίοδον] *should not be used*

³³⁴ On this metaphor, see *Comp.* 23,7.

³³⁵ See Dem., *Eloc.* 20.

³³⁶ *Comp.* 22.

³³⁷ *Comp.* 22,5.

³³⁸ *Comp.* 22,5.

³³⁹ *Comp.* 22,42-43.

³⁴⁰ See *Comp.* 22,5.

³⁴¹ This reading is attested both in F (Florentinus Laurentianus LIX 15, 10th or 11th century) and E (Parisinus gr. 2918, 14th century), and has been retained by W. Rhys Roberts (*On Literary Composition*, 118–119), and more recently by S. Usher (*Critical Essays*, vol. 2, 68–69). Note however that Parisinus gr. 1741 (10th century) has the negation μή before προσήκη, which gives the passage a completely different meaning: “These [= the periods] too must precede or follow one another in a closely harmonious

everywhere: and this very question—when periods should be used and to what extent, and when not—is one of particular relevance to the science of composition.³⁴²

The finest style of all is that which contains the greatest amount of relief from monotony and change of structure, when one thing is said in a period, another without period [ὅταν τουτί μὲν ἐν περιόδῳ λέγηται, τουτί δ' ἔξω περιόδου].³⁴³

However, the remark on the importance of knowing “when periods should be used and to what extent, and when not” makes it somewhat surprising that Dionysius does not discuss this issue further, and also that he does not give explicit examples of non-periodic sayings. To explain this silence, we might assume that Dionysius considers the non-periodic style much easier to achieve than the periodic style, such that he does not feel the need to provide models and give advice thereon.

6.4. Results

Like his predecessors, Dionysius of Halicarnassus considers prose to be structured in *côla*—short semantico-syntactic units usually consisting of 8 to 20 syllables—and in periods—longer units consisting of several *côla* combined. With respect to the number of *côla* that a period can comprise, we have seen that Dionysius accepts *at least* *dicôloi*, *tricôloi* and *tetracôloi* periods, and probably the *monocôlon* period as well. In terms of the number of syllables, the sayings that are explicitly referred to as periods extend up to 60 syllables; then, in certain extracts of Demosthenes and Isocrates, we probably find longer periods, up to around 80 syllables. Much like Demetrius and Cicero, Dionysius makes use of the metaphor of the circle to refer to the period. He also follows the Demetrian doctrine that not all periods are circular: in Dionysius' view, periods should

sequence, every time *that it is not appropriate to use [circular] periods* [ὅταν ἐν ταῖς περιόδοις μὴ προσήκη τὸν λόγον ἐκφέρειν]. For periodic style [i.e. “circular style”] should not be used everywhere [...].” If *μὴ* is retained, as is the case e.g. in the edition by Aujac and Lebel (*La composition stylistique*, 89, cf. also 205–206, n. 89), this would force us to assume that the word “period” takes on two distinct meanings in Dionysius' writings. Sometimes “period” would simply designate any combination of *côla* and/or *commata* that are closely linked (broad meaning); but at other times the same term would allude more specifically to the image of a “circle,” thereby referring to more sophisticated sentences (strict meaning). In this sense, it might be thought that Dionysius only expresses in *Comp.* 9,10–11 that “circular periods” should not be used everywhere: in other words, he would consider all prose as periodic. Hence, this passage would mean that when loose periods (i.e., non-circular ones) are appropriate, then the boundaries between those periods should also be somewhat blurred. See in this regard G. Aujac and M. Lebel's translation, which employs the vocabulary of welding: “Il convient en effet de *souder* la période qui précède à la période qui suit chaque fois que la convenance exclut le style périodique.” (*La composition stylistique*, 89; my emphasis). Given that such a reading would place Dionysius in flagrant contradiction with his predecessors, we should be careful not to embrace this interpretation without further investigating his work.

³⁴² *Comp.* 9,10–11.

³⁴³ *Comp.* 19,10.

be more or less circular according to the kind of harmonia one wishes to compose. Thus, in polite harmonia, periods are circular: their cōla are closely interwoven on the syntactic level, and they typically exhibit features such as metrical clausulae, antitheses, sound echoes, and equal length. These periods strongly recall the Demetrian “rhetorical periods.” By contrast, all of these sophisticated features are out of place in austere harmonia, where periods are reminiscent of the Demetrian “conversational periods” and might be qualified as “barely circular.”

7. Quintilian, *The Orator’s Education (Institutio oratoria [Inst.]—ca. 95 CE)*³⁴⁴

At the end of his life, after having retired from teaching and pleading, Quintilian (late 30s–ca. 100 CE) produced an exhaustive work on rhetoric, known by the title *Institutio oratoria* (commonly translated *The Orator’s Education*).³⁴⁵ This work, which comprises twelve volumes, was published around the year 95 CE.³⁴⁶ In addition to the theory and practice of rhetoric, it also addresses the foundational education and development of the “perfect orator,” from infancy up to the orator’s educated career.³⁴⁷ The elements concerning cōla (*membra*), commata (*incisa* or occasionally *caesa*) and periods are found primarily in book IX, which is devoted to *elocutio*. There is also a key passage in book XI, included in a discussion of delivery, where Quintilian addresses the different breaks, breaths, and intonations of the voice that must “punctuate” texts when they are read before an audience.³⁴⁸ Crucially, Quintilian explicitly links the placement of this “oral punctuation” to the issue of colometric structure.³⁴⁹

In his discussion of colometry, Quintilian relies on Cicero considerably, and explicitly. Most of the examples he proposes are taken from speeches by Cicero. Moreover, many of these examples are exactly the same as those found in the *Orator* and the *De oratore*, with almost the same comments sometimes being reproduced. Nevertheless, in contrast with Cicero, Quintilian is keen to provide definitions of the

³⁴⁴ *The Orator’s Education* (ed. and trans. D. A. Russell; 5 vol; LCL; 2002). The translations below are mine, based on the Latin text established by Russell; at certain places they are strongly influenced by Russell’s translation.

³⁴⁵ On Quintilian’s life and work, see G. A. Kennedy, *The Art of Rhetoric in the Roman World*, 487–514; cf. J. Connolly, “Fabius Quintilianus.”

³⁴⁶ See e.g. G. A. Kennedy, *The Art of Rhetoric in the Roman World*, 493.

³⁴⁷ This aim is announced in the preface to the first volume (*Inst.* I, preface, 9).

³⁴⁸ *Inst.* XI,3,33–39.

³⁴⁹ On the link between colometry and oral punctuation according to Quintilian, see below, Chapter 5, section 2.2.

membrum, the *incisum*, and the period. These three units are defined and illustrated in a single passage of book IX (4,122–125), which will be the focus of the discussion below.

7.I. *Membra and incisa*

7.I.I. *Incisum (= comma)*

When proposing his series of definitions of the *membrum*, the *incisum*, and the period, Quintilian begins with the former:

An *incisum*, in my view, is a thought without completeness of rhythm [*sensus non expleto numero conclusus*]. Most people define it as a part of a *membrum*. Here is Cicero's example: *Domus tibi deerat? At habebas. Pecunia superabat? At egebas*. ["You needed a house? But you had one. You had money to spare? But you were in need."] ³⁵⁰ But it also happens that *incisa* consist of a single word: *Diximus, testes dare volumus* ["We spoke; we are willing to provide witnesses"]. ³⁵¹ *Diximus* is an *incisum*. ³⁵²

The *incisum* is described as a thought with an incomplete rhythmical structure. It is worth noting that Quintilian also alludes to an alternative conception, which he presents as the majority opinion: "most people define it [the *incisum*] as a part of a *membrum*."³⁵³ Nevertheless, he makes clear that he personally disagrees with this popular definition. Could this be because of its popular nature, and therefore its status as a non-technical definition?³⁵⁴ Regarding the examples, *Domus tibi deerat?*, *At habebas*, *Pecunia superabat?*, and *At egebas* are all independent or "autonomous" *incisa* (i.e., they are not part of a period). The formulation does not clarify whether Quintilian considers *diximus* to be the first term of a short *dicôloi* period (*Diximus / testes dare volumus*), or whether *diximus* is also an independent comma, with *testes dare volumus* being then an autonomous *membrum*. Assuming that Quintilian follows Cicero's analysis of this passage,³⁵⁵ the second option is more likely.

³⁵⁰ Extract of Cicero's *Pro Scauro* XXII,45, also quoted by Cicero in *Or. Brut.* 223.

³⁵¹ Extract of Cicero's *Pro Cornelio*, also quoted by Cicero in *Or. Brut.* 225.

³⁵² *Inst.* IX,4,122.

³⁵³ Despite Quintilian's comment, this alternative definition is not widely found in ancient treatises, a point that might suggest that it corresponds to a more popular conception. Evidence of how the comma was conceived as a subpart of the *côlon* is found in some later authors: see Longinus (3rd century), who compares the *côla* to the legs of animals made of two articulated parts, each corresponding to a comma (*Rhet. fr.* 48, l. 329–339 Patillon [= p. 193 Hammer-Spengel]); Aquila Romanus (3rd century), *Fig.* 27,32–28,1 Halm [= p. 28–29 Elice]; cf. also a possible allusion to this conception in Pseudo-Aelius Aristides, *Pol.* 168 (see below, section 9.2).

³⁵⁴ Cf. below, footnote 476.

³⁵⁵ Cic., *Or. Brut.* 225.

7.1.2. *Membrum* (= *côlon*)

Having defined the *incisum*, Quintilian turns next to the *membrum*:

A *membrum*, however, is a thought which is rhythmically complete [*membrum autem est sensus numeris conclusus*], but separated from its parent body and ineffective on its own. *O callidos homines!* ["What shrewd men!"] is complete; yet it has no force without the rest, like a hand or a foot or a head on its own. *O rem excogitatam!* ["What ingenuity!"] When does it begin to be a complete body? When comes the final period [*conclusio*]: *Quem, quaeso, nostrum fefellit / id vos ita esse facturos?* ["Who of our number, I pray, failed to know / that you would act thus?"]. Cicero regards this as the shortest possible form [of period].³⁵⁶

Quintilian explains the difference between the *membrum* and the *incisum* in terms of rhythm: in contrast with the *incisum*, the *membrum* is rhythmically complete. According to Cicero's own analysis of the same example, "*O callidos homines*" and "*O rem excogitatam*" are both autonomous *membra* (i.e., not included within a period).³⁵⁷ At first glance this is a little bit confusing, owing to the bodily metaphor Quintilian uses: he compares these *membra* to parts of the body, and therefore uses precisely the same metaphor as that employed by Demetrius to refer to periodic *côla* and *commata*.³⁵⁸ However, there is no good reason to think that Quintilian would here depart from Cicero's analysis, all the more so as he explicitly refers to Cicero at the end of the passage, when he comments on the short conclusive period, "*Quem, quaeso, nostrum fefellit / id vos ita esse facturos?*" It is therefore likely that Quintilian offers here a general remark that applies to all kinds of *membra* and *incisa*, regardless of whether they take place within a period or not. In other words, he simply expresses the idea that *membra* and *incisa* are always part of a broader structure. He perhaps also wishes to stress the idea that the non-periodic style should not be maintained throughout the speech. Indeed, right after the examples of *membra*, Quintilian concludes that "as a rule *incisa* and *membra* are truncated fragments, and inevitably require a period [*conclusio*]." ³⁵⁹

7.1.3. *Length*

As a general rule, Quintilian agrees with Demetrius' recommendation that a *membrum* should be neither too long nor too short.³⁶⁰ Most of the examples he gives are in the range of 10–20 syllables. Nevertheless, it seems that a *membrum* can extend far further, up to around 30 syllables, as in the following example: *Animadverti iudices, omnem*

³⁵⁶ *Inst.* IX,4,123. These examples are from *Pro Cornelio* (also quoted by Cicero in *Or. Brut* 225).

³⁵⁷ *Cic., Or. Brut.* 225.

³⁵⁸ *Dem., Eloc.* 2.

³⁵⁹ *Inst.* IX,4,123. A close idea is found in Cicero, *Or. Brut.* 225–226.

³⁶⁰ *Inst.* IX,4,126 (see above, n. 95). Cf. also *Dem., Eloc.* 4.

accusatoris orationem, in duas, divisam esse partes? (“I noticed, members of the jury, that the prosecutor’s entire speech was divided into two parts.”)³⁶¹ There is no minimum length for *incisa*, which can be reduced to a single word, such as *diximus* in the example above. In light of the above examples, the limit between *membra* and *incisa* is situated around 7 or 8 syllables.

7.2. *Periods*

After the definitions of the *incisum* and the *membrum*, Quintilian turns to the period, which he usually designates using the Greek term transliterated as *perihodos*:

For the period, Cicero proposes a number of different names: *ambitus*, *circumitus*, *comprehensio*, *continuatio*, *circumscriptio*.³⁶² There are two types: one simple [*simplex*], when a single thought is deployed in a period of some length, and one composed of *membra* and *incisa*, which contains several thoughts: *Aderat ianitor carceris*, *carnifex praetoris*, and so on. A period has at least two *membra*. The average number seems to be four, though it often allows more. Its extent is fixed by Cicero either by the length of four *senarii* or by the length of a single breath [*spiritus*]. It must enclose a complete thought [*praestare debet ut sensum concludat*]; it must be clear so as to be intelligible [*sit aperta, ut intellegi possit*], and not too long to be retained in the memory.³⁶³

Quintilian states that there are two basic kinds of periods: the *composed period*, which has many *membra* and/or *incisa*, and the *simple period*. He does not explicitly state that the simple period contains one *membrum*—he only says that it comprises one “thought” (*sensus*). However, we can easily deduce from the context that Quintilian’s simple period is a monocôlon period, as his definition of the period immediately follows the passage on the *membrum*, in which the *membrum* is precisely defined as a thought (*sensus*). In addition, the term “*simplex*” recalls the terminology employed by Aristotle (ἀφελῆς περίοδος) and Demetrius (ἀπλή περίοδος) to describe the monocôlon period.³⁶⁴ The remark that “a period has at least two *membra*” does not really conflict with this interpretation. Indeed, a similar statement is also made by Demetrius, who states that “the shorter periods consist of two *côla*”³⁶⁵ before explaining that “[there are] also

³⁶¹ *Inst.* IX,4,68 (= Cic., *Pro Cluentio* 1). This saying is arguably a monocôlon period.

³⁶² Cf. Cic., *Or. Brut.* 204 and *ibid.* 208. Note that Cicero proposed *circuitus* instead of *circumitus*, and *comprehensio* instead of *comprehensio*. In *Inst.* IX,4,22, Quintilian also mentions the terms *circumductus* and *conclusio*.

³⁶³ *Inst.* IX,4,124–125.

³⁶⁴ Arist., *Rhet.* III,9,5; Dem., *Eloc.* 17.

³⁶⁵ Dem., *Eloc.* 16. Cf. above, section 3.2.1.

monocôlon periods, which are called simple.”³⁶⁶ We can note, however, that Quintilian’s definition of the simple period is less strict than that of Demetrius: while Demetrius insisted on the necessity of a *καμπή* in addition to the criterion of length,³⁶⁷ Quintilian seems to consider that every long *membrum* automatically becomes a period, regardless of the presence of a *καμπή*.

7.2.1. Length

Regarding the standard and the maximum length of periods, Quintilian merely paraphrases Cicero’s doctrine: this is arguably why he first indicates that “a period contains at least two *membra*,”³⁶⁸ even if this obviously contradicts the affirmation he just made on the simple period. His comment on the standard length, for its part, blends different recommendations of Cicero. First, Quintilian takes over Cicero’s description of the “full” period as comprising four *membra*, but he seems to consider this length to be an average rather than a maximum.³⁶⁹ Second, he alludes to the maximum length of four *scenarii*, which is also reminiscent of a recommendation made by Cicero, except that Cicero spoke of hexametres, not *senarii*.³⁷⁰ Third, Quintilian alludes to Cicero’s idea that periods can only extend as far as the respiratory capacity of the speaker will allow.³⁷¹ In light of these indications, we can only say that a period can comprise more than 4 members, and that it can extend to *at least* 70–80 syllables, i.e., the total length of 4 full *senarii*.³⁷²

At the end of the passage, Quintilian turns to a series of more general recommendations. In semantic terms, we find again the classical correspondence between a period and a complete thought.³⁷³ Quintilian also alludes to the pragmatic of reading and listening when he specifies that the period should be intelligible and also not too long. He indicates that the length is limited by memory capacity: this may refer either to the memory capacity of the reader or to that of the listeners, or perhaps to both at the same time.³⁷⁴

³⁶⁶ Dem., *Eloc.* 17. See above, section 3.2.1.

³⁶⁷ Dem., *Eloc.* 17.

³⁶⁸ *Inst.* IX,4,125.

³⁶⁹ *Inst.* IX,4,125. Cf. also Cic., *Or. Brut.* 222.

³⁷⁰ *Inst.* IX,4,125. Cf. also Cic., *Or. Brut.* 222.

³⁷¹ *Inst.* IX,4,125. Cf. also Cic., *De or.* III, 191.

³⁷² The iambic *senarius* can theoretically extend from 12 to 22 syllables, though the maximum attested is 18 syllables (B. W. Fortson, “Latin Prosody and Metrics,” 96–97).

³⁷³ Cf. Arist., *Rhet.* III,9,4–5; Dem., *Eloc.* 10; *Rhet. Her.* IV,19,27.

³⁷⁴ See the long treatment on *memoria* in *Inst.* XI,2.

7.2.2. Periodic vs non-periodic style

Quintilian recognises the possibility as well as the value of both periodic and non-periodic style. Like Cicero, he refers to the non-periodic style with the expression “speak in membra and caesa” (*membratim caesimque dicere*) or simply “speak in membra.”³⁷⁵ The appropriate style is to be chosen according to the type of text one wishes to compose, as well as the intended effect on the audience. Quintilian seems no more interested in discussing the exact boundary between the two styles than Cicero. Nevertheless, some of his remarks make clear that he works with a flexible conception of the period. Specifically, periods do not always correspond to a unique model that would be “circular.” Quintilian makes this explicit in a passage that speaks about “loosening” periods in narratives:

When we narrate, most of the time we shall speak in membra, or loosen up our periods themselves by having longer pauses and, as it were, looser knots [*aut ipsas perihodos maioribus intervallis et velut laxioribus nodis resolvemus*] – except when the narrative is intended as an ornament rather than an instruction, like the story of the Rape of Proserpina in *In Verrem*, where a gentle, flowing texture is appropriate.³⁷⁶

Narratives, Quintilian explains, should usually be composed in membra; more specifically, in autonomous membra. In this context, when periods are used, they must be loosened “by having longer pauses and, as it were, less tight knots.” In other words, the *côla* of “narrative periods” are only loosely connected to each other, such that the result resembles a succession of autonomous membra. This idea recalls Demetrius’ comment regarding “narrative periods,” or perhaps even more that which concerns “conversational periods,” which he places at the boundary between periodic and disjointed style.³⁷⁷ Quintilian mentions an exception to this rule: a more flowing texture is appropriate when the narrative is intended as an ornament rather than an instruction. By “flowing texture,” he arguably refers to the fine interweaving between the membra, as well as, possibly, to the absence of hiatus and consonant clashes.³⁷⁸

7.2.3. Characteristic features of periods

The features recommended and/or typically found in the periods quoted in the *Institutio oratoria* are the same as those in the previous treatises. Specifically, we often find syntactic constructions in which the membra are interwoven. The placement of a

³⁷⁵ See e.g. *Inst.*, IX,4,126–130; cf. *Cic., Or. Brut.* 212; *ibid.* 222.

³⁷⁶ *Inst.* IX,4,127.

³⁷⁷ *Dem., Eloc.* 21.

³⁷⁸ This kind of period would be closer to the Demetrian “rhetorical” period (see *Eloc.* 20).

key element as the final word, especially the verb, is greatly encouraged. Quintilian explicitly states “If the composition allows, it is much best to end with a verb, since the force of language is in the verbs.”³⁷⁹ He also discusses the three Gorgianic figures.³⁸⁰ Much like his predecessors, he understands antithesis (*contrapositum*) in a broad sense, meaning that the two parts of the antithesis do not always need to be actual opposites. For example: “To us first of all did the immortal gods give corn / we distributed to all lands what we alone received.”³⁸¹ As regards similarities in sounds, Quintilian tends to extend the possibilities by suggesting that the echoes may occur not only at the beginning or end of membra, but also in their middle. He even explains that permutations are possible, for example when middles answer to beginnings and ends to middles.³⁸² Finally, Quintilian offers a discussion of rhythm that is explicitly based on Cicero’s own discussion.³⁸³ He states that prose should be rhythmical but not contain actual verses³⁸⁴; metrical feet are to be encouraged especially at the extremities³⁸⁵; and a large range of feet are recommended, rather than just the paeon, as was the case in Aristotle and Demetrius.³⁸⁶ Quintilian also indicates that he is personally sceptical of the use of paeons.³⁸⁷

7.2.4. *Periods and breathing*

In the eleventh book of his *Institutio Oratoria*, Quintilian devotes an extensive discussion to the pragmatic of delivery (*actio*). This includes what might be termed “aural punctuation,” that is, the different kinds of breaks that structure the text when read

³⁷⁹ *Inst.* IX,4,26. This recommendation is found within a broader discussion of word order (IX,4,23–32).

³⁸⁰ On antithesis, see *Inst.* IX,3,81–86. On similarities in sound and similarities in length, see *Inst.* IX,3,75–80. Quintilian distinguishes four different cases: *parison* (the membra contain a word of which its sonority is close to its length); *homoeoteleuton* (final rhymes); *homoeoptoton* (similarity of case, which can occur at the beginning, middle, or end of membra); *isocolon* (approximative equality of length between the membra).

³⁸¹ *Inst.* IX,3,84 (*Nobis primis di immortales fruges dederant / nos quod soli accepimus in omnes terras distribuimus.*) According to Rutilius Lupus, *Fig.*, Halm 19,17, the author of this period is Demetrius of Phalerum.

³⁸² *Inst.* IX,3,78.

³⁸³ Quintilian’s discussion is found in *Inst.* IX,4,60–III; cf. Cicero, *Or. Brut.* 207–226. Quintilian nevertheless indicates that there are some problems in Cicero’s discussion on rhythm, especially as concerns terminology. On terminological issues, see M. Formarier, “Ῥυθμός, *rhythmos* et *numerus* chez Cicéron et Quintilien,” 143–148.

³⁸⁴ *Inst.* IX,4,72–78.

³⁸⁵ *Inst.* IX,4,61–66.

³⁸⁶ *Inst.* IX,4,79–III. Cf. Arist., *Rhet.* III,8; Dem., *Eloc.* 38.

³⁸⁷ *Inst.* IX,4,III. Cf. Cic., *Or. Brut.* 215.

aloud.³⁸⁸ Regarding the link between periods and breathing, the most relevant passage runs as follows:

So, when about to utter a lengthy period, the breath should be collected [*colligendus est spiritus*]; but we should not take a long time over it, do it noisily, or make it in any way obvious. At other points, the best strategy will be to recover breath at the junctures of the discourse [*inter iuncturas sermonis*].³⁸⁹

Although he refers to the length of a breath as the upper limit for periods, Quintilian clearly accepts that it might be necessary to take some internal breaths inside periods. However, taking a breath in the middle of a period is not ideal. It is rather a concession made to the physical need of the speakers to gain more air so as to ensure that they are able to maintain a pleasant sound until the end.³⁹⁰ As a general rule, Quintilian makes clear that the normal way of reading involves waiting for the “natural articulations of the discourse,” that is, to take a breath only when the period is finished.³⁹¹ For this reason, the possibility of internal breaths is limited to “lengthy periods.” Quintilian also stresses that, when internal breaths are needed, they should remain extremely discrete, meaning that the speaker should “not take a long time over it, do it noisily, or make it in any way obvious.” We can deduce from Quintilian’s remarks that these discrete breaths are to be taken at the breaks between the membra.

7.3. Results

Quintilian’s discussion of colometry in his *Institutio oratoria* appears merely as a reformulation of Cicero’s thoughts, with only small differences. One of these differences relates to the concept of the monocôlon period. Yet, beyond the obvious closeness with Cicero, Quintilian is also very close to Demetrius. He adopts all the changes that the author of the *Περὶ ἑρμηνείας* made to Aristotle’s theory: first, the validation of a style made of autonomous membra and incisa, which corresponds to the Demetrian disjointed style; second, the extension of the acceptable length of periods (on this question, Quintilian even goes further than Demetrius, since he follows Cicero in accepting periods of more than four membra); and, last but not least, the idea that the distinction between periodic and non-periodic style is somewhat porous.

³⁸⁸ *Inst.* XI,3,52–60.

³⁸⁹ *Inst.* XI,3,53.

³⁹⁰ Cf. *Inst.* IX,3,54.

³⁹¹ Cicero perhaps alludes to the same idea when he adds to his initial statement, “the longest group of words is that which can be reeled off in one breath” the further remark “however nature has its limits, and art has other ones” (Cic., *De or.* III,182).

8. Alexander Numenius, *On Figures* (Περὶ τῶν τῆς διανοίας καὶ τῆς λέξεως σχημάτων / *De figuris sententiarum et verborum* [Fig.] – middle of the 2nd century CE)³⁹²

Alexander, son of Numenius, most likely lived sometime in the mid-2nd century CE.³⁹³ He authored a treatise entirely devoted to figures, the Περὶ τῶν τῆς διανοίας καὶ τῆς λέξεως σχημάτων (*On Figures of Thought and Speech*). Only an epitome of it survives. This treatise had a profound influence on subsequent works on figures³⁹⁴: it was even used as a model by the Latin Aquila Romanus and Julius Rufinianus for their respective treatises on figures.³⁹⁵ Alexander offers a condensed discussion of colometry that consists of definitions associated with models as well as a few remarks. He begins by stating that periods, cōla, and commata are the “earliest and topmost figures of speech” and that every text is “twisted and arranged” using them.³⁹⁶ He then describes and illustrates each of these notions, beginning with the period. Note that this discussion of periods is later picked up almost unchanged in Pseudo-Herodian’s treatise *On Figures*, which uses exactly the same examples.³⁹⁷

8.I. Periods

8.I.I. Definition

Alexander provides a definition of the period that closely recalls that offered by Demetrius,³⁹⁸ although the terminology is not completely identical:

³⁹² This treatise seems to have been largely ignored in modern scholarship. As far as I am aware, no translation of this treatise exists in any modern language, and the only critical edition proposed after that of L. Spengel in the mid-19th-century (*Rhetores Graeci* III, 9–40) consists of an unpublished PhD dissertation from 2004 (A. Jaewon, *Alexandri de figuris sententiarum et verborum*; PhD diss., Georg-August Universität). The references below are given according to the pages and lines of Spengel’s edition.

³⁹³ Little is known of Alexander’s life. See the short discussion in G. A. Kennedy, *The Art of Rhetoric in the Roman World*, 618; cf. A. Jaewon, *Alexandri de figuris sententiarum et verborum*, I–VI.

³⁹⁴ G. A. Kennedy states that Alexander’s treatise was “apparently the best-known treatise on figures of speech after that of Caecilius [of Calacte]” (*The Art of Rhetoric in the Roman World*, 618; on Caecilius’ work, that has been lost, see *ibid.*, 364–369).

³⁹⁵ A critical edition of Aquila Romanus’ treatise, including an Italian translation, has been offered by M. Elice, *Romani Aquilae De figuris*; on cōla, commata and periods, see esp. pages 26–31 [= 27–28 Halm]. For Julius Rufinianus, scholars must still rely on the mid-19th edition by C. F. Halm, *RLM*, 38–62.

³⁹⁶ τὰ πρῶτα καὶ ἀνωτάτω σχήματα τῆς λέξεως ἐστὶ περίοδος καὶ κῶλον καὶ κόμμα· διὰ τούτων γὰρ πᾶσα λέξις πλέκεται καὶ συντίθεται (Alex., *Fig.* 28,9–10).

³⁹⁷ Herod., *Fig.* 24 (= 93,6–30 Sp. *RG* III). A critical edition has been offered by K. Hajdú (ed.), *Ps.-Herodian, De figuris*; cf. the 19th-century edition by L. Spengel, *RG* III, 85–104. According to modern scholarship, this treatise is certainly not by Aelius Herodian himself (a grammarian who lived in the second part of the 2nd century CE), although it may go back to the 2nd century (K. Hajdú, *De figuris*, 19–23; cf. also E. Dickey, *A Catalogue of Works*, 340).

³⁹⁸ Cf. Dem., *Eloc.* 10.

A period is a saying that, in a well-outlined arrangement of *côla*, communicates an independent thought [περίοδος μὲν οὖν ἔστι λόγος ἐν ἐυπεριγράφῳ κώλων συνθέσει αὐτοτελῇ³⁹⁹ διάνοιαν ἐκφέρων].⁴⁰⁰ For example, the following: ἀνήρ γὰρ ιδιώτης / ἐν πόλει δημοκρατουμένη / νόμῳ καὶ ψήφῳ βασιλεύει [“A member of the common people / in a democratic city / is a king by virtue of the law and his own vote”].⁴⁰¹ The period comes from the fact that the thought is unfolded according to a periodic path, as in a circle [περίοδος δὲ ἀπὸ τοῦ περιοδευομένου οἷον κύκλῳ τὴν διάνοιαν ἐκπλέκειν].⁴⁰²

The adjective *ἐυπερίγραφος* conveys the notion of clear limits, and perhaps also bears a circular connotation brought by the prefix *περί*. The arrangement of *côla* is therefore “well-outlined.” The traditional concept of circularity appears more explicitly in the later comment, in which Alexander states that the thought is “unfolded according to a periodic path, as in a circle.” It should be noted that the term *comma* is absent from this definition, in contrast with the Demetrian definition. Nevertheless, this omission is not especially significant: it may be easily explained if we consider that a comma is nothing other than a special category of *côla*, of which the special feature is its shortness. In any event, it is clear that, in Alexander’s mind, *commata* can also be part of a period: for example, the model of period that illustrates the definition is made up of short *côla* of 6, 9, and 9 syllables respectively, of which the first one arguably constitutes a comma.

³⁹⁹ The term *αὐτοτελῇ* may allude to Aristotle’s depiction of the period as having “an end in itself” (Arist., *Rhet.* III,9,3).

⁴⁰⁰ The text of this definition is uncertain; the reading above is one possible reconstruction, which owes a lot to the close definition found in Pseudo-Herodian, *Fig.* 93 (Sp., RG III). The reference manuscript for Alexander’s treatise, the 10th-century Parisinus Graecus 1741 (= P), reads as follows: *περίοδος μὲν οὖν ἔστι λόγος ἄνευ περιγραφῶν καὶ κώλων συνθέσει αὐτοτελῇ διάνοιαν ἐκφέρων*. This reading contains two difficulties, which may suggest that the text of P has been altered. The first difficulty lies in the presence of *καὶ* before *κώλων*. Might this be the result of a confusion with some well-known definitions that contain the couple “*côla* and *commata*” (cf. Aelius Arist., *Pol.* 167; Dem., *Eloc.* 10)? Second, it is difficult to make sense of the formulation *ἄνευ περιγραφῶν* (literally “without outline”), given that periods are usually described as having a well-delimited contour (cf. Arist., *Rhet.* III,9,3; Dem., *Eloc.* 10; Dion. Hal., *Comp.* 23,6.). Hence, it may be thought that the epsilon and the upsilon should be read with the following term in the sense of “well” (*εὖ*). This suggestion was already found in the preface to L. Spengel’s edition (RG III, page V): Spengel suggested that we should read *εὖ περιγράφων* (“a well-outlined [statement]”). However, in such a case the presence of *ἄν* remains to be explained. Alternatively, it might be thought that the text of P results from an incorrect reading of *ἐν ἐυπεριγράφῳ* (“in a well-outlined [arrangement]”), which is precisely the formulation found in Pseudo-Herodian, *Fig.* 24 (= 93,6–8 Sp. RG III). Apparently, this is the view defended by P. Chiron (*Pseudo-Démétrios de Phalère*, 112), although Chiron does not mention in this context that his reading differs from the manuscript of reference or explain the reasoning behind his choice. Despite its speculative character, such a reconstruction is not entirely unlikely if we consider that Pseudo-Herodian’s account on the period seems to be directly based on that of Alexander (Herod., *Fig.* 24 [= 93,6–30 Sp. RG III]; cf. Alex., *Fig.* 27,17–28,17). R. D. Anderson proposes a similar reconstruction in his *Glossary of Greek Rhetorical Terms*, 101, n. 110.

⁴⁰¹ The extract is taken from Aeschines, *Ctes.* 3,233. The division into three *côla* is made explicit by Alexander a few lines later (*Fig.* 28,9–12).

⁴⁰² *Fig.* 27,17–22.

8.1.2. *Length*

Alexander expresses the length of periods in terms of the number of *côla*. He mentions the *dicôloi* period, the *tricôloi* period and the *tetracôloi* period and provides illustrations for each. Nothing is said concerning the *monocôlon* period, which may suggest that he rejects this concept. In terms of the number of syllables, the longest example reaches 65 syllables⁴⁰³; this, however, should probably not be taken as the maximum possible length, given that the number of examples is too small to be representative.

8.1.3. *Figures*

What about Gorgianic figures of speech, which were so closely linked with the concept of the period in the writings of Alexander's predecessors? In the few examples of periods that Alexander provides, we can observe a tendency for *côla* to have approximately the same length and to exhibit sound echoes at their extremities. The placement of the verb at the very end is also found, for example in the extract of Aeschines' *Against Ctesiphon* that comes right after the definition of the period: Ἄνῆρ γὰρ ἰδιώτης / ἐν πόλει δημοκρατουμένη / νόμῳ καὶ ψήφῳ βασιλεύει ("A member of the common people / in a democratic city / by virtue of the law and his own vote *is a king*"). It is unclear, however, whether Alexander regards the presence of such figures as a necessary characteristic of periods. In view of the small number of examples he gives, it is impossible to determine how strict or broad is the notion of period he works with.

8.2. *Côla and commata*

8.2.1. *Côlon*

Let us turn now to the *côlon*. Alexander describes it solely as "a part of a period" (κῶλον δ' ἐστὶ περιόδου μέρος).⁴⁰⁴ He does not allude to *côla* that would stand outside a periodic structure, at least not in this context. In the examples he provides, the number of syllables range from 6 up to 19 syllables.⁴⁰⁵ Regarding the syntactic nature of *côla*, we can note that most of the *colâ* correspond to clauses. Nevertheless, there is also one

⁴⁰³ Alex., *Fig.* 28,13–17 (τίς γὰρ οὐκ ἂν ἠδέως μετάσχοι στρατείας / τῆς ὑπ' Ἀθηναίων τε καὶ Λακεδαιμονίων στρατηγουμένης / ὑπὲρ δὲ τῆς τῶν συμμάχων ἐλευθερίας ἀθροισομένης / ὑπὸ δὲ τῆς Ἑλλάδος ἀπάσης ἐκπεμπομένης = Isocrates, *Paneg.* 185).

⁴⁰⁴ Alex., *Fig.* 27,22.

⁴⁰⁵ The example of 6 syllables stands as follows: ἀνὴρ γὰρ ἰδιώτης (that this saying is a *côlon* is explicitly stated by Alexander, *Fig.* 28, 9–12). For a 19-syllable *côlon*, see *Fig.* 28,13–15 : τῆς ὑπ' Ἀθηναίων τε καὶ Λακεδαιμονίων στρατηγουμένης.

example of a prepositional phrase (έν πόλει δημοκρατουμένη) as well as one example of a nominal phrase (άνήρ γάρ ιδιώτης). Both of them are found in the model that illustrates the definition of the period (see above, section 8.1.1), which suggests that Alexander considers phrases-côla to be fully acceptable.⁴⁰⁶

8.2.3. *Comma*

Following the cōlon, Alexander introduces the *comma*. The comma is described as what is shorter than the cōlon and the period.⁴⁰⁷ In the six examples provided, the commata do indeed range from 4 to 7 syllables, which means that they fall below the average length of cōla. Alexander distinguishes between two kinds of commata: those that stand alone, and those that stand with others.⁴⁰⁸ The examples of the first kind are maxims that closely recall the examples of commata given by Demetrius: γνώθι σαυτόν (“Know yourself”), μέτρον ἄριστον (“Everything in moderation”), ἔπου θεῶ (“Follow God”).⁴⁰⁹ As to the second kind of commata, Alexander mentions ὄρκον αἰτεῖς, νόμον αἰτεῖς, δημοκρατίαν αἰτεῖς (“you ask for an oath, you ask for laws, you ask for democracy”).⁴¹⁰ It is difficult to know whether these last three commata together constitute a period. The term “period” is not used here, and from a syntactic point of view, each of these commata could also stand on its own. In any case, it seems obvious that in Alexander’s mind commata can form part of the composition of a period, alongside cōla,⁴¹¹ provided that the model of the tricoloi period is composed of short cōla (6, 9, and 9), the first of which can arguably, in view of its length, be called a comma.

8.3. *Results*

To sum up, Alexander stands close to his predecessors when it comes to the notions of cōlon, comma, and period. Specifically, his definition of the period is reminiscent of that proposed by Demetrius; and the model that illustrates his definition also recalls the model given by Demetrius, in that the thought becomes intelligible only with the final word.⁴¹² Alexander also agrees with Demetrius on fixing the maximum length of periods at four cōla; however, he says nothing about the monocōlon period, which

⁴⁰⁶ Note that the division of this period into three cōla is made explicit by Alexander himself (*Fig.* 28,10–12).

⁴⁰⁷ *Fig.* 28,1–2: κόμμα δ’ ἐστὶ τὸ περιόδου καὶ κώλου ἔλαττον.

⁴⁰⁸ λαμβάνεται δὲ καὶ κόμμα καθ’ αὐτὸ ... λαμβάνεται δὲ καὶ πρὸς ἕτερον ... (*Fig.* 28,1–5).

⁴⁰⁹ *Fig.* 28,3–4. Cf. Dem, *Eloc.* 9.

⁴¹⁰ *Fig.* 28,4–5.

⁴¹¹ See also Du Mesnil, “Begriff der drei Kunstformen der Rede,” 87.

⁴¹² Cf. Dem., *Eloc.* 10.

might suggest that he rather follows the Ciceronian doctrine on this matter.⁴¹³ From the different examples of periods provided, it appears that symmetry (such as equality in length and sound echoes) plays an important role in linking cōla and/or commata together to form a periodic structure. The placement of a key element at the end also seems to play an important role. Therefore, we may conclude that Alexander is perfectly in line with the tradition as concerns the characteristics of the “typical” or “ideal” periods. However, it is unclear where he would personally place the boundaries of the periodic style: the data are lacking as to how he would classify those sayings that are not typically periodic, while still presenting syntactic dependency. To put it another way, the question as to whether Alexander works with a strict or a broad conception of the period remains open.

9. Pseudo-Aelius Aristides, *On Political Discourse* (Περὶ τοῦ πολιτικοῦ λόγου [Pol.] – 2nd CE)⁴¹⁴

The treatise Περὶ τοῦ πολιτικοῦ λόγου (*On Political Discourse*) is attributed in the manuscript tradition to Aelius Aristides (117–ca. 180 CE), one of the most eminent representatives of the second sophistic.⁴¹⁵ It was transmitted together with a second treatise, *On Simple Style*, also attributed to Aristides. Both of these attributions are now rejected, and it is sometimes assumed that the two treatises do not even originate from the same author.⁴¹⁶ *On Political Discourse* can be safely dated to the 2nd century CE, provided that it contains a theory on virtues that is a draft of the theory of *ideai* found in Hermogenes’ *On Ideas*, a treatise which is dated to the late 2nd century or early 3rd century.⁴¹⁷

⁴¹³ See above, section 5.2.3.

⁴¹⁴ M. Patillon (ed. and trans.), *Pseudo-Aelius Aristide: Arts Rhétoriques. Tome I, Livre I: Le discours politique*. The translations below are mine, based on the Greek text established by M. Patillon; references are also given according to this edition. Cf. pages 459–512 in L. Spengel (ed.), *Rhetores Graeci II*.

⁴¹⁵ On the life and work of Aelius Aristides, see J. Walker, “Aelius Aristides”; cf. G. A. Kennedy, *The Art of Rhetoric in the Roman World*, 582–585.

⁴¹⁶ See Patillon, *Le discours politique*, VIII–X; cf. also W. Schmid, “Die sogenannte Aristidesrhetorik,” 238–244. Patillon suggests that *On Political Discourse* is in fact a combination of two works: the first part would be the work of Basilikos, while the second part would be the work of Dionysius of Miletus (*Le discours politique*, XX). For a critical assessment of this suggestion, see H. Podbielski, “Pseudo Aristides: *On political style* and *On simple style*. Attribution and the nature of treatises.”

⁴¹⁷ Patillon, *Le discours politique*, VII–XXIII. On the relation between Hermogenes’ *On Ideas* and Pseudo-Aelius Aristides’ *On Political Discourse*, see also H. Podbielski, “Pseudo Aristides: *On political style* and *On simple style*,” 251–265.

9.1. Three kinds of style: Continuous, loose, and periodic

At the end of the treatise, we find a passage devoted to “composition and expression”⁴¹⁸ in which Pseudo-Aristides explains the different ways *côla* and *commata* can be arranged to build the discourse. The discussion runs as follows:

Composition [σύνθεσις] is either continuous [συνεχής]—and if this continues this way, fastened together in rows [ειρομένη], such as “A dangerous disease, Atheniens, has fallen upon Greece...” [νόσημα γάρ, ὧ ἄνδρες Ἀθηναῖοι, ἐμπέπτωκεν εἰς τὴν Ἑλλάδα χαλεπὸν ...]⁴¹⁹—or loose [λελυμένη], then diffused [κεχυμένη], such as “Very well! Be it so! I have no objection!” [ἔστω, γιγνέσθω ταῦτα, οὐδὲν ἀντιλέγω.],⁴²⁰ or periodic [κατὰ περίοδον], the period being an arrangement of *côla* and *commata*, an expression that perfectly fits with the thought, such as “The matters that you are debating, men of Athens, are to my mind so important (/) and even vital to the State / that I will endeavour to offer you what I consider profitable advice on the subject.” [καὶ σπουδαῖα νομίζων, ὧ ἄνδρες Ἀθηναῖοι, περὶ ὧν βουλευέσθε (/) καὶ ἀναγκαῖα τῇ πόλει / πειράσομαι περὶ αὐτῶν εἰπεῖν ἃ νομίζω συμφέρειν.]⁴²¹

In contrast with what seems to represent the common idea among ancient rhetoricians, Pseudo-Aristides does not recognise a simple twofold division of style (“interwoven” or periodic vs. “disjointed” or non-periodic), but instead proposes a tripartite model. Specifically, Pseudo-Aristides distinguishes between the *continuous* or *fastened in rows* style,⁴²² the *loose* or *diffused* style,⁴²³ and the *periodic* style. Given the low number of examples, it is difficult to know exactly where the boundaries between these three ways of composing are situated. It is nevertheless quite easy to grasp the general idea: the periodic style and the loose style represent two extremes, while the continuous style stands somewhere in the middle.

9.1.1. The loose style

The “loose” composition consists of making short autonomous sayings one after another, for example “Very well! Be it so! I have no objection.” In modern terms, each of these short sayings (in Greek: ἔστω, γιγνέσθω ταῦτα and οὐδὲν ἀντιλέγω) possesses enough syntactic autonomy to stand on its own as a short sentence. In view of this

⁴¹⁸ Περὶ συνθέσεως καὶ φράσεως (*Pol.* 167–173).

⁴¹⁹ Demost., *De Falsa Legatione* 259.

⁴²⁰ Demosth., *On the Chersonese* 10.

⁴²¹ *Pol.* 167. The model of the period is taken from Demost., *Fourth Phillipic* 1 (the proposed division into *côla* is mine).

⁴²² Patillon suggests “continue” and “filée” as translations of *συνεχής* and *ειρομένη* (*Le discours politique*, 160). Schenkeveld, who follows here the Greek text established by Spengel (*RG* II, 507,1–2: σύνθεσις ἐστὶν ἢ μὲν συνεχῆς ἢ διὰ πλειόνων ἐξῆς εἰρομένη), proposes “continuous composition, which is connected into a series of several parts” (Schenkeveld, *Studies in Demetrius*, 38, n. 6).

⁴²³ Cf. the use of the term *διαλελυμένη* to refer to non-periodic style in Demetrius, *Eloc.* 13 and 15.

characteristic, Pseudo-Aristides's loose style recalls Demetrius' disjointed style⁴²⁴ or what Cicero and Quintilian called the composition "in membra and incisa."

9.1.2. *The periodic style*

At the other extreme, the periodic style is made of longer sayings, called periods, which consist of a combination of several *côla* and/or *commata*. Pseudo-Aristides' definition closely recalls that proposed by Demetrius, even if the terminology is not completely identical:

Pseudo-Aristides: "[The period is] an arrangement [σύνταξις] of *côla* and *commata*, an expression [φράσις] that perfectly fits with the thought [εἰς διάνοιαν ἀπερτισμένη]."⁴²⁵

Demetrius: "The period is a system [σύστημα] of interwoven *côla* or *commata*, which perfectly fits with the underlying thought [πρὸς τὴν διάνοιαν τὴν ὑποκειμένην ἀπερτισμένον]."⁴²⁶

It might be thought that Pseudo-Aristides' definition is based on that proposed by Demetrius,⁴²⁷ but simplifies it. At the very least, the core idea is the same, i.e., the idea of a perfect correspondence between a *thought*, on the one hand, and a *formulation* made of many *côla* and *commata*, on the other.

With respect to the number of *côla* that a period can comprise, the author of *On Political Discourse* mentions the *monocôlon*, the *dicôloi*, and the *tricôloi*; the author then adds that longer periods are acceptable, without, however, setting an upper limit.⁴²⁸ This might indicate that, from his or her point of view, periods of more than 3 *côla* are the exception rather than the norm. Regarding the number of syllables, the shortest period found in the examples has 27 syllables, while the longest extends up to 60 syllables. Given the limited number of examples, however, these lengths cannot be taken as representing the minimum and maximum number of possible syllables.

⁴²⁴ Dem., *Eloc.* 12–13.

⁴²⁵ [...] ἢ δὲ κατὰ περίοδον, ἣτις ἐστὶν σύνταξις κώλων καὶ κομμάτων εἰς διάνοιαν ἀπερτισμένη [φράσις]. The final word, φράσις, is placed within brackets and left untranslated in Patillon's edition, despite being present in the manuscript of reference, the Parisinus Graece 1741. Φράσις might indeed represent an explanative addition, but it could alternatively be considered an apposition—as in the case of my translation above. The sense of the perfect participle ἀπερτισμένη could also be discussed further (on the different possible meanings of ἀπαρτίζω, cf. the discussion above, section 3.3.2). Patillon retains the idea of completion, and therefore translates: "[...] un système de *côla* et de *commata* qui s'achève avec la pensée" (*Le discours politique*, 160; my emphasis).

⁴²⁶ Dem., *Eloc.* 10. See the discussion above, section 3.3.2.

⁴²⁷ The similarities between the two definitions have been stressed by H. Schenkl ("Zur Kritik der Schrift des Demetrios Περὶ ἐρμηνείας," 67); see above, footnote 155.

⁴²⁸ *Pol.* 169.

Turning now to the typical features of periods, we can note that many of the examples have their main verb at the end. The Gorgianic figures are also present, as e.g. in the model of the dicôloi period: τὸ μὲν γὰρ ἐξ ἀρχῆς τι μὴ δοῦναι γνώμη χρησαμένων ἔργων ἐστὶν ἀνθρώπων / τὸ δὲ τοὺς ἔχοντας ἀφελῆσθαι φθονούντων.⁴²⁹ This period consists of an antithetic construction and also exhibits paromoioses, both at the beginning (τὸ μὲν / τὸ δέ) and at the end (ἀνθρώπων / φθονούντων). Finally, it is worth noting that Pseudo-Aelius Aristides quotes the very same extract of Demosthenes' *Leptines* as a model of the tricôloi period that Demetrius proposed as a model of a rhetorical period.⁴³⁰ All of these elements indicate that the author of the *Περὶ τοῦ πολιτικοῦ λόγου* agrees with his or her predecessors on what typical periods should look like.

9.1.3. *The continuous style*

The case of the *continuous* composition is more complex. The model, which is an extract from Demosthenes' *De Falsa Legatione*, stands as follows: νόσημα γάρ, ᾧ ἄνδρες Ἀθηναῖοι, ἐμπέπτωκεν εἰς τὴν Ἑλλάδα, χαλεπὸν... (“A disease, Atheniens, has fallen upon Greece, which is dangerous...”). This extract is incomplete; if we complete it, we have: νόσημα γάρ, ᾧ ἄνδρες Ἀθηναῖοι, [δεινὸν] ἐμπέπτωκεν εἰς τὴν Ἑλλάδα, [καὶ] χαλεπὸν καὶ πολλῆς τινὸς εὐτυχίας καὶ παρ’ ὑμῶν ἐπιμελείας δεόμενον (“A strange and distressing epidemic, men of Athens, has invaded all Greece, calling for extraordinary good fortune, and for the most anxious treatment on your part.”).⁴³¹ This saying appears as a midpoint between the periodic and the loose styles. In fact, it is neither completely “loose” like the example of the loose composition above (Ἔστω. Γιγνέσθω ταῦτα. Οὐδὲν ἀντιλέγω.), nor is it typically periodic, in the sense that it would be possible, from a syntactic point of view, to stop after Ἑλλάδα.

It would be interesting to imagine how other rhetoricians might have analysed this extract from Demosthenes. Demetrius would probably have considered it to be an instance of a “conversational,” period, i.e., a saying that looks like a blend of the periodic and the disjointed style but which should still be classified as periodic.⁴³² Quintilian would also have probably considered this extract to be a period, though an

⁴²⁹ “Because not to give right from the start is a mark of people using judgement / whereas to remove from those who have already received is a mark of spiteful people.” (= Demost., *Lept.* 56; quoted by Pseudo-Aelius Aristides in *Pol.* 169).

⁴³⁰ Cf. Dem., *Eloc.* 20; see above, section 3.2.5.

⁴³¹ Demost., *De Falsa Legatione* 259.

⁴³² Dem., *Eloc.* 19–21; see the discussion above, section 3.2.5.

atypical one. The same possibly also extends to Dionysius of Halicarnassus, as he too seems to work with a rather flexible conception of the period, as we have seen above. In contrast, we can imagine that Aristotle would have rejected this extract as belonging to the non-periodic *lexis*, the one that is “endless” and “united only by particles.”⁴³³ In this regard, it is worthwhile recalling that Aristotle called this non-periodic style *εἰρομένη* (“sewn” or “strung-on”), which is precisely the second term used by Pseudo-Aristides to describe the continuous style! And what about Alexander? He would certainly not have regarded this extract to be a typical period.⁴³⁴ Perhaps he would have shared Pseudo-Aristides’s view concerning the tripartition of style. Indeed, Alexander nowhere explicitly states that he works with a simple bipartite division between periodic and non-periodic style. Despite their necessarily speculative nature, these remarks illustrate how difficult it is to situate the precise boundary between the periodic style and the other style(s). Or, to be exact, it reveals that ancient rhetoricians do not all agree on this issue. Moreover, most rhetoricians were somewhat ambiguous in their definitions and examples, and we have seen that some of them even recognise the permeability of this boundary.⁴³⁵ Hence, we may think that Pseudo-Aristides’ tripartition constitutes an attempt to clarify the picture; it formalises the existence of a third category under which the rhetorician classifies those sayings that are not fully periodic but neither completely “loose.” To put it another way, the author of the *Περὶ τοῦ πολιτικοῦ λόγου* keeps the term “period” to designate only “typical” (or “circular”) periods. Thus, Pseudo-Aristides classifies the sayings that Demetrius qualified “conversational periods”⁴³⁶ as “continuous.”

A few lines later, Pseudo-Aristides briefly comments on the usage of each of the three styles.⁴³⁷ “The continuous and the loose styles seem to be adapted to facts [ἔργα] and passions [πάθη],” whereas “the periodic style is adapted to demonstrations, exords and enthymems.”⁴³⁸ Notably, the continuous and loose styles appear here together as a group that contrasts the periodic style. This clearly suggests that Pseudo-Aristides still

⁴³³ See Arist., *Rhet.* III,9,1–3. Note the three uses of *καί*.

⁴³⁴ Cf. the examples of periods that Alexander provides (*Fig.* 27,17–28,17).

⁴³⁵ The most explicit comment in this sense is found in Dem., *Eloc.* 21; cf. Dion. Hal., *Comp.* 22,42–43; Quint., *Inst.* IX,4,127.

⁴³⁶ Dem., *Eloc.* 19–21.

⁴³⁷ *Pol.* 170.

⁴³⁸ *Pol.* 170. Patillon interprets *ἔργα* and *πάθη* as referring to “narration” and “péroraison” (*Le discours politique*, 96–97). Alternatively, as my translation suggests, we may think that *πάθη* alludes to the impression of vehemence created by the usage of juxtaposed short *côla*; cf. Dem., *Eloc.* 7; *Rhet. Her.* IV,19,27. Cic., *Or. Brut.* 224; Herm., *Id.* I,8,10.

considered the main division to be between sayings that are periodic and those that are non-periodic—much like his or her predecessors.

9.2. *Côla and commata*

Pseudo-Aristides defines the côlon as “a composition of two nouns [ὀνομάτων δύο] or more.”⁴³⁹ As M. Patillon suggests, the term ὄνομα may refer to substantives, verbs, and pronouns.⁴⁴⁰ At the very least, this implies that a single word cannot constitute a côlon on its own, which is quite logical, given that such a short unit would, in principle, be called a comma. When it comes to defining the comma, Pseudo-Aristides’ comments are ambiguous:

A comma is a part [μέρος] of a côlon that stands either on its own, such as “Know yourself” or “Avoid extremes,” or [stands] with others, such as: “I implore [you] on behalf of your children / on behalf of your wives / on behalf of all who are dear to you.”⁴⁴¹

At first glance, this definition may be understood to imply that a comma is a subpart [μέρος] of a côlon. This would then converge with the alternative, “popular” conception of the comma to which Quintilian alluded in his *Institutio Oratoria*.⁴⁴² Nevertheless, as we have seen when discussing Pseudo-Aristides’ conception of the period, the comma stands in his or her definition of the period alongside the côlon (“[the period is] an arrangement of côla *and commata*”), which rather suggests that both of these units possess the same status in relation to the period. In addition, we can note that the two above examples of commata that “stand on their own” are not included within côla: they seem to stand on their own as autonomous units, just as autonomous côla would do. As for the three commata that “stand with others,” their status is more ambiguous: it is difficult to know whether they together form a côlon, or rather constitute a short period made of three commata. Should we then consider that the text of the *Περὶ τοῦ πολιτικοῦ λόγου* attests to two conflicting conceptions of the comma (the comma as a subpart of the côlon *and* the comma as a short côlon), and therefore reveals that its definition was ambiguous? Or should we rather argue that the formulation μέρος κώλου does not really mean that a comma is a *subpart* of a côlon, but rather a *portion* of it, in that a comma is a côlon that is somewhat “incomplete” with respect to its unusual

⁴³⁹ *Pol.* 168.

⁴⁴⁰ Patillon, *Le discours politique*, 160, n. 425.

⁴⁴¹ *Pol.* 168; cf. a close description in Alex., *Fig.* 28,1–5. The last example is from Demosthenes, *Against Aphobus* II,20: Ἀντιβολῶ πρὸς παίδων / πρὸς γυναικῶν / πρὸς τῶν ὄντων ὑμῖν ἀγαθῶν.

⁴⁴² Quint., *Inst.* IX,4,122.

shortness? I would personally lean towards the second option, as it seems to me that this agrees better with the examples.

9.3. Results

Pseudo-Aelius Aristides departs from the traditional twofold division between periodic and non-periodic styles, proposing instead a tripartition according to the categories “periodic,” “loose,” and “continuous.” Nevertheless, the model is not fundamentally different from that of his or her predecessors. In fact, in light of the different models that Pseudo-Aelius Aristides provides, it appears that the definition of a typical period remains unchanged. Specifically, the models of periods provided in the *Περὶ τοῦ πολιτικοῦ λόγου* have a key element that is placed at the end as well as, for some of them, Gorgianic figures, meaning that they perfectly correspond to the typical examples of periods found in the previous treatises. We have also noted the closeness between Pseudo-Aristides’ and Demetrius’ respective definitions of the period. The major change that Pseudo-Aelius Aristides introduces consists of formalising the existence of a third style that stands between the two extremes of “periodic” and “loose” styles. This third style clarifies the status of those sayings that are not really “disjointed” but are too loose to be truly considered periods.

10. Hermogenes, *On Ideas* (*Περὶ ιδεῶν / De ideai [Id.]* – late 2nd century or early 3rd century CE)⁴⁴³

The *Περὶ ιδεῶν* is a treatise in two volumes focused on *elocutio*, dated to the late 2nd or early 3rd century CE.⁴⁴⁴ It was transmitted as part of a set known as the “Hermogenic Corpus,” which consists of five works compiled by an unknown rhetorician in the 5th or 6th century: *Προγυμνάσματα* (*On Rhetorical Exercises*), *Περὶ στάσεων* (*On Stases*), *Περὶ εὐρέσεως* (*On Invention*), *Περὶ ιδεῶν* (*On Ideas*), and *Περὶ μεθόδου δεινότητος* (*On the Method of Speaking Effectively*).⁴⁴⁵ These works are traditionally attributed to a certain

⁴⁴³ The first and only English translation of this treatise is that by C. W. Wooten (*Hermogenes’ On Types of Style*), based on the Greek text established in the early-20th century by H. Rabe. For a critical edition that includes a French translation, see *Corpus Rhetoricum, Tome IV: Prolégomènes au De Ideis. Hermogène, Les catégories stylistiques du discours* (De Ideis). *Synopses des exposés sur les Ideai* (ed. and trans. M. Patillon; Les Belles Lettres]. The translations below are mine, based on the Greek text established by Patillon and also referenced according to this edition; at certain places, however, I am indebted to C. W. Wooten’s translation.

⁴⁴⁴ On the issue of the date of *Περὶ ιδεῶν*, see Patillon, *Les catégories stylistiques du discours*, VIII–IX.

⁴⁴⁵ A critical edition of the entire hermogenic corpus, including a French translation, has been published by M. Patillon in the collection “Les Belles Lettres”: *Corpus Rhetoricum* (ed. and trans. M. Patillon; 5 vol.; 2008–2014). See also the extensive study by Patillon entitled *La théorie du discours chez*

Hermogenes, who is generally assumed to be Hermogenes of Tarsus (160–ca. 225 CE), a sophist described by Philostratus as a child prodigy whose oratorical powers suddenly vanished when he reached manhood.⁴⁴⁶ In reality, the Hermogenic corpus contains works of different authors. Modern scholars consider only *On Ideas* and *On Stases* to be likely works of Hermogenes.⁴⁴⁷

The *Περὶ ἰδεῶν* presents in detail seven different “types” or “categories” of style (ἰδέαι): clarity, grandeur, beauty, rapidity, ethos, sincerity, and force.⁴⁴⁸ For each of these types, Hermogenes gives numerous examples to illustrate his recommendations for word choice, the use of figures, rhythm, as well as the different characteristics of cōla, including their length and how they should be arranged to compose texts.

10.1. *Periodic and non-periodic style*

10.1.1. *Validation of both styles*

Hermogenes fully recognises the possibility that cōla and commata might stand outside a periodic structure, even though he does not use a specific term to designate this non-periodic style. This point is made clear in a comment concerning the cōla belonging to “purity” (a type of style that is a subcategory of “clarity”). The cōla of “purity,” he explains, “should be short, in the range of commas, and each of them should contain a complete thought. Long cōla and periods are inappropriate for purity.”⁴⁴⁹ The last remark logically implies that it is not only possible for cōla (and commata) to stand outside periodic structures, but that sometimes they *should* be used in such a way. That

Hermogène le rhéteur. Essai sur les structures linguistiques de la rhétorique ancienne. The treatises *On Invention* and *On the Method of Speaking Effectively* have been translated into English by G. A. Kennedy (*Invention and Method: Two Rhetorical Treatises from the Hermogenic Corpus*); *On Ideas* has been translated into English by C. W. Wooten (*Hermogenes’ On Types of Style*); *On Stases* has been translated into English by M. Heath (*Hermogenes on Issues: Strategies of Argument in Later Greek Rhetoric*).

⁴⁴⁶ Philostratus, *Lives of the Sophists* II,7; cf. the article Ἐρμογένης in the Souda. On the life and work of Hermogenes, see G. A. Kennedy, *The Art of Rhetoric in the Roman World*, 619–633, or J. B. Davis, “Hermogenes of Tarsus.” Cf. M. Patillon, who considers the attribution to Hermogenes of Tarsus unlikely, but nevertheless suggests that the treatise should be dated to the late 2nd century or early 3rd century CE (*La théorie du discours chez Hermogène le rhéteur*, 13–17; cf. Id., “Introduction” [*Les catégories stylistiques du discours*], VIII–IX).

⁴⁴⁷ G. A. Kennedy, *Invention and Method*, xiii.

⁴⁴⁸ Different translations have been proposed for ἰδέαι, including “forms,” “ideas” “types,” and “categories” of style; see M. Patillon, “Introduction” (*Arts rhétoriques* I), 23, n. 41. C. W. Wooten retains “types of style” (thus the title of her translation: *On Types of Style*); G. A. Kennedy first suggested “forms” (G. A. Kennedy, *The Art of Rhetoric in the Roman World*, 630–632), and then “ideas” (G. A. Kennedy, “On Invention: Introduction,” xiii). Patillon prefers the French term “catégories stylistiques,” which he retains for the title of his critical edition (*Les catégories stylistiques du discours*).

⁴⁴⁹ *Id.* I,3,17.

being said, it is unclear whether Hermogenes works with a simple bipartition of style (periodic vs non-periodic), or would rather concur with Pseudo-Aelius Aristides in distinguishing three (or even more?) different kinds of style.⁴⁵⁰ In the discussion below, the expression “non-periodic style” will be used as a simplified means to refer to all sayings that do not belong to the periodic style.

10.1.2. *Periodic cōla vs non-periodic cōla*

In Hermogenes’ discussion on “purity,” we find examples of rearrangements that illustrate the difference between periodic and non-periodic style. Here is one of them, with the first formulation being periodic: Κροΐσου ὄντος Λυδοῦ μὲν γένος / παιδὸς δὲ Ἀλυάττεω / τυράννου δὲ ἐθνῶν τῶν ἐντος Ἑλλοσ ποταμοῦ ... (“Since Croesus was a Lydian by birth / son of Alyattes / ruler of those nations on the side of the Halys River [...]”).⁴⁵¹ In this case, the thought that started in the first cōlon is left hanging in the air, owing to the use of the absolute genitive at the beginning, which necessitates that something more be supplied. According to Hermogenes, this is not what the cōla of purity should look like. Rather, the appropriate version would consist of autonomous cōla and/or commata: Κροΐσος ἦν Λυδοῦ μὲν γένος. Παιὶς δὲ Ἀλυάττεω. Τύραννος δὲ ἐθνέων... (“Croesus was a Lydian by birth. He was the son of Alyattes. He ruled the nations...”).⁴⁵² In the latter formulation, each cōlon forms a complete thought in itself, meaning that it can stand on its own as a short sentence. Concretely, the rearrangement of words consists of removing all the relationships of syntactic dependency between the cōla: as a result, the period has disappeared, being replaced by a succession of autonomous cōla. This example of rearrangement closely recalls Demetrius’ discussion regarding the crucial role of *synthesis* in periodic style, as well as the examples of rearrangements he provided.⁴⁵³

It is especially noteworthy that the cōla of purity are said to contain a complete thought (“...each of them should contain a complete thought”)⁴⁵⁴: this too recalls Demetrius, especially his remark that the cōla of disjointed style are “complete in

⁴⁵⁰ Cf. Ael. Arist., *Pol.* 167.

⁴⁵¹ *Id.* I,3,12. This is a modified version of Herodotus, *Histories*, I,6,1 (the division into cōla is mine). See another example of rearrangement a few lines after, in *Id.* I,3,14–17.

⁴⁵² In fact, this “rearrangement” corresponds to Herodotus’ original version. Cf. Aristotle and Demetrius’s comments that Herodotus composes a-periodically: Arist., *Rhet.* III,9,2 ; Dem., *Eloc.* 12.

⁴⁵³ Dem, *Eloc.* II; see above, 3.4.2.

⁴⁵⁴ καθ’ ἑαυτὰ ἀπαρτίζοντα τὰς ἐννοίας (*Id.* I,3,17).

themselves.”⁴⁵⁵ In contrast, when Hermogenes develops on “beauty,” he states that the *côla* are “woven together [...] in such a way that none of them contains a complete thought, but they must all be taken together.”⁴⁵⁶ Indeed, a look at the models of “beautiful” sayings—many of which are from Demosthenes—reveals that their *côla* are typically interlinked at the syntactic level. Moreover, among the devices that create “beautiful *côla*,” Hermogenes lists the same elements that his predecessors mentioned as typical of the periodic style: the abundance of figures, including sound echoes between the *côla*⁴⁵⁷ and hyperbaton,⁴⁵⁸ the avoidance of hiatus,⁴⁵⁹ and a quasi-metrical rhythm.⁴⁶⁰

10.2. Length of *côla* and periods

10.2.1. *Côla* and *commata*

The length of *côla* varies considerably, depending on the type of style (*îδέα*), as each type has its own rules. Although no indication of the number of syllables is given, Hermogenes’ systematic and precise recommendations regarding which length is appropriate to each *îδέα* makes it possible to get a precise picture of what he considers “normal,” “very short,” “quite short,” “quite long” or “long.” Hermogenes usually applies the label “short” to the *côla* that are under 12–13 syllables.⁴⁶¹ We can note that this limit corresponds to the lower limit for a hexametre verse.⁴⁶² Those *côla* under 7 or 8 syllables are considered “very short” and preferably called *commata*.⁴⁶³ *Commata* appear to have no minimum length: there are instances of only one word or very short expressions of no more than 2 or 3 syllables.⁴⁶⁴ While the formal distinction between

⁴⁵⁵ See Dem., *Eloc.* 2.

⁴⁵⁶ *Id.* I,12,41.

⁴⁵⁷ *Id.* I,12,11–20. Hermogenes groups different kinds of sound echoes under the generic term “*pariosis*,” which was used by the other rhetoricians to designate equality of length.

⁴⁵⁸ *Id.* I,12,35.

⁴⁵⁹ *Id.* I,12,45.

⁴⁶⁰ *Id.* I,12,46.

⁴⁶¹ See the examples given for “clarity” (*Id.* I,3–4), a style for which short *côla* are recommended: most of the *côla* are under 12–13 syllables (see esp. 3,17 and 4,17). I say “most of the *côla*” because Hermogenes accepts the presence of some long *côla* even in “clarity.” Cf. the passage concerning “noble *côla*” (*Id.* I,6,30).

⁴⁶² Cf. Demetrius, *Eloc.* 4, who compares *côla* with hexametres; cf. also Cic., *Or. Brut.* 222, and Quint., *Inst.* IX,4,124–125.

⁴⁶³ Throughout the treatise, units under 6 syllables are systematically called *commata*, while units above 9 syllables are systematically called *côla*: see e.g. I,12,19.

⁴⁶⁴ Such an extreme shortness remains an exception. Hermogenes notes that the term “comma” is not completely appropriate for referring to these units (*Id.* I,8,10).

the cōlon and the comma is clearly one of length,⁴⁶⁵ Hermogenes also mentions that the effect of a discourse made of commata differs from that of a discourse made of cōla. Specifically, the use of commata is associated with vehemence, exactly as was the case in Demetrius, the *Rhetoric for Herennius* and Cicero.⁴⁶⁶ Then, from around 16–17 syllables, cōla are qualified as “quite long.” They are then considered “long” when they are above 20 syllables.⁴⁶⁷ The longest cōlon that can be identified with certainty in the *Περὶ ἰδεῶν* comprises 33 syllables.⁴⁶⁸ We can note that these lengths correspond well with those that appear in the previous treatises.

10.2.2. *Maximum length of periods*

In contrast with the terms κῶλον and κόμμα, which appear numerous times throughout the treatise, the term περίοδος is rarely used by Hermogenes. This causes some ambiguity concerning the periodic status of the sayings. Nonetheless, it is still possible to offer a few remarks based on those examples with a clear periodic status, owing to the close interweaving of their cōla. Hermogenes accepts long periods, up to around 90 syllables at least. For instance, this long Demosthenean period from the *First Olynthiac* receives his approval:

Τὸ μὲν γὰρ πολλὰ ἀπολωλεκέναι κατὰ τὸν πόλεμον τῆς ἡμετέρας ἀμελείας ἂν τις θεῖη δικαίως / τὸ δὲ μήτε πάλαι τοῦτο πεπονθέναι / πεφηνέναι τέ τινα ἡμῖν συμμαχίαν τούτων ἀντίρροπον, ἂν βουλώμεθα χρῆσθαι / τῆς παρ’ ἐκείνων εὐνοίας εὐεργέτημ’ ἂν ἔγωγε θείην.⁴⁶⁹

⁴⁶⁵ In Hermogenes, it is clear that a comma is nothing but a subcategory of cōla; that is, a cōlon which is especially short, even shorter than short cōla: see e.g. his comments in *Id.* I,3,17 (these kinds of cōla are “almost commata”) and in I,7,19 (“these cōla are better named commata”).

⁴⁶⁶ See e.g. *Id.* I,8,10. Cf. Dem., *Eloc.* 7; *Rhet. Her.* IV,19,27; Cic., *Or. Brut.* 224.

⁴⁶⁷ See notably the examples given for “brilliance,” where long cōla are recommended (*Id.* I,9,18–19).

⁴⁶⁸ See this cōlon taken from Demosth., *Olynthiac* I,10: τὸ μὲν γὰρ πολλὰ ἀπολωλεκέναι κατὰ τὸν πόλεμον τῆς ἡμετέρας ἀμελείας ἂν τις θεῖη δικαίως (quoted by Hermogenes in *Id.* I,12,15; cf. below, n. 469). Another very long cōlon, of 30 syllables, can be found in *Id.* I,9,8: τοῦτο τὸ ψήφισμα τὸν τότε τῆ πόλει περιστάντα κίνδυνον παρελθεῖν ἐποίησεν ὥσπερ νέφος. Contra M. Patillon, who suggests a radically different interpretation. In his view, this saying contains 3 cōla, which he delineates as follows: τοῦτο τὸ ψήφισμα / τὸν τότε τῆ πόλει περιστάντα κίνδυνον / παρελθεῖν ἐποίησεν ὥσπερ νέφος (*La théorie du discours chez Hermogène*, 193). However, such an analysis is inconsistent with Hermogene’s own description of this saying as consisting of one single cōlon (*Id.* I,9,8). Note that Patillon understands cōla purely as “flow units” (French “unités de débit”; see Patillon, *La théorie du discours chez Hermogène*, 188–195), which leads him to place a boundary whenever a break seems necessary, regardless of how short this break may be.

⁴⁶⁹ “To have lost so many possessions in the war anyone would attribute to our negligence / but that we did not suffer this long ago / and that the alliance with these men offers us some compensation if we are willing to take advantage of it / I would attribute this good fortune to the benevolence of the gods.” This is an extract of Demosth., *Olynthiac* I,10 (= *Or.* I,10), quoted by Hermogenes in *Id.* I,12,15. The division

Regarding the number of *côla* that a period can comprise, all we can say with certainty is that Hermogenes accepts periods extending up to 4 *côla* *at least*, as is the case in the example above, as well as in the following example, which is this time taken from Demosthenes' *De corona*: τὸ λάβεῖν οὖν τὰ διδόμενα / ὁμολογῶν ἔννομον εἶναι / τὸ χάριν τούτων ἀποδοῦναι / παρανόμων γράφῃ; (“Therefore to accept gifts / you consider this legal / but to feel gratitude for them / you indict this as illegal?”).⁴⁷⁰ Hermogenes specifies that this saying begins with 3 short *côla* of 9 syllables and ends with a comma of 6 syllables.⁴⁷¹ But what about the maximum number of *côla* and/or *commata* that a period can contain? There are two examples found in the same passage that might suggest that Hermogenes approves of periods of at least 7 *côla*. Below is one of them:

οὐ τοίνυν μόνον μὴ Λεύκον ἀδικηθῆ / δεῖ σκοπεῖν / ᾧ φιλοτιμίας ἔνεκα ἢ περὶ τῆς δωρεᾶς
 σπουδῆ γένοιτ' ἄν / οὐ χρείας / ἀλλὰ καὶ εἴ τις ἄλλος εὖ μὲν ἐποίησεν ὑμᾶς / εὖ πράττων /
 εἰς δέον δὲ νῦν γέγονεν αὐτῷ τὸ παρ' ὑμῶν λαβεῖν τότε τὴν ἀτέλειαν.⁴⁷²

To be clear, in this example Hermogenes does not explicitly state the number of *côla* it contains or where the boundaries between them are situated. Nevertheless, his comment that “all of the *côla* are short, except for the last one,” supports the view that Hermogenes approves of periods of at least seven *côla*. At the very least, this saying must comprise more than four *côla*; otherwise, the comment on the shortness of *côla* would make no sense.⁴⁷³ In sum, the author of the *Περὶ ἰδεῶν* stands on the side of Cicero and Quintilian when it comes to the length of periods, insofar as he does not stipulate an upper limit in terms of the number of *côla*.

10.3. Results

In view of the aim of this study, the interest of the *Περὶ ἰδεῶν* mainly lies in the fact that it attests to the stability of the rhetoricians' discourses on colometry up until the turn of the 3rd century BCE. This continuity not only concerns terminology, but also the

into 4 *côla* is easily established on the basis of Hermogenes's comment (*Id.* I,12,15.). See also two periods of around 80 syllables in 12,41 and 12,42.

⁴⁷⁰ *Id.* I,12,19.

⁴⁷¹ Cf. Dionysius of Halicarnassus, *Comp.* 7,6, who quotes the same example and offers the same analysis.

⁴⁷² *Id.*, I,12,41 (“Not only that Leucon is not treated unjustly / we must ensure / whose enthusiasm for this grant comes from his sense of honor / not from need / but also whether someone else treated you well / when this one was prosperous / but has now come to need the exemption that he received from you then”); cf. also the second example in 12,42.

⁴⁷³ Cf. Patillon (*Les catégories stylistiques du discours*, p. 121, n. 532), who even delineates 12 *côla* in this period! Cf. also footnote 468 above.

characteristics of *côla*, *commata* and periods. With regard to the distinction between periodic and non-periodic style, we have seen that the nature of the syntactic links between the *côla* plays a key element, as was the case in Hermogenes' predecessors. Specifically, when they are part of a period, the *côla* tend to be interlinked at the syntactic level, but when they stand outside periods, the *côla* are autonomous from a syntactic point of view, and thereby correspond to short sentences. With respect to the length of *côla*, Hermogenes' systematic comments on the appropriate length for each type of style (*ιδέα*) provide a valuable foundation for determining the boundaries outside which the *côla* are considered very short (under 7–8 syllables; such *côla* are better named *commata*), short (under 12–13 syllables), “quite long” (from 16–17 syllables) or long (above 20 syllables). This only strengthens the idea expressed in the previous treatises that the ideal or standard length of *côla* corresponds to the extent of a hexametre verse. Regarding the length of periods, we have seen that Hermogenes accepts long ones, at least up to 90 syllables. Finally, with respect to the number of *côla* that a period can comprise, he seems to agree with Cicero and Quintilian by not fixing an upper limit.⁴⁷⁴

II. Synthesis and Conclusion

In this chapter, we have looked closely at the data from some ten treatises, covering the period from the mid-4th century BCE (Aristotle's *Rhetoric*) up until the turn of the 3rd century CE (Hermogenes' *On Ideas*). We have also arranged these treatises in chronological order, which has allowed us to observe both the continuities and the variations between them. This survey has shown that the rhetoricians' remarks on colometry are relatively stable throughout the centuries. I would even say that these remarks are unusually stable, given the extend timeframe considered. This stability is especially evident in the rhetorical works from the time of Demetrius onwards, as the Aristotelean doctrine differs from those of his successors on many points, as was shown above.

The notion of the “*côlon*” (Latin: *membrum*) is especially stable: for all rhetoricians this represents the primary building block of prose texts, being at the same time a prosodic unit to be uttered in a single breath (as an order of magnitude, *côla* have the length of a hexametre verse) and a unit of information presenting relative semantico-syntactic independence (typically a clause or a phrase qualified by a dependent). The

⁴⁷⁴ See Cic., *Or. Brut.* 221–222; Quint., *Inst.* 9,4,125.

notion that the “comma” (Latin: *incisum* or *caesum*)⁴⁷⁵ consists of a short cōlon is also stable.⁴⁷⁶

Things get more complicated when it comes to determining how such cōla and commata should be combined to form texts. While all the rhetoricians seem to recognise the possibility that cōla and commata can either be interwoven within “periods” (περίοδοι)⁴⁷⁷ or simply put side by side outside any periodic structure,⁴⁷⁸ there are some discrepancies with respect to the very concept of the period. Specifically, the rhetoricians agree on a core definition: a period is a saying that consists of many cōla (and/or commata), which together convey a complete thought. They also share the idea that periods cannot extend *ad infinitum*. Rather, their length is limited by the breathing capacity of the speakers.⁴⁷⁹ However, the exact definition of the period differs in two key ways.

First, there is a debate on the number of cōla that a period can comprise. Aristotle recognises only the monocōlon and the dicōloi periods. Demetrius adds the tricōloi and the tetracōloi periods. Later rhetoricians all follow Demetrius by recognising that periods may extend up to 4 cōla at least.⁴⁸⁰ Some even go further (for instance, Cicero, Quintilian, Pseudo-Aelius Aristides, and Hermogenes), by setting no maximum limit in terms of the number of cōla. We have also seen that the concept of the monocōlon period is often considered problematic, with some rhetoricians denying the possibility that a single cōlon can be a period, either implicitly (so Cicero and Alexander) or explicitly (so Aquila Romanus).⁴⁸¹

Second, there is a debate as to how cōla must be combined if the resulting combination is to deserve the name “period.” In his *Rhetoric*, Aristotle works with a very strict understanding: not only is the extent of the period limited to 2 cōla, but he also

⁴⁷⁵ These are the two most common Latin equivalents to the Greek κόμμα, used notably in Cicero and Quintilian. The *author ad Herennium* employs *articulus* (*Rhet. Her.* IV,19,27).

⁴⁷⁶ Note, however, that some treatises preserve traces of an alternative definition of the comma as being a subpart of the cōlon. See Quintilian, who alludes to this alternative definition but rejects it (*Inst.* IX,4,122); cf. Long., *Rhet.* fr. 48, l. 329–339 [ed. Patillon]; Aqu. Rom., *Fig.* 27,32–28,5 Halm [= p. 29 Elice].

⁴⁷⁷ Latin rhetoricians use numerous terms to designate the period: *continuatio*, *ambitus*, *comprehensio*, *comprensio*, *circuitus*, *circumitus*, *circumscripio*, *circumductus*, *conclusio*, as well as the transliteration of the Greek term, *periohodos* (see Cic., *Or.* 204 and 208; Quint., *Inst.* IX,4,124 and IX,4,22).

⁴⁷⁸ Note, however, that Aristotle (*Rhet.* III,9) defines the cōlon solely in relation to the period and therefore remains unclear on the appropriate terminology for the sayings of non-periodic style.

⁴⁷⁹ See e.g. *Rhet. Her.* IV,12,18; Cic., *De or.* III, 191; Quint., *Inst.* IX,4,124–125.

⁴⁸⁰ A possible exception is the *author ad Herennium*: see the discussion above, under section 4.4.2.

⁴⁸¹ See Cic., *Or. Brut.* 225; Alex., *Fig.* 28; cf. also Aquila Romanus, *Fig.* 28,14–18 Halm [= p. 31 Elice]. Cf. also Dem., *Eloc.* 17, who is careful to clarify the difference between a monocōlon period and a simple cōlon.

states that the period should be rhythmical and possess “a beginning and an end in itself.”⁴⁸² Concretely, the Aristotelean period is a highly codified unit, which typically consists of a binary structure with *côla* that exhibit one or more of the so-called Gorgianic figures (antithesis, paromoiosis, parisosis), and with extremities that are in principle marked by paeons. Sayings that lack “a beginning and an end in themselves” are rejected as belonging to the non-periodic style, a style that Aristotle calls “sewn (εἰρομένη) *lexis*” and considers unpleasant.⁴⁸³ In contrast, Demetrius’ *Περὶ ἑρμηνείας* reveals a much broader conception of the period, one that is, in certain respects, closer to the modern concept of a “complex sentence.”⁴⁸⁴ In fact, according to the Demetrian line of thought, periods can be more or less sophisticated, or, to borrow his metaphor of a circular race, periods can be more or less “circular.”⁴⁸⁵ Concretely, while the shape of archetypal periods evokes a circle (fluid texture, delay of a key element until the end, rhythmical clausula, balanced *côla*, and sometimes also antithesis and/or sound echoes at the extremities), Demetrius also describes periods with loosely connected *côla* and ends that are only barely discernible. Such periods, he explains, represent a midpoint between the “interwoven” (κατεστραμμένη, i.e., periodic) and the “disjointed” (διηρημένη, i.e., non-periodic) style. In the works of later rhetoricians, the metaphor of the circle becomes a widespread means to refer to the period.⁴⁸⁶ Several rhetoricians, including at least Quintilian and Dionysius of Halicarnassus, also adopt the Demetrian notion that periods can be more or less “circular.” By contrast, Pseudo-Aelius Aristides works with a stricter definition: he keeps the term “period” for typical periods and theorises the existence of a third style that is an intermediary between the periodic and disjointed styles. Under this third style he classifies those sayings that are not typically periodic but are not sufficiently disconnected from each other to fall under the umbrella of “disjointed style.” For the other rhetoricians, it is unclear where exactly they would place the boundary between periodic and non-periodic styles.

When it comes to non-periodic style, we have seen that Demetrius’ recommendations greatly differ from those of Aristotle. Aristotle considers non-periodic style to be unpleasant because of its “endless” or “unlimited” aspect and therefore recommends that texts should be composed only using periods. Demetrius, by

⁴⁸² Arist., *Rhet.* III,9,3.

⁴⁸³ Arist., *Rhet.* III,9,2.

⁴⁸⁴ See the discussion above, sections 3.2.2 to 3.2.5.

⁴⁸⁵ Dem., *Eloc.* II; cf. also *ibid.*, §19–21.

⁴⁸⁶ On the metaphors used to refer to periods from Aristotle to Cicero, see M. Heckenkamp, “Περίοδος und *continuatio*: Der Wandel der Metaphorik und der Konzeption der Periode von Aristoteles zu Cicero.”

contrast, recommends that we should alternate between the two styles, using a balanced mix of periods and disjointed *côla*. Later rhetoricians all agree with Demetrius that periods are not appropriate in every instance. We have also noted that the models of non-periodic style the later rhetoricians provide align perfectly with those presented by Demetrius: specifically, the non-periodic *côla* are autonomous from a semantico-syntactic point of view, and thereby correspond to what we would now label short sentences.⁴⁸⁷

To sum up, there seems to be a gap between the theory on colometry outlined in Aristotle's *Rhetoric*, on the one hand, and the theories found in later treatises, on the other hand. It seems that Demetrius initiated a doctrine that would then remain (relatively) stable for a few centuries. The differences are especially striking when defining the notion of the period, which Demetrius and apparently all of his successors define much more broadly than Aristotle, both in terms of its length and characteristic features.⁴⁸⁸ That being said, Aristotle's descriptions in *Rhet.* III,9 seem so codified that we may wonder whether they actually reflect the stylistic practices of his contemporaries, or rather represent the Aristotelean ideal of what prose texts should look like. Aristotle's strong rejection of the "sewn" *lexis* favours the second option. Indeed, the very fact that he feels the need to reject the non-periodic style and to explain why this is unpleasant⁴⁸⁹ suggests that this "old" style was, in fact, still widely used by his contemporaries!

We have now answered the question raised in the introduction of this chapter. In view of the above investigation, there is ample justification to speak of *the* ancient system of colometry or *the* ancient theory of *côla*, *commata*, and periods, in the singular, and to imagine that a theoretical framework was used by rhetoricians of the Hellenistic and Roman periods to understand the micro-structure of prose texts. Or, if we wish to be more careful, we could specify that this statement holds true at least for the timeframe between Demetrius (sometime in the late 2nd or early 3rd century BCE [?])⁴⁹⁰ and Hermogenes (turn of the 3rd century CE). The issue of how stable the theory remained after the 3rd century CE, or rather how it may have evolved, exceeds the limits of our study. If we optimistically assume that the rhetorical treatises are not completely

⁴⁸⁷ This holds true at least for Cicero (see above, section 5.3.3), Quintilian (see above, sections 7.1.1–7.1.2), Pseudo-Aristides (if we consider his "loose" style; see above, section 9.1.1) and Hermogenes (see above, section 10.2.1).

⁴⁸⁸ See also in this sense P. Chiron, *Un rhéteur méconnu*, 79–116.

⁴⁸⁹ Arist., *Rhet.* III,9,3.

⁴⁹⁰ See above, footnote 87.

disconnected from actual practices, we can assume that this theory of structuration reflects widespread conventions of composition for Greek and Latin authors, as well as widespread guidelines of interpretation for readers and listeners. That being said, the question as to what extent early Christian texts respected those conventions is still another issue, which should be addressed through a close examination of their micro-structure in light of the theories exposed in the treatises. In the limits of this study, I will only address the specific case of Paul's letters: this will be the task of Chapter 4.

CHAPTER 3

Towards a Method of Colometric Analysis

I. Introduction: Purpose and Methodology

I.I. Purpose of this chapter

Our exploration of the rhetorical treatises has provided copious information concerning ancient colometry. Taken together, these enable us to get a relatively precise picture of how people familiar with the Græco-Roman rhetorical conventions used to conceive of the micro-structure of texts in prose.¹ We have proposed that these data can serve as a basis for proceeding to *colometric analysis*, understood as a modern analysis of the colometric structure of ancient texts in Greek or in Latin. Concretely, the aim of this chapter is to develop a set of criteria for cōla and periods² delineation that best reproduces the ancient conventions of structuration—one that both correct and go beyond the guidelines currently proposed in the field of “sound mapping” of the New Testament.³ Together, these criteria form what might be called a *method of colometric analysis*.

To be clear, the notion of reproduction should here be understood purely in terms of the result rather than the process. There is no claim to reproduce something like a “method of analysis” that ancient readers would have applied when preparing a text for delivery. The very idea of a *method of colometric analysis* is not present in the treatises and is certainly foreign to both ancient rhetoricians and readers. However, as modern exegetes, we need criteria to make choices of delineation that do not rely too much on our modern habits of understanding the micro-structure of texts in terms of clauses and sentences. The intended result of our method is to obtain a proposed structure for a given text (a “colometric disposition”) that most closely aligns with the structure that people familiar with the Graeco-Latin stylistical conventions would have proposed if they had discussed the micro-structure of that text.

¹ On my use of the term “text,” see above in the general introduction, footnote 10.

² Since the intention of this study is to analyse the colometric structure of Greek texts, the discussion will focus on the case of Greek, even if most of the remarks would also be valid for Latin texts. For the same reason, I will favour the Greek terminology throughout the chapter.

³ Lee and Scott, *Sound Mapping the New Testament*, 167–195, esp. 169–173; Nässelqvist, *Public Reading in Early Christianity*, 119–180, esp. 126–140.

1.2. Between too restrictive and too flexible: The challenge of developing appropriate criteria

Describing *côla*, *commata*, and periods in general terms is relatively easy. We could, for example, say that a *côlon* is the primary building block of the discourse, consisting of a short semantic unit meant to be uttered in a single breath. A comma might be described as a shortened *côlon* whose usage is often associated with vigorous or even vehement passages. As for a period, we may define it as a combination of several *côla* and/or *commata* which conveys a complete thought, whose extent is limited by the respiratory capacity of the speakers, and which is the object of stylistic elaboration.⁴ The ability to delineate those units in a given text, however, is a much more complex task, because we are confronted with the difficulty that the *côlon* and the period are highly flexible notions. Indeed, *côla* have extremely variable lengths, ranging from a few syllables (in which case they are better called *commata*) up to some 30 syllables. They usually encompass an entire clause, but this is not an absolute rule. In addition, *côla* can either take place within a period or succeed one another in a “disjointed” manner. Periods also have variable lengths, depending on how many *côla* they comprise. They typically exhibit figures such as hyperbaton in the form of the delay of a key element up to the end, antithesis, *pariosis* (length equality), or *paromoiosis* (sound echoes), but this is not always the case. Moreover, within a period, the *côla* are most often syntactically interlinked by means of subordination or pairs of particles, but again this is not uniform. The list of complexities could go on.

In order to develop an efficient method of colometric analysis and not a caricature of ancient conventions of structuration, the challenge is to formulate criteria that both reflect the different tendencies observed in the treatises and take the flexibility of *côla* and periods into account.⁵ Therefore, when establishing the criteria for delineation, it is necessary first to distinguish between broad criteria that should always be respected, and on the other hand more restricted ones that only correspond to tendencies. It is necessary to distinguish between those features whose presence is binding in regard to the delineation choices (e.g., the presence of an antithesis is arguably a sufficient criterion to group two *côla* within a period),⁶ and those features that represent only clues for delineation (e.g., the presence of

⁴ For all these elements of definition, see the “synthesis and conclusion” in Chapter 2, section II.

⁵ It is precisely this balance that the pioneering works in the field of sound mapping have failed to reach, which has resulted in guidelines and criteria that are often either too broad to be efficient (e.g. the description of the period in Lee and Scott [see the discussion below, section 3.2]) or overly strict (e.g. the description of the period in Nässelfqvist [see the discussion below, section 3.2] or the syntactic description of the *côlon* in both Lee and Scott and Nässelfqvist [see the discussion below, section 2.2]).

⁶ See below, section 3.4.1.

sound echoes on subsequent cōla is not a sufficient criterion to link those cōla within a period).⁷ In other words, the approach ought to be multi-levelled, with criteria classified according to their relative importance.

In the discussion below, I will formulate a series of rules that collectively serve as a criteriology for delineating cōla and periods. I will call “laws” (L) the rules that are absolute (i.e., the assertions labelled “L” are always valid and should be consistently respected). In contrast, I will call “tendencies” (T) the rules that are non-absolute (i.e., the assertions labelled “T” are valid most of the time, but not always). Some laws are always applicable (e.g., the minimal and the maximal length for cōla), while others refer to the presence of an optionnal feature and thereby apply only when the feature in question is present (e.g., the laws concerning antithesis, which obviously make sense only when there is an antithetic construction). In the same way, some tendencies describe “typical” cōla or periods (e.g., the standard length), while other tendencies concern only the situations where a specific feature is present (e.g., the figure of paromoiosis).

The criteria proposed in this chapter will refer to the categories of length, syntax, and Gorgianic figures (antithesis, pariosis, paromoiosis).⁸ I shall begin by discussing the notion of cōlon (section 2 below), including the subcategory of comma, according to the categories of length and of syntax. I will then address the issue of how we could identify periods (section 3 below), considering successively their length, their syntactic characteristics, and the role of the so-called Gorgianic figures. Finally, a synthetic presentation of all these rules will be proposed in a table as a recapitulation of our results (section 4).

⁷ See below, section 3.4.2.

⁸ It would be tempting to also add the category of prosody, by relying on the correspondence between, on the one hand, the cōlon and the modern concept of *intonational phrase* (IP)—also sometimes called *intonation unit* (IU)—, and on the other hand, the period and the *utterance* (U). These technical terms refer to the theory of prosodic phonology, which involves both how the flow of speech is organised into prosodic units and the interactions between prosody and grammar (see J. Pierrehumbert, *The Phonology and Phonetics of English Intonation*; E. Selkirk, *Phonology and Syntax*; M. Nespor and I. Vogel, *Prosodic Phonology*; D. R. Ladd, *Intonational Phonology*). However, a prosodic approach cannot serve as a solid basis for colometric analysis, as our modern habits of delivering a text obviously do not entirely correspond to the conventions at use in the Graeco-Roman world. Furthermore, the very notion of “modern habits” is problematic: there are considerable variations between languages, meaning that what sounds “natural” in one language might sound “artificial” in another one.

Excursus: Some reflections on the conditions for the “scientificity” of the method⁹

Before discussing the criteria for colometric analysis, it is important to adopt a critical point of view on our research methodology. In fact, we are about to propose a method based on the works of Greek and Latin rhetoricians, and we suggest to apply this method to early Christian texts to explain their inner logic of structuration. Several questions guide the course of the following analysis. What are our theoretical assumptions and working hypotheses and how do we justify them? Where do the difficulties and risks of shortcuts in reasoning lie, and how can we at best prevent from them? More generally, how can we ensure that our method is a scientific one? The below graphic is an attempt to summarise our research methodology, with the process of developing and testing the method being highlighted in orange, and the main questions and difficulties signalled with thin black arrows.

Figure 1: Methodology of Research

⁹ On the conditions for the scientificity of a method in the field of NT studies, see J. Zumstein, “L’interprétation du Nouveau Testament,” 51–52.

(1) *Rhetoricians' theories vs actual practices*

One of the basic assumptions of our study is that the rhetorical treatises accurately describe authorial practices of composition. In other words, the adopted methodology assumes that the rhetoricians' theories are not too disconnected from actual practices. There are a few elements in the treatises that lead us to adopt this assumption. Firstly, we can note that the examples provided are always "real" examples taken from classical literature, not examples made by rhetoricians for the unique purpose of illustrating their theories. Second, the rhetoricians' discourse is not rigid: many rhetoricians recognise the flexibility of the notions that they work with,¹⁰ and some of them even point out the existence of borderline cases.¹¹ Third, the rhetoricians highlighted the variety of style among authors. Taken together, these three points suggest that rhetoricians operated according to a theory that was not purely prescriptive but which mirrored actual practices.

However, it seems reasonable to think that theories tend to be stricter than practices. For this reason, I shall adopt the following principle when discussing the criteria to be used for colometric analysis: when there are disagreements between rhetoricians (e.g. as concerns the number of cōla that a period can comprise or the definition of the period) I will retain the broader definitions, as they are more inclined to reflect the variety of practices. This means notably that little weight will be given to Aristotle's doctrine, since, as we have previously seen, the *Rhetoric* contains a theory on colometry that is much stricter than those found in later treatises.¹²

(2) *Adequation between the approach and the object of study*

As with every method that claims to be scientific, we have to question the *adequation between the approach* (i.e., the colometric approach)¹³ and the *object of study*. We have started this research with the undelying hypothesis that early Christian texts in general are composed colometrically, meaning that they follow the same conventions as other Greek prose texts from the same time era with respect to micro-structure. Put another way, the very idea of applying the categories of cōlon and period to NT texts presupposes that these texts are actually structured in cōla and periods. Indeed, this was a necessary working hypothesis to start with—and this hypothesis is reasonable from a socio-cultural point of view, as was seen in Chapter 1.¹⁴ Yet, we cannot simply assume that early Christian authors all used the Graeco-Latin rhetorical theory. We may imagine that some of them were not especially attentive to the issue of micro-structure or may

¹⁰ We may think of the discussion on the maximum length of periods in Cicero and Quintilian (Cic., *Or. Brut.* 221–222; Quint., *Inst.* IX,4,124–125), of the passages on long and short cōla in Demetrius (*Eloc.* 4–9), or, still in Demetrius, on the discussion on the different kinds of periods (*Eloc.* 19–21).

¹¹ See the typology of periods presented in Dem., *Eloc.* 21, where Demetrius explains that the dialogue period stands somewhere between the periodic and the disjointed style.

¹² See above, Chapter 2, section 2.

¹³ I say "approach" rather than "method" because the issue of adequation does not concern specifically the specific method of colometric analysis proposed in our study, but rather the very idea of approaching NT texts using the notions of cōlon and period.

¹⁴ See above, Chapter 1, section 3.1.3.

have made use of other codes of structuration, that either belong to another rhetorical tradition (a Semitic tradition?) or were used in more “popular” classes. Further, we may wonder whether all NT texts were designed with an aural reception in mind. If this were not the case, would it still make sense to look for aural structuring devices in those “mute” writings? With respect to Paul’s letters more specifically, one additional difficulty is their very nature as letters. For sure, it is almost certain that these letters were intended to be read aloud at some point—as is strongly suggested, for example, in 1 Th 5:27, where Paul commands that “this letter be read to all the brothers”¹⁵—and also very likely that they were later reread (or “performed”) in liturgical contexts.¹⁶ However, can we simply conclude that Paul conceived his letters as *oral compositions* and thus carefully crafted them by using aural structural devices while also adjusting the length of his sentences to the respiratory capacity of readers? In sum, when analysing the micro-structure of NT texts, it is essential not to lose sight of the possibility that part of them might not respect the stylistic conventions described in the treatises—or respect them only in a loose manner.

How can we ensure that the rhetorical categories of cōlon and periods are adequate for analysing NT texts? There is no better method than empirical tests: we must proceed with colometric analyses of different texts, and then evaluate—for each text/author separately—whether the categories seem appropriate. For that purpose, it is not sufficient to analyse a few verses, but rather long passages; at least one or two entire chapter(s) should be considered. When discussing this issue, it is also crucial to keep in mind the risk of the hermeneutical circle. That is, it is necessary to ensure that we do not find “cōla” and “periods” in a given text just because we are looking for them. In the limits of this study, I will discuss the appropriateness of a colometric approach only for Paul’s letters, based on the case study of 2 Corinthians 10–13. This will be done in Chapter 4 (see esp. the discussion under section 3.1).

(3) *From the treatises to criteria for delineation: Coherence and operationality of the method*

The major challenge of our study resides in converting the data concerning colometry from ancient sources into a modern criteriology. The treatises do not provide ready-to-use criteria, but simply definitions, examples, and series of recommendations. All these data need first to be collected and interpreted (we did that in Chapter 2), and then reformulated in the best possible way in the form of criteria (as follows in the present chapter). Such a process of reformulation obviously contains numerous risks of misunderstanding, simplification, and overinterpretation. For example, we will sometimes be forced to deduce a rule from only a small number of examples, thus risking unaccurately reflecting the rhetoricians’ thoughts. Notably, this will be the case as concerns the maximum length acceptable for cōla: although rhetoricians never make this limit explicit, we need to place a limit to guide our analyses. In order to develop criteria useable by modern exegetes, I will also make an attempt to translate the rhetoricians’ discourse

¹⁵ On this, see S. Buttica, “Que cette lettre soit lue à tous les frères’ (1 Thessaloniens 5,27). Les lettres de Paul et le rôle du lector dans l’Antiquité.” The public reading of a letter seems to have been a normal practice in antiquity (see e.g., Tacitus, *Annals* I,25,3).

¹⁶ On the performance of Jewish letters in Antiquity, see an insightful study in M. L. Miller, *Performances of Ancient Jewish Letters: From Elephantine to MMT*.

in terms of syntactic categories, which runs the risk of not corresponding exactly to what rhetoricians had in mind. Indeed, our method must not only be highly *coherent with the ancient sources* at disposal—a condition that will be ensured by discussing each law and each tendency of the method in light of the data from the treatises—but it should also prove that it is *operational* (i.e., sufficiently precise to permit to guide the choices of delineation).¹⁷ The operability of the method for a given corpus should be checked empirically through testing. In Chapter 4, I will perform this test through the case study of 2 Corinthians 10–13. The ideal means to ensure that the method is effective would involve different persons analysing the same text and evaluating whether they found the same colometric disposition.¹⁸ Within the limits of this study, however, such a test of replicability cannot be undertaken. In place of that, I will discuss the doubts and the difficulties encountered during the application, taking examples from different passages where the criteria might lead to different possibilities of delineation (see Chapter 4, section 3.2).

In the discussion on the delineation criteria below, I will frequently refer to Lee and Scott’s and Nässelqvist’s works, highlighting both the points on which my results concur with theirs and the points on which I have a different interpretation.

2. Identifying Cōla and Commata¹⁹

2.1. Length

2.1.1. The notion of comma

Let us begin by clarifying the difference between the *cōlon* and the *comma* (κόμμα, from κόπτω, “strike” or “cut off” = Latin: *incisum* or *caesum*). In *Sound Mapping*, M. E. Lee and B. B. Scott allude to the comma but do not use the term when commenting on their sound maps. They seem to consider that a comma is simply a very short *cōlon*.²⁰ In contrast, D. Nässelqvist argues that a comma is not a subcategory, but a component of a *cōlon*. He explains that commata are in principle too short to stand alone and should thus either be grouped by twos or be joined to a *cōlon* in order to form a unit of acceptable length.²¹ This

¹⁷ Under the umbrella “operability of the method,” I do not include the issue of exegetical and hermeneutical benefits. The method of colometric analysis aims only to identify *cōla* and periods boundaries, the intended result being simply a “colometric disposition.” Therefore, from a formal point of view, the potential implications and benefits for exegesis are not part of what I call the “method.”

¹⁸ On the rule of reproducibility as a condition for scientific discovery, see K. R. Popper, *The Logic of Scientific Discovery*, 23–24. 66–67. 192–197.

¹⁹ Unless otherwise stated, the translations of ancient texts proposed in this chapter are mine. For the references of the editions used, see the works preceded by an asterisk in the final bibliography.

²⁰ Lee and Scott, *Sound Mapping*, 111.

²¹ Nässelqvist, *Public Reading*, 130; also *ibid.*, 132–133. Note that the *Handbook of Ancient Rhetoric*—which, in contrast to what its title suggests, is clearly focused on ancient Christian literature—also defines the comma

description indeed echoes a conception that seems to have circulated in antiquity (at least among Latin rhetoricians) as attested in Cassius Longinus and Aquila Romanus, as well as in an allusion by Quintilian, who indicates that “most people define it [the incisum] as a part of a membrum.”²² However, when one compares the definitions and examples from the different treatises, such a conception clearly fails to represent a “technical” standard.²³ Pseudo-Demetrius considers the comma simply as a short cōlon, and the same holds true for the author *ad Herennium*, Cicero, Dionysius of Halicarnassus, Quintilian (who explicitly rejects the “popular” definition of the incisum as a part of a membrum), Alexander, Hermogenes, as well as probably for Pseudo-Aelius Aristides.²⁴ In sum, most rhetoricians took the comma to be nothing more than a subcategory of cōlon, whose specificity is to be unusually short. Therefore, when proceeding with colometric analyses of ancient texts, there is no reason to group many commata into a cōlon, or to join a comma to a cōlon.

The length limit between the comma and the cōlon is flexible. In the treatises, there is a certain terminological fluidity concerning units between seven and nine syllables, with some of them being called cōla and others being called commata.²⁵ We can thus formulate the following law:

LI: short cōla of less than 7 syllables are better called commata. Units between 7 and 9 syllables can be considered either cōla or commata.

According to rhetoricians, such shortened cōla are to be used especially in vigorous passages (i.e. when the style is meant to be choppy so as to reflect the vehemence of the words).²⁶ The author of the *Rhetorica ad Herennius* and Cicero even compare the effect of *incisa* to that of stabs, while Demetrius compares short cōla to “a wild beast [who] gathers itself together for

as a subpart of the cōlon: “as the colon is subordinate to the period, so the comma is subordinate to the colon” (G. Rowe, “Style,” 152).

²² Quint. *Inst.* IX,4,122; Long., *Rhet.* fr. 48, 329–339 (ed. Patillon); Aq. Rom., *Fig.*, p. 29, l. 4–11 Elice (= 27,32–28,5 Halm, *RLM*).

²³ See a similar remark in Habinek, *The Colometry of Latin Prose*, 27–28; also see Anderson, *Glossary of Greek Rhetorical Terms*, 101, n. 108.

²⁴ Dem., *Eloc.* 9; Cic., *Or. Brut.* 222–225; Dion. Hal., *Comp.* 26,1; Quint., *Inst.* 9,4,122; Alex., *Fig.* 28,1–5; Herm., *Id.* I,7,19; cf. I,3,17; Ael.-Arist., *Pol.* 168 (see the discussion above, Chapter 2, section 9.2).

²⁵ See, e.g., Cic., *Or. Brut.* 222–225; Dion. Hal., *Comp.*, 26,11–12; Herm., *Id.* I,3,17. The limit is made explicit in Pseudo-Hermogenes, *On Inventio* 4,4 (= p. 184 Rabe), who notes that “a comma consists of from four and five up to six syllables, while anything beyond seven and eight and ten syllables, approaching the length of a trimeter and going up to that of a hexameter, becomes a straight extended colon” (trans. G. A. Kennedy). On the issue of the boundary between cōla and commata, see also the discussion in Du Mesnil, “Begriff der drei Kunstformen der Rede,” 70–72.

²⁶ See, e.g., Dem., *Eloc.* 6–8; cf. also *ibid.*, §241; *Rhet. Her.* IV,19,27; Cic., *Or. Brut.* 224; Herm., *Id.* I,8,10.

an attack.”²⁷ A typical example can be found in the following extract from Cicero’s *Pro Scauro*, which begins with four commata:

Example 1

Domus tibi deerat?	[“Did you lack a house?”]
At habebas.	[Yet you had one.]
Pecunia superabat?	[Was there money left?]
At egebas.	[Yet you were in want.]
Incurristi amens in columnas.	[You have madly dashed against the columns.]
In alienos insanus insanisti.	[You have raved wildly against strangers.]
Depressam, caecam, iacentem domum pluris quam te et quam fortunas tuas aestimasti.	[A fallen, dark and prostrate home] [you thought more valuable than yourself and your fortunes.”] ²⁸

Maxims are also a privileged place for using commata, as in γνῶθι σεαυτόν (“know yourself”), ἔπου θεῶ (“follow God”), or μέτρον ἄριστον (“everything in moderation”).²⁹ Finally, as Demetrius notes, commata are also appropriate when the subject evoked is “small,” such as when Xenophon describes the river Teleboas in these terms: οὗτος δὲ ἦν μέγας μὲν οὐ / καλὸς δὲ (“it was not large / beautiful it was, though”).³⁰

2.1.2. Standard length and acceptable length

M.E. Lee and B.B. Scott do not define length limits for cōla. In the multiple examples of sound maps they provide in *Sound Mapping*, we can observe extremely various lengths, including very short (from 3 syllables)³¹ and very long cōla (up to 50 syllables).³² In contrast, D. Nässelfqvist defines both a standard length (9–23 syllables) and an acceptable length (7–30 syllables).³³ I fully agree with Nässelfqvist, we must set an upper limit for cōla as those

²⁷ *Rhet. Her.* IV,19,27; Cic., *Or. Brut.* 224; Dem., *Eloc.* 8.

²⁸ Cic., *Pro Scauro* XXII,45 (trans. H. M. Hubbell); quoted and analysed by Cicero himself in *Or. Brut.* 222–223, and retaken by Quintilian in *Inst.* IX,4,122.

²⁹ The two first examples are found both in Dem., *Eloc.* 9 and in Alex., *Fig.* 28,3–4 (ed. Spengel); the third example is found in Alex., *Fig.* 28,3–4 (ed. Spengel).

³⁰ Dem., *Eloc.* 6 (= Xen., *Anabasis* IV,4,3). See above, Chapter 2, section 3.1.2.

³¹ Examples of very short cōla are frequent, notably in the sound map of Jn 20 (Lee and Scott, *Sound Mapping*, 269–73): see for instance the first cōlon of period 2 in unit 1 (τρέχει οὖν), or the third cōlon in the same period (καὶ λέγει αὐτοῖς).

³² For long cōla, see e.g. cōlon n°24 in the sound map of Mk 15 (Lee and Scott, *Sound Mapping*, 220: ἦσαν δὲ καὶ γυναῖκες ἀπὸ μακρόθεν θεωροῦσαι, ἐν αἷς καὶ Μαρία ἡ Μαγδαληνὴ καὶ Μαρία ἡ Ἰακώβου τοῦ μικροῦ καὶ Ἰωσήτος μήτηρ καὶ Σαλώμη), or the first cōlon of period 15 in the sound map of Jn 20 (*Ibid.*, 271: οὐσης οὖν ὀψίας τῇ ἡμέρᾳ ἐκείνῃ τῇ μιᾷ σαββάτων καὶ τῶν θυρῶν κεκλεισμένων ὅπου ἦσαν οἱ μαθηταὶ διὰ τὸν φόβον τῶν Ἰουδαίων, ἦλθεν ὁ Ἰησοῦς).

³³ Nässelfqvist, *Public Reading*, 129.

delineated by Lee and Scott are indeed excessively long when compared to ancient habits attested in the rhetorical treatises. As to the maximum length that Nässelqvist suggests (30 syllables), this accurately reflects the examples given by ancient rhetoricians. I would nevertheless opt to extend this limit a little bit up to 35 syllables. Indeed, even if *côla* of more than 30 syllables are an exception in the treatises, there is at least one instance of a 33-syllables *côlon* in Hermogenes,³⁴ a 31-syllables *côlon* in Demetrius,³⁵ and a 33-syllables *côlon* in Pseudo-Herodian.³⁶ Hence, an upper limit set at 35 syllables seems more reasonable so as to include the possibility of exceptionally long *côla*. However, the minimal length of seven syllables that Nässelqvist suggests is less convincing, and thus his claim that Lee and Scott would delineate *côla* that are too short.³⁷ There is no apparent basis in the treatises for such a lower limit. Conversely, there are many examples of *côla* that have less than seven syllables. This includes Aristotle (ἡ ζῶντας ἔξειν),³⁸ Pseudo-Demetrius (ὁ βίος βραχύς, ἡ τέχνη μακρά, ὁ καιρὸς ὀξύς and καλὸς δέ, to cite only a few),³⁹ Dionysius of Halicarnassus (ἡ μόνη ἐλπὶς),⁴⁰ and Cicero and Quintilian (e.g. “at habebas,” “at egebas” and “diximus”).⁴¹ Indeed, such *côla* are “special *côla*” (better called *commata*; see above, section 2.2.1), but it still remain that they stand on their own—either within a period or outside any periodic structure—exactly as “normal-length” *côla* would do. Therefore, we should renounce to define a lower limit for the length of *côla*.

This leaves us with a exceptionnaly large framework (one to 35 syllables), within which it is useful to distinguish a standard length, following Nässelqvist’s proposition.⁴² I would personally suggest the range between seven and 25 syllables.⁴³ Note that this standard length is not to be confused with what rhetoricians considered “ideal length,” which would rather

³⁴ See the example of tetracoloï period in Herm., *Id.* I,12,15: τὸ μὲν γὰρ πολλὰ ἀπολωλεκέναι κατὰ τὸν πόλεμον τῆς ἡμετέρας ἀμελείας ἂν τις θεῖη δικαίως (= Demosth., *Olynthiac* I,10).

³⁵ Dem., *Eloc.* 45: ὁ γὰρ Ἀχελῷος ποταμὸς ῥέων ἐκ Πίνδου ὄρους διὰ Δολοπίας καὶ Ἀγριανῶν καὶ Ἀμφιλόχων (= Thuc., *Pelop.* II,102,2).

³⁶ Herod., *Fig.* 24 (= 93,23–29 Sp., RG III): τίς γὰρ οὐκ ἂν ἠδέως μετὰσχοι στρατιᾶς τῆς ὑπὸ Ἀθηναίων μὲν καὶ Λακεδαιμονίων στρατηγουμένης (= Isocr., *Paneg.* IV,185).

³⁷ Nässelqvist, *Public Reading*, 130, esp. n. 42.

³⁸ Aristotle, *Rhet.* III,9,7 (= Isocr., *Paneg.* 186).

³⁹ Dem., *Eloc.* 4 (= Hippocrates, *Aphorisms* I,1) and 6 (= Xen., *Anabasis* IV,4,3); see above, Chapter 2, footnote 104).

⁴⁰ Dion. Hal., *Comp.* 7,4 (= Thucyd., *Pelop.* III,57,4).

⁴¹ Cic., *Or. Brut.* 223 (= *Pro Scauro* 22) and 225 (= *Pro Cornelio*); see the same examples retaken in Quint., *Inst.*, IX,4,122.

⁴² Nässelqvist, *Public Reading*, 129.

⁴³ Based on my observation of the treatises discussed in Chapter 2, *côla* below or above this interval are significantly less frequent.

correspond to the length of the hexameter verse (i.e., between 12 and 17 syllables, or between 10 and 20 syllables if we consider the approximative length).⁴⁴ We can thus formulate the following rules:

T1: cōla usually comprise between 7 and 25 syllables (= standard length)

L2: cōla do not extend beyond 35 syllables (= acceptable length)

It might also be useful to note the tendency to have balanced cōla within a period. If the equality of length between the cōla constitutes a figure of speech—called *pariosis* or *isocōlon* (see section 3.4.1 below)—typically the cōla are not the exact same length but are still relatively balanced. We can formulate the following tendency:

T2: within a period, cōla tend to be balanced

Note that this tendency holds true for “grand style” and, albeit to a lesser extent, for “middle style.” In contrast, the cōla of “plain style” are unbalanced in principle.⁴⁵

2.2. The description of cōla in terms of syntax

In the rhetorical treatises, the cōlon is often described semantically, but never syntactically.⁴⁶ To borrow Demetrius’ description, the cōlon is either “a complete thought in itself” or “a part of [a complete thought], yet a complete part.”⁴⁷ As we have seen, such a distinction in fact refers to the basic distinction between the periodic and the non-periodic (or “disjointed”) style. In disjointed style, cōla are “complete thoughts,” while in periodic style, each cōlon is “a part of [a complete thought], yet a complete part.” Demetrius also compares the cōla of the disjointed style to “stones which are simply thrown about near one another and not built into a structure,” while the cōla of the periodic style are like “stones which support and hold together the roof which encircles them.”⁴⁸ As powerful as these semantic and metaphoric

⁴⁴ See, e.g., Dem., *Eloc.* 4; Cic., *Or. Brut.* 222; Quint., *Inst.* IX,4,124–125. That “ideal” cōla are within the range of a hexameter can also be observed in Hermogenes (see above, Chapter 2, section 10.2.1).

⁴⁵ See, e.g., Dionysius of Halicarnassus’s remarks concerning respectively the cōla of the polite harmony (*Comp.* 23,5) and those of the austere harmony (*Comp.* 22,45).

⁴⁶ On the loose relationship between ancient rhetoric and syntax, see Swiggers and Wouters (ed.), *Syntax in Antiquity*, especially the article by Swiggers and Wouters, “Réflexions à propos de (l’absence de ?) la syntaxe dans la grammaire gréco-latine,” 25–40; see also the remarks by Chiron, “Les cōla en rhétorique,” 38–40.

⁴⁷ Dem., *Eloc.* 2.

⁴⁸ Dem., *Eloc.* 13.

descriptions are, they are not sufficient when it comes to proceed to colometric analysis. Thus, it might be helpful to try translating them into modern syntactic categories. Thanks to the numerous examples given in the treatises, it is possible to do so without too much speculation.

2.2.1. *Côla, clauses, and the presence of a verb*

It has often been observed that *côla*-boundaries tend to occur between clauses. Indeed, the analogy between the *côlon* and the modern concept of the clause cannot escape one's attention when reading the treatises. However, it is a mistake to assume that *côla* would *always* correspond to clauses, or at least contain a verb and thereby, in a certain way, look like clauses. Such an idea appears notably in Heinrich Lausberg's *Handbuch der literarischen Rhetorik* or in the *Historisches Wörterbuch der Rhetorik* edited by Gert Ueding.⁴⁹ It should also be noted that the term *κῶλον* is rendered "clause" in certain translations, such as in the Loeb Classical Library series.⁵⁰ This same idea also guides the colometric analyses realised by exegetes involved in sound mapping—possibly because both Lee and Scott and Nässelqvist rely considerably on Lausberg's article?⁵¹ Whatever led them to this opinion, Lee and Scott indicate that *côla* correspond either to "a predicate and all of its related elements" or to "a sense unit controlled by a finite verb or some other verbal element, such as a participle or

⁴⁹ H. Lausberg, in the paragraphs he devotes to the *côlon* ("Elocutio," §928–934), distinguishes three different cases that he classifies according to their respective degree of completeness: "complete (main or subordinate) clauses" [§930: "vollständigen (Haupt- oder Neben-)Sätze"]; "word groups with infinite predicative word forms, whether a predicative verbal form (infinitive, participle) or a predicative nominal form (predicate noun)" [§930: "die Wortgruppen, die eine prädikative Verbalform (Infinitiv, Partizip) oder eine prädikative Nominalform (Prädikatsnomen) enthalten"]; "word groups without predicative word forms" [§930: "Wortgruppen ohne Prädikative"]. For the third case, Lausberg provides a single example that he takes from Alex., *Fig.* 27,26 (ed. Spengel): ἄτοπον δ' ἐστὶ σὲ μὲν ἐν τοῖς ἄλλοτρίοις / ἐμὲ δὲ ἐν τοῖς ἰδίοις ἀπορεῖσθαι. Lausberg comments that σὲ μὲν ἐν τοῖς ἄλλοτρίοις has no predicative word form on its own, but "die Illusion eines jeweils prädikatshaltigen Kolon wird erzeugt durch die Tatsache, dass das Hauptprädikat der ganzen Periode ἄτοπον δ' ἐστὶ zum ersten Kolon, das Prädikativ ἀπορεῖσθαι zum zweiten Kolon gezählt wird" (§931, n. 1). If we read between the lines, it seems that Lausberg is of the opinion that a single clause can occasionally be divided into two *côla*, on the condition that each part still looks like a clause due to the presence of a verbal form. Note that a very close description of the *côlon* is found in the *Historisches Wörterbuch der Rhetorik* edited by G. Ueding (see P. Dräger, "Kolon," col. 1138–1139; actually, Dräger's syntactic description of the *côlon* seems to be retaken directly from Lausberg).

⁵⁰ This is the case at least in the editions of Aristotle's *Rhetoric*, Demetrius' *On Style*, and Dionysius of Halicarnassus' *On Literary Composition*. Note that in these same editions, *κόμμα* is rendered as "phrase."

⁵¹ Lee and Scott mention Lausberg's article ("Elocutio," §928–934) several times to justify their assertions (see *Sound Mapping*, 127, n. 51 and 52; 159, n. 8). The indications they give regarding the syntactic nature of *côla* (*Sound Mapping*, 169) are also reminiscent of Lausberg's descriptions ("Elocutio," §930). The same holds true for Nässelqvist, who quotes Lausberg's syntactic description and explicitly agrees with it (*Public Reading in Early Christianity*, 127–129). On the more general tendency from the part of biblical scholars to rely on Lausberg's *Handbuch der literarischen Rhetorik*, see R. J. Anderson, "Use and Abuse of Lausberg."

infinitive” when the composition presents “complex syntax and multiple levels of grammatical subordination.”⁵² As far as I understand this formulation, they envisage the possibility that a clause may be divided into two or more *côla*, as long as each of these is “controlled by a verb” and thus in some way looks like a clause.⁵³ They specify that the verb may be implied, either through ellipsis or an implied form of εἶμι.⁵⁴ They also signal that *côla* can occasionally contain more than one finite verb.⁵⁵ Finally, if we look at the examples of sound maps that Lee and Scott propose, we may notice that they consider also certain direct addresses in the vocative case as *côla*.⁵⁶ For his part, Nässelqvist formulates a strict equivalence between the concept of *côlon* and the modern concept of clause: he insists that a *côlon* consists of “an entire clause and all its related elements.”⁵⁷ Just as Lee and Scott, he specifies that the verbal element can be a participle or an infinitive and that it is occasionally implied.⁵⁸ These indications apply at least for *côla*. In contrast, as concerns *commata*, Nässelqvist indicates that they do not necessarily contain a verb.⁵⁹ However, as we have seen above (section 2.1.1), he considers the comma as a subpart of a *côlon*, meaning that in the end a verb is effectively present or implied in all the *côla* he delineates.

Such descriptions are surprising because the rhetorical treatises provide many examples where the *côla* do neither correspond to clauses or combination of clauses, nor to units “controlled by a verb.” Specifically, it just so happens that a phrase or a combination of

⁵² *Sound Mapping*, 169–170.

⁵³ This idea recalls Lausberg’s observation in “Elocutio,” §931, n. 1.

⁵⁴ *Sound Mapping*, 170.

⁵⁵ *Sound Mapping*, 169.

⁵⁶ See notably *Sound Mapping*, 270–271, where Κύριε and Μαρία are interpreted as *côla*.

⁵⁷ Nässelqvist, *Public Reading*, 132: “The colon is a sense unit, which means that it *consists of* an entire clause with at least one verbal form and its related elements” [my emphasis]; also see *ibid.*, 342. See *Id.*, “The Question of Punctuation,” 186: “a colon should consist of an entire clause.” The only exceptions that Nässelqvist recognises are “parenthetical clauses” and “imperative clauses” (*Public Reading*, 129). As an example of the first type, he mentions the second *côlon* in the opening period of Demosthenes’ *Leptines*, as quoted by Demetrius in *Eloc.* 10 (Nässelqvist, *Public Reading*, 129, n. 38); see below, section 3.3.2, example 12. As for the second type, he mentions “the first of the two *côla* from Thucydides [*Pelop.* III,57,4],” as quoted in Dionysius of Halicarnassus, *Comp.* 7 (Nässelqvist, *Public Reading*, 129, n. 38). Nässelqvist seems to regard Ὑμεῖς τε ὃ Λακεδαιμόνιοι, ἡ μόνη ἐλπίς [“O you, Lacedaemonians, our only hope”] as the first *côlon*; in my view, by contrast, this Thucydidean period contains three *côla*, with Ὑμεῖς τε ὃ Λακεδαιμόνιοι and ἡ μόνη ἐλπίς forming two distinct *côla* (see below, section 2.2.2, example 4).

⁵⁸ Nässelqvist, *Public Reading*, 132, cf. also 342.

⁵⁹ Nässelqvist, *Public Reading*, 132; see also *ibid.*, 342. This remark is not unfounded, as phrase-*côla* indeed tend to be short. However, in the treatises there are also some longer phrase-*côla*, that could not be considered *commata*. See the examples below, under section 2.2.2.

phrases qualify as *côla* (see some examples below, section 2.2.2).⁶⁰ This is the case for those phrases that contain a relative clause and are thus “controlled by a verb” in some way or could even be considered clauses—if we work with a broad definition of “clause.”⁶¹ It is also the case for phrases that do not contain any verb. To put it another way, the concept of *côlon* is more flexible than currently advanced by scholars involved in sound mapping—at least as long as *periodic style* is considered. Paradoxically, the syntactic descriptions that these same scholars use are *too strict* when it comes to *côla* of a *non-periodic style*. Actually, the list of the syntactic units that may be determined to be a *côlon* differs depending on whether the *côlon* stands within or outside of a period. The importance of this point for colometric analysis should not be underestimated. It implies concretely that the periodic and the non-periodic *côla* must be treated separately in terms of their syntactic nature. In other words, it is crucial to maintain the semantic distinction between the two kinds of *côla* as established by Demetrius: complete thought (disjointed style) versus complete part of a complete thought.⁶² We now turn to how this semantic distinction can be rendered in terms of syntax.

2.2.2. *Côla within periods*

When they stand within periods, *côla* usually correspond to clauses, either dependent or independent. A nominal or a prepositional phrase also qualifies as a *côlon*, as in the few examples below:

Example 2

ἐν Ἐλέᾳ τῆς Ἰταλίας	[“at Elea in Italy]
πρεσβύτερῳ δὴ τὴν ἡλικίαν ὄντι	[when being already old in years] ⁶³

⁶⁰ This point has been regularly noticed in classical scholarship. See, e.g., Du Mesnil, “Begriff der drei Kunstformen der Rede,” 59–60; Habinek, *The Colometry of Latin Prose*, 29–36; also see Kennedy’s remark that a *côlon* presents “syntactical completion (at least a phrase)” (*On Rhetoric: A Theory of Civic Discourse*, 214).

⁶¹ I am thinking here of *côla* like οἱ μὲν πολλοὶ τῶν ἐνθάδε ἤδη εἰρηκότων (“most of those who have spoken here before me”—see Dion. Hal., *Comp.* 18,3 [= Thucyd., *Pelop.* II,35,1]) or ὅσῃν εὐνοίαν ἔχων ἐγὼ διατελώ τῇ τε πόλει καὶ πᾶσιν ὑμῖν (“all the loyal affection I bear my whole life through to the city and all of you”—see Dion. Hal., *Comp.* 18,16–19 [= Demosth., *On the Crown* 1]), that might be considered clauses if one works with a broad definition. Lee and Scott as well as Nässelqvist accept such *côla*. See, e.g., *côlon* 1 and *côlon* 2 in the first period of Philemon’s sound map (*Sound Mapping*, 239); cf. Nässelqvist, *Public Reading*, 128.

⁶² Dem., *Eloc.* 2.

⁶³ Dem., *Eloc.* 182. This is only an extract of a period, hence the lowercase at the beginning and the absence of a final punctuation mark.

Example 3

Cur de perfugis nostris [“Why from our own deserters]
copias comparant contra nos? [do they prepare a militia against us ?”]⁶⁴

Example 4

Ὑμεῖς τε ὦ Λακεδαιμόνιοι [“O you, Lacedaemonians]
ἡ μόνη ἐλπίς [our only hope]
δέδιμεν μὴ οὐ βέβαιοι ᾗτε. [we fear that you are not steadfast.”]⁶⁵

Example 5

Ἔργων γὰρ εὖ πραχθέντων [“When deeds have been nobly done]
λόγῳ καλῶς ῥηθέντι [then through speech finely uttered]
μνήμη καὶ κόσμος γίνεται [there comes honour and remembrance]
τοῖς πράξασι παρὰ τῶν ἀκουσάντων. [to the doers from the hearers.”]⁶⁶

Example 6

Ἀνὴρ γὰρ ἰδιώτης [“A member of the common people]
ἐν πόλει δημοκρατουμένῃ [in a democratic city]
νόμῳ καὶ ψήφῳ βασιλεύει. [is a king by virtue of the law and his own vote.”]⁶⁷

All cōla and commata in bold correspond to phrases rather than to clauses. In example 2, the first cōlon (ἐν Ἑλέα τῆς Ἰταλίας) is a prepositional phrase. In example 3, there are two cōla but a single clause: the main verb is found in the second cōlon, while the first cōlon is simply a prepositional phrase (*de perfugis nostris*) associated with the interrogative “cur.”⁶⁸ Example 4 contains two phrase-cōla: a nominal phrase in the vocative case (ὕμεῖς τε ὦ Λακεδαιμόνιοι), followed by another nominal phrase that stands in apposition (ἡ μόνη ἐλπίς).⁶⁹ Then, in example 5, the fourth cōlon (τοῖς πράξασι παρὰ τῶν ἀκουσάντων) consists of a combination of a nominal phrase and a prepositional phrase. Formally, there are two

⁶⁴ Cic., *Or. Brut.* 223.

⁶⁵ Thucyd., *Pelop.* III,57,4; quoted by Dionysius in *Comp.* 7,4 (cf. also *ibid.*, 7,5). I concur with Habinek’s conclusion that ἡ μόνη ἐλπίς forms a cōlon (or rather a comma) on its own, at least according to Dionysius’ analysis; see Habinek, *The Colometry of Latin Prose*, 31–32, esp. n. 20.

⁶⁶ Dion. Hal, *Comp.* 9,4; the extract is from Plato, *Menex.*, 236d; trans. S. Usher. Dionysius identifies only the last cōlon, yet his remarks that the cōla of this period are equal (*Comp.* 9,5) leaves little room for doubt regarding the place of the other caesurae.

⁶⁷ Alex., *Fig.* 27,19–20. The extract is from Aeschines, *Ctes.* 3,233.

⁶⁸ The division into two membra is somewhat surprising and is probably the consequence of Cicero’s rejection of the concept of monocōlon period (see above, Chapter 2, section 5.2.3).

⁶⁹ Näselsqvist (*Public Reading*, 129, n. 38) treats this example as an exception to his rule that each cōlon contains a verb. Note as well that he regards ὕμεῖς τε ὦ Λακεδαιμόνιοι and ἡ μόνη ἐλπίς as forming a single cōlon that he qualifies as an “imperative clause.” Cf. above, footnote 57.

verbal forms in this cōlon (the participles *πράξασι* and *ἀκουσάντων*), but both function here as substantives, making it difficult to assert that this cōlon is really “controlled by a verb.” Finally, example 6 above comprises a single clause, with the verb occurring in the last cōlon. Its first cōlon (*ἄνῆρ γὰρ ιδιώτης*) is a noun phrase, while its second cōlon (*ἐν πόλει δημοκρατουμένη*) is a prepositional phrase: here, the participle *δημοκρατουμένη* acts as an adjective, meaning that it is difficult to argue that *ἐν πόλει δημοκρατουμένη* consists of a clause or is “controlled by a verb.”

Considering the above examples, in addition to clauses and “units controlled by a verb,” phrases and combinations of phrases also qualify as cōla. This is the case at least as concerns nominal and prepositional phrases, and we may reasonably suppose that this is also the case for adjectival and adverbial phrases. We may note that the phrases-cōla mentioned above are either qualified by dependents (the first cōlon in example 2, the second cōlon in example 4, and the first two cōla in example 6), associated with a pronoun (the first cōlon in example 3, as well as the first cōlon in example 4), or grouped by two (the last cōlon in example 5). It seems that these characteristics invest such phrases with enough semantico-syntactic independence to allow them to stand on their own as cōla. In light of the small number of examples, however, it would be hazardous to take this last remark as an absolute rule.

In summation, the syntactic nature of periodic cōla is substantially more flexible than currently assumed by scholars involved in sound mapping. If most of cōla indeed correspond to clauses, or at least are controlled by a verb in some way, the key notion seems rather to be a certain degree of semantico-syntactic completeness (i.e., a relative semantico-syntactic autonomy), rather than the presence of a verb. We may of course attempt to provide a list of the different syntactic units that can constitute a cōlon. Yet, such a list would include so many possibilities that it would prove unproductive. Aside from clauses dependent and independent clauses, we would at least have to add nominal and prepositional phrases, combinations of two (or even more?) clauses, combinations of two (or more?) nominal or prepositional phrases, as well as “partial clauses” (i.e., a verbal form associated with one or more of its complement(s) but not with all of them).⁷⁰ We should also mention adverbial phrases and adjectival phrases, as well as any possible combination of two or more phrases. Finally, we may even think of interjections. Instead of proposing an

⁷⁰ The term “complement” is used here in a broad, non-technical sense, designating any element that can be seen as completing the verb, such as a subject noun phrase, a noun phrase functioning as a direct or an indirect object, an adverb or a prepositional phrase that behaves adverbially, an attribute (= subject and object complements in traditional grammar), or a final clause.

extensive list of all the syntactic units that can form a cōlon, it is easier and equally effective to say that any word or combination of words can, under the right circumstances, form a cōlon.⁷¹ Based on this assertion, it is possible to formulate the following law:

L3: within a period, any word or combination of words is able to form a cōlon, as long as this presents a certain degree of semantico-syntactic completeness.

To clarify what is understood with “a certain degree of semantico-syntactic completeness,” we may add the following tendency, formulated in two parts:

T3(a): within periods, there is a clear tendency for cōla boundaries to coincide with the division between clauses.

T3(b): when cōla do not encompass a single clause, they tend to correspond to either a) a combination of two clauses, or b) a nominal or prepositional phrase which is qualified by at least one dependent.

2.2.3. Cōla outside periods (disjointed style)

As regards their syntactic characteristics, non-periodic cōla are more codified than periodic cōla. Indeed, a look at the few examples provided in the treatises suggests that when the non-periodic style is used, each cōlon has a sufficient syntactic autonomy to stand on its own, much like a short sentence.⁷² This can be observed notably in the four examples below, where each cōlon has been punctuated with a full stop to highlight its independent character.

Example 7

Ἐκαταῖος Μιλήσιος ὧδε μυθεῖται.
Τάδε γράφω, ὡς μοι δοκεῖ ἀληθέα εἶναι.
Οἱ γὰρ Ἑλλήνων λόγοι πολλοὶ τε καὶ γελοῖοι, ὡς ἐμοὶ φαίνονται, εἰσὶν.

*[Hecataeus of Miletus thus relates.
I write these things as they seem to me to be true.
For the tales told by the Greeks are, as it appears to me, many and absurd.]*⁷³

⁷¹ Borrowing T. Habinek’s formulation here, we could say that “almost any constituent can, under the right circumstances, be a cōlon.” (*The Colometry of Latin Prose*, 28).

⁷² I refer here to Otto Jespersen’s definition of the sentence: “A sentence is a (relatively) complete and independent human utterance—the completeness and independence by its standing alone or its capability of standing alone, i.e. of being uttered by itself.” (*The Philosophy of Grammar*, 307).

⁷³ Dem., *Eloc.* 12 (= Hecat. of Miletus, *Gen.* I); trans. Innes. The last cōlon is arguably—from Demetrius’ point of view—a monocōlon period (see *Eloc.* 17).

Example 8

O callidos homines! [What shrewd men!]
O rem excogitatam! [What ingenuity!]
O ingenia metuenda! [What dangerous cleverness!]
Diximus. [We have spoken.]
Testis dare volumus. [We wish to offer witnesses.]⁷⁴

Example 9

Ἔστω! [Very well!]
Γιγνέσθω ταῦτα. [Be it so!]
Οὐδὲν ἀντιλέγω. [I have no objection.]⁷⁵

Example 10

Κροῖσος ἦν Λυδὸς μὲν γένος. [Croesus was a Lydian by birth.]
Παῖς δὲ Ἀλυάττεω. [He was the son of Alyattes.]
Τύραννος δὲ ἐθνέων ... [He ruled the nations ...]⁷⁶

Due to this syntactic characteristic, the *côla* (and *commata*) of the disjointed style can be termed “autonomous.” This aligns with Demetrius’ description of semantics, and also fits well with his metaphor of stones that are thrown near one another.⁷⁷ I therefore suggest that syntactic independence should be considered a necessary criterion for delineating the *côla* with a disjointed style.⁷⁸ We may formulate the following law:

L4: an autonomous cōlon has a semantico-syntactic independence that permits it to stand on its own as a short sentence.

The fact that the *côla* of the disjointed style are autonomous at the syntactical level does not mean that our modern habits of analysis would always lead us to consider them as short sentences. It only means that those *côla* can be considered independent sentences without disrupting our modern habits. In other words, it would seem correct to a modern reader to place a full punctuation mark at the end of each disjointed *cōlon*—even if this might occasionally seem somewhat artificial, as in example 10 above, where modern conventions would favour commas instead of full stops.

⁷⁴ Cic., *Second Speech for Cornelius*, quoted by Cic., *Or. Brut.* 225.

⁷⁵ Dem., *On the Chersonese* 10; quoted in Ael.-Arist., *Pol.* 167.

⁷⁶ Herodot., *Hist.*, I,6,1; quoted in Hermog., *Id.* I,3,12.

⁷⁷ See the introduction to section 2.2 above.

⁷⁸ Note, however, that not all rhetoricians would agree with this statement: see above, in Chapter 2, the discussions regarding Aristotle’s conception of the “sewn *lexis*” (section 2.1) and Pseudo-Aelius Aristides’ description of the “continuous style” (section 9.1.3).

Additionally, it must be specified that the criterion of syntactic independence is a *necessary* criterion, not a sufficient one. It happens that a cōlon presenting syntactic completeness is part of a period. It even happens that subsequent cōla that present syntactic autonomy belong to the same period, such as in the model of the narrative period provided by Demetrius: Δαρείου καὶ Παρυσάτιδος γίνονται παῖδες / πρεσβύτερος μὲν Ἀρταξέρξης, νεώτερος δὲ Κῦρος (“Darius and Parysatis had sons / the elder was Artaxerxes, the younger Cyrus”).⁷⁹ Nevertheless, the criterion of syntactic independence helps to clarify the boundary between the disjointed and the periodic styles. Crucially, it implies that every cōlon that does not meet this criterion cannot be considered “autonomous” and should therefore be grouped with one or more other cōla into a period. This last point constitutes a crucial correction to Nässelqvist’s description of the period (see below, section 3.2).

3. Identifying Periods

3.1. Length of periods

A kind of a mantra in the treatises is that periods should not be made too long.⁸⁰ In fact, periods are prosodic units meant to be uttered in a suspensive manner *as if it were* in one breath, meaning that the maximum length is limited by the respiratory capacity of the speaker.⁸¹ Quintilian also links the limited extent of periods to the capacity of the memory.⁸² Rhetoricians often express the maximum length in terms of number of cōla: for instance, Demetrius recommends to avoid composing periods of more than four cōla⁸³; of course, this nevertheless suggests that in practice longer periods were sometimes composed. The limit of four cōla is also found later in Alexander⁸⁴ and Pseudo-Herodian.⁸⁵ In contrast, Cicero and Quintilian do not place an upper limit in terms of number of cōla, but their comments and the examples they provide still suggest that periods rarely extend beyond four cōla.⁸⁶ As to Pseudo-Aelius Aristides, he mentions the monocōlon, the dicōloi, and the tricōloi, but states

⁷⁹ Xen., *Anab.* I.; quoted by Dem., *Eloc.* 19 (also see *Eloc.* 3).

⁸⁰ It appears notably in Arist., *Rhet.* III,9,6; Dem., *Eloc.* 16; *Rhet. Her.* IV,12,18; Cic., *De or.* III,191; Quint., *Inst.* IX,4,125. See also Anonym. Seg., *Pol.* 245.

⁸¹ See esp. *Rhet. Her.* IV,12,18; Cic., *De Or.* III,191; Quint., *Inst.* IX,4,125 (cf. also XI,3,53); see Augustine’s remark that periods are pronounced in a suspensive manner (*Doct. Chr.* IV,7,11).

⁸² Quint., *Inst.* IX,4,125.

⁸³ Dem., *Eloc.* 16.

⁸⁴ Alex., *Fig.* 28,13–17.

⁸⁵ Herod., *Fig.* 24 (= 93 Sp. RG III).

⁸⁶ Cic., *Or. Brut.* 221–222; Quint., *Inst.* IX,4,124–125.

that longer periods are also acceptable.⁸⁷ In Hermogenes, there are even two examples of periods that might be divided into seven *côla* and *commata*.⁸⁸ In view of these remarks, it seems reasonable to conclude that periods usually do not exceed 4 *côla*.

What about the minimum length for periods? Most rhetoricians consider that a single *côlon* can form a period called *monocôlon* or “simple period” under certain conditions.⁸⁹ However, the concept of a *monocôlon* period is rejected by some other rhetoricians, the most explicit rejection being that of Aquila Romanus, who states that a period with only one member is nonsense.⁹⁰ In fact, the very concept raises the issue of the distinction between an autonomous *côlon* and a *monocôlon* period. Even Demetrius and Quintilian—who both defend the concept—argue that periods have a minimum of two *côla*, later discussing the *monocôlon* period in a separated development. The rhetorical treatises also preserve traces of debates concerning the conditions required for a single *côlon* to “earn” the status of period. In Quintilian’s view, every (autonomous) *membrum* of a certain length is a *monocôlon* period, whereas Demetrius regards both a certain length and a “rounding off” (*καμπή*) as necessary prerequisites. As we have seen, this “rounding off” arguably relates to the placement of a key element at the end,⁹¹ so that the listeners have to wait until the last word to grasp the meaning, as in the example below:

Example II

Ἡ γὰρ σαφῆς φράσις πολὺ φῶς παρέχεται ταῖς τῶν ἀκουόντων διανοίαις.

[“*Clear expression sheds much light on the hearers’ minds.*”]⁹²

I will adopt Demetrius’ view in this study, which clarifies the distinction between an autonomous *côlon* and a *monocôlon* period. Only those *côla* that are long (let us say, above 15 syllables) *and* in which a key element appears as the last word should be called *monocôlon* periods. We can thus formulate the two following rules, with the second one comprising two parts (a and b):

⁸⁷ Ael. Arist., *Pol.* I, 169 (= 507, 18–32 Sp., RG II).

⁸⁸ Herm., *Id.* I, 12, 41 and 12, 42.

⁸⁹ Arist., *Rhet.* III, 9, 5; Dem., *Eloc.* 17; Quint., *Inst.* IX, 4, 124–125; Ael.-Arist., *Pol.* 169 (= p. 507 Sp., RG II). Cf. also *Rhet. Her.* IV, 19, 27. (see above, Chapter 2, section 4.3.1) and Dion. Hal., *Comp.* 23, 5 (see above, chapter 2, section 6.2.1).

⁹⁰ Aqu. Rom., *Fig.* 31, 4–9 [= Halm 28].

⁹¹ See above, Chapter 2, section 3.2.1.

⁹² Dem., *Eloc.* 17; trans. Innes.

T4: periods typically comprise between 2 and 4 cōla.

L5 (a): monocōlon periods have a minimum length of 15 to 16 syllables.

L5 (b): the final word of a monocōlon period is a key term for understanding the meaning of the period.

Then, we can specify that the length of periods is not only a question of number of cōla—as the length of cōla varies considerably—, but also of the total length in terms of syllables. If we were to define the standard length, we could reasonably say that periods typically have between 25 and 60 syllables. The upper limit of 60 syllables does not only correspond to the majority of examples found in the treatises, but also echoes Cicero’s comment that the “full period” has the approximative length of four full hexametres.⁹³ As to the maximal acceptable length, in the treatises there are a few examples that reach 80 syllables, and even one with 90 syllables.⁹⁴ It can of course be thought that periods could sometimes be even longer in practice, and hence, I suggest not placing an upper limit. It is better simply retain the strong tendency that periods do not go beyond 80 to 90 syllables. We can thus formulate two rules:

T5: periods typically comprise between 25 and 60 syllables.

T6: normally, periods do not extend beyond 80 to 90 syllables.

3.2. What makes a set of cōla a period?

What is a period in ancient rhetoric? In principle, it is composed of many cōla and/or commata that convey a complete thought (with the exception of the special case of a monocōlon). But what are the minimal characteristics necessary for a set of cōla qualify as a period? In the field of *sound mapping*, we find two very contrasting approaches to this question.⁹⁵ M. E. Lee and B. B. Scott work with an extremely broad conception of the period: they consider all prose to be made of periods, meaning that a period is simply a combination of cōla that are more or less closely connected. They believe that even the non-periodic style—what they call “continuous” style—is made of periods. The difference between the

⁹³ Cic., *Or. Brut.* 221–222.

⁹⁴ For examples of long periods of around 80 syllables, see Dem., *Eloc.* 45; Dion. Hal., *Comp.* 23,19 and 25,4; Hermog., *Id.* 12,41 and 12,42; also see the example of tetracōloi period in Pseudo-Herodian, *Fig.* 24 (= 93 Sp., RG III). A 90-syllables period is found in Hermog., *Id.* I,12,15.

⁹⁵ For a more detailed presentation of Lee and Scott’s and Nässelqvist’s respective comprehensions of the period, see above, Chapter 1, sections 2.3.2. and 2.4.2.

two styles would simply be that the periods of the continuous style are “looser” (i.e., their *côla* are loosely connected).⁹⁶ In contrast, D. Nässelqvist works with a much narrower conception of the period: according to his understanding, the period is more codified than the “sentence,” and not all *côla* are combined within periods.⁹⁷ He understands the period as an artistic arrangement of *côla* that always presents a well-turned ending, a feature he calls “bending back at the end.”⁹⁸ When it comes to identifying periods in ancient texts, these two different approaches obviously lead to constrating results.

In my view, both the approaches fail to respect the way that ancient rhetoricians distinguished between the periodic and the disjointed style. Specifically, the flexible approach advanced by Lee and Scott’s tends to produce long periods—many of which ancient rethoricians would have regarded as a set of two or even three distinct periods, or as a combination of one or two periods associated with some autonomous *côla*.⁹⁹ It is also noteworthy that a considerable number of periods that Lee and Scott delineate encompass many sentences from NA’s or UBS’s editions.¹⁰⁰ It seems as though they believe that the presence of some sound echoes or other types of symmetry is sufficient for linking *côla* together into a period, regardless of the syntactic discontinuity.¹⁰¹ Additionally, they do not sufficiently take account for the fact that periods have a limited length because of the constraints related to the conventions of reading aloud. Furthermore, Lee and Scott’s description of the continuous style as composed of periods contradicts the data from the treatises. As for Nässelqvist, he is perfectly right in stating that the concept of the period is more restrictive than the concept of the sentence. Nevertheless, he moves a little bit too far in the opposite direction by working with an overly narrow conception of the period—one that is too restrictive to reflect the general view expressed in the treatises accurately. As explored in Chapter 2, many rhetoricians consider that periods can be more or less “circular,” or “periodic.” For instance, Demetrius explains that the end of “dialogue periods”

⁹⁶ *Sound Mapping*, 179–181.

⁹⁷ *Public Reading*, 125.

⁹⁸ *Public Reading*, 134–138; cf. also 125 and 342.

⁹⁹ See a close remark in Nässelqvist, *Public Reading*, 138.

¹⁰⁰ In this regard, it is striking that some periods that Lee and Scott present in their sound maps still contain a full stop inside. See, e.g., in the sound map of Lk 2,1–20, periods 1, 2, 4, 7, 9, and 10 (*Sound Mapping*, 299–300), or in the sound map of Philemon, periods 8, 9, and 10 (*Sound Mapping*, 239–40). It seems that Lee and Scott simply reproduce the punctuation commonly found in critical editions such as UBS and NA, without adapting it to the colometric layout they propose—why they decide to let this punctuation is unclear to me. On the link between punctuation and colometry, see Chapter 5 below.

¹⁰¹ See e.g. period 4 in the sound map of Luke’s Nativity (Lee and Scott, *Sound Mapping*, 299).

is barely perceptible, and that these periods are in fact close to the disjointed style.¹⁰² Dionysius of Halicarnassus states that in the case of austere harmony one should not add words solely in order to “complete the circle” of periods.¹⁰³ As to Quintilian, he explains that the periods appropriate in narratives should be “loosened” by having less tight knots between their cōla.¹⁰⁴ The pattern of a well-turned ending is thus not necessary, although it is typical.¹⁰⁵ To put it another way, Nässelqvist’s strict definition corresponds only to “circular” or “ideal” periods, which are the ones that Demetrius called “rhetorical.”¹⁰⁶ Concretely, Nässelqvist’s definition sometimes leads to the determination of a “disjointed” set of cōla that most of rhetoricians would have regarded as a period.¹⁰⁷

In sum, the concept of a period is more codified than the theory advanced by Lee and Scott (not all cōla are part of periodic structures), though it is a bit more flexible than the theory suggested by Nässelqvist (e.g., the pattern of a well-turned ending is typical, yet not necessary). This raises the question again: what are the minimal characteristics required for a set of cōla qualify as a period? I suggest addressing this question from two different angles: the syntactic characteristics of periods (section 3.3. below), and the role of the so-called Gorgianic figures (section 3.4. below).

¹⁰² Dem., *Eloc.* 21. Cf. Demetrius’ description of the three kinds of periods in *Eloc.* 19–21.

¹⁰³ Dion. Hal., *Comp.* 22,5.

¹⁰⁴ Quint., *Inst.* IX,4,127.

¹⁰⁵ Concerning this point, it seems that Nässelqvist was influenced by his understanding of Demetrius’ definition of the period in *Eloc.* 10: “a combination of cola and commata which has brought the underlying thought to a conclusion *with a well-turned ending*” (*Public Reading*, 134 [my emphasis]). For a discussion on this definition and the defence of an alternative translation that does not put such an accent on the ending, see above, Chapter 2, section 3.2.2.

¹⁰⁶ Dem., *Eloc.* 20. A strict definition of the period indeed seems to have circulated in antiquity, as attested in Aristotle (Arist., *Rhet.* III,9,3) or in Pseudo-Aelius Aristides (Ael.-Arist., *Pol.* 167; see the discussion above, Chapter 2, section 9.1.3), but it clearly fails at representing a “technical standard,” as most rhetoricians work with a flexible definition.

¹⁰⁷ See e.g. Nässelqvist’s analysis of John 10:4a, which contains two cōla: ὅταν τὰ ἴδια πάντα ἐκβάλῃ (“when he has brought out all his own [= his sheep]”) and ἔμπροσθεν αὐτῶν πορεύεται (“ahead of them he goes”). Nässelqvist considers that this saying belongs to the disjointed style (*Public Reading*, 151), because, according to his strict definition, there are not enough elements to group these two cōla into a period. In contrast, I would rather suggest that we have here a clear example of a period. Indeed, the first cōlon (“when he has brought out all his own”) cannot stand on its own as an independent sentence (see above, section 2.2.3): it is syntactically subordinated to what follows, the main clause being found in the second cōlon (“ahead of them he goes”). The combination of these two cōla results in a short period, which is well-balanced with its two cōla of equal length (10 and 9 syllables), and in which the sense ends with the last word, πορεύεται.

3.3. *Syntactic characteristics of periods*

3.3.1. *Periods and sentences*

From a semantic point of view, ancient rhetoricians describe the period as a saying that encompasses a “complete thought.”¹⁰⁸ In light of the examples they provide, this semantic characteristic can be easily translated at the syntactic level: periods are sentences.¹⁰⁹ In most cases, they correspond to complex or compound sentences (with a tendency for each clause to correspond to a cōlon (see above, section 2.2.2). We may thus formulate the following law and associated tendency:

L6: from a syntactic point of view, a period corresponds to a sentence.

T7: periods usually correspond to complex or compound sentences.

Nevertheless, it also happens that a single clause is considered a period, as in examples 3, 4, and 6 above (section 2.2.2). A clause that forms a period on its own is also typically found in the case of monocōlon periods, as is the case notably in example II above (section 3.1).¹¹⁰

3.3.2. *The interweaving of cōla*

Rhetoricians also outline that cōla and commata are interlinked or “interwoven” within periods. As was seen in Chapter 2, the term κατεστραμμένη used by Demetrius and Aristotle to designate the periodic style bears this idea of interweaving.¹¹¹ Dionysius of Halicarnassus made this metaphor of weaving even more explicit by comparing the polite harmony—which is the periodic harmony *par excellence*—to “finely-woven cloths” (εὐήτριοι ὕφη).¹¹² This characteristic relates to the notion that periodic cōla are usually closely interlinked at the syntactic level and are mutually dependent on each other. Three features are typically found: delay of a key element up to the end of the period, grammatical subordination, and coordination by means of particle pairings, such as typically μέν ... δέ, οὔτε... τε, or τε ... τε.

¹⁰⁸ See Arist., *Rhet.* III,9,4; Dem., *Eloc.* 10; *Rhet. Her.* IV,19,27; Quint., *Inst.* IX,4,125; Alex., *Fig.* 27,17–22; Ael.-Arist., *Pol.* 167.

¹⁰⁹ This holds true at least for Demetrius and his successors. The case is ambiguous in Aristotle (see above, Chapter 2, section 2.2.1).

¹¹⁰ Cf. also Dem., *Eloc.* 17.

¹¹¹ Arist., *Rhet.* III,9,1; Dem., *Eloc.* 12.

¹¹² Dion. Hal., *Comp.* 23,3.

Firstly, periods frequently exhibit hyperbaton in the form of the delay of a key element—such as a word or a group of words that bears the main semantic content—up to the end. Daniel Markovic showed that such “closing” hyperbata had a pragmatic function in that they were frequently used by ancient authors to mark the end of a discourse unit, such as the end of a period.¹¹³ Placing a key element at the end is indeed an easy and clear way to signal an ending, as the conclusion of the thought and of the formulation perfectly coincide. We may also note that such a delay creates a suspense that gives periods a sense of unity, as it “leaves the listeners hanging in suspense before they can understand how the utterance is structured and its overall meaning”¹¹⁴; this is especially true when the element in question is delayed over multiple *côla*. The delayed element is often a verb, as in the Demosthean period below that Demetrius provided as a model:

Example 12

Μάλιστα μὲν εἵνεκα τοῦ νομίζειν συμφέρειν τῇ πόλει λελύσθαι τὸν νόμον
εἶτα καὶ τοῦ παιδὸς εἵνεκα τοῦ Χαβρίου
ὠμολόγησα τούτοις, ὡς ἂν οἴός τε ὦ, **συνερεῖν**.

*["Chiefly because I thought it was in the interest of the state for the law to be repealed
but also for the sake of Chabrias' boy
I have agreed in their support, to the best of my ability, to speak."]¹¹⁵*

We can also consider the model of *tricôloi* period given by Alexander (see above, example 6): Ἄνῆρ γὰρ ιδιώτης / ἐν πόλει δημοκρατουμένη / νόμῳ καὶ ψήφῳ βασιλεύει
[“A member of the common people / in a democratic city / by virtue of the law and his own vote rules”].¹¹⁶ Latin authors—especially Cicero¹¹⁷—also had a tendency to place the verb at the end of a period. Quintilian explicitly recommended making the verb the last word of a period: “If the composition allows, it is better to end with a verb, since the force of language is in the verbs.”¹¹⁸ Therefore, paying special attention to the presence of closing hyperbata

¹¹³ D. Markovic, “Hyperbaton in the Greek Literary Sentence.” Markovic argues that the figure of hyperbaton “belongs to the set of those rhetorical devices that should be considered the ancestors of the later developed system of punctuation” (127–128). On the figure of hyperbaton, see the study by A. Devine, and L. D. Stephens, *Discontinuous Syntax: Hyperbaton in Greek*; also see Chiron, “La figure d’hyperbate.”

¹¹⁴ S. M. Baugh, “Hyperbaton and Greek Literary Style in Hebrews,” 196.

¹¹⁵ Dem., *Eloc.* 10; the extract is from Demosthenes, *Lept.* 1; trans. D. C. Innes.

¹¹⁶ See above, n. 67.

¹¹⁷ See this remark in Du Mesnil, “Begriff der drei Kunstformen der Rede,” 46.

¹¹⁸ Quint., *Inst.* IX,4,26. This recommendation takes place within a broader development on word order (*Inst.* IX,4,23–32).

may be particularly helpful when delineating periods in a given text. Although as previously stated, such a word arrangement is only an optional characteristic of periods, but is in no way necessary.

Second, a periodic cōlon is typically subordinated to either the following or the preceding cōlon. Periods often begin with a temporal, contextual, causal, local, or manner complement.¹¹⁹ This is the case in example 12 above (section 3.3.2), where the first two cōla indicate the reasons for Demosthenes' acceptance of supporting the plaintiffs. This is also the case in the model of tricōloi period given by Alexander (see above, example 6, section 2.2.2). While the first cōlon contains the subject, the second one does not introduce the predicate. Instead it consists of a prepositional phrase (ἐν πόλει δημοκρατουμένη) that contextualizes the statement expressed in the third cōlon as true. Another instance is found in example 5 above (section 2.2.2), where the period begins with two absolute participial clauses—the first one in genitive (ἔργων γὰρ εὖ πραχθέντων), and the second one in dative (λόγῳ καλῶς ῥηθέντι). A cōlon can also be subordinated to the preceding one by means of “subordinating” conjunctions or relative pronouns, as in the two examples below:

Example 13

Οἱ μὲν πολλοὶ τῶν ἐνθάδε ἤδη εἰρηκότων
ἐπαινοῦσι τὸν προσθέντα τῷ νόμῳ τὸν λόγον τόνδε
ὡς καλὸν ἐπὶ τοῖς ἐκ τῶν πολέμων θάπτομένοις ἀγορεύεσθαι αὐτόν.

*["Most of those who have spoken here before me
commend the one who made this speech a statutory event
as it is right for it to be delivered at the burial of those who fall in battle"]¹²⁰*

Example 14

Ἔργῳ μὲν ἡμῖν οἶδε ἔχουσιν τὰ προσήκοντα σφίσιν αὐτοῖς
ᾧ τυχόντες πορεύονται τὴν εἰμαρμένην πορείαν.

*["In respect of deeds, these men have already received from us their due
endowed wherewith they are going their predestined road."]¹²¹*

In example 13, the third cōlon is subordinated to the preceding ones with the conjunction ὡς. In example 14, the second cōlon is subordinated to the first one with the relative pronoun ᾧ. In addition to these cases illustrated in the treatises, it seems reasonable

¹¹⁹ Cf. Lausberg, “Elocutio,” §947.

¹²⁰ Dion. Hal., *Comp.* 18,3 (= Thucyd., *Pelop.* II,35,1).

¹²¹ Dion. Hal., *Comp.* 18,9 (= Plato, *Menex.* 236d).

to stipulate that also participial constructions can serve as a means to subordinate a cōlon to what precedes it.

A word of clarification should be added, however, regarding the notion of subordination. The subordinate status of a cōlon is occasionally ambiguous. This is notably the case when participles are used. In the treatises, we find several instances in which a participle is the main verb of a period. In those cases, it seems that participles act like (or almost like) finite verbs. To offer one example, we can mention the following extract of Thucydides' *Peloponnesian War*, as quoted by Dionysius of Halicarnassus:

Example 15

Ἀρξάμενος εὐθὺς καθισταμένου / καὶ ἐλπίσας μέγαν τε ἔσεσθαι καὶ ἀξιολογώτατον τῶν προγεγενημένων.

[“He began the task as soon as the war broke out / in the belief that it would be great and memorable above all the wars that had gone before.”]¹²²

Dionysius explicitly regards this saying as a dicōloi period,¹²³ although there is no finite verb in it. Here, the participle ἀρξάμενος is the main verb of the period. This point aligns with the observation made by some grammarians that participles can occasionally function independently or almost independently, thereby standing as the sole verb in a sentence.¹²⁴ Therefore, we should avoid assuming that participles automatically have a subordinating function. Though not explicitly mentioned in the treatises, we can note two other situations in which the status of subordination may be ambiguous: when a clause is linked to what precedes it by means of either the “relative pronoun” ὃς, ἣ, ὅ, or with a “subordinating conjunction.” In the first case, the so-called “relative pronoun” can almost function as a demonstrative pronoun that refers to an antecedent that is found in the preceding sentence. Therefore, it is possible for a relative pronoun to be the first word of an autonomous cōlon or of a period.¹²⁵ The same remark holds true regarding the presence of conjunctions traditionally classified as “subordinating,” such as e.g. ὅτι, ἐπεὶ, or ὡς. We must avoid

¹²² Thucyd., *Pelop.* I,1; quoted in Dionysius of Halicarnassus, *Comp.* 22.

¹²³ Dion. Hal., *Comp.* 22.

¹²⁴ However, most grammairians assert that such participles do not have exactly the exact same value as a finite verb. See Robertson, *A Grammar of the Greek New Testament*, 1132; D. B. Wallace, *Greek Grammar Beyond the Basics*, 653; S. E. Runge, *Discourse Grammar of the Greek New Testament*, 245–246. There are debates about the frequency of this phenomenon and the exact status of such “independent participles.”

¹²⁵ See T. D. Goodell’s remark that “The connecting force of ὃς may be no stronger than that of a demonstrative. The ὃς clause is then really independent.” (*A School Grammar of Attic Greek*, §213).

automatically assuming that the presence of these conjunctions implies a subordinate relationship to what precedes them.¹²⁶ Each of these three situations (participles, relative pronouns, and “subordinating” conjunctions) must be carefully analysed by taking into account not only how the *côlon* relates semantically to what precedes it and to what follows it, but also the stylistic characteristics of the surrounding text. In terms of style, it is important to consider the presence of sound echoes (*paromoiosis*) and equality in length between the *côla* (*pariosis*). These two features may confirm the presence of a period, as discussed below (section 3.4.1).

Third, *côla* are often connected within a period by particle pairings. The *μὲν ... δέ* construction is common and is typically used to express an antithesis (on the link between periods and antitheses, see below, section 3.4.1). Other possible constructions include *οὔτε ... τε* and *τε ... τε*. In this case, the first particle creates the expectation that a related clause will follow, thereby connecting the *côla*. Below are three examples taken from the treatises:

Example 16

Οἱ μὲν γὰρ αὐτῶν κακῶς ἀπώλοντο [*“Some of them perished miserably*]
οἱ δ’ αἰσχρῶς ἐσώθησαν. [*others saved themselves disgracefully.”*]¹²⁷

Example 17

Ὡς οὔτε ὧν πυνθάνονται ἀπαξιούντων τὸ ἔργον
οἷς τε ἐπιμελὲς εἶη εἰδέναι οὐκ ὄνειδιζόντων.
[“Since neither do those who are questioned disown the deed]
*[nor do those who are concerned to know censure it.”]*¹²⁸

Example 18

Δωρητοὶ τ’ ἐπέλοντο [*“They were ready for gifts*]
παράρητοί τ’ ἐπέεσσιν. [*and for persuasion by words.”*]¹²⁹

¹²⁶ On the possible usage of *ἐπεὶ* as a discourse marker or particle rather than as a subordinating conjunction, see D. Muchnová, *Entre conjonction, connecteur et particule: le cas de epei en grec ancien. Etude syntaxique, pragmatique et sémantique*. From Muchnová, see also her article on the paratactic usage of *ὥς*: “Les emplois paratactiques de *ὥς*.” On *ὅτι*, see e.g. the short remarks in Kühner and Gerth, *Ausführliche Grammatik der griechischen Sprache*, vol. II/2, 463, n. 5.

¹²⁷ Isocrates, *Paneg.* 149; mentioned as an example of a *dicôloi* period by Aristotle, *Rhet.* III,9,7.

¹²⁸ Thucyd., *Pelop.* 1,5,3; quoted by Demetrius in *Eloc.* 25.

¹²⁹ Hom., *Iliad* IX,526; quoted by Aristotle in *Rhet.* III,9,7.

As a synthesis of the above discussion, we may formulate the following rule. Note that this rule has only the status of a strong tendency, as *côla* belonging to the same period occasionally do not present any of these features:

T8: within a composed period, côla are usually either dependent on each other at the syntactical level (by means of subordination and/or hyperbaton) or connected with a pair of particles (such as μέν ... δέ, οὔτε... τε, or τε ... τε, etc.).

3.3.3. The structuring role of γάρ

From a mere glance at the rhetorical treatises, it appears that *côla* are often introduced by a particle, among which the most common are τε, μέν, δέ, and γάρ. Indeed, particles play a crucial role in the structure of ancient Greek texts—though their exact functions are matters of debate.¹³⁰ It is plausible that certain particles occasionally function merely as markers of the colometric structure, rather than as words invested with a specific semantic function. Unfortunately, the range of examples in the treatises is too narrow to allow us to conclude exactly how each particle behaves in regards to colometry. For this reason, it would be far too speculative to include a list of particles that would always—or even would simply tend to—introduce a new *côlon*.¹³¹ Moreover, such criteria would partially overlap with T3(a), which addresses the tendency for *côla*-boundaries to correspond with clause-boundaries.

That being said, a clear tendency is discernible for the particle γάρ. In the examples of periods provided by ancient rhetoricians, γάρ appears frequently, and always stands at the beginning of a new unit. As far as I am aware, in the treatises there is no example in which γάρ is found in the middle of a *côlon*, nor introducing the second or any other subsequent *côlon* within a period. In contrast, there are numerous examples where γάρ occurs in P2 in

¹³⁰ I use the term “particle” in a broad sense here, without getting into the complex debates of what exactly is a particle, the relationship between particles and conjunctions, and the terminological issue (discourse particles? pragmatic particles? discourse markers? pragmatic markers?). For recent discussions on the topic of particles in ancient Greek, see the major work in five volumes by A. Bonifazi, A. Drummen, and M. de Kreij, *Particles in Ancient Greek Discourse: Exploring Particle Use across Genres*. On the use of the different particles in the NT, see also M. E. Thrall, *Greek Particles in the New Testament: Linguistic and Exegetical Studies*.

¹³¹ The role of particles in delineating “Kola” has been extensively studied by E. Fraenkel (see “Kolon und Satz I”; “Kolon und Satz II”; *Noch einmal Kolon und Satz; Leseproben aus den Werken Ciceros und Catos*). However, as we have seen in Chapter 1 (see the excursus “Ancient colometry as an object of study by classicists,” §2, pages 37–38), Fraenkel does not define the “Kolon” in direct reference to the rhetorical treatises, but rather as the unit to which certain rules of word order apply. Precisely, one of these rules is the so-called Wackernagel’s law, which refers to “the tendency of certain enclitics and postpositives to occur second within their clause or sentence” (D. Goldstein, “Wackernagel’s law I”). In other words, in Fraenkel’s methodology, certain particles are taken as markers of a new Kolon; however, this rule is not directly based on evidences in the treatises and is therefore not in line with the methodology adopted in our study.

the first cōlon of a period, perhaps serving as a typical way to mark the beginning of a period.¹³² Without entering here into the complex debate on the function of γάρ,¹³³ we can simply conclude that the evidence suggests a very strong tendency for γάρ to occur in the first cōlon of a period, and we can thus formulate the following rule:

T9: γάρ (almost?) always marks the beginning of a period or autonomous cōlon.

3.4. Gorgianic figures

The so-called Gorgianic figures of speech (antithesis, parisosis, and paromoiosis) are typically found in periods.¹³⁴ The presence of these figures is helpful not only in identifying periods, but also in delineating the cōla within a given period. Two or even three figures often occur in the same period.

3.4.I. Antithesis

Antithesis is to be understood in a broad sense comprising also “false antithesis,” which is when cōla seem oppose each other because of the formulation, but in fact convey the same meaning. Antithetic cōla are especially easy to identify, as they are most often structured by means of μέν... δέ. In view of the numerous examples provided by rhetoricians, it seems that the two terms of an antithesis always correspond to distinct cōla and that these always

¹³² To mention only a few examples taken from the treatises: Arist., *Rhet.* III,9,7 (Οἱ μὲν γὰρ αὐτῶν κακῶς ἀπώλοντο / οἱ δ’ αἰσχυρῶς ἐσώθησαν = Isocrates, *Paneg.* 149); *ibid.*, 9,9 (Ἀγρὸν γὰρ ἔλαβεν / ἀργὸν παρ’ αὐτοῦ = Aristophanes, *Frag.* 649); Dem., *Eloc.* 17 (Ἡ γὰρ σαφῆς φράσις πολὺ φῶς παρέχεται ταῖς τῶν ἀκουόντων διανοίαις. – unknown origin); *ibid.*, 18 (Οὐ γὰρ τὸ εἰπεῖν καλῶς καλόν / ἀλλὰ τὸ εἰπόντα δρᾶσαι τὰ εἰρημένα. – unknown origin); *ibid.*, 28 (Ποίαν γὰρ πόλιν τῶν ἐχθρῶν τοιαύτην ἔλαβον / ὁποῖαν τὴν ἰδίαν ἀπέβαλον. = Arist., *Περὶ δικαιοσύνης*); *ibid.*, 31 (Ὡσπερ γὰρ εἶ τις ἐκείνων ἐάλω, σὺ τὰδ’ οὐκ ἂν ἔγραψας / οὕτως ἂν σὺ νῦν ἀλῶς, ἄλλος οὐ γράψει. = Demosth., *Aristocr.* 99); *ibid.*, 45 (Ὁ γὰρ Ἀχελῷος ποταμὸς ῥέων ἐκ Πίνδου ὄρους διὰ Δολοπίας καὶ Ἀγριανῶν καὶ Ἀμφιλόχων ... = Thuc., *Pelop.* 2.102.2); Dion. Hal., *Comp.* 9,2 (Ὁ γὰρ οἷς ἂν ἐγὼ ληφθεῖην / ταῦτα πράττων καὶ κατασκευαζόμενος ... = Dem., *Phil.* 3, 17); *ibid.*, 9,4 (Ἐργων γὰρ εὖ πραχθέντων / λόγῳ καλῶς ῥηθέντι ... = Plato, *Men.* 236d); Alex., *Fig. Sp.*, RG III,27,17–22 (Ἀνὴρ γὰρ ἰδιώτης / ἐν πόλει δημοκρατουμένη / νόμῳ καὶ ψήφῳ βασιλεύει. = Aeschines, *Ctes.* 3.233); *ibid.*, 28,13–17 (Τίς γὰρ οὐκ ἂν ἠδέως μετὰσχοι στρατείας / τῆς ὑπ’ Ἀθηναίων τε καὶ Λακεδαιμονίων στρατηγουμένης ... = Isocrates, *Paneg.* 185); Ael-Arist., *Pol.* 169 (Τὸ μὲν γὰρ ἐξ ἀρχῆς τι μὴ δοῦναι γνώμη χρησαμένων ἔργων ἐστὶν ἀνθρώπων ... = Demosth., *Lept.* 56); Herm., *Id.* I,12,15 (Τὸ μὲν γὰρ πολλὰ ἀπολωλεκέναι κατὰ τὸν πόλεμον τῆς ἡμετέρας ἀμελείας ἂν τις θεῖη δικαίως ... = Demosth., *Olynthiac* I,10. It is noteworthy that γάρ occurs in Demetrius’ definition of the period (*Eloc.* 10: Ἔστιν γὰρ ἡ περίοδος σύστημα ἐκ κώλων ἢ κομμάτων εὐκαταστροφῶν / πρὸς τὴν διάνοιαν τὴν ὑποκειμένην ἀπηρτισμένον.), a definition which, as argued above (Chapter 2, n. 204), itself consists of a model of a period.

¹³³ For an overview of this debate, see S. Casson, *Engaging with γάρ*, 17–30.

¹³⁴ See Arist., *Rhet.* III,9,7–10; Dem., *Eloc.* 15; Cic., *Or. Brut.* 165.

belong to the same period. In addition, two antithetic cōla tend to form a period together—even if it is imaginable that an antithesis can be included within a longer period. We can thus formulate the two following laws and an associated tendency:

L7: the two terms of an antithesis each correspond to a cōlon.

L8: two antithetic cōla belong to the same period.

T10: two antithetic cōla usually form a period on their own.

3.4.2. Paromoiosis and parisosis

Parisosis (alternatively called “isocōlon”) refers to the equality of length between the cōla of a given period. Rhetoricians makes it clear that this equality only needs to be approximate.¹³⁵ Thus, if two cōla have for instance 13 and 15 syllables respectively, there is still a parisosis, as listeners perceive these cōla as having similar length.

Paromoiosis designates sound echoes of vowels and sometimes also consonants in subsequent cōla. The typical placement of these echoes are the extremities of the cōla (beginning and/or end¹³⁶), although the similarities can also occur in the middle.¹³⁷ In this context, “beginning” does not solely refer to the first syllable(s). For example, the echoes can also occur at the end of the respective first words of the cōla, as in: Δωρητοί τ’ ἐπέλοντο / παράρρητοί τ’ ἐπέεσσιν.¹³⁸ In contrast, in the examples of similarities at the end that rhetoricians provide, the repetition always includes the vowel of the last syllable,¹³⁹ which suggests that final paromoioses essentially consist of rhymes.

If parisosis and paromoiosis are unquestionably characteristic of periods, their presence within subsequent cōla does not automatically imply that these cōla form a period. In fact, in contrast with antithesis, parisosis and paromoiosis do not per se involve an interdependence between the cōla in which they occur. The presence of these figures may also be linked to a desire to give a certain rhythm to a passage in disjointed style, as in the following example that Cicero provided as a model of speech “in membra and incisa”: *Domus*

¹³⁵ See e.g., *Rhet. Her.* IV, 20; Quint., *Inst.* IX,3,75–80; cf. also Dem., *Eloc.* 25.

¹³⁶ When similarities occur at the end of cōla, we can alternatively speak of homoeoteleuton. See *Rhet.* III,9,9; Dem., *Eloc.* 26; Quint., *Inst.* IX,3,77.

¹³⁷ On similarities in the middle, see, e.g., Quintilian, *Inst.* IX,3,78.

¹³⁸ See Arist., *Rhet.* III,9,9; Dem., *Eloc.* 25.

¹³⁹ See esp. Arist., *Rhet.* III,9,9; Dem., *Eloc.* 26.

tibi deerat? At habebas. Pecunia superabat? At egebas. Incurristi amens in columnas. In alienos insanus insanisti. (“Did you lack a house? Yet you had one. Was there money left? Yet you were in want. You have madly dashed against the columns. You have raved wildly against strangers.”).¹⁴⁰ Moreover, sound echoes and/or equality in length may also emerge inadvertently from the flow of words. Therefore, in the process of identifying periods, the presence of these figures should not be given too much weight. Parisoses and paromoioses should rather be seen as clues that can draw our attention to the possibility of a period. For example, the detection of similarities in length and/or in sounds might serve as a confirmation that two or more *côla* together form a period in those cases where the syntactic dependency is ambiguous (use of participles, certain conjunctions, or relative pronouns).¹⁴¹

We can formulate the three following tendencies:

TI1: *within a period, it frequently happens that the côla have similar or approximatively similar lengths (= parisosis).*

TI2: *within a period, it frequently happens that the côla exhibit sound echoes at their extremities (= paromoiosis).*

TI3: *subsequent côla that present both paromoiosis and parisosis typically belong to the same period.*

3.4.2. Paromoiosis and the issue of vowel pronunciation

Anyone who wishes to analyse sound echoes in ancient Greek texts has to address the issue of pronunciation. Lee, Scott, and Nässelqvist argued that knowing the exact pronunciation is not necessary to detect sound echoes. Indeed, it is often sufficient to assume that a given letter or combination of letters is in principle pronounced in the same manner throughout a given text.¹⁴² It is nonetheless crucial to determine which model of pronunciation we work with. This point has already been noted by some scholars involved

¹⁴⁰ Cic., *Pro Scauro* XXII,45 (trans. H. M. Hubbell); quoted and analysed by Cicero himself in *Or. Brut.* 222–223, and retaken by Quintilian in *Inst.* IX,4,122.

¹⁴¹ See above, section 3.3.2.

¹⁴² Lee and Scott, *Sound Mapping*, 81; see also Lee, *A Method for Sound Analysis*, 4; Id., “Sound Mapping Reassessed,” 15 (“The phonetic character of the Greek language ensures that letters and diphthongs would be voiced consistently”); Nässelqvist, *Public Reading*, 123–124.

in sound mapping, including J.E. Brickle and T. Boomershine.¹⁴³ Specifically, J.E. Brickle tested two different systems in his analysis of the prologue of First John, namely the “Erasmian pronunciation”¹⁴⁴ and the “historical Greek pronunciation.”¹⁴⁵ T. Boomershine suggested that “in Mark’s time Greek was pronounced more like modern Greek than the Erasmian pronunciation.”¹⁴⁶ Deciding which system we work with is especially important in the case of vowels, as linguists tend to think that different vowels were pronounced in the same way from an early stage.¹⁴⁷ For instance, when looking for sound echoes in a NT text, should we consider that the diphthong αι and the letter ε are pronounced in the same way or at least in a close way, both corresponding to the phoneme /ε/ ? The same question arises concerning οι and υ (/y/), and ει and ι (/i/), respectively. Or perhaps οι, υ, ει, ι et η should all be pronounced /i/, as in modern Greek?

The choice of the pronunciation system must always be appropriate to the text, with respect both to the timeframe and the social location. In fact, evolutions in pronunciation do not take place at the same moment everywhere and in every social class. In particular, aristocratic classes tend to maintain a more conservative pronunciation for longer compared to lower classes.¹⁴⁸ When analysing Pauline letters, we have to consider the middle of the 1st century. As concerns the social location, we may reasonably posit that Paul’s pronunciation of Greek was not especially conservative (aristocratic).¹⁴⁹ In the analysis of

¹⁴³ Brickle, *Aural Design*, 19–24; Boomershine, *The Messiah of Peace*, 383–386. See also a similar remark in J. Pilch’s review of *Sound Mapping*, 955.

¹⁴⁴ This refers to Erasmus’ reconstruction of ancient Greek pronunciation, a system which is traditionally used—with some modifications—for teaching ancient Greek in Western schools. See on this topic M. Dillon, “Erasmian Pronunciation.”

¹⁴⁵ The “historical Greek pronunciation” refers to the system proposed by C. Caragounis, *The Development of Greek*.

¹⁴⁶ Boomershine, *The Messiah of Peace*, 385. However, when himself performing Mk 14–16 (“Mark 14–16 told in Greek”), Boomershine makes use of the so-called “Erasmian pronunciation,” which modern listeners are more familiar with.

¹⁴⁷ See Horrocks, *Greek: A History of the Language and its Speakers*, esp. 160–188. Among the studies on ancient Greek phonology, we can mention R. B. Smith, *Empirical Evidences and Theoretical Interpretations of Greek Phonology*; F. T. Gignac, *A Grammar of the Greek Papyri of the Roman and Byzantine Periods*, vol. I; S.-T. Teodorsson, *The Phonology of Ptolemaic Koine*; Id., *The Phonology of Attic in the Hellenistic Period*;

¹⁴⁸ On this, compare for example Teodorsson’s reconstruction of the pronunciation of the majority system by 350 BC (*The Phonemic System of the Attic Dialect 400–340 BC*, 286–299) with his reconstruction of the “conservative pronunciation” used by the aristocracy of the same time era (*The Phonology of Attic in the Hellenistic Period*, 94–96). See also Horrocks, *Greek: A History of the Language and its Speakers*, 165–170 ; cf. the remarks by J. E. Brickle, *Aural Design and Coherence*, 20.

¹⁴⁹ There are extremely contrasting views concerning Paul’s social location; however, it is generally recognised that Paul did not belong to the aristocracy—though he might have been of “relatively high status.” On this issue, see an overview of scholarship in Schellenberg, *Rethinking Paul’s Rhetorical Education*, 17–56.

sound echoes in 2 Cor 10–13 (Chapter 4), I will work with the following model, which relies a lot on Teodorsson’s proposed model for the “standard” (i.e., non-aristocratic, non-vulgar) pronunciation in use from the 2nd century BCE.¹⁵⁰

Table 1: Vocalic system proposed for Pauline letters

<i>phoneme</i>	<i>spelling</i>
/i/	ι, η, ει (before a consonant or at the end of a word)
/e/	η, ε, αι, ει (before a vowel)
/a/	α, α̣
/o/	ο, ω, ω̣
/u/	ου
/y/	υ, οι
/aφ/ /aβ/ ¹⁵¹	αυ
/eφ/ /eβ/	ευ
/iw/	ηυ

3.4.3. *Paromoiosis and the issue of accents*

Linked to the question of vowel pronunciation is that of accents. Rhetoricians do not theorise this point, and as a first application test of the method (see Chapter 4) I shall not give much importance to accents. However, it seems logical that sound echoes can be reinforced when they occur on accented vowels, or on the contrary attenuated when one term of the echo occurs on an accented syllable whereas the other term occurs on an unaccented syllable.¹⁵² This principle holds true regardless of which model is adopted for the phonetic realisation of accents (pitch/melodic or stress). However, stressed accents are perhaps perceived as stronger than pitch/melodic accents, especially if we assume that the discourse’s rhythm is

¹⁵⁰ Note that this system is quite close to modern Greek pronunciation. See Teodorsson, *The Phonology of Ptolemaic Koine*, 251–256 (on the pronunciation of the grapheme οι, see 254–255); cf. also the discussion in Horrocks, *Greek: A History of the Language and its Speakers*, 167–170.

¹⁵¹ On the development of a fricative articulation for the second element of the diphthongs ending in -υ, see G. Horrocks, *Greek: A History of the Language and its Speakers*, 169.

¹⁵² In this regard it is worth to note that in the few examples of paromoioses given by Aristotle (Arist., *Rhet.* III,9,9) and Pseudo-Demetrius (*Eloc.* 25–26) the two terms of a vocalic echo always fall on two vowels (or diphthongs) that have the same status with respect to accentuation (i.e., two vowels marked with a circumflex accent, or two vowels marked with an acute accent, or two vowels marked with a grave accent, or two vowels without any accent).

based on them (instead of being based on syllables duration). The choice of the model also modifies the way accented syllables are identified, particularly as concerns grave accent. If we work with pitch or “melodic” accents, the vowels marked with a grave accent should arguably be taken as unaccented, at the same level as vowels without any accent.¹⁵³ If, by contrast, we assume that in Paul’s time the shift from a primary pitch accent to a primary stress accent was completed—as is generally recognised—then vowels marked with a grave accent should be considered equivalent to those marked by an acute or a circumflex accent.¹⁵⁴ In any case, however, the choice we make concerning this aspect does not radically change the way sound echoes are identified. At most, this impact on the perceived weight of the paromoioses, but not on their presence.

3.5. *Rhythmical patterns*

It is a common idea among Greek and Latin rhetoricians that prose should be rhythmical without being metrical. Concretely, certain metrical feet are welcome, but these should be placed sparingly (i.e., they should not follow each other in a continuous chain as this would give prose an overly poetic tempo).¹⁵⁵ Rhetoricians agree that the typical placement for metrical feet are the extremities of *côla*, in particular the end of periods: thus, elegant periods are often “closed” by an appropriate *clausula* that mark their end.¹⁵⁶

The question is, could the presence of certain feet serve as an additional criterion for identifying periods and *côla* boundaries? My answer is quite pessimistic, for at least three different reasons.¹⁵⁷ First, it is unknown precisely until when the distinction between long and short vowels remained in use, and therefore we do not know, as regards Pauline letters and early Christian texts more generally, whether the scansion should still be based on the

¹⁵³ See e.g., J.-V. Vernhes, “Qu’est-ce que l’accent grec ancien? Les accents du grec ancien étudiés en eux-mêmes et comparés à ceux du lituanien.”

¹⁵⁴ On the shift from a primary pitch accent to a primary stress accent, see e.g. Devine and Stephens, “Stress in Greek?”; cf. Horrocks, *Greek: A History of the Language and its Speakers*, 169–170.

¹⁵⁵ See Arist., *Rhet.* III,8,3; Cic., *Or. Brut.*, 187; 227; Quint., *Inst.* IX,4,72–78.

¹⁵⁶ See Arist., *Rhet.* III,8,6; Dem., *Eloc.* 39; Dion. Hal., *Comp.* 23,6; Quint., *Inst.* IX,4,61–63.

¹⁵⁷ To these reasons, we might add Augustine’s remark that rhythmical *clausulae* are largely absent in the New Testament (August., *Doct. Christ.* IV,20,41). Note, however, that his comment applies to the Latin translation.

length of syllables¹⁵⁸ or rather on (stress) accents.¹⁵⁹ Then, even assuming that we could determine this point, rhythmical patterns are too frequent to serve as clues: feet can occur anywhere, not only at the beginning and end of cōla, as they emerge naturally from the flow of words. Last but not least, not all rhetoricians agree on which feet to favour,¹⁶⁰ meaning that we also do not even know which feet to look for.

This is not to say that rhythm should not be taken into account when discussing the colometry of Paul's letters (or other early Christian texts). Of course, it may be fruitful to observe the rhythmical patterns occurring in a given author's works in order to better understand the author's style and tendencies. In some cases, this might also permit us to refine the delineation criteria for an individual author: for instance, if we find that X tends to mark the end of periods with a 4th paeon, then the presence of a 4th paeon could be considered an additional criterion to identify periods in X. However, in view of the different points mentioned above, it would be too speculative at this stage to identify rhythmical feet *as a means* for delineating cōla and periods in Pauline letters, and I renounce to do that in the limits of this study.

4. Synthesis and Conclusion

In this chapter, we have discussed how modern scholars can use the data from the ancient rhetorical treatises to delineate cōla and periods in ancient Greek prose texts. The examination of the sources in Chapter 2 has permitted us to refine the understanding of ancient colometry, and, beyond, to formulate criteria for colometric analysis that are more

¹⁵⁸ It is generally believed that the distinction between long and short vowels was already lost in the speech of the majority of Greek speakers by the mid-2nd century BCE (see the discussion in Horrocks, 160–170; cf. also Teodorsson, *The phonology of Attic in the Hellenistic period*, 96–98; Id., *The Phonology of Ptolemaic Koine*, 251–256). However, a sense of vowel quantity seems to have endured later in some circles. In this regards, we may note that in his rhythmical analyses, Dionysius of Halicarnassus still works with a system based on the distinctive vowel length (see e.g. *Comp.* 17–18). Cf. Teodorsson, *The Phonology of Attic in the Hellenistic period*, 94–96, who argues that the eventual elimination of vowel-length distinctions among aristocracy took place in the Roman period; see also Horrocks, *Greek: A History of the Language and its Speakers*, 164.

¹⁵⁹ For rhythmical analyses based on the “accents d'intensité,” see J. Irigoin, “La composition rythmique des cantiques de Luc.”

¹⁶⁰ Aristotle and Demetrius praised the 1st paeon (one long syllable followed by three short) at the beginning and the 4th paeon (three short syllables followed by a long one) at the end (Arist., *Rhet.* III,8; Dem., *Eloc.* 38–43). Demetrius specifies that the paeons do not need to be perfect, the most important being that periods are framed with long syllables (*Eloc.* 41). Dionysius of Halicarnassus mentions various feet, though he also seems to favour the use of long syllables at the end of periods (see the discussion and examples in *Comp.* 17–18). As to Latin rhetoricians, they considerably extended the list of the recommended clausulae (see Cic., *Or. Brut.* 207–226; Quint., *Inst.* IX,4,60–111).

historically informed than those typically used by scholars involved in sound mapping. The discussion resulted in a set of 21 rules (eight laws [L] and 13 tendencies [T]) meant to be used as criteria to guide the colometric analysis process. Again, “laws” (L) are and should always be respected when practicing colometric analysis. In contrast, “tendencies” (T) represent non-absolute rules that serve as complementary criteria. Laws express the minimal characteristics of cōla and periods, but are sometimes too broad to be effective for making choices. Therefore, it is necessary to supplement them with non-absolute yet often observed rules that can be described as “tendencies.” It is possible to present these 21 rules in a table:

*Table 2: Criteria for colometric analysis*¹⁶¹

<i>Length</i>		
cōlon		period
<p>T1: cōla usually comprise between 7 and 25 syllables (= standard length).</p> <p>T2: within a period, cōla tend to be balanced.</p> <p>L2: cōla do not extend beyond 35 syllables (= acceptable length).</p> <p>L1: short cōla of less than 7 syllables are better called “commata.” Units between 7 and 9 syllables can be considered either cōla or commata.</p>		<p>T4: periods typically comprise between 2 and 4 cōla.</p> <p>T5: periods typically comprise between 25 and 60 syllables.</p> <p>T6: normally, periods do not extend beyond 80 to 90 syllables.</p> <p>L5(a): monocōlon periods have a minimum length of 15 to 16 syllables.</p>
<i>Syntax (and semantics)</i>		
autonomous cōlon “a complete thought in itself” ¹⁶²	cōlon within a period “a part of [a complete thought], yet a complete part.” ¹⁶³	period a complete thought
L4: an autonomous cōlon presents a semantico-syntactic independence that permits it to	L3: within a period, any word or combination of words is able to form a cōlon, as long as it	L6: from a syntactic point of view, a period corresponds to a sentence.

¹⁶¹ The numbering of rules and tendencies simply refers to the order in which these have been discussed above. Numbering has nothing to do with a classification of criteria according to their relative importance.

¹⁶² Dem., *Eloc.* 2.

¹⁶³ Dem., *Eloc.* 2.

stand on its own as a short sentence.	presents a certain degree of semantico-syntactic completeness. T ₃ (a) : within periods, there is a clear tendency for cōla boundaries to coincide with the division between clauses. T ₃ (b): when cōla do not encompass a single clause, they tend to correspond to either (a) a combination of two clauses, or (b) a nominal or prepositional phrase which is qualified by at least one dependent.	T ₇ : periods usually correspond to complex or compound sentences. T ₈ : within a composed period, cōla are usually either dependent on each other at the syntactical level (e.g., by means of subordination and/or hyperbaton) or connected with a pair of particles (such as μέν ... δέ, οὔτε... τε, or τε ... τε, etc.) L ₅ (b): the final word of a monocōlon period is a key element for understanding the meaning of the period.
T ₉ : γάρ (almost?) always marks the beginning of a period or of an autonomous cōlon.		
<i>Gorgianic figures (parallelisms)</i>		
<p>Antithesis</p> <p>L₇: the two terms of an antithesis each correspond to a cōlon.</p> <p>L₈ : two antithetic cōla belong to the same period.</p> <p>T₁₀: two antithetic cōla usually form a period on their own.</p> <p>Paromoiosis and parisosis</p> <p>T₁₁: within a period, it frequently happens that the cōla have similar or approximatively similar lengths (= parisosis).</p> <p>T₁₂: within a period, it frequently happens that the cōla exhibit sound echoes at their extremities (= paromoiosis).</p> <p>T₁₃: subsequent cōla that present both paromoiosis and parisosis typically belong to the same period.</p>		

Our study highlights that the cōla of the non-periodic style have enough syntactic autonomy to stand on their own as short sentences (see section 2.2.3). The disjointed style is close to what we would currently term “choppy” (i.e., a composition where short sentences

succeed one another). This point helps to clarify the boundary between the periodic and the non-periodic style and thereby represents an important correction to both Lee and Scott's and Nässelqvist's approaches. Another crucial correction concerns the syntactic nature of periodic cōla. According to the approach typically used in sound mapping, cōla are always constructed around a verb, whether present or implied.¹⁶⁴ In contrast, it has been demonstrated that cōla are highly flexible when they are part of a period (see section 2.2.2). The key point seems to be a certain degree of semantico-syntactic completeness, rather than the presence of a verb. Crucially, a phrase regularly forms a cōlon on its own. Beyond these two main corrections, we are also able to specify the minimal and maximal length for both cōla (see section 2.1.2) and periods (see section 3.1), to clarify the notion of comma as being nothing more than a particularly short cōlon (see section 2.1.1), and finally to bring some light on the syntactic characteristics of periods (see sections 3.3.1 to 3.3.3).

This concludes the part of our study devoted to the development of the colometric analysis method. In the next two chapters, we will apply this method to an extract of the Pauline corpus, namely 2 Cor. 10–13. Chapter 4 consists of an essay of a colometric analysis of this passage, including a critical evaluation of the results. Then, in Chapter 5, we will explore some implications of colometry for the exegesis of Paul's letters—and more broadly of the New Testament—especially as concerns syntactic ambiguities and punctuation issues.

¹⁶⁴ Lee and Scott, *SMNT*, 169–170; Nässelqvist, *Public Reading*, 132 (see also Id., “The Question of Punctuation,” 186). See the discussion above, section 2.2.1.

CHAPTER 4

Paul and Colometry: Essay of a Colometric Analysis of 2 Corinthians 10–13

I. Introduction: Purposes and Method

In this chapter, we turn to Paul's letters and a colometric analysis of 2 Corinthians 10–13. There is a significant consensus in scholarship that these four chapters form a unit, even among scholars who defend the composite character of the Second Epistle to the Corinthians.¹ With respect to rhetoric, this is a text that is “widely considered emblematic of Paul's rhetorical prowess.”² For instance, it has been qualified as “Paul's rhetorical tour

¹ As to whether 2 Corinthians originated as a single letter or is rather composed from extracts of different letters, there have been continuous vivid debates, with various propositions being made for identifying the fragments (see, e.g., J. Weiss, *Der erste Korintherbrief*, xxxix–xlili, who identified four different letters [letter A = 2 Cor 6:14–7:1; letter B = 2 Cor 8:1–24; letter C = 2 Cor 2:14–6:13 + 7:2–4 + 10:1–13:13; letter D = 2 Cor 1:1–2:13 + 7:5–16 + 9:1–15]; G. Bornkamm, *Gesammelte Aufsätze*, vol. IV, 169–194, who identified extracts from five different letters [letter C = 2 Cor 2:14–6:13 + 7:2–4; letter D = 2 Cor 10:1–13:10 = “letter of tears”; letter E = 2 Cor 1:1–2:13 + 7:5–16; letter F = 2 Cor 8:1–24; letter G = 2 Cor 9:1–15]; also see W. Schmithals, *Briefe*, 19–85, who thinks that 2 Corinthians combines portions from seven different letters, among a total of 13 letters written by Paul to the Corinthians [letter C = 2 Cor 6:14–7:1; letter H = 2 Cor 6:3–13 + 7:2–4a; letter J = 2 Cor 4:2–14; letter K = 2 Cor 2:14–3:18 + 4:16–6:2; letter L = 2 Cor 10:1–13:13 = “letter of tears”; letter M = 2 Cor 8:1–24a; letter N = 2 Cor 1:1–2:13 + 7:5–7 + 7:8–16 + 9:1–15]). A widespread view is that chapters 1–9 and chapters 10–13 belong to different historical situations (on the reasons for separating 10–13 from 1–9, see a synthesis in M. J. Harris, *The Second Epistle to the Corinthians*, 29–34), with chapters 1–9 composing a first letter and chapters 10–13 composing a second letter written later (for classic defences of this hypothesis, see H. Windisch, *Der zweite Korintherbrief*, 11–21; or more recently M. E. Thrall, *The Second Epistle to the Corinthians*, vol. 1, 5–13). Another version of this hypothesis posits that chapters 10–13 had been written before chapters 1–9 and that they either keep or consist of part of the so-called “severe letter” (also called “letter of tears”) alluded to in 2 Cor 1:23–2:11 and 7:6–16 (the classic defence of this hypothesis was given by J. H. Kennedy, *The Second and Third Epistles of Paul to the Corinthians*; for the objections against this hypothesis, see L. L. Welborn, “The Identification of 2 Cor 10–13 with the ‘Letter of Tears’”). H. D. Betz was certainly right when he wrote, in 1992, that “few scholars continue to defend the unity of 2 Corinthians” (“Corinthians, Second Epistle to the,” 1149). However, this claim now needs revision, given that from the late 20th century an increasing number of scholars are defending the integrity of the entire letter. This trend is associated notably with the names of F. M. Young and D. F. Ford (*Meaning and Truth in 2 Corinthians*, esp. 37–44), F. W. Danker (“Paul's Debt to the *De Corona* of Demosthenes: A Study of Rhetorical Techniques in 2 Corinthians”), B. Witherington III (*Conflict and Community in Corinth*), D. A. Hester (“The Unity of 2 Corinthians: A Test Case for a Re-Discovered and Re-Invented Rhetoric”), J. D. H. Amador (“Revisiting 2 Corinthians: Rhetoric and the Case for Unity”), M. J. Harris (*The Second Epistle to the Corinthians*, 42–51), and F. J. Long (*Ancient Rhetoric and Paul's Apology: The Compositional Unity of 2 Corinthians*). A complete presentation of the different positions and a good discussion (in support of the literary integrity of the letter) are provided by Harris, *The Second Epistle to the Corinthians*, 8–51.

² See R. S. Schellenberg, *Rethinking Paul's Rhetorical Education: Comparative Rhetoric and 2 Corinthians 10–13*, 57. Among the studies devoted to the rhetoric of 2 Cor 10–13, we can mention H. D. Betz, *Der Apostel Paulus und die sokratische Tradition: eine exegetische Untersuchung zu seiner Apologie 2 Korinther 10–13*; W. Danker, “Paul's Debt to the *De Corona* of Demosthenes: A Study of Rhetorical Techniques in 2 Corinthians”; J. Zmijewski, *Der Stil der paulinischen “Narrenrede”*; D. F. Watson, “Paul's Boasting in 2 Corinthians 10–13 as Defense of His Honor: A Socio-rhetorical Analysis”; A. Pitta, “Il ‘discorso del pazzo’

de force,”³ “a magnificent composition,”⁴ or “a brilliant piece of text.”⁵ This excerpt will serve as a case study for testing the method of colometric analysis that was developed in the previous chapter. To be clear, by “testing the method,” I do not mean exploring its potential hermeneutical benefits, but evaluating if the proposed method is a heuristic analytical tool to explain the micro-structure of Paul’s prose. This question consists of two concerns, each recalling of the “conditions for scientificity” discussed in the introduction to Chapter 3.

The first concern relates to the *adequation between the approach and the object of study*.⁶ The underlying question can be formulated as follows: is it really valide to analyse Paul’s letters using the rhetorical categories of cōlon and period? More concretely, the question arises: does our analysis provide “evidence” that 2 Cor 10–13 was composed colometrically? Or instead, does it reveal a certain gap between Paul’s style and the conventions of structuration as described by the Greek and Latin rhetoricians? In other words, we have to ask whether the analysis of 2 Cor 10–13 undertaken in this chapter confirms the working hypothesis formulated at the beginning of this study, namely that Paul used to structure his texts according to cōla and periods.⁷

The second concern is linked with the method itself, and centres on the *operationality of the method*. Fundamentally, the question is: can the criteria developed in Chapter 3 effectively guide the delineation of cōla and periods? Are these criteria sufficiently precise? Conversely, do some criteria appear too strict when applied to a long text? And more generally, what are the difficulties encountered in application and which points deserve further investigation?⁸

o periautologia immoderata? Analisi retoricoletteraria di 2 Cor 11,1–12,18”; M. Wojciechowski, “Paul and Plutarch on Boasting”; J. T. Fitzgerald, “Paul, the Ancient Epistolary Theorists, and 2 Corinthians 10–13”; M. M. DiCicco, *Paul’s Use of Ethos, Pathos, and Logos in 2 Corinthians 10–13*; M. M. Mitchell, “A Patristic Perspective on Pauline περιавтоλογία”; C.A. Wanamaker, “By the Power of God’: Rhetoric and Ideology in 2 Corinthians 10–13”; R. S. Schellenberg, *Rethinking Paul’s Rhetorical Education*. See also C. F. G. Heinrich, *Der Zweite Brief an die Korinther*, 313–314, who paid special attention to what he called “Klangfiguren,” i.e., aurally pleasing stylistic features; also see J. Weiss, *Beiträge zur Paulinischen Rhetorik*, 185–188; cf. also J. D. Harvey, *Listening to the Text*, 193–216. For an overview of scholars’ engagement in the rhetorical approach to 2 Cor 10–13, see R. S. Schellenberg, *Rethinking Paul’s Rhetorical Education*, 57–77.

³ Witherington, *Conflict and Community in Corinth*, 373.

⁴ M. M. Mitchell, “A Patristic Perspective on Pauline περιавтоλογία,” 354.

⁵ H.-D. Betz, “Rhetoric and Theology,” 155.

⁶ See Chapter 3, section 1.3.1.

⁷ See the general introduction (pages 3 and 5) as well as the excursus “Some reflections on the conditions for the scientificity of the method” (Chapter 3, pages 140–143.)

⁸ See Chapter 3, section 1.3.2.

I will begin (section 2 below) by disposing the 2 Cor 10–13 text in cōla and periods, a layout that I will refer to as “colometric disposition.” The Greek text is placed on the left-hand pages, while the right-hand pages contain an English translation. This bilingual layout is then followed by a series of remarks aimed to signal some difficulties and hesitations encountered in the process of delineation (section 2.3 below). Then, in the second part of this chapter (section 3 below), I will adopt a critical view of the results to address the issues of formal adequation and operability of the method.

Let us make clear that the proposed analysis deals only with colometry, in accordance with the announced aim of our study. It is not meant to be a “complete” analysis of the soundscape of 2 Cor 10–13, and even less a complete stylistic analysis of the passage.

Before turning to the text, a brief discussion of the content of 2 Cor 10–13 is necessary. In the final part of his Second Epistle to the Corinthians, Paul⁹ harshly criticises a group of adversaries—or perhaps two distinct groups—whom he calls “false apostles” (ψευδαπόστολοι, see 11:13) and “super-apostles” (ὑπερλίαν ἀπόστολοι, see 11:5 and 12:11). These people mock him (e.g., 10:2; 10:9–10) and deliver ideas that conflict with the Gospel that Paul himself announced to the Corinthian community (e.g., 11:4).¹⁰ Paul notably faced a rumour that he would “walk according to the flesh” and lack apostolic authority

⁹ Note that formally, the Second Epistle to the Corinthians is presented as co-authored by Paul and Timothy (see 2 Cor 1:1, Παῦλος ἀπόστολος Χριστοῦ Ἰησοῦ διὰ θελήματος θεοῦ καὶ Τιμόθεος ὁ ἀδελφὸς τῆ ἐκκλησίᾳ τοῦ θεοῦ τῆ οὔσῃ ἐν Κορίνθῳ σὺν τοῖς ἁγίοις πᾶσιν τοῖς οὔσῃ ἐν ὅλῃ τῇ Ἀχαΐᾳ). It is difficult to determine, however, the exact roles of co-authors or co-senders in Paul’s epistles (on this issue, see notably the discussion in S. Buttica, “Auctorialité et autorité dans les lettres de Paul.”) In the specific case of 2 Cor 10–13, the potential composite character of the letter (see above, footnote 1) makes the question even more difficult. To me, it seems clear that Paul should be considered the *auctor* of chapters 10–13: in this passage, he speaks in his own name, using mainly the first person singular (see 10:1, Αὐτὸς δὲ ἐγὼ Παῦλος παρακαλῶ ὑμᾶς ...) and making abundant references to his personal situation. It still remains, however, that Timothy—or, should we adopt the composite hypothesis, another or several other persons?—might have influenced the style of these chapters.

¹⁰ Numerous and contrasting suggestions have been made regarding the identity of these adversaries. All of these hypotheses can be reduced—following the summary proposed by M. J. Harris—to four principal categories: “Hellenistic Jewish propagandists, pneumatics, Gnostics, and Judaizers” (Harris, *The Second Epistle to the Corinthians*, 80). On this issue, see also the detailed discussions in T. Schmeller, *Der zweite Brief an die Korinther*, vol. II, 149–171; and in M. E. Thrall, *The Second Epistle to the Corinthians*, 926–945. There is also a debate as to whether Paul faces a single group of opponents in Corinth or two distinct groups, the key question being whether the “false apostles” (11:13) should be classified with the “super-apostles” (11:5; 12:11). The literature on this topic is immense: among the classical studies, we can mention G. Friedrich, “Die Gegner des Paulus im 2. Korintherbrief”; D. Georgi, *Die Gegner des Paulus im 2 Korintherbrief*; Barrett, “Paul’s Opponents in II Corinthians”; R. Bieringer and J. Lambrecht, *Studies on 2 Corinthians*, 192–221; J. L. Sumney, *Identifying Paul’s Opponents: The Question of Method in 2 Corinthians*. See also a detailed discussion in M. J. Harris, *The Second Epistle to the Corinthians*, 67–87; also see M. E. Thrall, *The Second Epistle to the Corinthians*, vol. II, 671–678.

(10:1–11).¹¹ The letter also details a controversy on Paul’s refusal of financial support from the part of the Corinthians (11:7–9; 12:13–16): the opponents seemingly accuse Paul of refusing payment as a devious means to trick the Corinthians into commitment to him and to the collection for Jerusalem (12:16–18).¹² Confronted with such attacks, Paul defends his apostolic legitimacy and authority in a vigorous, and at times even aggressive, manner.¹³ He also engages in extensive boasting—the so-called “Fool’s Speech”¹⁴ of 11:1–12:13—, though he repeats numerous times that he undertakes such a boasting with much reluctance and qualifies himself as a fool for venturing into such territory (11:16–17; 11:21; 12:1; 12:5–6; 12:11). To borrow from Charles K. Barrett’s wording, we may describe 2 Cor 10–13 as, “a puzzling mixture of humility and aggression, of self-abasement and authority.”¹⁵

2. Essay of a Colometric Analysis of 2 Cor 10–13

2.1. Preliminary remarks

The text submitted to analysis below is an eclectic text. A few text-critical issues are given in footnotes¹⁶—these notes are limited to issues judged worth to mention to support the Greek text retained.¹⁷ The notes also indicate when the choice between different readings

¹¹ On this, see C. Clivaz, “La rumeur, une catégorie pour articuler autoportraits et réceptions de Paul. ‘Car ses lettres, dit-on, ont du poids ... et sa parole est nulle’ (2 Co 10,10).”

¹² The content of the accusation in 12:16 is not explicit. It is usually thought that it refers to the financial participation that Paul requests from the part of the Corinthians for the benefit of the church of Jerusalem. The accusation would thus be that Paul only pretended not to be interested in money, but in fact diverted part of the Corinthians’ contributions to the collection for his own benefit (so A. Plummer, *A Critical and Exegetical Commentary on the Second Epistle of St. Paul to the Corinthians*, 364; H. Windisch, *Der zweite Korintherbrief*, 404; Barrett, *The Second Epistle to the Corinthians*, 324–325; R. P. Martin, *2 Corinthians*, 445; Grässer, *Der zweite Brief an die Korinther*, vol. II, 228–229; Harris, *The Second Epistle to the Corinthians*, 889; Thrall, *The Second Epistle to the Corinthians*, vol. 2, 856; Schmeller, *Der zweite Brief an die Korinther*, vol. 2, 350–351). It is also unclear whether this allegation originated with the opponents or with the Corinthians themselves.

¹³ On the use of aggressive language in 2 Corinthians, see P. Lampe, “Can Words Be Violent or Do They Only Sound That Way? Second Corinthians: Verbal Warfare from Afar as a Complement to a Placid Personal Presence.”

¹⁴ This designation comes from H. Windisch, *Der zweite Konrintherbrief* (published in 1924), 316.

¹⁵ C. K. Barrett, “Boasting (καυχᾶσθαι, κτλ.) in the Pauline Epistles,” 368. On the topic of Paul’s boasting in 2 Cor 10–13, see also the classical work of H. D. Betz, *Der Apostel Paulus und die sokratische Tradition*.

¹⁶ The list of witnesses cited is largely inspired by the conventions adopted by the NA editors (see NA²⁸, “Introduction,” 64.). I also use the sigla and abbreviations of NA²⁸ (see NA²⁸, “Codices graeci et latini in hac editione adhibiti,” 792–819; “Signa et abbreviationes,” 879–890; cf. also “Introduction,” 80–81).

¹⁷ For more complete critical apparatuses, see in priority (but for Greek manuscripts only) the work of R. J. Swanson, *New Testament Greek Manuscripts: Variants Readings Arranged in Horizontal Lines Against Codex Vaticanus: 2 Corinthians*; cf. Nestle-Aland *Novum Testamentum Graece* 28th ed. (B. Aland, K. Aland et al. (ed),

may influence the delineation of cōla and/or periods. Let us also specify that the text was established prior to and independently from colometric considerations; in other words, what fits better with the principles of colometry was *not* used as an argument to make textual choices. As to the few punctuation marks that appear in the colometric disposition below, they were of course placed after the delineation process was completed.¹⁸

Though it was not always possible, there was an attempt to respect the Greek word order in the translation, which sometimes leads to odd wording in English. Words placed within brackets do not figure in the Greek text but have been added to clarify the meaning and/or facilitate the reading. A few translation difficulties are mentioned in footnotes.

In the disposition of both the Greek and the English texts, each line contains a single and entire cōlon, except when a cōlon is too long for a single line. In this case, the excess text is placed on a second line and aligned to the right, with an opening bracket to signal that it belongs with the above line. Autonomous cōla (and commata) are framed with vertical bars, while periods (whether they comprise many cōla/commata or a single cōlon) are framed with double vertical bars.¹⁹ The following conventions have been retained regarding the use of punctuation marks and capitals:

Greek

- Periods begin with a capital letter and are punctuated with a full stop, or when appropriate, with a question mark [;] or an exclamation mark [!].

Novum Testamentum Graece [based on the work of Eberhard and Erwin Nestle]), which also gives an overview of the Latin, Coptic, and Syriac traditions.

¹⁸ It seems that M.E Lee and B.B. Scott (*Sound Mapping the New Testament*) retain the punctuation marks present in the most recent editions of NA or UBS; see their remarks in Chapter 3, n. 96 (I did not check this point in a systematic way throughout their work, however, so there might be some exceptions that escaped my attention). Why Lee and Scott keep this punctuation even when it conflicts with the colometric disposition they propose is unclear. As to D. Nässelqvist, he explicitly indicates that he follows NA²⁸ only in determining the text and that his proposed punctuation occasionally diverges from that found in NA (*Public Reading*, 120); see also his article “The Question of Punctuation in John 1:3–4: Arguments from Ancient Colometry.”

¹⁹ This has also the advantage of differentiating between monocōlon periods and autonomous cōla.

- Similarly, autonomous côla (and commata) begin with a capital letter and are punctuated with a full stop,²⁰ or when appropriate, a question mark [;] or an exclamation mark [!].

- No other punctuation marks (such as commas, semi-colons, colons, or parentheses) are used in the Greek text. This choice was made to avoid influencing the reader's understanding of the relationships between the côla belonging to the same period or between the words inside a given côlon as much as possible. Note that the absence of any internal punctuation within côla does not imply that no break is needed in delivery.²¹

English translation

- Periods begin with a capital letter and are punctuated with a full stop, or when appropriate, with a question mark or an exclamation mark;

- Similarly, autonomous côla (and commata) begin with a capital letter and are punctuated with a full stop, or when appropriate, with a question mark or an exclamation mark.

- As a general rule, there are no punctuation marks between the côla belonging to the same period. Exceptions include hyphens (aimed to signal parenthetical elements) and occasional a colon.

- Within côla and commata, a comma [,] is occasionally included. The use of these commas follows the modern conventions of punctuating English. Their presence does not always reflect the structure of the Greek text.

The so-called Gorgianic figures are systematically indicated, whether they play a role in the choice of delineation or not:

- Antitheses (in a broad sense)²² are italicized.

- Parisoses are signalled by indicating the number of syllables in parentheses at the end of the concerned côla/commata.

- As a general rule, paromoioses are signalled only when they occur at the extremities of côla, using colour code when they concern vowels (yellow for /i/,

²⁰ According to my understanding that the disjointed style is made of segments which—from a semantico-syntactic point of view— can be considered short sentences. See the discussion above, Chapter 3, section 2.2.3.

²¹ On the possibility of having slight breaks within a côlon, see Chapter 5, section 2.2.4.

²² See, e.g., Arist., *Rhet.* III,9,10; Dem., *Eloc.* 24.

orange for /e/, pink for /a/, purple for /o/, blue for /u/, and green for /y/)²³; repeated consonants are simply underlined. In addition, sound repetitions that involve accented vowels are highlighted in bold.²⁴ When the same word (or two words with the same root) are repeated at the extremities of subsequent cōla, these words are encased.

In addition, the marker γάρ—which (according to T9) can play a role in signalling the beginning of a new period or of a new autonomous cōlon—is bolded.

²³ See the pronunciation system proposed in Chapter 3, section 3.4.2.

²⁴ The vowels marked by a grave accent are considered as accented syllables (see Chapter 3, section 3.4.3).

2.2. 2 Cor 10–13 disposed in cōla and periods, with an English translation

[2 Cor 10:1–5]

|| ^[10:1] Αὐτὸς δὲ ἐγὼ Παῦλος παρακαλῶ ὑμᾶς (13)

διὰ τῆς πραῦτητος καὶ ἐπιεικειᾶς τοῦ Χριστοῦ (14)

ὃς κατὰ πρόσωπον μὲν ταπεινὸς ἐν ὑμῖν (13)

ἀπὼν δὲ θαρρῶ εἰς ὑμᾶς. ||

|| ^[2] Δέομαι δὲ τὸ μὴ παρὼν θαρρῆσαι τῇ πεποιθήσει ἣ λογίζομαι τολμήσαι ἐπὶ τινος
τούς λογιζομένους ἡμᾶς ὡς κατὰ σάρκα περιπατοῦντας. ||

|| ^[3] Ἐν σαρκὶ γὰρ περιπατοῦντες (9)

οὐ κατὰ σάρκα στρατευόμεθα. (10) ||

|| ^[4] Ἦ γὰρ ὄπλα τῆς στρατείας¹ ἡμῶν οὐ σαρκικά

ἀλλὰ δυνατὰ τῷ θεῷ πρὸς καθαίρεσιν ὀχυρωμάτων. ||

|| Λογισμοὺς καθαίρουσιν

^[5] καὶ πᾶν ὑψωμα ἐπαιρόμενον κατὰ τῆς γνώσεως τοῦ θεοῦ. || (19)

¹ 10:4 – The oldest witnesses have either the unaccented στρατιας (see § B* C D*) or the unaccented στρατειας (P⁴⁶ – note that NA28 erroneously gives στρατιας for P46), both of which may, by itacism, stand for either στρατιά (“army”; but also occasionally “campaign” [see BAGD 770d]) or στρατεία (“campaign,” “warfare”). The two terms (with accents) are attested in later witnesses. For a detailed overview of the textual tradition, see Swanson, *New Testament Greek Manuscripts: 2 Corinthians*, 128. Above, I retain στρατείας because the meaning “warfare” seems more likely in the context; but uncertainty remains as to the original reading.

|| ^[1] I, then, Paul myself, exhort you
by the meekness and forbearanceⁱ of Christ
who am humble when face to face with you
but when absent am bold towards you. ||

|| ^[2] Yes, I ask when present not to be bold with the confidence by which I reckon to show courage
[in front of some [people]]
those who reckon us as walking according to the flesh.ⁱⁱ ||

|| ^[3] For although we are walking in the flesh
we do not wage war according to the flesh. ||

|| ^[4] For the weapons of our warfare are not fleshy
but powerful for Godⁱⁱⁱ for the destruction of strongholds. ||

|| We destroy arguments
^[5] and every obstacle that sets itself up against the knowledge of God. ||

ⁱ 10:1 – There is an astonishing variety of translations proposed for ἐπιείκεια, among which “kindness,” “magnanimity,” “gentleness” (e.g. KJV), “fairness,” and “reasonableness” (e.g. Long, *II Corinthians: A Handbook on the Greek Text*, 181) – see a more exhaustive list in Harris, *The Second Epistle to the Corinthians*, 667. In the proposed translation, I follow Harris’ suggestion to refer to the usage of ἐπιείκεια and its derivated terms in the LXX: “... in the LXX, the word group ἐπιείκεια–ἐπιεικῆς–ἐπιεικῶς describes God’s character of gracious forbearance” (Harris, *The Second Epistle to the Corinthians*, 667–68; see e.g., 1 Kgdms 12:22; Ps. 85:5; Dan. 3:42; 4:27; 2 Macc. 10:4).

ⁱⁱ 10:2 – The first colon is difficult to render in English. Most commentators argue that δέομαι more likely introduces a request than a prayer (so e.g., Martin, *2 Corinthians*, 303; Harris, *The Second Epistle to the Corinthians*, 671; Guthrie, *2 Corinthians*, 469; Thrall, *2 Corinthians*, 604–605). The idea behind δέομαι τὸ μὴ παρῶν θαρρῆσαι is thus certainly “do not force me, when I will come back, to act boldly.” A possible paraphrase of the entire period could be as follows: “I implore you not to force me—when I will come back—to act boldly against you in the same way as I plan to act against those who accuse me of walking according to the flesh.”

ⁱⁱⁱ 10:4 – Various interpretations have been proposed for the dative noun phrase τῷ θεῷ (see a synthetic presentation of the different opinions in Harris, *The Second Epistle to the Corinthians*, 679–680). One possibility would be to take τῷ θεῷ as a dative of opinion or an ethical dative, i.e., as “an idiomatic way of expressing an emphatic (almost superlative) quality” (Culy and Parsons, *Acts: A Handbook on the Greek Text*, 125; quoted from Long, *II Corinthians*, 183–184). The sense of δυνατὰ τῷ θεῷ would thus be “extremely powerful.”

| **Καί** αἰχμαλωτίζοντες πᾶν νόημα εἰς τὴν ὑπακοὴν **τοῦ** Χριστοῦ. | (20)

|| ^[6] Καὶ ἐν ἐτοιμίῳ ἔχοντες ἐκδικῆσαι πᾶσαν **παρακοήν**
ὅταν πληρωθῇ ὑμῶν ἡ **ὑπακοή**. ||

| ^[7] τὰ κατὰ πρόσωπον βλέπετε. |

|| Εἴ τις πέποιθεν ἑαυτῷ Χριστοῦ **εἶναι** (12)

τοῦτο λογιζέσθω πάλιν ⁱ ἐφ’ ἑαυτοῦ (12)

ὅτι καθὼς αὐτὸς Χριστοῦ

οὕτως καὶ **ἡμεῖς**. ||

|| ^[8] Ἐάν τε ⁱⁱ γὰρ περισσώτερόν τι καυχῆσώμαι ⁱⁱⁱ περὶ τῆς ἐξουσίας ἡμῶν (23)

ἧς ἔδωκεν ὁ κύριος εἰς οἰκοδομὴν καὶ οὐκ εἰς καθαίρεσιν ὑμῶν (21)

οὐκ αἰσχυνησώμαι ^[9] ἵνα μὴ δόξω ὡς ἂν ἐκφοβεῖν ὑμᾶς διὰ τῶν ἐπιστολῶν. (24) ||

ⁱ 10:7 – Numerous Greek witnesses read ἀφ’ ἑαυτοῦ, including C D F G H K P Ψ 0209. 0243. 33. 81. 104. 365. 630. 1241. 1739. 1881. 2464. ℣ (see Swanson, *New Testament Greek Manuscripts: 2 Corinthians*, 129). This textual variant may have arisen as scribes sought to clarify the rare construction ἐπί + ἑαυτοῦ by replacing it with its more common equivalent ἀπό + ἑαυτοῦ (see in this sense Long, *2 Corinthians: A Handbook on the Greek Text*, 187).

ⁱⁱ 10:8 – The particle τε is missing in several important witnesses, including ℞⁴⁶ B F G H 0243. 6. 33. 365. 630. 1175. 1739. 1881 (see Swanson, *New Testament Greek Manuscripts: 2 Corinthians*, 130). Most Old Latin witnesses and a few Vulgate manuscripts also omit any particle. UBS⁵ and NA²⁸ place τε in brackets. For my choice to retain the particle, I follow Long’s argumentation that although the omission has strong external support, “the presence of τε may be more grammatically difficult and unusual, may have been considered unnecessary, and would be more likely to have given rise to its removal than to have been added, if not originally present.” (Long, *2 Corinthians: A Handbook on the Greek Text*, 188). This τε *solitarium* may serve to connect the statement of Christ’s authority (v. 8) with the previous statement of belonging to Christ (v. 7). On the τε *solitarium*, see Levinsohn, *Discourse Features of New Testament Greek*, 106–107; cf. Thrall, *Particles*, 96–97; cf. Denniston, *The Greek Particles*, 1954², 536; cf. Blass (BDF), *A Greek Grammar of the New Testament*, §443[3].

ⁱⁱⁱ 10:8 – Many witnesses have the indicative future καυχῆσώμαι (℞ L P 0209. 0243. 6. 104. 326. 1175. 1241. 1505. 1881*; cf. also g [77]), which is arguably a scribal error, as the presence of ἐάν at the beginning of the clause rather requires a subjunctive. The aorist subjunctive καυχῆσωμαι is supported by B C D (F G καυχῆσωμα) K Ψ 81. 365. 630. 1739. 1881^c. 2464. ℣ (see Swanson, *New Testament Greek Manuscripts: 2 Corinthians*, 130). Note that P⁴⁶ combines the two readings (καυχῆσωμαι καυχῆσώμαι), “if I do boast ... I will boast”

[10:5-9]

| *And we make captive every thought for obedience to Christ.* |

|| ^[6] *We also stand ready to punish any trace of disobedience
once is complete your own obedience.* ||

| ^[7] *Look at what is before your eyes!* |

|| *If anyone is confident that he is Christ's
let him consider this in himself
that just as he is Christ's
so also do we.* ||

|| ^[8] *If I do boast something more about our authority
which the Lord gave for your edification and not for your destruction
I shall not be ashamed, ^[9] lest I may seem as if I am terrifying you by letters.* ||

|| ^[10] Ὅτι αἱ ἐπιστολαὶ μὲνⁱ φησὶνⁱⁱ βαρεῖαι καὶ ἰσχυραὶ
ἢ δὲ παρουσία τοῦ σώματος ἀσθενῆς καὶ ὁ λόγος ἐξουθενημένος. ||

|| ^[11] Τοῦτο λογιζέσθω ὁ τοιοῦτος (11)
ὅτι οἱοί ἐσμεν τῷ λόγῳ δι’ ἐπιστολῶν ἀπόντες
τοιούτοι καὶ παρόντες τῷ ἔργῳ. (10) ||

|| ^[12] Οὐ γὰρ τολμῶμεν ἐγκρίναι ἢ συγκρίναι ἑαυτοὺς τισιν τῶν ἑαυτοὺς συνιστανόντων. ||

|| Ἄλλ’ αὐτοὶ ἐν ἑαυτοῖς ἑαυτοῦς μετροῦντες (13)
καὶ συγκρίνοντες ἑαυτοῦς ἑαυτοῖς (11)
ⁱⁱⁱ οὐ συνιᾶσιν. ||

|| ^[13] Ἡμεῖς δὲ οὐκ εἰς τὰ ἄμετρα καυχησόμεθα
ἀλλὰ κατὰ τὸ μέτρον τοῦ κανόνος οὗ ἐμέρισεν ἡμῖν ὁ θεὸς μέτρου
ἐφικέσθαι ἄχρι καὶ ὑμῶν. ||

ⁱ 10:10 – Numerous witnesses read αἱ μὲν ἐπιστολαί, with μὲν before ἐπιστολαί (κ² D F G I K L P Ψ 0209. 0243. 33. 81. 104. 365. 630. 1241. 1505. 1739. 1881. 2464 ℳ sy^h). This is arguably a correction made by scribes because μὲν usually stands as the second word of a μὲν... δέ construction. The more difficult reading αἱ ἐπιστολαὶ μὲν (attested notably in κ* B H 326. 1175. and likely in P⁴⁶) is to be preferred.

ⁱⁱ 10:10 – The text is uncertain here. Instead of the singular φησὶν, read by the majority of witnesses, B reads the plural φασὶν (“they say”). The plural is also attested in the Syriac manuscript tradition as well as in the Vulgate and in part of the Old Latin witnesses. In P⁴⁶, only the sigma and the final nu are readable (see Swanson, *New Testament Greek Manuscripts: 2 Corinthians*, 132), which leaves the door opened for either the singular or the plural. The grammatical context more likely requires a singular (see τις in v. 7 and ὁ τοιοῦτος in v. 11); however, one may also use this point as an argument to prefer the plural, as scribes may have sought to harmonise the verb with the context.

ⁱⁱⁱ 10:12–13 – The word group οὐ συνιᾶσιν ἡμεῖς δέ is absent in several witnesses of the Western text (D* F G, ar [61] b [89] vg, Ambst). I follow here the major view among scholars that this shorter reading is secondary and may be explained as a transcriptional accident, when the eye of the copyist of the Claromontanus (D) passed from οὐ to οὐκ. For more arguments in support of the longer reading, see the detailed discussions in K. H. Wong, *Boasting and Foolishness*, 97–103, or in Thrall, *The Second Epistle to the Corinthians*, vol. 2, 636–640; cf. also Harris, *The Second Epistle to the Corinthians*, 706–707; cf. also Metzger, *A Textual Commentary*, 514). Should the shorter reading be retained, this would modify the meaning, as it would imply to read the participles μετροῦντες and συγκρίνοντες as a first person referring to Paul (thus, “Though we measure ourselves against ourselves and compare ourselves with ourselves ...”). With respect to the colometric structure, the choice of the shorter reading would also imply that the whole segment from Ἄλλ’ αὐτοὶ up to ἐφικέσθαι ἄχρι καὶ ὑμῶν belongs to a single period.

|| ^[10] *For his letters, it is said, are weighty and mightyⁱ
but his bodily presence is weak and his speech is contemptible.* ||

|| ^[11] *Such a person should reckon this
that such as we are in word by letters when absent
such we [are] when present in action.* ||

|| ^[12] *True, we do not dare to classify or to compare ourselves with any of those who
[commend themselves.]* ||

|| *But they themselves, when measuring themselves with themselves
and comparing themselves to themselves
they lack understanding.* ||

|| ^[13] *We, however, will not boast beyond proper limits
but will take as a limit the ruleⁱⁱ that God has appointed to us as a limit
namelyⁱⁱⁱ to reach as far as even you.* ||

ⁱ 10:10 – Different propositions have been made for the translation of βαρύς and ἰσχυρός. The choice depends heavily on whether the comment on Paul’s letters is understood as a positive concessive statement that contrasts with the negative comment on his presence (“his letters are weighty and strong” – so e.g. Long, *II Corinthians: A Handbook on the Greek Text*, 186), or is rather taken as a critique (“his letters are tyrannical and aggressive” – so Harris, *The Second Epistle to the Corinthians*, 665).

ⁱⁱ 10:13 – The exact relationship between μέτρον and κανόνας (κατὰ τὸ μέτρον τοῦ κανόνας) is difficult to grasp, as each of the terms can mean “rule” or “limit.” Different translations have been proposed, with various interpretations for κανόνας, where the more common are territorial (so Long, *II Corinthians: A Handbook on the Greek Text*, 186: “according to the measure of the sphere of action that God has apportioned to us”; also see Barrett, *2 Corinthians*, 265; Metzger, *Canon*, 290; Wong, *Boasting and Foolishness*, 134–135; BAGD 504d, 515b; LSJ; NASB; NRSV; etc.) or administrative (so Harris, *The Second Epistle to the Corinthians*, 705: “[we will take] as a limit [for our boasting] the assignment that God has allocated to us as a limit”; cf. also in this sense Furnish, *II Corinthians*, 471; Lambrecht, *Second Corinthians*, 165; Carrez, *La deuxième épître de Saint Paul aux Corinthiens*, 204–206). A detailed discussion on the different possible interpretations can be found in Harris, *The Second Epistle to the Corinthians*, 709–716.

ⁱⁱⁱ 10:13 – I take the infinitive ἐφικέσθαι as expegetical to μέτρου (so also Harris, *The Second Epistle to the Corinthians*, 715–716; Long, *II Corinthians: A Handbook on the Greek Text*, 192; Robertson, *A Grammar of the Greek New Testament*, 4th ed., 1078; Lambrecht, *Second Corinthians*, 166). Alternatively, ἐφικέσθαι might be taken as telic (“so that we may reach ...” – so e.g. Barrett, *2 Corinthians*, 255; Thrall, *The Second Epistle to the Corinthians*, vol. 2, 647, n. 370) or consecutive (“with the result that we reached...” – so e.g. Bultmann, *Der zweite Brief an die Korinther*, 194).

| ^[14] Οὐ γὰρ ὡς μὴ ἐφικνούμενοι εἰς ὑμᾶς ὑπερεκτείνομεν ἑαυτοῦς. (21) |

| Ἄχρι γὰρ καὶ ὑμῶν ἐφθάσαμεν ἐν τῷ εὐαγγελίῳ τοῦ Χριστοῦ. (20) |

| ^[15] Οὐκ εἰς τὰ ἄμετρα καυχώμενοι ἐν ἀλλοτρίοις κόποις. |

|| Ἐλπίδα δὲ ἔχοντες ἀύξανομένης τῆς πίστεως ὑμῶν (13)

ἐν ὑμῖν μεγαλυνθῆναι κατὰ τὸν κανόνα ἡμῶν (11)

εἰς περισσεῖαν

^[16] εἰς τὰ ὑπερέκεινα ὑμῶν εὐαγγελίσασθαι (10)

οὐκ ἐν ἀλλοτρίῳ κανόνι εἰς τὰ ἔτοιμα καυχήσασθαι. (13) ||

|| ^[17] Ὁ δὲ καυχώμενος (6)

ἐν κυρίῳ καυχάσθω. (7) ||

|| ^[18] Οὐ γὰρ ὁ ἑαυτὸν συνιστάνων ἐκεῖνός ἐστιν δόκιμος

ἀλλ' ὃν ὁ κύριος συνίστησιν. ||

|| ^[11:1] Ὁφελον ἀνείχεσθέ μου μικρόν τι¹ ἀφροσύνης ! ||

| ἀλλὰ καὶ ἀνέχεσθέ μου. |

¹ 11:1 – τι is absent in numerous witnesses (F G H K L P 81. 104. 630. 1175. 1241. 1505. 2464 ℳ, it, Lcf Ambst) but should be retained as there is superior support for its inclusion (ℱ⁴⁶ & B D Ψ 0121. 0243. 6. 33. 365. 1739. 1881., f t vg, sy^h). It is also easier to imagine that τι was dropped than added, as it may seem redundant in view of the preceding μικρόν.

[10:14–11:1]

| ^[14] *For it is not that we are overstepping ourselves as if we did not reach as far as you.* |

| *Indeed, we have reached as far as to you with the Gospel of Christ!* |

| ^[15] *We do not boast beyond proper limits in the labour of others.* |

|| *But we have hope, as your faith increases
that among youⁱ our work may be enlarged, according to our rule
until it overflowsⁱⁱ
^[16] so that [we may] evangeliseⁱⁱⁱ into places beyond you
without boasting in what is already done in someone else's rule.* ||

|| ^[17] *Rather, let the one who boasts
boast in the Lord.* ||

|| ^[18] *For it is not the one who commends himself who is approved
but the one whom the Lord commends.* ||

|| ^[1] *If only you would put up with me in a little bit of foolishness!* ||

| *Yes, do put up with me!* |

ⁱ 10:15 – In my proposed translation, ἐν ὑμῖν is understood as locative, thus “among you” or “in you” (see in this sense e.g. Barrett, *2 Corinthians*, 267; Lambrecht, *Second Corinthians*, 167; Long, *II Corinthians: A Handbook on the Greek Text*, 194). Alternatively, ἐν ὑμῖν may be understood as instrumental or as indicating circumstances, thus “by your aid” (so Bruce, *An Expanded Paraphrase of the Epistles of Paul*, 151) or “with your help” (so Harris, *The Second Epistle to the Corinthians*, 720).

ⁱⁱ 10:15 – εἰς περισσεῖαν functions as a modifier of μεγαλυνθῆναι that intensifies the meaning of the verb, thus “to the point of abundance,” “abundantly” or “until it overflows” (Harris, *The Second Epistle to the Corinthians*, 721; cf. Long, *II Corinthians: A Handbook on the Greek Text*, 194).

ⁱⁱⁱ 10:16 – Commentators have various views as to how the infinitives εὐαγγελίσασθαι and καυχῆσασθαι relate to the rest of the sentence (10:15). See a summary of the different possibilities in Harris, *The Second Epistle to the Corinthians*, 722–723.

| ^[2] ζηλώ γάρ ὑμᾶς θεοῦ ζήλω· |

|| Ἡρμοσάμην γάρ ὑμᾶς ἐνὶ ἀνδρί (11)
παρθένον ἀγνήν παραστήσαι τῷ Χριστῷ. (12) ||

|| ^[3] Φοβοῦμαι δὲ μή πως
ὡς ὁ ὄφις ἐξηπάτησεν Εὐάν ἐν τῇ πανουργίᾳ αὐτοῦ (19)
φθαρῆ τὰ νοήματα ὑμῶν
ἀπὸ τῆς ἀπλότητος καὶ τῆς ἀγνότητοςⁱ τῆς εἰς τὸν Χριστόν. (18) ||

|| ^[4] Εἰ μὲν γάρ ὁ ἐρχόμενος ἄλλον Ἰησοῦν κηρύσσει ὃν οὐκ ἐκηρύξαμεν
ἢ πνεῦμα ἕτερον λαμβάνετε ὃ οὐκ ἐλάβετε (16)
ἢ εὐαγγέλιον ἕτερον ὃ οὐκ ἐδέξασθε (15)
καλῶς ἀνέχεσθε.ⁱⁱ ||

|| ^[5] Λογίζομαι γάρ μηδὲν ὑστερηκέναι τῶν ὑπερλίαν ἀποστόλων. ||

ⁱ 11:3 – Numerous witnesses omit καὶ τῆς ἀγνότητος (8² H K L P Ψ 0121. 0243. 365. 630. 1175. 1241. 1505. 1739. 1881. 2464 ℳ, (b) f* vg, sy^p; JulCl). However, the manuscript tradition rather supports the inclusion of καὶ τῆς ἀγνότητος, as this reading is attested both in the earliest manuscripts (P⁴⁶, 8*, B) and in the Western tradition (D* [ἀπὸ τῆς ἀγνότητος καὶ τῆς ἀπλότητος] F G). The reading without καὶ τῆς ἀγνότητος may be easily explained as a scribal oversight due to homoeoteleuton (–ότητος and –ότητος). Note that WH, NA²⁸ and UBS⁵ all place this καὶ τῆς ἀγνότητος within brackets (on this choice from the part of the committee of NA and UBS, see Metzger, *A Textual Commentary on the Greek New Testament*, 514–515). In any case, the choice to retain καὶ τῆς ἀγνότητος or not has no decisive impact on the delineation of cola.

ⁱⁱ 11:4 – Instead of the present ἀνέχεσθε (attested in P⁴⁶ B D¹ [D* 33 ἀνέχεσθαι], r, sa), the manuscript tradition also provides strong support for the imperfect ἀνείχεσθε (P³⁴ 8 D² F^{vid} G H K L P Ψ 0121. 0243. 0278. 81. 104. 365. 630. 1175. 1241. 1505. 1739. 1881. 2464 ℳ, lat, sy). Although the imperfect tense certainly represents the most difficult reading (see the two preceding present, κηρύσσει and λαμβάνετε), the present tense is to be preferred on the basis that it “better accords with Paul’s directness in the context (cf. vv. 6, 8, 10, 13–15), than does a hypothetical (with ἄν understood) and more gentle statement, ‘if someone comes and preaches ... you would tolerate him well enough’” (Harris, *2 Corinthians*, 731, note g).

[11:2–5]

| ^[2] *For I am jealous for you with God's jealousy.* |

|| *Indeed, I betrothed you to one husband
in order to present you as a pure maiden to Christ.* ||

|| ^[3] *But I am afraid that somewhat
just as the snake deceived Eve by his cunning
your minds may be corrupted
[and thus lured away] fromⁱ the generosity and the purity towards Christ.* ||

|| ^[4] *For indeed, if the one who comes preaches another Jesus whom we did not preach
or you receive a different spirit which you did not receive
or [you accept] a different gospel which you did not accept
you put up [with it] beautifully!* ||

|| ^[5] *I reckon I am not at all inferior to those super-apostles.* ||

ⁱ 11:3 – The combination φθαρῆ and ἀπό (litteraly, “corrupted *from*”) is sometimes rendered in translations by two verbs, with the first one expressing the corruption of the thoughts (φθαρῆ τὰ νοήματα ὑμῶν) and the second one expressing the loss of the devotion towards Christ (ἀπό τῆς ἀπλότητος καὶ τῆς ἀγνότητος τῆς εἰς τὸν Χριστόν). See the discussion in Harris, *The Second Epistle to the Corinthians*, 739–740.

|| ^[6] Εἰ δὲ καὶ ἰδιώτης τῷ λόγῳ
ἀλλ' οὐ τῇ γνώσει. ||

| ἀλλ' ἐν παντὶ φανερώσαντεςⁱ ἐν πᾶσιν εἰς ὑμᾶς. ||

| ^[7] Ἡ ἀμαρτία^υ ἐποίησα ἐμαυτὸν ταπεινῶν ἵνα ὑμεῖς ὑψωθῆτε (23)
ὅτι δωρεὰ^υ τὸ τοῦ θεοῦ εὐαγγέλιον εὐηγγελισάμην ὑμῖν ; (22) ||

|| ^[8] Ἄλλας ἐκκλησίας ἐσύλησα
λαβὼν ὀψώνιον πρὸς τὴν ὑμῶν διακονίαν. ||

|| ^[9] Καὶ παρῶν πρὸς ὑμᾶς καὶ ὑστερηθεῖς
οὐ κατενάρκησα οὐθενός. ||

|| Τὸ γὰρ ὑστέρημά μου προσανεπλήρωσαν οἱ ἀδελφοὶ ἐλθόντες ἀπὸ Μακεδονίας. ||

|| Καὶ ἐν παντὶ ἀβαρῆ ἐμαυτὸν ὑμῖν ἐτήρησα
καὶ τηρήσω. ||

|| ^[10] Ἐστὶν ἀλήθεια Χριστοῦ ἐν ἐμοί
ὅτι ἡ καύχησις αὕτη οὐ φραγῆσεται εἰς ἐμὲ ἐν τοῖς κλίμασιν τῆς Ἀχαΐας. ||

ⁱ II:6 – Instead of the active participle φανερώσαντες, numerous witnesses have the passive form φανερωθεντες (including B³⁴ K² D² K L P Ψ 0278. 81. 104. 365. 1175. 1241. 1505. 2464 W, r), while other witnesses read the singular passive φανερωθεις (“I am revealed” – D*, lat; Ambst). The active form was retained above because it is easier to explain a change from active towards passive rather than the reverse, as one would expect an object to be expressed with the active participle (on this, see Harris, 2 *Corinthians*, 731, n. i).

|| ^[6] *Moreover, even if I am unskilled in speech
yet I am not in knowledge.* ||

| *On the contrary, in every way we have revealed it to you in all things.* |

|| ^[7] *Or did I commit a sin by humbling myself so that you might be elevated
in that I preachedⁱ the Gospel of God to you free of charge?* ||

|| ^[8] *Other churches I robbed
by accepting support [from them] for your service.* ||

|| ^[9] *And when I was with you and in need
I did not burden anyone.* ||

|| *In fact, my needs were supplied by the brothers who came from Macedonia.* ||

|| *And in every way I kept myself unburdensome to you
and so will I keep.* ||

|| ^[10] *The truth of Christ is in me
that this boasting will not be silenced for meⁱⁱ among the regions of Achaia.* ||

ⁱ II:7 – ὅτι is understood here to indicate the content of Paul’s “sin” (cf. in this sense notably Lambrecht, *Second Corinthians*, 172, “in that I preached the Gospel of God”; Bultmann, *Der zweite Brief an die Korinther*, 207, “indem Ich euch unentgeltlich das Evangelium Gottes verkündigte”; Barrett, *2 Corinthians*, 281, “by preaching the Gospel of God”; Grässer, *Der zweite Brief an die Korinther, vol. II*, 133, “indem ich unentgeltlich das Evangelium Gottes verkündigte”; Harris, *The Second Epistle to the Corinthians*, 753–754, “by preaching the Gospel of God”; Guthrie, *2 Corinthians*, 515, “by preaching God’s gospel”). Some commentators prefer to take ὅτι as causal, thus “because I preached ...” (so e.g. A. Plummer, *A Critical and Exegetical Commentary on the Second Epistle of St. Paul to the Corinthians*, 301–302; Martin, *2 Corinthians*, 343; Long, *II Corinthians: A Handbook on the Greek Text*, 203). As Harris concludes, “the sense differs little whichever of these alternatives is preferred” (Harris, *The Second Epistle to the Corinthians*, 754).

ⁱⁱ II:10 – I associate εἰς ἐμέ with οὐ φραγήσεται (so too Harris, *The Second Epistle to the Corinthians*, 764–765; Long, *II Corinthians: A Handbook on the Greek Text*, 205; Guthrie, *2 Corinthians*, 524; see also Lambrecht, *Second Corinthians*, 172; Thrall, *The Second Epistle to the Corinthians, vol. 2*, 656; and Barrett, *2 Corinthians*, 270). A possible paraphrase would be “as far as I am concerned, this boasting will not be silenced...” Alternatively, εἰς ἐμέ is sometimes associated with ἡ καύχησις αὐτε and then understood as locative: “this boasting (which is) in me,” thus “my boasting” or “the boasting of mine” (so e.g. Furnish, *2 Corinthians*, 484; Martin, *2 Corinthians*, 327).

| ^[11] διὰ τί ; |

| ὅτι οὐκ ἀγαπῶ ὑμᾶς ; |

| ὁ θεὸς οἶδεν· |

|| ^[12] Ὁ δὲ ποιῶ (4)

καὶ ποιήσω (4)

Ἰνα ἐκκόψω τὴν ἀφορμὴν τῶν θελώντων ἀφορμὴν (16)

Ἰνα ἐν ᾧ καυχῶνται εὐρεθῶσιν καθὼς καὶ ἡμεῖς. (16) ||

|| ^[13] Οἱ γὰρ τοιοῦτοι ψευδαπόστολοι

ἐργάται δόλιοι μετασχηματιζόμενοι εἰς ἀποστόλους Χριστοῦ. ||

| ^[14] καὶ οὐ θαῦμα· |

| αὐτὸς γὰρ ὁ σατανᾶς μετασχηματίζεται εἰς ἄγγελον φωτός· |

| ^[15] οὐ μέγα οὖν εἰ καὶ οἱ διάκονοι αὐτοῦ μετασχηματίζονται ὡς διάκονοι δικαιοσύνης· |

| ᾧ τὸ τέλος ἔσται κατὰ τὰ ἔργα αὐτῶν· |

| ^[11] *Why?* |

| *Because I do not love you?* |

| *God knows I do!* |

|| ^[12] *And what I am doing
that I will also [continue to] do
in order to cut off occasion to those who want an occasion
in order to be found, in what they boast about, just as even we.ⁱ* ||

|| ^[13] *For such people are false apostles
deceitful workers disguising themselves into apostles of Christ.* ||

| ^[14] *And no wonder!* |

| *For Satan himself disguises himself as an angel of light!* |

| ^[15] *So it is not a great surprise if his servants also disguise themselves as servants of
[righteousness.]* |

| *Their end will be according to their works.* |

ⁱ II:12 – There are various propositions for the translation of ἵνα ἐν ᾧ καυχῶνται εὐρεθῶσιν καθὼς καὶ ἡμεῖς, depending on the interpretation of ἐν ᾧ καυχῶνται: e.g. “... [an opportunity] to become, in their boasting, just what we are” (Barrett, *2 Corinthians*, 284); “in order to be found with something about which they would boast, just as even we (have)” (Long, *II Corinthians: A Handbook on the Greek Text*, 201); “... [an opportunity] to be regarded as our equals in what they are boasting about” (Lambrecht, *Second Corinthians*, 177); “[a chance] to be considered our equals in the things about which they boast” (Guthrie, *2 Corinthians*, 515). As most commentators argue, the second ἵνα clause more likely describes the ἀφορμή (“occasion,” “opportunity”) that Paul’s rivals are seeking than Paul’s intention (so A. Plummer, *A Critical and Exegetical Commentary on the Second Epistle of St. Paul to the Corinthians*, 307; Barret, 284–285; Lambrecht, *Second Corinthians*, 177–178; Grässer, *Der zweite Brief an die Korinther*, vol. II, 142; Harris, *The Second Epistle to the Corinthians*, 768–769; Long, *II Corinthians: A Handbook on the Greek Text*, 201; Guthrie, *2 Corinthians*, 525–526). Note, however, that some commentators prefer to analyse the second ἵνα clause in tandem with the first one, meaning that it expresses the second or final aim of ποιήσω: according to this understanding, Paul wishes to force his opponents to become financially independent from the Corinthians, just as he himself is (so Meyer, *Critical and Exegetical Hand-book to the Epistles to the Corinthians*, 649–651).

|| ^[16] Πάλιν λέγω
μή τις με δόξη ἄφρονα εἶναι ! ||

|| Εἰ δὲ μή γε
κἂν ὡς ἄφρονα δέξασθ^ε με (9)
ἵνα κἀγὼ μικρόν τι καυχ^ήσωμαι. (11) ||

|| ^[17] Ὁ λαλω
οὐ κατὰ κύριον λαλω
ἀλλ' ὡς ἐν ἀφροσύνη
ἐν ταύτῃ τῇ ὑποστάσει τῆς καυχήσεως. ||

|| ^[18] Ἐπεὶ πολλοὶ καυχῶνται κατὰ ⁱ σάρκα
κἀγὼ καυχῆσομαι. ||

|| ^[19] Ἡδέως γὰρ ἀνέχεσθε τῶν ἀφρόνων
φρόνιμοι ὄντες. ||

|| ^[20] Ἀνέχεσθε γὰρ εἴ τις ὑμᾶς καταδουλοῖ
εἴ τις κατεσθίει (6)
εἴ τις λαμβάνει (5)
εἴ τις ἐπαίρεται (6)
εἴ τις εἰς πρόσωπον ὑμᾶς δέρει. ||

ⁱ 11:18 – Numerous witnesses contain an additional τὴν before σάρκα (ℵ² B D¹ K L P Ψ 0121. 630. 1241. 1739^c. 1881^c. 2464 ℳ). Above, I retain the reading without τὴν (attested in ℱ⁴⁶ ℵ* D* F G H 098. 0278. 33. 81. 104. 365. 629. 1175. 1505. 1739*. 1881*) in view of Paul's normal usage of the idiom κατὰ σάρκα (Rm 1:3; 4:1; 8:4-5.12.13; 9:3-5; 1 Co 1:26; 10:18; 2 Co 1:17; 5:16; 10:2; 11:18; Ga 4:23.29).

|| ^[16] *I say it again:*

let no one think me a fool! |

|| *But if this were not the case*

then welcome me as a fool

so that I too may boast a little. ||

|| ^[17] *What I say*

I do not say according to the Lord

but as it were in foolishness

as I undertakeⁱ this boasting. ||

|| ^[18] *Since many people are boasting according to the flesh*

I too will boast. ||

|| ^[19] *For gladly you put up with the fools*

you who are so wise. ||

|| ^[20] *Indeed, you put up with it if someone enslaves you*

if someone devoursⁱⁱ [you]

if someone takes advantage [of you]

if someone elevates himself

if someone strikes you in the face. ||

ⁱ 11:17 – Here I follow F. W. Danker (*II Corinthians*, 176), W. Harris (*The Second Epistle to the Corinthians*, 781), and F. Long (*II Corinthians: A Handbook on the Greek Text*, 211–212) in understanding ὑπόστασις to mean “undertaking.” Thus, ἐν ταύτῃ τῇ ὑποστάσει τῆς καυχήσεως designates the boasting that Paul is about to undertake (in 11:16–12:10); also see Thrall, *The Second Epistle to the Corinthians*, vol. 2, 714, who suggests “project.” Alternatively, ὑπόστασις may signify “confidence,” thus “in this confidence of boasting” or “in this boastful confidence” (see e.g. in this sense A. Plummer, *A Critical and Exegetical Commentary on the Second Epistle of St. Paul to the Corinthians*, 312; Barrett, *2 Corinthians*, 290; Carrez, *La deuxième épître aux Corinthiens*, 217; also see RSV; NASB; NRSV; Seg. 21). As to the ἐν that precedes, I take it as temporal, hence my translation “as I undertake” (see also in this sense Harris, *The Second Epistle to the Corinthians*, 781). However, this ἐν might also mean “in respect of” (so e.g. Thrall, *The Second Epistle to the Corinthians*, vol. 2, 709), “with regard to” (so e.g., Lambrecht, *Second Corinthians*, 187) or “with respect to” (so e.g., Long, *II Corinthians: A Handbook on the Greek Text*, 209).

ⁱⁱ 11:20 – In order to render the idea behind εἴ τις κατεσθίει, Barrett suggests the expression “if someone eats out of house and home” (Barrett, *2 Corinthians*, 291); cf. the discussion in Harris, *The Second Epistle to the Corinthians*, 785.

|| ^[21] Κατὰ ἀτιμίαν λέγω (8)
ὡς ὅτι ἡμεῖς ἡσθενήκαμεν^ι. (10) ||

|| Ἐν ᾧ δ' ἄν τις τολμῶ (6)
ἐν ἀφροσύνη λέγω (7)
τολμῶ κἀγώ. ||

| ^[22] ἔβραῖοι εἰσιν ; |

| κἀγώ· |

| Ἰσραηλιταί εἰσιν ; |

| κἀγώ· |

| σπέρμα Ἀβραάμ εἰσιν ; |

| κἀγώ· |

| ^[23] Διάκονοι Χριστοῦ εἰσιν ; |

|| Παραφρονῶν λαλῶ
ὑπὲρ ἐγώ ! ||

ⁱ 11:21 – In place of the perfect ἡσθενήκαμεν (attested in \mathfrak{P}^{46} & B H 0243. 0278. 33. 69. 81. 330. 1175. 1739*. 1881. 2400. – see Swanson, *New Testament Greek Manuscripts: 2 Corinthians*, 152), an impressive array of Greek witnesses read the aorist ἡσθενήσαμεν (including D F G I K L P Ψ 0121. 104. 365. 630. 1241. 1505. 1739^c. 2464 \mathfrak{M} – see Swanson, *New Testament Greek Manuscripts: 2 Corinthians*, 152). Harris suggests that “some scribe(s) may have been troubled by Paul’s confession, ἡμεῖς ἡσθενήκαμεν, and, to avoid any suggestion that he was currently “weak,” substituted the aorist.” (Harris, *The Second Epistle to the Corinthians*, 778). On the value of the perfect in this context, see the discussion in Harris, *The Second Epistle to the Corinthians*, 788. Note that after the aorist ἡσθενήσαμεν, a few witnesses (notably D and 1735) add ἐν τούτῳ τῷ μέρει, “in this matter,” which also attenuates the idea of Paul’s weakness by specifying in which area he has been weak.

|| ^[21] *To my shame I confess:
we have been weak.*ⁱ ||

|| *Yet in whatever way any of them is bold
– I am speaking in pure folly –
I am just as bold myself.* ||

| ^[22] *Are they Hebrews?* |

| *So am I.* |

| *Are they Israelites?* |

| *So am I.* |

| *Are they offspring of Abraham?* |

| *So am I.* |

| ^[23] *Are they servants of Christ?* |

|| *I am out of my mind when I say this:
I [am] more!* ||

ⁱ 11:21 – There are different ways of understanding the combination ὡς ὄτι in v. 21 – see a list of the various options in Harris, *The Second Epistle to the Corinthians*, 787–788. In the above translation, I take this expression to be equivalent to ὄτι (so too Lambrecht, *Second Corinthians*, 187; Harris, *The Second Epistle to the Corinthians*, 787–788; Barrett, *2 Corinthians*, 292). The idea would thus be “I have been weak *in comparison*,” i.e., in comparison with the “strongness” of Paul’s rivals evoked in v. 20. It is also possible that ὡς serves to call into question the validity of the statement that follows (which is introduced by ὄτι): see in this sense Long, *II Corinthians: A Handbook on the Greek Text*, 213; cf. Barrett, *2 Corinthians*, 292. On the combination ὡς ὄτι, see BDF §396; also see a similar construction 2 Th. 2:2.

| ἐν κόποις περισσοτέρως· (8) |

| ἐν φυλακαῖς περισσοτέρως· (9) |

| ἐν πληγαῖς ὑπερβαλλόντως·ⁱ (8) |

| ἐν θανάτοις πολλάκις· (7) |

||^[24] Ὑπὸ Ἰουδαίων πεντάκις τεσσαράκοντα παρὰ μίαν ἔλαβον. ||

|^[25] τρις ἐρραβδίσθην· (5) |

| ἅπαξ ἐλιθάσθην· (6) |

| τρις ἐναυάγησα· (6) |

| νυχθήμερον ἐν τῷ βυθῷ πεποίηκα· |

|^[26] ὁδοιπορίαις πολλάκις· |

| κινδύνοις ποταμῶν· (6) |

| κινδύνοις ληστῶν· (5) |

ⁱ II:23 – In the two phrases ἐν φυλακαῖς περισσοτέρως and ἐν πληγαῖς ὑπερβαλλόντως, five variations in word order are attested in the manuscript tradition, of which three have strong support: (1) ἐν φυλακαῖς περισσοτέρως ἐν πληγαῖς ὑπερβαλλόντως (P⁴⁶ B D^{*2} 0243 33 629. 630. 1739. 1881, lat; Ambst) ; (2) ἐν πληγαῖς περισσοτέρως ἐν φυλακαῖς ὑπερβαλλόντως (8^{*} F G ; Or) ; (3) ἐν πληγαῖς ὑπερβαλλόντως ἐν φυλακαῖς περισσοτέρως (8² D¹ H Ψ 0121 38¹ sy^p). For my choice to retain reading (1), I follow Harris' argumentation that the sequence labours-beatings-prisons-death sentences, present in (2) and (3), represents a more natural gradation of severity and thus is arguably a correction (see Harris, *2 Corinthians*, 792, n. a).

| *Withⁱ far more labours.* |

| *With far more prisons.* |

| *With countless beatings.* |

| *With frequent death sentences.* |

|| ^[24] *From the Jews five times I received the forty minus one [lashes].* ||

| ^[25] *Three times I was beaten with a rod.* |

| *Once I was pelted with stones.* |

| *Three times I was shipwrecked.* |

| *A night and a day I have spent adrift at sea.* |

| ^[26] *[I have been]ⁱⁱ on journeys frequently.* |

| *Withⁱⁱⁱ dangers from rivers.* |

| *With dangers from bandits.* |

ⁱ 11:23 – The formulations of this cōlon and of the three that follow are elliptical. The idea is certainly something like this: “*I have proved to be a better servant of Christ* in the midst of / with respect to labours, prisons, beatings, and death sentences, *that I have experienced far more / frequently.*” Nonetheless, there is no need to supply a verb in the translation, as these four cōla are perfectly intelligible even without a verb. The preposition ἐν can be read in a circumstantial or contextual sense, “in the context of ...” (so Long, *II Corinthians: A Handbook on the Greek Text*, 214); as “with” (Harris, *The Second Epistle to the Corinthians*, 797); in a locative sense, “in/in the midst of”; in a referential sense, “with respect to”; or, in a causal sense, “because of”? In any case, the four sufferings evoked inv. 23 are all illustrative of why and how Paul is “superior” to his adversaries.

ⁱⁱ 11:26 – The Greek has no verb. In the translation I supply “I have been” for the sake of intelligibility.

ⁱⁱⁱ 11:26 – This cōlon and the ones that follow (up to Κινδύνοις ἐν ψευδαδέλφοις at the end of v. 26) list specific dangers associated with travel. The dative κινδύνοις arguably expresses associated circumstances (see Harris, *The Second Epistle to the Corinthians*, 806). The idea is each time “*During these frequent journeys I was exposed to dangers from rivers / dangers from bandits / dangers from my people / etc.*”

| κινδύνοις ἐκ γένους· (6) |

| κινδύνοις ἐξ ἔθνων· (6) |

| κινδύνοις ἐν πόλει· (6) |

| κινδύνοις ἐν ἐρημίᾳ· (8) |

| κινδύνοις ἐν θαλάσση· (7) |

| κινδύνοις ἐν ψευδαδέλφοις· (8) |

| ^[27] ἰ κόπω καὶ μόχθω· |

| ἐν ἀγρυπνίαις πολλάκις· (8) |

| ἐν λιμῷ καὶ δίψει· (6) |

| ἐν νηστείαις πολλάκις· (7) |

| ἐν ψύχει καὶ γυμνότητι· (8) |

|| ^[28] Χωρὶς τῶν παρεκτός

ἢ ἐπίστασις ⁱⁱ μοι ⁱⁱⁱ ἢ καθ' ἡμέραν (II)

ἢ μέριμνα πασῶν τῶν ἐκκλησιῶν. (II) ||

ⁱ II:27 – Before κόπω, an impressive array of witnesses have an additional ἐν (κ¹ H K L P 0121. 33. 81. 104. 365. 630. 1175. 1241. 1505. 1881. 2464 ℳ, lat; Ambst). The reading without ἐν (attested in ℱ⁴⁶ κ* B D F G Ψ 0243. 1739) is to be preferred as *lectio difficilior* (see the following four cases of ἐν in v. 27).

ⁱⁱ II:28 – The reading ἐπίστασις (ℱ^{46,99} κ B D [F G ἐπίστασεις] H* 0243. 0278. 33. 81. 326. 1175. 1739. 1881) is certainly to be preferred over ἐπισύστασις (H^c I 0121. 104. 365. 630. 1241. 1505. 2464. ℳ) and ὑπόστασις (K L P Ψ 049. 075. [see Swanson, *New Testament Greek Manuscripts: 2 Corinthians*, 156]), based on its stronger support in the manuscript tradition. In addition, the meaning “pressure” (ἐπίστασις) makes more sense in this context than “disturbance, insurrection” (ἐπισύστασις) or “foundation” (ὑπόστασις).

ⁱⁱⁱ II:28 – In place of the dative μοί, numerous witnesses (κ² D K L P Ψ 0121. 0243. 104. 365. 630. 1241. 1505. 1739. 1881. 2464 ℳ lat; Ambst) read the genitive μοῦ, thus “my attention” or “my responsibility.” However, the reading μοί has strongest support in the earlier manuscript tradition (ℱ⁴⁶ κ* B H and d [75]; see also F G 0278. 33. 81. 1175 b[89]) and accords better with the preceding ἐπίστασις (“the pressure on me,” “what presses on me”).

| *With dangers from my people.* |

| *With dangers from Gentiles.* |

| *With dangers in the city.* |

| *With dangers in the desert.* |

| *With dangers on the sea.* |

| *With dangers among false brothers.* |

| *(I have known)ⁱ labour and toil.* |

| *Withⁱⁱ sleepless nights frequently.* |

| *With hunger and thirst.* |

| *With fasting frequently.* |

| *With coldness and nakedness.* |

|| ^[28] *Apart from these external circumstancesⁱⁱⁱ*
there is what presses on me every day
[namely] the anxiety^{iv} for all the churches. ||

ⁱ 11:27 – The Greek has no verb here. In the translation I supply “I have known” merely in order to signal that this colon introduces a new topic (that of “labour and toil”) that is no longer a subcategory of the “journeys” of v. 26.

ⁱⁱ 11:27 – I understand the ἐν + dative to express circumstances, thus my translation “with.” Alternatively, the datives may be locative, “in” or “in the midst of” (so Barrett, *2 Corinthians*, 288).

ⁱⁱⁱ 11:28 – Alternatively, the expression χωρὶς τῶν παρεκτὸς can mean “apart from what I leave unmentioned,” which would imply that 11:23–27 is intended only as an illustrative list of Paul’s sufferings, not as an exhaustive list.

^{iv} 11:28 – I take ἡ μέριμνα πασῶν τῶν ἐκκλησιῶν as expegetical of ἡ ἐπίστασις (so too, among others, A. Plummer, *A Critical and Exegetical Commentary on the Second Epistle of St. Paul to the Corinthians*, 329–330; Barrett, *2 Corinthians*, 300–301; Harris, *The Second Epistle to the Corinthians*, 811; Long, *II Corinthians: A Handbook on the Greek Text*, 219; Thrall, *The Second Epistle to the Corinthians*, vol. 2, 749, n. 671). An alternative would be to consider that ἡ μέριμνα ἡ μέριμνα expresses the cause of Paul’s ἐπίστασις: “... the daily pressure imposed by

| ^[29] **τ**ίς ἀσθενεῖ καὶ οὐκ ἀσθενῶ ; |

| **τ**ίς σκανδαλίζεται καὶ οὐκ ἐγὼ πυροῦμαι ; |

|| ^[30] Εἰ καυχᾶσθαι δεῖ
τὰ τῆς ἀσθενείας μουⁱ καυχῆσομαι. ||

|| ^[31] Ὁ θεός καὶ πατήρ τοῦ κυρίου Ἰησοῦ οἶδεν
ὁ ὧν εὐλογητός εἰς τοὺς αἰῶνας
ὅτι οὐ ψεύδομαι. ||

| ^[32] ἐν Δαμασκῶ ὁ ἐθνάρχης Ἀρέτα τοῦ βασιλέως ἐφρούρει τὴν πόλιν Δαμασκηῶν
[πιάσαι με·ⁱ |

|| ^[33] **κ**αὶ διὰ θυρίδος ἐν σαργάνῃ (9)
ἐχάλασθην διὰ τοῦ τείχους (8)
καὶ ἐξέφυγον τὰς χεῖρας αὐτοῦ. (10) ||

| ^[12:1] καυχᾶσθαι δεῖ·ⁱⁱ |

my anxious care for all the churches.” However, as Harris notes, such a relation would normally be expressed by the subjective genitive (Harris, *The Second Epistle to the Corinthians*, 811).

ⁱ 11:32 – The participle θέλων is added in numerous and important witnesses, either after με (8, D², H, K, L, P, Ψ, 0121, 0243, 0278^{vid}, 33, 104, 326, 365, 630, 1175, 1836, 1837, 2464, *Wt al.*) or before πιάσαι (F G [θέλων πιάσαι μαι] 1739 [θέλων με πιάσαι]), thus “wishing to arrest me” or “because he wished to arrest me”—see Swanson, *New Testament Greek Manuscripts: 2 Corinthians*, 158. This longer reading is also attested in sy^h and bo. Although the support for the inclusion of θέλων is strong, the participle is more likely secondary: this addition might result from a desire to improve the style and/or as an anticipation of v. 33, where it is specified that the ethnarch’s plan to apprehend Paul did not succeed (see in this sense Harris, *The Second Epistle to the Corinthians*, 817; cf. also Metzger, *A Textual Commentary*, 515–516). With respect to colometry, this longer reading would perhaps imply to take πιάσαι με θέλων as a cōlon on its own.

ⁱⁱ 12:1 – In place of δεῖ, “it is necessary,” some important witnesses read δέ (8 D* Ψ cf. also bo). If one adopts this reading, then καυχᾶσθαι δέ and οὐ συμφέρον μὲν form a single cōlon (“Boasting is not beneficial ...”). Because this alternative reading is easier in that it avoids asyndeton (Harris, *The Second Epistle to the Corinthians*, 828) and clarifies the meaning (Metzger, *A Textual Commentary*, 516), it is arguably secondary. Note that a few witnesses have εἰ before καυχᾶσθαι δεῖ, thus “If it is necessary to boast ...” (8² H 81, 326, 1175, 1837, 1874, ar f vg sa Ambst. *al.* [see Swanson, *New Testament Greek Manuscripts: 2 Corinthians*, 159]), probably influenced by the wording in 11:30.

[11:29–12:1]

| ^[29] *Who is weak and I am not weak?* |

| *Who is tripped up and I do not burn?* |

|| ^[30] *If boasting is necessary*

[this is] about matters of my weakness [that] I will boast. ||

|| ^[31] *The God and Father of the Lord Jesus knows*

who is blessed for all ages

that I am not lying. ||

| ^[32] *In Damascus the ethnarch of King Aretas was guarding the city of the Damascenes*
[in order to arrest me.] |

|| ^[33] *And through a window, in a basket*

I was let down through the wall

and so I escaped out of his hands. ||

| ^[1] *It is necessary to continue boasting.*ⁱ |

ⁱ 12:1 – I follow Guthrie in taking the present infinitive *καυχᾶσθαι* as progressive, thus “to continue boasting,” since “Paul speaks about the “boast” as an ongoing activity that is currently involved (i.e., Paul is in the middle of this “boasting” speech)” (Guthrie, *2 Corinthians*, 577; see in the same sense Lambrecht, *Second Corinthians*, 199; Martin, *2 Corinthians*, 394; Long, *II Corinthians: A Handbook on the Greek Text*, 222).

|| Οὐ συμφέρον μὲνⁱ
 ἐλεύσομαι δέⁱⁱ εἰς ὄπτασίας καὶ ἀποκαλύψεις κυρίου. ||

|| ^[2] Οἶδα ἄνθρωπον ἐν Χριστῷ πρὸ ἐτῶν δεκατεσσάρων (16)

εἴτε ἐν σώματι οὐκ οἶδα

εἴτε ἐκτὸς τοῦ σώματος οὐκ οἶδα

ὁ θεὸς οἶδεν

ἀρπαγέντα τὸν τοιοῦτον ἕως τρίτου οὐρανοῦ. (15) ||

|| ^[3] Καὶ οἶδα τὸν τοιοῦτον ἄνθρωπον (10)

εἴτε ἐν σώματι εἴτε χωρὶς τοῦ σώματος οὐκ οἶδα

ὁ θεὸς οἶδεν

^[4] ὅτι ἠρπάγη εἰς τὸν παράδεισον (11)

καὶ ἤκουσεν ἄρρητα ῥήματα (10)

ἃ οὐκ ἐξὸν ἀνθρώπῳ λαλῆσαι. (10) ||

|| ^[5] Ὑπέρ τοῦ τοιούτου καυχῶμαι (10)

ὕπερ δὲ ἐμαυτοῦ οὐ καυχῶμαι (11)

εἰ μὴ ἐν ταῖς ἀσθενείαιςⁱⁱⁱ. ||

ⁱ 12:1 – Several witnesses read συμφέροι μοι (D¹, H, K, L, Ψ, 049, 075, 104, 326, 365, 630, 1175, 1241, 1505, 1735, 1837, 1881, 2464. ℣ it vg^{ms} sy^h Ambst. Pel. al.) or simply συμφέροι (D* 81, 1245.) in place of συμφέρον μὲν (see Swanson, *New Testament Greek Manuscripts: 2 Corinthians*, 159), thus “[boasting] does not benefit me.” This alternative reading might result from an attempt to ameliorate the syntax.

ⁱⁱ 12:1 – Many of the witnesses mentioned in the preceding footnote also change the δέ into γάρ (thus D, K, L, 049, 075, 104, 365, 630, 1241, 1505, 1734, 1735, 1738, 1881. ℣ sy – see Swanson, *New Testament Greek Manuscripts: 2 Corinthians*, 159), which strengthens the boundary between v. 1b and v. 1c by breaking the μὲν ... δέ construction. Should this last reading be retained, our choice of delineation would have been different, with οὐ συμφέρον μὲν and ἐλεύσομαι γὰρ εἰς ὄπτασίας καὶ ἀποκαλύψεις κυρίου being each an autonomous colon (see T9).

ⁱⁱⁱ 12:5 – The μοῦ that is found after ἀσθενείαις in numerous and important manuscripts (℣ D² F G K L P Ψ 049, 075, 0121, 81, 104, 365, 630, 1241, 1505, 1734, 1738, 1881, 2464.; cf. also lat; Ambst – see Swanson, *New Testament Greek Manuscripts: 2 Corinthians*, 161) should arguably be explained as an addition made to avoid any ambiguity that the weaknesses are that of Paul.

|| *Although it is not helpful*

I will nonetheless come to visions and revelations granted by the Lord. ||

|| ^[2] *I know a man in Christ above fourteen years ago*

– *whether in the body I do not know*

whether outside the body I do not know

[only] God knows –

this man was caught up to the third heaven. ||

|| ^[3] *And I know this man*

– *whether in body or apart from the body I do not know*

[only] God knows –

^[4] *that [he] was caught up into paradise*

and heard inexpressible wordsⁱ

which are not permissibleⁱⁱ for a person to speak. ||

|| ^[5] *On behalf of such a person I will boast*

but on behalf of myself I will not boast

– *except in my weaknesses.* ||

ⁱ 12:4 – Note that ῥήματα might also be understood to mean “things” rather than “words” (cf. the use of ῥῆμα in 2 Cor 13:1; Mt 18:16; Lk 1:37; 2:15; 2:19; Ac 5:32; 13:42).

ⁱⁱ 12:4 – I take ἄρρητα and οὐκ ἐξόν both as referring to permissibility. However, each of these terms may also refer to possibility. For the different interpretative options for this passage, see the discussion in Grässer, *Der zweite Brief an die Korinther, vol. II*, 190–191; also see Harris, *The Second Epistle to the Corinthians*, 843–844.

|| ^[6] Ἐὰν γὰρ θελήσω καυχῆσασθαι
οὐκ ἔσομαι ἄφρων. ||

| ἀλήθειαν γὰρ ἐρῶ· |

|| Φείδομαι δέ

μὴ τις εἰς ἐμέ λογίσηται ὑπὲρ ὃ βλέπει με ἢ ἀκούει τιⁱ ἐξ ἐμοῦ

^[7] καὶ τῇ ὑπερβολῇ τῶν ἀποκαλύψεων. ||

ⁱ 12:6 – Important witnesses omit τι (thus κ* B D² F G I 6. 33. 81. 1175. 1739. *al.* [see Swanson, *New Testament Greek Manuscripts: 2 Corinthians*, 162]; cf. also in this sense, ar b; co). UBS⁵ and NA²⁸ place τι in brackets (on this choice, see Metzger, *A Textual Commentary*, 516). Commentators disagree on which reading is the more difficult: see Harris, who considers that the inclusion of τι is the more difficult reading and should thus be preferred (Harris, *The Second Epistle to the Corinthians*, 829); cf. Long, *II Corinthians: A Handbook on the Greek Text*, 227, who argues on the contrary that the shorter reading is harder. If τι is retained, then τι may be understood as an accusative of respect (“in any respect”) – see in this sense Harris, *The Second Epistle to the Corinthians*, 829, note j. For the text retained above, I follow Harris’s opinion. In any case, the choice of whether or not to retain τι changes nothing with respect to the delineation of cōla.

|| ^[6] *So if I wanted to boast*

I would not be foolish. ||

| *For I would only tell the truth.* |

|| *But I am refraining [of boasting]*

lest anyone should esteem me more beyond what he sees in me or hears from me

^[7] – *and also because of the extraordinary character of the revelations.*ⁱ ||

ⁱ 12:7 – The translation of this cōlon is difficult. In the proposed translation I consider that the *καί* + dative introduces a second reason for Paul’s refraining from boasting (*φείδομαι δέ*)—with the dative being causal and the conjunctive *καί* linking the negative reason (*μή τις εἰς ἐμὲ λογίσηται ὑπὲρ...*) and the positive one (*καὶ τῇ ὑπερβολῇ τῶν ἀποκαλύψεων*). Some commentators rather understand *καί* as exegetical (“*specifically*, because of the extraordinary nature of the revelations” or “*namely*, because of the extraordinary nature of the revelations” – so Furnish, *2 Corinthians*, 528; R.P. Martin, *2 Corinthians*, 410; Grässer, *Der zweite Brief an die Korinther*, vol. II, 177; Schmeller, *Der zweite Brief an die Korinther*, vol. II, 275), while others treat *καί* as emphatic (“*even with respect* of the extraordinary nature of the revelations” or “*indeed* on the basis of ...” – so Long, *II Corinthians: A Handbook on the Greek Text*, 227; Young and Ford, *Meaning and Truth in 2 Corinthians*, 274). It should also be noted that many commentators and translations—perhaps the majority of them—connect 7a with what follows rather than with v. 6; thus: “Because of the extraordinary nature of the revelations, so that I might not become over-elated, I was given a thorn in the flesh ...” (so Garland, *2 Corinthians*, 507; Bultmann, *Der zweite Brief an die Korinther*, 215; Barrett, *2 Corinthians*, 305; Carrez, *La deuxième épître aux Corinthiens*, 226; Harris, *The Second Epistle to the Corinthians*, 851–853; Lambrecht, *Second Corinthians*, 199; Thrall, *The Second Epistle to the Corinthians*, vol. 2, 805–806; KJV; NASB; NIV; ESV). Such an interpretation often goes with the choice to drop the *διό* at the beginning of v. 7b (on this, see below, page 214, n. i), though some commentators argue both to keep *διό* and to connect 7a with what follows (so Barrett, *2 Corinthians*, 313–314; Lambrecht, *Second Corinthians*, 202; Thrall, *The Second Epistle to the Corinthians*, vol. 2, 805–806; Harris, *The Second Epistle to the Corinthians*, 851–853; Guthrie, *2 Corinthians*, 572). With Metzger (*A Textual Commentary*, 516), Long (*II Corinthians: A Handbook on the Greek Text*, 227), Bultmann (*Der zweite Brief an die Korinther*, 226), Martin (*2 Corinthians*, 389) and others, I think that if the reading with *διό* is retained, this implies almost inevitably that 7a be read as the conclusion of v. 6.

[12:7–9]

|| Διὸ ἵνα μὴ ὑπεραίρωμαι (9)
 ἐδόθη μοι σκόλοψ τῇ σαρκί (9)
 ἄγγελος σατανᾶ ἵνα με κολαφίζῃ
ἵνα μὴ ὑπεραίρωμαιⁱ. ||

|| ^[8] Ὑπὲρ τούτου τρίς τὸν κύριον παρεκάλεσα
 ἵνα ἀποστῇ ἀπ’ ἐμοῦ. ||

|| ^[9] Καὶ εἴρηκέν μοι
 ἄρκεῖ σοι ἡ χάρις μου.
 ἡ γὰρ δύναμις ἐν ἀσθενείᾳ τελεῖται. ||

ⁱ 12:7 – The conjunction διό is missing in several important witnesses (P⁴⁶ D K L P Ψ 049. 075. 104. 326. 365. 630. 1241. 1505. 1881. 2464. ℵ – see Swanson, *New Testament Greek Manuscripts: 2 Corinthians*, 163 – see also in this sense lat. sa Ir^{lat}). I agree with most commentators that διό is to be retained on the basis of strong external support (κ A B F G 0243. 33. 81. 1175. 1739. sy^h bo al. – Swanson, *New Testament Greek Manuscripts: 2 Corinthians*, 163) and because it is more difficult reading (so Hughes, *Paul’s Second Epistle to the Corinthians*, 448, n. 138; A. Plummer, *A Critical and Exegetical Commentary on the Second Epistle of St. Paul to the Corinthians*, 347; Martin, *2 Corinthians*, 389, note h; Harris, *The Second Epistle to the Corinthians*, 829, note k; Guthrie, *2 Corinthians*, 599; Metzger, *A Textual Commentary*, 516; Long, *II Corinthians: A Handbook on the Greek Text*, 228). B. Metzger suggests that “the excision of the conjunction seems to have occurred when copyists mistakenly began a new sentence with καὶ τῇ ὑπερβολῇ, instead of taking these words with the preceding sentence.” (*A Textual Commentary*, 516). Indeed, the choice to retain or not retain διό has significant implications on how the phrase καὶ τῇ ὑπερβολῇ τῶν ἀποκαλύψεων (v. 7a) should be construed, i.e., either as the conclusion of v. 6 (as in our translation) or as the introduction for what follows. Specifically, if the reading without διό is chosen, then καὶ τῇ ὑπερβολῇ τῶν ἀποκαλύψεων should be read with what follows, thus “Because of the extraordinary nature of the revelations, so that I might not become over-elated ...”. If, however, διό is retained, then it is more likely that it introduces a new sentence, which arguably implies that καὶ τῇ ὑπερβολῇ τῶν ἀποκαλύψεων should be read with v. 6 (as in our colometric disposition above; so too Martin, *2 Corinthians*, 388; Long, *II Corinthians: A Handbook on the Greek Text*, 226; Furnish, *2 Corinthians*, 528; Grässer, *Der zweite Brief an die Korinther*, vol. II, 177; Young and Ford, *Meaning and Truth in 2 Corinthians*, 274). Note, however, that some commentators maintain διό but nevertheless construe 7a with what follows (so Guthrie, *2 Corinthians*, 572: “And due to the extraordinary character of the revelations, therefore, so that I might not become consumed with self-importance ...”; Harris, *The Second Epistle to the Corinthians*, 828: “And because of the extraordinary nature of the revelations, therefore, so that I might not become over-elated ...”; also see Barrett, *2 Corinthians*, 313–314; Lambrecht, *Second Corinthians*, 202).

ⁱⁱ 12:7 – The words ἵνα μὴ ὑπεραίρωμαι are missing in several important witnesses (κ* A D F G 33. 629*. al. – see Swanson, *New Testament Greek Manuscripts: 2 Corinthians*, 163– cf. also in this sense, lat. Ir^{lat}), possibly because they were considered superfluous given that they already appear in v. 12:7b.

[12:7–9]

|| *For this reason, so that I might not become over-elated
there was given me a thorn in the flesh
a messenger of Satan to beat me
so that I might not become over-elated.* ||

|| ^[8] *About this three times I implored the Lord
that it should leave me.* ||

|| ^[9] *And he has said to me:
“My grace is sufficient for you.
For this is in weakness that [my] power reaches perfection.”* ||

[12:9–11]

|| Ἡδιστα οὖν μᾶλλον καυχῆσομαι ἐν ταῖς ἀσθενείαις μου (17)
ἵνα ἐπισκηνώσῃ ἐπ’ ἐμὲ ἡ δύναμις τοῦ Χριστοῦ. (17) ||

|| ^[10] Διὸ εὐδοκῶ ἐν ἀσθενείαις (9)

ἐν ὑβρεσιν (4)

ἐν ἀνάγκαιςⁱ (4)

ἐν διωγμοῖς καὶⁱⁱ στενοχωρίαις (9)

ὑπὲρ Χριστοῦ. (4) ||

|| Ὅταν γὰρ ἀσθενῶ (6)

τότε δυνατός εἰμι. (7) ||

| ^[11] γέγονα ἄφρων· |

| ὑμεῖς με ἠναγκάσατε ! |

| ἐγὼ γὰρ ὄφειλον ὑφ’ ὑμῶν συνίστασθαι· |

|| Οὐδὲν γὰρⁱⁱⁱ ὑστέρησα τῶν ὑπερλίαν ἀποστόλων
εἰ καὶ οὐδὲν εἰμι. ||

ⁱ 12:10 – Before ἐν ἀνάγκαις, P⁴⁶ and κ* have καί, which is arguably a stylistic improvement to permit two pairs of nouns to be linked by καί (ἐν ὑβρεσιν καὶ ἐν ἀνάγκαις / ἐν διωγμοῖς καὶ στενοχωρίαις). From a colometric point of view, adopting this alternative reading would change the delineation, with ἐν ὑβρεσιν καὶ ἐν ἀνάγκαις becoming a single colon.

ⁱⁱ 12:10 – Before στενοχωρίαις, numerous witnesses read καὶ instead of ἐν (κ² A D F G K L P Ψ 33. 81. 365. 1241. 1505. 2464 ℳ latt sy; Tert). Above I retain the reading with καὶ not only because it has strong attestation in the earliest manuscripts (P⁴⁶ κ* B 104. 326. 1175) but also because it is the most difficult reading, as ἐν aligns with the three preceding ἐν in v. 10.

ⁱⁱⁱ 12:11 – After γὰρ, two major witnesses (P⁴⁶ and B*) add τί (see Swanson, *New Testament Greek Manuscripts: 2 Corinthians*, 166), which strengthens the οὐδέν, thus “in no way,” “not at all.” The omission of τί has stronger support. Uncertainty remains, however, as we may also assume that τί was dropped by later scribes because it seemed redundant after οὐδέν.

[12:9–11]

*|| So most gladly I will boast in my weaknesses
so that would reside in me the power of Christ. ||*

*||^[10] Therefore I am pleased with weaknesses
with insults
with afflictions
with persecutions and difficulties
for Christ's sake. ||*

*|| For whenever I am weak
them I am powerful. ||*

|^[11] I have been a fool. |

| You forced me! |

| For it is I who ought to have been commended by you. |

*|| Indeed, in nothing am I inferior to those super-apostles
even if I am nothing. ||*

[12:12–15]

|| ^[12] Τὰ μὲν σημεῖα τοῦ ἀποστόλου κατεργάσθη ἐν ὑμῖν (17)
ἐν πάσῃ ὑπομονῇ σημείοις τε¹ καὶ τέρασιν καὶ δυνάμεσιν. (20) ||

|| ^[13] Τί γὰρ ἐστὶν ὃ ἠσώθητε ὑπὲρ τὰς λοιπὰς ἐκκλησίας (18)
εἰ μὴ ὅτι αὐτὸς ἐγὼ οὐ κατενάρκησα ὑμῶν ; (16) ||

| χάρισασθέ μοι τὴν ἀδικίαν ταύτην· |

| ^[14] Ἴδού ! |

| Τρίτον τοῦτο ἐτοίμως ἔχω ἐλθεῖν πρὸς ὑμᾶς. |

| Καὶ οὐ καταναρκήσω. |

|| Οὐ γὰρ ζητῶ τὰ ὑμῶν
ἀλλ' ὑμᾶς. ||

|| Οὐ γὰρ ὀφείλει τὰ τέκνα τοῖς γονεῦσιν θησαυρίζειν
ἀλλ' οἱ γονεῖς τοῖς τέκνοις. ||

| ^[15] Ἐγὼ δὲ ἤδιστα δαπανήσω καὶ ἐκδαπανηθήσομαι ὑπὲρ τῶν ψυχῶν ὑμῶν. |

¹ 12:12 – Many witnesses omit the particle τε (A D κ¹² K L P Ψ F G 049. 075. 104. 365. 1241. 1505. 1734. 1738. ℳ [see Swanson, *New Testament Greek Manuscripts: 2 Corinthians*, 167]; cf. also, lat Ambst Pel), possibly because it was seen as superfluous in view of the καί ... καί construction. At least, in light of the syntax of the sentence, it is easier to imagine that τε was dropped rather than added. Note that among the mentioned manuscripts, many also add ἐν before σημείοις (including notably κ² D² K L P Ψ 049. 075. 104. 365. 1241. 1505. 1734. 1738. ℳ), which arguably arose from a desire to clarify the relation between σημείοις καὶ τέρασιν καὶ δυνάμεσιν and σημεῖα τοῦ ἀποστόλου in v. 12a (“the signs of an apostle were produced ... *through* signs and marvels and powerful deeds”).

[12:12–15]

|| ^[12] *The signs of an apostle were produced among you
by means of every kind of endurance, [through] signs and marvels and mighty deeds.* ||

|| ^[13] *In what respect were you put lower than the other churches
except that I myself did not burden you?* ||

| *Forgive me this injury!* |

| ^[14] *Look!* |

| *I am ready to visit you for the third time.* |

| *And I will not be a burden.* |

|| *For I do not seek your possessions
but you [yourselves].* ||

|| *For children ought not to store up for their parents
but parents for their children.* ||

| ^[15] *So for my part I will gladly spend and be completely spent for your souls.* |

|| Εἰ περισσοτέρως ὑμᾶς ἀγαπῶνⁱⁱ

ἤσσον ἀγαπῶμαι ; ||

| ^[16]Ἔστω δέ. |

|| Ἐγὼ οὐ κατεβάρησα ὑμᾶςⁱⁱⁱ

ἀλλ' ὑπάρχων πανοῦργος δόλω ὑμᾶς ἔλαβον ; ||

|| ^[17] Μὴ τινα ὧν ἀπέσταλκα πρὸς ὑμᾶς (II)

δι' αὐτοῦ ἐπλεονέκτησα ὑμᾶς ; (II) ||

| ^[18] Παρεκάλεσα Τίτον καὶ συναπέστειλα τὸν ἀδελφόν. |

| Μήτι ἐπλεονέκτησεν ὑμᾶς Τίτος ; |

| Οὐ τῷ αὐτῷ πνεύματι περιπατήσαμεν ; |

ⁱ 12:15 – The conjunction εἰ is followed by an added καί in many witnesses (κ² D^{1,2} K L P Ψ 049. 075. 0243. 81^c. 104. 326. 365. 440. 630. 1175. 1241. 1505. 1738. 1739. 1881. 2464. ℣ [see Swanson, *New Testament Greek Manuscripts: 2 Corinthians*, 170]; cf. also f [78] vg; sy). Should this longer reading be retained, it would change the choice of delineation, as it would mean that v. 15b-c forms a period with 15a, with 15b-c being concessive: “So for my part I will gladly spend and be completely spent for your souls / *even if* the more I love you ...” Also note that D* has neither εἰ nor εἰ καί (cf. also in this sense, ar g r ; Ambst). Above, I retain the reading εἰ (without καί) because this has the strongest support in the earliest manuscripts, including both proto-alexandrian (P⁴⁶ κ* B), later Alexandrian (A 33. 81*), and Western witnesses (F G).

ⁱⁱ 12:15 – Several witnesses read the indicative ἀγαπῶ instead of the participle ἀγαπῶν (thus κ* A 33. 104*. 330. 1241. 1505. *al.* [see Swanson, *New Testament Greek Manuscripts: 2 Corinthians*, 170]). Each variant may be explained as arising from either adding or dropping ν before η. For this reason, NA²⁸ and UBS⁵ place the ν in brackets (Metzger, *A Textual Commentary*, 517). Above, I retain the participial form merely because this has the strongest support (P⁴⁶ κ² B D F G K L P Ψ 049. 0243. 104^c. 1738. 1739. 1881. ℣ [see Swanson, *New Testament Greek Manuscripts: 2 Corinthians*, 170] and the entire Latin tradition). We may also argue that ἀγαπῶν is the most difficult reading, as it necessitates the reader to take εἰ as interrogative or alternatively to supply εἰμί (see in this sense Harris, *The Second Epistle to the Corinthians*, 881, note d; cf. Thrall, *The Second Epistle to the Corinthians*, vol. 2, 848–49; cf. Metzger, *A Textual Commentary*, 517). As regards colometry, the choice between the two variants does not change anything.

ⁱⁱⁱ 12:16 – In place of οὐ κατεβάρησα (attested in A B D² K L P Ψ 0243. 33. 365. 630. 1175. 1241. 1505. 1739. 2464^c (- ου 2464*) ℣), two witnesses have the easier form οὐκ ἐβάρησα (℞⁴⁶ D*), while others have the verb καταναρκάω (οὐ κατενάρκησα ὑμῶν ℞ F G 81. 326. 629. [οὐ κατενάρκησα ὑμᾶς 104. 1881.]). The last reading probably arose under the influence of the the formulation in 11:13. As to the reading οὐκ ἐβάρησα, we may assume that it arose as a simplification and possibly as a harmonisation with 2 Co 1:8 and 5:4.

[12:15–18]

|| *If I love you the more
am I loved the less?* ||

| ^[16] *So be it!* |

|| *[So you think] I was not a burden on you
but crafty as I am I took you in by a trick?!* ||

|| ^[17] *Not with anyone of those whom I have sent to you
through him I did not exploit you, did I?*ⁱ ||

| ^[18] *I urged Titus and sent along with him the brother.* |

| *Titus did not exploit you, did he?* |

| *Did we not walk in the same spirit?* |

ⁱ 12:17 – The μή at the beginning of v. 17 introduces a question expecting a negative answer. My proposed translation reproduces that by Long (*II Corinthians: A Handbook on the Greek Text*, 234).

| Οὐ τοῖς αὐτοῖς ἴχνεσιν ; |

|| ^[19] Πάλαιⁱ δοκεῖτε ὅτι ὑμῖν ἀπολογούμεθα ; ||

| Κατέναντι θεοῦ ἐν Χριστῷ λαλοῦμεν. |

|| Τὰ δὲ πάντα ἀγαπητοὶ ὑπὲρ τῆς ὑμῶν οἰκοδομῆς. ||

|| ^[20] Φοβοῦμαι γὰρ μή πως ἐλθὼν οὐχ οἴους θέλω εὔρω ὑμᾶς κἀγὼ εὐρεθῶ ὑμῖν
[οἶον οὐ θέλετε (30)
μή πως ἔρις ζήλος θυμοὶ ἐριθείαι καταλαλαίαι ψιθυρισμοὶ φυσιώσεις
[ἀκαταστασίαι. (31) ||

|| ^[21] Μὴ πάλιν ἐλθόντος μουⁱⁱ ταπεινώσῃⁱⁱⁱ με ὁ θεός μου πρὸς ὑμᾶς (19)
καὶ πενήθῃσω πολλοὺς τῶν προσημαρτηκότων καὶ μὴ μετανοησάντων (21)
ἐπὶ τῇ ἀκαθαρσίᾳ καὶ πορνείᾳ καὶ ἀσελγείᾳ ἣ ἔπραξαν ! (21) ||

ⁱ 12:19 – In place of πάλαι (“for a long time,” “all this time”), several witnesses read πάλιν, “again” (thus κ² D K L P Ψ 049. 075. 0278. 104. 630. 1241. 1505. 1735. 2464. ℣ [see Swanson, *New Testament Greek Manuscripts: 2 Corinthians*, 172]; cf. also in this sense g vg^{mss} syr bo). This alternative reading is easier, as πάλιν is a very common adverb in Paul, in contrast with πάλαι, which is found only here (see Harris, *2 Corinthians*, 893, n. a). For this reason, and also in view of its superior attestation (P⁴⁶ κ* A B F G 0243. 6. 33. 81. 330. 365. 1175. 1739. 1881. lat al – see Swanson, *New Testament Greek Manuscripts: 2 Corinthians*, 172), πάλαι is certainly preferable. Note that P⁴⁶ adds the negation οὐ before πάλαι, which transforms v. 19a into a question that expects an affirmative answer.

ⁱⁱ 12:21 – In place of ἐλθόντος μου, many witnesses read ἐλθόντα με (κ² D K Ψ L 049. 075. 0243. 0278. 33. 104. 424. 945. 1175. 1734. 1735. 1738. 1739. sy^p al. – see Swanson, *New Testament Greek Manuscripts: 2 Corinthians*, 175). As Harris suggests, this is certainly a syntactic improvement due to the rule that in genitive constructions the noun or pronoun is normally unrelated to the other parts of the sentence: here, μου is then picked up by με (ταπεινώσῃ με), which “breaks” this rule (Harris, *The Second Epistle to the Corinthians*, 894, note f).

ⁱⁱⁱ 12:21 – In place of the aorist subjunctive ταπεινώσῃ, numerous witnesses have the future indicative ταπεινώσει (thus P⁴⁶ B D F G L P 0278. 6. 33. 81. 104. 326. 365. 630. 1175. 1505. 2464. al. – see Swanson, *New Testament Greek Manuscripts: 2 Corinthians*, 175). From a grammatical point of view, the subjunctive agrees better with the μή at the beginning of v. 21, as the future ταπεινώσει would instead require the negation οὐ. The reading ταπεινώσει might result from a desire to stress the idea that the situation foreseen is in the future (i.e., it concerns the time where Paul will return to Corinth); or this reading might simply be the result of an orthographical error, as η and ει arguably sounded identical (see Horrocks, *Greek: A History of the Language and its Speakers*, 167–168.).

| *Were our footsteps not the same?* |

|| ^[19] *Have you been thinking all this time that we are defending ourselves before you?* ||

| *This is before God, in Christ, that we are speaking.* |

|| *All things, beloved, are for your edification.* ||

|| ^[20] *For I fear that, when I come, I may perhaps find you not how I wish and I may be found
[by you not how you wish
that there might perhaps be strife, jealousy, displays of anger, selfish ambitions, slanders,
[gossips, conceits, disorders. ||*

|| ^[21] *Let not God,ⁱⁱ when I come back, humble me before you
and let me not mourn over many who have sinned previously and did not repent
because of the impurity and sexual immorality and licentiousness that they practiced!* ||

ⁱ 12:19 – This saying can be read as either a statement (“All this time you have been thinking that ...”) or a question (“Have you been thinking all this time that ...?”). In my translation, I follow most commentators by treating it as a question, despite the absence of any interrogative particle (so Harris, *The Second Epistle to the Corinthians*, 894; Plummer, *A Critical and Exegetical Commentary on the Second Epistle of St. Paul to the Corinthians*, 367; Martin, *2 Corinthians*, 450; Lambrecht, *Second Corinthians*, 214; Thrall, *The Second Epistle to the Corinthians*, vol. 2, 859; Guthrie, *2 Corinthians*, 609). In contrast, Barrett, *2 Corinthians*, 327–328, argues that 19a is better read as a statement; also see Bultmann, *Der zweite Brief an die Korinther*, 238; Grässer, *Der zweite Brief an die Korinther*, vol. II, 234; Long, *II Corinthians: A Handbook on the Greek Text*, 234–235.

ⁱⁱ 12:21 – Here I understand the construction μή + aorist subjunctive to introduce a negative exhortation (hortatory subjunctive or prohibitive subjunctive – see e.g. H. W. Smyth, *A Greek Grammar for Colleges* §1798, §1800, §1840). See a close construction with God as the subject (but with an imperative, not a subjunctive) in Ex. 20:19. Another possibility would be to include φοβοῦμαι from v. 20, thus “I fear that, when I come back, God will humble me ...” Note that my proposed construction goes against the majority—indeed perhaps all—of translations and commentators, who instead take 12:20–21 as a single sentence, with φοβοῦμαι introducing three different concerns (so e.g. Harris, *The Second Epistle to the Corinthians*, 900–901; Long, *II Corinthians: A Handbook on the Greek Text*, 243; Guthrie, *2 Corinthians*, 622–623; Barrett, *2 Corinthians*, 326; Plummer, *A Critical and Exegetical Commentary on the Second Epistle of St. Paul to the Corinthians*, 366; Martin, *2 Corinthians*, 451; Grässer, *Der zweite Brief an die Korinther*, vol. II, 234; Lambrecht, *Second Corinthians*, 211; Bultmann, *Der zweite Brief an die Korinther*, 238; NRSV; KJV; NIV; ASV; ESV). On this issue, see the discussion in Chapter 5, section 3.6.

| ^[13:1] Τρίτον τοῦτο ἔρχομαι πρὸς ὑμᾶς. |

|| Ἐπὶ στόματος δύο μαρτύρων καὶ τριῶν σταθήσεται πᾶν ῥῆμα. ||

|| ^[2] **Προείρηκα καὶ** προλέγω

ὡς παρῶν τὸ δεύτερον καὶ ἀπῶν νῦν (11) ⁱ

τοῖς προημαρτηκόσιν καὶ τοῖς λοιποῖς πᾶσιν (13)

ὅτι ἐὰν ἔλθω εἰς τὸ πάλιν οὐ φείσομαι! (14) ||

|| ^[3] Ἐπεὶ δοκιμὴν ζητεῖτε τοῦ ἐν ἐμοὶ λαλοῦντος Χριστοῦ. ||

|| Ὅς εἰς ὑμᾶς οὐκ ἀσθενεῖ (8)

ἀλλὰ δυνατεῖ ἐν ὑμῖν. (8) ||

|| ^[4] **Καὶ γὰρ** ἐσταυρώθηⁱⁱ ἐξ ἀσθενείας (11)

ἀλλὰ ζῆ ἐκ δυνάμεως θεοῦ. (10) ||

ⁱ 13:2 – Many witnesses add γράφω after νῦν (thus D² K L P Ψ 049. 075. 104. 326. 365. 1505. 1734. 1735. 2464. ℵ [see Swanson, *New Testament Greek Manuscripts: 2 Corinthians*, 176]; cf. also the Syriac and Coptic traditions [both bo and sa]). The shorter reading is certainly preferable in view of the stronger support it has in the manuscript tradition, especially in the oldest witnesses (P⁴⁶ 8 A B D^{*c} F G I 0243. 6. 33. 81. 630. 1175. 1739. 1881. 2464. [see Swanson, *New Testament Greek Manuscripts: 2 Corinthians*, 176] ; cf. also the Vulgate manuscripts and part of the Old Latin witnesses). The addition of γράφω might come from a desire to emphasise the role of the epistolary media in Paul's mission or it may be linked to stylistic improvement, as the presence of γράφω makes the first two cōla rhyme (... προλέγω / ... γράφω).

ⁱⁱ 13:4 – Several witnesses read εἰ before ἐσταυρώθη (8² A D¹ L Ψ 630. 1175. 1505. 1881. 2464. ℵ; cf. also lat sy Amb), but the reading without εἰ should certainly be preferred based on its superior support in the manuscript tradition (including P^{46vid} 8* B D* F G K P 0243. 33. 81. 104. 365. 1241. 1734. 1739. al. [see Swanson, *New Testament Greek Manuscripts: 2 Corinthians*, 178]; cf also co Eus). The insertion of εἰ strengthens the contrast between v. 4a and 4b while at the same time, by concessive force, it also subordinates the idea of Christ's weakness to that of God's power: "For even if he [Christ] was crucified because of his weakness / he lives because of God's power."

[13:1-4]

| ^[13:1] *This is the third time I am coming to you.* |

| *“Upon the mouth of two and three witnesses shall every matter be established.”*ⁱ |

|| ^[2] *I have warned and I warn again
as while present the second time and absent now
to those who have sinned before and all the others
that if I come again I will not spare!* ||

|| ^[3] *For you seek proof of Christ speaking in me.* ||

|| *He who in dealing with you is not weak
but is powerful among you.* ||

|| ^[4] *For indeed he was crucified from weakness
but he lives from*ⁱⁱ *God’s power.* ||

ⁱ 13:1 – This is an allusion to Dt. 19:15, hence the quotation marks added in the translation.

ⁱⁱ 13:4 – Here the preposition ἐκ (which is repeated three times in v. 4) introduces a cause (first of the crucifixion, then of the living), and might also be rendered by “through,” “due to,” “because of,” or “as a result of.”

|| Καὶ γὰρ ἡμεῖς ἀσθενοῦμεν ἐν αὐτῷⁱ
ἀλλὰ ζήσομεν σὺν αὐτῷ ἐκ δυνάμεως θεοῦ εἰς ὑμᾶςⁱⁱ. ||

| ^[5] Ἐαυτοὺς πειράζετε εἰ ἐστὲ ἐν τῇ πίστει. |

| Ἐαυτοὺς δοκιμάζετε. |

| Ἡ οὐκ ἐπιγινώσκετε ἑαυτοὺς ὅτι Χριστὸς Ἰησοῦςⁱⁱⁱ ἐν ὑμῖν^{iv}; |

| Εἰ μήτι ἀδόκιμοί ἐστε. |

| ^[6] Ἐλπίζω δὲ ὅτι γνώσεσθε ὅτι ἡμεῖς οὐκ ἐσμὲν ἀδόκιμοι. |

|| ^[7] Εὐχόμεθα δὲ πρὸς τὸν θεὸν μὴ ποιῆσαι ὑμᾶς κακὸν μηδέ^v

οὐχ ἴνα ἡμεῖς δόκιμοι φανῶμεν (II)

ἀλλ' ἴνα ὑμεῖς τὸ καλὸν ποιῆτε (II)

ἡμεῖς δὲ ὡς ἀδόκιμοι ὦμεν. (IO) ||

ⁱ 13:4 – In place of ἐν αὐτῷ, some witnesses have σὺν αὐτῷ, “with him” (κ A F G [see Swanson, *New Testament Greek Manuscripts: 2 Corinthians*, 179]; cf. also r sy^p bo), probably under the influence of the σὺν αὐτῷ in the following clause. Note that in other manuscripts the same phenomenon occurred in the opposite direction, with σὺν αὐτῷ in v. 4d being replaced by ἐν αὐτῷ (thus P⁴⁶ D* 33. 326. 1646. – see Swanson, 179).

ⁱⁱ 13:4 – εἰς ὑμᾶς is missing in B and D² (see Swanson, *New Testament Greek Manuscripts: 2 Corinthians*, 179) as well as in the Old Latin witness r. Metzger suggests that this phrase was omitted as an “awkward addendum,” since it is unclear whether it should be taken with ζήσομεν or with δυνάμεως θεοῦ (Metzger, 519).

ⁱⁱⁱ 13:5 – There is uncertainty concerning the order of the words Χριστὸς and Ἰησοῦς. The order Χριστὸς Ἰησοῦς was preferred above because (1) it has strong support (κ A F G P 0243. 81. 326. 629. 630. 1175. 1241. 1739. 1881. 2464 b vg; Cl Ambst) and (2) it represents the more difficult reading, as Paul more commonly uses Ἰησοῦς Χριστὸς. Note that NA²⁸ and UBS⁵ retain Ἰησοῦς Χριστὸς, as attested in B D K L Ψ 33. 104. 365. 1505 ℣ ar vg^{ms} sy.

^{iv} 13:5 – Important witnesses supply ἐστίν after ἐν ὑμῖν (κ A D^{1,2} F G K L P Ψ 0243. 81. 104. 365. 630. 1175. 1241. 1505. 1734. 1739. 1881. 2464. ℣ [see Swanson, *New Testament Greek Manuscripts: 2 Corinthians*, 180]). This longer reading may have arisen as a desire to improve the style. The addition of ἐστίν at the end indeed closes the question of 5c with the verb. With regard to colometry, this addition would arguably give 5c the status of a monoclon period (on the difference between an autonomous colon and a monoclon period, see the discussion above: Chapter 3, section 3.1; also see Dem., *Eloc.* 17).

[13:4-7]

|| *For we also are weak in him
but we will live with him, from God's power, in [our] dealing with you.* ||

| ^[5] *Examine yourselves whether you are in the faith.* |

| *Test yourselves.* |

| *Or do you not recognise yourselves that Jesus Christ is in you?!* |

| *Unless indeed you failed the test.ⁱ* |

| ^[6] *And I hope you will recognise that we also did not fail the test.* |

|| ^[7] *Now we pray to God that you would do nothing evil
not so that we would appear as having passed the testⁱⁱ
but so that you would do what is right
even if we may seem to have failed the test.* ||

ⁱ 13:5 – Literally, “unless indeed you are *unapproved*” or “unless indeed you are *reprobate*” (see LSJ) on the various possible meanings of ἀδόκιμοι when referring to persons). The translation “fail the test” is an attempt at wordplay with δοκιμάζετε (“test”) in 13:5.

ⁱⁱ 13:7 – Literally, “not so that we may appear as *approved*” (cf. endnote lxxxiii).

|| ^[8] Οὐ γὰρ δυνάμεθά τι κατὰ τῆς ἀληθείας

ἀλλ' ὑπὲρ τῆς ἀληθείας ||

|| ^[9] Χαίρομεν γὰρ ὅταν ἡμεῖς ἀσθενῶμεν

ὑμεῖς δὲ δυνατοὶ ᾗτε. ||

|| Τοῦτο καὶ εὐχόμεθα (7)

τὴν ὑμῶν κατάρτισιν. (7) ||

|| ^[10] Διὰ τοῦτο ταῦτα ἀπὼν γράφω (10)

ἵνα παρῶν μὴ ἀποτόμως χρήσωμαι (12)

κατὰ τὴν ἐξουσίαν ἣν ὁ κύριος ἔδωκέν μοι (10)

εἰς οἰκοδομὴν καὶ οὐκ εἰς καθαίρεσιν. (12) ||

| ^[11] Λοιπὸν ἀδελφοί χαίρετε! |

| Καταρτίζεσθε! (5) |

| Παρακαλεῖσθε! (5) |

| Τὸ αὐτὸ φρονεῖτε! (6) |

| Εἰρηνεύετε! (5) |

| Καὶ ὁ θεὸς τῆς ἀγάπης καὶ εἰρήνης ἔσται μεθ' ὑμῶν. |

[13:8–11]

|| ^[8] *For we are not able [to do] anything against the truth
but [only] for the truth.* ||

|| ^[9] *For we rejoice when we are weak
but you are strong.* ||

| *This also we pray for
[namely] your restoration.* |

|| ^[10] *This is whyⁱ I am writing these things when absent
in order that when present I would not act severely
in accordance with the authority that the Lord gave me
[which is] for edification and not for destruction.* ||

| ^[11] *Finally, brothers, rejoice!* |

| *Be restored.* |

| *Be encouraged.* |ⁱⁱ

| *Have a common mind!* |

| *Be at peace!* |

| *And the God of love and peace shall be with you.* |

ⁱ 13:10 – In my translation I take διὰ τοῦτο as looking back on v. 9 (so Long, *II Corinthians: A Handbook on the Greek Text*, 255; cf. Martin, *2 Corinthians*, 451; cf. Carrez, *La deuxième épître aux Corinthiens*, 240; cf. Grässer, *Der zweite Brief an die Korinther*, vol. II, 256). Others understand διὰ τοῦτο as prospective and anticipating the ἵνα clause that follows: “The reason why, in my absence from you, I am writing these things, is that I may not, when present, exercise severity ...” (so Barrett, *2 Corinthians*, 340; cf. Harris, *The Second Epistle to the Corinthians*, 928–929; cf. Lambrecht, *Second Corinthians*, 222; cf. Bultmann, *Der zweite Brief an die Korinther*, 249).

ⁱⁱ 13:11 – I take καταρτίζεσθε and παρακαλεῖσθε as passives, but they might also be understood as middles, thus “work at your restoration” and “exhort one another.” On this issue, see the discussion in Harris, *The Second Epistle to the Corinthians*, 933.

| ^[12] Ἀσπάσασθε ἀλλήλους ἐν ἀγίῳ φιλήματι. |

| Ἀσπάζονται ὑμᾶς οἱ ἅγιοι πάντες. |

|| ^[13] Ἡ χάρις τοῦ κυρίου Ἰησοῦ Χριστοῦ (11)

καὶ ἡ ἀγάπη τοῦ θεοῦ

καὶ ἡ κοινωνία τοῦ ἁγίου πνεύματος (13)

μετὰ πάντων ὑμῶν.ⁱ ||

ⁱ 13:13 – Several witnesses add a conclusive ἀμήν after ὑμῶν (thus κ² D K L P Ψ 049. 075. 104. 326. 365. 1505. 1734. 2464. ℣ [see Swanson, *New Testament Greek Manuscripts: 2 Corinthians*, 185]; cf. also lat, sy, and bo). In addition, numerous manuscripts have a subscription indicating that the letter is addressed to the Corinthian community (see Swanson, *New Testament Greek Manuscripts: 2 Corinthians*, 186).

[13:12–13]

| ^[12] *Greet one another with a holy kiss.* |

| *All the saints greet you.* |

|| ^[13] *The grace of the Lord Jesus Christ
and the love of God
and the fellowship of the Holy Spirit
be with you all.* ||

2.3. Comments on the choices of delineation

Below are a few comments on passages that require justification or explanation of the delineation choice. The list provided is not meant to be exhaustive of all the difficulties encountered while analysing 2 Cor 10–13 in terms of cōla and periods.

10:4–5

Λογισμούς καθαιρούντες / καὶ πᾶν ὕψωμα ἐπαιρόμενον κατὰ τῆς γνώσεως τοῦ θεοῦ (?) καὶ αἰχμαλωτίζοντες πᾶν νόημα εἰς τὴν ὑπακοὴν τοῦ Χριστοῦ. Here the choice of delineation is very uncertain. The difficulty is to determine whether the last clause (καὶ αἰχμαλωτίζοντες πᾶν νόημα εἰς τὴν ὑπακοὴν τοῦ Χριστοῦ) should be attached to the preceding clause within a period, or instead represents an autonomous cōlon. In the proposed delineation above, I followed the second option, by relying on T8 (i.e., the strong tendency for periodic cōla to be closely intertwined at the syntactical level). Alternatively, if more weight was given to the linking role of paromoiosis and parisosis (see T13), the passage καὶ αἰχμαλωτίζοντες πᾶν νόημα εἰς τὴν ὑπακοὴν τοῦ Χριστοῦ could be attached to what precedes it. This is based on the similar length between “πᾶν ὕψωμα ἐπαιρόμενον κατὰ τῆς γνώσεως τοῦ θεοῦ” and “καὶ αἰχμαλωτίζοντες πᾶν νόημα εἰς τὴν ὑπακοὴν τοῦ Χριστοῦ” (19 and 20 syllables) and the assonance between τοῦ θεοῦ and τοῦ Χριστοῦ. This analysis would also represent a defensible choice of segmentation (a tricōloi period of a standard length [46 syllables, see T5], with parisosis and paromoiosis between the second and the third cōlon).

10:8–9

... / οὐκ αἰσχυνθήσομαι (?) ἵνα μὴ δόξω ὡς ἂν ἐκφοβεῖν ὑμᾶς διὰ τῶν ἐπιστολῶν. This saying could also be separated into two cōla (with a division between αἰσχυνθήσομαι and ἵνα), each corresponding to a single clause (see T3). The choice to group the ἵνα clause with οὐκ αἰσχυνθήσομαι relies mainly on considerations regarding the balance between the cōla, as grouping these two clauses enables the third cōlon to have almost the same length as the two preceding ones (23, 21, and 24 syllables respectively [see T 11]). However, we may imagine a slight break before the ἵνα clause, which may be signalled by a comma.¹⁰³

¹⁰³ Note that the status of 10:9 is a much debated issue: see the detailed discussion in Chapter 5, section 3.2.

10:10

Ὅτι αἱ ἐπιστολαὶ μὲν φησὶν βαρεῖαι καὶ ἰσχυραὶ / ἢ δὲ παρουσία τοῦ σώματος ἀσθενῆς (?) καὶ ὁ λόγος ἐξουθενημένος. Here, T₃ suggests that the second and third clauses each correspond to a cōlon. However, L₇ forces us to group the two clauses together, as they form the second term of an antithesis.¹⁰⁴

10:14

Οὐ γὰρ ὡς μὴ ἐφικνούμενοι εἰς ὑμᾶς ὑπερεκτείνομεν ἑαυτούς. Ἄχρι γὰρ καὶ ὑμῶν ἐφθάσαμεν ἐν τῷ εὐαγγελίῳ τοῦ Χριστοῦ. Here, the presence of a final paromoiosis (... ἐαυτούς / ... Χριστοῦ) combined with a parisosis (21 and 20 syllables) might suggest that the two cōla should be read together as a period (see T₁₃), even though they are both syntactically independent. However, the presence of γὰρ at the beginning of 14b rather suggests that Ἄχρι γὰρ καὶ ὑμῶν ἐφθάσαμεν ἐν τῷ εὐαγγελίῳ τοῦ Χριστοῦ consists of an autonomous cōlon (see T₉).

11:4

Εἰ μὲν γὰρ ὁ ἐρχόμενος ἄλλον Ἰησοῦν κηρύσσει (?) ὃν οὐκ ἐκηρύξαμεν / ἢ πνεῦμα ἕτερον λαμβάνετε (?) ὃ οὐκ ἐλάβετε / ἢ εὐαγγέλιον ἕτερον (?) ὃ οὐκ ἐδέξασθε / καλῶς ἀνέχεσθε. The three relative clauses may be separate cōla, and thus place additional breaks may be placed before ὃν οὐκ ἐκηρύξαμεν, before ὃ οὐκ ἐλάβετε, and before ὃ οὐκ ἐδέξασθε. On one hand, this would comply with the observed tendency for cōla to encompass a clause (see T₃). It would also present the advantage of producing a more balanced period with respect to the length of cōla (see T₂). On the other hand, this alternative delineation would result in a seven-cōla period, which is above the standard limit of four cōla (see T₄). It would also produce two supplementary short cōla that are under the standard limit of seven syllables (ὃ οὐκ ἐλάβετε and ὃ οὐκ ἐδέξασθε—see T₁). Considering the different criteria as a whole, both delineation choices seem equally possible.

11:9

Καὶ ἐν παντὶ ἀβαρῆ ἑμαυτὸν ὑμῖν ἐτήρησα (?) καὶ τηρήσω. Alternatively, this saying might represent a monocōlon period (Καὶ ἐν παντὶ ἀβαρῆ ἑμαυτὸν ὑμῖν ἐτήρησα [see L₅])

¹⁰⁴ This revises my previous suggestion that ἢ δὲ παρουσία τοῦ σώματος ἀσθενῆς and καὶ ὁ λόγος ἐξουθενημένος represent two distinct cōla (P. Marschall, “Punctuating Paul’s Letters in Light of the Ancient Theory of Cōla and Periods,” 118–119).

followed by an autonomous comma (καὶ τηρήσω). In fact, καὶ τηρήσω meets the minimal criterion for standing as an autonomous comma (see L4). In the proposed disposition, however, I consider that the two clauses are part of the same thought that Paul does not want to burden the Corinthians: the first clause expresses this point with respect to the past, while the second clause expresses this same point with respect to the future.¹⁰⁵ In support of this interpretation, we may also argue that ἀβαρῆ ἑμαυτὸν ὑμῖν is necessary to supply from the first clause (“and I will keep *myself unburdensome to you*”), such that καὶ τηρήσω is intrinsically linked in some way to what precedes it.

II:13

Οἱ γὰρ τοιοῦτοι ψευδαπόστολοι / ἐργάται δόλιοι (/) μετασχηματιζόμενοι εἰς ἀποστόλους Χριστοῦ.

In this passage, the choice of delineation is debatable. Alternatively to the proposition retained above (only one break, between ψευδαπόστολοι and ἐργάται δόλιοι), ἐργάται δόλιοι could be analysed as a colon on its own. The choice of delineation is directly correlated with how the status of the participle μετασχηματιζόμενοι is understood.¹⁰⁶ If the participle μετασχηματιζόμενοι is taken as a substantival participle that offers a third description of the ψευδαπόστολοι, then a division must be placed between δόλιοι and μετασχηματιζόμενοι.¹⁰⁷ If, by contrast, μετασχηματιζόμενοι is taken as an attributive modifier of ἐργάται δόλιοι (“deceitful workers who ...”), then no break is required. There is no strong argument for either of these options from a colometric point of view. Perhaps we could advance that the delineation proposed above is slightly preferable in that it avoids having an unusual short cōlon of 6 syllables (ἐργάται δόλιοι – see T1). However, alone this argument is rather weak.

II:16

Πάλιν λέγω (?) μή τις με δόξη ἄφρονα εἶναι. From a strict syntactic point of view, each of these cōla could stand autonomously (“I say it again. Let no one think me a fool!”). The reason for grouping them within a period is that μή τις με δόξη ἄφρονα εἶναι arguably expresses the content of what Paul is “saying again” (πάλιν λέγω). Thus, the second cōlon is necessary to make the thought intelligible. Considering both the syntax but and the meaning

¹⁰⁵ See the discussion in Dem., *Eloc.* 2–3.

¹⁰⁶ On the different possible roles for μετασχηματιζόμενοι, see F. J. Long, *II Corinthians: A Handbook on the Greek Text*, 206.

¹⁰⁷ We can note in passing that this seems to be the interpretation offered by the editors of NA²⁸ and UBS⁵, who place a comma after ἐργάται δόλιοι. The same remark is made in Guthrie, *2 Corinthians*, 526, n. 29.

of the clause, it appears that *πάλιν λέγω* does not entirely satisfy L4. Following modern English punctuation conventions, the most appropriate punctuation mark to express the link between the two *côla* would certainly be a colon: “I say it again: let no one think me a fool.”

II:23

Παραφρονῶν λαλῶ / ὑπὲρ ἐγώ (?) Ἐν κόποις περισσοτέρως (?) Ἐν φυλακαῖς περισσοτέρως (?) Ἐν πληγαῖς ὑπερβαλλόντως (?) Ἐν θανάτοις πολλάκις. Παραφρονῶν λαλῶ / ὑπὲρ ἐγώ. This verse requires two comments. First, the reason for grouping the first two *commata* Παραφρονῶν λαλῶ and ὑπὲρ ἐγώ within a period—instead of considering each an autonomous comma—is that ὑπὲρ ἐγώ (“I [am] more”) expresses the content of what Paul is saying “out of his mind.” To put it differently, the expression παραφρονῶν λαλῶ does not fulfil L4 on a semantic level (see the above argumentation for II:16).

The second point concerns the series of prepositional phrases introduced by *ἐν*. In the proposed colometric disposition, I treat each of these phrases as an autonomous comma. This implies to consider that despite the absence of verbs, each of the phrases has enough semantico-syntactic autonomy to stand outside a period (see L4). Alternatively, we may still consider this series of phrases as part of the period introduced by Παραφρονῶν λαλῶ / ὑπὲρ ἐγώ. Such a delineation would be in line with T13 (subsequent *côla* that present both *parisosis* and *paromoiosis* typically belong to the same period). However, in view of both the tendency for *côla* within periods to be more closely connected at the syntactic level (see T8) and the tendency for periods not to extend beyond four *côla* (T4), I find it preferable to treat each of these *commata* as autonomous.¹⁰⁸

II:26

Ὅδοιπορίας πολλάκις (?) Κινδύνους ποταμῶν (?) Κινδύνους ληστῶν (?) Κινδύνους ἐκ γένους (?) Κινδύνους ἐξ ἔθνῶν (?) Κινδύνους ἐν πόλει (?) Κινδύνους ἐν ἐρημίᾳ (?) Κινδύνους ἐν θαλάσῃ (?) Κινδύνους ἐν ψευδαδέλφοις. As is the case for v. 23, the series of phrases beginning with *κινδύνους* might alternatively be treated as a period, in which Ὅδοιπορίας πολλάκις would be the first *côlon*: “I have been on journeys frequently: with dangers from rivers, with dangers from bandits, ...” (so virtually all translations and commentators). The

¹⁰⁸ To be fair, the choice of delineation here was also influenced by Augustine’s comment on the style of 2 Cor II:16–30. In a passage of his *Christian Doctrine* (*Doct. christ.* IV,7,12–13), Augustine provides an analysis of the structure of 2 Cor II:16–30—based on the Latin text—in terms of *membra*, *caesa*, and periods. He seems to consider *in laboribus plurimum*, *in carceribus abundantius*, *in plagis supra modum*, and *in mortibus saepius* as *commata* on their own, not being part of a period (*Doct. christ.* IV,7,13).

reasons for taking each of these phrases as autonomous commata echo those stated above for v. 23.¹⁰⁹

II:27

Κόπῳ καὶ μόχθῳ (?) Ἐν ἀγρυπνίαις πολλάκις (?) Ἐν λιμῷ καὶ δίψει (?) Ἐν νηστείαις πολλάκις (?) Ἐν ψύχει καὶ γυμνότητι. Here again, we may hesitate between taking each of the phrases introduced by ἔν as an autonomous comma or grouping them together to form a period that begins with Κόπῳ καὶ μόχθῳ: “I have known labours and toils: with sleepless nights frequently, with hunger and thirst, ...” (so virtually all translations and commentators). The reasons for treating each of these phrases as autonomous commata echo those stated above for v. 23.¹¹⁰

II:32

Ἐν Δαμασκῷ ὁ ἐθνάρχης Ἀρέτα τοῦ βασιλέως ἐφρούρει τὴν πόλιν Δαμασκηνῶν (?) πιάσαι με. Alternatively, the final purpose clause πιάσαι με might represent a distinct comma. In this case, it would become the second cōlon of a dicōloi period (see T3). However, not only is πιάσαι με unusually short to stand alone (see T1), but placing a break before it would also result in a completely unbalanced period (see T2). The first cōlon would be very long (26 syllables) and the second very short (three syllables). In addition (to borrow from Demetrius’ description of periodic cōla), we may wonder whether “to arrest me” really contains a thought that is somewhat “complete in itself.”¹¹¹ Note that the choice of delineation would perhaps have differed if the longer reading πιάσαι με θέλων (as found in some manuscripts) was retained,¹¹² as in this case we may argue that from a semantic point of view, the expression, “because he wanted to arrest me” is somewhat more complete than the simple expression, “to arrest me.” In addition, should the longer reading be retained, we may note that θέλων would rhyme with Δαμασκηνῶν (see T12).

II:1

Οὐ συμφέρον μὲν (?) ἐλεύσομαι δὲ εἰς ὀπτασίας καὶ ἀποκαλύψεις κυρίου. The reason for linking this comma and this cōlon into a period is our understanding of οὐ συμφέρον μὲν

¹⁰⁹ See also Augustine, *Doct. christ.* IV,7,13.

¹¹⁰ See also Augustine, *Doct. christ.* IV,7,13.

¹¹¹ Dem., *Eloc.* 2.

¹¹² See below, endnote xlvii.

as concessive.¹¹³ If, by contrast, οὐ συμφέρον μὲν represented a simple statement, then the comma and the cōlon should be considered autonomous: “It is not helpful. However, I will come to visions and revelations of the Lord.”

12:6

... / οὐκ ἔσομαι ἄφρων (?) Ἀλήθειαν γὰρ ἐρῶ. The choice to treat Ἀλήθειαν γὰρ ἐρῶ as an autonomous comma—rather than belonging to the preceding period—relies both on T8 and T9. This choice is uncertain, however, as the presence of a final rhyme between the two commata (οὐκ ἔσομαι ἄφρων / ἀλήθειαν γὰρ ἐρῶ) might also suggest that these clauses belong to the same period, especially when considering the similarity in length (six and seven syllables) (see T13). Within this alternative delineation, γὰρ might be understood to have a clearer subordinate function (“... / I would not be foolish / *since* I would only tell the truth.”).

12:9

Καὶ εἶρηκέν μοι / ἀρκεῖ σοι ἡ χάρις μου (?) ἡ γὰρ δύναμις ἐν ἀσθενείᾳ τελεῖται. Here, in contrast with 10:14 and 12:6, I did not consider the presence of γὰρ in this verse as a sufficient reason for separating Ἡ γὰρ δύναμις ἐν ἀσθενείᾳ τελεῖται from what precedes (see T9). Both Ἀρκεῖ σοι ἡ χάρις μου and Ἡ γὰρ δύναμις ἐν ἀσθενείᾳ τελεῖται are part of the Lord’s direct speech (Καὶ εἶρηκέν μοι, “And he said to me: ...”). Therefore, it would be somewhat artificial to place a strong break before Ἡ γὰρ δύναμις. However, to be fair, I found no basis in the rhetorical treatises for such a claim. Note that the introductory formula καὶ εἶρηκέν μοι (“And he said to me”) could also be considered an autonomous comma.

12:16

Ἔστω δέ (?) οὐ κατεβάρησα ὑμᾶς (?) ἀλλ’ ὑπάρχων πανούργος δόλω ὑμᾶς ἔλαβον. The delineation is uncertain here, depending on the interpretation of the expression ἔστω δέ. In the proposed disposition, I took ἔστω as retrospective, meaning that Paul is answering his own question in v. 15b: “If I love you the more, am I loved the less? So be it!”¹¹⁴ Others

¹¹³ So Lambrecht, *Second Corinthians*, 200; Martin, *2 Corinthians*, 388; Grässer, *Der zweite Brief an die Korinther*, vol. II, 177; Harris, *The Second Epistle to the Corinthians*, 830–831; Guthrie, *2 Corinthians*, 577; Thrall, *The Second Epistle to the Corinthians*, vol. 2, 772.

¹¹⁴ Scholars who take ἔστω as retrospective notably includes Robertson, *A Grammar of the Greek New Testament*, 4th ed., 392; Barrett, *2 Corinthians*, 324; Harris, *The Second Epistle to the Corinthians*, 888; Guthrie, *2 Corinthians*, 612–613; Long, *II Corinthians: A Handbook on the Greek Text*, 239.

take ἔστω as prospective, introducing a point on which the Corinthians agree with Paul (ἔγώ οὐ κατεβάρησα ὑμᾶς): “Let it be assumed that I did not burden you” (NRSV).¹¹⁵ Following the latter interpretation, the choice of delineation would differ, with ἔστω δέ (/) ἔγώ οὐ κατεβάρησα ὑμᾶς being a short dicôloi period (or perhaps an autonomous còlon, given the brevity of ἔστω δέ—see T1), and ἀλλ’ ὑπάρχων πανοῦργος δόλω ὑμᾶς ἔλαβον being a monocôlon period: “Let it be assumed that I did not burden you. But [you think that] crafty as I am I took you in by a trick ?!”.

12:20

Φοβοῦμαι γὰρ μή πως ἐλθὼν οὐχ οἴους θέλω εὔρω ὑμᾶς (/) κἀγὼ εὔρεθῶ ὑμῖν οἶον οὐ θέλετε / ... The delineation is uncertain here. Indeed, following both T1 (côla usually do not extend beyond 25 syllables) and T3 (côla usually encompass a clause), an additional break could be placed between ὑμᾶς and κἀγὼ. This would result in a tricôloi period: “For I fear that, when I come, I may perhaps find you not how I wish / and I may be found by you not how you wish / that there might perhaps be strife, jealousy, displays of anger, selfish ambitions, slanders, gossips, conceits, disorders.” The reason for considering κἀγὼ εὔρεθῶ ὑμῖν οἶον οὐ θέλετε to belong with the first còlon is that such a delineation produces a well-balanced period, with two còla of almost the same length (see T2 and T11) that exhibit sound echoes both at the beginning (Φοβοῦμαι ... / μή πως ἔρις... – note the presence of the sound /e/ on the third syllables, as well as the repetition of the /o/ sound) and the end (... θέλετε / ἀκαταστασίαι – see T12). Although these còla are unusually long—with 30 and 31 syllables, respectively (see T1)—they are still of acceptable length (see L2).

12:21

Μὴ πάλιν ἐλθόντος μου ταπεινώσῃ με ὁ θεὸς μου πρὸς ὑμᾶς / καὶ πενθήσω πολλοὺς τῶν προημαρτηκότων (?) καὶ μὴ μετανοησάντων (?) ἐπὶ τῇ ἀκαθαρσίᾳ καὶ πορνείᾳ καὶ ἀσελγείᾳ ἧ ἔπραξαν. The delineation of còla in this period is dependent on how we relate ἐπὶ to what precedes it. Most commentators read ἐπὶ τῇ ἀκαθαρσίᾳ καὶ πορνείᾳ καὶ ἀσελγείᾳ ἧ ἔπραξαν as the complement of μετανοησάντων (“repent of”),¹¹⁶ in which case no break

¹¹⁵ See also A. Plummer, *A Critical and Exegetical Commentary on the Second Epistle of St. Paul to the Corinthians*, 363; Martin, *2 Corinthians*, 425; Schmeller, *Der zweite Brief an die Korinther*, vol. 2, 345; M. Thrall, *The Second Epistle to the Corinthians*, vol. 2, 849, n. 599.

¹¹⁶ See A. Plummer, *A Critical and Exegetical Commentary on the Second Epistle of St. Paul to the Corinthians*, 370; Lambrecht, *Second Corinthians*, 211; Barrett, *2 Corinthians*, 326; Martin, *2 Corinthians*, 451; Harris, *The Second Epistle to the Corinthians*, 903; Long, *II Corinthians: A Handbook on the Greek Text*, 235; Thrall, *The Second Epistle to the Corinthians*, vol. 2, 857; Schmeller, *Der zweite Brief an die Korinther*, vol. 2, 353; also see most of—if not all?—

should separate the verb from its complement: “... mourn over many who have sinned previously and *did not repent* of the impurity and sexual immorality and licentiousness that they practiced.” An alternative construction is defensible from a grammatical point of view, namely to relate ἐπὶ τῇ ἀκαθαρσίᾳ καὶ πορνείᾳ καὶ ἀσελγείᾳ ἣ ἔπραξαν with πενθήσω. Following this analysis, μετανοησάντων has no complement and thus simply means “repent,” while ἐπὶ ... clarifies the reason for Paul’s mourning by detailing the sins that a fraction of the Corinthians practised (“...mourn over many who have sinned previously and did not repent / *because of* the impurity and sexual immorality and licentiousness that they practiced”). A few commentators mention this possibility, noting that elsewhere in the NT, when μετανοέω is followed by a preposition with the sense “repent of,” that preposition is ἀπό or ἐκ, not ἐπὶ.¹¹⁷ It is this interpretation that was retained above in the proposed colometric disposition. To be fair, I retain this second option mainly for stylistic considerations, because a strict application of T2—which stipulates the tendency for cōla to be balanced within a period [see also T11 on pariosis]—pleads for it. Indeed, placing a break between μετανοησάντων and ἐπὶ results in a well-balanced tricōloi period with cōla of 19, 21, and 21 syllables, respectively. In contrast, the construction argued by most commentators involves unbalanced cōla and the third of which is of unusual length (19, 13, and 29 syllables [see T1]).

13:3b

“Ὅς εἰς ὑμᾶς οὐκ ἀσθενεῖ / ἀλλὰ δυνατεῖ ἐν ὑμῖν. Here, there was no sufficient reason to link these two antithetic commata with what precedes them, despite the presence of the relative pronoun ὅς. Additionally, T10 stipulates that two antithetic cōla usually form a period on their own. According to the proposed disposition, ὅς functions in the same way as a demonstrative whose antecedent, Christ, is to be found in the preceding cōlon (v. 3).

translations (including KJV; ESV; NASB; NRSV; NIV). On the connection of 12:21 with 12:19–20, see the discussion below, Chapter 5, section 3.6.

¹¹⁷ ἀπό (Acts 8:22; cf. μετανοίας ἀπό, Heb 6:1); ἐκ (Rev. 2:21–22; 9:20–21; 16:11). Plummer (*The Second Epistle of Paul the Apostle to the Corinthians*, 218) and Harris (*2 Corinthians*, 903) mention this argument but reject it, arguing that the construction μετανοέω + ἐπὶ is not uncommon in the LXX (Joel 2:13; Amos 7:3, 6; Jonah 3:10; 4:2). Guthrie (*2 Corinthians*, 625) associates ἐπὶ τῇ ἀκαθαρσίᾳ ... with μετανοησάντων, but thinks that ἐπὶ introduces the basis for the action of repenting (“... have not repented in response to the uncleanness and sexual immorality ...”); see a similar proposition in BDAG 364.6.

3. Discussion of the Results

Having completed the colometric analysis of 2 Cor 10–13, we have now sufficient material to discuss the two issues mentioned in the introduction. First, what can be said with respect to the appropriateness of a colometric approach for Paul’s letters (section 3.1)? This is the question of the *adequation of the approach for the object of study*. Second, has the proposed set of criteria been sufficient in practice (section 3.2)? This question centres on the *operationality of our method of colometric analysis*.

3.1. Paul and colometry: Appropriateness of a colometric approach

In observing the colometric disposition of 2 Cor 10–13, multiple elements strongly suggest that Paul composed his letters in accordance with the conventions of structuration described in the rhetorical treatises. These “evidences” can be grouped into two categories (see sections 3.1.1. and 3.1.2. below). First, the “côla” and “periods” identified in 2 Cor 10–13 comply well with the recommendations made by ancient rhetoricians. Second, there are some passages where certain phenomena (such as an unusual formulation, the presence of a word which is unnecessary from a semantic point of view, or a specific choice of word order) are correlated with the presence of sound echoes. Let us explore these two kinds of “evidence” in detail.

3.1.1. Characteristics of côla and periods in 2 Cor 10–13

The units we identified as côla and periods in 2 Cor 10–13 correspond to the examples found in the treatises. Most often, they also comply with the recommendations made by rhetoricians in terms of length or the use of figures.

To begin with the length of côla. The majority of units we identified as côla are of a standard length—where the standard length is defined as containing between seven and 25 syllables.¹¹⁸ Of course, one may argue that these results are rather self-evident, as standard length was used in the above analysis as a criterion for delineating côla (= T 1). In response to such a critique, we may answer that length was neither the sole criterion used, nor even the primary one. We also relied upon various criteria related to syntax in our analysis (L3, L4, T3). The point is, there is a clear tendency for clauses and other units presenting a relative semantico-syntactic completeness to fit with the length that rhetoricians recommended for a côlon. What about the côla that do not respect the standard length? Among a total of around 300 côla, there are only seven that extend beyond 25 syllables (10:2; 10:12; 11:9; 11:15;

¹¹⁸ See the discussion in Chapter 3, section 2.1.2.

11:32; 12:20 [2x]). More frequently, however, there are very short *côla* (commata) of less than seven syllables (almost 60), which represents around one fifth of the total of the *côla*. It is noteworthy that more than half of these commata are concentrated in the so-called “Fool’s Speech” (11:1–12:13), where Paul harshly criticises his opponents without hesitating to use aggressive language at some points.¹¹⁹ In this context, there is nothing surprising about such an abundance of commata. On the contrary, this concentration of commata is perfectly in line with rhetoricians’s recommendation to use commata in vehement passages.¹²⁰

Second, we may note that among the units identified as periods (around 80 as a total),¹²¹ more than 80% have a standard length of two to four *côla*.¹²² Precisely, there are six monocôlon periods¹²³ (in 10:12; 11:9; 11:24; 12:19 [x2]; 13:1; and 13:3), and six periods that extend beyond the standard limit of four *côla* (11:15–16 [six *côla*]; 11:20 [five *côla*]; 12:2 [five *côla*]; 12:3–4 [six *côla*]; 12:10 [five *côla*] and 13:11 [six *côla*]). With respect to the number of syllables, the majority of periods identified in 2 Cor 10–13 contain the normal range of 25–60 syllables (see T5). There are only three periods that extend slightly beyond 60 syllables (10:8 [around 70 syllables]; 12:20 [61 syllables]; and, 12:21 [61 syllables]). The delineation criteria used in this study cannot alone explain such a close correspondence between the lengths of periods observed in 2 Cor 10–13 and the recommendations of rhetoricians. In most

¹¹⁹ On aggressive language in 2 Corinthians, see P. Lampe, “Can Words Be Violent or Do They Only Sound That Way? Second Corinthians: Verbal Warfare from Afar as a Complement to a Placid Personal Presence.”

¹²⁰ See Dem., *Eloc.* 6–8; cf. §241; *Rhet. Her.* IV,19,27; Cic., *Or. Brut.* 224; Herm., *Id.* I,8,10.

¹²¹ This abundance of periods contrasts with the claim sometimes made that Paul’s style is generally non-periodic (see, e.g., Weiss, *Beiträge zur Paulinischen Rhetorik*, 167 [“It is generally accepted that Paul did not write in periodic style [...] the basic element of the speech of the apostle is the individual short sentence, which is only rarely bound with others into a larger, genuine period” (the English translation is taken from Schellenberg, *Rethinking Paul’s Rhetorical Education*, 259, n. 8)]; Anderson, *Ancient Rhetorical Theory and Paul*, 161 [“As far as sentence structure is concerned, the style is generally paratactic, showing no use of extended periods”—note that this comment applies to the epistle to the Galatians, see pages 111–167]; also see BDF §464). The gap between these assertions and our own observations may be explained to a large extent by the fact that modern scholars seem to work with a very strict definition of the period. For instance, Weiss states that “the sentences with [subordinating conjunctions] also belong to paratactic, not periodic, speech when, as is almost always the case, the main clause does not embrace them in periodic style and thus lead to a conclusion that rounds off the sentence. Even the longer complex sentence consists only of loosely connected clauses that can be multiplied at will ...” (*Beiträge zur Paulinischen Rhetorik*, 167 [the English translation is that found in Schellenberg, *Rethinking Paul’s Rhetorical Education*]). As to Anderson, he defines the period as “a sentence containing at least two subordinate clauses wherein the main clause, interrupted by the subordinate clauses, is left in suspense and only completed by the last few words of the whole sentence” (*Ancient Rhetorical Theory and Paul*, 161, n. 414—but see a less strict definition in Anderson’s *Glossary of Greek Rhetorical Terms*, 94–101). As explored in Chapter 3 (see the discussion under section 3.2), such strict definitions echo Demetrius’ definition of the “rhetorical period” (see *Eloc.* 20); they fail, however, at reflecting the more loose periods also recognised by Demetrius, namely the “narrative period” and the “dialogue period” (see Dem., *Eloc.* 19–21).

¹²² On the standard length for periods, see the discussion in Chapter 3, section 3.1

¹²³ On the definition of the monocôlon period, see Chapter 3, section 3.1.

cases, standard length (whether in terms of syllables or number of cōla) was not the primary criterion used to delineating periods. Rather, I relied mainly on the periods' typical syntactic characteristics, especially the tendency for periodic cōla to be interwoven (see T8). To a lesser extent, I also relied on T10 (the rule that two antithetic cōla usually form a period on their own) and T13 (the tendency for subsequent cōla that present both pariosis and paromoiosis to be part of the same period).

The third point, which is the most striking, concerns the presence of the so-called Gorgianic figures. In addition to antitheses—that are commonly mentioned by commentators—our analysis reveals numerous sound echoes (paromoiosis) as well as numerous cases where two or more cōla belonging to the same period have approximately an equal length (pariosis). The amount of these figures is impressive: leaving aside the periods built on an antithesis, virtually all the periods in 2 Cor 10–13 comprises at least one paromoiosis or one pariosis. Even while acknowledging that sound echoes naturally occur provided that any language has a finite number of sounds, such frequency of echoes—some of which consist of sequences of three, four, or even more vowels (e.g., 10:1; 10:15–16; 11:4; 11:12; 11:28; 12:5; 12:7; 13:10)—are hardly explained by pure coincidence. This is all the more true if we consider that sound echoes regularly appear in cōla that also have approximately the same length and/or are antithetic (e.g., 10:11; 11:12; 11:28; 12:5; 12:6–7a; 12:17; 13:3b; 13:7). Therefore, we may assert that besides the figure of antithesis (of which he seems particularly fond) Paul also made a frequent use of the two other Gorgianic figures—perhaps even overly frequent, if we consider Demetrius' warning against the excessive use of Gorgianisms.¹²⁴

3.1.2. Choice of words, word order, and sound echoes

We can observe several passages in 2 Cor 10–13 where an unusual formulation or the choice of a specific word order¹²⁵ is correlated with the presence of paromoioses.

¹²⁴ Dem., *Eloc.* 27–29. On the rhetoricians' critique on the excessive use of Gorgianisms, see M. P. Noël, "Gorgias et l'«invention» des γοργίεια σχήματα."

¹²⁵ On the topic of word order in ancient Greek, see the classical study by H. Dik, *Word Order in Ancient Greek: A Pragmatic Account of Word Order Variation in Herodotus*; also see S. J. Bakker, *The noun phrase in Ancient Greek: A functional analysis of the order and articulation of NP constituents in Herodotus*; D. Matić, "Topic, Focus, and Discourse Structure: Ancient Greek Word Order"; G. G. A. Celano, "Word Order"; B. Nicolas, "Information Structure and Greek"; Id., *L'ordre des mots chez Homère. Structure informationnelle, localisation et progression du récit*. Cf. also C. de Jonge, "From Demetrius to Dik. Ancient and Modern Views on Natural Word Order." On the specific case of NT Greek, see Porter, *Idioms of the Greek New Testament*, 286–297; Levinsohn, *Features of the New Testament Greek*, 1–67; Runge, *Discourse Grammar of the Greek New Testament*, 181–205. Finally, we can mention Long, *II Corinthians: A Handbook on the Greek Text*, who has systematically noted instances of unusual word orders in 2 Corinthians.

10:1

Αὐτός δὲ ἐγὼ Παῦλος ...

This formulation, which is a *hapax legomenon*, combines two phrases that Paul uses elsewhere to refer to himself: αὐτός ἐγὼ (“I myself,” [e.g. Rom 7:25; 9:3; 15:14; 2 Cor 12:13]) and ἐγὼ Παῦλος (“I, Paul,” [e.g., Gal 5:2; Philem 19]). Of course (as classically explained by commentators) such wording is emphatic and stresses the personal nature of the appeal.¹²⁶ Without denying this emphatic value, it is worth noting that the choice of this unusual expression also gives this opening period a euphonious touch. Indeed, it creates a strong sound echo between the beginnings of the first and the fourth cōla (Αὐτός δὲ ἐγὼ ... / ὁπῶν δὲ θαρρῶ), with the sequence of sounds /a/, /o/, /e/, /o/ occurring in both cases on the first, second, third, and fifth syllables.

10:2

... ἐπί τινας / τοὺς λογιζομένους ἡμᾶς ὡς κατὰ σάρκα περιπατοῦντας.

It is worth considering the articulation between the two cōla of 10:2. Where we could have simply expected the formulation ἐπί τοὺς λογιζομένους ἡμᾶς ὡς κατὰ σάρκα περιπατοῦντας (“against *those who* reckon us as walking according to the flesh”), Paul adds the semantically unnecessary τινας (“... against *some* [people] / *those who* reckon us as walking according to the flesh”). From both a structural and euphonic point of view, however, the presence of τινας is useful. Indeed, this enables a break to be placed before τοὺς λογιζομένους, after a first cōlon that is already very long with 28 syllables. At the same time this creates a final paromoiosis between the two cōla (repetition of the sounds /e/, /i/ and /a/, as well as repetition of the consonants π, τ ν and σ: ... ἐπί τινας / ... περιπατοῦντας).

10:6

... ὑμῶν ἡ ὑπακοή

Here the genitive modifier ὑμῶν is pre-positioned: it precedes the noun that it qualifies (ἡ ὑπακοή), instead of following the head noun (ἡ ὑπακοή ὑμῶν). Some commentators note that such a word order emphasises that the “obedience” is that of the Corinthians (“your *own* obedience”).¹²⁷ In light of the colometric disposition proposed above, we may also advance a

¹²⁶ See, e.g., Harris, *The Second Epistle to the Corinthians*, 666; Guthrie, *2 Corinthians*, 466.

¹²⁷ See this remark in Harris, *The Second Epistle to the Corinthians*, 685; also see Plummer, *A Critical and Exegetical Commentary on the Second Epistle of St. Paul to the Corinthians*, 278. Barrett does not discuss this point, but the emphasis is reflected in his proposed translation: “when your *own* [my emphasis] obedience is

euphonic explanation for this choice of word arrangement: in fact, such a word order allows the two cōla of the period to rhyme, with a final paromoiosis between παρακοήν and υπακοή.

10:15–16

... / ἐν ὑμῖν μεγαλυνθῆναι κατὰ τὸν κανόνα ἡμῶν / ... / ^[16] εἰς τὰ ὑπερέκεινα ὑμῶν εὐαγγελίσασθαι / οὐκ ἐν ἀλλοτρίῳ κανόνι εἰς τὰ ἔτοιμα καυχῆσασθαι.

Here ἐν ὑμῖν is pre-positioned (assuming that it should be construed with what follows),¹²⁸ such that it stands at the very beginning of the second cōlon of the period. We may note that this initial positioning produces sound echoes between the beginnings of the first two cōla, with the same sequence /e/, /i/, /e/ occurring on their four initial syllables (Ἐλπίδα δὲ ... / ἐν ὑμῖν με- ...). Within the same period, we can also note the final positions of the two infinitives in v. 16 (εὐαγγελίσασθαι and καυχῆσασθαι),¹²⁹ which create a final paromoiosis between the fourth and fifth cōla (-σασθαι and -σασθαι).

11:4

... / καλῶς ἀνέχεσθε.

In 11:4, the adverb καλῶς (“well”) is pre-positioned.¹³⁰ This certainly serves to emphasise καλῶς, and thus, ironically dramatizes the idea that the Corinthians put up with the teaching of the “super-apostles”: not only do the Corinthians put up with this teaching, but they do so “very well” or “beautifully.”¹³¹ That being said, we can note that such a word order also produces a supplementary sound echoe within the period, in that it makes the final comma rhyme with the three preceding cōla (... ἐκηρύξαμεν / ... ἐλάβετε / ... ἐδέξασθε / ... ἀνέχεσθε).

complete” (Barrett, *2 Corinthians*, 243; italics are mine). Long notes a “genitival emphasis” (Long, *II Corinthians: A Handbook on the Greek Text*, 203; see his remark on genitival emphasis on page 10: “this draws attention to the modifier as a qualifier, and thus to the qualification itself”). On the phenomenon of pre-positioned genitives in the NT and their possible emphatic role, see Levinsohn, *Discourse Features of New Testament Greek*, 62–67; also see Porter, *Idioms of the Greek New Testament*, 291; Id., “Prominence: An Overview,” 69. See also the remarks by C. Viti, “Genitive Word Order in Ancient Greek: A Functional Analysis of Word Order Freedom in the Noun Phrase.”

¹²⁸ Long, *II Corinthians: A Handbook on the Greek Text*, 194; cf. Harris, *The Second Epistle to the Corinthians*, 721.

¹²⁹ As Long mentions (*II Corinthians: A Handbook on the Greek Text*, 194), εἰς τὰ ὑπερέκεινα, ἐν ἀλλοτρίῳ and κανόνι εἰς τὰ ἔτοιμα are all pre-positioned.

¹³⁰ As noticed by Long, *II Corinthians: A Handbook on the Greek Text*, 200–201.

¹³¹ In this respect, we may add that the very construction of the period, with the main clause placed at the end and preceded by an accumulation of conditional clauses, creates a certain tension.

II:8

... τὴν ὑμῶν διακονίαν

In this nominal phrase, the genitive personal pronoun ὑμῶν is pre-positioned.¹³² We notice that such a word order permits the two cōla of the period to end with the same /a/ sound (... ἐσύλησα / ... διακονίαν).

II:16

Εἰ δὲ μή γε / κἄν ὡς ἄφρονα δέξασθέ με / ἵνα κἀγὼ μικρόν τι καυχῆσωμαι.

In this tricōloi period, both ἄφρονα and μικρόν τι are pre-positioned.¹³³ Such a word order adds a euphonious touch to the passage, as it produces sound echoes between the ends of the three cōla (... δὲ μή γε / ... δέξασθέ με / ... καυχῆσωμαι).

12:9

... / ἵνα ἐπισκηνώσῃ ἐπ' ἐμέ ἡ δύναμις τοῦ Χριστοῦ

In 12:9, ἐπ' ἐμέ is pre-positioned. Naturally, the purpose for this may be to ensure that the final emphasis rests on ἡ δύναμις τοῦ Χριστοῦ (“the power of Christ”).¹³⁴ Without denying this explanation, we can also remark that this word order produces a final paromoiosis between the two cōla of the period (... ἐν ταῖς ἀσθενείαις μου / ... ἡ δύναμις τοῦ Χριστοῦ). Had the expected word order been respected (ἡ δύναμις τοῦ Χριστοῦ ἐπ' ἐμέ), this rhyme would not have existed.

13:3

Ὁς εἰς ὑμᾶς οὐκ ἀσθενεῖ / ἀλλὰ δυνατεῖ ἐν ὑμῖν.

In the first comma of this short period, εἰς ὑμᾶς is pre-positioned.¹³⁵ In addition to producing a chiasmus (εἰς ὑμᾶς = A, οὐκ ἀσθενεῖ = B, ἀλλὰ δυνατεῖ = B', ἐν ὑμῖν = A') that “has the effect of highlighting items A and A', that is, the personal relationship of Christ to the Corinthians,”¹³⁶ this word order makes the two commata end with the same /i/ sound

¹³² Long notes a “genitival emphasis” (Long, *II Corinthians: A Handbook on the Greek Text*, 203; see his remark on genitival emphasis on page 10).

¹³³ See Long, *II Corinthians: A Handbook on the Greek Text*, 211.

¹³⁴ As Long suggests (*II Corinthians: A Handbook on the Greek Text*, 230); see a similar view in Harris, *The Second Epistle to the Corinthians*, 866.

¹³⁵ Long, *II Corinthians: A Handbook on the Greek Text*, 249.

¹³⁶ Harris, *The Second Epistle to the Corinthians*, 912.

(...ἀσθενεῖ / ... ἐν ὑμῖν). As a result, this period exhibits the three Gorgianic figures of antithesis, pariosis (eight and eight syllables), and paromoiosis.

When taken together, the few examples mentioned above strongly suggest that Paul deliberately arranged words in order to achieve sound echoes.¹³⁷

3.2. *Operationality of the proposed set of criteria*

Let us now turn to the method itself—specifically the operationality of the proposed set of criteria when it comes to make choices of delineation. By relying on the different laws and tendencies, in most cases it was quite an easy task to identify *côla* and periods. Of course, there are many passages where a different delineation could have been made while still respecting the criteria—a few of these passages have been mentioned under section 2.2.3. Nevertheless, generally speaking, the proposed set of criteria is precise enough to guide the process of analysis. Moreover, we can note that nowhere was it necessary to defy the traditional grammatical rules or posit awkward constructions to make Paul’s prose fit with the theoretical frame of the method. In this sense, none of the criteria seems to be too strict when confronting a real text. It may thus be fairly concluded that the proposed method of colometric analysis is operational with respect to Paul’s prose.

Following this optimistic conclusion, let us say a few words on the limits of our method. In fact, it must be acknowledged that the proposed method of colometric analysis still leaves room for interpretation. I shall outline three kinds of difficulties or questions that arose during the process of analysis, all of which revolve around the question of the limit between the periodic and non-periodic styles.

A question that regularly appears is the weight that should be given to T₁₃. This echoes a difficulty already observed in Chapter 3: similarities in sound and similarities in length are characteristic of periods; yet, they may also occur in non-periodic *côla* and therefore they do not systematically indicate that the concerned *côla* belong to the same period.¹³⁸ In the 2 Cor 10–13 analysis process, it sometimes happens that subsequent *côla* exhibit both equality in length and sound echoes (in which case T₁₃ suggests that these *côla* together form a period) but do not present the syntactical interweaving that is typical of periods (and thus,

¹³⁷ This conclusion concurs with the conclusions of R. Merda de Villeneuve, who discussed Paul’s use of sound echoes in 1 Corinthians (*L’elocutio en 1 Corinthiens: Inventaire, stratégie et herméneutique*, see esp. 266–268).

¹³⁸ See Chapter 3, section 3.4.1.

T8 rather suggests that there is no period). This is the case in 10:4c–5; 10:14; 11:23; 11:26; 11:27; 12:6; and 13:11. In my choices of delineation above, I systematically favoured T8 over T13, thereby assuming that sound echoes and equality in length—even when they are combined—are not sufficient clues for linking *côla* within a period. However, such a choice was made with considerable hesitation and it should not be elevated to the rank of a new rule. In view of the clear link that rhetoricians establish between Gorgianic figures and the periodic style,¹³⁹ it might be that *paromoiosis* and/or *pariosis* are sometimes the only cues that two or more *côla* should be read together as a period. Further researchs on the binding role of *pariosis* and *paromoiosis* would be welcomed in order to clarify the respective importance of T8 and T13.

Another question that arose when analysing the micro-structure of 2 Cor 10–13 is how to treat two *côla* that are not syntactically dependent on each other, but where the second *côlon* provides information that is in some way expected following the first *côlon*. Such a situation was found in 11:16 and 11:23. In these two cases, I argued above that the two *côla* together form a period, though there is no explicit rule in the method on which this decision can be based. The point is that the first *côlon* creates an expectation that is then fulfilled with the second *côlon*, such that the two *côla* together form a complete thought (following modern habits of punctuating English, we would typically use a colon to express this link). Such an argument finds some basis in ancient sources, as it may be paralleled in the model of a narrative period that Demetrius provides: Δαρείου καὶ Παρυσάτιδος γίνονται παῖδες / πρεσβύτερος μὲν Ἀρταξέρξης, νεώτερος δὲ Κῦρος (“Darius and Parysatis had sons: the elder was Artaxerxes, the younger Cyrus.”).¹⁴⁰ Here, the two *côla* are syntactically independent from each other, yet Demetrius makes it clear that together they form a period. Indeed, following the information that Darius and Parysatis had sons, complementary information is expected concerning the number of sons and/or their names.¹⁴¹ It might be judicious to add a supplementary rule in our method in order to take these kinds of periods into account.

Finally, this colometric analysis also raised the issue of the status of reported speeches and quotations. In the sole instance of a reported speech found in 2 Cor 10–13 (12:9), I treated the introductory *côlon* (καὶ εἶρηκέν μοι) and the entire content of the quotation as forming a single period (see above, under section 2.3.). However, this way of proceeding is questionable and cannot be considered a rule. In fact, it seems clear that always considering

¹³⁹ See, e.g., Arist., *Rhet.* III,9,7–10; Dem., *Eloc.* 15; Cic., *Or. Brut.* 165.

¹⁴⁰ Dem., *Eloc.* 19 (= Xen., *Anab.* I); see the same example in *Eloc.* 3.

¹⁴¹ See Demetrius’ discussion in *Eloc.* 3.

the entire content of a reported speech or of a quotation as part of the same period would not be a solution, because this would regularly result in periods that are too long.¹⁴² In addition, it might also be thought that the formula that introduces a reported speech or a quotation sometimes constitutes an autonomous cōlon. Unfortunately, as far as I am aware, there is simply no basis in the treatises to know how ancient rhetoricians used to conceive the status of such sayings.

4. Conclusion

This study of 2 Cor 10–13 enables us to draw a series of conclusions with respect to the appropriateness of the method for understanding the micro-structure of Paul’s prose. As for the relevance of applying the categories of cōlon and period to Paul’s letters (i.e., the issue of adequation between the approach and the object of study),¹⁴³ our analysis produced encouraging results. Not only do the units identified as “cōla” and “periods” in 2 Cor 10–13 perfectly correspond with the cōla and periods that are described in the rhetorical treatises. This degree of correspondance is not solely explainable by the active search for cōla and periods in this text.¹⁴⁴ There are also several places where a change in usual word order—especially, prepositioned genitives in nominal phrases—seems to be made for, or at least *notably* for, the purpose of producing sound echoes between the extremities of cōla. In view of this evidence, we can fairly conclude that 2 Corinthians (and likely all the Pauline letters) are structured in cōla and periods. To put it another way, we have compelling reasons to think that when composing his letters, Paul employed the same conventions of structuration as the contemporary Greek authors.

The method itself (i.e., the issue of operationality)¹⁴⁵ proved to be operational in most cases. Namely, the proposed set of laws and tendencies effectively guide the choices of delineation, although there are some cases where the criteria fail to provide a solid basis for decision. Most of the difficulties encountered revolve around the question of the limit between the periodic style and the non-periodic style. This is not surprising, as in the rhetorical treatises a certain blur surrounds this question.¹⁴⁶ Specifically, we have pointed out (1) the question of the role of *pariosis* and *paromoiosis* in identifying periods (and thus,

¹⁴² See the discussion in Chapter 3, section 3.1.

¹⁴³ See Chapter 3, section 1.3.

¹⁴⁴ See above, section 3.1.

¹⁴⁵ See Chapter 3, section 1.3.3.

¹⁴⁶ See the discussion in Chapter 3, section 3.3.

concretely, the question of the weight that should be given to T13); (2) the cases of dicôloi periods whose cōla are syntactically independent from each other, but where the second cōlon provides information that is somehow expected after the first cōlon (following modern habits of punctuation, we would typically use a colon [:] to separate these cōla); (3) the issue of how reported speeches and quotations should be treated. As concerns the first and the third points, the ancient sources do not offer a sufficient basis for establishing rules. With respect to the second point, however, a parallel can be found in Demetrius' example of "narrative period,"¹⁴⁷ which suggests that those kinds of constructions should be treated as periods.

At the end of this chapter, we can thus be relatively confident that our method of colometric analysis is an appropriate analytical tool—in other words, a tool that may be called "scientific"—for grasping the micro-structure of Paul's prose. This conclusion opens fresh perspectives on how to deal with syntactical ambiguities and issues of punctuation in the Pauline letters: this will be the focus of Chapter 5.

¹⁴⁷ Dem., *Eloc.* 19; cf. *Eloc.* 3.

CHAPTER 5

Re-punctuating Paul's Letters in Light of their Colometric Structure

I. Introduction

Having shown that the micro-structure of Paul's prose readily lends itself to an analysis in terms of *côla*, *commata* and periods, we will now consider the implications of this point for how his letters should be punctuated using modern punctuation marks. My choice to exclusively focus on the issue of punctuation in this chapter stemmed from the idea that a colometric approach has the most direct consequences within this area. Indeed, when the structure of a text is analysed in terms of colometry, it inevitably leads to specific understandings of the semantico-syntactic relationships between certain words, phrases, and/or clauses. Such understandings may in turn require specific punctuation choices. In addition, an attention to the colometric structure of a text can more generally provide us with a sense of its style or "musicality." This aspect can also be rendered in written form with punctuation marks.

In other words, colometry may renew the modern punctuation of Paul's letters in two different areas. Firstly, colometry introduces new elements into the debates on those passages that contain syntactic ambiguities that are connected to issues of discourse segmentation. As will be shown below, a colometric approach helps to disambiguate the syntax, particularly when the issue is determining where breaks should be placed as well as the respective importance of each of them. This first area is explored and illustrated in section 2 below, using a few examples from 2 Cor 10–13. Secondly, from a broader perspective, colometry invites us to imagine new ways of disposing Paul's letters. These new methods reflect the letters' stylistic, aural characteristics better than current critical editions—such as the Nestle-Aland *Novum Testamentum Graece* (NA)¹ or the UBS *Greek New Testament*²—do. To rephrase a remark by the classicist David Sansone and apply it to Paul: it is unscientific to assume that one can rely on the punctuation in a modern edition of Paul's letters to provide evidence for Paul's stylistic characteristics.³ In order to

¹ I will refer to the 28th edition published in 2012 in particular (B. Aland, K. Aland *et al.* (ed), *Novum Testamentum Graece* [based on the work of Eberhard and Erwin Nestle]).

² I will refer to the 5th edition published in 2014 in particular (B. Aland, K. Aland *et al.* (ed), *The Greek New Testament*).

³ Sansone's original formulation runs as follows: "It is unscientific to assume that one can rely on the punctuation in a modern text of a classical author to provide evidence for the stylistic characteristics of that author." (D. Sansone, "The Computer and the *Historia Augusta*: A Note on Marriott," 174).

better reflect the stylistic characteristics of Paul's prose, one option would simply be to produce colometric editions of his letters. Another option that remains closer to our modern conventions of disposing texts would be to convert the colometric boundaries identified in his letters in terms of graphical punctuation marks. Thus, we could propose a system of written punctuation that would merely indicate *côla* while also signalling when a set of *côla* should be read together as a period. It is this latter option of an "elocutionary-based punctuation"⁴ that will be explored below, in section 3—2 Cor 10–13 remains a case study throughout.

However, before turning to the discussion on how colometry may shed light on the punctuation of 2 Cor 10–13, we must first draw some connection between colometry and what might be termed "aural punctuation" (i.e., the different breaks that are meant to be observed when texts are read aloud). Rhetoricians have established multiple links between colometry and delivery that make it clear that the appropriate aural punctuation for a given text is directly connected to its colometric structure, specifically concerning pausing and prosody. For example, we can think of the opening of the *Περὶ ἑρμηνείας*, where Pseudo-Demetrius states that "*côla* give a sort of rest [*ἀναπαύοντα*] to both the speaker and what is actually being said;"⁵ or of Quintilian's remark that "there are short *membra* in all speech, where we can draw breath if we need to ...;"⁶ or of Saint Augustine's statement that disjointed *côla* and *commata* are pronounced separately, while periodic *côla* are "suspended on the voice of the speaker until the last one."⁷ More simply, we could note that the Greek triad of the comma, the *côlon*, and the period gave their names to the major punctuation marks in English (though British English favours the term "full stop" over "period"). Nevertheless, it is worth further exploring the ancient discourses on *pronunciatio* (i.e., the last of the five canons of rhetoric, also called *actio*) in order to develop a more detailed understanding of the origin and nature of the link between colometry and aural punctuation. This will provide a more solid foundation for my proposal to repunctuate Paul's letters on the basis of their colometric structure.

⁴ On the different approaches to punctuation marks, see below, section 4.1.

⁵ Dem., *Eloc.* I (my translation).

⁶ Quint., *Inst.* XI,3,110 (my translation).

⁷ Augustine, *Doc. Chr.* IV,7,11 (my translation).

2. Colometry and Punctuation

We will first address the system of colometry in connection with the sparing use of punctuation marks in ancient manuscripts. Then, we shall consider the concrete aspect of the relationship between colometry and delivery, specifically by trying to grasp the pragmatism of uttering a text in terms of pauses, intonation, and breathing.

2.1. *Ancient discourses on punctuation*

It is well-known that the earliest Greek manuscripts of the New Testament do not include fully punctuated text. They do however contain different punctuation signs, making an even greater use of them than non-Christian manuscripts.⁸ In this sense, the claim sometimes made that the oldest testimonies of the NT lack punctuation cannot be sustained. However, it should be acknowledged that these signs occur only sparingly. This sparing use of punctuation marks contrasts sharply with modern critical editions such as the Nestle-Aland *Novum Testamentum Graece* (NA),⁹ the UBS *Greek New Testament*,¹⁰ Reuben Swanson's series of comparative transcriptions of Greek manuscripts (GMNT),¹¹ or the ongoing project of the *Editio Critica Maior* (ECM),¹² all of which provide a fully punctuated text.

2.1.1. *The importance of punctuation*

The sparing use of punctuation marks in ancient manuscripts does not mean that punctuation—in the general sense of indicating the divisions of a text—was considered unimportant and completely left for the reader to decipher. On the contrary, the ancient sources provide various pieces of evidence showing that in antiquity, discourse segmentation mattered to grammarians, rhetoricians, and other scholars. Thus, in the

⁸ See Hurtado, "Manuscripts and the Sociology of Early Christian Reading," esp. 58.

⁹ See above, footnote 1.

¹⁰ See above, footnote 2.

¹¹ R. J. Swanson, *New Testament Greek Manuscripts: Variant Readings Arranged in Horizontal Lines against Codex Vaticanus* (volumes are currently available for the four Gospels, the Acts of the Apostles, Romans, Galatians, and 1 and 2 Corinthians).

¹² The project of the *Editio Critica Maior* (ECM) was undertaken in the 1990's by the Institut für neutestamentliche Textforschung, in Münster. Thus far, the Catholic Letters (two volumes) and the Acts of the Apostles (four volumes) have been published (Institut für Neutestamentliche Textforschung, *Novum Testamentum Graecum. Editio Critica Maior, vol III: Die Apostelgeschichte/Acts*, 4 vol. [published in 2017]; *vol. IV: Die Katholischen Briefe/Catholic Letters*, 2 vol. [2nd ed. 2013]). The Gospel of John is currently under preparation in collaboration with the International Greek New Testament Project. See a presentation of the ECM project in H. Houghton, D. Parker, P. Robinson, K. Wachtel, "The *Editio Critica Maior* of the Greek New Testament: Twenty Years of Digital Collaboration."

second part of the 2nd century BC, Dionysius of Thrax (ca. 170–90 BCE) noted the importance of an accurate division (i.e., pauses) while reading:

Reading [ἀνάγνωσις] is the faultless pronunciation of poetic or prose texts. One must read with due regard to expression, prosody, and division [διαστολή]. Through the expression we can see the excellence [of the speech]; from the prosody, the art [of the reader]; and from the division, the meaning intended to be conveyed.¹³

In the eleventh book of his *Institutio oratoria*, which is entirely devoted to the art of delivery, Quintilian insisted that punctuation is a crucial aspect of the reader's work:

Speech must be distinct; that is, the speaker must begin and stop at the right place [...]. Virtue of punctuation [*virtus distinguendi*] may seem to be a small thing; but without it there can be no other virtue in delivery.¹⁴

Regarding the Christian tradition more specifically, Saint Augustine's concern for the correct punctuation of sacred texts is notable.¹⁵ Referring notably to passages from Paul's letters, he illustrated some difficulties of interpretation that stem from ambiguities in punctuation; that is, passages in which the rules of grammar allow for different constructions. With respect to those passages, the bishop of Hippo called readers to rely on the "rule of faith" as a guide to decide where to place breaks (however, his concerns mainly appears to be ensuring that the meaning induced by the pauses observed while reading were compatible with the Christian doctrine).¹⁶ A similar concern was expressed two centuries prior by Irenaeus, who complained in his work *Against Heresies* that heretics "do not even know how to read Paul." With this remark, he meant concretely that these persons had misplaced the pauses.¹⁷ Finally, we may also quote the later warning by Photius, the archbishop of Constantinople (9th century CE), that "even the

¹³ Dion. Thrax, *Grammar 2* (my translation, based on the Greek text established by G. Uhlig, *Grammatici Graeci* I,1; reproduced in J. Lallot, *La grammaire de Denys le Thrace*, 42). Although modern scholarship has largely questioned the traditionnal attribution of this Τέχνη Γραμματική to the grammarian Dionysius Thrax (see Di Benedetto's argument, "Dionisio Trace e la Techne a lui attribuita," who proposed a datation between the 3rd and the 5th centuries CE for the major material of the treatise), the first five chapters are generally considered to be from Dionysius' hand (on this question, see a synthesis in J. Lallot, *La grammaire de Denys le Thrace*, 25–26). For an overview of the question of authenticity, see R. H. Robins, "The Authenticity of the Techne: The status quaestionis"; also see J. Lallot, "Vers une typologie de l'argumentation pro et contra dans la question de l'authenticité de la Technè"; Id., *La grammaire de Denys le Thrace*, 20–26; cf. also M. Callipo, "Introduction" [*Dionisio Trace e la tradizione grammaticale*], 28–34).

¹⁴ Quint., *Inst.* XI,3,39 (my translation).

¹⁵ August., *Doc. Chr.* III,2,2–5.

¹⁶ August., *Doc. Chr.* III,2,2.

¹⁷ Iren., *Adv. Haer.* III,7,1.

smallest of signs, the mark of punctuation, wrongly used or over looked or misplaced, creates great heresy of every kind.”¹⁸

2.1.2. Punctuation marks

The sparing use of punctuation in ancient manuscripts does not suggest a general absence of reflection on the topic of graphical reading aids in the Graeco-Roman antiquity.¹⁹ In the Greek tradition, punctuation marks were occasionally used from the 4th century BCE at least, as some are attested in papyri from this time.²⁰ This point can also be easily deduced from Aristotle’s testimony. In the third book of his *Rhetoric*, Aristotle noted the structuring role of final long syllables when discussing the rhythm of prose by explaining that “the end should be brought to a close and made manifest by a long syllable: not by the scribe nor by a graphical mark [μη̄ διὰ τὸν γραφέα, μηδὲ διὰ τὴν παραγραφὴν], but rather by the rhythm itself.”²¹ Despite Aristotle’s own reluctance towards the idea of illuminating the micro-structure of a written text by means of graphical signs, this passage implies that such a practise was indeed somewhat common in the second half of the 4th century BCE. One century later, the chief librarian in the Library of Alexandria Aristophanes of Byzantium (257–180 BC) began introducing different lectional signs in the copies of Homer, including “points” (στιγμαί).²² His successor Aristarchus of Samothrace (220–143 BCE) then continued this practice.

¹⁸ *Amphil.* 1 (see N. G. Wilson, *Scholars of Byzantium*, 117–119; the above translation is reproduced from this book).

¹⁹ For a good synthesis on the origins of written punctuation in the Greek and Latin traditions, see N. Catach, *La ponctuation*, 11–23; also see M. B. Parkes, *Pause and Effect*, 9–19. On the Greek tradition more specifically, see R. Pfeiffer, *History of Classical Scholarship*, vol. I, 171–209; also see G. Fluck, *De Graecorum interpunctionibus*.

²⁰ R. Pfeiffer, *History of Classical Scholarship*, vol. I, 179. Pfeiffer mentions that there is even an attestation of punctuation dating from about 700 BCE, in a graffito found in Ischia (*History of Classical Scholarship*, vol. I, 179).

²¹ Arist., *Rhet.* III,8,6.

²² See G. A. Privitera, R. Pretagostini, *Soria e forme della letteratura greca*, vol. II, 676–684; Pfeiffer, 174–180; also see G. Fluck, *De Graecorum interpunctionibus*, esp. 4ff. In popular articles, it is often claimed that Aristophanes of Byzance is the “inventor” of punctuation marks. As Pfeiffer notes, this claim is false: Aristophanes rather continued a tradition that can at least be traced back to the 4th century BCE (Pfeiffer, *History of Classical Scholarship*, vol. I, 178–179). Actually, such an idea seems to come from Jacobus Diassorinus’ 16th century copy of Ps.-Arcadius’ epitome of Herodian’s *Καθολικὴ Προσωδία*, a copy in which Diassorinus added some sentences dealing with punctuation. He notably mixed Ps.-Arcadius’ text with some Scholia to Dionysius Thrax, thus making Aristophanes the “inventor” of punctuation; see these passages on punctuation published in W. Lameere, *Aperçus de paléographie homérique*, 91.

Descriptions of different systems of punctuation can even be found in the works of ancient grammarians. The most ancient system—which is probably the most famous and whose traces are still visible in modern occidental ways of punctuating—comprises three points, each of which indicate a specific degree of division. The first known description of this system is that given by Dionysius of Thrax in his *Τέχνη Γραμματική*, in the second part of the 2nd century BCE:

There are three points [στιγμαί]: the final point [τελεία], the medium point [μέση], the lower point [ὑποστιγμή]. The final point signals that the sense has been completed; the medium point is a sign of where to take breath; the lower point signals that the sense is not yet complete, but that something further must be added.²³

Rather than introducing a new system, this description seems to showcase classifications that were already in use when Dionysius wrote. Moreover, if we trust the ancient testimonies asserting that Dionysius was Aristarchus' pupil,²⁴ we could potentially assume that this three-point system corresponds to that applied by Aristarchus and Aristophanes in their editorial work at the Library of Alexandria—but there can be no certainty concerning this point. Nonetheless, this three-point system was prevalent in the subsequent centuries, as the numerous Scholia to the *Technē* testify.²⁵ It was also adopted by the Latins with the corresponding terminology: *distinctio* (= τελεία στιγμή), *media distinctio* (= μέση στιγμή), and *subdistinctio* (= ὑποστιγμή). The proximity between the Greek and the Latin triad can be observed, for example, in the *Ars grammatica* by Aelius Donatus (ca. 320–380). In fact, Donatus' description of the *distinctio*, the *media distinctio*, and the *subdistinctio* seems to be nothing more than a reformulation of the description of the three points that Dionysius provided five centuries before.²⁶ The system elaborated by Nicanor of Alexandria—a grammarian of the early 2nd century CE who earned the nickname of “Stigmatias” (ὁ Στιγματίας, “the punctuator”) because of his focus on punctuation—is also noteworthy.²⁷ Working mainly with the Homeric epics, Nicanor

²³ Dion. Thrax, *Grammar 4* (my translation, based on the Greek text established by J. Lallot, *La grammaire de Denys le Thrace*). On the authorship and datation of this treatise, see above, n. 14.

²⁴ See J. Lallot, *La grammaire de Denys le Thrace*, 20; on the ancient sources on the life of Dionysius of Thrax, see Pfeiffer, *History of Classical Scholarship*, vol. 1, 266.

²⁵ For an overview of these Scholia, see the comments in J. Lallot, *La grammaire de Denys le Thrace*, 69–256.

²⁶ Donatus, *Ars Maior* I,6. On Donatus, see L. Holtz, “Aelius Donatus (um die Mitte des 4. Jahrhunderts n. Chr.),” 109–131. For an edition of the *Ars Maior*, see A. Schönberger: *Die Ars maior des Aelius Donatus: lateinischer Text und kommentierte deutsche Übersetzung einer antiken Lateingrammatik des 4. Jahrhunderts für den fortgeschrittenen Anfängerunterricht*.

²⁷ The story about this surname is found in the Suda; see the article “Νικάνωρ.”

proposed an elaborate model consisting of eight different punctuation marks (five στιγμαί, two υποστιγμαί, and one διαστολή).²⁸

It clearly appears that punctuation, in the general sense of dividing the discourse in an appropriate manner, mattered to ancient authors. Accurate punctuation was recognised as a crucial aspect of delivery, both for euphonic and semantic reasons. In addition, systems of written punctuation existed in antiquity, having been formalised by grammarians. However, these systems were rarely (or only partially) mobilised in manuscripts. This presents a paradox: if aural punctuation was considered so important, why was a system of graphical signs not systematically used to guarantee a correct understanding on the part of the readers and to ensure—in the case of reading aloud—that readers provided the listeners with a correct delivery?

The simplest and perhaps the most convincing explanation is to assume that ancient authors adhered to a particular concept of the art of composition, wherein the syntactic structure of a text must stem from the text itself rather than from external signs (such as punctuation marks). Such an ideology finds its better illustration in the following precept by Aristotle:

... that which is written should be easy to read [εὐανάγνωστον] or easy to utter [εὐφραστον], which is the same thing. Now, this is not the case when there is a number of connecting particles [σύνδεσμοι], or when the punctuation is not easy to do [μὴ ῥάδιον διαστίζαι], as in the writings of Heraclitus. Indeed, punctuating [διαστίζαι] Heraclitus' work is hard, since it is unclear to which [word] another belongs, whether to that which follows or that which precedes, as for instance at the beginning of his writing. He says: "Of this reason which exists always men are ignorant" [τοῦ λόγου τοῦδ' ἐόντος ἀεὶ ἀξύνετοι ἄνθρωποι γίνονται]. Here it is unclear with which of the two words [i.e., "exists" (ἐόντος) or "ignorant" (ἀξύνετοι)] the word "always" [ἀεὶ] belongs.²⁹

Aristotle's view is clear: a text with an ambiguous structure, i.e., where "punctuation is not easy to do" (μὴ ῥάδιον διαστίζαι), is a poorly composed text. It is obvious that Aristotle had a text that had not been previously punctuated by means of graphical marks in mind. The excerpt from Heraclitus represents an example of such an ambiguity. In the sentence quoted, it is unclear whether the word ἀεὶ ("always") should be read with what precedes

²⁸ On this system, see R. Nünlist, "Nicanor's System of Punctuation." The works in which Nicanor exposed his system have been lost, therefore his system is known from two main sources: a scholium to Dionysius Thrax's *Τέχνη Γραμματική*, which presents the system (Hilgard, *Scholia in Dionysii Thracis artem grammaticam*, 24-28; reproduced in R. Nünlist, "Nicanor's System of Punctuation," 133-137), and different scholia to the *Iliad* (for the relevant passages of these scholia, see R. Nünlist, "Nicanor's System of Punctuation," 137-138).

²⁹ Arist., *Rhet.* III,5,6-7 (my translation).

(thus: “the reason which *always* exists”) or with what follows (thus: “men are *always* ignorant”). In contrast, a well-composed text should be easy for readers to punctuate (i.e., easy to divide) despite the absence of punctuation marks. Therefore, if we assume that Aristotle’s opinion on punctuation (in the general sense of “discourse division” or “discourse segmentation”) is not original but rather reflects a trend of thought in Graeco-Roman antiquity, we may advance the hypothesis that the non-systematic use of punctuation marks in ancient manuscripts was at least partially due to such signs being considered unnecessary.³⁰ More precisely, reading aids in the form of punctuation marks were *supposed* to be superfluous, as words were *supposed* to be chosen and arranged in a way that made their syntactic relationships sufficiently clear.³¹

2.1.3. Colometry as a “decoding code”

This brings me to insist on an aspect of colometry that I have thus far only briefly alluded to.³² The system of colometry was not designed only as a framework of composition for authors, but was also envisioned as a framework of interpretation for readers and listeners.³³ This is evidenced by the fact that ancient rhetoricians discussed colometry in relation to style (*elocutio*) as well as in relation to aspects of their works that were devoted to the art and pragmatic of delivery (*actio* or *pronunciatio*).³⁴ It may be fairly assumed that colometry conventions were supposed to compensate for the lack of punctuation marks (which does not mean that this was the primary purpose of colometry).

Of course, this is merely the theory. In practice, there were likely more nuances, as shown by Aristophanes’ and Aristarchus’ undertakings as well as the systems of punctuation proposed by ancient grammarians. Within the Christian tradition, the habits of not punctuating sacred texts led to multiple and sometimes vigorous debates on interpretation. Readings judged incompatible with the Christian doctrine were rejected as “heretical.” This can be seen in the vivid debates surrounding the expression ὁ θεός

³⁰ I reject the assertion sometimes made that ancient manuscripts were typically not punctuated because of the cost of making documents, i.e., the quasi-absence of punctuation marks would be merely due to a desire to save paper. This idea is found e.g. in B. Witherington, *New Testament Rhetoric: An Introductory Guide to the Art of Persuasion in and of the New Testament*, 2.

³¹ As a complementary explanation for the rare use of punctuation marks in ancient manuscripts, we can conclude (in agreement with Johnson) that the deliberate choice not to punctuate texts was intended to reflect the elite nature of the cultural settings where these manuscripts were meant to be read (W. Johnson, “Toward a Sociology of Reading in Classical Antiquity”).

³² See above the general introduction as well as the introduction to Chapter 3.

³³ See Nässelqvist, *Public Reading*, who insists on this point (esp. pages 325–326).

³⁴ See Quint., *Inst.* XI,3.

τοῦ αἰῶνος τούτου in 2 Cor 4:4. It is uncertain whether this expression should be read without any break (thus: “[in whom] the god of this world [has blinded the minds of the unbelievers]”) or with a break after θεός, in which case τοῦ αἰῶνος τούτου refers to the unbelievers rather than to God (thus: “God, of the unbelievers of this world has blinded the minds.”) Unsurprisingly, the former option was harshly rejected by the Church fathers—notably Irenaeus—as it may imply that they are two distinct gods, “one god of this world, but another who is beyond all principality, and beginning, and power.”³⁵ Centuries later, Photius also discussed this passage. In order to prevent from a dualist interpretation, he recommended that a point should be included in manuscripts between ὁ θεός and τοῦ αἰῶνος τούτου.³⁶

Other debates about the correct division of NT passages can be found in Augustine’s *Christian Doctrine*. When discussing the importance of accurately punctuating sacred texts,³⁷ Augustine notably included the opening of John’s Gospel (John 1:1–2) as an example:

Here is a division that is heretical: “*In principio erat verbum, et verbum erat apud Deum, et Deus erat*” (“In the beginning was the Word, and the Word was with God, and God was”). It makes the next sentence run as follows: “*Verbum hoc erat in principio apud Deum*” (“The Word was with God from the beginning”), which denies that the Word was God. But this error must be rejected by the rule of faith, which, by teaching us the equality of the Trinity, directs us to read “*et Deus erat verbum*” (“and the Word was God”) and then to add “*hoc erat in principio apud Deum*” (“He was with God from the beginning”).³⁸

Here, Augustine recognises that there is an ambiguity in the text (in this case, the Latin translation). The issue is whether a break should occur between *erat* and *verbum* (“*et Deus erat / verbum hoc erat in principio apud Deum*”) or between *verbum* and *hoc* (thus “*et Deus erat verbum / hoc erat in principio apud Deum*”). To resolve this ambiguity, Augustine explains that one must rely on what he calls “the rule of faith.” Following this rule, it is clear that the latter option is preferable, since the first proposition would deny the divinity of the Word that the rule of faith teaches and should thus be rejected as heretical.

³⁵ Irenaeus, *Adv. Her.* III,7,1. Also see *Adv. Her.* III,7,2, where Irenaeus discusses the difficulty of punctuating 2 Th 2:8.

³⁶ See N. G. Wilson, *Scholars of Byzantium*, 117–119.

³⁷ August., *Doc. Chr.* III,2,2–5.

³⁸ August., *Doct. Christ.* III,2,3 (my translation).

In addition to these few examples, the more frequent use of punctuation signs in Christian manuscripts³⁹ also attests to the difficulties that readers encountered while dealing with non-punctuated texts. Reading in antiquity, which almost systematically meant reading aloud, was incontestably a difficult task.⁴⁰ Besides the physical challenges of maintaining the breath and accompanying the performance with appropriate gestures,⁴¹ ancient readers were left to their own syntactical interpretations considerably often more than readers are today. As William A. Johnson said: “A surprising amount of the burden to interpret the text was shifted from author to reader.”⁴² Accordingly, reading aloud was clearly not to be done spontaneously. On the contrary, reading without preparation was likely a rather rare practice. In the *Satyricon*, the figure of Trimalchio expresses his profound admiration for a slave who was able to “read a book at sight” (*librum ab oculo legit*).⁴³ Reading typically required preparatory work,⁴⁴ during which the reader notably had to analyse the micro-structure of the text at stake. It seems that this preparatory work sometimes involved the suppletion of graphical marks to signal the places of articulation and the breathing breaks, specifically in order to facilitate the reading.⁴⁵ That being said, ancient Greek and Latin readers—including the first readers of Paul’s letters—were arguably not completely left to themselves in their task of punctuating texts. Conversely, it may be fairly assumed that they were guided by a whole series of structuration conventions related to colometry that acted as a sort of “decoding code.” This concretely means that the first readers of Paul were probably much better equipped to grasp the micro-structure of his apostolic letters than modern readers are.

³⁹ See L. Hurtado, “Manuscripts and the Sociology of Early Christian Reading,” esp. 58.

⁴⁰ For a detailed study of the culture of reading in antiquity focused on the case of Rome, see E. Valette-Cagnac, *La lecture à Rome* and C. Salles, *Lire à Rome*. Also see W. A. Johnson, “Toward a Sociology of Reading in Classical Antiquity”; D. Nässelqvist, *Public Reading*, 17–62. On the specific case of reading in early Christian communities, see Nässelqvist, *Public Reading* 63–118; L. Hurtado, “Manuscripts and the Sociology of Early Christian Reading.”

⁴¹ For a description of gestures that were typically associated with public reading, see Quint., *Inst.* XI,3,65–136.

⁴² W. A. Johnson, “Toward a Sociology of Reading in Classical Antiquity,” 620.

⁴³ Petronius, *Satyricon* 74–75.

⁴⁴ On this preparatory work, see e.g. Nässelqvist, *Public Reading*, 26–29.

⁴⁵ See W. A. Johnson, “Toward a Sociology of Reading in Classical Antiquity,” 620, esp. n. 39; also see Feeney, “*Hic finis fandi*: On the Absence of Punctuation for the Endings (and Beginnings) of Speeches in Latin Poetic Texts,” 47–48: “The norm (...) would have been that it was up to the individual reader to mark up a text if he wanted to, relying on his own interpretation of what it meant and how it ran; in particular, the reader could use *distinctiones* or *punctūs* to signal places to pause or stop.” But cf. L. Hurtado, who, in the case of early NT manuscripts, insists that the punctuation marks were inscribed by the copyists, not by the readers (“Manuscripts and the Sociology of Early Christian Reading,” 58).

2.2. *Uttering cōla and periods: Pauses, breathing, and intonation*

We now move on from the ancient views on punctuation to explore the more concrete issue of the delivery of texts. What did the aural punctuation observed by ancient readers look like? How ought the colometric structure of a text to be rendered, when reading aloud, in terms of the different kinds of pauses and their associated intonation? The ancient sources are full of allusions to these questions. Notably, there are some very concrete instructions regarding intonation, pauses, and breathing found under the pen of Quintilian.⁴⁶ When taken together, these passages give us a rather solid—though general—idea of the ancient conventions of “punctuating” texts by means of aural signals.

2.2.1. *The importance of breathing*

The issue of breathing appears to be the backbone of the entire theory of delivery. Reading aloud indeed involves the challenge of maintaining a regular and pleasant sound, especially before a group. The intelligibility for the listeners is essential, as they receive texts as a linear stream and have no possibility of going back to hear a difficult passage again.⁴⁷ Another reason for this recommended brevity is more trivial: the limited respiratory capacity of the readers.⁴⁸ Indeed, periods were generally meant to be pronounced in a single breath. Although it is possible that the respiratory capacity of ancient orators and readers was superior as the result of an intense practice and training,⁴⁹ it still remains that it was not infinite. In many ways, this fact seems to have shaped not only the art of composition but also the delivery conventions.

Among ancient rhetoricians, Quintilian provides us with the most instructive breathing suggestions. His general rule centres around the need to find the balance between two extremes; specifically, the respirations must neither be too frequent nor too scarce:

As to breath, it should not be taken so often that we break up the sense [*spiritus quoque nec crebro receptus concidat sententiam*]; nor yet should it be held until we fail [*nec eo usque trahatur donec deficiat*]. In fact, when we are exhausted the sound becomes unpleasant; and the breathing resembles that of a man who has been held under water for a while,

⁴⁶ Quint., *Inst.* XI,3,33–65.

⁴⁷ Arist., *Rhet.* III,9,6; Dem., *Eloc.* 16; *Rhet. Her.* IV,12,18; Cic., *De or.* III,191; Quint., *Inst.* IX,4,125. Also see Anonym. *Seg., Pol.* 245. On this, see above, Chapter 3, section 3.1.

⁴⁸ See e.g., Cic. *De or.* III, 191. Cf. *Rhet. Her.* IV,12,18.

⁴⁹ See Quint., *Inst.* XI,3,33–65.

and the fresh intake is long and inopportune, since it happens when it must and not when we choose.⁵⁰

The first extreme involves breathing each time readers “break up the sense.” Even if Quintilian is not explicit on this point, we can conclude that he is alluding to the breaks between the *côla*. The second extreme involves waiting too long before breathing, thereby producing an unpleasant sound as well as inopportune and overly long respirations. The end of the above excerpt also establishes the basic principle that respirations should occur “when we choose,” rather than when needed; that is, taking breath at the right place and in an appropriate manner represented an integral part of the art of delivering. It seems that there was, a real technique or art to managing the breath, at least in Quintilian’s mind.

2.2.2. Uttering a passage in periodic style

One certain point is that periods ought to be recited in a suspensive manner; that is, with only slight pauses separating their *côla* and with a continuing prosody (with the exception of the last *côlon*, which is marked by a conclusive prosody and associated with a longer pause). This is made explicit in a comment by Augustine. He speaks of “the *ambitus* or *circuitus*, that the Greeks name *period*, whose *membra* are pronounced in a suspensive manner until the end of the last one.”⁵¹ The comparison frequently found in the rhetorical treatises between the period and a (circular) race—or the period and a circle⁵²—also perfectly corresponds with this description.

As concerns the internal pauses within periods, Quintilian’s description is especially instructive. He explains that pauses occur between each *côlon* of a period; these pauses should be short in order to avoid breaking the structure of the whole:

There are sometimes also pauses [*morae*] without respiration even in periods. Hence, in *In coetu vero populi Romani, negotium publicum gerens, magister equitum*,⁵³ and so on, there are many *membra* (there are a number of thoughts, one after another) but only one period [*sed unam circumductionem*]; so it is a case for placing short pauses [*paulum morandum*] in the intervals, not for breaking up the structure of the whole [*non interrompendus est contextus*].⁵⁴

⁵⁰ Quint., *Inst.* XI,3,53 (my translation).

⁵¹ August., *Doct. Christ.* IV,7,11 (my translation).

⁵² See e.g., Arist., *Rhet.* III,9,2; Dem., *Eloc.* II; Cic., *Or. Brut.*, 207 (also *ibid.*, 204 and 208). On the notion of circularity, cf. above, Chapter 2, sections 3.2.4 and 5.2.1.

⁵³ Cicero, *Philippics* 2,63.

⁵⁴ Quint., *Inst.*, II,3,39 (my translation).

Another point to note in this extract is that these pauses in question do not include a respiration. This echoes Cicero's remark that periods should not be "longer than the strength and the breath can last."⁵⁵ But things were more subtle in reality. In an another passage immediately following his general recommendations on breathing (see above, section 2.2.1), Quintilian distinguishes two different situations:

So, when about to utter a lengthy period, the breath should be collected [*colligendus est spiritus*]; but we should not take a long time over it, do it noisily, or make it in any way obvious. At other points, the best strategy will be to recover breath at the junctures of the discourse [*inter iuncturas sermonis*].⁵⁶

The first situation considered are long periods. In these periods, Quintilian explains that the breath should be "collected." In view of the recommendation that immediately follows, he is certainly alluding to the possibility of breathing within periods in order to avoid the problems previously mentioned (unpleasant sound and overly long respirations). These breaths should be discrete and almost imperceptible. Quintilian contrasts with the "normal" situation, wherein breath should be recovered at the junctures of the discourse: in this context, the junctures are arguably the boundaries between periods, which correspond to the moments where there is enough time to rest and recover breath. The possibility of breathing surreptitiously in the middle of a long period appears to be a concession made to ensure the readers have enough air to complete the period at stake.⁵⁷

Quintilian's testimony is also instructive concerning the manner of concluding a period. In particular, Quintilian makes it clear that there is not a fixed way to mark off the end of a period by means of an aural signal. On the contrary, there is room for nuances, depending on "whether it [the *distinctio*] marks the end of a *sermo* or of a *sensus*."⁵⁸ He illustrates with the beginning of the *Aeneid*:

I shall take a new breath immediately after the *distinctio* at *litora*, but when I come to *atque altae moenia Romae*, I shall deposit [*deponam*] and wait [*morabor*] and make a fresh beginning [*novum rursus exordium faciam*].⁵⁹

⁵⁵ Cic. *De or.* III, 191 (cf. above, Chapter 2, section 5.2.3. Cf. *Rhet. Her.* IV, 12, 18).

⁵⁶ Quint., *Inst.*, II, 3, 53 (my translation). Cf. above, Chapter 2, section 7.2.4.

⁵⁷ Perhaps it is also these kinds of discrete breaths that Cicero has in mind when he specifies, after his initial statement that "the longest group of words is that which can be reeled off in one breath," that "nature has its limits, and art has other ones." (Cic. *De or.* III, 182 [my translation]).

⁵⁸ Quint., *Inst.*, II, 3, 37 (my translation).

⁵⁹ Quint., *Inst.* XI, 3, 38 (translation D. A. Russel, slightly modified). The text referred to here is the very beginning of Virgil's *Aeneid* (I, lines 1–7).

The passage that Quintilian refers to runs as follows (here, I reproduce the modern punctuation found in the LCL edition⁶⁰; the two places of *distinctiones* that Quintilian alludes to are marked by a double vertical bar):

*Arma virumque cano, Troiae qui primus ab oris Italiam fato profugus Laviniaque venit Litora. ||
Multum ille et terris iactatus et alto vi superum, saevae memorem Iunonis ob iram, multa quoque et
bello passus, dum conderet urbem, inferretque deos Latio; genus unde Latinum Albanique patres
atque altae moenia Romae. ||*

Quintilian indicates that strong breaks (*distinctiones*) are warranted at least after *litora* and after *Romae*—he does not make it clear whether one or more other *distinctiones* must be placed elsewhere in the passage. Assuming that Quintilian effectively regards these two places as corresponding to the ends of periods (this is not made fully explicit⁶¹), he is concretely illustrating that not all periods should be punctuated in the same way in terms of the final break and intonation. The length of the final break as well as the intonation that precedes it has to be adapted to the context. This might be compared to the fact that we do not apply the same kind of prosody to all sentences when we read aloud a text.

In summation, periods are meant to be pronounced in a suspensive manner, with the internal boundaries between the *côla* marked by short pauses. The final *côlon* is marked by a final prosody (in principle, a falling intonation), whereas the ends of the preceding *côla* present a continuing prosody. If we refer to the modern conception of the phonological hierarchy, periods could most readily be compared to what we call an “utterance” (U),⁶² in which each *côlon* would consist of an “intonational phrase” (I-phrase)⁶³; in other words, each *côlon* has a coherent intonation contour within the period. The typical prosodic realisation of a period might be illustrated as follows, where |

⁶⁰ Virgil, *Aeneid* I,1 (*Ecloques. Georgics. Aeneid: Books 1-6* [LCL], 262). For the rest, I keep the punctuation found in the LCL edition, though it might not correspond to what Quintilian would have recommended. In particular, it is unclear whether this passage should, in Quintilian’s view, include other *distinctiones*.

⁶¹ The broader context of the passage (*Inst.* XI,3,35–39; see esp. the beginning of 39) makes almost certain that Quintilian speaks here about the pronunciation of the end of periods. The poetic nature of the extract is not a problem: significantly, Quintilian does not even allude to the structure in verses, which suggests that he is treating this extract as prose. On the possibility of analysing poetry as if it were prose, see Dion. Hal., *Comp.* 22–26.

⁶² On the notion of “utterance,” see D. Goldstein, “Utterance.”

⁶³ D. Goldstein, “Intonational Phrase.” As Goldstein notes, there are different terms used to refer to this prosodic constituent, such as “intermediate phrase” (Janet B. Pierrehumbert, *The Phonology and Phonetics of English Intonation*), “tone unit” (M. A. K. Halliday, *Intonation and Grammar in British English*), or “intonation unit” (W. Chafe, *Discourse, Consciousness, and Time: The Flow and Displacement of Conscious Experience in Speaking and Writing*, 53–70). On the intonational phrase in Ancient Greek, see A. M. Devine and L. D. Stephens, *The Prosody of Greek Speech*, esp. 409–455 (note that Devine and Stephens refer to the intonational phrase as the “major phrase”).

indicates a break marked by a continuing prosody, and || marks the stronger break of a final prosody:

Ἔργων γὰρ εὖ πραχθέντων | λόγῳ καλῶς ῥηθέντι | μνήμη καὶ κόσμος γίνεται | τοῖς πράξασι παρὰ τῶν ἀκουσάντων || (Plato, *Menexenus* 236e)⁶⁴

Εἴ τις πέποιθεν ἑαυτῷ Χριστοῦ εἶναι | τοῦτο λογιζέσθω πάλιν ἐφ' ἑαυτοῦ | ὅτι καθὼς αὐτὸς Χριστοῦ | οὕτως καὶ ἡμεῖς || (2 Corinthians 10:11)

2.2.3. Uttering a passage in disjointed style

What about the pronunciation of autonomous *côla* and *commata*? From the few ancient descriptions alluding to this question, we can conclude that the breaks marking the boundaries between non-periodic *côla* and/or *commata* were more evident than those occurring between the periodic ones, at least as a general rule. Augustine notably commented on the pronunciation differences between the two kinds of *côla*. Specifically, he said that autonomous *côla* and *commata* are each pronounced separately⁶⁵; this is in contrast with the *membra* of a period, which “are pronounced in a suspensive manner until the end of the last one.” Cicero seems to refer to the same idea when he noted that “if we wish to speak in *membra*, we stop, and when necessary, easily and often turn off from a course [the period’s course] which offends.”⁶⁶ In view of its immediate literary context, Cicero’s remark clearly refers to the delivery of non-periodic *côla*. It is very clear that the distinction between the two kinds of *côla* has notably to do with their respective delivery (or their “prosodic realisation”) differing. Namely, non-periodic *côla* present an intonation contour that is sufficiently discernible to make them appear as autonomous from a prosodic point of view.

Therefore, in terms of phonological hierarchy, an autonomous *côlon* might be compared to an intonational phrase that forms an utterance on its own, or to a short utterance comprising only one intonational unit.⁶⁷ Keeping the double vertical bar as a way to indicate final prosodic boundaries, the prosodic realisation of a passage in disjointed style could be represented as in the two examples below:

⁶⁴ As quoted by Dionysius of Halicarnassus in *Comp.* 9,4.

⁶⁵ August., *Doct. Christ.* IV,7,11.

⁶⁶ Cic., *Or. Brut.*, 222 (trans. G. L. Hendrickson, H. M. Hubbell [LCL]).

⁶⁷ On these two concepts, see D. Goldstein, “Utterance,” and Id., “Intonational Phrase.”

Ἑκαταῖος Μιλήσιος ὧδε μυθεῖται || τάδε γράφω ὥς μοι δοκεῖ ἀληθέα εἶναι || οἱ γὰρ Ἑλλήνων λόγοι πολλοί τε καὶ γελοῖοι ὡς ἐμοὶ φαίνονται εἶσιν ||
(Hecataeus, *Genealogies* 1)⁶⁸

Ἰσραηλιταὶ εἶσιν || κἀγὼ || σπέρμα Ἀβραάμ εἶσιν || κἀγὼ || Διάκονοι Χριστοῦ εἶσιν ||
Παραφρονῶν λαλῶ | ὑπὲρ ἐγὼ ||
(2 Corinthians 11:22–23)

That said, the distinction stressed by some rhetoricians between the monocôlon period and the autonomous cōlon implies that the typical pronunciation of these two units should differ in some way. We may for example think that the end of an autonomous cōlon was less obvious than the end of a period, whether in terms of intonation (the intonation was perhaps not as “concluding” as that occurring at the end of a period) or in terms of the length of the pause (the length was arguably shorter than the pause typically observed after a period).

2.2.4. *Internal breaks within cōla*

In addition to the two levels of prosodic units identified above (utterance = period or autonomous cōlon; intonational phrase = periodic cōlon), Quintilian alludes to what seems to be a third, inferior level that concerns the internal structure of cōla:

For, while the beginnings and the clausulae are most important whenever a thought begins and ends, there are also, as it were, fresh starts in the middle part, and these involve light pauses—just as the foot of a runner, even though it does not rest, still leaves a print. So not only must members and incisa begin and end properly, but even in parts which are unquestionably linked together and involve no pause for breath, there are these, as it were, hidden stages. Who can doubt that there is only one thought [*unum sensum*] and one breath [*unum spiritum*] in *Animadverti iudices, omnem accusatoris orationem, in duas, divisam esse partes?* Yet the two first words, the next three, and then again the next two and three, have their own special rhythms (*quasi numeros habent*); and we maintain our breathing [*spiritum sustinemus*] as determined by the rhythm. And as these subsections are solemn or vigorous, slow or quick, relaxed or excited, so the whole which is made up of them will be austere or lavish, compact or unstructured.⁶⁹

In the Ciceronian saying “*Animadverti iudices, omnem accusatoris orationem, in duas, divisam esse partes,*”⁷⁰ Quintilian identifies three internal divisions, which results in the separation

⁶⁸ As quoted by Demetrius, *Eloc.* 12.

⁶⁹ Quint., *Inst.* IX,4,68–69 (trans. D. A. Russell [LCL]; slightly modified).

⁷⁰ Cic., *Pro Cluentio* 1.

of the saying into four short units: “*animadverti iudices*,” “*omnem accusatoris orationem*,” “*in duas*” and “*divisam esse partes*.” In view of the remark that the saying in question consists of “only one thought [*unum sensum*] and one breath [*unum spiritum*],” it is likely that these four units together form a cōlon, rather than standing each as an individual cōlon. This understanding is supported by the immediate literary context—more precisely by the preceding sentence, where Quintilian stipulates that “not only must members and incisa begin and end properly, but even in parts which are unquestionably linked together and involve no pause for breath, there are these, as it were, hidden stages.” Hence, it may fairly be concluded that Quintilian has a distinct kind of unit in mind, one that is a subpart of a cōlon and is generally made up of two or three words.

As concerns the prosodic realisation of such groups of words within cōla, Quintilian indicates that each group has its own rhythm. His explanations make it clear that very short pauses mark the boundaries between these rhythmic units. Specifically, Quintilian compares these pauses to the prints left by the foot of a runner: the runner does not stop at each footstep, but nevertheless each of his or her footsteps leaves a mark. This clearly implies that the breaks placed between these word groups ought to be much more discrete than those occurring between (periodic) cōla. As an analogy, in reference to the phonological hierarchy, we may compare such small rhythmical units to “phonological phrases”; or rather, the constituent that stands immediately beneath the intonational phrase in the prosodic hierarchy.⁷¹

This is arguably also the kind of slight pauses that Quintilian had in mind when he stated—in reference to the pronunciation of the first period of Virgil’s *Aeneid*—that “suspensions” are needed after *Italiam* and before *Laviniaque* “because *fato profugus* is parenthetical and interrupts the continuity of *Italiam* and *Laviniaque*.”⁷² The pronunciation of this period could thus be presented as follows (with the simple vertical bar indicating a cōlon-boundary marked by a continuing prosody, the double vertical bar indicating the end of the period marked by a final prosody, and the straight apostrophes signalling the two points of “suspension” within the last cōlon):

*Arma virumque cano | Troiae qui primus ab oris | Italiam ' fato profugus ' Laviniaque venit
Litora ||*

⁷¹ On the concept of “phonological phrase,” see D. Goldstein, “Phonological Phrase.”

⁷² Quint., *Inst.* XI,4,36–37 (trans. D. A. Russell [LCL]). In this context, Quintilian uses a passive form of the verb *suspendo*.

In Paul's prose, such brief pauses within *côla* should also regularly occur. For instance, in the *dicôloi* period of 2 Cor 10:10, we may assume that light pauses are warranted before and after *φησίν* in the first *côlon*, and then between *ἀσθενής* and *καί*, in the second *côlon*:

Ὅτι αἱ ἐπιστολαὶ μὲν ᾗ φησίν ᾗ βαρεῖαι καὶ ἰσχυραὶ | ἡ δὲ παρουσία τοῦ σώματος
ἀσθενήσ᾿ καὶ ὁ λόγος ἐξουθενημένος ||

2.2.5. Results and limits

From the above, a system of aural punctuation emerges: this can be summarised in a table. For each kind of unit (i.e., period; periodic *côlon*; autonomous *côlon*; word or group of word within a *côlon*), the table indicates which prosodic unit of the phonological hierarchy it might be compared to, what the intonation contour looks like, what kind of break occurs at the end, and whether a respiration may occur at the end.

Table 3: A system of aural punctuation

	Period	Periodic <i>côlon</i>	Autonomous <i>côlon</i>	Rhythmic unit (word or group of words within a <i>côlon</i>)
Phonological hierarchy	utterance (U)	intonational phrase (I-phrase)	utterance made of a single intonational phrase (I-phrase)	phonological phrase (P-phrase)
Intonation contour	final, concluding prosody	continuing prosody (except the final <i>côlon</i>)	final prosody (but not completely concluding ?)	continuing prosody
Break at the end	long	short (except the final <i>côlon</i>)	middle	very short
Breathing at the end	yes	possible if needed, but very discrete	possible	no

This theoretical presentation is necessarily schematical. Practices were obviously more nuanced and depended not only on the habits and preferences of the reader but also certainly on the style of the text and the passage at stake. Furthermore, they arguably depended upon the syntactical and logical relationships between the different units

being uttered. For example, in the case of a passage with a disjointed style, we can imagine that readers varied both the intonation contour and the length of the breaks between the *côla*. While some autonomous *côla* were punctuated with a fully concluding prosody (i.e., in the same way as or a similar manner as the end of a period), some others were marked by an intonation that is of a style between a final and a continuing prosody. We may also postulate that “loose” periods (e.g., those that Pseudo-Demetrius called “conversational periods”⁷³) were pronounced in a somewhat less suspensive way than the more “circular” ones,⁷⁴ with longer silences being observed between their *côla* (this characteristic makes them similar to a disjointed style at the level of prosody).⁷⁵ This brings us back to the idea that the division between the periodic and the non-periodic styles is malleable.⁷⁶ Indeed, it is malleable not only in terms of syntax, but certainly also with respect to delivery.

2.3. *Intermediate conclusion*

In summary, in Graeco-Roman antiquity, (written) punctuation marks were not regarded as an integral part of texts. Such graphical signs were rather seen as a secondary, optionnal, and somehow *ideologically* unnecessary codification. In accordance with this conception, punctuation marks were not typically placed by the scribes that the authors dictated to, but were sometimes added (in a far from systematic way) by later scribes or readers. In this regard, the ancient conception of punctuation could not differ more strongly from our modern conception wherein punctuation marks are normally placed by the authors themselves and are an integral part of a text to the extent that they should be reproduced consistently when copying, reediting, or quoting. Notwithstanding these obvious differences, punctuation (in the general sense of marking the divisions of a text) did still matter to ancient authors. Rhetoricians and interpreters were plenty aware of the interpretational errors that may result from faulty text divisions. Beyond the issues strictly related to the meaning, they considered aural punctuation (i.e., the punctuation placed by the readers during delivery by means of breaks and intonation) to be a crucial aspect of the art of delivery.

⁷³ Dem., *Eloc.* 21.

⁷⁴ See e.g., Demetrius’ description of “rhetorical periods” (Dem., *Eloc.* 20).

⁷⁵ See Quint., *Inst.* IX,4,127.

⁷⁶ See the discussion above, in Chapter 3, section 3.2.

Regarding the ways that ancient readers dealt with non-punctuated or sparsely punctuated manuscripts, they may have relied on a series of stylistic conventions that served as a guide to help them grasp the micro-structure of the text at stake. In this manner, they were certainly more armed than modern readers would be when confronting the same manuscripts. In other words, the structural logic of a text was supposed to be clear enough for readers without the addition of punctuation marks. Specifically, I have advanced the hypothesis that the system of colometry served as a shared “code” between authors and readers. At least theoretically, this code allowed the readers not only to understand the structure of a text but also to punctuate it in an appropriate manner when reading it aloud. Furthermore, based on the ancient sources—including Quintilian, Cicero and Augustine—I have outlined a general picture of how a text in *côla* and periods was meant to be uttered. According to the ancient conventions of *pronunciatio*, each kind of colometric unit (period; periodic *côlon*; autonomous *côlon*; word or group of words within a *côlon*) is associated with a specific kind of prosody, especially in terms of the length of the pauses that mark their boundaries.

3. Benefits of Colometry for Resolving Syntactic Ambiguities in Paul’s Letters: A Few Examples from 2 Cor 10–13

In the exegesis of Paul’s letters, there are long-lasting debates over the syntactic logic of some passages. These debates often go hand in hand with punctuation issues, as the question generally is whether a word, a phrase, or a clause belongs with what precedes or with what follows. Emblematic passages include Rom 9:4–5, where the question of whether Paul calls Christ God depends on the choice between a comma or a full stop;⁷⁷ or 1 Thessalonians 2:14–16, where the presence or the absence of a comma yields to

⁷⁷ The literature on this passage is immense: see, among others, T. Dwight, “On Romans ix.5”; E. Abbot, “On the Construction of Romans ix. 5”; Id., “Recent Discussions on Rom. IX. 5”; W. Sanday et A. C. Headlam, *A Critical and Exegetical Commentary on the Epistle to the Romans*, 233–238; A. Durand, “La divinité de Jésus-Christ dans St. Paul, Rom. IX,5”; F. C. Burkitt, “On Romans ix.5 and Mark xiv.61”; H. M. Faccio, *De divinitate Christi: juxta S. Paulum, Rm 9,5*; R. Brown, “Does the New Testament Call Jesus God?”; B. M. Metzger, “The Punctuation of Rom. 9:5”; O. Kuss, “Zu Römer 9,5”; M. Harris, *Jesus as God: The New Testament Use of Theos in Reference to Jesus*, 144–172; H.-C. Kammler, “Die Prädikation Jesu Christi als “Gott” und die paulinische Christologie. Erwägungen zur Exegese von Röm 9,5b”; G. Carraway, *Christ is God over All: Romans 9:5 in the Context of Romans 9–11*. For a colometric approach to Rm 9:5, see P. Marschall “Christ est-il appelé Dieu en Romains 9:5? L’argument des figures gorgianiques” (forthcoming).

diverging understandings of Paul’s view on Judaism;⁷⁸ or 2 Corinthians 10:8–11, where the choice between a minor punctuation (a comma) or a major punctuation (a full stop) before v. 9 produces different pictures of how Paul envisions his authority.⁷⁹ On such occasions, exegetes are usually left to evaluate the likelihood construction of various constructions in light of the literary context, as well as in view of Paul’s stylistic habits and his theology.

To what extent might an attention to colometry help in dealing with such ambiguous passages? Let us explore this with a few examples taken from 2 Cor 10–13. Below, we will examine a selection of passages in which the punctuation (or alternatively, the “segmentation” or the “division”) is disputed. For each, we shall discuss whether an attention to their colometric structure may illuminate the syntactic logic.

3.1. *The series of participles in 10:4c–6*

^[3] ἐν σαρκὶ γὰρ περιπατοῦντες οὐ κατὰ σάρκα στρατευόμεθα ^[4] τὰ γὰρ ὄπλα τῆς στρατείας ἡμῶν οὐ σαρκικά ἀλλὰ δυνατὰ τῷ θεῷ πρὸς καθαίρεσιν ὀχυρωμάτων λογισμοῦς καθαροῦντες ^[5] καὶ πᾶν ὑψωμα ἐπαιρόμενον κατὰ τῆς γνώσεως τοῦ θεοῦ καὶ αἰχμαλωτίζοντες πᾶν νόημα εἰς τὴν ὑπακοὴν τοῦ Χριστοῦ ^[6] καὶ ἐν ἐτοιμίῳ ἔχοντες ἐκδικῆσαι πᾶσαν παρακοὴν ὅταν πληρωθῇ ὑμῶν ἡ ὑπακοή

There are two main ways of understanding the series of three plural participles in vv. 10:4c–6 (καθαροῦντες, αἰχμαλωτίζοντες, ἔχοντες). Grammatically speaking, these participles can either be considered dependent upon the verb στρατευόμεθα in v. 3, or be taken as absolutes that are independent from what precedes. In the first option, v. 4a–b forms an explanative parenthesis, and the three participles of v. 4c–6 then define the means of the warfare (“we wage war ... *by means of* destroying arguments..., *and by* making captive every thought..., *and by* standing ready to punish any trace of disobedience...”).⁸⁰ Critical editions seem to follow this option by punctuating vv. 3–6 as

⁷⁸ On this punctuation issue, see F. D. Gilliard, “The Problem of the Antisemitic Comma between 1 Thessalonians 2.14 and 15”; C. Amphoux, “1 Th 2, 14-16: Quels Juifs sont-ils mis en cause par Paul ?”; M.-F. Baslez, “Transmission et surinterprétation des textes religieux. L’imprécation de Paul contre les Juifs (1 Thessaloniens 2,15-16).”

⁷⁹ On 2 Cor 10:8–11, see the detailed discussion and the references to secondary literature below, under section 3.2. Also see P. Marschall, “Punctuating Paul’s Letters in Light of the Ancient Theory of Cōla and Periods.”

⁸⁰ See e.g., A. J. Malherbe, *Ancient Epistolary Theorists*, 166, n. 130. Cf. also A. Plummer, *2 Corinthians*, 275, who notes that “in form this verse [4a-b] is a parenthesis to confirm the truth of the preceding statement, and καθαροῦντες in v. 5 goes back in grammatical constr. to στρατευόμεθα in v. 3.” However, Plummer considers that “in idea καθαροῦντες is obviously connected with πρὸς καθαίρεσιν in v. 4, and the const. of v. 3 seems to be forgotten” (*2 Corinthians*, 275). More recently, F. J. Long also considers the construction in

a single sentence: NA²⁸, UBS⁵, and NTGM⁸¹ punctuate the entire sequence of vv. 3–6 with commas; a full stop only occurs after ἡ ὑπακοή. The Westcott Hort [WH] edition⁸² even makes use of dashes to emphasise the parenthetical status of v. 4. In contrast, most commentators (and most translations) prefer to construe the three participle independently from v. 3, thus taking καθαροῦντες, αἰχμαλωτίζοντες and ἔχοντες to be nominative absolutes that should be read as finite verbs (“We destroy arguments ... ; and we make captive every thought ... ; and we stand ready to punish all disobedience ...”).⁸³ If we follow this construction, the resulting meaning does not drastically change, as the three participles of v. 4c-6 still somewhat describe or illustrate how Paul is “waging war.” However, treating these participles as independent rather than dependent on the στρατευόμεθα of v. 3 puts more emphasis on the statement of v. 4a-b: instead of being a parenthetical explanation of v. 3, verse 4 introduces the evidence that Paul was not conducting his campaign according to human standards. In this way, the actions described in v. 4c-6 can be understood as manifestations of the divine nature of Paul’s warfare.

Here, an attention to the colometry of the passage tends to confirm the option preferred by most of the commentators—namely, to take the three participles of v. 4c-6 as independent. Indeed, construing the series of participles with what precedes (as dependent on στρατευόμεθα) would result in an extremely long period of nine cōla and almost 130 syllables. Considering the recommendations and examples given by ancient rhetoricians, this is very unlikely (see T4, T5, and T6).⁸⁴ Therefore, when it comes to punctuating the Greek text of this passage with modern punctuation marks, we should perhaps revise the choice found in modern critical editions and place a supplementary

which καθαροῦντες, αἰχμαλωτίζοντες, and ἔχοντες are dependent on στρατευόμεθα as a valid option (Long, *2 Corinthians: A Handbook on the Greek Text*, 184–185).

⁸¹ Reuben J. Swanson, *New Testament Greek Manuscripts: 2 Corinthians* (published in 2005).

⁸² Here and below, I refer to the 2007 edition (B. F. Westcott and F. J. A. Hort, foreword by E. J. Epp, *The Greek New Testament with Comparative Apparatus showing variations from the Nestle-Aland and Robinson-Pierpont Editions*).

⁸³ See R. Bultmann, *Der zweite Brief an die Korinther* 187; V.P. Furnish, *II Corinthians*, 458–459; J. Lambrecht, *Second Corinthians*, 155; W. Harris, *The Second Epistle to the Corinthians*, 680–681; G.H. Guthrie, *2 Corinthians*, 187; T. Schmeller, *Der zweite Brief an die Korinther*, vol. II, 121. One of the reasons advanced in favour of this option is that the three participles are “masculine nominative plurals and therefore not in agreement with the preceding neuter ὄπλα” (Harris, *The Second Epistle to the Corinthians*, 681). F. J. Long (*II Corinthians: A Handbook on the Greek Text*, 184–185) suggests that the participles may function periphrastically with an implied ἔσμεν (“We are destroying arguments...”).

⁸⁴ On the typical and maximal length of periods, see Chapter 3, section 3.1. For the division of vv. 3–6 into 9 cōla, see above, Chapter 4, section 2.3.

full stop after πρὸς καθαίρεσιν ὀχυρωμάτων (v. 4b) in order to make it clear that the three participles that follow are not dependent on στρατευόμεθα. In sum, colometry supports a new argument in favour of the interpretation that most commentators already defend. Another full stop should arguably be placed between vv. 3 and 4 due to the presence of γάρ at the beginning of v. 4 (see T9). Depending on the details of the colometric analysis, additional full stops might possibly be added between vv. 5a and 5b and between vv. 5 and 6 as well.⁸⁵

3.2. *The ἵνα clause in 10:9*

[8] ἔάν τέ γάρ περισσώτερόν τι καυχῆσωμαι περὶ τῆς ἐξουσίας ἡμῶν ἧς ἔδωκεν ὁ κύριος εἰς οἰκοδομήν καὶ οὐκ εἰς καθαίρεσιν ὑμῶν οὐκ αἰσχυνθήσομαι [9] ἵνα μὴ δόξω ὡς ἂν ἐκφοβεῖν ὑμᾶς διὰ τῶν ἐπιστολῶν [10] ὅτι αἱ ἐπιστολαὶ μὲν φησὶν βαρεῖαι καὶ ἰσχυραὶ ἢ δὲ παρουσία τοῦ σώματος ἀσθενῆς καὶ ὁ λόγος ἐξουθενημένος [11] τοῦτο λογιζέσθω ὁ τοιοῦτος ὅτι οἱοί ἐσμεν τῷ λόγῳ δι’ ἐπιστολῶν ἀπόντες τοιοῦτοι καὶ παρόντες τῷ ἔργῳ

The punctuation of 2 Cor. 10:8–11 is greatly disputed amongst exegetes.⁸⁶ The problem at issue is how the ἵνα clause of v. 9 (lit. “lest I may seem as if I am terrifying you by my letters”) relates syntactically to what precedes or follows. Strictly regarding the grammar, there are three main options, which I briefly present below.

The first option is to consider that v. 9 is looking back to οὐκ αἰσχυνθήσομαι in v. 8, and thus to place a simple comma before ἵνα.⁸⁷ This implies a relation of finality between vv. 8 and 9: namely, v. 9 is the purpose or the result clause of v. 8. A possible translation would be: “I am not ashamed, lest I seem somehow to be terrifying you with my letters.”⁸⁸ This option is often rejected by the exegetes on the grounds that there would be no logical connection between Paul’s refusal to be ashamed and his unwillingness to appear as if he terrifies the Corinthians with his letters.⁸⁹ An alternative argument sometimes

⁸⁵ See the proposed punctuation below, under section 4.3.

⁸⁶ For an overview of the debates, see M. E. Thrall, *The Second Epistle to the Corinthians*, vol. II, 629–629; Harris, *The Second Epistle to the Corinthians*, 695–698.

⁸⁷ In support of this construction, see J. Héring, *La Seconde Epître de Saint Paul aux Corinthiens*, 80; F. M. Young and D. Ford, *Meaning and Truth in 2 Corinthians*, 272; F. J. Long, *2 Corinthians: A Handbook on the Greek Text*, 189; R. Bultmann, *Der zweite Brief an die Korinther*, 191. T. Schmeller also considers this construction as tenable (*Der zweite Brief an die Korinther*, vol. II, 143).

⁸⁸ F. J. Long, *2 Corinthians: A Handbook on the Greek Text*, 186.

⁸⁹ See, for example, R. S. Schellenberg, *Rethinking Paul’s Rhetorical Education*, 267: “There simply is no logical connection between Paul’s refusal to be ashamed and the purpose or result clause that follows.”

found against this construction is that it could imply that Paul intended “to put fear into the Corinthians by his personal presence on his next visit or by his very letters.”⁹⁰ This was suggested, for example, in the translation by Young and Ford (“I will not be shamed into seeming not to terrify you with my letters”⁹¹) or, more explicitly, in the NJB (“... I am not going to be shamed into letting you think that I can put fear into you only by letter.”) Apparently, many commentators regard such an intention on the part of Paul to be fairly unlikely and therefore do not further discuss the possible meaning.⁹²

The second option is to take v. 9 as a protasis stating the purpose of the following clause.⁹³ If this is the case with 2 Cor 10:9–11, then the sentence introduced by ἵνα extends until v. 11, and thus results in a long and quite complex sentence. Specifically, the ἵνα clause expresses the purpose of the main clause in v. 11; v. 10 is an explanatory parenthetical wherein Paul interjects the words of his rivals. A possible loose translation would be: “Lest I should seem to be relying on letters to frighten you into obedience (for this is what they are accusing me of), let anyone who thinks this take note of the fact that what I say in my letters I carry out in practice.”⁹⁴ As Ryan S. Schellenberg rightly points out, “this leaves us with rather garbled syntax,”⁹⁵ not only because the parenthetical v. 10 provides the antecedent of the τοιοῦτος in v. 11,⁹⁶ but also because the transition between vv. 8 and 9 is abrupt (a connective such as δέ or καί would have been expected⁹⁷). However, this construction is regularly defended in the commentaries.⁹⁸

This view seems to be shared by M. E. Thrall, *The Second Epistle to the Corinthians*, vol. II, 626; E. Grässer, *Der zweite Brief an die Korinther*, vol. II, 97; and Windisch, *Der zweite Korintherbrief*, 305.

⁹⁰ Harris, *The Second Epistle to the Corinthians*, 696.

⁹¹ Young and Ford, *Meaning and Truth in 2 Corinthians*, 272.

⁹² See e.g., Harris, *The Second Epistle to the Corinthians*, 696. Also see Guthrie, who, commenting on Young and Ford’s translation (see above in the main text), notes that “the result of this position seems strained at best” (2 *Corinthians*, 481).

⁹³ On this construction, see e.g. BDF 255.

⁹⁴ Harvey, *Renewal through Suffering*, 96, n. 13.

⁹⁵ R. S. Schellenberg, *Rethinking Paul’s Rhetorical Education*, 268.

⁹⁶ R. S. Schellenberg, *Rethinking Paul’s Rhetorical Education*, 268; also see T.≤ Schmeller, *Der zweite Brief an die Korinther*, vol. II, 143.

⁹⁷ See this remark in Héring, *La Seconde Epître de Saint Paul aux Corinthiens*, 72. Also see Meyer, *Critical and Exegetical Handbook to the Epistles to the Corinthians*, vol. II, 402 and Harris, *The Second Epistle to the Corinthians*, 697.

⁹⁸ Commentators who argue for this construction include notably R. P. Martin, 2 *Corinthians*, 310–311; D. E. Garland, 2 *Corinthians*, 445, n. 103; A. E. Harvey, *Renewal through Suffering: A Study of 2 Corinthians*, 96, n. 13; or more recently G. Guthrie, 2 *Corinthians*, 481–482.

Finally, the third option—which seems to represent the majority opinion among the commentators of the past few decades⁹⁹—is to construe v. 9 as an independent sentence that is directly dependent on neither v. 8 nor v. 11. There are then different variants. Some translations treat the ἵνα clause as imperative (thus “May I not seem as one frightening you through letters”¹⁰⁰). However, most commentators with this option argue that the formulation of v. 9 is elliptical. The supplemental words could be, for instance, θέλω (thus “I do not want to seem as if I am terrifying you by my letters...”¹⁰¹) or τοῦτο λέγω (“I say this so that I may not seem as if I am trying to terrify you with my letters”¹⁰²).¹⁰³

The debate surrounding the ἵνα clause in 2 Cor. 10:9 is reflected in the critical editions, where the punctuation of vv. 8–11 is subject to variations. The current editions of the NA (28th ed.) and of the UBS *Greek New Testament* (5th ed.) adopt punctuation that compels the reader to interpret v. 9 (or vv. 9–10) as an independent sentence. Specifically, the NA has full stops between vv. 8 and 9 as well as between vv. 10 and 11, and a high point between v. 9 and v. 10. The UBS edition also has full stops between vv. 8 and 9 and between vv. 10 and 11, but no punctuation at all between v. 9 and 10. Interestingly, former editions of the NA presented a different punctuation: the 25th edition, for example, contained a comma between vv. 8 and 9,¹⁰⁴ thus implying that the ἵνα clause should be read as the purpose or the result of οὐκ αἰσχυνθήσομαι, thus conforming with the first option presented above. Finally, we may note that the Westcott-Hort edition¹⁰⁵ also places a comma between vv. 8 and 9.

Would colometry help to disambiguate the grammar of this passage? Firstly, we can conclude that the second option (i.e., vv. 8–11 constitute a single sentence) seems unlikely in view of the principles of colometry, as it would result in an extremely long period of 140 syllables. Hence, unless one supposes that in this case Paul broke what seems to have been a firmly established convention, the solution to our syntactic issue is certainly to be

⁹⁹ See a similar statement in R. Schellenberg, *Rethinking Paul's Rhetorical Education*, 268.

¹⁰⁰ NAB². Also see BDF § 387. An imperatival construction is also mentioned as a plausible interpretation by T. Schmeller, *Der zweite Brief an die Korinther*, vol. II, 142–143.

¹⁰¹ See e.g. M. Carrez, *La deuxième épître aux Corinthiens*, 201; J. Lambrecht, *Second Corinthians*, 153. A close suggestion is made by V. P. Furnish, *II Corinthians*, 467–468, who supplies βούλομαι.

¹⁰² I reproduce here Harris' proposition of translation (*The Second Epistle to the Corinthians*, 697). In the same sense, see M. E. Thrall, *The Second Epistle to the Corinthians*, vol. II, 626; E. Grässer, *Der zweite Brief an die Korinther*, vol. II, 97.

¹⁰³ See supplementary suggestions to fulfill the ellipsis in A. Plummer, *2 Corinthians*, 299; as well as in C. K. Barrett, *The Second Epistle to the Corinthians*, 259.

¹⁰⁴ The 25th edition of the NA was published in 1963.

¹⁰⁵ See above, footnote 82.

found in one of the two alternative options. Let us now retake the colometric disposition proposed in Chapter 4:

^[8] Ἐάν τε γὰρ περισσότερόν τι καυχῆσωμαι περὶ τῆς ἐξουσίας ἡμῶν (23)

ἧς ἔδωκεν ὁ κύριος εἰς οἰκοδομήν καὶ οὐκ εἰς καθαίρεσιν ὑμῶν (21)

οὐκ αἰσχυνθήσομαι ^[9] ἵνα μὴ δόξω ὡς ἂν ἐκφοβεῖν ὑμᾶς διὰ τῶν ἐπιστολῶν. (24)

According to this disposition, the ἵνα clause of v. 9 is part of a three-côla period that starts with v. 8. More specifically, v. 9 forms the second part of the third cōlon of this period and thus expresses the purpose or the result of οὐκ αἰσχυνθήσομαι. From a strictly stylistic point of view, this is clearly the most convincing option, given that such a delineation yields to a well-balanced period with three cōla that not only rhyme (...ἡμῶν / ... ὑμῶν / ... τῶν ἐπιστολῶν) but also are approximatively the same length (23, 21, and 24 syllables). Furthermore, in light of colometry, can we pursue the third option and take v. 9 as an independent sentence? In this case, the balance of the period is disrupted: a three-côla period remains that presents paromoiosis and parisosis only between its first two cōla, and which is then abruptly concluded with a short cōlon of six syllables (οὐκ αἰσχυνθήσομαι). Indeed, from a stylistic point of view, there is no major issue with this latter option. Paul may have wished to emphasise his absence of shame by devoting a single prosodic line to οὐκ αἰσχυνθήσομαι. Moreover, it might be that the rhyme between ἐπιστολῶν and the preceding ἡμῶν and ὑμῶν, as well as the parisosis that appears when ἵνα μὴ δόξω ὡς ἂν ἐκφοβεῖν ὑμᾶς διὰ τῶν ἐπιστολῶν is read with οὐκ αἰσχυνθήσομαι, are both coincidental. Nevertheless, an attention to the ancient principles of colometry clearly suggests that the first option is preferable, which in turn invites us to re-examine its possible meaning.

The question is thus whether the meaning suggested by the first option of construction (i.e., v. 9 as the purpose or result clause of v. 8) can make sense in the context of 10:8–11. Furthermore, to what extent is it consistent with the broader context of chapters 10–13?¹⁰⁶ Indeed, the issue of the meaning constitutes the precise reason why many commentators so firmly reject the idea of reading v. 9 as dependent on οὐκ αἰσχυνθήσομαι. It would be more accurate to say *meanings* in plural; two distinct arguments are found in the commentaries, which seem to correspond to two diverging understandings of the meaning derived by the construction in which v. 9 is dependent

¹⁰⁶ For a more detailed discussion on this issue, see P. Marschall, “Punctuating Paul’s Letters in Light of the Ancient Theory of Cōla and Periods: The Example of 2 Cor. 10:8–11.”

on v. 8. On one hand, some exegetes propose that there is simply no logical link between Paul's refusal to be ashamed (οὐκ αἰσχυνθήσομαι) and his unwillingness to appear as if he is using the epistolary medium to terrify Corinthians—this seems to reveal that they take for granted that Paul did not at all want to put fear into the Corinthian community.¹⁰⁷ On the other hand, some exegetes believe that there might be a logical connection between v. 8 and v. 9, but they find that the semantic implications are unlikely to correspond to Paul's intention, and therefore also reject this option. According to these exegetes, reading the ἵνα clause of v. 9 together with v. 8 implies that Paul did not see a problem if his letters were considered severe and somewhat frightening.¹⁰⁸ On the contrary, he would even vindicate this severity. Evidently, this idea seems to constitute a problem in the eyes of many exegetes.¹⁰⁹

However, I personally do not find the idea that Paul intended a degree of severity problematic. On the contrary, when taking into account the accusation reported in v. 10 (“For his letters, it is said, are weighty and mighty, but his bodily presence is weak and his speech is contemptible”)¹¹⁰ and the warning against the persons who spread this accusation (v. 11: “Such a person should reckon this ...”), it seems rather likely that in vv. 8–11 Paul is adopting a firm, severe attitude. This does not mean that his *primary* intention is to terrify the Corinthians, however. In my view, in v. 9, Paul is already anticipating the critic of v. 10. This critic is built upon a supposed inconsistency between Paul's attitude when absent (“his letters are weighty and mighty”) and his attitude when present (“his bodily presence is weak and his speech is contemptible”). Behind this rumour, there is certainly a more general accusation that Paul had usurped his title of apostle (cf. 10:2, where Paul refers to a rumour that he is “walking according to the flesh”).¹¹¹ Hence, it seems to me that what Paul is doing in 10:8–11 is simply defending his status of apostle against those who question it. Furthermore, he is—in an anticipatory manner—defending himself against those who would be tempted to put his status into question

¹⁰⁷ See above, footnote 90.

¹⁰⁸ See above, footnote 93.

¹⁰⁹ See in particular the almost rhetorical question by M. J. Harris, *2 Corinthians*, 696 (“But did Paul actually intend to put fear into the Corinthians by his personal presence of his next visit or by his very letters?”), or the comment by G. Guthrie, *2 Corinthians*, 482 (“Paul begins in v. 9 by stating that he does not want his letters to be perceived as weapons of terrors.”)

¹¹⁰ My translation. See above, Chapter 4, section 2.2 (page 190).

¹¹¹ On the rumours that circulated about Paul, see C. Clivaz, “La rumeur, une catégorie pour articuler autoportraits et réceptions de Paul”; P. Botha, “Paul and Gossip: A Social Mechanism in Early Christian Communities.”

by adhering to the rumour. As concerns his strategy of defence, Paul does not seek to deny that his letters are frightening. Instead, he seems to accept this part of the accusation and works towards vindicating his apostolic authority in a vigorous, almost aggressive manner. He warns that he will not be ashamed to use it during his next visit. Concretely, he is ready to be bold, severe, and intransigent. According to his vision—and probably also according to his audience’s opinion—such an attitude constitutes a sign of apostleship. In other words, Paul plans to prove his apostleship by making use of the authority that is closely associated with it.

If we briefly consider the broader literary context, such an interpretation of 10:8–11 appears perfectly consistent with Paul’s posture throughout chapters 10–13. In fact, from the very beginning, in 10:2, Paul announces that he plans to be bold with “some people, those who reckon us as walking according to the flesh.” At the same occasion, he insinuates that he could also act with severity against every person that would adhere to this accusation. A few lines after, in 10:6, he warns that he stands “ready to punish all disobedience.” And later, in 13:10, he alludes to the authority “that the Lord gave [him]” according to a formulation that recalls 10:8. Specifically, he expresses the wish not to be forced to use this authority during his next visit among the Corinthian community, but he nevertheless makes clear that he could very well use it, if needed.

In sum, an attention to colometry brings a new, stylistic argument that strongly supports the first option of construction; that is, to read v. 9 as closely attached to v. 8, and therefore expressing the purpose of Paul’s refusal to be ashamed (οὐκ αἰσχυνθήσομαι ἵνα μὴ δόξω ὡς ἂν ἐκφοβεῖν ὑμᾶς ...). As discussed, it is perfectly possible to make sense of this construction if one accepts to work with the idea that Paul might have been perceived as frightening by the Corinthians and, above all, that he might not have wanted to deny this aspect of his ministry. As concerns the potential punctuation between vv. 8 and 9, this idea leads us to oppose the choice of a full stop that is retained in the most recent critical editions (NA²⁸ and UBS⁵) to argue instead in favour of a comma (as proposed in WH and in NA²⁵).

3.3. *The status of ἐν ὑμῖν in 10:15*

ἐλπίδα δὲ ἔχοντες ἀξανομένης τῆς πίστεως ὑμῶν ἐν ὑμῖν μεγαλυνθῆναι κατὰ τὸν κανόνα ἡμῶν εἰς περισσεῖαν ^[16] εἰς τὰ ὑπερέκεινα ὑμῶν εὐαγγελίσασθαι οὐκ ἐν ἄλλοτρίῳ κανόνι εἰς τὰ ἔτοιμα καυχῆσασθαι

In 12:15, there is uncertainty as to whether ἐν ὑμῖν belongs with what precedes (ἀύξανομένης τῆς πίστεως ὑμῶν ἐν ὑμῖν, thus “as your faith increases *by your aid*” or “as your faith increases *among you*”) or with what follows. In the latter case, ἐν ὑμῖν would act as a modifier for μεγαλυνθῆναι (ἐν ὑμῖν μεγαλυνθῆναι κατὰ τὸν κανόνα ἡμῶν, thus “that *among you* our work may be enlarged...” or “that our work may be enlarged *by you*...”).¹¹² Numerous exegetes prefer the second option, arguing that the resulting ὑμῶν ἐν ὑμῖν is a tautology.¹¹³ Others support the first option with nuances concerning the sense of the preposition ἐν.¹¹⁴ Interestingly, critical editions (WH, NA²⁸, UBS⁵, GNTM) do not place any punctuation mark here—neither before nor after ἐν ὑμῖν—which leaves the door equally opened to both interpretations.

What about the colometric structure of the passage? In Chapter 4 (see section 2.2.), the following colometric structure was proposed for vv. 15b–16:

Ἐπίδα δὲ ἔχοντες ἀύξανομένης τῆς πίστεως ὑμῶν (I3)
 ἐν ὑμῖν μεγαλυνθῆναι κατὰ τὸν κανόνα ἡμῶν (I1)
 εἰς περισσεῖαν
^[16] εἰς τὰ ὑπερέκεινα ὑμῶν εὐαγγελίσασθαι (I0)
 οὐκ ἐν ἄλλοτρίῳ κανόνι εἰς τὰ ἔτοιμα καυχῆσασθαι. (I3)

When colometry is considered—and more specifically when attention is paid to the structuring function of parisisis and paromoiosis (see T11 and T12)¹¹⁵—it is preferable to place a break before ἐν ὑμῖν rather than after it. Indeed, this reading better accounts for the abundant presence of Gorgianic figures in vv. 15–16. Reading ἐν ὑμῖν with what precedes would not only break the equality in length between the first and the fifth cōlon as well as between the second and the fourth cōlon, respectively, but would also mitigate the sound echoes between ὑμῶν and ἡμῶν as well as between ἐπίδα δέ and εἰς περισσεῖαν. Hence, it is more likely that Paul expected ἐν ὑμῖν to be read as a modifier of

¹¹² On the value of ἐν in this context, see above, Chapter 4, endnote xvii.

¹¹³ So M. Harris, *The Second Epistle to the Corinthians*, 721; also see A. Plummer, *2 Corinthians*, 289. Commentators who follow this option include also C. K. Barrett (*The Second Epistle to the Corinthians*, 267); J. Lambrecht (*Second Corinthians* 167); G. H. Guthrie (*2 Corinthians* 487); and F. J. Long (*2 Corinthians: A Handbook on the Greek Text*, 194).

¹¹⁴ So e.g., R. Bultmann, *Der zweite Brief an die Korinther*, 196 (“wenn euer Glaube unter euch sich mehrt” [cf. his discussion on page 198]); E. Grässer, *Der zweite Brief an die Korinther*, vol. II, 100 (“when euer Glaube in euch sich mehrt”); T. Schmeller, *Der zweite Brief an die Korinther*, vol. II, 173 (“wenn euer Glaube bei euch zunimmt” [see 185 for his study of the structure of vv. 15–16]).

¹¹⁵ On this, see above, Chapter 3, section 3.4.

μεγαλυνθῆναι. According to modern conventions of punctuation, a comma could be placed before ἐν ὑμῖν in order to clarify the structure.

3.4. *The status of verse 12:7a*

φείδομαι δέ μή τις εἰς ἐμέ λογίσηται ὑπὲρ ὃ βλέπει με ἢ ἀκούει τι ἐξ ἐμοῦ [7] καὶ τῆ ὑπερβολῆ τῶν ἀποκαλύψεων [διὸ] ἵνα μὴ ὑπεραίρωμαι ἐδόθη μοι σκόλοψ τῆ σαρκί ἄγγελος σατανᾶ ἵνα με κολαφίζῃ ἵνα μὴ ὑπεραίρωμαι

In this passage, there is a vivid debate among commentators surrounding the status of the clause καὶ τῆ ὑπερβολῆ τῶν ἀποκαλύψεων (12:7a). The problem at issue is whether this clause should be attached to what precedes or to what follows. The debate is complicated by a textual uncertainty concerning the conjunction διό,¹¹⁶ which most exegetes retain but which is nevertheless absent from several important witnesses, including notably P⁴⁶ and D. In short, from a grammatical point of view, καὶ τῆ ὑπερβολῆ τῶν ἀποκαλύψεων can either be linked with what precedes (in which case vv. 6–7a form a single sentence, and [διὸ] ἵνα begins a new sentence) or with what follows (in which case v. 6 forms a sentence on its own and 7a begins a new sentence that embraces the whole v. 7).

If construed with what precedes, καὶ τῆ ὑπερβολῆ τῶν ἀποκαλύψεων could take different values. It can, for example, introduce a second reason for Paul’s refrain from boasting, as suggested in our translation in Chapter 4: “But I am refraining [of boasting] lest anyone should esteem me more beyond what he sees in me or hears from me [7] – and also because of the extraordinary character of the revelations.”¹¹⁷ Alternative understandings that still respect this construction take καί as epexegetic (“specifically, because of the extraordinary nature of the revelations” or “namely, because of the extraordinary nature of the revelations”),¹¹⁸ or as emphatic (“even with respect of the extraordinary nature of the revelations”¹¹⁹). Critical editions (NA²⁸, UBS⁵, WH, GNTM) put a full stop between 7a and 7b, thus clearly treating καὶ τῆ ὑπερβολῆ τῶν

¹¹⁶ See Swanson, *New Testament Greek Manuscripts: 2 Corinthians*, 163. Cf. Chapter 4, page 213, footnote 1 and page 214, footnote 1.

¹¹⁷ See Chapter 4, page 213, footnote 1 and page 214, footnote 1.

¹¹⁸ So V. P. Furnish, *II Corinthians*, 528; R. P. Martin, *2 Corinthians*, 410; Grässer, *Der zweite Brief an die Korinther*, vol. II, 177; T. Schmeller, *Der zweite Brief an die Korinther*, vol. II, 275.

¹¹⁹ See F. J. Long, *II Corinthians: A Handbook on the Greek Text*, 227; Young and Ford, *Meaning and Truth in 2 Corinthians*, 274).

ἀποκαλύψεων as the conclusion of v. 6—note that these editions also all retain the reading with διό.

In contrast, if construed with what follows, καὶ τῇ ὑπερβολῇ τῶν ἀποκαλύψεων rather expresses the reason why Paul was given a thorn in the flesh: “Because of the extraordinary nature of the revelations, so that I might not become over-elated, I was given a thorn in the flesh ...”¹²⁰ (if διό is dropped), or “Because of the extraordinary nature of the revelations, *for that reason*, so that I might not become over-elated...”¹²¹ (if διό is retained).

In the colometric disposition of this passage in Chapter 4, I have placed a major break between 7a and 7b. My rationale was mainly based on the presence of the conjunction διό at the beginning of 7b, which I personally regard as strong evidence that 7b starts a new period.¹²² However, as noted, there remains some uncertainty as to whether διό should be dropped. In addition (as was also previously mentioned), many commentators think that the presence of διό does not necessarily indicate the start of a new sentence in 7b. In fact, though it is effectively pleonastic, διό may be understood to “serve as a bridge between the cause of the ἐδόθη (viz. καὶ τῇ ὑπερβολῇ τῶν ἀποκαλύψεων) and its purpose (viz. ἵνα μὴ ὑπεραίρωμαι).”¹²³ In view of these considerations, it is worth examining the colometric structure of the passage independent of the presence of διό. In my opinion, the following constitutes the best option:

Φείδομαι δέ

μή τις εἰς ἐμέ λογίσηται ὑπὲρ ὃ βλέπει με ἢ ἀκούει τι ἐξ ἐμοῦ

^[7] καὶ τῇ ὑπερβολῇ τῶν ἀποκαλύψεων.

[Διό] ἵνα μὴ ὑπεραίρωμαι

ἐδόθη μοι σκόλοψ τῇ σαρκί

ἄγγελος σατανᾶ ἵνα με κολαφίζῃ

ἵνα μὴ ὑπεραίρωμαι.

¹²⁰ So D. E. Garland, *2 Corinthians*, 507; R. Bultmann, *Der zweite Brief an die Korinther*, 215; C. K. Barrett, *The Second Epistle to the Corinthians*, 305; M. Carrez, *La deuxième épître aux Corinthiens*, 226; Harris, *The Second Epistle to the Corinthians*, 851–853; Lambrecht, *Second Corinthians*, 199; M. E. Thrall, *The Second Epistle to the Corinthians*, vol. II, 805. Also see KJV; NASB; NIV; ESV.

¹²¹ So C. K. Barrett, *The Second Epistle to the Corinthians*, 313–314; Harris, *The Second Epistle to the Corinthians*, 851–853; Guthrie, *2 Corinthians*, 572; Lambrecht, *Second Corinthians*, 202.

¹²² See Chapter 4, page 213, footnote 1 and page 214, footnote 1.

¹²³ Harris, *The Second Epistle to the Corinthians*, 853; C. K. Barrett, *The Second Epistle to the Corinthians*, 313–314; Guthrie, *2 Corinthians*, 572.

We can detect sound echoes between 7a and the two preceding cōla in the repetition of the sounds /e/ and /i/ over the first four syllables. The similarity is especially striking between the beginnings of the second and the third cōla, where the same sequence of sounds /e/ – /t/ – /i/ is repeated over the first two syllables (μή τις and καὶ τῆ).¹²⁴ Moreover, we can note that paromoioses are abundant in the immediate literary context (see 12:1–10), making it plausible that Paul here uses sound echoes as a structuring device or at least as cues underlining the structure (see especially T13).¹²⁵ All in all, an attention to colometry suggests that 7a has been stylistically designed to be read with v. 6.

Accordingly, when sonority is taken into account, the issue of the punctuating of 12:6–7 might be summed up as follows: if διό is retained, then its presence makes it very unlikely that a major break should be placed before 7a, especially when considering colometry.¹²⁶ In other words, an attention to the aural profile of vv. 6–7 supports the choice of punctuation made in modern critical editions: a major break between 7a and 7b. However, the situation is not as clear should the reading without διό be retained. In this case, the sole argument of sound echoes is not necessarily conclusive.

3.5. *The status of ἐν πάση ὑπομονῇ in 12:12*

τὰ μὲν σημεῖα τοῦ ἀποστόλου κατειργάσθη ἐν ὑμῖν ἐν πάση ὑπομονῇ σημείους τε καὶ τέρασιν καὶ δυνάμεσιν

In 12:12, the status of the second preposition ἐν is at issue, and the question is whether ἐν introduces only πάση ὑπομονῇ or also the three following items (σημεῖους τε καὶ τέρασιν καὶ δυνάμεσιν). This question can be reformulated in terms of whether the phrase ἐν πάση ὑπομονῇ should be taken with what precedes or with what follows. Most scholars link it with what precedes.¹²⁷ Accordingly, ἐν πάση ὑπομονῇ expresses the manner, whereas σημείους τε καὶ τέρασιν καὶ δυνάμεσιν expresses the means. A possible translation would be: “The signs of an apostle were produced among you *in all endurance, through* signs and marvels and mighty deeds.” To note—critical editions (including the

¹²⁴ On the model of pronunciation retained, see above, Chapter 3, Table 1 (page 172).

¹²⁵ On the structuring role of paromoioses, see the discussion above in Chapter 3, section 3.4.1.

¹²⁶ Defendants of the linkage between καὶ τῆ ὑπερβολῆ τῶν ἀποκαλύψεων and διό ἵνα μὴ ὑπεράρρωμαι ... must admit that here Paul has produced a particularly awkward and unclear passage.

¹²⁷ See e.g. M. E. Thrall, *The Second Epistle to the Corinthians*, vol. II, 838; Harris, *The Second Epistle to the Corinthians*, 874–875; E. Grässer, *Der zweite Brief an die Korinther*, vol. II, 215; F. J. Long, *2 Corinthians: A Handbook on the Greek Text*, 236; Guthrie, *2 Corinthians*, 601; T. Schmeller, *Der zweite Brief an die Korinther*, vol. II, 334–335, esp. n. 617.

NA²⁸, the UBS⁵, or the WH, all place a comma after ὑπομονῆ, which arguably also supports this interpretation.¹²⁸ Some scholars, however, consider ἐν πάσῃ ὑπομονῆ instrumental and expressive of the signs (σημεῖα) of Paul’s apostleship, along with the σημεῖα, the τέρατα and the δυνάμεις (thus “*by means of every kind of endurance, signs and marvels and mighty deeds*”).¹²⁹

In this case, could a colometric analysis of the passage help in this case to disambiguate the status of ἐν πάσῃ ὑπομονῆ? The proposed colometric disposition of 12:12 in Chapter 4 links ἐν πάσῃ ὑπομονῆ with what follows, thus forming a single cōlon with σημείους τε καὶ τέρασιν καὶ δυνάμεσιν.¹³⁰ Such an analysis suggests that ἐν πάσῃ ὑπομονῆ represents one of the signs of an apostle (σημεῖα τοῦ ἀποστόλου), with the instrumental ἐν being related both to πάσῃ ὑπομονῆ and to the three plural datives that follow. However, it must be specified here that my reasoning for this delineation was not particularly strong. I based my choice on the fact that this delineation results in a better balance within the period (see ΤΙΙ), as its two cōla have in this way approximatively the same length (17 and 20 syllables). Taken alone, this sole argument is far from conclusive.¹³¹ Moreover, it should be noticed that ὑπομονή (“endurance”) belongs to a very different semantic field than σημείον, τέρας and δύναμις—all of which are related to the marvelousness category. Therefore, it is perhaps more logical to construe it with what precedes. The presence of τε after σημείους and the absence of a connector between ὑπομονῆ and σημείους also suggest that a break should be placed before the expression σημείους τε καὶ τέρασιν καὶ δυνάμεσιν.¹³² For these two reasons, it seems preferable to construe ἐν πάσῃ ὑπομονῆ separately from σημείους τε καὶ τέρασιν καὶ δυνάμεσιν. This concretely implies that a cōlon-boundary should be placed between the two expressions. Accordingly, the colometric disposition proposed in Chapter 4 should perhaps be revised and transformed as follows:

¹²⁸ See such an understanding on the meaning of the comma in Harris, *The Second Epistle to the Corinthians*, 874, n. 30.

¹²⁹ See e.g., J. Héring, *La Seconde Epître de Saint Paul aux Corinthiens*, 95; C. K. Barrett, *The Second Epistle to the Corinthians*, 318. 321.

¹³⁰ See Chapter 4, section 2.2 (page 218).

¹³¹ See Chapter 3, section 3.4.1. Note that the similarity in sound between ἐν ὑμῖν and δυνάμεσιν does not consist of a supplementary argument in favour of the delineation retained. In fact, following the model of pronunciation retained in this study (see above, Chapter 3, section 3.4.2), δυνάμεσιν also rhymes with ὑπομονῆ, meaning that the paromoiosis would not disappear if the boundary between the two cōla was placed after ἐν πάσῃ ὑπομονῆ.

¹³² See a good overview of the different arguments in M. E. Thrall, *The Second Epistle to the Corinthians*, vol. II, 838.

- a) τὰ μὲν σημεῖα τοῦ ἀποστόλου κατειργάσθη ἐν ὑμῖν ἐν πάσῃ ὑπομονῇ
- b) σημείους τε καὶ τέρασιν καὶ δυνάμεσιν

The above example reveals the limits of the argument of colometry, especially when the choice of delineation is based on a very general tendency, such as the approximative equality of length between the *côla*.¹³³ This suggests that we should avoid applying the T-rules (“tendencies”) in a dogmatic manner. Rather, we should always consider the results of colometric analysis with a critical eye in order to ensure that the proposed segmentation does not conflict with other structuring cues or with the probable meaning of the passage at stake.

3.6. *The construction of 12:20–21*

[20] φοβοῦμαι γὰρ μή πως ἐλθὼν οὐχ οἴους θέλω εὔρω ὑμᾶς κἀγὼ εὔρεθῶ ὑμῖν οἶον οὐ θέλετε μή πως ἔρις ζῆλος θυμοὶ ἐριθείαι καταλαλαί ψιθυρισμοὶ φυσιώσεις ἀκαταστασίαι [21] μή πάλιν ἐλθόντος μου ταπεινώσῃ με ὁ θεὸς μου πρὸς ὑμᾶς καὶ πενθήσω πολλοὺς τῶν προημαρτηκότων καὶ μὴ μετανοησάντων ἐπὶ τῇ ἀκαθαρσίᾳ καὶ πορνείᾳ καὶ ἀσελείᾳ ἧ ἔπραξαν

This last example differs from the preceding ones, as at first glance there seems to be no conflict at all. In fact, as far as I am aware, all commentators find that the three occurrences of *μή* are dependent on *φοβοῦμαι*, and that each *μή* introduces one content of the fear: “I fear that, when I come, I may perhaps find you not how I wish ... I fear that there might perhaps be strife ... I fear that, when I come back, God may humble me ... and that I have to mourn over many”¹³⁴ According to this understanding, vv. 20–21 together form a single sentence. The punctuation proposed in critical editions support this construction (NA²⁸ has high points before *μή πως ἔρις ...* and before *μή πάλιν ἐλθόντος μου ...* ; UBS⁵ has a high point before *μή πως ἔρις...* and then no punctuation mark before *μή πάλιν ἐλθόντος μου...* ; WH has a comma before *μή πως ἔρις ...* and a high point before *μή πάλιν ἐλθόντος μου...*).

¹³³ See Chapter 3, section 3.4.1.

¹³⁴ See e.g., A. Plummer, *2 Corinthians*, 369; R. Bultmann, *Der zweite Brief an die Korinther*, 238; C. K. Barrett, *The Second Epistle to the Corinthians*, 326; R. P. Martin, *2 Corinthians*, 450–451; M. E. Thrall, *The Second Epistle to the Corinthians*, vol. II, 865; E. Grässer, *Der zweite Brief an die Korinther*, vol. II, 234; Harris, *The Second Epistle to the Corinthians*, 901; F.J. Long, *2 Corinthians: A Handbook on the Greek Text*, 243; Guthrie, *2 Corinthians*, 619; T. Schmeller, *Der zweite Brief an die Korinther*, vol. II, 359.

However, this construction is put into question when attention is paid to colometry. Indeed, treating each μή as dependent on φοβοῦμαι yields to a period of unusual length. Reaching almost 130 syllables, this extends far beyond all the examples found in the rhetorical treatises (see T6).¹³⁵ This observation leads us to wonder whether an alternative construction would be possible for 12:20–21—perhaps one that would involve at least one strong break somewhere in the middle. The colometric disposition proposed in Chapter 4 showcases such an alternative: the passage is divided into two periods and a major break is placed between v. 20 and v. 21. According to this analysis, the third μή construction (μή πάλιν ἐλθόντος μου ταπεινώση με ὁ θεός μου ...) does not directly relate to φοβοῦμαι. Instead, it is an independent construction in which the aorist subjunctive conveys a hortatory or a prohibitive force: “Let not God,¹³⁶ when I come back, humble me before you, and [let] me [not] mourn over many who have previously sinned and did not repent ...”¹³⁷ In other words, in v. 21, Paul is still expressing one of his fears, but he does so in a different form. He formulates a negative wish (or, more likely, a command) that might even convey a warning or a veiled threat. This warning is addressed to the Corinthians, not to God or to Paul himself. We may paraphrase the underlying idea as follows: “Prepare yourself so as to make sure that when I will come back among you, God will not humble me before you, and also make sure that I will not be forced to mourn”

Is this alternative understanding of v. 21 consistent with the formulation of vv. 20–21—and with Paul’s rhetoric in 2 Cor. 10–13 more broadly? Various elements support an affirmative answer. To begin with, we may note that the context of Paul’s next visit to the Corinthian community is specified at the beginning of v. 21 (by means of the genitive clause ἐλθόντος μου), although it was already made perfectly clear in v. 20 (see ἐλθών). Such a repetition perhaps makes more sense if v. 21 begins a new sentence. In addition, we may note that the μή construction of v. 21 omits the word πως (“somehow” or “perhaps”), which occurs twice in v. 20. This may indicate that the concern expressed in v. 21 does not stand on the same level as that expressed in v. 20. In contrast with the fears expressed in v. 20, Paul’s concern that God may humiliate him and that he may have to

¹³⁵ On the maximal length of periods, see the discussion in Chapter 3, section 3.1.

¹³⁶ See a close construction with God as the subject (with an imperative, however, instead of the subjunctive) in Ex 20:19 LXX, when the people say to Moses: “let not God speak to us, lest we die” (μή λαλείτω πρὸς ἡμᾶς ὁ θεός, μήποτε ἀποθάνωμεν).

¹³⁷ On these possible values of the subjunctive after μή, see e.g., BDF §364. In Paul, examples of a hortatory subjunctive introduced by μή are found in 2 Cor 11:16 (μή τις με δόξη ἄφρονα εἶναι, “let no one think me a fool!”) and in 1 Cor 16:11 (μή τις οὖν αὐτὸν ἐξουθενήσῃ, “let no one despise him!”).

mourn over many unrepented sinners is not softened by the expression of a potential character. The tone becomes more compelling, and the concern expressed in v. 21 resonates more like a request or even as an order addressed to the Corinthians: “Make sure that this will not happen!” Furthermore, if we look at the rhetoric of 2 Cor 10–13 more generally, it appears that Paul does not deny the severe character of his letters (see 10:9–10).¹³⁸ Rather, he makes his intention to use his apostolic authority during his next visit perfectly clear (see 10:2; 10:6; 10:8–9; 10:11; 13:2; also see 13:10), including his intent to punish “all disobedience” (10:6). Finally, as the construction μή + aorist subjunctive is already used in 11:16 to give a command to the Corinthians (μή τις με δόξη ἄφρονα εἶναι, “let no one think me a fool!”), it would not be surprising that in 12:21 Paul adopts a similar formulation in order to give a command that conveys some sort of warning. In view of these different elements, the suggested alternative understanding for v. 21 is indeed plausible and is perhaps even more likely to correspond to Paul’s intention than the classical interpretation.

3.7. Conclusion: Benefits and limits

Following these few examples, what can be said about the efficacy of colometric analysis as a tool for disambiguating Paul’s syntax? The results are rather encouraging: on many occasions, an attention to colometry yields new arguments that orient the debates. As was shown with the example of 12:20–21, colometry may also bring attention to alternative constructions that are not commonly suggested in the commentaries. Of course, these arguments are more or less convincing depending on the issue considered. They range from quite convincing (e.g., as concerns the status of the participles in 10:4–6, of the ἵνα clause in 10:9, or of the phrase ἐν ὑμῖν in 10:15) to inconclusive (e.g., as in 12:12, where the doubt remains over whether ἐν πάσῃ ὑπομονῇ should be read with what precedes or with what follows). Additionally, colometry is helpless to determinate the appropriate punctuation in 2 Cor 11:13, where it is still unclear how the participle μετασχηματιζόμενοι relates to the immediately preceding noun clause ἐργάται δόλοιοι.¹³⁹ In other words, colometric analysis illuminates Paul’s logic, but it also happens that Paul’s intended meaning remains unclear even when attention is paid to colometry.

¹³⁸ See the discussion above, section 3.2.

¹³⁹ On the different possible roles for μετασχηματιζόμενοι, see F. J. Long, *2 Corinthians: A Handbook on the Greek Text*, 206. On how the choice of punctuation influences on the interpretation of this passage, see Guthrie, *2 Corinthians*, 526.

Borrowing from Aristotle’s comment on Heraclitus’ writings, we could say that Paul’s prose is sometimes “hard to punctuate, since it is unclear to which [word] another belongs, whether to that which follows or that which precedes.”¹⁴⁰ Another difficulty is that the colometry argument can itself be quite convincing but can be weakened by textual criticism: this is the case in 12:7, where the uncertainty surrounding the presence of *διό* casts doubt upon the relevance of the proposed segmentation. In sum, colometric analysis obviously does not provide an easy answer to all punctuation issues that relate to syntactic ambiguities. That having been said, an attention to the principles of colometry regularly proves to be helpful when evaluating the punctuation that is the most likely to reflect Paul’s intention. For this reason alone, colometric analysis deserves to be integrated into exegetes’ palette of tools.

4. Towards an Elocutionary Approach to the Punctuation of Paul’s Letters

We now move on to more broadly consider the implications of colometry for the general (written) punctuation of Paul’s letters—not only for those passages with syntactic ambiguities, but for the whole text. Specifically, we will explore how the analysis of the colometric structure of 2 Cor 10–13 (as conducted in Chapter 4) may allow us to punctuate this text in a way that better reflects its aural character and therefore does more justice to Paul’s style.

4.1. *Punctuation marks, between grammar and prosody*

It is perhaps worth saying here a few words on the function of punctuation marks. In terms of what might be called “Western punctuation,” we can distinguish two different approaches to this question: an *elocutionary* one and a *grammatical* one. According to the elocutionary approach (which is sometimes also called “rhetorical”), punctuation marks are essentially cues for where breaks should occur; punctuation marks have a prosodic function, indicating where and how to pause while reading. In contrast, the *grammatical* approach, as its name indicates, insists on the punctuation marks’ function of illuminating the grammar. Ultimately, grammar-based punctuation shows where

¹⁴⁰ Arist., *Rhet.* III,5,6–7; see above, section 2.1.2.

grammatical boundaries are and also suggests how segments (words, phrases, clauses, sentences) relate to one another.¹⁴¹

In the Western tradition, the elocutionary approach has a much longer history than the grammatical approach. In fact, it is largely acknowledged that punctuation originally served performative needs, due to its roots in the practices of reading aloud and performing.¹⁴² As Anna Bonifazi summarises, the elocutionary function was largely dominant in the Western practices of punctuation—at least up to the first printed editions of classical texts at the end of the 15th century.¹⁴³ It might be expected that punctuation’s role as a “mirror of aurality” is dependent on the habits of reading aloud, and that therefore punctuation conventions should have gradually evolved into a more grammatical approach that paralleled the progressive evolutions of reading practices towards silent reading. However, even the generalisation of silent reading did not mark the end of the idea that written punctuation is, somewhat, a “mirror of aurality.” In the current use of many languages (for example English, French, or Italian), both the grammatical and the elocutionary functions are typically recognised and combined. As argued by Wallace Chafe in an article intitled “Punctuation and the Prosody of Written Language,” written language somehow has its own prosody: namely, even in a text that is not specifically intended to be read aloud, both the writer and the readers experience what he calls the “auditory imagery” of intonation, accents, and hesitations.¹⁴⁴ In this sense, punctuation reveals the prosody of the writer’s inner voice. To draw a comparison with music, we may say that punctuation conveys a sense of the “musicality” of the speech, in the sense that it highlights “such literary qualities as rhythm, direction, pitch, tone and flow.”¹⁴⁵ More simply, we may say that punctuation is an integral part of the style of a text.

More fundamentally, the two approaches to punctuation should not be too strongly opposed. Indeed, they often concur when it comes to the marking of segmentation. This holds true—albeit to a lesser extent—even for languages that adopted a very codified

¹⁴¹ See e.g., the definition of punctuation given by H. W. Fowler and F. G. Fowler in 1906: “the work of punctuation is mainly to show, or hint at, the grammatical relation between words, phrases, clauses, and sentences.” (H. W. Fowler and F. G. Fowler, *The King’s English*, 233).

¹⁴² See e.g. R. Skelton, *Modern English Punctuation*, 163; Parkes, *Pause and Effect*, 1–4; S. Patt, *Punctuation as a Means of Medium-Dependent Presentation Structure in English: Exploring the Guide Functions of Punctuation*, 71; A. Bonifazi, “Discourse Segmentation,” §28; also see L. Truss, *Eats, Shoots and Leaves*, 72.

¹⁴³ A. Bonifazi, “Discourse Segmentation,” §28.

¹⁴⁴ W. Chafe, “Punctuation and the Prosody of Written Language.”

¹⁴⁵ L. Truss, *Eats, Shoots and Leaves*, 70.

approach to punctuation based on grammar. In fact, grammatical boundaries often coincide with prosodic boundaries. When determining where to place punctuation marks in a text, the two approaches often provide similar results. The close connection between elocution and grammar was outlined in the early 1950s by Eric Partridge, in his *Guide to Punctuation*. Partridge stated:

There have been two systems of punctuation: the rhetorical or dramatic or elocutionary (...) and the grammatical or constructional or logical (...). But to insist upon the dichotomy *dramatic-grammatical* would be both pedantic and inept. For much of the time, as is inevitable, the two coincide: a speaker tends to pause wherever either logic or grammar makes a pause; and even the most 'logical' or 'grammatical' of punctuators tends, when he is writing dialogue, to point what is clearly an elocutionary or dramatic pause (...).¹⁴⁶

In the subsequent decades, and even more following the publication of Wallace Chafe's seminal article in 1988 ("Punctuation and the Prosody of Written Language"), several scholars have examined the prosodic values of the different punctuation marks.¹⁴⁷ Others have discussed the link between prosody and syntax more generally, showing how prosodic continuity and discontinuity often convey the grammatical segmentation of discourse.¹⁴⁸ All these studies suggest to reinterpret the functional duality of punctuation, "in terms of deep interlacing rather than opposition, and in terms of co-construction of boundaries, structure, and meaning."¹⁴⁹

Despite this close interlacing, the distinction between the elocutionary and the grammatical functions of punctuation remains useful when thinking about the punctuation of Paul's letters, or the NT writings more generally. Modern critical editions of the NT (e.g., the NA, the UBS, the NTGM series, or the ECM)¹⁵⁰ essentially adopt a grammatical approach to the question of punctuation, showing little interest for the

¹⁴⁶ E. Partridge, *You Have a Point There: A Guide to Punctuation and its Allies*, 6–7 (italics in the original).

¹⁴⁷ Chafe, "Punctuation and the Prosody of Written Language"; cf. R. J. Scholes and Brenda J. Willis, "Prosodic and Syntactic Functions of Punctuation: A Contribution to the Study of Orality and Literacy"; Esther Borochofsky Bar-Aba, "Punctuation Marks: Procedural and Conceptual uses."

¹⁴⁸ On the relationship between syntax and prosody more generally, see, among others, Elizabeth Couper-Kuhlen and Margret Selting (eds.), *Prosody in Conversation: Interactional Studies*; Margret Selting, "On the interplay of syntax and prosody in the constitution of turn constructional units and turns in conversation," *Pragmatics*, vol. 6, no. 3, pp. 371–388; Elizabeth Couper-Kuhlen, "Prosodic Cues of Discourse Units"; Mary Dalrymple and Louise Mycock, "The prosody-syntax interface"; Nicole Dehé, *Parentheticals in Spoken English: The Syntax-Prosody Relation*.

¹⁴⁹ A. Bonifazi, "Discourse Segmentation," §12.

¹⁵⁰ As also noted by S. Crisp, "Scribal Marks and Logical Paragraphs: Discourse Segmentation Criteria in Manuscripts of the Pauline Corpus," 78.

original aural character of the NT writings.¹⁵¹ This is evidenced by the frequent presence of long units that do not contain any punctuation marks. These unpunctuated units regularly extend beyond 30 syllables and can sometimes reach up to 40 syllables or even more.¹⁵² Due to their length, they are unable to be read without a rest or a breath. There are also few “strong” punctuation marks, such as full stops or high points. To be short, we may say that the editors of these editions tend to be minimalist when it comes to punctuation. In general, they place a punctuation mark only when needed to clarify the grammar; they also favour slight punctuation marks (commas and high points) over full stops.

When dealing with ancient texts intended to be read aloud, it makes more sense to favour an elocutionary approach that takes performative needs into account. As a general rule, the units left unpunctuated should not be longer than a reader can pronounce in a single breath.¹⁵³ The punctuation should not only leave sufficient room for resting and breathing, but also for grasping the meaning without needing to stop and reread a passage multiple times. This is important because the listeners receive a text as a linear stream. These remarks hold true even if modern readers of ancient texts generally do not plan to read these texts aloud. Indeed, punctuation marks impact the perception of a given text’s style, by revealing its “inner voice.” The challenge is thus to punctuate ancient texts in a way that suggests how they were meant to be perceived by ancient readers and listeners. As concerns the texts structured in *côla* and periods—including Paul’s letters—the more appropriate way to deal with the issue of their modern punctuation is to model it on their colometric structure. Building on our discussion of the ancient conventions of *pronunciatio* (see section 2.2 above), it is possible to “translate” the system of aural punctuation into a system of written punctuation. I will expound upon this idea further below.

¹⁵¹ In matters of punctuation, K. Aland and B. Aland specify that the editors of the Nestle-Aland (they refer here to the 26th edition) tried “to represent Greek usage, departing from it only when strict consistency might cause difficulties for the modern reader.” (*The Text of the New Testament: An Introduction to the Critical Editions and to the Theory and Practice of Modern Textual Criticisms*, 47). It is not specified, however, which Greek usage they have in mind. F. D. Gilliards suggests that the editors “must have tried to represent medieval or modern usage, applying it to ancient Greek.” (“The Problem of the Antisemitic Comma between 1 Thessalonians 2.14 and 15,” 487, n. 4).

¹⁵² In the NA²⁸, long unpunctuated units are found notably in 2 Cor. 10:2, 10:8; 10:12; 11:10; 12 :21; 13:10.

¹⁵³ See also in this sense A. Bonifazi, “Discourse Segmentation,” §14: “The performance-constraint implies that listeners/spectators were supposed to receive smaller chunks of information at a time. This should constitute a caveat when we modern readers approach the modern punctuation of ancient Greek texts.”

4.2. *A system of punctuation based on colometry*¹⁵⁴

What would colometry-based punctuation look like? The system I propose maintains the signs that are familiar to modern readers of ancient Greek text (i.e., the comma, the high point, the full stop, and the semicolon) while making the colometric structure explicit. The system also includes two supplementary signs that do not currently appear in critical editions: the exclamation mark, to signal an exclamative tone, and the caron [ˇ], to mark a slight prosodic break within a cōlon:

- **Punctuation of periods:** periods are punctuated by a full stop, or, when appropriate, with a semicolon (i.e., a Greek question mark) or an exclamation mark.
- **Punctuation of periodic cōla:** within periods, the boundaries between the cōla are signalled with commas.
- **Punctuation of autonomous cōla:** autonomous cōla are punctuated with a high point (which, following the conventions of punctuating Greek, corresponds to an English colon or semicolon), or, when appropriate, a semicolon (i.e., a Greek question mark) or an exclamation mark.
- **Punctuation of rhythmical group within a cōlon:** in some place, minor prosodic breaks within cōla are suggested with a caron [ˇ].
- **Use of capitals:** periods begin with a capital letter, whereas autonomous cōla begin with a lower-case letter.

In this system, there is an effort to punctuate each type of colometric unit (period; periodic cōlon or comma; autonomous cōlon or comma; rhythmic unit within a cōlon) in a consistent manner by always using in principle the same sign in a specific situation. This renders the status of the different units explicit for the readers. However, there are some exceptions to this general rule concerning the use of the semicolon and the exclamation mark: both of these signs may stand either at the end of a period or of an autonomous cōlon. Nevertheless, even in this case periods and autonomous cōla are still distinguishable on the basis of the letter case (capital for periods, lower-case for cōla).

¹⁵⁴ Below, I also use the term cōlon to include short cōla (commata).

The notion of “minor prosodic breaks” requires further comment. This refers to the light pauses that are sometimes necessary within a cōlon—typically between words and/or phrases that are juxtaposed, or before and after a word and/or a phrase that forms a short parenthetical within the cōlon.¹⁵⁵ The use of a distinct sign (a caron) that signals these breaks ensures that they are not mistaken for cōla boundaries. However, as concerns the text of 2 Cor 10–13 presented below, it should be specified that the marking of these minor breaks is uncertain, as an analysis of the colometric structure of a text does not directly inform us about the presence of such kinds of breaks.

4.3. *2 Cor 10–13 repunctuated*

In the following presentation of 2 Cor 10–13, the main text (in bold)¹⁵⁶ has been punctuated using the colometry-based system proposed above (see section 4.2). The text from the NA (28th edition) is reproduced just below in order to ease the comparison between the two punctuation styles. The paragraph breaks present in the NA are signalled using the sign §.

¹⁵⁵ See the discussion above, section 2.2.4.

¹⁵⁶ Below, I re-use the Greek text present in Chapter 4, without again signalling the variants found in the manuscripts.

^[10.1] Αὐτὸς δὲ ἐγὼ Παῦλος ἔ παρακαλῶ ὑμᾶς, διὰ τῆς πραϋτητος καὶ ἐπεικειίας τοῦ Χριστοῦ, §^[10.1] Αὐτὸς δὲ ἐγὼ Παῦλος παρακαλῶ ὑμᾶς διὰ τῆς πραϋτητος καὶ ἐπεικειίας τοῦ Χριστοῦ,

ὃς κατὰ πρόσωπον μὲν ταπεινὸς ἐν ὑμῖν, ἀπὼν δὲ θαρρῶ εἰς ὑμᾶς. ^[2] Δέομαι δὲ τὸ μὴ παρῶν ὃς κατὰ πρόσωπον μὲν ταπεινὸς ἐν ὑμῖν, ἀπὼν δὲ θαρρῶ εἰς ὑμᾶς. ^[2] δέομαι δὲ τὸ μὴ παρῶν

θαρρῆσαι τῇ πεποιθήσει ἢ λογίζομαι τολμῆσαι ἐπὶ τινας, τοὺς λογιζομένους ἡμᾶς ὡς κατὰ σάρκα θαρρῆσαι τῇ πεποιθήσει ἢ λογίζομαι τολμῆσαι ἐπὶ τινας τοὺς λογιζομένους ἡμᾶς ὡς κατὰ σάρκα

περιπατοῦντας. ^[3] Ἐν σαρκὶ γὰρ περιπατοῦντες, οὐ κατὰ σάρκα στρατευόμεθα. ^[4] Τὰ γὰρ ὄπλα περιπατοῦντας. ^[3] Ἐν σαρκὶ γὰρ περιπατοῦντες οὐ κατὰ σάρκα στρατευόμεθα, ^[4] τὰ γὰρ ὄπλα

τῆς στρατείας ἡμῶν οὐ σαρκικὰ, ἀλλὰ δυνατὰ τῷ θεῷ πρὸς καθαίρεσιν ὀχυρωμάτων. Λογισμοὺς τῆς στρατείας ἡμῶν οὐ σαρκικὰ ἀλλὰ δυνατὰ τῷ θεῷ πρὸς καθαίρεσιν ὀχυρωμάτων, λογισμοὺς

καθαίρουντες, ^[5] καὶ πᾶν ὑψωμα ἐπαιρόμενον κατὰ τῆς γνώσεως τοῦ θεοῦ. καὶ αἰχμαλωτίζοντες καθαίρουντες ^[5] καὶ πᾶν ὑψωμα ἐπαιρόμενον κατὰ τῆς γνώσεως τοῦ θεοῦ, καὶ αἰχμαλωτίζοντες

πᾶν νόημα εἰς τὴν ὑπακοὴν τοῦ Χριστοῦ. ^[6] Καὶ ἐν ἐτοιμῷ ἔχοντες ἐκδικῆσαι πᾶσαν παρακοήν, πᾶν νόημα εἰς τὴν ὑπακοὴν τοῦ Χριστοῦ, ^[6] καὶ ἐν ἐτοιμῷ ἔχοντες ἐκδικῆσαι πᾶσαν παρακοήν,

ὅταν πληρωθῇ ὑμῶν ἡ ὑπακοή. ^[7] τὰ κατὰ πρόσωπον βλέπετε. Εἴ τις πέποιθεν ἐαυτῷ Χριστοῦ ὅταν πληρωθῇ ὑμῶν ἡ ὑπακοή. § ^[7] Τὰ κατὰ πρόσωπον βλέπετε. εἴ τις πέποιθεν ἐαυτῷ Χριστοῦ

εἶναι, τοῦτο λογιζέσθω ἄλιν ἐφ' ἑαυτοῦ, ὅτι καθὼς αὐτὸς Χριστοῦ, οὕτως καὶ ἡμεῖς. ^[8] Ἐάν τε εἶναι, τοῦτο λογιζέσθω ἄλιν ἐφ' ἑαυτοῦ, ὅτι καθὼς αὐτὸς Χριστοῦ, οὕτως καὶ ἡμεῖς. ^[8] ἐάν [τε]

γὰρ περισσώτερόν τι καυχῆσωμαι περὶ τῆς ἐξουσίας ἡμῶν, ἧς ἔδωκεν ὁ κύριος εἰς οἰκοδομὴν γὰρ περισσώτερόν τι καυχῆσωμαι περὶ τῆς ἐξουσίας ἡμῶν ἧς ἔδωκεν ὁ κύριος εἰς οἰκοδομὴν

καὶ οὐκ εἰς καθαίρεσιν ὑμῶν, οὐκ αἰσχυνθήσομαι. ^[9] ἵνα μὴ δόξω ὡς ἂν ἐκφοβεῖν ὑμᾶς διὰ τῶν καὶ οὐκ εἰς καθαίρεσιν ὑμῶν, οὐκ αἰσχυνθήσομαι. ^[9] ἵνα μὴ δόξω ὡς ἂν ἐκφοβεῖν ὑμᾶς διὰ τῶν

ἐπιστολῶν. ^[10] Ὅτι αἱ ἐπιστολαὶ μὲν ἔ φησὶν ἔ βαρεῖαι καὶ ἰσχυραί, ἡ δὲ παρουσία τοῦ σώματος ἐπιστολῶν. ^[10] ὅτι αἱ ἐπιστολαὶ μὲν, φησὶν, βαρεῖαι καὶ ἰσχυραί, ἡ δὲ παρουσία τοῦ σώματος

ἀσθενῆς ἔ καὶ ὁ λόγος ἐξουθενημένος. ^[11] Τοῦτο λογιζέσθω ὁ τοιοῦτος, ὅτι οἷοί ἐσμεν τῷ λόγῳ ἔ ἀσθενῆς καὶ ὁ λόγος ἐξουθενημένος. ἢ τοῦτο λογιζέσθω ὁ τοιοῦτος, ὅτι οἷοί ἐσμεν τῷ λόγῳ

δι' ἐπιστολῶν ἀπόντες, τοιοῦτοι καὶ παρόντες τῷ ἔργῳ. ^[12] Οὐ γὰρ τολμῶμεν ἐγκρίναι ἢ δι' ἐπιστολῶν ἀπόντες, τοιοῦτοι καὶ παρόντες τῷ ἔργῳ. § ^[12] Οὐ γὰρ τολμῶμεν ἐγκρίναι ἢ

συγκρίναι ἑαυτοὺς τισιν τῶν ἑαυτοὺς συνιστανόντων. Ἄλλ' αὐτοὶ ἐν ἑαυτοῖς ἑαυτοὺς συγκρίναι ἑαυτοὺς τισιν τῶν ἑαυτοὺς συνιστανόντων, ἀλλ' αὐτοὶ ἐν ἑαυτοῖς ἑαυτοὺς

μετροῦντες, καὶ συγκρίνοντες ἑαυτοὺς ἑαυτοῖς, οὐ συνιάσιν. ^[13] Ἡμεῖς δὲ οὐκ εἰς τὰ ἄμετρα μετροῦντες καὶ συγκρίνοντες ἑαυτοὺς ἑαυτοῖς οὐ συνιάσιν. ^[13] ἡμεῖς δὲ οὐκ εἰς τὰ ἄμετρα

καυχησόμεθα, ἀλλὰ κατὰ τὸ μέτρον τοῦ κανόνος οὗ ἐμέρισεν ἡμῖν ὁ θεὸς μέτρου, ἐφικέσθαι καυχησόμεθα ἀλλὰ κατὰ τὸ μέτρον τοῦ κανόνος οὗ ἐμέρισεν ἡμῖν ὁ θεὸς μέτρου, ἐφικέσθαι

ἄχρι καὶ ὑμῶν. ^[14] οὐ γὰρ ὡς μὴ ἐφικνούμενοι εἰς ὑμᾶς ὑπερεκτείνομεν ἑαυτοὺς· ἄχρι γὰρ καὶ ἄχρι καὶ ὑμῶν. ^[14] οὐ γὰρ ὡς μὴ ἐφικνούμενοι εἰς ὑμᾶς ὑπερεκτείνομεν ἑαυτοὺς, ἄχρι γὰρ καὶ

ὑμῶν ἐφθάσαμεν ἐν τῷ εὐαγγελίῳ τοῦ Χριστοῦ. ^[15] οὐκ εἰς τὰ ἄμετρα καυχώμενοι ἐν ἀλλοτρίοις ὑμῶν ἐφθάσαμεν ἐν τῷ εὐαγγελίῳ τοῦ Χριστοῦ, ^[15] οὐκ εἰς τὰ ἄμετρα καυχώμενοι ἐν ἀλλοτρίοις

κόποις· Ἐλπίδα δὲ ἔχοντες ἄυξανομένης τῆς πίστεως ὑμῶν, ἐν ὑμῖν μεγαλυνθῆναι κατὰ τὸν κόποις, ἐλπίδα δὲ ἔχοντες ἀυξανομένης τῆς πίστεως ὑμῶν ἐν ὑμῖν μεγαλυνθῆναι κατὰ τὸν

κανόνα ἡμῶν, εἰς περισσεῖαν, ^[16] εἰς τὰ ὑπερέκεινα ὑμῶν εὐαγγελίσασθαι, οὐκ ἐν ἀλλοτρίῳ κανόνα ἡμῶν εἰς περισσεῖαν ^[16] εἰς τὰ ὑπερέκεινα ὑμῶν εὐαγγελίσασθαι, οὐκ ἐν ἀλλοτρίῳ

κανόνι εἰς τὰ ἔτοιμα καυχῆσασθαι. ^[17] ὁ δὲ καυχώμενος ἐν κυρίῳ καυχάσθω· Οὐ γὰρ ὁ ἑαυτὸν κανόνι εἰς τὰ ἔτοιμα καυχῆσασθαι. ^[17] Ὁ δὲ καυχώμενος ἐν κυρίῳ καυχάσθω· 18 οὐ γὰρ ὁ ἑαυτὸν

συνιστάνων ἑκεῖνός ἐστιν δόκιμος, ἀλλ' ὃν ὁ κύριος συνίστησιν. ^[18:1] ὄφελον ἀνείχεσθέ μου συνιστάνων, ἐκεῖνός ἐστιν δόκιμος, ἀλλ' ὃν ὁ κύριος συνίστησιν. § ^[18:1] Ὅφελον ἀνείχεσθέ μου

μικρόν τι ἀφροσύνης; ἀλλὰ καὶ ἀνέχεσθέ μου. ^[2] ζηλῶ γὰρ ὑμᾶς θεοῦ ζήλω· Ἡρμοσάμην γὰρ μικρόν τι ἀφροσύνης· ἀλλὰ καὶ ἀνέχεσθέ μου. ^[2] ζηλῶ γὰρ ὑμᾶς θεοῦ ζήλω, ἡρμοσάμην γὰρ

ὑμᾶς ἐνὶ ἀνδρὶ, παρθένον ἀγνήν παραστήσαι τῷ Χριστῷ. ^[3] Φοβοῦμαι δὲ μή πως ὡς ὁ ὄφεις ὑμᾶς ἐνὶ ἀνδρὶ παρθένον ἀγνήν παραστήσαι τῷ Χριστῷ. ^[3] φοβοῦμαι δὲ μή πως, ὡς ὁ ὄφεις

ἐξηπάτησεν Εὐάν ἐν τῇ πανουργίᾳ αὐτοῦ, φθαρῆ τὰ νοήματα ὑμῶν, ἀπὸ τῆς ἀπλότητος καὶ ἐξηπάτησεν Εὐάν ἐν τῇ πανουργίᾳ αὐτοῦ, φθαρῆ τὰ νοήματα ὑμῶν ἀπὸ τῆς ἀπλότητος [καὶ

τῆς ἀγνότητος τῆς εἰς τὸν Χριστόν. ^[4] Εἰ μὲν γὰρ ὁ ἐρχόμενος ἄλλον Ἰησοῦν κηρύσσει ὃν οὐκ τῆς ἀγνότητος] τῆς εἰς τὸν Χριστόν. ^[4] εἰ μὲν γὰρ ὁ ἐρχόμενος ἄλλον Ἰησοῦν κηρύσσει ὃν οὐκ

ἐκηρύξαμεν, ἢ πνεῦμα ἕτερον λαμβάνετε ὃ οὐκ ἐλάβετε, ἢ εὐαγγέλιον ἕτερον ὃ οὐκ ἐδέξασθε, ἐκηρύξαμεν, ἢ πνεῦμα ἕτερον λαμβάνετε ὃ οὐκ ἐλάβετε, ἢ εὐαγγέλιον ἕτερον ὃ οὐκ ἐδέξασθε,

καλῶς ἀνέχεσθε. ^[5] Λογίζομαι γὰρ μηδὲν ὑστερηκέναί τῶν ὑπερλίαν ἀποστόλων. ^[6] Εἰ δὲ καλῶς ἀνέχεσθε. § ^[5] Λογίζομαι γὰρ μηδὲν ὑστερηκέναί τῶν ὑπερλίαν ἀποστόλων. ^[6] εἰ δὲ

καὶ ιδιώτης τῷ λόγῳ, ἀλλ' οὐ τῇ γνώσει. Ἄλλ' ἐν παντὶ φανερώσαντες ἐν πᾶσιν εἰς ὑμᾶς. καὶ ιδιώτης τῷ λόγῳ, ἀλλ' οὐ τῇ γνώσει, ἀλλ' ἐν παντὶ φανερώσαντες ἐν πᾶσιν εἰς ὑμᾶς.

^[7] Ἡ ἀμαρτίαν ἐποίησα ἑμαυτὸν ταπεινῶν ἵνα ὑμεῖς ὑψωθῆτε, ὅτι δωρεὰν τὸ τοῦ θεοῦ

^[7] Ἡ ἀμαρτίαν ἐποίησα ἑμαυτὸν ταπεινῶν ἵνα ὑμεῖς ὑψωθῆτε, ὅτι δωρεὰν τὸ τοῦ θεοῦ

εὐαγγέλιον εὐηγγελισάμην ὑμῖν ; ^[8] Ἄλλας ἐκκλησίας ἐσύλησα λαβὼν ὀψώνιον πρὸς τὴν ὑμῶν εὐαγγέλιον εὐηγγελισάμην ὑμῖν ; ^[8] ἄλλας ἐκκλησίας ἐσύλησα λαβὼν ὀψώνιον πρὸς τὴν ὑμῶν

διακονίαν. ^[9] Καὶ παρῶν πρὸς ὑμᾶς καὶ ὑστερηθεῖς, οὐ κατενάρκησα οὐθενός. Τὸ γὰρ ὑστέρημά διακονίαν, ^[9] καὶ παρῶν πρὸς ὑμᾶς καὶ ὑστερηθεῖς οὐ κατενάρκησα οὐθενός· τὸ γὰρ ὑστέρημά

μου προσανεπλήρωσαν οἱ ἀδελφοὶ ἐλθόντες ἀπὸ Μακεδονίας. Καὶ ἐν παντὶ ἀβαρῆ ἑμαυτὸν μου προσανεπλήρωσαν οἱ ἀδελφοὶ ἐλθόντες ἀπὸ Μακεδονίας, καὶ ἐν παντὶ ἀβαρῆ ἑμαυτὸν

ὑμῖν ἐτήρησα, καὶ τηρήσω. ^[10] Ἔστιν ἀλήθεια Χριστοῦ ἐν ἐμοί, ὅτι ἡ καύχησις αὕτη οὐ φραγήσεται ὑμῖν ἐτήρησα καὶ τηρήσω. ^[10] ἔστιν ἀλήθεια Χριστοῦ ἐν ἐμοί ὅτι ἡ καύχησις αὕτη οὐ φραγήσεται

εἰς ἐμέ ἐν τοῖς κλίμασιν τῆς Ἀχαΐας. ^[11] διὰ τί ; ὅτι οὐκ ἀγαπῶ ὑμᾶς ; ὁ θεὸς οἶδεν. ^[12] Ὁ δὲ ποιῶ, εἰς ἐμέ ἐν τοῖς κλίμασιν τῆς Ἀχαΐας. ^[11] διὰ τί ; ὅτι οὐκ ἀγαπῶ ὑμᾶς ; ὁ θεὸς οἶδεν. § ^[12] Ὁ δὲ ποιῶ,

καὶ ποιήσω, ἵνα ἐκκόψω τὴν ἀφορμὴν τῶν θελώντων ἀφορμὴν, ἵνα ἐν ᾧ καυχῶνται εὐρεθῶσιν καὶ ποιήσω, ἵνα ἐκκόψω τὴν ἀφορμὴν τῶν θελώντων ἀφορμὴν, ἵνα ἐν ᾧ καυχῶνται εὐρεθῶσιν

καθὼς καὶ ἡμεῖς. ^[13] Οἱ γὰρ τοιοῦτοι ψευδαπόστολοι, ἐργάται δόλιοι μετασχηματιζόμενοι εἰς καθὼς καὶ ἡμεῖς. ^[13] οἱ γὰρ τοιοῦτοι ψευδαπόστολοι, ἐργάται δόλιοι, μετασχηματιζόμενοι εἰς

ἀποστόλους Χριστοῦ. ^[14] Καὶ οὐ θαῦμα ! Αὐτὸς γὰρ ὁ σατανᾶς μετασχηματίζεται εἰς ἄγγελον ἀποστόλους Χριστοῦ. ^[14] καὶ οὐ θαῦμα· αὐτὸς γὰρ ὁ σατανᾶς μετασχηματίζεται εἰς ἄγγελον

φωτός. ^[15] Οὐ μέγα οὖν εἰ καὶ οἱ διάκονοι αὐτοῦ μετασχηματίζονται ὡς διάκονοι δικαιοσύνης. φωτός. ^[15] οὐ μέγα οὖν εἰ καὶ οἱ διάκονοι αὐτοῦ μετασχηματίζονται ὡς διάκονοι δικαιοσύνης·

ᾧ τὸ τέλος ἔσται κατὰ τὰ ἔργα αὐτῶν. ^[16] Πάλιν λέγω, μὴ τίς με δόξη ἄφρονα εἶναι. Εἰ δὲ μὴ γε, ᾧ τὸ τέλος ἔσται κατὰ τὰ ἔργα αὐτῶν. § ^[16] Πάλιν λέγω, μὴ τίς με δόξη ἄφρονα εἶναι· εἰ δὲ μὴ γε,

κἂν ὡς ἄφρονα δέξασθέ με, ἵνα καὶ γὰρ μικρόν τι καυχῆσωμαι. ^[17] Ὁ λαλῶ, οὐ κατὰ κύριον λαλῶ, κἂν ὡς ἄφρονα δέξασθέ με, ἵνα καὶ γὰρ μικρόν τι καυχῆσωμαι. ^[17] ὁ λαλῶ, οὐ κατὰ κύριον λαλῶ

ἀλλ' ὡς ἐν ἀφροσύνῃ, ἐν ταύτῃ τῇ ὑποστάσει τῆς καυχήσεως.^[18] Ἐπεὶ πολλοὶ καυχῶνται κατὰ ἀλλ' ὡς ἐν ἀφροσύνῃ, ἐν ταύτῃ τῇ ὑποστάσει τῆς καυχήσεως.^[18] Ἐπεὶ πολλοὶ καυχῶνται κατὰ

σάρκα, κἀγὼ καυχῆσομαι.^[19] Ἠδέως γὰρ ἀνέχεσθε τῶν ἀφρόνων φρόνιμοι ὄντες.^[20] Ἀνέχεσθε γὰρ σάρκα, κἀγὼ καυχῆσομαι.^[19] Ἠδέως γὰρ ἀνέχεσθε τῶν ἀφρόνων φρόνιμοι ὄντες.^[20] ἀνέχεσθε γὰρ

εἷ τις ὑμᾶς καταδουλοῖ, εἷ τις κατεσθίει, εἷ τις λαμβάνει, εἷ τις ἐπαίρεται, εἷ τις εἰς πρόσωπον εἷ τις ὑμᾶς καταδουλοῖ, εἷ τις κατεσθίει, εἷ τις λαμβάνει, εἷ τις ἐπαίρεται, εἷ τις εἰς πρόσωπον

ὑμᾶς δέρει.^[21] Κατὰ ἀτιμίαν λέγω, ὡς ὅτι ἡμεῖς ἡσθενήκαμεν. Ἐν ᾧ δ' ἂν τις τολμᾷ, ἐν ἀφροσύνῃ ὑμᾶς δέρει.^[21] κατὰ ἀτιμίαν λέγω, ὡς ὅτι ἡμεῖς ἡσθενήκαμεν. § Ἐν ᾧ δ' ἂν τις τολμᾷ, ἐν ἀφροσύνῃ

λέγω, τολμῶ κἀγώ.^[22] Ἐβραῖοί εἰσιν; κἀγώ· Ἰσραηλιταί εἰσιν; κἀγώ· σπέρμα Ἀβραάμ εἰσιν; κἀγώ· λέγω, τολμῶ κἀγώ.^[22] Ἐβραῖοί εἰσιν; κἀγώ· Ἰσραηλιταί εἰσιν; κἀγώ· σπέρμα Ἀβραάμ εἰσιν; κἀγώ.

^[23] διάκονοι Χριστοῦ εἰσιν; Παραφρονῶν λαλῶ, ὑπὲρ ἐγώ. ἐν κόποις περισσοτέρως· ἐν φυλακαῖς ^[23] διάκονοι Χριστοῦ εἰσιν; παραφρονῶν λαλῶ, ὑπὲρ ἐγώ· ἐν κόποις περισσοτέρως, ἐν φυλακαῖς

περισσοτέρως· ἐν πληγαῖς ὑπερβαλλόντως· ἐν θανάτοις πολλάκις.^[24] Ὑπὸ Ἰουδαίων πεντάκις περισσοτέρως, ἐν πληγαῖς ὑπερβαλλόντως, ἐν θανάτοις πολλάκις.^[24] Ὑπὸ Ἰουδαίων πεντάκις

τεσσεράκοντα παρὰ μίαν ἔλαβον.^[25] τρίς ἐρραβδίσθη· ἄπαξ ἐλιθάσθη· τρίς ἐναυάγησα· τεσσεράκοντα παρὰ μίαν ἔλαβον,^[25] τρίς ἐρραβδίσθη, ἄπαξ ἐλιθάσθη, τρίς ἐναυάγησα,

νυχθήμερον ἐν τῷ βυθῷ πεποίηκα.^[26] ὁδοιπορίας πολλάκις· κινδύνοις ποταμῶν· κινδύνοις νυχθήμερον ἐν τῷ βυθῷ πεποίηκα.^[26] ὁδοιπορίας πολλάκις, κινδύνοις ποταμῶν, κινδύνοις

ληστῶν· κινδύνοις ἐκ γένους· κινδύνοις ἐξ ἐθνῶν· κινδύνοις ἐν πόλει· κινδύνοις ἐν ἐρημίᾳ· ληστῶν, κινδύνοις ἐκ γένους, κινδύνοις ἐξ ἐθνῶν, κινδύνοις ἐν πόλει, κινδύνοις ἐν ἐρημίᾳ,

κινδύνοις ἐν θαλάσῃ· κινδύνοις ἐν ψευδαδέλφοις.^[27] κόπῳ καὶ μόχθῳ· ἐν ἀγρυπνίαις πολλάκις· κινδύνοις ἐν θαλάσῃ, κινδύνοις ἐν ψευδαδέλφοις,^[27] κόπῳ καὶ μόχθῳ, ἐν ἀγρυπνίαις πολλάκις,

ἐν λιμῷ καὶ δίψει· ἐν νηστείαις πολλάκις· ἐν ψύχει καὶ γυμνότητι.^[28] Χωρὶς τῶν παρεκτός, ἐν λιμῷ καὶ δίψει, ἐν νηστείαις πολλάκις, ἐν ψύχει καὶ γυμνότητι.^[28] χωρὶς τῶν παρεκτός

ἢ ἐπίστασίς μοι ἢ καθ' ἡμέραν, ἢ μέριμνα πασῶν τῶν ἐκκλησιῶν.^[29] τίς ἀσθενεῖ καὶ οὐκ ἀσθενῶ; ἢ ἐπίστασίς μοι ἢ καθ' ἡμέραν, ἢ μέριμνα πασῶν τῶν ἐκκλησιῶν.^[29] τίς ἀσθενεῖ καὶ οὐκ ἀσθενῶ;

τίς σκανδαλίζεται καὶ οὐκ ἐγὼ πυροῦμαι;^[30] εἰ καυχᾶσθαι δεῖ, τὰ τῆς ἀσθενείας μου καυχῆσομαι. τίς σκανδαλίζεται καὶ οὐκ ἐγὼ πυροῦμαι;^[30] εἰ καυχᾶσθαι δεῖ, τὰ τῆς ἀσθενείας μου καυχῆσομαι.

^[31] Ὁ θεὸς καὶ πατὴρ τοῦ κυρίου Ἰησοῦ οἶδεν, ὃ ὧν εὐλογητὸς εἰς τοὺς αἰῶνας, ὅτι οὐ ψεύδομαι.

^[31] ὁ θεὸς καὶ πατὴρ τοῦ κυρίου Ἰησοῦ οἶδεν, ὃ ὧν εὐλογητὸς εἰς τοὺς αἰῶνας, ὅτι οὐ ψεύδομαι.

^[32] Ἐν Δαμασκῷ ὁ ἐθνάρχης Ἀρέτα τοῦ βασιλέως ἐφρούρει τὴν πόλιν Δαμασκηνῶν ἵπιάσαι με.

^[32] ἐν Δαμασκῷ ὁ ἐθνάρχης Ἀρέτα τοῦ βασιλέως ἐφρούρει τὴν πόλιν Δαμασκηνῶν πιάσαι με,

^[33] Καὶ διὰ θυρίδος ἐν σαργάνῃ, ἐχαλάσθην διὰ τοῦ τείχους, καὶ ἐξέφυγον τὰς χεῖρας αὐτοῦ.

^[33] καὶ διὰ θυρίδος ἐν σαργάνῃ ἐχαλάσθην διὰ τοῦ τείχους καὶ ἐξέφυγον τὰς χεῖρας αὐτοῦ.

^[12:1] καυχᾶσθαι δεῖ· οὐ συμφέρον μὲν, ἐλεύσομαι δὲ εἰς ὀπτασίας καὶ ἀποκαλύψεις κυρίου.

§ ^[12:1] Καυχᾶσθαι δεῖ, οὐ συμφέρον μὲν, ἐλεύσομαι δὲ εἰς ὀπτασίας καὶ ἀποκαλύψεις κυρίου.

^[2] Οἶδα ἄνθρωπον ἐν Χριστῷ πρὸ ἐτῶν δεκατεσσάρων, εἴτε ἐν σώματι ἢ οὐκ οἶδα, εἴτε ἐκτὸς τοῦ

^[2] οἶδα ἄνθρωπον ἐν Χριστῷ πρὸ ἐτῶν δεκατεσσάρων, εἴτε ἐν σώματι οὐκ οἶδα, εἴτε ἐκτὸς τοῦ

σώματος ἢ οὐκ οἶδα, ὁ θεὸς οἶδεν, ἀρπαγέντα τὸν τοιοῦτον ἕως τρίτου οὐρανοῦ. ^[3] Καὶ οἶδα τὸν

σώματος οὐκ οἶδα, ὁ θεὸς οἶδεν, ἀρπαγέντα τὸν τοιοῦτον ἕως τρίτου οὐρανοῦ. ^[3] καὶ οἶδα τὸν

τοιοῦτον ἄνθρωπον, εἴτε ἐν σώματι ἢ εἴτε χωρὶς τοῦ σώματος ἢ οὐκ οἶδα, ὁ θεὸς οἶδεν, ^[4] ὅτι ἠρπάγη

τοιοῦτον ἄνθρωπον, εἴτε ἐν σώματι εἴτε χωρὶς τοῦ σώματος οὐκ οἶδα, ὁ θεὸς οἶδεν, ^[4] ὅτι ἠρπάγη

εἰς τὸν παράδεισον, καὶ ἤκουσεν ἄρρητα ῥήματα, ἃ οὐκ ἐξὸν ἀνθρώπῳ λαλῆσαι. ^[5] Ὑπὲρ τοῦ

εἰς τὸν παράδεισον καὶ ἤκουσεν ἄρρητα ῥήματα ἃ οὐκ ἐξὸν ἀνθρώπῳ λαλῆσαι. ^[5] ὑπὲρ τοῦ

τοιοῦτου καυχῆσομαι, ὑπὲρ δὲ ἑμαυτοῦ οὐ καυχῆσομαι, εἰ μὴ ἐν ταῖς ἀσθενείαις. ^[6] Ἐὰν γὰρ

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θελήσω καυχῆσασθαι, οὐκ ἔσομαι ἄφρων· ἀλήθειαν γὰρ ἐρῶ· φείδομαι δέ, μή τις εἰς ἐμέ λογίσσεται

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ὑπὲρ ὃ βλέπει με ἢ ἀκούει τι ἐξ ἐμοῦ, ^[7] καὶ τῆ ὑπερβολῆ τῶν ἀποκαλύψεων. διὸ ἵνα μὴ

ὑπὲρ ὃ βλέπει με ἢ ἀκούει [τι] ἐξ ἐμοῦ ^[7] καὶ τῆ ὑπερβολῆ τῶν ἀποκαλύψεων. διὸ ἵνα μὴ

ὑπεραίρωμαι, ἐδόθη μοι σκόλοψ τῆ σαρκί, ἄγγελος σατανᾶ ἵνα με κολαφίζῃ, ἵνα μὴ ὑπεραίρωμαι.

ὑπεραίρωμαι, ἐδόθη μοι σκόλοψ τῆ σαρκί, ἄγγελος σατανᾶ, ἵνα με κολαφίζῃ, ἵνα μὴ ὑπεραίρωμαι.

^[8] Ὑπὲρ τούτου τρίς τὸν κύριον παρεκάλεσα, ἵνα ἀποστῆ ἀπ' ἐμοῦ. ^[9] Καὶ εἰρηκέν μοι, ἀρκεῖ σοι ἡ

^[8] ὑπὲρ τούτου τρίς τὸν κύριον παρεκάλεσα ἵνα ἀποστῆ ἀπ' ἐμοῦ. ^[9] καὶ εἰρηκέν μοι· ἀρκεῖ σοι ἡ

χάρις μου, ἡ γὰρ δύναμις ἐν ἀσθενείᾳ τελεῖται. Ἦδιστα οὖν μᾶλλον καυχῆσομαι ἐν ταῖς ἀσθενείαις

χάρις μου, ἡ γὰρ δύναμις ἐν ἀσθενείᾳ τελεῖται. Ἦδιστα οὖν μᾶλλον καυχῆσομαι ἐν ταῖς ἀσθενείαις

μου, ἵνα ἐπισκηνώσῃ ἐπ’ ἐμὲ ἡ δύναμις τοῦ Χριστοῦ. ^[10] Διὸ εὐδοκῶ ἐν ἀσθενείαις, ἐν ὕβρεσιν, μου, ἵνα ἐπισκηνώσῃ ἐπ’ ἐμὲ ἡ δύναμις τοῦ Χριστοῦ. ^[10] διὸ εὐδοκῶ ἐν ἀσθενείαις, ἐν ὕβρεσιν,

ἐν ἀνάγκαις, ἐν διωγμοῖς καὶ στενοχωρίαις, ὑπὲρ Χριστοῦ. Ὅταν γὰρ ἀσθενῶ, τότε δυνατός εἰμι. ἐν ἀνάγκαις, ἐν διωγμοῖς καὶ στενοχωρίαις, ὑπὲρ Χριστοῦ· ὅταν γὰρ ἀσθενῶ, τότε δυνατός εἰμι.

^[11] γέγονα ἄφρων· ὑμεῖς με ἠναγκάσατε ! ἐγὼ γὰρ ὄφειλον ὑφ’ ὑμῶν συνίστασθαι· Οὐδὲν γὰρ ^[11] Γέγονα ἄφρων, ὑμεῖς με ἠναγκάσατε. ἐγὼ γὰρ ὄφειλον ὑφ’ ὑμῶν συνίστασθαι· οὐδὲν γὰρ

ὑστέρησα τῶν ὑπερλίαν ἀποστόλων, εἰ καὶ οὐδὲν εἰμι. ^[12] Τὰ μὲν σημεῖα τοῦ ἀποστόλου ὑστέρησα τῶν ὑπερλίαν ἀποστόλων εἰ καὶ οὐδὲν εἰμι. ^[12] τὰ μὲν σημεῖα τοῦ ἀποστόλου

κατειργάσθη ἐν ὑμῖν ἐν πάσῃ ὑπομονῇ, σημείοις τε καὶ τέρασιν καὶ δυνάμεσιν. ^[13] Τί γὰρ ἐστὶν κατειργάσθη ἐν ὑμῖν ἐν πάσῃ ὑπομονῇ, σημείοις τε καὶ τέρασιν καὶ δυνάμεσιν. ^[13] τί γὰρ ἐστὶν

ὁ ἡσώθητε ὑπὲρ τὰς λοιπὰς ἐκκλησίας, εἰ μὴ ὅτι αὐτὸς ἐγὼ οὐ κατενάρκησα ὑμῶν; χαρίσασθέ ὁ ἡσώθητε ὑπὲρ τὰς λοιπὰς ἐκκλησίας, εἰ μὴ ὅτι αὐτὸς ἐγὼ οὐ κατενάρκησα ὑμῶν; χαρίσασθέ

μοι τὴν ἀδικίαν ταύτην. ^[14] ἰδοὺ ! τρίτον τοῦτο ἐτοίμως ἔχω ἐλθεῖν πρὸς ὑμᾶς· καὶ οὐ καταναρκήσω· μοι τὴν ἀδικίαν ταύτην. § ^[14] Ἰδοὺ τρίτον τοῦτο ἐτοίμως ἔχω ἐλθεῖν πρὸς ὑμᾶς, καὶ οὐ καταναρκήσω·

Οὐ γὰρ ζητῶ τὰ ὑμῶν, ἀλλ’ ὑμᾶς. Οὐ γὰρ ὀφείλει τὰ τέκνα τοῖς γονεῦσιν θησαυρίζειν, ἀλλ’ οἱ οὐ γὰρ ζητῶ τὰ ὑμῶν ἀλλ’ ὑμᾶς. οὐ γὰρ ὀφείλει τὰ τέκνα τοῖς γονεῦσιν θησαυρίζειν ἀλλ’ οἱ

γονεῖς τοῖς τέκνοις. ^[15] ἐγὼ δὲ ἡδιστα δαπανήσω καὶ ἐκδαπανηθήσομαι ὑπὲρ τῶν ψυχῶν ὑμῶν· γονεῖς τοῖς τέκνοις. ^[15] ἐγὼ δὲ ἡδιστα δαπανήσω καὶ ἐκδαπανηθήσομαι ὑπὲρ τῶν ψυχῶν ὑμῶν.

Εἰ περισσοτέρως ὑμᾶς ἀγαπῶν, ἦσσον ἀγαπῶμαι; ^[16] ἔστω δέ· Ἐγὼ οὐ κατεβάρησα ὑμᾶς, ἀλλ’ εἰ περισσοτέρως ὑμᾶς ἀγαπῶ[ν], ἦσσον ἀγαπῶμαι; ^[16] Ἔστω δέ, ἐγὼ οὐ κατεβάρησα ὑμᾶς· ἀλλ’

ὑπάρχων πανοῦργος δόλω ὑμᾶς ἔλαβον; ^[17] Μὴ τινα ὦν ἀπέσταλκα πρὸς ὑμᾶς, δι’ αὐτοῦ ὑπάρχων πανοῦργος δόλω ὑμᾶς ἔλαβον. ^[17] μὴ τινα ὦν ἀπέσταλκα πρὸς ὑμᾶς, δι’ αὐτοῦ

ἐπλεονέκτησα ὑμᾶς; ^[18] παρεκάλεσα Τίτον καὶ συναπέστειλα τὸν ἀδελφόν· μῆτι ἐπλεονέκτησεν ἐπλεονέκτησα ὑμᾶς; ^[18] παρεκάλεσα Τίτον καὶ συναπέστειλα τὸν ἀδελφόν· μῆτι ἐπλεονέκτησεν

ὑμᾶς Τίτος; οὐ τῷ αὐτῷ πνεύματι περιεπατήσαμεν; οὐ τοῖς αὐτοῖς ἴχνεσιν; ^[19] Πάλαι δοκεῖτε ὑμᾶς Τίτος; οὐ τῷ αὐτῷ πνεύματι περιεπατήσαμεν; οὐ τοῖς αὐτοῖς ἴχνεσιν; § ^[19] Πάλαι δοκεῖτε

ὅτι ὑμῖν ἀπολογούμεθα; κατέναντι θεοῦ ἐν Χριστῷ λαλοῦμεν· Τὰ δὲ πάντα ἄγαπητοί ὑπὲρ τῆς ὅτι ὑμῖν ἀπολογούμεθα. κατέναντι θεοῦ ἐν Χριστῷ λαλοῦμεν· τὰ δὲ πάντα, ἀγαπητοί, ὑπὲρ τῆς

ὕμῶν οἰκοδομῆς. ^[20] Φοβοῦμαι γὰρ μή πως ἐλθὼν οὐχ οἴους θέλω εὕρω ὑμᾶς ἢ καὶ εὐρεθῶ ὑμῖν ὕμῶν οἰκοδομῆς. ^[20] φοβοῦμαι γὰρ μή πως ἐλθὼν οὐχ οἴους θέλω εὕρω ὑμᾶς καὶ γὰρ εὐρεθῶ ὑμῖν

οἶον οὐ θέλετε, μή πως ἔρις ἢ ζήλος ἢ θυμοὶ ἢ ἐριθείαι ἢ καταλαλιαί ἢ ψιθυρισμοὶ ἢ φυσιώσεις ἢ οἶον οὐ θέλετε· μή πως ἔρις, ζήλος, θυμοὶ, ἐριθείαι, καταλαλιαί, ψιθυρισμοὶ, φυσιώσεις,

ἀκαταστασίαι. ^[21] Μὴ πάλιν ἐλθόντος μου ταπεινώσῃ με ὁ θεὸς μου πρὸς ὑμᾶς, καὶ πενήθῃσω ἀκαταστασίαι. ^[21] μὴ πάλιν ἐλθόντος μου ταπεινώσῃ με ὁ θεὸς μου πρὸς ὑμᾶς καὶ πενήθῃσω

πολλοὺς τῶν προημάρτηκόντων καὶ μὴ μετανοησάντων, ἐπὶ τῇ ἀκαθαρσίᾳ καὶ πορνείᾳ καὶ πολλοὺς τῶν προημάρτηκόντων καὶ μὴ μετανοησάντων ἐπὶ τῇ ἀκαθαρσίᾳ καὶ πορνείᾳ καὶ

ἀσελγείᾳ ἢ ἔπραξαν! ^[13:1] τρίτον τοῦτο ἔρχομαι πρὸς ὑμᾶς· Ἐπὶ στόματος δύο μαρτύρων καὶ ἀσελγείᾳ ἢ ἔπραξαν. § ^[13:1] Τρίτον τοῦτοἔρχομαι πρὸς ὑμᾶς· ἐπὶ στόματος δύο μαρτύρων καὶ

τριῶν σταθήσεται πᾶν ῥῆμα. ^[2] Προεῖρηκα καὶ προλέγω, ὡς παρῶν τὸ δεύτερον καὶ ἀπῶν νῦν, τριῶν σταθήσεται πᾶν ῥῆμα. ^[2] προεῖρηκα καὶ προλέγω, ὡς παρῶν τὸ δεύτερον καὶ ἀπῶν νῦν,

τοῖς προημάρτηκόσιν καὶ τοῖς λοιποῖς πᾶσιν, ὅτι ἐὰν ἔλθω εἰς τὸ πάλιν ἢ οὐ φείσομαι! ^[3] Ἐπεὶ τοῖς προημάρτηκόσιν καὶ τοῖς λοιποῖς πᾶσιν, ὅτι ἐὰν ἔλθω εἰς τὸ πάλιν οὐ φείσομαι, ^[3] ἐπεὶ

δοκιμὴν ζητεῖτε τοῦ ἐν ἐμοὶ λαλοῦντος Χριστοῦ. Ὅς εἰς ὑμᾶς οὐκ ἀσθενεῖ, ἀλλὰ δυνατεῖ ἐν ὑμῖν. δοκιμὴν ζητεῖτε τοῦ ἐν ἐμοὶ λαλοῦντος Χριστοῦ, ὅς εἰς ὑμᾶς οὐκ ἀσθενεῖ ἀλλὰ δυνατεῖ ἐν ὑμῖν.

^[4] Καὶ γὰρ ἐσταυρώθη ἐξ ἀσθενείας, ἀλλὰ ζῆ ἐκ δυνάμεως θεοῦ. Καὶ γὰρ ἡμεῖς ἀσθενοῦμεν ἐν ^[4] καὶ γὰρ ἐσταυρώθη ἐξ ἀσθενείας, ἀλλὰ ζῆ ἐκ δυνάμεως θεοῦ. καὶ γὰρ ἡμεῖς ἀσθενοῦμεν ἐν

αὐτῷ, ἀλλὰ ζήσομεν σὺν αὐτῷ ἢ ἐκ δυνάμεως θεοῦ ἢ εἰς ὑμᾶς. ^[5] ἑαυτοὺς πειράζετε εἰ ἐστὲ ἐν τῇ αὐτῷ, ἀλλὰ ζήσομεν σὺν αὐτῷ ἐκ δυνάμεως θεοῦ εἰς ὑμᾶς. § ^[5] Ἐαυτοὺς πειράζετε εἰ ἐστὲ ἐν τῇ

πίστει· ἑαυτοὺς δοκιμάζετε· ἢ οὐκ ἐπιγινώσκετε ἑαυτοὺς ὅτι Ἰησοῦς Χριστὸς ἐν ὑμῖν; εἰ μήτι πίστει, ἑαυτοὺς δοκιμάζετε· ἢ οὐκ ἐπιγινώσκετε ἑαυτοὺς ὅτι Ἰησοῦς Χριστὸς ἐν ὑμῖν; εἰ μήτι

ἀδόκιμοὶ ἐστε. ^[6] ἐλπίζω δὲ ὅτι γνώσεσθε ὅτι ἡμεῖς οὐκ ἐσμέν ἀδόκιμοι. ^[7] Εὐχόμεθα δὲ πρὸς τὸν ἀδόκιμοὶ ἐστε. ^[6] ἐλπίζω δὲ ὅτι γνώσεσθε ὅτι ἡμεῖς οὐκ ἐσμέν ἀδόκιμοι. ^[7] εὐχόμεθα δὲ πρὸς τὸν

θεὸν μὴ ποιῆσαι ὑμᾶς κακὸν μηδέν, οὐχ ἵνα ἡμεῖς δόκιμοι φανῶμεν, ἀλλ' ἵνα ὑμεῖς τὸ καλὸν θεὸν μὴ ποιῆσαι ὑμᾶς κακὸν μηδέν, οὐχ ἵνα ἡμεῖς δόκιμοι φανῶμεν, ἀλλ' ἵνα ὑμεῖς τὸ καλὸν

ποιῆτε, ἡμεῖς δὲ ὡς ἀδόκιμοι ὤμεν. ^[8] Οὐ γὰρ δυνάμεθά τι κατὰ τῆς ἀληθείας, ἀλλ' ὑπὲρ τῆς ποιῆτε, ἡμεῖς δὲ ὡς ἀδόκιμοι ὤμεν. ^[8] οὐ γὰρ δυνάμεθά τι κατὰ τῆς ἀληθείας ἀλλ' ὑπὲρ τῆς

ἀληθείας.^[9] Χαίρομεν γὰρ ὅταν ἡμεῖς ἀσθενῶμεν, ὑμεῖς δὲ δυνατοὶ ᾗτε. Τοῦτο καὶ εὐχόμεθα, τὴν ἀληθείας.^[9] χαίρομεν γὰρ ὅταν ἡμεῖς ἀσθενῶμεν, ὑμεῖς δὲ δυνατοὶ ᾗτε· τοῦτο καὶ εὐχόμεθα, τὴν

ὑμῶν κατάρτισιν.^[10] Διὰ τοῦτο ταῦτα ἀπὼν γράφω, ἵνα παρὼν μὴ ἀποτόμως χρήσωμαι, κατὰ τὴν ὑμῶν κατάρτισιν.^[10] Διὰ τοῦτο ταῦτα ἀπὼν γράφω, ἵνα παρὼν μὴ ἀποτόμως χρήσωμαι κατὰ τὴν

ἐξουσίαν ἣν ὁ κύριος ἔδωκέν μοι, εἰς οἰκοδομὴν καὶ οὐκ εἰς καθαίρεσιν.^[11] λοιπόν ἄδελφοί ἄ
ἐξουσίαν ἣν ὁ κύριος ἔδωκέν μοι εἰς οἰκοδομὴν καὶ οὐκ εἰς καθαίρεσιν. §^[11] Λοιπόν, ἀδελφοί,

χαίρετε· καταρτίζεσθε· παρακαλεῖσθε· τὸ αὐτὸ φρονεῖτε· εἰρηνεύετε· καὶ ὁ θεὸς τῆς ἀγάπης καὶ
χαίρετε, καταρτίζεσθε, παρακαλεῖσθε, τὸ αὐτὸ φρονεῖτε, εἰρηνεύετε, καὶ ὁ θεὸς τῆς ἀγάπης καὶ

εἰρήνης ἔσται μεθ' ὑμῶν.^[12] ἀσπάσασθε ἀλλήλους ἐν ἀγίῳ φιλήματι· ἀσπάζονται ὑμᾶς οἱ ἅγιοι
εἰρήνης ἔσται μεθ' ὑμῶν.^[12] Ἀσπάσασθε ἀλλήλους ἐν ἀγίῳ φιλήματι. Ἀσπάζονται ὑμᾶς οἱ ἅγιοι

πάντες.^[13] Ἡ χάρις τοῦ κυρίου Ἰησοῦ Χριστοῦ, καὶ ἡ ἀγάπη τοῦ θεοῦ, καὶ ἡ κοινωνία τοῦ ἁγίου
πάντες. §^[13] Ἡ χάρις τοῦ κυρίου Ἰησοῦ Χριστοῦ καὶ ἡ ἀγάπη τοῦ θεοῦ καὶ ἡ κοινωνία τοῦ ἁγίου

πνεύματος, μετὰ πάντων ὑμῶν.

πνεύματος μετὰ πάντων ὑμῶν.

4.4. *Comment: Differences between the punctuation from the NA²⁸ and the punctuation based on colometry*

When comparing the two versions of 2 Cor 10–13 presented above, it is immediately notable that in general, there are more punctuation marks in the version punctuated on the basis of the colometric structure (bold text). Additionally, the colometry-based punctuation tends to be “stronger,” in the sense that it involves more full stops and high points than the NA version. Let us detail and try to make sense of these differences:

- 1) Numerous commas that appear in the NA are replaced by high points in the colometry-based version. This is because we identified the units marked off by these commas as autonomous *côla* or *commata*, while the editors of the NA read the same units as being part of a sentence. The high points suggest that the concerned units require more autonomy, therefore producing a style that is less continuous or, we might say, less “flowing.”
- 2) There are also more full stops in the colometry-based version than in the NA version. Oftentimes, elements that we identified as major prosodic breaks (i.e., the end of a period) are marked in the NA with a high point or even simply with a comma (see e.g., 10:3–5; 10:12; 11:2; 11:8; 11:9; 11:15; 11:19; 11:32; 12:10; 13:3; 13:9). This reveals a “literary bias” in the NA, or a general tendency to interpret Paul’s style as consisting of long sentences. In other words, the aural character of Paul’s style is not addressed, nor the concrete need for speakers to rest and breath.
- 3) In addition, there are sometimes commas in the colometry-based version in places that lack punctuation in the NA (see e.g., 10:1; 10:3; 10:12; 11:2; 11:9; 11:28; 11:33; 12:4; 12:11; 12:14; 12:14; 12:21; 13:8; 13:10). This difference was predictable; it regularly happens that two or more *côla* are linked at the syntactical level in a way that does not necessitate a punctuation mark when a grammar-based approach of punctuation is adopted.¹⁵⁷

Most of the changes that colometry-based punctuation brings to the text of 2 Cor. 10–13 are almost insignificant when they are taken separately. Aside from a few passages (some of which have been discussed above; see section 3), the choice of punctuation does not drastically impact the meaning conveyed (see above, section 3). However, when the changes in punctuation are taken as a whole, their significance becomes clearer. The

¹⁵⁷ On the grammatical approach to punctuation, see above, section 4.1.

greater impact is the sense of rhythm and the perception of the tone. Due to the more frequent use of punctuation marks and the tendency for these marks to be stronger than in the NA, the speech appears more structured and more rhythmical. At some points, the style even sounds “choppy,” whereas the punctuation found in the NA suggests a more flowing texture. The best illustration of this point is the list of hardships in 11:23–27. The NA mostly punctuates this passage with commas, which suggests that it should be read as an enumeration (i.e., by marking only very slight pauses). Alternatively, the high points and full stops present in the colometry-based punctuation reveal a more vigorous, vehement tone. In sum, Paul’s prose seems more “lively” when it is re-punctuated based on its colometric structure.

5. Synthesis and Conclusion

In this chapter, we have discussed the implications of colometry for the punctuation of Paul’s letters, taking once again 2 Cor 10–13 as a case study. After investigating how ancient rhetoricians conceived the relationship between colometry and the art of delivery—especially as concerns what we termed “aural punctuation”—we explored the benefits of a colometric approach for the punctuation of Paul’s letters in two different areas: “punctuation issues” and “general punctuation.” Let us now sum up the results.

First, an attention to colometry offers fresh insights on certain punctuation issues that are connected to syntactical ambiguities. In fact, when the difficulty consists of segmenting the discourse—which concretely means deciding where the breaks should be placed—colometric analysis is helpful in orienting the debate. It can bring to light aural structuring devices that are not evident when the text is treated as a silent composition, such as sound echoes and equality in length. Furthermore, paying attention to the colometric structure of a passage reveals how certain interpretations are unlikely for reasons of length, as they would result periods that are too long. Of course, colometric analysis is not an instant solution that would permit exegetes to eventually resolve all the issues linked to discourse segmentation. This brings me to the following warning: we should not expect too much from colometric analysis. Sometimes attention to colometry illuminates the structure of a passage, but sometimes it does not, or the argument of colometry is inconclusive. Even when colometry clearly supports one interpretative option, the other options are not invalidated simply because they are “stylistically less good” from a colometric point of view. In other words, it would be erroneous to fall into a stylistic dogmatism that would judge the validity of an interpretation primarily by its

stylistic quality.¹⁵⁸ When dealing with punctuation issues in Paul's letters, the argument of colometry should be weighted by other classic arguments, such as Paul's theology, Paul's stylistic habits, or the literary context of the passage. With these warnings in mind, colometric analysis—whether using the method I proposed in this study or another method that would rely on different criteria of delineation—may serve as an additional tool to orient the debates concerning punctuation issues. I would even argue that colometric analysis *should* serve as an additional tool; NT exegetes cannot ignore the principles of ancient colometry when dealing with punctuation issues.

Secondly, colometry invites us to revise the general punctuation of Paul's letters in modern critical editions and to move towards a system that mirrors the colometric structure. This revised punctuation is *elocutionary* (rather than grammatical) by nature, as it gives an approximation of the expected breaks during aural delivering in accordance with the ancient conventions of *pronunciatio*. In doing so, it brings us closer to the aural character of Paul's letters. As shown with 2 Cor 10–13, there is certainly an aspect of Paul's "inner voice"¹⁵⁹ that can be transmitted through the choice of punctuation marks, despite all the uncertainties surrounding the actual prosodic realisation that Paul intended. The colometric-punctuated text sounds more structured, more rhythmical, and also more vigorous in some places. To conclude, let us return to the modified version of David Sansone's warning that we proposed in the introduction to this chapter: "it is unscientific to assume that one can rely on the punctuation in a modern edition of Paul's letters to provide evidence for the stylistic characteristics of Paul."¹⁶⁰ This effectively holds true insofar as the choices of punctuation are essentially made with the purpose of illuminating the grammar and without attention to the aural nature of Paul's style. However, the elocutionary, colometry-based approach to punctuation suggests that this state of things is not inevitable. Assuming that our study has been conducted in a rigorous manner in each of its steps, it may fairly be asserted that the proposed punctuation for 2 Cor 10–13 reflects Paul's style, although in an imperfect and partial way.

¹⁵⁸ See also my concluding remarks in P. Marschall, "Christ est-il appelé Dieu en Romains 9:5?" (forthcoming).

¹⁵⁹ On how punctuation marks can reveal the writer's "inner voice," see Chafe, "Punctuation and the Prosody of Written Language."

¹⁶⁰ See Sansone's original formulation above, footnote 3 (D. Sansone, "The Computer and the Historia Augusta: A Note on Marriott," 174).

Conclusion

We have reached the end of this study of ancient colometry and its possible application to Paul's prose. Below we will recall the main questions that stand at the origin of our investigation and its intended purposes, then retrace the steps we went through in the preceding chapters as well as the main results obtained. Finally, we will present a few avenues of reflections for the future development of colometric analysis of Pauline letters or of the NT writings more generally.

I. Origins and Aims of this Study

This thesis research started as a reaction to the “sound mapping” movement that has been emerging in NT studies for some ten years now. More specifically, I engaged with the first and second steps of M. E. Lee and B. B. Scott's proposed method for developing sound maps, which consist of delineating “côla” and grouping these côla into “periods.”¹ The discussion also involved the modified version of the method offered by D. Nässelqvist.² As explained in the introduction, I was simultaneously attracted by these scholars' endeavours to explain the micro-structure of early Christian texts in terms of côla and periods and sceptical about some aspects of their approaches. I found two points in particular to be disputable in the treatment of ancient colometry. I reformulate these two concerns below, alongside with a short recapitulation of how the present study sought to address each of them.

The first concern relates to the way that practitioners of sound mapping delineate côla and periods. Indeed, some aspects of Lee and Scott's proposed guidelines appear problematic when compared with the ancient descriptions of colometry that are found in the rhetorical treatises from the Graeco-Roman world; the same remark holds true with respect to the revised criteria proposed by Nässelqvist (although this later refined some aspects of the methodology). As a response to these limits, the present study endeavoured to develop a set of criteria for côla and periods delineation that are more historically-informed. The resulting criteria could then provide NT exegetes with a tool that enables them to analyse the micro-structure of the NT writings in a way that best mirrors the ancient conventions. The first step involved re-examining numerous

¹ M. E. Lee and B. B. Scott, *SMNT*, 169–173. See above, Chapter I, section 2.3.2.

² D. Nässelqvist, *Public Reading*, 126–140. See above, Chapter I, section 2.4.2.

passages from various ancient rhetorical treatises dealing with the topic of colometry. As a second step, the data collected were discussed and transformed into a “method of colometric analysis” (i.e., a set of criteria for identifying cōla and determining when several cōla together form a period).

In parallel with this task of establishing delineation criteria, our study was also concerned with the justifications for applying the notions of cōlon and period to the NT writings. This is a point that had thus far been insufficiently treated by theorists and practitioners of sound mapping. True, the oral-aural environment in which early Christian literature emerged offers strong evidence that NT texts were structured in terms of cōla and periods, following a standard practice of their time. This argument based on the socio-cultural context is underlying in Lee and Scott and in Nässelqvist’s work (although it is not explicitly expressed in terms of justifying the sound mapping approach).³ Be that as it may, such a theoretical justification is not conclusive in itself. At best, one can outline a socio-cultural “plausibility framework” suggesting that NT texts should *probably* have been composed colometrically.⁴ However, the question as to what extent each of the early Christian authors complied with the Graeco-Roman rhetorical conventions remains, especially with respect to colometry. Therefore, it is necessary to proceed to empirical tests—considering one author at a time—and to critically assess whether the categories of cōlon and period appear appropriate for explaining the structural logic of the prose. In the limits of this study, such an empirical verification was conducted for Paul’s prose only, using 2 Cor 10–13 as a test case.

2. *Development and Main Results*

We will now recap the steps of our study and the main results obtained. The development is summarised chapter by chapter below.

Chapter 1 presented the state of research on NT scholarship’s engagement with the topic of ancient colometry while trying to situate the sound mapping movement among other methodologies and approaches in NT studies. We have seen that the recent interest in colometry that has manifested in sound mapping is part of the more general turn of

³ See Lee and Scott, *SMNT*, Chapter 1 (“The Technology of Writing in the Greco-Roman World”), Chapter 2 (“The Woven Composition”), Chapter 3 (“The Grammar of Sound”); D. Nässelqvist, *Public Reading in Early Christianity*, esp. chapter 2 (“Pragmatics of Reading”) and chapter 3 (“Lectors in Early Christian Communities”).

⁴ See above, Chapter 1, section 3.1.3; also see the excursus in Chapter 3, pages 141–143, §2.

biblical studies towards orality. Indeed, within sound mapping, the analysis of a text's colometric structure serves as a means to illuminate the text's sound characteristics and to grasp its aural logic. We have also insisted that sound mapping is a historico-rhetorical approach. Through its use of the rhetorical treatises from the Graeco-Roman world, sound mapping in some ways continues the "rhetorical criticism" approach of the NT as introduced 40 years ago by Hans Dieter Betz and George A. Kennedy.⁵ We have also seen that NT scholars' interest in colometry is not a completely new phenomenon. An aspect that is new, however, is the desire to provide clear and historically-informed criteria to assist exegetes in the task of identifying cōla and periods boundaries. This aspect distinguishes sound mapping from earlier initiatives using colometry, such as the German colometric translations of biblical texts that were published in the 1920s.⁶ We also presented the two methodologies proposed so far by NT scholars for analysing a text's colometric structure (namely, the guidelines established by Lee and Scott, and the revised set of criteria advanced by Nässelqvist), before pointing out some limits in these proposals and more broadly questioning whether a colometric approach to NT texts is well-founded.

Chapter 2 consisted of the philological part of our study. We went through some ten rhetorical treatises—from Aristotle's *Rhetoric* (second part of the 4th century BCE) to Hermogenes' *On Types of Style* (late 2nd or early 3rd century CE)—looking for all forms of useful data on the topic of colometry. The treatises were discussed sequentially as a means of distinguishing each rhetorician's doctrine, which permitted us ensure the stability of the notions of cōlon, comma, and period.⁷ This exploration revealed the richness of ancient sources on the topic of colometry; in the treatises, we find not only definitions and models, but also a large range of recommendations, and numerous examples taken from various pieces of classical literature. When these data are taken together, it becomes possible to form a rather precise idea of what ancient rhetoricians had in mind when using the terms cōlon, comma, and period. If we attempt to give synthetic—and necessarily imperfect—description, we could say the following: a cōlon is a prosodic unit meant to be uttered in a single breath, which limits its maximum extent to around 30 syllables (or slightly above). It conveys a thought that is either complete in

⁵ H. D. Betz, "The Literary Composition and Function of Paul's Letter to the Galatians"; Id., *Galatians: A Commentary on Paul's Letter to the Churches in Galatia*; G. A. Kennedy, *New Testament through Rhetorical Criticism*.

⁶ On this, see above, Chapter I, section 2.I.

⁷ On this question of stability, see above, Chapter 2, sections I.I and II.

itself or that consists of a complete part of a longer thought.⁸ A comma is a cōlon whose specificity resides in its shortened length. There are two ways that such cōla and commata can be combined to form the discourse. Sometimes cōla (or commata) stand on their own, in which case the resulting style is “disjointed.” At other times, several cōla and/or commata are “interwoven” to form a period. A period is thus a combination of many cōla and/or commata (usually between two and four). Typically, periods exhibit stylistic features such as antithesis, hyperbaton of the main verb (which is placed as the end), parisosis (equality in length) or paromoiosis (sound echoes).

In Chapter 3, we further discussed the notions of cōlon, comma, and period, and looked for strategies that may enable modern readers to identify these units in ancient Greek texts. The discussion also involved a critical assessment of Lee and Scott’s as well as Nässelqvist’s respective descriptions of these notions. We focused particularly on the aspects of length, syntax, and figures. One important correction to Lee and Scott’s and Nässelqvist’s descriptions was our assertion of the syntactical autonomy of non-periodic cōla, which somewhat clarified the complex issue of the boundary between the periodic style and the disjointed style. In the task of formulating delineation criteria, the main difficulty encountered was that the system of colometry appeared highly flexible—and this point arguably explains some of the problems in Lee and Scott’s and Nässelqvist’s descriptions. That is, besides the typical cōla and the typical periods (which are relatively codified and thus easy to describe), there is room for important variations in terms of length, syntactic characteristics, or the use of figures. This led us to formulate the delineation criteria into two distinct categories: *laws* (which express rules that are always valid) and *tendencies* (which express rules that are often, yet not always, valid). The result was a set of 21 rules (8 laws and 13 tendencies), to be used together as a method of colometric analysis.⁹

In Chapter 4, I applied this set of delineation rules to 2 Cor 10–13. This essay of colometric analysis served both to evaluate the operationality of the proposed criteria and to critically assess whether the categories of cōlon and period are appropriate to explain the micro-structure of Paul’s letters. Generally speaking, the criteria revealed efficient at making delineation choices, although some hesitations and open questions remained. One major difficulty was to determine the weight that the figures of paromoiosis (sound echoes) and parisosis (equality in length) should be awarded to in

⁸ A clearer description of this point is that given by Pseudo-Demetrius, *Eloc.* 2–3.

⁹ For a summary table, see Chapter 3, section 4 (figure 3).

the process of identifying periods. Indeed, as previously discussed in Chapter 3, these two figures typically occur in periodic style; however, we were not able to determine whether or not the sole presence of these figures in subsequent *côla* ever constitutes a sufficient ground for concluding that these *côla* together form a period.¹⁰ Another practical question that arose in application was how to treat direct speeches. Concerning the appropriateness of a colometric approach to Paul's letters, we sought not only to ensure that it is *possible* to analyse 2 Cor 10–13 in terms of *côla* and periods, but we further discussed whether the results of such an analysis *actually capture the text's inner logic*. As we have seen, various elements can be advanced that together strongly suggest that the text of 2 Cor 10–13 was indeed structured in *côla* and periods. In order to consolidate these initial results, we would now welcome the application of our method to extracts of other letters or even idealistically to the entire Pauline corpus.

Finally, Chapter 5 considered the implications of colometry for the specific area of punctuation. We explored the link between colometry and punctuation, suggesting that the conventions of colometric structuration assisted ancient readers in their task of orally “punctuating” texts in terms of pauses, breathing, and intonation. The discussion then turned to the concrete implications for punctuating Paul's letters with modern punctuation marks. Using a few examples from 2 Cor 10–13, it was demonstrated that an attention to colometry can in some cases renew the debates surrounding the correct segmentation of Paul's discourse. This is perhaps the first and most direct implication of colometry for the exegesis of Paul's letters. However, despite these encouraging perspectives, exegetes should carefully avoid falling a form of “stylistic dogmatism”: colometric analysis does not support definitive arguments in the debates concerning punctuation. Colometric analysis should instead be seen as a supplementary tool to be articulated with other arguments related to grammar, the literary context, as well as to Paul's theology, stylistic habits, and rhetorical strategies. Finally, we illustrated how the correspondence between the principles of colometric structuration and the ancient conventions of delivery may assist us in punctuating Paul's prose in a way that better reflects its inner “aural” logic. We argued that the appropriate punctuation of Paul's letters is elocutionary-based rather than grammatical.¹¹ This last point invites exegetes to think further about the value of punctuation marks in terms of imparting a particular rhythm and a particular tone to the printed text.

¹⁰ On this issue, see Chapter 3, section 3.4.1. and Chapter 4, section 3.2.

¹¹ On this fundamental distinction, see above, Chapter 5, section 4.1.

3. *Suggestions for the Future Development of Colometric Analysis*

As a conclusion to this study, I wish to offer a few remarks, suggestions, and open questions to be considered for the future development of colometric analysis. I will begin with Pauline studies before turning to NT studies in general.

Analysing and comparing the colometric structures of the different letters of the Pauline corpus may provide new arguments in the debates over the authenticity of certain letters. Indeed, paying attention to the colometric characteristics of a text (such as the length of *côla*, the frequency of *paromoiosis* and *pariosis*, the use of *hyperbaton*, etc.) may lead us to develop a better understanding of its author's stylistic habits, thereby introducing new elements of comparison between the letters of the Pauline corpus.

Further, the awareness of the ancient conventions of colometry may renew the field of stylistic analysis of Paul's letters. Colometric analysis—as defined in this study—has a very limited scope of investigation, as it focuses only on those elements that are useful to grasp the colometric structure of a text. It would thus be worth integrating colometric analysis within a broader, more complete historico-rhetorical investigation of Paul's style. This new stylistic approach should include the various oral-aural aspects of the Greek stylistic conventions (for example, taking the sound mapping methodology as a model) while also considering the more “silent” aspects of these conventions, such as figures of thought and tropes or the theory of levels of style (grand, middle, plain).

Another area of application worth considering is the question of Paul's education or of his degree of expertise in rhetoric. Indeed, it is generally thought that the art of arranging a text in *côla* and periods was part of the final stage of the Greek educational system.¹² Of course, we should avoid hastily concluding that Paul's use of the codes of colometry is evidence of a formal training in rhetoric. This would be a shortcut in reasoning, as rhetoric is a largely informal social practice that can be learned through imitation.¹³ In regard to Paul's rhetorical skills, however, it might be fruitful to look for rhythmical patterns in his letters. Was Paul mindfully favouring certain feet upon the recommendations of Greek rhetoricians? Do certain metrical feet typically occur at the

¹² See notably P. Chiron, “Les *côla* en rhétorique: respiration, sens, esthétique,” 33–34. One element that supports this view is the absence of discussion of colometry in the *progymnasmata* (see *ibid.*, 33).

¹³ I agree here with R. S. Schellenberg, *Rethinking Paul's Rhetorical Education*, esp. 243–254. On the art of imitation, see notably Cic., *De or.* III,31 and August., *Doctr. Chr.* IV,3,4–5.

end of his periods or at the cola-boundaries?¹⁴ If that were the case, it would attest to a certain mastery in style (and indeed a mastery of the Greek language).

In this study, we focused exclusively on the case of Paul's prose. Now, if we move away from Paul to consider the NT literature more generally, a question that remains is the *area of validity* of the colometric approach. Despite the positive conclusions reached with respect to Paul, we should not be compelled to conclude that *all* NT texts can be analysed through the lens of ancient colometry. It might be the case that some early Christian authors were not especially mindful of the micro-structure of their compositions, or that they relied on other conventions that differ from those described by the Greek and Latin rhetoricians. Therefore, one next step for the development of colometric analysis of the NT— and of the sound mapping movement beyond—should be to perform empirical tests on books other than Paul's letters so as to verify whether or not these also seem to adopt the codes of colometry.

Finally, I would welcome other NT scholars to engage in a close examination of the ancient sources of colometry in order to critically assess and refine our proposed set of criteria. If perfection in this domain is unattainable, there is certainly room for further improvements.

¹⁴ On the use of rhythms in prose, see notably Arist., *Rhet.* III,8; Dem., *Eloc.* 39; Cic., *Or. Brut.* 187 and 227; Dion. Hal., *Comp.* 23; Quint., *Inst.* IX,4.

BIBLIOGRAPHY

I. Ancient Sources

I.1. Rhetorical treatises

Alexander, *On Figures (Fig.)*

Ahn Jaewon (ed.), *Alexandri de figuris sententiarum et verborum*. (PhD diss., Georg-August Universität, 2004).

[= *Pages 9–40 in *Rhetores Graeci*, vol. III. Edited by Leonhard von Spengel. Leipzig: Teubner, 1856].

[Anonymous], *Rhetoric for Herennius (Rhet. Her.)*

Achard, Guy (ed. and trans.). *Rhétorique à Herennius*. Paris: Les Belles Lettres, 1989.

Bornecque, Henri (ed. and trans.), *Rhétorique à Hérennius*. Paris: Garnier, 1932.

*Caplan, Harry (trans.), *Rhetorica ad Herennium*. Based on the Latin text established by F. Marx. LCL 403. Cambridge: Harvard University Press, 1954.

Nisard, M. (ed.) and M. Thibaut (trans.), *Rhétorique, à C. Herennius*. Vol. I of *Cicéron. Œuvres complètes*. Paris: Didot, 1864.

[Anonymous], *Rhetoric to Alexander*

R. Mayhew and D. C. Mirhady (ed. and trans.), *Aristotle, Problems: books 20–38. Rhetoric to Alexander* (LCL). Cambridge: Harvard University Press, 2011.

Anonymus Seguerianus, *Art of Political Speech*

* Patillon, Michel (ed. and trans.), *Anonyme de Séguier: Art du discours politique*. Paris: Les Belles Lettres, 2005.

Dilts, Mervin R. and G. A. Kennedy (ed. and trans.), *Two Greek Rhetorical Treatises from the Roman Empire: Introduction, Text, and Translation of the Arts of Rhetoric Attributed to Anonymus Seguerianus & to Aspines of Gadara*. Leiden: Brill, 1997.

Aquila Romanus, *On Figures*

* Elice, Martina (ed. and trans.), *Romani Aquilae De figuris*. Hildesheim / Zurich / New York: George Olms Verlag, 2007.

[= Pages 22–37 in Karl Halm (ed), *Rhetores Latini Minores*. Leipzig: Teubner, 1863].

Aristotle, *Art of Rhetoric (Rhet.)*

Dufour, Médéric and André Wartelle (ed. and trans.), *Aristote, Rhétorique (Livre III)*. Paris: Les Belles Lettres, 2011.

* Freese, John H. (trans.), *Aristotle, Art of Rhetoric*. Revised by Gisela Striker. Based on the Greek text established by Rudolf Kassel. LCL 193. Cambridge (MA) / London: Harvard University Press, 2020. [1st ed. 1926, trans. J. H. Freese].

Kassel, Rudolf (ed.), *Aristotelis Ars Rhetorica*. Berlin: de Gruyter, 1976.

Kennedy, George A. (trans.), *Aristotle. On Rhetoric: A Theory of Civic Discourse*. Oxford: Oxford University Press, 2006.

Waterfield, Robins (trans.), *Aristotle, The Art of Rhetoric*. With an introduction and notes by Harvey Yunis. Oxford: Oxford University Press, 2018.

Aspines of Gadara, *Art of Rhetoric*

Dilts, Mervin R. and George A. Kennedy (trans.), *Two Greek Rhetorical Treatises from the Roman Empire: Introduction, Text, and Translation of the Arts of Rhetoric Attributed to Anonymous Segerianus & to Aspines of Gadara*. Leiden: Brill, 1997.

Patillon, Michel (ed. and trans.), *Art rhétorique. Problèmes à faux-semblant*. Paris: Les Belles Lettres, 2001.

Cicero, *Orator (Or.)*

* Hendrickson, G. L. and H. M. Hubbell (ed. and trans.), *Cicero: Brutus. Orator*. LCL 342. Cambridge: Harvard University Press, 1939.

Yon, Albert (ed. and trans.), *L'orateur. Du meilleur genre d'orateur*. Paris: Les Belles Lettres, 1964.

Cicero, *On the Orator (De or.)*

Bornecque, Henry (ed.), Edmond Courbaud and H. Bornecque (trans.), *De l'orateur, livre III*. Paris: Les Belles Lettres, 1971.

* Rackham, H. (ed. and trans.), *On the Orator, Book 3. On Fate. Stoic Paradoxes. Divisions of Oratory*. Based on the Latin text established by V. Bétolaud. LCL. Cambridge: Harvard University Press, 1942.

Dionysius of Halicarnassus, *On Literary Composition (Comp.)*

Aujac, Germaine, and M. Lebel (ed. and trans.), *Denys d'Halicarnasse: La composition stylistique*. Vol. 3 of *Opuscules rhétoriques*. Paris: Les Belles Lettres, 1981 (repr. 2003).

Roberts, W. Rhys (ed. and trans.), *Dionysius of Halicarnassus on Literary Composition, being the Greek text of the de Compositione Verborum*. London: Macmillan, 1910.

*Usher, Stephen (ed. and trans.), *On Literary Composition. Dinarchus. Letters to Ammaeus and Pompeius*. Vol. 2 of *Dionysius of Halicarnassus: Critical Essays*. LCL 466. Cambridge: Harvard University Press, 1985.

Hermogenes, *On Ideas (Id.)*

*Patillon, Michel (ed. and trans.), *Prolégomènes au De Ideis. Hermogène: Les catégories stylistiques du discours (De Ideis). Synopses des exposés sur les Ideai*. Vol. IV of *Corpus Rhetoricum*. Paris: Les Belles Lettres, 2012.

Wooten, Cecil W., *Hermogenes' On Types of Style*. Based on the Greek text established by Hugo Rabe [H. Rabe, *Hermogenis opera*. Leipzig: Teubner, 1913. Repr. Stuttgart: Teubner, 1969]. Chapel Hill: University of North Carolina Press, 1987.

Hermogenes, *On Stases*

Heath, Malcolm (trans.), *Hermogenes on Issues: Strategies of Argument in Later Greek Rhetoric*. Oxford: Clarendon Press, 1995.

Julius Rufinianus, *On Figures*

Pages 37–62 in Karl Halm (ed.), *Rhetores Latini Minores*. Leipzig: Teubner, 1863.

Longinus, *Art of Rhetoric*

Patillon, Michel and Luc Brisson (ed. and trans.), *Longin: Fragments. Art Rhétorique. Rufus: Art rhétorique*. Paris: Les Belles Lettres, 2001.

[= Pages 179–197 in Hammer-Spengel (eds), *Rhetores Graeci*. Leipzig: Teubner, 1894].

Pseudo-Aelius Aristides, *Political Discourse (Pol.)*

* Patillon, Michel (ed. and trans.), *Pseudo-Aelius Aristide, Discours politique*. Vol. I of *Arts Rhétoriques*. Paris: Les Belles Lettres, 2002.

[= Pages 459–512 in Leonhard Spengel (ed.), *Rhetores Graeci*, vol. II. Leipzig: Teubner, 1856].

Pseudo-Demetrius, *On Style (Eloc.)*

*Chiron, Pierre (ed. and trans.), *Démétrios: Du style*. Paris: Les Belles Lettres, 1993 [reprinted 2002].

Grube, G. M. A. (ed. and trans.), *A Greek Critic: Demetrius on Style*. Toronto: University of Toronto Press, 1961.

Innes, Doreen C., *Aristotle: Poetics. Longinus: On the Sublime. Demetrius: On Style*. Based on the translation by W. R. Roberts. LCL 199. Cambridge: Harvard University Press, 1995.

Marini, Nicoletta (ed. and trans.), *Demetrio, Lo Stile*. Roma: Edizioni di storia e letteratura, 2007.

Roberts, W. Rhys (ed. and trans.), *Demetrius On Style. The Greek Text of Demetrius De*

Elocutione, edited after the Paris Manuscript. New York: Cambridge University Press, 1902 (repr. New York: Cambridge University Press, 2010).

Pseudo-Hermogenes, *On Invention*

Kennedy, George A. (trans.). *Invention and Method: Two Rhetorical Treatises from the Hermogenic Corpus*. Based on the text established by Hugo Rabe [H. Rabe, *Hermogenis opera*. Leipzig: Teubner, 1913. Repr. Stuttgart: Teubner, 1969]. Atlanta: Society of Biblical Literature, 2005.

Patillon, Michel (ed. and trans.), *Pseudo-Hermogène, L'Invention. Anonyme, Synopse des Exordes. Anonyme, Scolies au traité Sur l'Invention du Pseudo-Hermogène*. Vol. III of *Corpus Rhetoricum*. Paris: Les Belles Lettres, 2012.

Pseudo-Hermogenes, *On the Method of Speaking Effectively*

Kennedy, George A. (trans.), *Invention and Method: Two Rhetorical Treatises from the Hermogenic Corpus*. Based on the text established by Hugo Rabe [H. Rabe, *Hermogenis opera*. Leipzig: Teubner, 1913. Repr. Stuttgart: Teubner, 1969]. Atlanta: Society of Biblical Literature, 2005.

Pseudo-Herodian, *On Figures (Fig.)*

Hajdú, Kerstin et al. (ed.), *Aelius Herodianus, Ps.-Herodian: De figuris / Das attizistische Lexikon des Moeris*. Berlin: W. de Gruyter, 1998.

[= Pages 85–104 in Leonhard von Spengel (ed.), *Rhetores Graeci*, vol. III. Leipzig: Teubner, 1856].

Pseudo-Longinus, *On the Sublime*

Fyfe, W. Hamilton (trans.). *Aristotle: Poetics. Longinus: On the Sublime. Demetrius: On Style*. Revised by D. A. Russell. LCL 199. Cambridge (MA): Harvard University Press, 1995.

Rutilius Lupus, *On Figures*

Brooks, Edward Jr., *Rutilii Lupi De figuris sententiarum et elocutionis*. Leiden: Brill, 1970.

[= Pages 3–21 in Karl Halm (ed.), *Rhetores Latini minores*. Leipzig: Teubner, 1863].

Quintilian. *The Orator's Education (Inst.)*

Cousin, Jean (ed. and trans.), *Institution oratoire (Inst.)*. 7 vol. Vol. I: book I. Vol. II: books II–III. Vol. III: books IV and V. Vol. IV: books VI and VII. Vol. V: books VIII and IX. Vol. VI: books X and XI. Vol. VII: book XII and index. Paris: Les Belles Lettres, 1975–1980.

*Russell, Donald A. (ed. and trans.), *The Orator's Education*. 5 vols. LCL. Cambridge (MA): Harvard University Press. Vol. I: books 1–2. Vol. II: books 3–5. Vol. III: books 6–8. Vol. IV: books 9–10. Vol. V: books 11–12.

1.2. Other ancient sources

- Aeschines, *Against Ctesiphon*. Translated by C. D. Adams. *Aeschines: Speeches*. LCL 106. Cambridge (MA): Harvard University Press, 1919.
- Aeschylus, *Agamemnon*. Edited and translated by Alan H. Sommerstein. *Aeschylus: Oresteia: Agamemnon. Libation-Bearers. Eumenides*. LCL 146. Cambridge (MA): Harvard University Press, 2009.
- Aristophanes, *The Clouds*. Edited and translated by Jeffrey Henderson. *Aristophanes: Clouds. Wasps. Peace*. LCL 488. Cambridge (MA): Harvard University Press, 1998.
- [Aristotle], *Περὶ ακουστῶν / De Audibilibus (On Things Heard)*. Pages 98–110 in *Greek Musical Writings*. Vol. II: *Harmonic and Acoustic Theory* (ed. Andrew Barker). Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 1989.
- Aristotle, *Politics*. Translated by H. Rackham. LCL 264. Cambridge (MA): Harvard University Press, 1989.
- Augustine, *De doctrina Christiana / Christian Doctrine*. Translated by Madeleine Moreau. *La doctrine chrétienne, livre IV*. Paris: Institut d'Études Augustiniennes, 1997.
- Cicero, *Letters to Friends*. Translated by D. R. Shackleton Bailey. 3 vols. LCL 205, 216, and 230. Cambridge (MA): Harvard University Press, 2001.
- , *The Orations of Marcus Tullius Cicero*. Translated by C. D. Yonge. 4 vols. London: G. Bell and Sons, 1913–1921.
- Demosthenes, *Orations*. Translated by J. H. Vince, C. A. Vince, A. T. Murry, N. J. De Witt, and N. W. De Witt. 7 vol. LCL. Cambridge (MA): Harvard University Press, 1926–1949.
- Dionysius of Thrax, *Grammar*. Edited and translated by Jean Lallot. *La grammaire de Denys le Thrace*. Paris: CNSR Editions, 1998.
- Erasmus, *De recta latini graecique sermonis pronuntiatione dialogus* (published 1528). *The Right Way of Speaking Latin and Greek: A Dialogue*. Translated and annotated by Maurice Pope. Toronto: University of Toronto Press, 1985.
- Eustathius of Thessalonica, *Commentary on the Iliad*. Edited by Marchinus van der Valk. *Eustathii archiepiscopi Thessalonicensis Commentarii ad Homeri Iliadem pertinentes*. 4 vol. Leiden: Brill, 1971–1987.
- Herodotus, *The Persian Wars*. Translated by A. D. Godley. 2 vol. LCL 117–120. Cambridge (MA): Harvard University Press, 1920–1925.
- Hippocrates, *Aphorisms*. Translated W. H. S. Jones. *Hippocrates: Nature of Man. Regimen in Health. Humours. Aphorisms. Regimen 1-3. Dreams. Heracleitus: On the Universe*. LCL 150. Cambridge (MA): Harvard University Press, 1931.
- Homer, *Iliad*. Translated by A. T. Murray, revised by W. R. Wyatt. 2 vol. LCL 170 and 171. Cambridge (MA): Harvard University Press, 1924–1925.
- Irenaeus, *Against Heresies*. Edited and translated by Adelin Rousseau and Louis Doutreleau. *Irénée de Lyon: Contre les hérésies. Edition critique*. 10 vol. Sources chrétiennes. Paris: Cerf, 1965–1982.

- Isocrates, *Panegyricus*. Translated by George Norlin. *Isocrates*, vol. I: *To Demonicus. To Nicocles. Nicocles or the Cyprians. Panegyricus. To Philip. Archidamus*. LCL. Cambridge (MA): Harvard University Press, 1928.
- Jerome, “Prologue to the Book of Isaiah” (*Prolog. Is.*). Edited and translated by Aline Canellis. Pages 432–437 in *Préfaces aux livres de la Bible*. Paris: Cerf, 2017. [= Col. 771-774 in *Patrologiae Cursus Completus, Series Latina*. Vol. 28. Edited by Jacques-Paul Migne, 1846.]
- , “Prologue to the Book of Ezekiel” (*Prolog. Ez.*). Edited and translated by Aline Canellis. Pages 444–449 in *Préfaces aux livres de la Bible*. Paris: Cerf, 2017. [= Col. 937-940 in *Patrologiae Cursus Completus, Series Latina*. Vol. 28. Edited by Jacques-Paul Migne, 1846].
- Ovid, *Metamorphoses*. Translated by Frank J. Miller. 2 vol. LCL 42 and 43. Cambridge (MA): Harvard University Press, 1916.
- Petronius, *Satyricon*. Edited and translated by Gareth Schmeling. *Petronius: Satyricon. Seneca: Apocolocyntosis*. LCL. Cambridge (MA): Harvard University Press, 2020.
- Philostratus, *Lives of the Sophists*. Translated by Wilmer C. Wright (*Philostratus: Lives of the Sophists. Eunapius: Lives of the Philosophers and Sophists*). LCL 134. Cambridge (MA): Harvard University Press, 1921.
- Plato, *Menexenus*. Translated by R. G. Bury. *Plato: Timaeus. Critias. Cleitophon. Menexenus. Epistles*. LCL 234. Cambridge (MA): Harvard University Press, 1929.
- Plato, *Politicus / Statesman*. Translated by H. N. Fowler. *Plato: Statesman. Philebus. Ion*. LCL 164. Cambridge (MA): Harvard University Press, 1925.
- Plato, *Republic*. Edited and translated by Chris Emlyn-Jones and William Preddy. Vol. I: books 1–5. Vol. II: books 6–10. LCL. Cambridge (MA): Harvard University Press, 2013.
- [Soudas], Θρασύμαχος, in Id., *Suidae Lexicon*. Edited by Emmanuel Bekker. Berlin: G. Reimer, 1854, page 508.
- , Νικάνωρ, in Id., *Suidae Lexicon*. Edited by Emmanuel Bekker. Berlin: G. Reimer, 1854, page 742.
- , Ἐρμογένης, in Id., *Suidae Lexicon*. Edited by Emmanuel Bekker. Berlin: G. Reimer, 1854, page 422.
- Theophrastus, *On Diction (Περὶ λέξεως)*. Edited by A. Mayer. *Theophrasti Περὶ λέξεως libri fragmenta*. Leipzig: Teubner, 1855.
- Thucydides, *History of the Peloponnesian War*. Translated by C. S. Smith. 4 vol. LCL 108, 109, 110, and 169. Cambridge (MA): Harvard University Press. 1919–1923.
- Virgil, *Aeneid*. Translated by H. Rushton Fairclough, revised by G. P. Goold. *Virgil: Eclogues. Georgics. Aeneid: Books 1-6*. LCL 63. Cambridge (MA): Harvard University Press, 1969.
- Xenophon, *Anabasis*. Translated by Carleton L. Brownson, revised by John Dillery. LCL 90. Cambridge (MA): Harvard University Press, 1998.

1.3. Critical Editions of the New Testament

- Aland, Barbara and Kurt Aland, *et al.* (eds), *Novum Testamentum Graece*. Based on the work of Eberhard and Erwin Nestle. 28th ed. Stuttgart: Deutsche Bibelgesellschaft, 2012 (= NA²⁸).
- Aland, Barbara and Kurt Aland, *et al.* (eds), *The Greek New Testament*. 5th ed. London / New York: United Bible Societies, 2014 (= UBS⁵).
- Institut für Neutestamentliche Textforschung, *Novum Testamentum Graecum. Editio Critica Maior*. Vol III: *Die Apostelgeschichte / Acts* (4 vols., 2017). Vol. IV: *Die Katholischen Briefe/Catholic Letters* (2 vols., 2nd ed., 2013).
- Metzger, Bruce M., *A Textual Commentary on the Greek New Testament: A Companion Volume to the United Bible Societies' Greek New Testament*. 3rd ed. London / New York: United Bible Societies, 1971.
- Swanson, Reuben J. (ed.), *New Testament Greek Manuscripts: Variant Readings Arranged in Horizontal Lines against Codex Vaticanus. 2 Corinthians*. Pasadena: William Carey International University Press, 2006.
- Westcott, B. F., and F. J. A. Hort (eds), *The Greek New Testament with Comparative Apparatus Showing Variations from the Nestle-Aland and Robinson-Pierpont Editions*. Peabody, Mass.: Hendrickson Publishers, 2007.

2. Dictionaries, Encyclopaedias, and Grammars

- Aune, David Edward, *The Westminster Dictionary of New Testament and Early Christian Literature*. Louisville (Ky.) / London: Westminster John Knox Press, 2003.
- Bailly, Anatole, *Dictionnaire grec-français* (1895). Revised by L. Séchan and P. Chantraine. Paris: Hachette, 2000.
- Bakker S. J., and G. C. Wakker (eds), *Discourse Cohesion in Ancient Greek*. Leiden / Boston: Brill, 2009.
- Ballif, Michelle and Michael G. Moran (eds), *Classical Rhetorics and Rhetoricians: Critical Studies and Sources*. Westport / London: Prager, 2005.
- Barker, A., "The Peripatetic *De Audibilibus*." Pages 98–110 in *Greek Musical Writings*. Vol. II: *Harmonic and Acoustic Theory* (ed. Andrew Barker). Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 1989.
- Bauer, Walter (edited and revised by Frederick W. Danker), *A Greek-English Lexicon of the New Testament and Other Early Christian Literature* (BDAG). 3rd ed. Chicago / London: University of Chicago Press, 2000.
- Blass, Frierich W., Debrunner Albert, Funk, Robert W., *A Greek Grammar of the New Testament and Other Early Christian Literature*. Chicago / London: The University of Chicago Press, 1986.

- Bonifazi, Anna, Annemieke Drummen, and Mark de Kreij. *Particles in Ancient Greek Discourse: Exploring Particle Use across Genres*. 5 vol. Washington DC: Center for Hellenic Studies, 2016.
- Cancik, Hubert, Helmuth Schneider, Manfred Landfester (eds.), *Der Neue Pauly* (ed.). Print version (19 vol.): Stuttgart / Weimar: J. B. Metzler, 1996–2003. Online version: *Der Neue Pauly Online*: Brill, 2006 (ET: *Brill's New Pauly [online]*, edited by Christine F. Salazar and Francis G. Gentry).
- Giannakis, Georgios K. et al (eds.), *Encyclopedia of Ancient Greek Language and Linguistics*. 3 vol. Leiden / Boston: Brill, 2014.
- Goodell, Thomas D., *A School Grammar of Attic Greek*. New York: D. Appleton & Co, 1902.
- Keith, Chrys, Tom Thatcher, R. F. Person, and E. R. Stern (eds), *Dictionary of the Bible and Ancient Media*. New York: Bloomsbury / T&T Clark, 2017.
- Kühner, Raphael, Bernhard Gerth, and Kühner-Gerth, *Ausführliche Grammatik der griechischen Sprache*. 2 vol. Hannover: Hahn'sche, 1890–1904.
- Lausberg, Heinrich, *Handbuch der literarischen Rhetorik: eine Grundlegung der Literaturwissenschaft* (ed. H. Lausberg). 2nd ed. München: M. Hueber, 1973 [ET: *Handbook of Literary Rhetoric: A Foundation for Literary Study*. Leiden / Boston: Brill, 1998].
- Levinsohn, Stephen H., *Discours Features of New Testament Greek: A Coursebook on the Information Structure of New Testament Greek*. 2nd ed. Dallas: SIL International, 2010.
- Liddle, Henry, and Scott, Robert (eds.), *A Greek-English Lexicon* (1843). Revised by Henry Stuart Jones and Roderick McKenzie. 10 vol. Oxford: Clarendon Press, 1925–1940. Online version: <Thesaurus Linguae Graecae, 2011: <http://stephanus.tlg.uci.edu/lsg/>>.
- Louw and Nida, *Greek-English Lexicon of the New Testament Based on Semantic Domains*. 2nd ed. New York: United Bible Societies, 1989.
- Porter, Stanley E., *Idioms of the Greek New Testament*. 2nd ed. Sheffield: Sheffield Academic, 1999.
- Porter, Stanley E. (ed.), *Handbook of Classical Rhetoric in the Hellenistic Period 330 B.C.-A.D. 400*. Leiden: Brill, 1997.
- Porter, Stanley E. and S.A. Adams (eds). *Paul and the Ancient Letter Form*. Leiden: Brill, 2010.
- Robertson, Archibald T., *A Grammar of the Greek New Testament in the Light of Historical Research*. New York: Hodder & Stoughton, 1919.
- Runge, Steven E., *Discourse Grammar of the Greek New Testament: A Practical Introduction for Teaching and Exegesis*. 4th ed. Peabody (Mass): Hendrickson Publishers, 2015.
- Thrall, Margaret E., *Greek Particles in the New Testament: Linguistic and Exegetical Studies*. Leiden: Brill, 1962.
- Ueding, Gert (ed.), *Historisches Wörterbuch der Rhetorik*. 12 vol. Tübingen / Berlin: Niemeyer / De Gruyter, 1992–2016.

Wallace, Daniel B., *Greek Grammar Beyond the Basics: An Exegetical Syntax of the New Testament*. Grand Rapids (MI): Zondervan, 1997.

3. Secondary Literature

Abbott, Ezra, "Recent Discussions on Rom. IX. 5." *JSBLE* 3 (1883): 90–112.

—, "On the Construction of Romans ix. 5." *JSBLE* 1/2 (1881): 87–154.

Achard, Guy, "Introduction" (*Rhétorique à Hérennius*). Pages v–xxxiv in Id. (ed. and trans.), *Rhétorique à Herennius*. Paris: Les Belles Lettres, 1989.

Achtemeier, Paul. J., "Omne verbum sonat: The New Testament and the Oral Environment of Late Western Antiquity." *Journal of Biblical Literature* 109/1 (1990): 3–27.

Adamik, T., "Aristotle's Theory of the Period." *Philologus* 128 (1984): 184–201.

Aland, Kurt, and Barbara Aland, *The Text of the New Testament: An Introduction to the Critical Editions and to the Theory and Practice of Modern Textual Criticisms*. Translated by E. F. Rhodes Grand Rapids / Leiden Eerdmans / Brill, 1987. [German original: *Der Text des Neuen Testaments*. Stuttgart: Deutsche Bibelgesellschaft, 1981].

Aland, Barbara, Kurt Aland, et al. (eds), "Introduction." Pages 46–88 in *Novum Testamentum Graece*. Based on the work of Eberhard and Erwin Nestle. 28th ed. Stuttgart: Deutsche Bibelgesellschaft, 2012 (= NA²⁸).

—, "Codices graeci et latini in hac editione adhibiti." Pages 792–819 in *Novum Testamentum Graece*. Based on the work of Eberhard and Erwin Nestle. 28th ed. Stuttgart: Deutsche Bibelgesellschaft, 2012 (= NA²⁸).

—, "Signa et abbreviationes." Pages 879–890 in *Novum Testamentum Graece*. Based on the work of Eberhard and Erwin Nestle. 28th ed. Stuttgart: Deutsche Bibelgesellschaft, 2012 (= NA²⁸).

Albrecht, Michael von, *Cicero's Style: A Synopsis, Followed by Selected Analytic Studies*. Leiden: Brill, 2003.

Alexander, Loveday, "Ancient Book Production and the Circulation of the Gospels." Pages 71–111 in *The Gospels for All Christians: Rethinking the Gospel Audiences* (ed. Richard Bauckham). Grand Rapids: Eerdmans, 1998.

—, "The Living Voice: Skepticism Towards the Written Word in Early Christian and in Graeco-Roman Texts." Pages 221–47 in *The Bible in Three Dimensions* (ed. D. A. Clines). Sheffield, UK: JSOT Press, 1990.

Amador, J. D. H., "Revisiting 2 Corinthians: Rhetoric and the Case for Unity." *NTS* 46 (2000): 92–111.

Amphoux, Christian B., "1 Th 2, 14-16: Quels Juifs sont-ils mis en cause par Paul?" *Filología neotestamentaria* 16 (2003): 85–101.

- Anderson, R. Dean (Jr.), "Use and Abuse of Lausberg." Pages 66–76 in *Rhetorical Argumentation in Biblical Texts: Essays from the Lund 2000 Conference* (ed. Anders Eriksson, Thomas H. Olbricht, and Walter Übelacker). Harrisburg, Penn.: Trinity Press International, 2002.
- , *Glossary of Greek Rhetorical Terms Connected to Methods of Argumentation, Figures and Tropes from Anaximenes to Quintilian*. Leuven: Peeters, 2000.
- , *Ancient Rhetorical Theory and Paul*. Kampen: Kok Pharos, 1996.
- Atwill, J. M., "Aristotle." Pages 51–61 in *Classical Rhetorics and Rhetoricians: Critical Studies and Sources* (ed. Ballif, Michelle and Michael G. Moran). Westport / London: Prager, 2005.
- Aune, David Ed., "Periodic sentence." Pages 346–347 in David E. Aune, *The Westminster Dictionary of New Testament and Early Christian Literature*. Louisville, KY: Westminster John Knox Press, 2003.
- Aujac, Germaine, "Introduction." Pages 9–34 in Germaine Aujac (ed. and trans.), *Denys d'Halicarnasse: Opuscules rhétorique, vol. I: Les orateurs antiques*. Paris: Les Belles Lettres, 1978.
- Bagnall, Roger S., *Everyday Writing in the Graeco-Roman East*. University of California Press, 2011.
- Bakker, Stéphanie J., *The Noun Phrase in Ancient Greek: A Functional Analysis of the Order and Articulation of NP Constituents in Herodotus*. Leiden: Brill, 2009.
- Ballif, Michelle and Michael G. Moran (eds), *Classical Rhetorics and Rhetoricians: Critical Studies and Sources*. Westport / London: Prager, 2005.
- Bar-Ilan, M., "Illiteracy in the Land of Israel in the First Centuries C.E." Pages 46–61 in *Essays in the Social Scientific Study of Judaism and Jewish Society*. Vol. 2 (ed. S. Fishbane, S. Schoenfeld, and A. Goldschlaeger). New York: Ktav, 1992.
- Barnard, Jody A., "The "Erasmian" Pronunciation of Greek: Whose Error is It?" *Erasmus Studies* 37 (2017): 109–132.
- Barrett, Charles K., "Boasting (καυχᾶσθαι, κτλ.) in the Pauline Epistles." Pages 363–368 in *L'Apôtre Paul. Personnalité, style et conception du ministère* (ed. Albert Vanhoye). Leuven: Leuven University Press, 1986.
- , *A Commentary on the Second Epistle to the Corinthians*. London: A. and C. Black, 1976.
- , "Paul's Opponents in II Corinthians." *NTS* 17/3 (1971): 233–254.
- Baslez, Marie-Françoise, "Transmission et surinterprétation des textes religieux. L'imprécation de Paul contre les Juifs (1 Thessaloniens 2, 15-16)." *Pallas* 90 (2013): 75–90.
- Baugh, S. M., "Hyperbaton and Greek Literary Style in Hebrews." *Novum Testamentum* 59/2 (2017): 194–213.
- Becker, Jürgen, *Paulus: Der Apostel der Völker*. Tübingen: J. C. B. Mohr, 1989.
- Beckman, Mary E. and Janet B. Pierrehumbert. "Intonational Structure in Japanese and English." *Phonology* 3 (1986): 255–309.

- Berglund, Carl Johan. "Interpreting readers: the Role of Greco-Roman Education in Early Interpretation of New Testament Writings." Pages 204–246 in *Scriptural Interpretation at the Interface between Education and Religion: In Memory of Hans Conzelmann* (ed. Florian Wilk). Leiden: Brill, 2018.
- Benedetto, Vincenzo di, "Dionisio Trace e la Techne a lui attribuita." *Annali della Scuola Normale Superiore di Pisa. Lettere, Storia e Filosofia*, s. II, 28 (1959): 87–118.
- Bernhardt, Emanuel, *Begriff und Grundform der griechischen Periode*. Wiesbaden: Stein'she, 1854.
- Bertrand, Nicolas., "Information Structure and Greek." Pages 238–243 in *Encyclopaedia of Greek Language and Linguistics*, vol. 2 (ed. Georgios K. Giannakis). Leiden / Boston: Brill, 2014. [Published online 2013. Consulted online on 21 March 2021 <http://dx.doi.org/10.1163/2214-448X_eagll_COM_00000190>]
- , *L'ordre des mots chez Homère: structure informationnelle, localisation et progression du récit* (PhD diss., Paris, Sorbonne, 2010).
- Betz, Hans Dieter, "Corinthians, Second Epistle to the." Pages 1148–1154 in *Anchor Bible Dictionary*. Vol. 1. (ed. David N. Freedman). New York: Doubleday, 1992.
- , "The Problem of Rhetoric and Theology according to the Apostle Paul" (1986). Pages 126–62 in Id., *Paulinische Studien. Gesammelte Aufsätze III*. Tübingen: Mohr Siebeck, 1994.
- , *Galatians: A Commentary on Paul's Letter to the Churches in Galatia*. Philadelphia: Fortress Press, 1979.
- , "The Literary Composition and Function of Paul's Letter to the Galatians." *NTS* 21 (1975): 353–379.
- , *Der Apostel Paulus und die sokratische Tradition: eine exegetische Untersuchung zu seiner Apologie 2 Korinther 10-13*. Tübingen: Mohr, 1972.
- Bieringer, R., and Lambrecht, J., *Studies on 2 Corinthians*. Leuven: Leuven University Press / Peeters, 1994.
- Blass, F., "Zur Frage über die Stichometrie der Alten." *RheinMus* 24 (1869): 524–532.
- , "Stichometrie und Kolometrie." *RheinMus* 34 (1879): 214–236.
- Bonifazi, Anna, "Discourse Segmentation." Vol. IV / section 3, in Anna Bonifazi, Annemieke Drummen, and Mark de Kreij, *Particles in Ancient Greek Discourse: Exploring Particle Use across Genres*. Washington DC: Center for Hellenic Studies, 2016.
- Bonner, S. F., *The Literary Treatises of Dionysius of Halicarnassus: A Study in the Development of Critical Method*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 1939.
- Boomershine, Thomas, "The New Testament Soundscape and the Puzzle of Mark 16:8." Pages 215–244 in *Sound Matters: New Testament Studies in Sound Mapping* (ed. M. E. Lee). Eugene (OR): Cascade Books, 2018.
- , *The Messiah of Peace: A Performance-Criticism Commentary on Mark's Passion-Resurrection Narrative*. Eugene (OR): Cascade Books, 2015.

- , “The Messiah of Peace: Mark 14–16 told in Greek by Dr. Tom Boomershine.” *YouTube*, uploaded by GoTellStory, 26 April 2014, www.youtube.com/watch?v=3dwo3z9T7HY.
- Bornecque, Henri, “Comment Cicéron rend le mot grec περίοδος.” Pages 66–68 in *Mélanges P. Thomas. Recueil de mémoires concernant la philologie classique dédié à Paul Thomas*, Bruges: Sainte Catherine, 1930.
- , *Les clausules métriques latines*. Lille: Université, 1907.
- , “La prose métrique et le dialogue des orateurs” *Revue de Philologie* 23 (1899): 334–342.
- , *La prose métrique dans la correspondance de Cicéron*. Paris: Bouillon, 1898.
- Bornkamm, Günther, *Gesammelte Aufsätze*. Vol. 4. München: C. Kaiser, 1971.
- Borochofsky Bar-Aba, Esther, “Punctuation Marks: Procedural and Conceptual Uses.” *Journal of Pragmatics* 35/7 (2003): 1031–1048.
- Botha, Pieter J. J., *Orality and Literacy in Early Christianity*. Eugene (OR): Cascade Books, 2012.
- , “New Testament Texts in the Context of Reading Practices of the Roman Period: The Role of Memory and Performance.” *Scriptura* 90 (2005): 621–640.
- , “Paul and Gossip: A Social Mechanism in Early Christian Communities.” *Neotestamentica* 32/2 (1998): 267–288.
- , “Letter Writing and Oral Communication in Antiquity: Suggested Implications for the Interpretation of Paul’s Letter to the Galatians.” *Scriptura* 42 (1992): 17–38.
- , “Greco-Roman Literacy as Setting for New Testament Writings.” *Neotestamentica* 26 (1992): 195–215.
- Brickle, Jeffrey E., “Caves, Cattle, and *Koinonia*: Acoustic Shadows across Textual Walls.” Pages 69–83 in *Sound Matters: New Testament Studies in Sound Mapping* (ed. Margaret E. Lee). Eugene (OR): Cascade Books, 2018.
- , *Aural Design and Coherence in the Prologue of First John*. London: T&T Clark, 2012.
- Broadhead, H. D., *Latin Prose Rhythm: A New Method of Investigation*. Cambridge: Deighton, Bell and Co, 1922.
- Brown, Raymond E., *An Introduction to the New Testament* (1997). New Haven / London: Yale University Press, 2010.
- Buber, Martin, “Aus den Anfängen unserer Schriftübertragung.” Pages 316–329 in Id. and Franz Rosenzweig, *Die Schrift und ihre Verdeutschung*. Berlin: Schocken, 1936. [ET: “From the Beginnings of our Bible Translation.” Pages 176–183 in M. Buber and F. Rosenzweig, *Scripture and Translation*. Translated by L. Rosenwald and E. Fox. Bloomington: Indiana University Press, 1994.]
- Buber, Martin, and Franz Rosenzweig, *Die Schrift. Aus dem Hebräischen verdeutschte von Martin Buber gemeinsam mit Franz Rosenzweig* (1926–1938). 4 vols. Stuttgart: Deutsche Bibelgesellschaft, 1992.
- Bruce, F. F., *An Expanded Paraphrase of the Epistles of Paul*. Exeter: Paternoster, 1965.
- Burkitt, F. C., “On Romans ix.5 and Mark xiv.61.” *JTS* 5 (1904): 451–455.

- Butticaz, Simon, "Auctorialité et autorité dans les lettres de Paul." *Novum Testamentum* 58/3 (2016): 318–337.
- , "«Que cette lettre soit lue à tous les frères' (1 Thessaloniens 5,27). Les lettres de Paul et le rôle du *lector* dans l'Antiquité." Pages 361–375 in *Le lecteur. Sixième colloque international du RRENAB, Université catholique de Louvain, 24-26 mai 2012* (ed. Régis Burnet, Didier Luciani, and Geert Van Oyen). Leuven / Paris: Peeters, 2015.
- Bultmann, Rudolf, *Der zweite Brief an die Korinther*. Göttingen: Vandenhoeck und Ruprecht, 1976.
- Callipo, M., "Introduzione." Pages 9–53 in Id. (ed.), *Dionisio Trace e la tradizione grammaticale*. Rome: Bonanno, 2011.
- Caplan, Harry, "Introduction" (*Rhetorica ad Herennium*). Pages VII–LXII in *Rhetorica ad Herennium*. Translated by H. Caplan. LCL 403. Cambridge (MA): Harvard University Press, 1954.
- Caragounis, Chrys C., *The Development of Greek and the New Testament: Morphology, Syntax, Phonology, and Textual Transmission*. Tübingen: Mohr Siebeck, 2004.
- Carraway, G., *Christ is God over All: Romans 9:5 in the Context of Romans 9–11*. London: T&T Clark, 2013.
- Carrez, Maurice, *La deuxième épître de Saint Paul aux Corinthiens*. Genève: Labor et Fides, 1987.
- Casson, Sarah, *Engaging with γάρ: A Relevance-Theoretic Approach to the Connective's Communicative Role in Romans* (PhD diss., London, King's College, 2017).
- Catach, Nina, *La ponctuation*. Paris: PUF, 1994.
- Ceccarelli, Paola, *Ancient Greek Letter Writing: A Cultural History (600 BC - 150 BC)*. Oxford: Oxford University Press, 2013.
- Celano, Giuseppe G. A., "Word Order." Pages 532–539 in *Encyclopedia of Ancient Greek Language and Linguistics* (ed. Georgios K. Giannakis). Vol. 3. Leiden / Boston: Brill, 2014. [Published online 2013. Consulted online on 21 March 2021, http://dx.doi.org/10.1163/2214-448X_eagll_COM_00000378].
- Chafe, Wallace, *Discourse, Consciousness, and Time. The Flow and Displacement of Conscious Experience in Speaking and Writing*. Chicago and London: University of Chicago Press, 1994.
- , "Punctuation and the Prosody of Written Language." *Written Communication* 5/9 (1988): 395–426.
- Chevigny, Jacqueline de (Sœur Jeanne d'Arc), *Évangile selon Jean*. Paris: Desclée de Brouwer / Les Belles Lettres, 1990.
- , *Évangile selon Luc*. Paris: Desclée de Brouwer / Les Belles Lettres, 1988.
- , *Évangile selon Matthieu*. Paris: Desclée de Brouwer / Les Belles Lettres, 1987.
- , *Évangile selon Marc*. Paris: Desclée de Brouwer / Les Belles Lettres, 1986.

- Chiron, Pierre, "Les doctrines antiques des figures: quelques idées reçues." *Pratiques* [Online] 165–166 (2015), <https://doi.org/10.4000/pratiques.2462>.
- , "Les côla en rhétorique. Respiration, sens, esthétique." *Revue de philologie, de littérature et d'histoire anciennes* 84 (2010): 31–50.
- , "La figure d'hyperbate." Pages 311–335 in *Rhetorica philosophans. Mélanges offerts à M. Patillon* (ed. Luc Brisson and Pierre Chiron). Paris: Vrin, 2010.
- , "Musique des mots et persuasion dans deux traités de rhétorique d'époque hellénistique et romaine (Ps.-Démétrios de Phalère, *Du Style*, Denys d'Halicarnasse, *La Composition stylistique*)." *Modèles Linguistiques* 58 (2008): 27–45.
- , Review of N. Marini, *Lo Stile* (Roma, 2007). [Review]. *Revue de Philologie* 81/2 (2007): 379–383.
- , *Pseudo-Démétrios de Phalère. Un rhéteur méconnu. Essai sur les mutations de la théorie du style à l'époque hellénistique*. Paris: Les Belles Lettres, 2006.
- , "La période chez Aristote." Pages 103–130 in *Théories de la phrase et de la proposition de Platon à Averroès* (ed. Stéphane Diebler, Philippe Büttgen and Marwan Rashed). Paris: Éditions Rue d'Ulm, 1999.
- , "Introduction" (*Démétrios: Du style*). Pages VII–CXXXVIII in Id. (ed. and trans.), *Démétrios: Du style*. Paris: Les Belles Lettres, 1993 [reprinted 2002].
- Classen, C. Joachim, "Can the Theory of Rhetoric Help Us to Understand the New Testament, and in Particular the Letters of Paul?" Pages 13–40 in *Paul and Ancient Rhetoric: Theory and Practice in the Hellenistic Context* (ed. Stanley E. Porter and Bryan R. Dyer). Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 2016.
- , *Rhetorical Criticism of the New Testament*. Tübingen: Mohr Siebeck, 2000.
- , "Philologische Bemerkungen zur Sprache des Apostels Paulus." *Wiener Studien* 107/108 (1994–1995): 321–335.
- , "St Paul's Epistle and Ancient Graeco-Roman Rhetoric." Pages 265–291 in *Rhetoric and the New Testament: Essays from the 1992 Heidelberg Conference* (ed. Stanley E. Porter and Thomas H. Olbricht). Sheffield: Sheffield Academic Press, 1993.
- , C. Joachim Classen, "St. Paul's Epistles and Ancient Greek and Roman Rhetoric." *Rhetorica* 10/4 (1992): 319–344.
- Clivaz, Claire, "La rumeur, une catégorie pour articuler autoportraits et réceptions de Paul. 'Car ses lettres, dit-on, ont du poids ... et sa parole est nulle' (2 Co 10,10)." Pages 239–259 in *How Pauline is Luke-Acts? Le paulinisme du Luc-Actes. Actes du colloque tenu à l'Université de Lausanne en avril 2008* (ed. Daniel Marguerat). Leuven: Peeters, 2009.
- Cloete, W. T. W., "The Colometry of Hebrew Verse." *JNSL* 15 (1989): 15–29.
- Connolly, J., "Fabius Quintilianus." Pages 320–330 in *Classical Rhetorics and Rhetoricians: Critical Studies and Sources* (ed. Michelle Ballif and Michael G. Moran). Westport et al.: Praeger, 2005.

- Coote, Robert B., "The Application of Oral Theory to Biblical Hebrew Literature." *Semeia* 5 (1976): 51–64.
- Copeland, Rita, and Ineke Sluiter, "Aelius Donatus, *Ars minor*, *Ars maior*, Life of Virgil, CA. 350." *Medieval Grammar and Rhetoric: Language Arts and Literary Theory, AD 300-1475* (ed. Copeland, Rita, and Ineke Sluiter). Oxford: Oxford University Press, 2012. [Online: Oxford Scholarship Online, 2015, 10.1093/acprof:osobl/9780199653782.001.0001].
- Cotarcic, Ana, *Aristotle on Language and Style: The Concept of Lexis*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 2021.
- Couper-Kuhlen, Elizabeth, "Prosodic Cues of Discourse Units" (1993). Pages 178–182 in *Encyclopedia of English Language and Linguistics*, vol. 10. (ed. Keith Brown). 2nd ed. Boston: Elsevier, 2005.
- Criore, Raffaella, *Gymnastics of the Mind. Greek Education in Hellenistic and Roman Egypt*. Princeton / Oxford: Princeton University Press, 2001.
- Crisp, S., "Scribal Marks and Logical Paragraphs: Discourse Segmentation Criteria in Manuscripts of the Pauline Corpus." Pages 77–87 in *Current Trends in Scripture Translation: Definition and Identity* (ed. Philip. A. Noss et al.). New York: United Bible Societies, 2005.
- McCreesh, Thomas P., *Biblical Sound and Sense: Poetic Sound Patterns in Proverbs 10-29*. Sheffield: JSOT Press, 1991.
- Culy, Martin M., Parsons, Mikeal C., *Acts: A Handbook on the Greek Text*. Waco (Texas): Baylor University Press, 2003.
- Dalrymple, Mary, and Louise Mycock, "The Prosody-Syntax Interface." Pages 173–193 in *Proceedings of LFG II Conference* (ed. Miriam Butt & Tracy Holloway King). Stanford, CA: CSLI Publications, 2011.
- Danker, Frederick W., "Paul's Debt to the De Corona of Demosthenes: A Study of Rhetorical Techniques in 2 Corinthians." Pages 262–280 in *Persuasive Artistry: Studies in New Testament Rhetoric in Honor of George A. Kennedy* (ed. D. F. Watson). Sheffield: JSOT, 1991.
- , *2 Corinthians*. Minneapolis: Augsburg, 1989.
- Darby, Peter, "The Codex Amiatinus Maiestas Domini and the Gospel Prefaces of Jerome." *Speculum* 92/2 (2017): 343–371.
- Davis, Casey W., *Oral Biblical Criticism: The Influence of the Principle of Orality on the Literary Structure of Paul's Epistle to the Philippians*. Sheffield: Sheffield Academic Press, 1999.
- Davis, J. B., "Hermogenes of Tarsus." Pages 194–202 in *Classical Rhetorics and Rhetoricians: Critical Studies and Sources* (ed. Michelle Ballif and Michael G. Moran). Westport [et al.]: Praeger, 2005.
- Dean, Margaret E (= M. E. Lee), "The Grammar of Sound in Greek Texts: Toward a Method of Mapping the Echoes of Speech in Writing." *Australian Biblical Review* 44 (1996): 53-70.

- Dean, Margaret E (= M. E. Lee) and Bernard B. Scott, "A Sound Map of the Sermon on the Mount." Pages 311–378 in *Treasures New and Old: Contributions to Matthean Studies* (ed. David R., Bauer, Mark A. Powell). Atlanta: Scholar Press, 1996.
- Debrunner, Albert, "Grundsätzliches über Kolometrie im Neuen Testament." *TBI* 5 (1926): 231–233.
- Dehé, Nicole, *Parentheticals in Spoken English: The Syntax-Prosody Relation*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 2014.
- Deissmann, A., *Licht vom Osten. Das Neue Testament und die neuentdeckten Texte der hellenistisch-römischen Welt*. Tübingen: Mohr, 1908–1909.
- Devine, Andrew M. and Laurence D. Stephens, *Discontinuous Syntax: Hyperbaton in Greek*. New York, 2000.
- , *The Prosody of Greek Speech*. Oxford: Oxford University Press, 1994.
- , "Stress in Greek?." *Transactions of the American Philological Association* 115 (1985): 125–152.
- Dewey, Arthur J., "Competing Gospels: Imperial Echoes, A Dissident Voice." Pages 64–82 in *The Bible in Ancient and Modern Media* (ed. Holly E. Hearon and Philip Ruge-Jones). Eugene (OR): Cascade Books, 2009.
- Dewey, Joanna, "Textuality in an Oral culture: A Survey of the Pauline Tradition." *Semeia* 65 (1994): 37–65.
- , "The Gospel of Mark as an Oral-Aural Event: Implications for Interpretation." Pages 145–63 in *The New Literary Criticism and the New Testament* (ed. Edgar V. McKnight and Elizabeth Struthers Malbon). Sheffield: Sheffield Academic Press, 1994.
- , "Mark as Interwoven Tapestry: Forecasts and Echoes for a Listening Audience." *The Catholic Biblical Quarterly* 53/2 (1991): 221–236.
- DiCicco, Mario M., *Paul's Use of Ethos, Pathos, and Logos in 2 Corinthians 10–13*. Lewiston: Mellen Biblical Press, 1995.
- Dik, Helma J. M., *Word Order in Ancient Greek: A Pragmatic Account of Word Order Variation in Herodotus*. Amsterdam: J. C. Gieben, 1995.
- Dickey, Eleanor, "A catalogue of works attributed to the grammarian Herodian." *Classical Philology* 109/4 (2014): 325–345.
- Dillery, John, "Herodotus' Proem and Aristotle, Rhetorica 1409a." *The Classical Quarterly* 42/2 (1992): 525–528.
- Dillon, Matthew, "Erasmian Pronunciation." [Online, 2013]. *Encyclopedia of Greek Language and Linguistics* (ed. Georgios K. Giannakis). Consulted online on 28 March 2021, http://dx.doi.org/10.1163/2214-448X_eagll_SIM_00000403 [Printed edition: Leiden / Boston: Brill, 2014].
- Doan, William, and Giles, Terry, *Prophets, Performance, and Power: Performance Criticism of the Hebrew Bible*. New York: T & T Clark International, 2005.

- Doering, Lutz, *Ancient Jewish Letters and the Beginnings of Christian Epistolography*. Tübingen: Mohr Siebeck, 2012.
- Dominicy, Marc, “Colométrie, période et rythme dans le lyrisme choral en Grèce ancienne.” *Les Etudes Classiques* 70/4 (2002): 321–352.
- Dorandi, Tiziano, *Le stilet et la tablette. Dans le secret des auteurs antiques*. Paris: Les Belles Lettres, 2000.
- Dorn, Klaus, *Paulus. Geschichte – Überlieferung – Glaube*. Leiden / Boston: Brill, 2019.
- Doty, William G., *Letters in Primitive Christianity*. Philadelphia, Pa.: Fortress, 1973.
- Dover, K. J., *The Evolution of Greek Prose*. Oxford: Clarendon Press, 1997.
- Dräger, P., “Periode.” Col. 1138–1151 in *Historisches Wörterbuch der Rhetorik* (ed. Gert Ueding), vol. 6. Tübingen / Berlin: Niemeyer / De Gruyter, 2003.
- , “Kolon.” Col. 750–764 in *Historisches Wörterbuch der Rhetorik* (ed. Gert Ueding), vol. 4. Tübingen / Berlin: Niemeyer / De Gruyter, 1998.
- , “Komma.” Col. 1176–1179 in *Historisches Wörterbuch der Rhetorik* (ed. Gert Ueding), vol. 4. Tübingen / Berlin: Niemeyer / De Gruyter, 1998.
- Durand, A., “La divinité de Jésus-Christ dans St. Paul, Rom. IX,5.” *RB* 12 (1903): 550–570.
- Dwight, Timothy, “On Romans ix.5.” *Journal of the Society of Biblical Literature and Exegesis* 1/1 (1881): 22–55.
- Elice, Martina, “Introduzione.” Pages IXL–CCX in *Romani Aquilae De figuris*. Edited and translated by M. Elice. Hildesheim / Zurich / New York: George Olms Verlag, 2007.
- Enos, R. L., “Marcus Tullius Cicero.” Pages 101–110 in *Classical Rhetorics and Rhetoricians: Critical Studies and Sources* (ed. Michelle Ballif and Michael G. Moran). Westport [et al.]: Praeger, 2005.
- , “*Rhetorica ad Herennium*.” Pages 331–338 in *Classical Rhetorics and Rhetoricians: Critical Studies and Sources* (ed. Michelle Ballif and Michael G. Moran). Westport [et al.]: Praeger, 2005.
- Eriksson, Anders, Thomas H. Olbricht, Walter Übelacker (eds), *Rhetorical Argumentation in Biblical Texts: Essays from the Lund 2000 Conference* (ed. Anders Eriksson, Thomas H. Olbricht, and Walter Übelacker). Harrisburg Penn.: Trinity Press International, 2002.
- Faccio, H. M., *De divinitate Christi: juxta S. Paulum, Rm 9,5*. Jérusalem: Typis PP. Franciscanorum, 1945.
- Feeney, D. C., “*Hic Finis Fandi*: On the Absence of Punctuation for the Endings (and Beginings) of Speeches in Latin Poetic Texts.” *Materiali e discussioni per l'analisi dei testi classici* 66 (2011): 45–91.
- Fitzgerald, J. T., “Paul, the Ancient Epistolary Theorists, and 2 Corinthians 10–13.” Pages 190–200 in *Greeks, Romans, and Christians: Essays in Honor of Abraham J. Malherbe* (ed. D. L. Balch, E. Ferguson, and W. A. Meeks). Minneapolis: Fortress, 1990.

- Flemming, Thomas, "The Origin of the Period." *Quaderni Urbinati di Cultura Classica New Series* 82/1 (2006): 95–102.
- Fluck, G., *De Graecorum interpunctionibus* (Phd. Diss., Greifswald, 1908).
- Foley, John M., *The Singer of Tales in Performance*. Bloomington / Indianapolis: Indiana University Press, 1995.
- , *The Theory of Oral Composition: History and Methodology*. Bloomington / Indianapolis: Indiana University Press, 1988.
- Forbes, Christopher, "Ancient Rhetoric and Ancient Letters: Models for Reading Paul, and their Limits." Pages 143–160 in *Paul and Rhetoric* (ed. J. P. Sampley and P. Lamp). New York / London: T&T Clark, 2010.
- Formarier, Marie, *Entre rhétorique et musique. Essai sur le rythme latin antique et médiéval*. Paris: Brepols, 2014.
- , "Ῥυθμός, rhythmos et numerus chez Cicéron et Quintilien. Perspectives esthétiques et génériques sur le rythme oratoire latin." *Rhetorica: A Journal of the History of Rhetoric* 31/2 (2013): 133–149.
- , "Rythme et persuasion chez Cicéron – Qu'est-ce que le rythme latin ?" *Rhuthmos*, 9 janvier 2011 [online], <http://rhuthmos.eu/spip.php?article251>.
- , "Modéliser le rythme 'haché' de Cicéron: propositions et perspectives." *Revue de philologie, de littérature et d'histoire anciennes* 84/1 (2010): 81–104.
- Fortson, Benjamin W., "Latin Prosody and Metrics." Pages 92–104 in *A Companion to the Latin Language* (ed. James Clackson). Malden (MA) / Oxford / Chichester: Wiley-Blackwell, 2011.
- Fowler, R. L., "Aristotle on the Period (Rhet. 3.9)." *Classical Quarterly* 32/1 (1982): 89–99.
- Fowler, Henry W., and Francis G. Fowler, *The King's English*. Oxford: Clarendon Press, 1906.
- Fraenkel, Eduard, *Leseproben aus den Werken Ciceros und Catos*. Rome: Storia e Letteratura, 1968.
- , *Noch einmal Kolon und Satz*. München: Verlag der Bayerischen Akademie der Wissenschaften, 1965.
- , "Nachträge zu 'Kolon und Satz II.'" Pages 131–139 in E. Fraenkel, *Kleine Beiträge zur klassischen Philologie*. Vol I.: *Zur Sprache. Zur griechischen Literatur*. Rome: Edizioni di Storia e Letteratura, 1964.
- , "Kolon und Satz. Beobachtungen zur Gliederung des antiken Satzes II." *NAWG* (1933), 319–354.
- , "Kolon und Satz. Beobachtungen zur Gliederung des antiken Satzes I." *NAWG* (1932), 197–213.
- Fraser, B., "What are Discourse Markers?" *Pragmatics* 6 (1996): 167–190.
- Freese, John H. and Gisela Striker, "Introduction." Pages XI–XX in *Aristotle: Art of Rhetoric*. LCL 193. Cambridge (MA) / London: Harvard University Press, 2020.

- Friedrich, Gerhard, "Die Gegner des Paulus im 2. Korintherbrief." Pages 181–215 in *Abraham Unser Vater: Juden und Christen im Gespräch über die Bibel. Festschrift für Otto Michel zum 60. Geburtstag* (ed. O. Betz et al). Leiden/Köln: Brill, 1963.
- Furnish, Victor P., *II Corinthians*. New York: Doubleday, 1986.
- Gamble, Harry Y., *Books and Readers in the Early Church: A History of Early Christian Texts*. New Haven / London: Yale University Press, 1995.
- Garland, David E., *2 Corinthians: An Exegetical and Theological Exposition of Holy Scripture*. Nashville, Ten.: Broadman & Holman, 1999.
- Georgi, Dieter, *Die Gegner des Paulus im 2 Korintherbrief: Studien zur religiösen Propaganda in der Spätantike*. Neukirchen-Vluyn: Neukirchener Verl., 1964
- Gignac, F. T., *A Grammar of the Greek Papyri of the Roman and Byzantine Periods*. Vol. 1: *Phonology*. Milan: Istituto Editoriale Cisalpino-La Goliardica, 1976.
- Gilliard, Frank D., "The Problem of the Antisemitic Comma between 1 Thessalonians 2.14 and 15." *New Testament Studies* 35/4 (1989): 481–502.
- Goldstein, David, "Wackernagel's law I," in *Encyclopedia of Ancient Greek Language and Linguistics* (ed. Georgios K. Giannakis). Consulted online on 28 July 2020, http://dx.doi.org/10.1163/2214-448X_eagll_COM_00000375 [Printed version: Leiden / Boston: Brill, 2014].
- , "Utterance," in *Encyclopedia of Ancient Greek Language and Linguistics* (ed. Georgios K. Giannakis). Consulted online on 25 March 2021, http://dx.doi.org/10.1163/2214-448X_eagll_COM_00000362 [Printed version: Leiden / Boston: Brill, 2014].
- , "Intonational Phrase," in *Encyclopedia of Ancient Greek Language and Linguistics* (ed. Georgios K. Giannakis). Consulted online on 25 March 2021, http://dx.doi.org/10.1163/2214-448X_eagll_COM_00000192 [Printed version: Leiden / Boston: Brill, 2014].
- , "Phonological Phrase." *Encyclopedia of Ancient Greek Language and Linguistics* (ed. Georgios K. Giannakis). Consulted online on 25 March 2021, http://dx.doi.org/10.1163/2214-448X_eagll_COM_00000282 [Printed version: Leiden / Boston: Brill, 2014].
- Gotoff, H.C., "The Concept of Periodicity in the *Ad Herennium*." *Harvard Studies in Classical Philology* 77 (1973): 217–223
- Grappe, Christian, "Paul et la rhétorique. Regard sur l'histoire et les enjeux d'un débat." *RHPR* 89/4 (2009): 511–530.
- Grässer, Erich, *Der zweite Brief an die Korinther*. Vol. 2: *Kapitel 8,1-13,13*. Gütersloh: Gütersloher Verlagshaus, 2005.
- Groot, A. W. de, *Der Antike Prosarhythmus*. Groningen: Haag, 1921.
- , *A Handbook of Antique Prose-Rhythm*. Groningen: Haag, 1919.
- Guthrie, George H., *2 Corinthians*. Grand Rapids (MI): Baker Academic, 2015.

- Habinek, Thomas N., *The Colometry of Latin Prose*. Berkeley (CA.): The University of California Press, 1985.
- Haines-Eitzen, K., *Guardians of Letters: Literacy, Power, and the Transmitters of Early Christian Literature*. New York / Oxford: Oxford University Press, 2000.
- Halliday, M. A. K., *Intonation and Grammar in British English*. The Hague / Paris: Mouton, 1967.
- Harris, J. Rendel, *Stichometry*. London: Clay & Sons, 1893.
- Harris, Murray J., *Jesus as God: The New Testament Use of Theos in Reference to Jesus* (1992). Eugene: Wipf and Stock, 2008.
- , *The Second Epistle to the Corinthians: A Commentary on the Greek Text*. Grand Rapids, Mich. / Milton Keynes: Eerdmans / Paternoster, 2005.
- Harris, William V., *Ancient Literacy*. Cambridge (MA) / London, Harvard University Press, 1989.
- Harris, H., “A Simile in Aristotle’s Rhetoric (III.9.6).” *Classical Review* 24 (1974): 178–179.
- Harvey, A. E., *Renewal through Suffering: A Study of 2 Corinthians*. Edinburgh: T. & T. Clark, 1996.
- Harvey, John D., *Listening to the Text: Oral Patterning in Paul’s Letters*. Grand Rapids (MI): Baker Books, 1999.
- Heath, Malcolm, “Invention.” Pages 89–119 in *Handbook of Classical Rhetoric in the Hellenistic Period (330 B.C.–A.D. 400)* (ed. Stanley E. Porter). Leiden / New York / Köln: Brill, 1997.
- Hearon, Holly E., “M. E. Lee and B. B. Scott, *Sound Mapping the New Testament*” [Review]. *Interpretation: A Journal of Bible and Theology* 65/3 (2011): 314–316.
- , “The Implications of Orality for Studies of the Biblical Text.” Pages 3–20 in *Performing the Gospel: Orality, Memory, and Mark* (ed. R. A. Horsley, J. A. Draper and J. M. Foley). Minneapolis: Fortress, 2006.
- Hearon, Holly E., and Ruge-Jones, Philip (eds), *The Bible in Ancient and Modern Media*. Eugene (OR): Cascade Books, 2009.
- Heberden, C. B., “Rhythmica.” Pages 2559–2565 in *A Dictionary of Greek and Roman Antiquities* (ed. William Smith). London: John Murray, 1890. [Re-ed. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 2013].
- Heckenkamp, Marcus, “Περίοδος und continuatio: Der Wandel der Metaphorik und der Konzeption der Periode von Aristoteles zu Cicero.” Pages 139–164 in *Papers on Rhetoric IV* (ed. Lucia Calboli Montefusco). Roma: Herder, 2002.
- Heinrici, Karl F. G., *Der zweite Brief an die Korintherbrief*. Göttingen: Vandenhoeck und Ruprecht, 1890.
- Héring, Jean, *La Seconde Epître de Saint Paul aux Corinthiens*. Neuchâtel: Delachaux et Niestlé, 1958.
- Hester, Davis A., “The Unity of 2 Corinthians: A Test Case for a Re-Discovered and Re-Invented Rhetoric.” *Neotestamentica* 33 (1999): 411–432.

- Hezser, Catherine, *Jewish Literacy in Roman Palestine*. Tübingen: Mohr Siebeck, 2001.
- Hill, Charles E., and Michael J. Kruger (ed.), *The Early Text of the New Testament*. Oxford: Oxford University Press, 2012.
- Hock, R. F., “Paul and Greco-Roman Education.” Pages 198–227 in *Paul and the Greco-Roman World: A Handbook* (ed. P. Sampley). Harrisburg, PA: Trinity Press International, 2003.
- Holland, G. S., “‘Delivery, Delivery, Delivery’: Accounting for Performance in the Rhetoric of Paul’s Letters.” Pages 119–140 in *Paul and Ancient Rhetoric: Theory and Practice in the Hellenistic Context* (ed. Stanley E. Porter and Bryan R. Dyer). Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 2016.
- Holtz, L., “Aelius Donatus (um die Mitte des 4. Jahrhunderts n. Chr.).” Pages 109–131 in *Lateinische Lehrer Europas. Fünfzehn Portraits von Varro bis Erasmus von Rotterdam* (ed. Wolfram Ax). Köln / Weimar U. Wien: Böhlau, 2005.
- Hoogewoud, F. J., “From ‘Writtenness’ to ‘Spokenness’: Martin Buber and His Forgotten Contemporaries on Colometry.” Pages 104–114 in *Hebrew Texts in Jewish, Christian and Muslim Surroundings* (ed. K. Spronk and Eveline Staalduine-Sulman). Leiden / Boston: Brill, 2018.
- Hoop, R. de, “The Colometry of Hebrew Verse and Massoretic Accents: Evaluation of a Recent Approach (Part 1).” *JNSL* 26/1 (2000), 47–73.
- Horrocks, Geoffrey G., *Greek: A History of the Language and its Speakers*. 2nd ed. Malden (MA) / Oxford, Wiley / Blackwell, 2010.
- Horsley, R. A., Draper, J. A., and J. M. Foley (eds). *Performing the Gospel: Orality, Memory, and Mark*. Minneapolis: Fortress, 2006.
- Houghton, Hugh., David Parker, Peter Robinson, and Klaus Wachtel, “The Editio Critica Maior of the Greek New Testament: Twenty Years of Digital Collaboration.” *Early Christianity* 11/1 (2020): 97–117.
- Hurtado, Larry W., “Oral Fixation and New Testament Studies ? ‘Orality,’ ‘Performance’ and Reading Texts in Early Christianity.” *New Testament Studies* 60/3 (2014): 321–340.
- , *The Earliest Christian Artifacts: Manuscripts and Christian Origins*. Grand Rapids (MI): Eerdmans, 2006.
- , “Manuscripts and the Sociology of Early Christian Reading.” Pages 49–62 in *The Early Text of the New Testament* (ed. Charles E Hill, Michael J. Kruger). Oxford: Oxford University Press, 2012.
- Hurtado, Larry W., and Chrys Keith, “Writing and Book Production in the Hellenistic and Roman Periods.” Pages 63–80 in *The New Cambridge History of the Bible*, vol. 1: *From the Beginnings to 600* (ed. James Carleton Paget and Joachim Schaper). Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 2013.
- Hutchinson, G. O., “Rhythm, Style, and Meaning in Cicero’s Prose.” *The Classical Quarterly* 45/2 (1995): 485–499.
- Innes, Doreen C., “Introduction” (*Demetrius: On Style*). Pages 309–340 in *Aristotle: Poetics*.

- Longinus: On the Sublime. Demetrius: On Style.* Edited and translated by Doreen C. Innes, based on the translation by W. R. Roberts. LCL 199. Cambridge: Harvard University Press, 1995.
- , “Period and Cōlon: Theory and Examples in Demetrius and Longinus.” Pages 36–53 in *Peripatetic Rhetoric after Aristotle* (ed. W. W. Fortenbaugh and D. C. Mirhady). New Brunswick (NJ) / London: London: Transaction Publishers, 1994.
- Irigoin, Jean, “La version lucanienne du Notre Père.” *Revue d’Histoire et de Philosophie religieuses* 80/2 (2000): 207–212.
- , “La composition rythmique des cantiques de Luc.” *Revue Biblique* 98 (1991): 5–50.
- Iverson, Kelly R., “Oral Fixation or Oral Corrective? A Response to Larry Hurtado.” *NTS* 62/2 (2016): 183–200.
- , “Orality and the Gospels: A Survey of Recent Research.” *Currents in Biblical Research* 8/1 (2009): 71–106.
- Jacon, Christophe, *La Sagesse du Discours. Analyse rhétorique et épistolaire de 1 Corinthiens*, Genève: Labor et Fides, 2006.
- Jespersen, Otto, *The Philosophy of Grammar*. Chicago: University of Chicago Press, 1924.
- Johnson, William A., “Towards a Sociology of Reading in Classical Antiquity.” *The American Journal of Philology* 121/4 (2000): 593–627.
- Johnson, William A., Holt N. Parker (eds), *Ancient Literacies: The Culture of Reading in Greece and Rome*. Oxford: Oxford University Press, 2009.
- Jonge, Casper C. de, “Nicoletta Marini, *Demetrio, Lo Stile*” [Review]. *Bryn Mawr Classical Review*, 2009.08.12.
- , *Between Grammar and Rhetoric: Dionysius of Halicarnassus on Language, Linguistics and Literature*. Leiden: Brill, 2008.
- , “From Demetrius to Dik. Ancient and Modern Views on Natural Word Order.” Pages 211–232 in *The Language of Literature. Linguistic Approaches to Classical Texts* (ed. R. Allan and M. Buijs). Leiden / Boston: Brill, 2007.
- Jousse, Marcel, *Memory, Memorization, and Memorizers: Marcel Jousse on the Galilean Oral-style Tradition and Its Traditionists* (ed. Edgard Sienaert). Eugene (OR): Cascade Books, 2018.
- Judge, Edwin A., “Cultural Conformity and Innovation in Paul: Some Clues from Contemporary Documents.” *Tyndale Bulletin* 35 (1984): 3–24.
- , “Paul’s Boasting in Relation to Contemporary Professional Practice.” *Australian Biblical Review* 16 (1968): 37–50.
- , “The Early Christians as a Scholastic Community – Part I.” *The Journal of Religious History* 1/3 (1961): 125–137.
- , “The Early Christians as a Scholastic Community – Part I.” *The Journal of Religious History* 1/1 (1960) Vol.1(1): 4–15.
- Kaibel, G., *Stil und Text der Πολιτεία Ἀθηναίων des Aristoteles*, vol. I. Berlin: Weidmann, 1893.

- Kammler, H.-C., “Die Prädikation Jesu Christi als “Gott” und die paulinische Christologie. Erwägungen zur Exegese von Röm 9,5b.” *ZNW* 94 (2003): 164–180.
- Keener, Craig S., *The Gospel of Matthew: A Socio-Rhetorical Commentary*, Grand Rapids (MI) / Carlisle: Eerdmans / Paternoster Press, 2009.
- Kelber, Werner H., “M. E. Lee and B. B. Scott, *Sound Mapping the New Testament*” [Review]. *Review of Biblical Literature*, 2016.3.34.
- , *The Oral and the Written Gospel: The Hermeneutics of Speaking and Writing in the Synoptic Tradition, Mark, Paul, and Q*. Philadelphia: Fortress Press, 1983.
- Kennedy, George A., “On Invention: Introduction.” Pages xiii–xix in *Invention and Method: Two Rhetorical Treatises from the Hermogenic Corpus*. Translated by G. A. Kennedy. Based on the text established by Hugo Rabe [H. Rabe, *Hermogenis opera*. Leipzig: Teubner, 1913. Repr. Stuttgart: Teubner, 1969]. Atlanta: Society of Biblical Literature, 2005.
- , *Classical Rhetoric and Its Christian and Secular Tradition from Ancient to Modern Times*. 2nd ed. revised and updated. Chapel Hill / London: The University of Carolina Press, 1999.
- , “The Genres of Rhetoric.” Pages 43–50 in *Handbook of Classical Rhetoric in the Hellenistic Period 330 B.C.-A.D. 400* (ed. S. E. Porter). Leiden: Brill, 1997.
- , *A New History of Classical Rhetoric*. Princeton: Princeton University Press, 1994.
- , *New Testament Interpretation through Rhetorical Criticism*. Chapel Hill / London: The University of North Carolina Press, 1984.
- , *The Art of Rhetoric in the Roman World: 300 B.C.–A.D. 300*. Vol. III of *A History of Rhetoric*. Princeton University Press, 1972.
- , “Aristotle on the Period.” *CQ* 32/1 (1958): 89–99.
- Keeline, Tom, and Tyler Kirby, “Auceps syllabarum: A Digital Analysis of Latin Prose Rhythm.” *The Journal of Roman Studies* 109 (2019): 161–204.
- Kennedy, James H., *The Second and Third Epistles of St. Paul to the Corinthians*. London: Methuen, 1900.
- Kleist, James A., “Colometry and the New Testament.” *Classical Bulletin* 3 (1927): 18–19.
- , “Colometry and the New Testament (Concluded).” *Classical Bulletin* 4 (1928): 26–27.
- Koopman, William T., *Joshua 24 as Narrative Poetry*. Sheffield: Sheffield Academic Press, 1990.
- Korpel, Marjo C. A., and J. C. de Moor, *The Structure of Classical Hebrew Poetry: Isaiah 40-55*. Leiden: Brill, 1998.
- Kuss, O. “Zu Römer 9,5.” Pages 291–303 in *Rechtfertigung. Festschrift für Ernst Käsemann zum 70. Geburtstag* (ed. J. Friedrich, W. Pöhlmann, P. Stuhlmacher). Göttingen: Vandenhoeck & Ruprecht, 1976.
- Ladd, D. Robert, *Intonational Phonology* (1996). Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 2008.

- Lallot, J., “Grammatici certant’: vers une typologie de l’argumentation pro et contra dans la question de l’authenticité de la Technè.” Pages 27–39 in *Dionysius Thrax and the Technè grammatike* (V. Law and I. Sluiter). Münster, 1995.
- Lameere, William, *Aperçus de paléographie homérique. à propos des papyrus de l’Iliade et de l’Odyssée des collections de Gand, de Bruxelles et de Louvain* (= Les publications de Scriptorium IV). Paris: Editions Erasme, 1960.
- Lampe, Peter, “Can Words Be Violent or Do They Only Sound That Way? Second Corinthians: Verbal Warfare from Afar as a Complement to a Placid Personal Presence.” Pages 223–240 in *Paul and Rhetoric* (ed. J. P. Sampley and Peter Lampe). New York / London: T & T Clark, 2010.
- , “Rhetorical Analysis of Pauline Texts – Quo Vadit ? Methodological Reflexions.” Pages 3–21 in *Paul and Rhetoric* (ed. J. P. Sampley and Peter Lampe). New York / London: T & T Clark, 2010.
- Lambrecht, Jan, *Second Corinthians*. Collegeville: The Liturgical Press, 1999.
- Laughton, E., “E. Fraenkel, *Leseproben aus Reden Ciceros und Catos*” [Review]. *Journal of Roman Studies* 60 (1970): 188–194.
- Laurens, Pierre, “Cicéron, maître de la *brevitas*.” Pages 29–41 in *Présence de Cicéron* (ed. R. Chevallier). Paris, 1984.
- Lausberg, Heinrich, “Elocutio.” §453–1082 in *Handbuch der literarischen Rhetorik: eine Grundlegung der Literaturwissenschaft* (ed. H. Lausberg). 2nd ed. München: M. Hueber, 1973.
- Lee, Margaret E. (ed.), *Sound Matters: New Testament Studies in Sound Mapping*. Eugene (OR): Cascade Books, 2018.
- , “Sound Mapping Reassessed.” Pages 8–26 in *Sound Matters: New Testament Studies in Sound Mapping* (ed. M. E. Lee). Eugene (OR): Cascade Books, 2018.
- , “Introduction.” Pages 1–7 in *Sound Matters: New Testament Studies in Sound Mapping* (ed. M. E. Lee). Eugene (OR): Cascade Books, 2018.
- , “Sound Mapping.” Pages 372–379 in *Dictionary of the Bible and Ancient Media* (ed. Tom Thatcher et al.). New York: Bloomsbury / T&T Clark, 2017.
- , “Colon.” Page 63 in *Dictionary of the Bible and Ancient Media* (ed. Tom Thatcher et al.). New York: Bloomsbury / T&T Clark, 2017.
- , “Period.” Page 293 in *Dictionary of the Bible and Ancient Media* (ed. Tom Thatcher et al.). New York: Bloomsbury / T&T Clark, 2017.
- , “Sound and Structure in the Gospel of Matthew.” Pages 97–130 in *From Text to Performance: Narrative and Performance Criticisms in Dialogue and Debate* (ed. Kelly R. Iverson). Eugene (OR): Cascade Books, 2014.
- , *A Method for Sound Analysis in Hellenistic Greek: The Sermon on the Mount as a Test Case*. (Phd Diss., Melbourne College of Divinity, 2005).

- Lee, Margaret E. and Bernard B. Scott, *Sound Mapping the New Testament*. Salem (OR): Polebridge Press, 2009.
- , “A Sound Map of the Sermon on the Mount.” Pages 311–378 in *Treasures New and Old: Contributions to Matthean Studies* (ed. David R. Bauer and Mark A. Powell). Atlanta: Scholar Press, 1996.
- Livesey, Nina E., “Rhythm, Sound, and Persuasion.” Pages 193–214 in *Sound Matters: New Testament Studies in Sound Mapping* (ed. Margaret E. Lee). Eugene (OR): Cascade Books, 2018.
- , “Sounding out the Heirs of Abraham (Rom 4:9-12).” *Oral Tradition* 27/1 (2012): 273–290.
- Long, Fredrick J., *2 Corinthians: A Handbook on the Greek Text*. Waco (TX): Baylor University Press, 2015.
- Longenecker, Richard N., “Ancient Amanuenses and the Pauline Epistles.” Pages 281–297 in *New Dimensions in New Testament Study* (ed. R. N. Longenecker and M. C. Tenney). Grand Rapids: Zondervan, 1974.
- Lord, Albert B., *The Singer of Tales*. Cambridge (MA): Harvard University Press, 1960.
- Loubser, J. A., *Oral and Manuscript Culture in the Bible*. Eugene (OR): Cascade Books, 2013.
- , “Reconciling Rhetorical Criticism with Its Oral Roots.” *Neotestamentica* 35 (2001): 95–110.
- Louw, J. P., *Semantics of New Testament Greek*. Philadelphia: Fortress, 1982.
- , “Discourse Analysis and the Greek New Testament.” *BT* 24 (1973): 101–118.
- Malbon, Elizabeth S., *Hearing Mark: A Listener’s Guide*. Bloomsbury: T & T Clark, 2002.
- Malherbe, Abraham J., *Ancient Epistolary Theorists*. Atlanta, Ga.: Scholars Press, 1988.
- Markovic, Daniel, “Hyperbaton in the Greek Literary Sentence.” *GRBS* 46 (2006): 127–146.
- Marschall, Priscille, “Punctuating Paul’s Letters in Light of the Ancient Theory of Cōla and Periods: The Example of 2 Corinthians 10:8–11.” *Biblical Interpretation* 28/1 (2020): 100–125.
- , “Refining the Criteria for Delineating Cōla and Periods: Some Remarks on the First and Second Steps of ‘Sound Mapping.’” *Neotestamentica* 54/2 (2020): 307–328.
- , “L’analyse colométrique du Nouveau Testament. Quelques remarques sur le projet de ‘cartographie sonore’ (*sound mapping*).” *Revue de théologie et de philosophie* (forthcoming).
- , “Christ est-il appelé Dieu en Romains 9,5 ? L’argument des figures gorgianiques” (forthcoming).
- Martin, Ralph P., *2 Corinthians*. Waco: Word Books, 1986.
- Martin, Troy W., “Invention and Arrangement in Pauline Rhetorical Studies: A Survey of the Practices and the Problems.” Pages 48–118 in *Paul and Rhetoric* (ed. J. P. Sampley and P. Lampe). New York: Continuum, 2010.
- Martinez, David G. “The Papyri and Early Christianity.” Pages 590–622 in *The Oxford Handbook of Papyrology* (ed. Roger S. Bagnall). Oxford: Oxford University Press, 2009.

- Mathisen, Ralph W., "Palaeography and Codicology." Pages 140–165 in *The Oxford Handbook of Early Christian Studies* (ed. Susan Ashbrook Harvey and David G. Hunter). Oxford: Oxford University Press, 2008.
- Matić, Dejan. "Topic, Focus, and Discourse Structure: Ancient Greek Word Order." *Studies in Language* 27/3 (2003): 573–633.
- McCreech, Thomas P., *Biblical Sound and Sense: Poetic Sound Patterns in Proverbs 10–29*. Sheffield: JSOT Press, 1991.
- Meeks, Wayne, *The First Urban Christians: The Social World of the Apostle Paul*. New Haven/London: Yale University Press, 1983.
- Meggitt, Justin, *Paul, Poverty and Survival*. Edinburgh: T. & T. Clark, 1998.
- Merda de Villeneuve, Rachel, *L'elocutio en 1 Corinthiens: Inventaire, stratégie et herméneutique* (Phd. Diss., University of Montreal, 2018).
- Mesnil, A. du, "Begriff der drei Kunstformen der Rede: Komma, Kolon, Periode, nach der Lehre der Alten." Pages 32–121 in *Zum zweihundertjährigen Jubiläum des königlichen Friedrichs-Gymnasiums*. Frankfurt on O., 1894.
- Metzger, Bruce M., *Manuscripts of the Greek Bible: An Introduction to Palaeography*. New York / Oxford: Oxford University Press, 1981.
- , "The Punctuation of Rom. 9:5." Pages 95–112 in *Christ and Spirit in the New Testament* (ed. B. Lindars and S. S. Smalley). Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 1973.
- , *A Textual Commentary on the Greek New Testament: A Companion Volume to the United Bible Societies' Greek New Testament*. 3rd ed. London / New York: United Bible Societies, 1971.
- Metzger, Bruce M., and Ehrman, Bart D., *The Text of the New Testament: Its Transmission, Corruption, and Restoration*. 4th ed. New-York / Oxford: Oxford University Press, 2005.
- Meyer, H. A. W., *Critical and Exegetical Handbook to the Epistles to the Corinthians*. 2 vol. New York: Funk and Wagnalls, 1884.
- Millard, Alan, *Reading and Writing in the Time of Jesus*. New York: New York University Press, 2000.
- Miller, Marvin L., *Performances of Ancient Jewish Letters: From Elephantine to MMT*. Göttingen: Vandenhoeck & Ruprecht, 2015.
- Mitchell, Margaret M., "A Patristic Perspective on Pauline περιαιτολογία." *New Testament Studies* 47 (2001): 354–371.
- , "New Testament Envoys in the Context of Greco-Roman Diplomatic and Epistolary Conventions: The Example of Timothy and Titus." *Journal of Biblical Literature* 111/4 (1992): 641–662.
- Morgan, Teresa, *Literate Education in the Hellenistic and Roman Worlds*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 1998.
- Morpurgo-Tagliabue, G., "Aristotelismo e Antiaristotelismo di Demetrio." *RSF* 34 (1979): 3–25.

- Muchnová, Dagmar, *Entre conjonction, connecteur et particule: le cas de epei en grec ancien. Etude syntaxique, pragmatique et sémantique*. Prague: Karolinum, 2011.
- , “Les emplois paratactiques de $\omega\varsigma$. Status quaestionis et théories nouvelles.” *AUC Philologica* 2004/2 (2004): 123–133.
- Nässelqvist, Dan, “The Question of Punctuation in John 1:3–4: Arguments from Ancient Colometry.” *Journal of Biblical Literature* 137/1 (2018) 175–191.
- , “Underexplored Benefits of Sound Mapping in New Testament Exegesis.” Pages 120–131 in *Sound Matters: New Testament Studies in Sound Mapping* (ed. Margaret E. Lee). Eugene (OR): Cascade Books, 2018.
- , *Public Reading in Early Christianity: Lectors, Manuscripts, and Sound in the Oral Delivery of John 1–4*. Leiden: Brill, 2015.
- , “Translating the Aural Gospel: The Use of Sound Analysis in Performance-Oriented Translation.” Pages 49–67 in *Translating Scripture for Sound and Performance: New Directions in Biblical Studies* (ed. James A. Maxey and Ernst R. Wendland). Eugene: Cascade Books, 2012.
- Nespor, Marina, and Irene Vogel, *Prosodic Phonology*. Dordrecht: Foris Publications, 1986.
- Neyrey, Jerome, “The Social Location of Paul : Education as the Key.” Pages 126–164 in *Fabrics of Discourse: Essays in Honor of Vernon K. Robbins* (ed. David B. Gowler, L. Gregory Bloomquist and Duane F. Watson). Harrisburg: Trinity Press International, 2003.
- Niccacci, Alviero, “Analysing Biblical Hebrew Poetry.” *JSOT* 74 (1997): 77–93.
- Noël, Marie-Pierre, “Gorgias et l’“invention” des ΓΟΡΤΙΕΙΑ ΣΧΗΜΑΤΑ.” *Revue des Etudes Grecques* 112 (1999): 193–211.
- Norden, Eduard, *Agnostos Theos. Untersuchungen zur Formengeschichte religiöser Rede*. Berlin: Teubner, 1913.
- , *Die antike Kunstprosa vom vi Jahrhundert vor Chr. bis in die Zeit der Renaissance*. 2 vols. Leipzig: Teubner, 1898 (reprinted Stuttgart: Teubner, 1995).
- Nünlist, René, “Nicanor’s System of Punctuation.” *GRBS* 60 (2020): 124–138.
- O’Dwyer, Bernard, *Modern English Structures: Form, Function, and Position*. Peterborough (Ont., CA): Broadview Press, 2006.
- Oestreich, Bernhard, “Investigations into the Sound’s Message of Philippians 1:27–2:18.” Pages 84–119 in *Sound Matters: New Testament Studies in Sound Mapping* (ed. M. E. Lee). Eugene (OR): Cascade Books, 2018.
- , *Performanzkritik der Paulusbriefe*. Tübingen: Mohr Siebeck, 2012.
- Olbricht, Thomas H., “Delivery and Memory. Pages 159–169 in *Handbook of Classical Rhetoric in the Hellenistic Period (330 B.C.– A.D. 400)* (ed. Stanley E. Porter). Leiden / New York / Köln: Brill, 1997.
- Ong, Walter, *Orality and Literacy: The Technologizing of the Word*. London: Methuen, 1982.

- Parker, Holt N., "Books and Reading Latin Poetry." Pages 186–230 in *Ancient Literacies: The Culture of Reading in Greece and Rome* (ed. William A. Johnson and Holt N. Parker). Oxford: Oxford University Press, 2009.
- Parkes, Malcolm B., *Pause and Effet: An Introduction to the History of Punctuation in the West*. Aldershot: Scolar Press, 1992.
- Parry, Milman, *The Making of Homeric Verse: The Collected Papers of Milman Parry* (ed. Adam Parry). Oxford: Clarendon Press, 1971.
- , *L'Épithète traditionnelle dans Homère. Essai sur un problème de style homérique*. Paris: Les Belles Lettres, 1928.
- Partridge, Eric, *You Have a Point There: A Guide to Punctuation and its Allies* (1953). Routledge, 1978.
- Patillon, Michel, *La théorie du discours chez Hermogène le rhéteur. Essai sur les structures linguistiques de la rhétorique ancienne*. Paris: Les Belles Lettres, 2010.
- , "Introduction" (*Anonyme de Séguier: Art du discours politique*). Pages V–XCIX in *Anonyme de Séguier: Art du discours politique*. Edited and translated by M. Patillon. Paris: Les Belles Lettres, 2005.
- , "Introduction" (*Hermogène: Les catégories stylistiques du discours*). Pages VII–CXLI in *Prolégomènes au De Ideis. Hermogène: Les catégories stylistiques du discours (De Ideis). Synopses des exposés sur les Ideai*. Vol. 4 of *Corpus Rhetoricum*. Edited and translated by Michel Patillon. Paris: Les Belles Lettres, 2012.
- , "Introduction" (*Corpus Rhetoricum III*). Pages VII–CXXIV in *Pseudo-Hermogène, L'Invention - Anonyme, Synopse des Exordes - Anonyme, Scolies au traité Sur l'Invention du Pseudo-Hermogène*. Vol. III/I of *Corpus Rhetoricum*. Edited and translated by M. Patillon. Paris: Les Belles Lettres, 2012.
- , "Introduction" (*Pseudo-Aelius Aristides: Art of Rhetoric*). Pages V–LXXX in *Pseudo-Aelius Aristides, Arts Rhétoriques, vol. I (= book I): Discours politique*. Edited and translated by Michel Patillon. Paris: Les Belles Lettres, 2002.
- Patt, Sebastian, *Punctuation as a Means of Medium-Dependent Presentation Structure in English: Exploring the Guide Functions of Punctuation*. Gunter Narr Verlag, 2013.
- Perry, P. S., "Biblical Performance Criticism: Survey and Prospects." *Religions* 10 (2019): 81–95.
- Petrovic, Andrej, Ivana Petrovic, and Edmund Thomas (eds), *The Materiality of Text: Placement, Perception, and Presence of Inscribed Texts in Classical Antiquity*. Leiden: Brill, 2018.
- Pfeiffer, Rudolf, *History of Classical Scholarship*. Vol. 1 : *From the Beginnings to the End of the Hellenistic Age*, Oxford : Clarendon Press, 1968.
- Pierrehumbert, Janet B., *The Phonology and Phonetics of English Intonation* (PhD diss., MIT, 1980).
- Pilch, John, "M. E Lee and B. B. Scott, *Sound Mapping the New Testament*" [Review]. *Theological Studies* 71/4 (2010): 954–956.

- Pitta, Antonio, "Il 'discorso del pazzo' o periautologia immoderata? Analisi retoricoletteraria di 2 Cor II,1–12,18." *Biblica* 87 (2006): 493–510.
- Plummer, Alfred, *A Critical and Exegetical Commentary on the Second Epistle of St. Paul to the Corinthians*. Edinburgh: T & T Clark, 1915.
- , *The Second Epistle of Paul the Apostle to the Corinthians*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 1903.
- Podbielski, Henryk, "Pseudo Aristides: *On political style* and *On simple style*. Attribution and the nature of treaties." *Roczniki Humanistyczne* 66/3 (2018): 249–267.
- Popper, Karl R. *The Logic of Scientific Discovery* (German original: *Logik der Forschung*, 1935). London: Hutchinson & Co., 1959.
- Porter, Stanley E., "Prominence. An Overview." Pages 58–59 in *The Linguist as Pedagogue* (ed. S. E. Porter and M. B. O'Donnell). Sheffield: Sheffield Phoenix, 2009.
- , "Discourse Analysis and New Testament Studies: An Introductory Survey." Pages 14–35 in *Discourse Analysis and Other Topics in Biblical Greek* (ed. Stanley E. Porter and D. A. Carson). London / New York: Bloomsbury, 2015 [1st ed. 1995, Sheffield Academic Press].
- , "Paul as Epistolographer and Rhetorician?." Pages 222–248 in: *The Rhetorical Interpretation of the Scripture: Essays from the 1996 Malibu Conference* (ed. Stanley E. Porter and Dennis Stamps). Sheffield Academic Press, 1999.
- , "The Theoretical Justification for Application of Rhetorical Categories to Pauline Epistolary Literature." Pages 100–122 in *Rhetoric and the New Testament: Essays from the 1992 Heidelberg Conference* (ed. Stanley E. Porter and Thomas H. Olbricht). Sheffield: Sheffield Academic Press, 1993.
- , "Word Order and Clause Structure in New Testament Greek: An Unexplored Area of Greek Linguistics Using Philippians as a Test Case." *FNT* 6 (1993): 177–206.
- Porter, Stanley E., and Olbricht, Thomas H. (eds), *Rhetoric and the New Testament: Essays from the 1992 Heidelberg Conference*. Sheffield: Sheffield Academic Press, 1993.
- Porter, Stanley E., and M. B. O'Donnell (eds), *The Linguist as Pedagogue*. Sheffield: Sheffield Phoenix, 2009.
- Porter, Stanley E., and Bryan R. Dyer (eds), *Paul and Ancient Rhetoric: Theory and Practice in the Hellenistic Context* Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 2016.
- Primmer, Adolf, *Cicero numerosus. Studien zum Antiken Prosarhythmus*. Wien: H. Böhlhaus, 1968.
- , "Schlichter Stil und eingliedrige Periode in Aristoteles' Rhetorik III 9." *Rheinisches Museum für Philologie* 109/1 (1966): 73–77.
- Privitera, G. A., Pretagostini R., *Soria e forme della letteratura greca*. Vol. II: *Età ellenistica ed età imperiale*. Turin: Einaudi, 1997.
- Probert, Philomen, *Early Greek Relative Clauses*. Oxford: Oxford University Press, 2015.
- Rastier, François, *Arts et sciences du texte*. Paris: PUF, 2001.

- Ready, Jonathan L., *Orality, Textuality, and Homeric Epic: A Study of Oral Texts, Dictated Texts, and Wild Texts*. Oxford: Oxford University Press, 2019.
- Redondo, Jordi, "Changes in the syntax of the discourse markers in New Testament Greek." *RivB LXIV* (2016): 209–224.
- Reed, Jeffrey T., "Using Ancient Rhetorical Categories to Interpret Paul's Letters: A Question of Genre." Pages 292–324 in: *Rhetoric and the New Testament: Essays from the 1992 Heidelberg Conference* (ed. Stanley E. Porter and Thomas H. Olbricht). Sheffield: Sheffield Academic Press, 1993.
- Reid, Robert S., "Dionysius of Halicarnassus' Theory of Compositional Style and the Theory of Literate Consciousness." *Rhetoric Review* 15/1 (1996): 44–46.
- Reynolds, Graham, *The Clausulae in the De Civitate Dei of St. Augustine*. Washington: The Catholic University of America, 1924.
- Rhoads, David, "The New Testament as Oral Performance." *Vimeo*, uploaded by Moravian Seminary, 23 March 2016, <https://vimeo.com/160142546>.
- , "Performance Events in Early Christianity: New Testament Writings in an Oral Context." Pages 166–193 in *The Interface of Orality and Writing. Speaking, Seeing, Writing in the Shaping of New Genres* (ed. Annette Weissenrieder and Robert B. Coote). Mohr Siebeck, 2010.
- , "What Is Performance Criticism?" Pages 83–100 in *The Bible in Ancient and Modern Media: Story and Performance* (ed. Holly E. Hearon and Philip Ruge-Jones). Eugene (OR): Cascade Books, 2009.
- , "Performance Criticism: An Emerging Discipline in Second Testament Studies—Part One." *Biblical Theology Bulletin* 36 (2006): 118–133.
- , "Performance Criticism: An Emerging Discipline in Second Testament Studies—Part Two." *Biblical Theology Bulletin* 36 (2006): 164–184.
- Richards, Ernest R., *Paul and First-Century Letter Writing: Secretaries, Composition, and Collection*. Downers Grove: InterVarsity Press, 2004.
- Robbins, Charles J., "A Colometric Arrangement of Cicero." *The Classical Journal* 75/1 (1979): 57–62.
- Rosenzweig, Franz, "Die Schrift und das Wort" (1926). Pages 76–87 in Martin Buber, Franz Rosenzweig, *Die Schrift und ihre Verdeutschung*. Berlin: Schocken, 1936.
- Rowe, Galen O., "Style." Pages 121–157 in *Handbook of Classical Rhetoric in the Hellenistic Period (330 B.C.–A.D. 400)* (ed. Stanley E. Porter). Leiden / New York / Köln: Brill, 1997.
- Russell D. A., and M. Winterbottom, *Ancient Literary Criticism: The Principal Texts in New Translations*. Oxford: Clarendon Press, 1972.
- Salles, Catherine, *Lire à Rome*. Paris: Les Belles Lettres, 2008.
- , "L'épistolographie hellénistique et romaine." Pages 79–97 in: *Paul de Tarse* (ed. J. Schlosser). Paris: Cerf, 1996.

- , “Le genre littéraire de la lettre dans l’Antiquité.” *CBFV* 24 (1985): 41–47.
- Sampley, J. Paul, and Peter Lamp (eds), *Paul and Rhetoric*. New York / London: T&T Clark, 2010.
- Sanday W., and A. C. Headlam, *A Critical and Exegetical Commentary on the Epistle to the Romans* (1895). New York: Charles Scribner’s Sons, 1902.
- D. Sansone, “The Computer and the Historia Augusta: A Note on Marriott.” *The Journal of Roman Studies* 80 (1990): 174–177.
- Schade, Gerson, “Periode,” in *Der Neue Pauly* (ed. Hubert Cancik, Helmuth Schneider, Manfred Landfester). Online version (Brill, 2006). Consulted online on 20 March 2021, http://dx.doi.org/10.1163/1574-9347_dnp_e914240.
- Schenkeveld, Dirk M., “Linguistic Theories in the Rhetorical Works of Dionysius of Halicarnassus.” *Glotta* 61 (1983): 67–94.
- , *Studies in Demetrius’ On Style*. Amsterdam: Hakkert, 1964.
- Schenkl, H., “Zur Kritik der Schrift des Demetrios Περὶ ἑρμηνείας.” *Wien. Stud.* 4 (1882): 55–76.
- Scheppers, Frank, “Discourse Segmentation, Discourse Structure, and Sound Mapping.” Pages 133–178 in *Sound Matters: New Testament Studies in Sound Mapping* (ed. M. E. Lee). Eugene (OR): Cascade Books, 2018.
- , *The Colon Hypothesis: Word Order, Discourse Segmentation and Discourse Coherence in Ancient Greek*. Bruxelles: VUB Press, 2011.
- Schmeller, Thomas, *Der zweite Brief an die Korinther*. Vol. II: 2Kor 7,5–13,13. Neukirchen-Vluyn/Ostfildern: Neukirchener Theologie / Patmos-Verl., 2015.
- Schmid, Walter, *Über die Klassische Theorie und Praxis des Antiken Prosarhythmus*. Wiesbaden: F. Steiner, 1959.
- , “Die sogenannte Aristidesrhetorik.” *RhM* 72 (1917–1918): 113–149 and 238–257.
- Schmithals, Walter, *Die Briefe des Paulus in ihrer ursprünglichen Form*. Zurich: Theologischer, 1984.
- Scholes, R. J., and Brenda J. Willis, “Prosodic and Syntactic Functions of Punctuation: A Contribution to the Study of Orality and Literacy.” *Interchange* 21 (1990): 13–20.
- Schönberger, Axel, *Die Ars maior des Aelius Donatus: lateinischer Text und kommentierte deutsche Übersetzung einer antiken Latein Grammatik des 4. Jahrhunderts für den fortgeschrittenen Anfängerunterricht*. Frankfurt: Valentia, 2009.
- Schütz, Roland, *Das Neue Testament für die deutsche Jugend nach Sinnzeiler aus dem griechischen übertragen*. Leipzig: Hinrichs, 1928.
- , “Die Bedeutung der Kolometrie für das Neuen Testament.” *Zeitschrift für die neutestamentliche Wissenschaft* 21 (1922): 161–184.
- , *Der Jakobusbrief nach Sinnzeilen ins Deutsche übertragen*. Leipzig: Hinrichs: 1922.

- , *Der parallele Bau der Satzglieder im Neuen Testament und seine Verwertung für die Textkritik und Exegese*. Göttingen: Vandenhoeck & Ruprecht, 1920.
- Scott, Bernard B., “Luke’s Strategy for Interpreting Parables.” Pages 42–68 in *Sound Matters: New Testament Studies in Sound Mapping* (ed. M. E. Lee). Eugene (OR): Cascade Books, 2018.
- , “A New Voice in the Amphitheater: Full Fidelity in Translating.” Pages 101–118 in *Fidelity and Translation: Communicating the Bible in New Media* (ed. Paul A. Soukup and Robert Hodgsons), 1999.
- Schellenberg, Ryan S., *Rethinking Paul’s Rhetorical Education: Comparative Rhetoric and Corinthians 10–13*. Atlanta: Society of Biblical Literature, 2013.
- Scherbenske, Eric W., “Codex Coislinianus and the Euthalian Edition of the *Corpus Paulinum*.” Pages 116–174 in Id., *Canonizing Paul: Ancient Editorial Practice and the Corpus Paulinum*. Oxford: Oxford University Press, 2013.
- Schnelle, Udo, *Paulus. Leben und Denken*. Berlin / New York: De Gruyter, 2003. [ET: *Apostle Paul: His Life and Theology*. Translated by M. Eugene Boring. Grand Rapids (MI): Baker Academic, 2012].
- Schroeder, Otto, *Nomenclator Metricus. Alphabetisch geordnete Terminologie der griechischen Verswissenschaft*. Heidelberg: C. Winter, 1929.
- Scodel, Ruth (ed.), *Between Orality and Literacy: Communication and Adaptation in Antiquity*. Leiden / Boston: Brill, 2014.
- Selkirk, Elisabeth. *Phonology and Syntax: The Relation between Sound and Structure*. Cambridge, MA: MIT Press, 1984.
- Selting, Margret, “On the Interplay of Syntax and Prosody in the Constitution of Turn Constructional Units and Turns in Conversation.” *Pragmatics* 6/3 (1996): 371–388.
- Shiell, William D., *Delivering from Memory: The Effect of Performance on the Early Christian Audience*. Eugene (OR): Wipf and Stock Publishers, 2011.
- , *Reading Acts: The Lector and the Early Christian Audience*. Leiden: Brill, 2004.
- Shiner, Whitney, *Proclaiming the Gospel: First-Century Performance of Mark*. Harrisburg / London / New York: Trinity Press International, 2003.
- Siebenborn, E., “Herkunft und Entwicklung des Terminus technicus ΠΕΠΙΟΔΟΣ: ein Beitrag zur Frage der Entstehung von Fachterminologie.” Pages 229–249 in *The History of Linguistic in the Classical Period* (ed. D. J. Taylor). Amsterdam: Benjamins, 1986, 229–249.
- Skelton, Reginald, *Modern English Punctuation*. London: Pitman, 1933.
- Small, Jocelyn P., *Wax Tablets of the Mind: Cognitive Studies of Memory and Literacy in Classical Antiquity*. London / New York: Routledge, 1997.
- Smith, R. B., *Empirical Evidences and Theoretical Interpretations of Greek Phonology: Prolegomena to a Theory of Sound Patterns in the Hellenistic Koine*. Ph.D. diss. (Indiana University, 1972).
- Starr, Raymond J., “Lectores and Roman Reading.” *CJ* 86 (1991): 337–343.

- , “The Circulation of Literary Texts in the Roman World.” *The Classical Quarterly* 37/1 (1987): 213–223.
- Smyth, Herbert W., *A Greek Grammar for Colleges*. Revised by Gordon M. Messing. Cambridge: Harvard University Press, 1956.
- Stegemann, Willy, “Ciceros Ausdrücke für περίοδος und ihre griechischen Äquivalente.” *Philologische Wochenschrift* 52 (1932): 139–146.
- Still, Todd D., and David G. Horrel (eds), *After the First Urban Christians: The Social-Scientific Study of Pauline Christianity Twenty-Five Years Later*. London / New York: T&T Clark, 2009.
- Stirewalt, M. Luther, *Paul, the Letter Writer*. Eerdmans, 2003.
- , *Studies in Ancient Greek Epistolography*. Atlanta, Ga.: Scholars Press, 1993.
- Sträterhoff, Barbara, *Kolometrie und Prosarhythmus bei Cicero und Livius. De imperio Cn. Pompei und Livius 1,1-26,8 kolometrisch ediert, kommentiert und statistisch analysiert*. 2 vols. Oelde: R. Festge, 1995.
- Strecker, Georg, “Die Legitimität des paulinischen Apostolates nach 2 Korinther 10–13.” *NTS* 38/4 (1992): 566–586.
- Streicher, Friedrich, *Neues Testament. Aus dem Urtext in Sinnzeilen übersetzt von Friedrich Streicher*. Freiburg / Basel, Herder, 1964.
- Stroh, Wilfried, *Die Macht der Rede. Eine kleine Geschichte der Rhetorik im alten Griechenland und Rom*. Berlin: Ullstein, 2009.
- Stowers, Stanley, “Apostrophe, Prosopoiia and Paul’s Rhetorical Education.” Pages 351–369 in: *Early Christianity and Classical Culture* (ed. J. T. Fitzgerald et al.). Leiden: Brill, 2003.
- , *Letter Writing in the Greco-Roman Antiquity*. Philadelphia, Pa.: Westminster Press, 1986.
- Sumney, Jerry L., *Identifying Paul’s Opponents: The Question of Method in 2 Corinthians*. Sheffield: JSOT Press, 1990.
- Swiggers, Pierre, and Wouters, Alfons, “Réflexions à propos de (l’absence de ?) la syntaxe dans la grammaire gréco-latine.” Pages 25–40 in *Syntax in Antiquity* (ed. P. Swiggers and A. Wouters). Leuven: Peeters, 2003.
- Teodorsson, Sven-Tage. *The phonology of Attic in the Hellenistic Period*. Göteborg: Acta Universitatis Gothoburgensis, 1978.
- , *The Phonology of Ptolemaic Koine*. Göteborg: Acta Universitatis Gothoburgensis, 1977.
- Theobald, Michael, “Der Kanon von der Rechtfertigung (Gal 2,16; Röm 3,28). Eigentum des Paulus oder Gemeingut der Kirche?.” Pages 164–225 in Id., *Studien zum Römerbrief*. Tübingen: Mohr Siebeck, 2001.
- Thomas, Rosalind, “Writing, Reading, Public and Private « Literacies » : Functional Literacy and Democratic Literacy in Greece.” Pages 13–45 in *Ancient Literacies: The Culture of Reading in Greece and Rome* (ed. William A. Johnson and Holt N. Parker). Oxford: Oxford University Press, 2009.

- , *Literacy and Orality in Ancient Greece*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 1992.
- Thompson, Edward M., *An Introduction to Greek and Latin Palaeography*. Oxford: Clarendon Press, 1912.
- Thrall, Margaret E., *The Second Epistle to the Corinthians*. Vol. I: *Introduction and Commentary on II Corinthians I–VIII*. Edinburgh: Clark, 1994. Vol. II: *Commentary on II Corinthians VIII–XIII*. Edinburgh: Clark, 2000.
- Towner, Philip H. “The Function of the Public Reading of Scripture in 1Timothy 4:13 and in the Biblical Tradition.” *SBJT* 7 (2003): 44–53.
- Trobisch, David, “Performance Criticism as an Exegetical Method: A Story, Three Insights, and Two Jokes.” Pages 194–201 in *The Interface of Orality and Writing. Speaking, Seeing, Writing in the Shaping of New Genres* (ed. Annette Weissenrieder and Robert B. Coote). Mohr Siebeck, 2010.
- Truss, Lynne, *Eats, Shoots and Leaves: The Zero Tolerance Approach to Punctuation*. London: Profile Books, 2003.
- Vaahtera, Jaana, “Phonetics and Euphony in Dionysius of Halicarnassus.” *Mnemosyne* 50/5 (1997): 586–595.
- Valette Cagnac, Emmanuelle, *La lecture à Rome. Rites et pratiques*. Paris: Belin, 1997.
- Veerkamp, T., *Das Evangelium nach Johannes in kolometrischer Übersetzung*. Lehrhaus e.V. Dortmund 2005.
- Vegge, Tor, *Paulus und das antike Schulwesen. Schule und Bildung des Paulus*. Berlin: Walter de Gruyter, 2006.
- Vernhes, Jean-Victor, “Qu’est-ce que l’accent grec ancien? Les accents du grec ancien étudiés en eux-mêmes et comparés à ceux du lituanien.” *LYCHNOS / Connaissance hellénique* 154 (2019). Online: <https://ch.hypotheses.org/3623>.
- Viljamaa, T., “Cōlon and Comma. Dionysius of Halicarnassus on the Sentence Structure.” Pages 163–178 in *Syntax in Antiquity* (ed. P. Swiggers and A. Wouters). Leuven: Peeters, 2003.
- Viti, Carlotta, “Genitive Word Order in Ancient Greek: A Functional Analysis of Word Order Freedom in the Noun Phrase.” *Glotta* 84 (2008): 203–238.
- Volkman, Richard, *Die Rhetorik der Griechen und Römer in systematischer Übersicht*, H. Ebeling & C. Plahn, 1872.
- Vouga, François, “Le corpus paulinien.” Pages 161–178 in *Introduction au Nouveau Testament. Son histoire, son écriture, sa théologie* (ed. Daniel Marguerat). Genève: Labor et Fides, 2008.
- Waal, Kayle B. de, “A Sound Map of Revelation 8,7–12 and the Implications for Ancient Hearers.” Pages 179–192 in *Sound Matters: New Testament Studies in Sound Mapping* (ed. M. E. Lee). Eugene (OR): Cascade Books, 2018.
- , *An Aural-Performance Analysis of Revelation I and II*. New York: Lang, 2015.

- Walde, Christine and Michael Weißenberger, "Rhetorik," in *Der Neue Pauly* (ed. Hubert Cancik, Helmuth Schneider, Manfred Landfester). Online version, Brill, 2006. Consulted online on 20 March 2021, http://dx.doi.org/10.1163/1574-9347_dnp_e1022090.
- Walker, Jeffrey, "Aelius Aristides." Pages 42–50 in *Classical Rhetorics and Rhetoricians: Critical Studies and Sources* (ed. Michelle Ballif and Michael G. Moran). Westport [et al.]: Praeger, 2005.
- , "Dionysius of Halicarnassus." Pages 137–141 in *Classical Rhetorics and Rhetoricians: Critical Studies and Sources* (ed. Michelle Ballif and Michael G. Moran). Westport [et al.]: Praeger, 2005.
- Watson, Duane F., "Paul's Boasting in 2 Corinthians 10–13 as Defense of His Honor: A Sociorhetorical Analysis." *NovT* 30 (1988): 57–88.
- , *The Rhetoric of the New Testament: A Bibliographic Survey*. Leiden: Brill, 2006.
- , "The Role of Style in the Pauline Epistles: From Ornamentation to Argumentative Strategies." Pages 119–140 in *Paul and Rhetoric* (ed. J. P. Sampley and P. Lampe). Bloomsbury / T & T Clark, 2010.
- , "The Three Species of Rhetoric and the Study of the Pauline Epistles." Pages 25–47 in *Paul and Rhetoric* (ed. J. P. Sampley and P. Lampe). Bloomsbury / T & T Clark, 2010.
- , "The Contribution and Limitations of Greco-Roman Rhetorical Theory for Constructing the Rhetorical and Historical Situations of a Pauline Epistle." Pages 125–151 in *The Rhetorical Interpretation of the Scripture: Essays from the 1996 Malibu Conference* (ed. Stanley E. Porter and Dennis Stamps). Sheffield Academic Press, 1999.
- , *Invention, Arrangement, and Style: Rhetorical Criticism of Jude and Second Peter*. Atlanta Ga.: Scholars Press, 1988.
- Watson, Duane F. and Alan J. Hauser, *Rhetorical Criticism of the Bible: A Comprehensive Bibliography with Notes on History and Method*. Leiden /New York: Brill, 1994.
- Webb, Ruth. "The Progymnasmata as Practice." Pages 289–316 in *Education in Greek and Roman Antiquity* (ed. Yun Lee Too). Leiden: Brill, 2001.
- Weiss, Johannes, *Beiträge zur paulinischen Rhetorik*. Göttingen: Vandenhoeck und Ruprecht, 1897.
- , *Der erste Korintherbrief*. 10th ed. Göttingen: Vandenhoeck und Ruprecht, 1925.
- Weissenrieder, Annette, Coote, Robert B. (eds), *The Interface of Orality and Writing: Speaking, Seeing, Writing in the Shaping of New Genres*. Tübingen: Mohr Siebeck, 2010.
- Welborn, L. L., "The Identification of 2 Cor 10–13 with the 'Letter of Tears.'" *Novum Testamentum* 37/2 (1995): 138–153.
- Welborn, *Politics and Rhetoric in the Corinthian Epistles*. Macon (GA): Mercer University Press, 1997.
- West, Martin L, "Kolon," in *Der Neue Pauly Enzyklopädie der Antike* (ed. Hubert Cancik, Helmuth Schneider, Manfred Landfester). Online version: Brill, 2006. Consulted online on 20 March 2021, http://dx.doi.org/10.1163/1574-9347_dnp_e618310.

- White, Adam G., "New Adventures in Sound Mapping: A First-Timer's Attempt at a New Methodology." Pages 27–41 in *Sound Matters: New Testament Studies in Sound Mapping* (ed. M. E. Lee). Eugene (OR): Cascade Books, 2018.
- Wilkinson, L. P., *Golden Latin Artistry*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 1963.
- Windisch, Hans, *Der zweite Korintherbrief*. Göttingen: Vandenhoeck & Ruprecht, 1924.
- Wire, Antoinette Clark. *The Case for Mark Composed in Performance*. Eugene: Cascade Books, 2011.
- Wischmeyer, Oda (ed.), *Paulus. Leben – Umwelt – Werk – Briefe*. Tübingen et al. : Francke, 2006 (ET: *Paul: Life, Setting, Work, Letters*. T & T Clark, 2012).
- Witherington III, Ben, *Paul's Letter to the Philippians: A Socio-Rhetorical Commentary*. Grand Rapids (MI) / Carlisle: Eerdmans / Paternoster Press, 2011.
- , *New Testament Rhetoric: An Introduction Guide to the Art of Persuasion in and of the New Testament*. Eugene (OR): Cascade Books, 2009.
- , *The Letters to Philemon, the Colossians, and the Ephesians: A Socio-Rhetorical Commentary on the Captivity Epistles*. Grand Rapids (MI) / Carlisle: Eerdmans / Paternoster Press, 2007.
- , *1 and 2 Thessalonians: A Socio-Rhetorical Commentary*. Grand Rapids (MI) / Carlisle: Eerdmans / Paternoster Press, 2006.
- , *The Gospel of Mark: A Socio-Rhetorical Commentary*. Grand Rapids (MI) / Carlisle: Eerdmans / Paternoster Press, 2001.
- , *Grace in Galatia: A Socio-Rhetorical Commentary on Paul's Letter to the Galatians*. Grand Rapids (MI) / Carlisle: Eerdmans / Paternoster Press, 1998.
- , *The Acts of the Apostles: A Socio-Rhetorical Commentary*. Grand Rapids (MI) / Carlisle: Eerdmans / Paternoster Press, 1998.
- , *Conflict and Community in Corinth: A Socio-Rhetorical Commentary on 1 and 2 Corinthians*. Grand Rapids (MI) / Carlisle: Eerdmans / Paternoster Press, 1995.
- Witherington III, Ben, and D. Hyatt, *Paul's Letter to the Romans: A Socio-Rhetorical Commentary*. Grand Rapids (MI) / Carlisle: Eerdmans / Paternoster Press, 2004.
- Silva, D. A. de, *Perseverance and Gratitude: A Socio-Rhetorical Commentary on the Epistle "to the Hebrews"*. Grand Rapids (MI) / Carlisle: Eerdmans / Paternoster Press, 2000.
- Wilson, Nigel G., *Scholars of Byzantium*. London: Gerald Duckworth; Baltimore: Johns Hopkins University Press, 1983.
- Wingo, E. Otha, *Latin Punctuation in the Classical Age*. The Hague and Paris: Mouton, 1972.
- Woerner, Roman, *ΑΠΟΚΑΛΥΨΙΣ: das ist Offenbarung des Johannes*. München: C.H. Beck'she, 1924.
- , *Die Frohen Botschaft nach Markus, nach Matthäus, nach Lukas, nach Johannes*. München: C.H. Beck'she, 1922.

- Woerther, Frédérique, *Commenting on Aristotle's Rhetoric, from Antiquity to the Present / Commenter la Rhétorique d'Aristote, de l'antiquité à la période contemporaine*. Leiden: Brill, 2018.
- Wojciechowski, Michael, "Paul and Plutarch on Boasting." *Journal of Greco-Roman Christianity and Judaism* 3 (2006): 99–109.
- Wong, K. H., *Boasting and Foolishness: A Study of 2 Cor 10:12-18 and 11:1a*. Hong Kong: Alliance Bible Seminary, 1998.
- Woolf, Greg, "Literacy or Literacies in Rome." Pages 46–68 *Ancient Literacies: The Culture of Reading in Greece and Rome* (ed. William A. Johnson and Holt N. Parker). Oxford: Oxford University Press, 2009.
- Wooten, Cecil W., "Roman Education and Rhetoric." Pages 1109–1120 in *Civilization of the Ancient Mediterranean: Greece and Rome* (ed. Michael Grant and Rachel Kitzinger). New York: Scribner, 1988.
- Wordsworth, John, White, Henry J. (eds), *Novum Testamentum Domini nostri Iesu Christi Latine, secundum editionem sancti Hieronymi*. 3 vol. Oxford: Clarendon Press, 1889–1954.
- Wuellner, Wilhelm, "Arrangement." Pages 51–87 in *Handbook of Classical Rhetoric in the Hellenistic Period (330 B.C.– A.D. 400)* (ed. Stanley E. Porter). Leiden / New York / Köln: Brill, 1997.
- Young, Frances M., and Ford, David F., *Meaning and Truth in 2 Corinthians*. Grand Rapids / London: Eerdmans / SPCK, 1987.
- Zander, C. M., *Eurythmia, vel Compositio Rythmica Prosae Antiquae*. Leipzig: Harrassowitz, 1913.
- Zehetmeier, J., "Die Periodenlehre des Aristoteles." *Philologus* 85/1–4 (1929): 192–208.
- Zieliński, T., *Der constructive Rhythmus in Ciceros Reden*. Leipzig: Dieterich, 1914.
- , *Das Clauseigesetz in Ciceros Reden*. Leipzig: Dieterich, 1904.
- Zmijewski, Josef, *Der Stil der paulinischen "Narrenrede." Analyse der Sprachgestaltung in 2 Kor. 11,1–12,10 als Beitrag zur Methodik von Stiluntersuchungen neutestamentlicher Texte*. Köln: Hanstein, 1978.
- Zumstein, Jean, "L'interprétation du Nouveau Testament." *Revue de théologie et de philosophie* 110 (1978): 49–63.

